

Triangular-Type Selfie Numbers: Digit's Order

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

Numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations are considered as **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of **basis operations** along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients, S-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers, quadratic numbers, cubic numbers**, etc. This paper brings **selfie numbers** with **triangular numbers** in digit's order. The previous work of author [21] is up to 4-digits numbers. This work extends to 5-digits numbers. The work on reverse order is given in a separate paper.

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¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012).
Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).
E-mail: ijjtaneja@gmail.com; **Web-site:** <https://inderjtaneja.com>;
Twitter: @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

1 Selfie Numbers

During past years, the author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides of the expressions are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. In past, these type of numbers were called **wild narcissistic numbers**. These can be obtained by use of **basis operations** along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients, S-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers, quadratic numbers, cubic numbers**, etc. This paper brings **selfie numbers** with **triangular numbers** in digit's order. The previous work of author [21] is up to 4-digits numbers. This work extends to 5-digits numbers. The work on reverse order is given in a separate paper. Below are some examples of **selfie numbers** in different situations.

1.1 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples:

$$13825 := 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5} = ((5-2) \times 8)^3 + 1$$

$$14641 := (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 = (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1$$

$$15552 := (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 2 = 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 1$$

$$16377 := (1 + 6 - 3)^7 - 7 = -7 + (7 - 3)^{6+1}$$

$$23328 := (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 = (8 - 2)^{3+3}/2$$

$$116565 := (-1 + 16) \times (-5 + 6^5) = 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1)$$

$$131072 := (1 + 3)^{1+0+7} \times 2 = 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1}$$

$$147419 := -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 = 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1$$

$$147429 := 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 = 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1)$$

$$147491 := 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 = 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1$$

$$156252 := 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 = 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6-5} + 1)$$

1.2 Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$$1463 := -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!!$$

$$10077 := -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7!$$

$$40585 := 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5!$$

$$80518 := 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8!$$

$$317489 := -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9!$$

$$352797 := -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7!$$

$$357592 := -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2!$$

$$357941 := 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!$$

$$361469 := 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9!$$

$$364292 := 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2!$$

$$397584 := -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4!$$

$$398173 := 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3!$$

$$408937 := -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7!$$

$$715799 := -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9!$$

$$720599 := -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9!$$

$$145 := 1! + 4! + 5!$$

$$733 := 7 + 3!! + 3!$$

$$5177 := 5! + 17 + 7!$$

$$363239 := 36 + 323 + 9!$$

$$363269 := 363 + 26 + 9!$$

$$403199 := 40319 + 9!$$

1.3 Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 936 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! &&= 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 1296 &:= \sqrt{(1+2)!^9/6} &&= 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)} \\
 2896 &:= 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) &&= (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2 \\
 331779 &:= 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} &&= \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\
 342995 &:= (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 &&= -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\
 759375 &:= (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 &&= (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7} \\
 759381 &:= 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 = -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7.
 \end{aligned}$$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For details refer [14, 15].

1.4 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence values are well know in the literature. The general formula to write **Fibonacci sequence** [10] is given by

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n+1) = F(n) + F(n-1), \quad n \geq 1. \quad (1)$$

In particular,

$$F(1) = 1, F(2) = 1, F(3) = 2, F(4) = 3, F(5) = 5, F(6) = 8, \text{ etc.}$$

The examples given in subsections, 3.3 and 3.4 are with **factorial** and **square-root**. While the subsection 3.2 brings values just with basic operations. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Fibonacci sequence** values. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 235 &:= 2 + F(F(F(3) + 5)) && 63 := 3 \times F(F(6)) \\
 256 &:= 2^5 \times F(6) && 882 := 2 \times F(8) \times F(8) \\
 4427 &:= (F(4) + 4^2) \times F(F(7)) && 1631 := F(13) \times (6 + 1) \\
 46493 &:= F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + 9)^3 && 54128 := 8 \times (F(2) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5))
 \end{aligned}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [22]. In [22], the author included the results with **factorial** too.

1.5 Triangle Numbers

According to equation (1) the triangular numbers are give by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2).$$

The examples given in above subsections are with **factorial**, **square-root**, **Fibonacci sequence** numbers, etc. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Triangular numbers**. See below:

$$1069 := T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9))$$

$$1081 := T(1 + T(08 + 1))$$

$$2887 := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7)$$

$$4965 := T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5)))$$

$$4999 := 49 + T(99)$$

$$99545 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5$$

$$99546 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6$$

$$874 := T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8)$$

$$0105 := 50 + T(10)$$

$$1155 := -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1)$$

$$1224 := T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) - 2 + 1$$

$$2418 := T(81) - T(42)$$

$$99632 := 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$$

$$99633 := 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's work [20]. For **simultaneous selfie numbers** with **Fibonacci** and **Triangular numbers** see the author's work [25].

There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial**, **square-root**, **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, **binomial coefficients**, **s-gonal values**, **centered polygonal numbers**, etc. Below is item-wise details of author's work on **selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order**, and in **reverse order of digits**:

1. Selfie numbers with **Basic Operations**; [14, 15, 16, 30];
2. Selfie numbers with **Factorial**: [26, 27];
3. Selfie numbers with **Square-root**: [14, 15];
4. Selfie numbers with **Factorial and Square-root**: [14, 15, 16];
5. Selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**: [23];
6. Selfie numbers with **Triangular numbers**: [21]; This work extends to 5-digits numbers.
7. Selfie numbers with **Fibonacci and Triangular numbers**: [24];
8. Selfie numbers with **Binomial coefficients**: [22];
9. Selfie numbers with **S-gonal numbers**: [17];
10. Selfie numbers with **Centered Polygonal**: [17];
11. Selfie numbers with **Concatenation-Type**: [28];
12. Selfie numbers with **Quadratic numbers**: [25];
13. Selfie numbers with **Cubic numbers**: [29];
14. Selfie numbers with **Binomial coefficients and Fibonacci sequence**: [31];

The last Section 3 is dedicated to summary of **selfie numbers** in different situations along with proper references.

The work on **triangular-type selfie numbers** given above in subsection 1.5 [21] is only up to 4-digits numbers. This work extend the same up to 5-digits numbers. Since there are lot of values, the work is divided in two parts. One in **digit's order** and another in **reverse order of digits**. See the author's work [21]. This work in digit's order. In order to have uniformity of results, results appearing in subsection 1.5 are also repeated. This is because in case of reverse order of digits, we have many numbers staring with 0, not included in [21].

2 Triangular-Type Selfie Numbers: Digit's Order

This section brings **triangular-type selfie numbers** in digit's order up to 5-digits numbers. It is divided in two subsection. The first one give **consecutive** and **symmetric** blocks of 10 or 100 numbers. The second subsection give general values.

2.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$\begin{aligned}120 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 0 \\121 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 1 \\122 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 2 \\123 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 3 \\124 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 4 \\125 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 5 \\126 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 6 \\127 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 7 \\128 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 8 \\129 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}190 &:= T(19) + 0 \\191 &:= T(19) + 1 \\192 &:= T(19) + 2 \\193 &:= T(19) + 3 \\194 &:= T(19) + 4 \\195 &:= T(19) + 5 \\196 &:= T(19) + 6 \\197 &:= T(19) + 7 \\198 &:= T(19) + 8 \\199 &:= T(19) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}210 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 0 \\211 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 1 \\212 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 2 \\213 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 3 \\214 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 4 \\215 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 5 \\216 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 6 \\217 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 7 \\218 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 8 \\219 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}990 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 0 \\991 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 1 \\992 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 2 \\993 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 3 \\994 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 4 \\995 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 5\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}996 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 6 \\997 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 7 \\998 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 8 \\999 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1090 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 0 \\1091 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 1 \\1092 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 2 \\1093 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 3 \\1094 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 4 \\1095 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 5 \\1096 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 6 \\1097 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 7 \\1098 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 8 \\1099 &:= T(10) + T(T(9)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1260 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 0 \\1261 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 1 \\1262 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 2 \\1263 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 3 \\1264 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 4 \\1265 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 5 \\1266 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 6 \\1267 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 7 \\1268 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 8 \\1269 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1540 &:= T(1 + 54) + 0 \\1541 &:= T(1 + 54) + 1 \\1542 &:= T(1 + 54) + 2 \\1543 &:= T(1 + 54) + 3 \\1544 &:= T(1 + 54) + 4 \\1545 &:= T(1 + 54) + 5 \\1546 &:= T(1 + 54) + 6 \\1547 &:= T(1 + 54) + 7 \\1548 &:= T(1 + 54) + 8 \\1549 &:= T(1 + 54) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1680 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 0 \\1681 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 1 \\1682 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1683 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 3 \\1684 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 4 \\1685 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 5 \\1686 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 6 \\1687 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 7 \\1688 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 8 \\1689 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1740 &:= T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 0 \\1741 &:= T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 1 \\1742 &:= T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 2 \\1743 &:= T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 3 \\1744 &:= T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 4 \\1745 &:= T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 5 \\1746 &:= T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 6 \\1747 &:= T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 7 \\1748 &:= T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 8 \\1749 &:= T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1770 &:= T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 0 \\1771 &:= T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 1 \\1772 &:= T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 2 \\1773 &:= T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 3 \\1774 &:= T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 4 \\1775 &:= T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 5 \\1776 &:= T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 6 \\1777 &:= T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 7 \\1778 &:= T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 8 \\1779 &:= T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1830 &:= T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 0 \\1831 &:= T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 1 \\1832 &:= T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 2 \\1833 &:= T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 3 \\1834 &:= T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 4 \\1835 &:= T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 5 \\1836 &:= T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 6 \\1837 &:= T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 7 \\1838 &:= T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 8 \\1839 &:= T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1980 &:= T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 0 \\1981 &:= T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 1 \\1982 &:= T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 2 \\1983 &:= T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 3 \\1984 &:= T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 4 \\1985 &:= T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 5 \\1986 &:= T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 6 \\1987 &:= T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 7 \\1988 &:= T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 8 \\1989 &:= T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2210 &:= T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) - 1 + 0 \\2211 &:= T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) - 1 + 1 \\2212 &:= T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) - 1 + 2 \\2213 &:= T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) - 1 + 3 \\2214 &:= T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) - 1 + 4 \\2215 &:= T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) - 1 + 5 \\2216 &:= T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) - 1 + 6 \\2217 &:= T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) - 1 + 7 \\2218 &:= T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) - 1 + 8 \\2219 &:= T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) - 1 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2310 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 0 \\2311 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 1 \\2312 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 2 \\2313 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 3 \\2314 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 4 \\2315 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 5 \\2316 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 6 \\2317 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 7 \\2318 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 8 \\2319 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2340 &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 0 \\2341 &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 1 \\2342 &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 2 \\2343 &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 3 \\2344 &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 4 \\2345 &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 5 \\2346 &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 6 \\2347 &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 7 \\2348 &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 8\end{aligned}$$

$$2349 := (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 9$$

$$2520 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 0$$

$$2521 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 1$$

$$2522 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 2$$

$$2523 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 3$$

$$2524 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 4$$

$$2525 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 5$$

$$2526 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 6$$

$$2527 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 7$$

$$2528 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 8$$

$$2529 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 9$$

$$2850 := T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 0$$

$$2851 := T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 1$$

$$2852 := T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 2$$

$$2853 := T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 3$$

$$2854 := T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 4$$

$$2855 := T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 5$$

$$2856 := T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 6$$

$$2857 := T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 7$$

$$2858 := T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 8$$

$$2859 := T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 9$$

$$2940 := T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 0$$

$$2941 := T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 1$$

$$2942 := T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 2$$

$$2943 := T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 3$$

$$2944 := T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 4$$

$$2945 := T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 5$$

$$2946 := T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 6$$

$$2947 := T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 7$$

$$2948 := T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 8$$

$$2949 := T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 9$$

$$3150 := T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 0$$

$$3151 := T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 1$$

$$3152 := T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 2$$

$$3153 := T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 3$$

$$3154 := T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 4$$

$$3155 := T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 5$$

$$3156 := T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 6$$

$$3157 := T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 7$$

$$3158 := T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 8$$

$$3159 := T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 9$$

$$3240 := T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 0$$

$$3241 := T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 1$$

$$3242 := T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 2$$

$$3243 := T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 3$$

$$3244 := T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 4$$

$$3245 := T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 5$$

$$3246 := T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 6$$

$$3247 := T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 7$$

$$3248 := T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 8$$

$$3249 := T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 9$$

$$3450 := T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 0$$

$$3451 := T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 1$$

$$3452 := T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 2$$

$$3453 := T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 3$$

$$3454 := T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 4$$

$$3455 := T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 5$$

$$3456 := T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 6$$

$$3457 := T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 7$$

$$3458 := T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 8$$

$$3459 := T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 9$$

$$3570 := T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 0$$

$$3571 := T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 1$$

$$3572 := T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 2$$

$$3573 := T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 3$$

$$3574 := T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 4$$

$$3575 := T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 5$$

$$3576 := T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 6$$

$$3577 := T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 7$$

$$3578 := T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 8$$

$$3579 := T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 9$$

$$3780 := T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 0$$

$$3781 := T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 1$$

$$3782 := T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 2$$

$$3783 := T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 3$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3784 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 4 \\ 3785 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 5 \\ 3786 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 6 \\ 3787 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 7 \\ 3788 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 8 \\ 3789 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4140 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 0 \\ 4141 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 1 \\ 4142 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 2 \\ 4143 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 3 \\ 4144 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 4 \\ 4145 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 5 \\ 4146 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 6 \\ 4147 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 7 \\ 4148 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 8 \\ 4149 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4270 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 0 \\ 4271 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 1 \\ 4272 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 2 \\ 4273 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 3 \\ 4274 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 4 \\ 4275 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 5 \\ 4276 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 6 \\ 4277 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 7 \\ 4278 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 8 \\ 4279 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4290 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 0 \\ 4291 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 1 \\ 4292 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 2 \\ 4293 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 3 \\ 4294 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 4 \\ 4295 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 5 \\ 4296 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 6 \\ 4297 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 7 \\ 4298 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 8 \\ 4299 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4560 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 0 \\ 4561 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 1 \\ 4562 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 2 \\ 4563 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 3 \\ 4564 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 4 \\ 4565 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 5 \\ 4566 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 6 \\ 4567 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 7 \\ 4568 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 8 \\ 4569 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4620 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 0 \\ 4621 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 1 \\ 4622 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 2 \\ 4623 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 3 \\ 4624 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 4 \\ 4625 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 5 \\ 4626 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 6 \\ 4627 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 7 \\ 4628 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 8 \\ 4629 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4650 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 0 \\ 4651 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 1 \\ 4652 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 2 \\ 4653 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 3 \\ 4654 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 4 \\ 4655 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 5 \\ 4656 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 6 \\ 4657 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 7 \\ 4658 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 8 \\ 4659 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4950 &:= T(4 + 95) + 0 \\ 4951 &:= T(4 + 95) + 1 \\ 4952 &:= T(4 + 95) + 2 \\ 4953 &:= T(4 + 95) + 3 \\ 4954 &:= T(4 + 95) + 4 \\ 4955 &:= T(4 + 95) + 5 \\ 4956 &:= T(4 + 95) + 6 \\ 4957 &:= T(4 + 95) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$4958 := T(4 + 95) + 8$$

$$4959 := T(4 + 95) + 9$$

$$6930 := T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 0$$

$$6931 := T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 1$$

$$6932 := T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 2$$

$$6933 := T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 3$$

$$6934 := T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 4$$

$$6935 := T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 5$$

$$6936 := T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 6$$

$$6937 := T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 7$$

$$6938 := T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 8$$

$$6939 := T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 9$$

$$8280 := T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 0$$

$$8281 := T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 1$$

$$8282 := T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 2$$

$$8283 := T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 3$$

$$8284 := T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 4$$

$$8285 := T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 5$$

$$8286 := T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 6$$

$$8287 := T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 7$$

$$8288 := T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 8$$

$$8289 := T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 9$$

$$8460 := T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 0$$

$$8461 := T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 1$$

$$8462 := T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 2$$

$$8463 := T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 3$$

$$8464 := T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 4$$

$$8465 := T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 5$$

$$8466 := T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 6$$

$$8467 := T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 7$$

$$8468 := T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 8$$

$$8469 := T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 9$$

$$9240 := (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 0$$

$$9241 := (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 1$$

$$9242 := (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 2$$

$$9243 := (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 3$$

$$9244 := (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 4$$

$$9245 := (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 5$$

$$9246 := (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 6$$

$$9247 := (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 7$$

$$9248 := (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 8$$

$$9248 := (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 9$$

$$9450 := T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 0$$

$$9451 := T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 1$$

$$9452 := T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 2$$

$$9453 := T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 3$$

$$9454 := T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 4$$

$$9455 := T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 5$$

$$9456 := T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 6$$

$$9457 := T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 7$$

$$9458 := T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 8$$

$$9459 := T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 9$$

$$10240 := 10 \times 2^{T(4)} + 0$$

$$10241 := 10 \times 2^{T(4)} + 1$$

$$10242 := 10 \times 2^{T(4)} + 2$$

$$10243 := 10 \times 2^{T(4)} + 3$$

$$10244 := 10 \times 2^{T(4)} + 4$$

$$10245 := 10 \times 2^{T(4)} + 5$$

$$10246 := 10 \times 2^{T(4)} + 6$$

$$10247 := 10 \times 2^{T(4)} + 7$$

$$10248 := 10 \times 2^{T(4)} + 8$$

$$10249 := 10 \times 2^{T(4)} + 9$$

$$10290 := 10 \times (-T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + 0$$

$$10291 := 10 \times (-T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + 1$$

$$10292 := 10 \times (-T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + 2$$

$$10293 := 10 \times (-T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + 3$$

$$10294 := 10 \times (-T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + 4$$

$$10295 := 10 \times (-T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + 5$$

$$10296 := 10 \times (-T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + 6$$

$$10297 := 10 \times (-T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + 7$$

$$10298 := 10 \times (-T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + 8$$

$$10299 := 10 \times (-T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + 9$$

$$10350 := 10 \times T(3 \times T(5)) + 0$$

$$10351 := 10 \times T(3 \times T(5)) + 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}10352 &:= 10 \times T(3 \times T(5)) + 2 \\10353 &:= 10 \times T(3 \times T(5)) + 3 \\10354 &:= 10 \times T(3 \times T(5)) + 4 \\10355 &:= 10 \times T(3 \times T(5)) + 5 \\10356 &:= 10 \times T(3 \times T(5)) + 6 \\10357 &:= 10 \times T(3 \times T(5)) + 7 \\10358 &:= 10 \times T(3 \times T(5)) + 8 \\10359 &:= 10 \times T(3 \times T(5)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}10450 &:= T(10) \times T(4 + T(5)) + 0 \\10451 &:= T(10) \times T(4 + T(5)) + 1 \\10452 &:= T(10) \times T(4 + T(5)) + 2 \\10453 &:= T(10) \times T(4 + T(5)) + 3 \\10454 &:= T(10) \times T(4 + T(5)) + 4 \\10455 &:= T(10) \times T(4 + T(5)) + 5 \\10456 &:= T(10) \times T(4 + T(5)) + 6 \\10457 &:= T(10) \times T(4 + T(5)) + 7 \\10458 &:= T(10) \times T(4 + T(5)) + 8 \\10459 &:= T(10) \times T(4 + T(5)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12240 &:= (T(T(12)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 + 0 \\12241 &:= (T(T(12)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 + 1 \\12242 &:= (T(T(12)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 + 2 \\12243 &:= (T(T(12)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 + 3 \\12244 &:= (T(T(12)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 + 4 \\12245 &:= (T(T(12)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 + 5 \\12246 &:= (T(T(12)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 + 6 \\12247 &:= (T(T(12)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 + 7 \\12248 &:= (T(T(12)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 + 8 \\12249 &:= (T(T(12)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12600 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 60 + 0 \\12601 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 60 + 1 \\12602 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 60 + 2 \\12603 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 60 + 3 \\12604 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 60 + 4 \\12605 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 60 + 5 \\12606 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 60 + 6 \\12607 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 60 + 7 \\12608 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 60 + 8 \\12609 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 60 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12640 &:= T(1 + T(2 \times 6)) \times 4 + 0 \\12641 &:= T(1 + T(2 \times 6)) \times 4 + 1 \\12642 &:= T(1 + T(2 \times 6)) \times 4 + 2 \\12643 &:= T(1 + T(2 \times 6)) \times 4 + 3 \\12644 &:= T(1 + T(2 \times 6)) \times 4 + 4 \\12645 &:= T(1 + T(2 \times 6)) \times 4 + 5 \\12646 &:= T(1 + T(2 \times 6)) \times 4 + 6 \\12647 &:= T(1 + T(2 \times 6)) \times 4 + 7 \\12648 &:= T(1 + T(2 \times 6)) \times 4 + 8 \\12649 &:= T(1 + T(2 \times 6)) \times 4 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13230 &:= T(-1 + T(3)^2) \times T(T(3)) + 0 \\13231 &:= T(-1 + T(3)^2) \times T(T(3)) + 1 \\13232 &:= T(-1 + T(3)^2) \times T(T(3)) + 2 \\13233 &:= T(-1 + T(3)^2) \times T(T(3)) + 3 \\13234 &:= T(-1 + T(3)^2) \times T(T(3)) + 4 \\13235 &:= T(-1 + T(3)^2) \times T(T(3)) + 5 \\13236 &:= T(-1 + T(3)^2) \times T(T(3)) + 6 \\13237 &:= T(-1 + T(3)^2) \times T(T(3)) + 7 \\13238 &:= T(-1 + T(3)^2) \times T(T(3)) + 8 \\13239 &:= T(-1 + T(3)^2) \times T(T(3)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13280 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (-2 + T(T(8))) + 0 \\13281 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (-2 + T(T(8))) + 1 \\13282 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (-2 + T(T(8))) + 2 \\13283 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (-2 + T(T(8))) + 3 \\13284 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (-2 + T(T(8))) + 4 \\13285 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (-2 + T(T(8))) + 5 \\13286 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (-2 + T(T(8))) + 6 \\13287 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (-2 + T(T(8))) + 7 \\13288 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (-2 + T(T(8))) + 8 \\13289 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (-2 + T(T(8))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13320 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)^2) + 0 \\13321 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)^2) + 1 \\13322 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)^2) + 2 \\13323 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)^2) + 3 \\13324 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)^2) + 4 \\13325 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)^2) + 5 \\13326 &:= (-1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)^2) + 6\end{aligned}$$

$$13327 := (-1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)^2) + 7$$

$$13328 := (-1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)^2) + 8$$

$$13329 := (-1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)^2) + 9$$

$$13340 := (1 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-3 - T(T(4))) + 0$$

$$13341 := (1 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-3 - T(T(4))) + 1$$

$$13342 := (1 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-3 - T(T(4))) + 2$$

$$13343 := (1 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-3 - T(T(4))) + 3$$

$$13344 := (1 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-3 - T(T(4))) + 4$$

$$13345 := (1 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-3 - T(T(4))) + 5$$

$$13346 := (1 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-3 - T(T(4))) + 6$$

$$13347 := (1 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-3 - T(T(4))) + 7$$

$$13348 := (1 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-3 - T(T(4))) + 8$$

$$13349 := (1 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-3 - T(T(4))) + 9$$

$$13380 := (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (3 + T(T(8))) + 0$$

$$13381 := (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (3 + T(T(8))) + 1$$

$$13382 := (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (3 + T(T(8))) + 2$$

$$13383 := (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (3 + T(T(8))) + 3$$

$$13384 := (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (3 + T(T(8))) + 4$$

$$13385 := (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (3 + T(T(8))) + 5$$

$$13386 := (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (3 + T(T(8))) + 6$$

$$13387 := (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (3 + T(T(8))) + 7$$

$$13388 := (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (3 + T(T(8))) + 8$$

$$13389 := (-1 + T(T(3))) \times (3 + T(T(8))) + 9$$

$$13530 := T(T(1+3)) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) + 0$$

$$13531 := T(T(1+3)) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) + 1$$

$$13532 := T(T(1+3)) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) + 2$$

$$13533 := T(T(1+3)) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) + 3$$

$$13534 := T(T(1+3)) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) + 4$$

$$13535 := T(T(1+3)) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) + 5$$

$$13536 := T(T(1+3)) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) + 6$$

$$13537 := T(T(1+3)) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) + 7$$

$$13538 := T(T(1+3)) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) + 8$$

$$13539 := T(T(1+3)) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) + 9$$

$$13650 := T(-1 + T(T(3))) \times 65 + 0$$

$$13651 := T(-1 + T(T(3))) \times 65 + 1$$

$$13652 := T(-1 + T(T(3))) \times 65 + 2$$

$$13653 := T(-1 + T(T(3))) \times 65 + 3$$

$$13654 := T(-1 + T(T(3))) \times 65 + 4$$

$$13655 := T(-1 + T(T(3))) \times 65 + 5$$

$$13656 := T(-1 + T(T(3))) \times 65 + 6$$

$$13657 := T(-1 + T(T(3))) \times 65 + 7$$

$$13658 := T(-1 + T(T(3))) \times 65 + 8$$

$$13659 := T(-1 + T(T(3))) \times 65 + 9$$

$$13860 := (-1 \times T(3) + T(T(8))) \times T(6) + 0$$

$$13861 := (-1 \times T(3) + T(T(8))) \times T(6) + 1$$

$$13862 := (-1 \times T(3) + T(T(8))) \times T(6) + 2$$

$$13863 := (-1 \times T(3) + T(T(8))) \times T(6) + 3$$

$$13864 := (-1 \times T(3) + T(T(8))) \times T(6) + 4$$

$$13865 := (-1 \times T(3) + T(T(8))) \times T(6) + 5$$

$$13866 := (-1 \times T(3) + T(T(8))) \times T(6) + 6$$

$$13867 := (-1 \times T(3) + T(T(8))) \times T(6) + 7$$

$$13868 := (-1 \times T(3) + T(T(8))) \times T(6) + 8$$

$$13869 := (-1 \times T(3) + T(T(8))) \times T(6) + 9$$

$$14250 := T(-1 + T(T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 + 0$$

$$14251 := T(-1 + T(T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 + 1$$

$$14252 := T(-1 + T(T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 + 2$$

$$14253 := T(-1 + T(T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 + 3$$

$$14254 := T(-1 + T(T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 + 4$$

$$14255 := T(-1 + T(T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 + 5$$

$$14256 := T(-1 + T(T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 + 6$$

$$14257 := T(-1 + T(T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 + 7$$

$$14258 := T(-1 + T(T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 + 8$$

$$14259 := T(-1 + T(T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 + 9$$

$$14280 := T(14) \times T(2 \times 8) + 0$$

$$14281 := T(14) \times T(2 \times 8) + 1$$

$$14282 := T(14) \times T(2 \times 8) + 2$$

$$14283 := T(14) \times T(2 \times 8) + 3$$

$$14284 := T(14) \times T(2 \times 8) + 4$$

$$14285 := T(14) \times T(2 \times 8) + 5$$

$$14286 := T(14) \times T(2 \times 8) + 6$$

$$14287 := T(14) \times T(2 \times 8) + 7$$

$$14288 := T(14) \times T(2 \times 8) + 8$$

$$14289 := T(14) \times T(2 \times 8) + 9$$

$$14490 := (1 \times 4 + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) + 0$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14491 &:= (1 \times 4 + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) + 1 \\ 14492 &:= (1 \times 4 + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) + 2 \\ 14493 &:= (1 \times 4 + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) + 3 \\ 14494 &:= (1 \times 4 + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) + 4 \\ 14495 &:= (1 \times 4 + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) + 5 \\ 14496 &:= (1 \times 4 + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) + 6 \\ 14497 &:= (1 \times 4 + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) + 7 \\ 14498 &:= (1 \times 4 + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) + 8 \\ 14499 &:= (1 \times 4 + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) + 9 \\ \\ 14520 &:= T(T(1+4)) + T(T(5))^2 + 0 \\ 14521 &:= T(T(1+4)) + T(T(5))^2 + 1 \\ 14522 &:= T(T(1+4)) + T(T(5))^2 + 2 \\ 14523 &:= T(T(1+4)) + T(T(5))^2 + 3 \\ 14524 &:= T(T(1+4)) + T(T(5))^2 + 4 \\ 14525 &:= T(T(1+4)) + T(T(5))^2 + 5 \\ 14526 &:= T(T(1+4)) + T(T(5))^2 + 6 \\ 14527 &:= T(T(1+4)) + T(T(5))^2 + 7 \\ 14528 &:= T(T(1+4)) + T(T(5))^2 + 8 \\ 14529 &:= T(T(1+4)) + T(T(5))^2 + 9 \\ \\ 14640 &:= -1 + (T(4) - T(6))^4 + 0 \\ 14641 &:= -1 + (T(4) - T(6))^4 + 1 \\ 14642 &:= -1 + (T(4) - T(6))^4 + 2 \\ 14643 &:= -1 + (T(4) - T(6))^4 + 3 \\ 14644 &:= -1 + (T(4) - T(6))^4 + 4 \\ 14645 &:= -1 + (T(4) - T(6))^4 + 5 \\ 14646 &:= -1 + (T(4) - T(6))^4 + 6 \\ 14647 &:= -1 + (T(4) - T(6))^4 + 7 \\ 14648 &:= -1 + (T(4) - T(6))^4 + 8 \\ 14649 &:= -1 + (T(4) - T(6))^4 + 9 \\ \\ 14940 &:= (-1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) \times T(4) + 0 \\ 14941 &:= (-1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) \times T(4) + 1 \\ 14942 &:= (-1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) \times T(4) + 2 \\ 14943 &:= (-1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) \times T(4) + 3 \\ 14944 &:= (-1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) \times T(4) + 4 \\ 14945 &:= (-1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) \times T(4) + 5 \\ 14946 &:= (-1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) \times T(4) + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14947 &:= (-1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) \times T(4) + 7 \\ 14948 &:= (-1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) \times T(4) + 8 \\ 14949 &:= (-1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) \times T(4) + 9 \\ \\ 15340 &:= T(-1+5) \times (-T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) + 0 \\ 15341 &:= T(-1+5) \times (-T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) + 1 \\ 15342 &:= T(-1+5) \times (-T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) + 2 \\ 15343 &:= T(-1+5) \times (-T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) + 3 \\ 15344 &:= T(-1+5) \times (-T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) + 4 \\ 15345 &:= T(-1+5) \times (-T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) + 5 \\ 15346 &:= T(-1+5) \times (-T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) + 6 \\ 15347 &:= T(-1+5) \times (-T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) + 7 \\ 15348 &:= T(-1+5) \times (-T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) + 8 \\ 15349 &:= T(-1+5) \times (-T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) + 9 \\ \\ 15400 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 00 \\ 15401 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 01 \\ 15402 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 02 \\ 15403 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 03 \\ 15404 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 04 \\ 15405 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 05 \\ 15406 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 06 \\ 15407 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 07 \\ 15408 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 08 \\ 15409 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 09 \\ 15410 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 10 \\ 15411 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 11 \\ 15412 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 12 \\ 15413 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 13 \\ 15414 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 14 \\ 15415 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 15 \\ 15416 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 16 \\ 15417 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 17 \\ 15418 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 18 \\ 15419 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 19 \\ 15420 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 20 \\ 15421 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 21 \\ 15422 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 22 \\ 15423 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 23 \\ 15424 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 24 \\ 15425 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 25 \\ 15426 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 26 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15427 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 27 \\ 15428 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 28 \\ 15429 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 29 \\ 15430 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 30 \\ 15431 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 31 \\ 15432 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 32 \\ 15433 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 33 \\ 15434 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 34 \\ 15435 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 35 \\ 15436 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 36 \\ 15437 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 37 \\ 15438 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 38 \\ 15439 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 39 \\ 15440 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 40 \\ 15441 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 41 \\ 15442 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 42 \\ 15443 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 43 \\ 15444 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 44 \\ 15445 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 45 \\ 15446 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 46 \\ 15447 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 47 \\ 15448 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 48 \\ 15449 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 49 \\ 15450 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 50 \\ 15451 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 51 \\ 15452 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 52 \\ 15453 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 53 \\ 15454 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 54 \\ 15455 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 55 \\ 15456 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 56 \\ 15457 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 57 \\ 15458 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 58 \\ 15459 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 59 \\ 15460 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 60 \\ 15461 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 61 \\ 15462 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 62 \\ 15463 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 63 \\ 15464 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 64 \\ 15465 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 65 \\ 15466 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 66 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15467 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 67 \\ 15468 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 68 \\ 15469 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 69 \\ 15470 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 70 \\ 15471 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 71 \\ 15472 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 72 \\ 15473 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 73 \\ 15474 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 74 \\ 15475 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 75 \\ 15476 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 76 \\ 15477 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 77 \\ 15478 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 78 \\ 15479 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 79 \\ 15480 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 80 \\ 15481 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 81 \\ 15482 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 82 \\ 15483 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 83 \\ 15484 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 84 \\ 15485 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 85 \\ 15486 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 86 \\ 15487 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 87 \\ 15488 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 88 \\ 15489 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 89 \\ 15490 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 90 \\ 15491 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 91 \\ 15492 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 92 \\ 15493 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 93 \\ 15494 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 94 \\ 15495 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 95 \\ 15496 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 96 \\ 15497 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 97 \\ 15498 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 98 \\ 15499 &:= T(-1+5) \times T(T(T(4))) + 99 \\ 15630 &:= -1 + 5^6 + T(3) + 0 \\ 15631 &:= -1 + 5^6 + T(3) + 1 \\ 15632 &:= -1 + 5^6 + T(3) + 2 \\ 15633 &:= -1 + 5^6 + T(3) + 3 \\ 15634 &:= -1 + 5^6 + T(3) + 4 \\ 15635 &:= -1 + 5^6 + T(3) + 5 \\ 15636 &:= -1 + 5^6 + T(3) + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$15637 := -1 + 5^6 + T(3) + 7$$

$$15638 := -1 + 5^6 + T(3) + 8$$

$$15639 := -1 + 5^6 + T(3) + 9$$

$$16320 := T(16) \times T(T(3+2)) + 0$$

$$16321 := T(16) \times T(T(3+2)) + 1$$

$$16322 := T(16) \times T(T(3+2)) + 2$$

$$16323 := T(16) \times T(T(3+2)) + 3$$

$$16324 := T(16) \times T(T(3+2)) + 4$$

$$16325 := T(16) \times T(T(3+2)) + 5$$

$$16326 := T(16) \times T(T(3+2)) + 6$$

$$16327 := T(16) \times T(T(3+2)) + 7$$

$$16328 := T(16) \times T(T(3+2)) + 8$$

$$16329 := T(16) \times T(T(3+2)) + 9$$

$$16380 := T(1 \times 6) \times T(3 + T(8)) + 0$$

$$16381 := T(1 \times 6) \times T(3 + T(8)) + 1$$

$$16382 := T(1 \times 6) \times T(3 + T(8)) + 2$$

$$16383 := T(1 \times 6) \times T(3 + T(8)) + 3$$

$$16384 := T(1 \times 6) \times T(3 + T(8)) + 4$$

$$16385 := T(1 \times 6) \times T(3 + T(8)) + 5$$

$$16386 := T(1 \times 6) \times T(3 + T(8)) + 6$$

$$16387 := T(1 \times 6) \times T(3 + T(8)) + 7$$

$$16388 := T(1 \times 6) \times T(3 + T(8)) + 8$$

$$16389 := T(1 \times 6) \times T(3 + T(8)) + 9$$

$$16400 := (-1 + T(6)) \times T(40) + 0$$

$$16401 := (-1 + T(6)) \times T(40) + 1$$

$$16402 := (-1 + T(6)) \times T(40) + 2$$

$$16403 := (-1 + T(6)) \times T(40) + 3$$

$$16404 := (-1 + T(6)) \times T(40) + 4$$

$$16405 := (-1 + T(6)) \times T(40) + 5$$

$$16406 := (-1 + T(6)) \times T(40) + 6$$

$$16407 := (-1 + T(6)) \times T(40) + 7$$

$$16408 := (-1 + T(6)) \times T(40) + 8$$

$$16409 := (-1 + T(6)) \times T(40) + 9$$

$$16560 := 16 \times T(T(T(5) - 6)) + 0$$

$$16561 := 16 \times T(T(T(5) - 6)) + 1$$

$$16562 := 16 \times T(T(T(5) - 6)) + 2$$

$$16563 := 16 \times T(T(T(5) - 6)) + 3$$

$$16564 := 16 \times T(T(T(5) - 6)) + 4$$

$$16565 := 16 \times T(T(T(5) - 6)) + 5$$

$$16566 := 16 \times T(T(T(5) - 6)) + 6$$

$$16567 := 16 \times T(T(T(5) - 6)) + 7$$

$$16568 := 16 \times T(T(T(5) - 6)) + 8$$

$$16569 := 16 \times T(T(T(5) - 6)) + 9$$

$$16740 := (-1 + T(T(6+7))) \times 4 + 0$$

$$16741 := (-1 + T(T(6+7))) \times 4 + 1$$

$$16742 := (-1 + T(T(6+7))) \times 4 + 2$$

$$16743 := (-1 + T(T(6+7))) \times 4 + 3$$

$$16744 := (-1 + T(T(6+7))) \times 4 + 4$$

$$16745 := (-1 + T(T(6+7))) \times 4 + 5$$

$$16746 := (-1 + T(T(6+7))) \times 4 + 6$$

$$16747 := (-1 + T(T(6+7))) \times 4 + 7$$

$$16748 := (-1 + T(T(6+7))) \times 4 + 8$$

$$16749 := (-1 + T(T(6+7))) \times 4 + 9$$

$$16790 := (-1 + T(T(6))) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + 0$$

$$16791 := (-1 + T(T(6))) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + 1$$

$$16792 := (-1 + T(T(6))) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + 2$$

$$16793 := (-1 + T(T(6))) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + 3$$

$$16794 := (-1 + T(T(6))) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + 4$$

$$16795 := (-1 + T(T(6))) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + 5$$

$$16796 := (-1 + T(T(6))) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + 6$$

$$16797 := (-1 + T(T(6))) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + 7$$

$$16798 := (-1 + T(T(6))) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + 8$$

$$16799 := (-1 + T(T(6))) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + 9$$

$$16800 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 80 + 0$$

$$16801 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 80 + 1$$

$$16802 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 80 + 2$$

$$16803 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 80 + 3$$

$$16804 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 80 + 4$$

$$16805 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 80 + 5$$

$$16806 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 80 + 6$$

$$16807 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 80 + 7$$

$$16808 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 80 + 8$$

$$16809 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 80 + 9$$

$$16920 := T(-1 + 6) \times T(T(9) + 2) + 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}16921 &:= T(-1+6) \times T(T(9)+2) + 1 \\16922 &:= T(-1+6) \times T(T(9)+2) + 2 \\16923 &:= T(-1+6) \times T(T(9)+2) + 3 \\16924 &:= T(-1+6) \times T(T(9)+2) + 4 \\16925 &:= T(-1+6) \times T(T(9)+2) + 5 \\16926 &:= T(-1+6) \times T(T(9)+2) + 6 \\16927 &:= T(-1+6) \times T(T(9)+2) + 7 \\16928 &:= T(-1+6) \times T(T(9)+2) + 8 \\16929 &:= T(-1+6) \times T(T(9)+2) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16940 &:= (-1+T(6)-9) \times T(T(T(4))) + 0 \\16941 &:= (-1+T(6)-9) \times T(T(T(4))) + 1 \\16942 &:= (-1+T(6)-9) \times T(T(T(4))) + 2 \\16943 &:= (-1+T(6)-9) \times T(T(T(4))) + 3 \\16944 &:= (-1+T(6)-9) \times T(T(T(4))) + 4 \\16945 &:= (-1+T(6)-9) \times T(T(T(4))) + 5 \\16946 &:= (-1+T(6)-9) \times T(T(T(4))) + 6 \\16947 &:= (-1+T(6)-9) \times T(T(T(4))) + 7 \\16948 &:= (-1+T(6)-9) \times T(T(T(4))) + 8 \\16949 &:= (-1+T(6)-9) \times T(T(T(4))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17400 &:= T(1+T(7)) \times 40 + 0 \\17401 &:= T(1+T(7)) \times 40 + 1 \\17402 &:= T(1+T(7)) \times 40 + 2 \\17403 &:= T(1+T(7)) \times 40 + 3 \\17404 &:= T(1+T(7)) \times 40 + 4 \\17405 &:= T(1+T(7)) \times 40 + 5 \\17406 &:= T(1+T(7)) \times 40 + 6 \\17407 &:= T(1+T(7)) \times 40 + 7 \\17408 &:= T(1+T(7)) \times 40 + 8 \\17409 &:= T(1+T(7)) \times 40 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17820 &:= (-1+T(7)) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(2))) + 0 \\17821 &:= (-1+T(7)) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(2))) + 1 \\17822 &:= (-1+T(7)) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(2))) + 2 \\17823 &:= (-1+T(7)) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(2))) + 3 \\17824 &:= (-1+T(7)) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(2))) + 4 \\17825 &:= (-1+T(7)) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(2))) + 5 \\17826 &:= (-1+T(7)) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(2))) + 6 \\17827 &:= (-1+T(7)) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(2))) + 7 \\17828 &:= (-1+T(7)) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(2))) + 8\end{aligned}$$

$$17829 := (-1+T(7)) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(2))) + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned}18270 &:= T(18/2) \times T(T(7)) + 0 \\18271 &:= T(18/2) \times T(T(7)) + 1 \\18272 &:= T(18/2) \times T(T(7)) + 2 \\18273 &:= T(18/2) \times T(T(7)) + 3 \\18274 &:= T(18/2) \times T(T(7)) + 4 \\18275 &:= T(18/2) \times T(T(7)) + 5 \\18276 &:= T(18/2) \times T(T(7)) + 6 \\18277 &:= T(18/2) \times T(T(7)) + 7 \\18278 &:= T(18/2) \times T(T(7)) + 8 \\18279 &:= T(18/2) \times T(T(7)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18480 &:= (-1+T(8)) \times T(4 \times 8) + 0 \\18481 &:= (-1+T(8)) \times T(4 \times 8) + 1 \\18482 &:= (-1+T(8)) \times T(4 \times 8) + 2 \\18483 &:= (-1+T(8)) \times T(4 \times 8) + 3 \\18484 &:= (-1+T(8)) \times T(4 \times 8) + 4 \\18485 &:= (-1+T(8)) \times T(4 \times 8) + 5 \\18486 &:= (-1+T(8)) \times T(4 \times 8) + 6 \\18487 &:= (-1+T(8)) \times T(4 \times 8) + 7 \\18488 &:= (-1+T(8)) \times T(4 \times 8) + 8 \\18489 &:= (-1+T(8)) \times T(4 \times 8) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18620 &:= (-1+T(T(8))) \times T(T(6)/T(2)) + 0 \\18621 &:= (-1+T(T(8))) \times T(T(6)/T(2)) + 1 \\18622 &:= (-1+T(T(8))) \times T(T(6)/T(2)) + 2 \\18623 &:= (-1+T(T(8))) \times T(T(6)/T(2)) + 3 \\18624 &:= (-1+T(T(8))) \times T(T(6)/T(2)) + 4 \\18625 &:= (-1+T(T(8))) \times T(T(6)/T(2)) + 5 \\18626 &:= (-1+T(T(8))) \times T(T(6)/T(2)) + 6 \\18627 &:= (-1+T(T(8))) \times T(T(6)/T(2)) + 7 \\18628 &:= (-1+T(T(8))) \times T(T(6)/T(2)) + 8 \\18629 &:= (-1+T(T(8))) \times T(T(6)/T(2)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18630 &:= T(T(1+8)) \times 6 \times 3 + 0 \\18631 &:= T(T(1+8)) \times 6 \times 3 + 1 \\18632 &:= T(T(1+8)) \times 6 \times 3 + 2 \\18633 &:= T(T(1+8)) \times 6 \times 3 + 3 \\18634 &:= T(T(1+8)) \times 6 \times 3 + 4 \\18635 &:= T(T(1+8)) \times 6 \times 3 + 5 \\18636 &:= T(T(1+8)) \times 6 \times 3 + 6\end{aligned}$$

$$18637 := T(T(1+8)) \times 6 \times 3 + 7$$

$$18638 := T(T(1+8)) \times 6 \times 3 + 8$$

$$18639 := T(T(1+8)) \times 6 \times 3 + 9$$

$$19920 := (-1 + T(9 \times 9)) \times T(T(2)) + 0$$

$$19921 := (-1 + T(9 \times 9)) \times T(T(2)) + 1$$

$$19922 := (-1 + T(9 \times 9)) \times T(T(2)) + 2$$

$$19923 := (-1 + T(9 \times 9)) \times T(T(2)) + 3$$

$$19924 := (-1 + T(9 \times 9)) \times T(T(2)) + 4$$

$$19925 := (-1 + T(9 \times 9)) \times T(T(2)) + 5$$

$$19926 := (-1 + T(9 \times 9)) \times T(T(2)) + 6$$

$$19927 := (-1 + T(9 \times 9)) \times T(T(2)) + 7$$

$$19928 := (-1 + T(9 \times 9)) \times T(T(2)) + 8$$

$$19929 := (-1 + T(9 \times 9)) \times T(T(2)) + 9$$

$$19950 := T(19) \times T(9+5) + 0$$

$$19951 := T(19) \times T(9+5) + 1$$

$$19952 := T(19) \times T(9+5) + 2$$

$$19953 := T(19) \times T(9+5) + 3$$

$$19954 := T(19) \times T(9+5) + 4$$

$$19955 := T(19) \times T(9+5) + 5$$

$$19956 := T(19) \times T(9+5) + 6$$

$$19957 := T(19) \times T(9+5) + 7$$

$$19958 := T(19) \times T(9+5) + 8$$

$$19959 := T(19) \times T(9+5) + 9$$

$$21420 := T(21 \times 4) \times T(T(2)) + 0$$

$$21421 := T(21 \times 4) \times T(T(2)) + 1$$

$$21422 := T(21 \times 4) \times T(T(2)) + 2$$

$$21423 := T(21 \times 4) \times T(T(2)) + 3$$

$$21424 := T(21 \times 4) \times T(T(2)) + 4$$

$$21425 := T(21 \times 4) \times T(T(2)) + 5$$

$$21426 := T(21 \times 4) \times T(T(2)) + 6$$

$$21427 := T(21 \times 4) \times T(T(2)) + 7$$

$$21428 := T(21 \times 4) \times T(T(2)) + 8$$

$$21429 := T(21 \times 4) \times T(T(2)) + 9$$

$$21450 := T(T(2)+1) \times T(-T(T(4))+T(T(5))) + 0$$

$$21451 := T(T(2)+1) \times T(-T(T(4))+T(T(5))) + 1$$

$$21452 := T(T(2)+1) \times T(-T(T(4))+T(T(5))) + 2$$

$$21453 := T(T(2)+1) \times T(-T(T(4))+T(T(5))) + 3$$

$$21454 := T(T(2)+1) \times T(-T(T(4))+T(T(5))) + 4$$

$$21455 := T(T(2)+1) \times T(-T(T(4))+T(T(5))) + 5$$

$$21456 := T(T(2)+1) \times T(-T(T(4))+T(T(5))) + 6$$

$$21457 := T(T(2)+1) \times T(-T(T(4))+T(T(5))) + 7$$

$$21458 := T(T(2)+1) \times T(-T(T(4))+T(T(5))) + 8$$

$$21459 := T(T(2)+1) \times T(-T(T(4))+T(T(5))) + 9$$

$$22050 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(20) \times 5 + 0$$

$$22051 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(20) \times 5 + 1$$

$$22052 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(20) \times 5 + 2$$

$$22053 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(20) \times 5 + 3$$

$$22054 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(20) \times 5 + 4$$

$$22055 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(20) \times 5 + 5$$

$$22056 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(20) \times 5 + 6$$

$$22057 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(20) \times 5 + 7$$

$$22058 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(20) \times 5 + 8$$

$$22059 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(20) \times 5 + 9$$

$$22110 := T(2+2) \times T(T(11)) + 0$$

$$22111 := T(2+2) \times T(T(11)) + 1$$

$$22112 := T(2+2) \times T(T(11)) + 2$$

$$22113 := T(2+2) \times T(T(11)) + 3$$

$$22114 := T(2+2) \times T(T(11)) + 4$$

$$22115 := T(2+2) \times T(T(11)) + 5$$

$$22116 := T(2+2) \times T(T(11)) + 6$$

$$22117 := T(2+2) \times T(T(11)) + 7$$

$$22118 := T(2+2) \times T(T(11)) + 8$$

$$22119 := T(2+2) \times T(T(11)) + 9$$

$$22330 := T(T(2+2)) \times T(T(T(T(3))/3)) + 0$$

$$22331 := T(T(2+2)) \times T(T(T(T(3))/3)) + 1$$

$$22332 := T(T(2+2)) \times T(T(T(T(3))/3)) + 2$$

$$22333 := T(T(2+2)) \times T(T(T(T(3))/3)) + 3$$

$$22334 := T(T(2+2)) \times T(T(T(T(3))/3)) + 4$$

$$22335 := T(T(2+2)) \times T(T(T(T(3))/3)) + 5$$

$$22336 := T(T(2+2)) \times T(T(T(T(3))/3)) + 6$$

$$22337 := T(T(2+2)) \times T(T(T(T(3))/3)) + 7$$

$$22338 := T(T(2+2)) \times T(T(T(T(3))/3)) + 8$$

$$22339 := T(T(2+2)) \times T(T(T(T(3))/3)) + 9$$

$$22440 := T(2) \times T(2^4) \times T(T(4)) + 0$$

$$22441 := T(2) \times T(2^4) \times T(T(4)) + 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}22442 &:= T(2) \times T(2^4) \times T(T(4)) + 2 \\22443 &:= T(2) \times T(2^4) \times T(T(4)) + 3 \\22444 &:= T(2) \times T(2^4) \times T(T(4)) + 4 \\22445 &:= T(2) \times T(2^4) \times T(T(4)) + 5 \\22446 &:= T(2) \times T(2^4) \times T(T(4)) + 6 \\22447 &:= T(2) \times T(2^4) \times T(T(4)) + 7 \\22448 &:= T(2) \times T(2^4) \times T(T(4)) + 8 \\22449 &:= T(2) \times T(2^4) \times T(T(4)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}22680 &:= T(T(2))^{T(2)} \times T(6+8) + 0 \\22681 &:= T(T(2))^{T(2)} \times T(6+8) + 1 \\22682 &:= T(T(2))^{T(2)} \times T(6+8) + 2 \\22683 &:= T(T(2))^{T(2)} \times T(6+8) + 3 \\22684 &:= T(T(2))^{T(2)} \times T(6+8) + 4 \\22685 &:= T(T(2))^{T(2)} \times T(6+8) + 5 \\22686 &:= T(T(2))^{T(2)} \times T(6+8) + 6 \\22687 &:= T(T(2))^{T(2)} \times T(6+8) + 7 \\22688 &:= T(T(2))^{T(2)} \times T(6+8) + 8 \\22689 &:= T(T(2))^{T(2)} \times T(6+8) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}22950 &:= T(2) \times T(T(2)) \times T(T(9) + 5) + 0 \\22951 &:= T(2) \times T(T(2)) \times T(T(9) + 5) + 1 \\22952 &:= T(2) \times T(T(2)) \times T(T(9) + 5) + 2 \\22953 &:= T(2) \times T(T(2)) \times T(T(9) + 5) + 3 \\22954 &:= T(2) \times T(T(2)) \times T(T(9) + 5) + 4 \\22955 &:= T(2) \times T(T(2)) \times T(T(9) + 5) + 5 \\22956 &:= T(2) \times T(T(2)) \times T(T(9) + 5) + 6 \\22957 &:= T(2) \times T(T(2)) \times T(T(9) + 5) + 7 \\22958 &:= T(2) \times T(T(2)) \times T(T(9) + 5) + 8 \\22959 &:= T(2) \times T(T(2)) \times T(T(9) + 5) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}23100 &:= T(2+3) \times T(T(10)) + 0 \\23101 &:= T(2+3) \times T(T(10)) + 1 \\23102 &:= T(2+3) \times T(T(10)) + 2 \\23103 &:= T(2+3) \times T(T(10)) + 3 \\23104 &:= T(2+3) \times T(T(10)) + 4 \\23105 &:= T(2+3) \times T(T(10)) + 5 \\23106 &:= T(2+3) \times T(T(10)) + 6 \\23107 &:= T(2+3) \times T(T(10)) + 7\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}23108 &:= T(2+3) \times T(T(10)) + 8 \\23109 &:= T(2+3) \times T(T(10)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}23940 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(9+T(4)) + 0 \\23941 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(9+T(4)) + 1 \\23942 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(9+T(4)) + 2 \\23943 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(9+T(4)) + 3 \\23944 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(9+T(4)) + 4 \\23945 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(9+T(4)) + 5 \\23946 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(9+T(4)) + 6 \\23947 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(9+T(4)) + 7 \\23948 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(9+T(4)) + 8 \\23949 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(9+T(4)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}24250 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) - 5 + 0 \\24251 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) - 5 + 1 \\24252 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) - 5 + 2 \\24253 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) - 5 + 3 \\24254 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) - 5 + 4 \\24255 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) - 5 + 5 \\24256 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) - 5 + 6 \\24257 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) - 5 + 7 \\24258 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) - 5 + 8 \\24259 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) - 5 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}24570 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 5 \times 7) + 0 \\24571 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 5 \times 7) + 1 \\24572 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 5 \times 7) + 2 \\24573 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 5 \times 7) + 3 \\24574 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 5 \times 7) + 4 \\24575 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 5 \times 7) + 5 \\24576 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 5 \times 7) + 6 \\24577 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 5 \times 7) + 7 \\24578 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 5 \times 7) + 8 \\24579 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 5 \times 7) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}24720 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(4) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) + 0 \\24721 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(4) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) + 1 \\24722 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(4) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) + 2 \\24723 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(4) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) + 3 \\24724 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(4) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) + 4 \\24725 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(4) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) + 5\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24726 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(4) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) + 6 \\ 24727 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(4) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) + 7 \\ 24728 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(4) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) + 8 \\ 24729 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(4) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24750 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \times 75 + 0 \\ 24751 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \times 75 + 1 \\ 24752 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \times 75 + 2 \\ 24753 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \times 75 + 3 \\ 24754 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \times 75 + 4 \\ 24755 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \times 75 + 5 \\ 24756 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \times 75 + 6 \\ 24757 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \times 75 + 7 \\ 24758 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \times 75 + 8 \\ 24759 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \times 75 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24760 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7)) - 6 + 0 \\ 24761 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7)) - 6 + 1 \\ 24762 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7)) - 6 + 2 \\ 24763 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7)) - 6 + 3 \\ 24764 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7)) - 6 + 4 \\ 24765 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7)) - 6 + 5 \\ 24766 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7)) - 6 + 6 \\ 24767 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7)) - 6 + 7 \\ 24768 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7)) - 6 + 8 \\ 24769 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7)) - 6 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24840 &:= 24 \times T(T(T(8)/4)) + 0 \\ 24841 &:= 24 \times T(T(T(8)/4)) + 1 \\ 24842 &:= 24 \times T(T(T(8)/4)) + 2 \\ 24843 &:= 24 \times T(T(T(8)/4)) + 3 \\ 24844 &:= 24 \times T(T(T(8)/4)) + 4 \\ 24845 &:= 24 \times T(T(T(8)/4)) + 5 \\ 24846 &:= 24 \times T(T(T(8)/4)) + 6 \\ 24847 &:= 24 \times T(T(T(8)/4)) + 7 \\ 24848 &:= 24 \times T(T(T(8)/4)) + 8 \\ 24849 &:= 24 \times T(T(T(8)/4)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24900 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(90)) + 0 \\ 24901 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(90)) + 1 \\ 24902 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(90)) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24903 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(90)) + 3 \\ 24904 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(90)) + 4 \\ 24905 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(90)) + 5 \\ 24906 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(90)) + 6 \\ 24907 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(90)) + 7 \\ 24908 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(90)) + 8 \\ 24909 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(90)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24960 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(4)) + 9) \times 6 + 0 \\ 24961 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(4)) + 9) \times 6 + 1 \\ 24962 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(4)) + 9) \times 6 + 2 \\ 24963 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(4)) + 9) \times 6 + 3 \\ 24964 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(4)) + 9) \times 6 + 4 \\ 24965 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(4)) + 9) \times 6 + 5 \\ 24966 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(4)) + 9) \times 6 + 6 \\ 24967 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(4)) + 9) \times 6 + 7 \\ 24968 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(4)) + 9) \times 6 + 8 \\ 24969 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(4)) + 9) \times 6 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25200 &:= T(T(2) \times 5) \times T(20) + 0 \\ 25201 &:= T(T(2) \times 5) \times T(20) + 1 \\ 25202 &:= T(T(2) \times 5) \times T(20) + 2 \\ 25203 &:= T(T(2) \times 5) \times T(20) + 3 \\ 25204 &:= T(T(2) \times 5) \times T(20) + 4 \\ 25205 &:= T(T(2) \times 5) \times T(20) + 5 \\ 25206 &:= T(T(2) \times 5) \times T(20) + 6 \\ 25207 &:= T(T(2) \times 5) \times T(20) + 7 \\ 25208 &:= T(T(2) \times 5) \times T(20) + 8 \\ 25209 &:= T(T(2) \times 5) \times T(20) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25290 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(2 \times T(9))) + 0 \\ 25291 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(2 \times T(9))) + 1 \\ 25292 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(2 \times T(9))) + 2 \\ 25293 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(2 \times T(9))) + 3 \\ 25294 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(2 \times T(9))) + 4 \\ 25295 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(2 \times T(9))) + 5 \\ 25296 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(2 \times T(9))) + 6 \\ 25297 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(2 \times T(9))) + 7 \\ 25298 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(2 \times T(9))) + 8 \\ 25299 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(2 \times T(9))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$25350 := T(25) \times T(-3 + T(5)) + 0$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25351 &:= T(25) \times T(-3 + T(5)) + 1 \\ 25352 &:= T(25) \times T(-3 + T(5)) + 2 \\ 25353 &:= T(25) \times T(-3 + T(5)) + 3 \\ 25354 &:= T(25) \times T(-3 + T(5)) + 4 \\ 25355 &:= T(25) \times T(-3 + T(5)) + 5 \\ 25356 &:= T(25) \times T(-3 + T(5)) + 6 \\ 25357 &:= T(25) \times T(-3 + T(5)) + 7 \\ 25358 &:= T(25) \times T(-3 + T(5)) + 8 \\ 25359 &:= T(25) \times T(-3 + T(5)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25620 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) + 0 \\ 25621 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) + 1 \\ 25622 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) + 2 \\ 25623 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) + 3 \\ 25624 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) + 4 \\ 25625 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) + 5 \\ 25626 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) + 6 \\ 25627 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) + 7 \\ 25628 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) + 8 \\ 25629 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25740 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(5 + 7) \times T(T(4)) + 0 \\ 25741 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(5 + 7) \times T(T(4)) + 1 \\ 25742 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(5 + 7) \times T(T(4)) + 2 \\ 25743 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(5 + 7) \times T(T(4)) + 3 \\ 25744 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(5 + 7) \times T(T(4)) + 4 \\ 25745 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(5 + 7) \times T(T(4)) + 5 \\ 25746 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(5 + 7) \times T(T(4)) + 6 \\ 25747 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(5 + 7) \times T(T(4)) + 7 \\ 25748 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(5 + 7) \times T(T(4)) + 8 \\ 25749 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(5 + 7) \times T(T(4)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25830 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5)) \times T(8 + T(3)) + 0 \\ 25831 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5)) \times T(8 + T(3)) + 1 \\ 25832 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5)) \times T(8 + T(3)) + 2 \\ 25833 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5)) \times T(8 + T(3)) + 3 \\ 25834 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5)) \times T(8 + T(3)) + 4 \\ 25835 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5)) \times T(8 + T(3)) + 5 \\ 25836 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5)) \times T(8 + T(3)) + 6 \\ 25837 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5)) \times T(8 + T(3)) + 7 \\ 25838 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5)) \times T(8 + T(3)) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$25839 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5)) \times T(8 + T(3)) + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25880 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8) + 8 + 0 \\ 25881 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8) + 8 + 1 \\ 25882 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8) + 8 + 2 \\ 25883 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8) + 8 + 3 \\ 25884 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8) + 8 + 4 \\ 25885 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8) + 8 + 5 \\ 25886 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8) + 8 + 6 \\ 25887 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8) + 8 + 7 \\ 25888 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8) + 8 + 8 \\ 25889 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8) + 8 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25990 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5) \times T(T(9))/9 + 0 \\ 25991 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5) \times T(T(9))/9 + 1 \\ 25992 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5) \times T(T(9))/9 + 2 \\ 25993 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5) \times T(T(9))/9 + 3 \\ 25994 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5) \times T(T(9))/9 + 4 \\ 25995 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5) \times T(T(9))/9 + 5 \\ 25996 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5) \times T(T(9))/9 + 6 \\ 25997 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5) \times T(T(9))/9 + 7 \\ 25998 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5) \times T(T(9))/9 + 8 \\ 25999 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5) \times T(T(9))/9 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26280 &:= T(-2 + 6) \times T(2 \times T(8)) + 0 \\ 26281 &:= T(-2 + 6) \times T(2 \times T(8)) + 1 \\ 26282 &:= T(-2 + 6) \times T(2 \times T(8)) + 2 \\ 26283 &:= T(-2 + 6) \times T(2 \times T(8)) + 3 \\ 26284 &:= T(-2 + 6) \times T(2 \times T(8)) + 4 \\ 26285 &:= T(-2 + 6) \times T(2 \times T(8)) + 5 \\ 26286 &:= T(-2 + 6) \times T(2 \times T(8)) + 6 \\ 26287 &:= T(-2 + 6) \times T(2 \times T(8)) + 7 \\ 26288 &:= T(-2 + 6) \times T(2 \times T(8)) + 8 \\ 26289 &:= T(-2 + 6) \times T(2 \times T(8)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26460 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(6) \times T(4) \times T(6) + 0 \\ 26461 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(6) \times T(4) \times T(6) + 1 \\ 26462 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(6) \times T(4) \times T(6) + 2 \\ 26463 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(6) \times T(4) \times T(6) + 3 \\ 26464 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(6) \times T(4) \times T(6) + 4 \\ 26465 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(6) \times T(4) \times T(6) + 5 \\ 26466 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(6) \times T(4) \times T(6) + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$26467 := T(T(2)) \times T(6) \times T(4) \times T(6) + 7$$

$$26468 := T(T(2)) \times T(6) \times T(4) \times T(6) + 8$$

$$26469 := T(T(2)) \times T(6) \times T(4) \times T(6) + 9$$

$$26540 := (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) + 0$$

$$26541 := (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) + 1$$

$$26542 := (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) + 2$$

$$26543 := (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) + 3$$

$$26544 := (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) + 4$$

$$26545 := (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) + 5$$

$$26546 := (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) + 6$$

$$26547 := (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) + 7$$

$$26548 := (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) + 8$$

$$26549 := (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) + 9$$

$$26550 := T(2^6 - 5) \times T(5) + 0$$

$$26551 := T(2^6 - 5) \times T(5) + 1$$

$$26552 := T(2^6 - 5) \times T(5) + 2$$

$$26553 := T(2^6 - 5) \times T(5) + 3$$

$$26554 := T(2^6 - 5) \times T(5) + 4$$

$$26555 := T(2^6 - 5) \times T(5) + 5$$

$$26556 := T(2^6 - 5) \times T(5) + 6$$

$$26557 := T(2^6 - 5) \times T(5) + 7$$

$$26558 := T(2^6 - 5) \times T(5) + 8$$

$$26559 := T(2^6 - 5) \times T(5) + 9$$

$$26790 := T(T(2)) \times T(T(6) + T(7) + T(9)) + 0$$

$$26791 := T(T(2)) \times T(T(6) + T(7) + T(9)) + 1$$

$$26792 := T(T(2)) \times T(T(6) + T(7) + T(9)) + 2$$

$$26793 := T(T(2)) \times T(T(6) + T(7) + T(9)) + 3$$

$$26794 := T(T(2)) \times T(T(6) + T(7) + T(9)) + 4$$

$$26795 := T(T(2)) \times T(T(6) + T(7) + T(9)) + 5$$

$$26796 := T(T(2)) \times T(T(6) + T(7) + T(9)) + 6$$

$$26797 := T(T(2)) \times T(T(6) + T(7) + T(9)) + 7$$

$$26798 := T(T(2)) \times T(T(6) + T(7) + T(9)) + 8$$

$$26799 := T(T(2)) \times T(T(6) + T(7) + T(9)) + 9$$

$$26910 := 26 \times T(T(9)) + 1 \times 0$$

$$26911 := 26 \times T(T(9)) + 1 \times 1$$

$$26912 := 26 \times T(T(9)) + 1 \times 2$$

$$26913 := 26 \times T(T(9)) + 1 \times 3$$

$$26914 := 26 \times T(T(9)) + 1 \times 4$$

$$26915 := 26 \times T(T(9)) + 1 \times 5$$

$$26916 := 26 \times T(T(9)) + 1 \times 6$$

$$26917 := 26 \times T(T(9)) + 1 \times 7$$

$$26918 := 26 \times T(T(9)) + 1 \times 8$$

$$26919 := 26 \times T(T(9)) + 1 \times 9$$

$$27280 := T(T(2) + T(7)) \times T(2 + 8) + 0$$

$$27281 := T(T(2) + T(7)) \times T(2 + 8) + 1$$

$$27282 := T(T(2) + T(7)) \times T(2 + 8) + 2$$

$$27283 := T(T(2) + T(7)) \times T(2 + 8) + 3$$

$$27284 := T(T(2) + T(7)) \times T(2 + 8) + 4$$

$$27285 := T(T(2) + T(7)) \times T(2 + 8) + 5$$

$$27286 := T(T(2) + T(7)) \times T(2 + 8) + 6$$

$$27287 := T(T(2) + T(7)) \times T(2 + 8) + 7$$

$$27288 := T(T(2) + T(7)) \times T(2 + 8) + 8$$

$$27289 := T(T(2) + T(7)) \times T(2 + 8) + 9$$

$$27360 := T(T(-2 + 7)) \times (-3 + T(T(6))) + 0$$

$$27361 := T(T(-2 + 7)) \times (-3 + T(T(6))) + 1$$

$$27362 := T(T(-2 + 7)) \times (-3 + T(T(6))) + 2$$

$$27363 := T(T(-2 + 7)) \times (-3 + T(T(6))) + 3$$

$$27364 := T(T(-2 + 7)) \times (-3 + T(T(6))) + 4$$

$$27365 := T(T(-2 + 7)) \times (-3 + T(T(6))) + 5$$

$$27366 := T(T(-2 + 7)) \times (-3 + T(T(6))) + 6$$

$$27367 := T(T(-2 + 7)) \times (-3 + T(T(6))) + 7$$

$$27368 := T(T(-2 + 7)) \times (-3 + T(T(6))) + 8$$

$$27369 := T(T(-2 + 7)) \times (-3 + T(T(6))) + 9$$

$$27450 := T(-2 + 7) \times T(4 \times T(5)) + 0$$

$$27451 := T(-2 + 7) \times T(4 \times T(5)) + 1$$

$$27452 := T(-2 + 7) \times T(4 \times T(5)) + 2$$

$$27453 := T(-2 + 7) \times T(4 \times T(5)) + 3$$

$$27454 := T(-2 + 7) \times T(4 \times T(5)) + 4$$

$$27455 := T(-2 + 7) \times T(4 \times T(5)) + 5$$

$$27456 := T(-2 + 7) \times T(4 \times T(5)) + 6$$

$$27457 := T(-2 + 7) \times T(4 \times T(5)) + 7$$

$$27458 := T(-2 + 7) \times T(4 \times T(5)) + 8$$

$$27459 := T(-2 + 7) \times T(4 \times T(5)) + 9$$

$$27720 := T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7 - 2)) + 0$$

$$27721 := T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7 - 2)) + 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}27722 &:= T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) + 2 \\27723 &:= T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) + 3 \\27724 &:= T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) + 4 \\27725 &:= T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) + 5 \\27726 &:= T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) + 6 \\27727 &:= T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) + 7 \\27728 &:= T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) + 8 \\27729 &:= T(T(2) \times 7) \times T(T(7-2)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}27950 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + 5 + 0 \\27951 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + 5 + 1 \\27952 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + 5 + 2 \\27953 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + 5 + 3 \\27954 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + 5 + 4 \\27955 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + 5 + 5 \\27956 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + 5 + 6 \\27957 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + 5 + 7 \\27958 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + 5 + 8 \\27959 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + 5 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}27990 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + T(9) + 0 \\27991 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + T(9) + 1 \\27992 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + T(9) + 2 \\27993 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + T(9) + 3 \\27994 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + T(9) + 4 \\27995 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + T(9) + 5 \\27996 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + T(9) + 6 \\27997 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + T(9) + 7 \\27998 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + T(9) + 8 \\27999 &:= 27 \times T(T(9)) + T(9) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}28080 &:= T(T(2) + T(8)) \times T(08) + 0 \\28081 &:= T(T(2) + T(8)) \times T(08) + 1 \\28082 &:= T(T(2) + T(8)) \times T(08) + 2 \\28083 &:= T(T(2) + T(8)) \times T(08) + 3 \\28084 &:= T(T(2) + T(8)) \times T(08) + 4 \\28085 &:= T(T(2) + T(8)) \times T(08) + 5 \\28086 &:= T(T(2) + T(8)) \times T(08) + 6 \\28087 &:= T(T(2) + T(8)) \times T(08) + 7 \\28088 &:= T(T(2) + T(8)) \times T(08) + 8 \\28089 &:= T(T(2) + T(8)) \times T(08) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}28230 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2 + T(3) + 0 \\28231 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2 + T(3) + 1 \\28232 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2 + T(3) + 2 \\28233 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2 + T(3) + 3 \\28234 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2 + T(3) + 4 \\28235 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2 + T(3) + 5 \\28236 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2 + T(3) + 6 \\28237 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2 + T(3) + 7 \\28238 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2 + T(3) + 8 \\28239 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2 + T(3) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}28560 &:= T(2 \times 8) \times T(T(T(5))/6) + 0 \\28561 &:= T(2 \times 8) \times T(T(T(5))/6) + 1 \\28562 &:= T(2 \times 8) \times T(T(T(5))/6) + 2 \\28563 &:= T(2 \times 8) \times T(T(T(5))/6) + 3 \\28564 &:= T(2 \times 8) \times T(T(T(5))/6) + 4 \\28565 &:= T(2 \times 8) \times T(T(T(5))/6) + 5 \\28566 &:= T(2 \times 8) \times T(T(T(5))/6) + 6 \\28567 &:= T(2 \times 8) \times T(T(T(5))/6) + 7 \\28568 &:= T(2 \times 8) \times T(T(T(5))/6) + 8 \\28569 &:= T(2 \times 8) \times T(T(T(5))/6) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}28680 &:= T(T(-T(2) + 8)) \times (T(T(6)) + 8) + 0 \\28681 &:= T(T(-T(2) + 8)) \times (T(T(6)) + 8) + 1 \\28682 &:= T(T(-T(2) + 8)) \times (T(T(6)) + 8) + 2 \\28683 &:= T(T(-T(2) + 8)) \times (T(T(6)) + 8) + 3 \\28684 &:= T(T(-T(2) + 8)) \times (T(T(6)) + 8) + 4 \\28685 &:= T(T(-T(2) + 8)) \times (T(T(6)) + 8) + 5 \\28686 &:= T(T(-T(2) + 8)) \times (T(T(6)) + 8) + 6 \\28687 &:= T(T(-T(2) + 8)) \times (T(T(6)) + 8) + 7 \\28688 &:= T(T(-T(2) + 8)) \times (T(T(6)) + 8) + 8 \\28689 &:= T(T(-T(2) + 8)) \times (T(T(6)) + 8) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}28710 &:= T(T(2) + 8) \times T(T(7) + 1) + 0 \\28711 &:= T(T(2) + 8) \times T(T(7) + 1) + 1 \\28712 &:= T(T(2) + 8) \times T(T(7) + 1) + 2 \\28713 &:= T(T(2) + 8) \times T(T(7) + 1) + 3 \\28714 &:= T(T(2) + 8) \times T(T(7) + 1) + 4 \\28715 &:= T(T(2) + 8) \times T(T(7) + 1) + 5 \\28716 &:= T(T(2) + 8) \times T(T(7) + 1) + 6\end{aligned}$$

$$28717 := T(T(2) + 8) \times T(T(7) + 1) + 7$$

$$28718 := T(T(2) + 8) \times T(T(7) + 1) + 8$$

$$28719 := T(T(2) + 8) \times T(T(7) + 1) + 9$$

$$28890 := (-T(2) \times 8 + T(T(8))) \times T(9) + 0$$

$$28891 := (-T(2) \times 8 + T(T(8))) \times T(9) + 1$$

$$28892 := (-T(2) \times 8 + T(T(8))) \times T(9) + 2$$

$$28893 := (-T(2) \times 8 + T(T(8))) \times T(9) + 3$$

$$28894 := (-T(2) \times 8 + T(T(8))) \times T(9) + 4$$

$$28895 := (-T(2) \times 8 + T(T(8))) \times T(9) + 5$$

$$28896 := (-T(2) \times 8 + T(T(8))) \times T(9) + 6$$

$$28897 := (-T(2) \times 8 + T(T(8))) \times T(9) + 7$$

$$28898 := (-T(2) \times 8 + T(T(8))) \times T(9) + 8$$

$$28899 := (-T(2) \times 8 + T(T(8))) \times T(9) + 9$$

$$28980 := 28 \times T(9 + T(8)) + 0$$

$$28981 := 28 \times T(9 + T(8)) + 1$$

$$28982 := 28 \times T(9 + T(8)) + 2$$

$$28983 := 28 \times T(9 + T(8)) + 3$$

$$28984 := 28 \times T(9 + T(8)) + 4$$

$$28985 := 28 \times T(9 + T(8)) + 5$$

$$28986 := 28 \times T(9 + T(8)) + 6$$

$$28987 := 28 \times T(9 + T(8)) + 7$$

$$28988 := 28 \times T(9 + T(8)) + 8$$

$$28989 := 28 \times T(9 + T(8)) + 9$$

$$29250 := 2 \times T(9) \times T(25) + 0$$

$$29251 := 2 \times T(9) \times T(25) + 1$$

$$29252 := 2 \times T(9) \times T(25) + 2$$

$$29253 := 2 \times T(9) \times T(25) + 3$$

$$29254 := 2 \times T(9) \times T(25) + 4$$

$$29255 := 2 \times T(9) \times T(25) + 5$$

$$29256 := 2 \times T(9) \times T(25) + 6$$

$$29257 := 2 \times T(9) \times T(25) + 7$$

$$29258 := 2 \times T(9) \times T(25) + 8$$

$$29259 := 2 \times T(9) \times T(25) + 9$$

$$29770 := T(T(2)) + (T(T(9)) + T(7)) \times T(7) + 0$$

$$29771 := T(T(2)) + (T(T(9)) + T(7)) \times T(7) + 1$$

$$29772 := T(T(2)) + (T(T(9)) + T(7)) \times T(7) + 2$$

$$29773 := T(T(2)) + (T(T(9)) + T(7)) \times T(7) + 3$$

$$29774 := T(T(2)) + (T(T(9)) + T(7)) \times T(7) + 4$$

$$29775 := T(T(2)) + (T(T(9)) + T(7)) \times T(7) + 5$$

$$29776 := T(T(2)) + (T(T(9)) + T(7)) \times T(7) + 6$$

$$29777 := T(T(2)) + (T(T(9)) + T(7)) \times T(7) + 7$$

$$29778 := T(T(2)) + (T(T(9)) + T(7)) \times T(7) + 8$$

$$29779 := T(T(2)) + (T(T(9)) + T(7)) \times T(7) + 9$$

$$29820 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(9) + 8) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 0$$

$$29821 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(9) + 8) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1$$

$$29822 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(9) + 8) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 2$$

$$29823 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(9) + 8) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 3$$

$$29824 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(9) + 8) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 4$$

$$29825 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(9) + 8) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 5$$

$$29826 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(9) + 8) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 6$$

$$29827 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(9) + 8) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 7$$

$$29828 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(9) + 8) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 8$$

$$29829 := T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(9) + 8) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 9$$

$$30690 := T(30) \times (T(6) + T(9)) + 0$$

$$30691 := T(30) \times (T(6) + T(9)) + 1$$

$$30692 := T(30) \times (T(6) + T(9)) + 2$$

$$30693 := T(30) \times (T(6) + T(9)) + 3$$

$$30694 := T(30) \times (T(6) + T(9)) + 4$$

$$30695 := T(30) \times (T(6) + T(9)) + 5$$

$$30696 := T(30) \times (T(6) + T(9)) + 6$$

$$30697 := T(30) \times (T(6) + T(9)) + 7$$

$$30698 := T(30) \times (T(6) + T(9)) + 8$$

$$30699 := T(30) \times (T(6) + T(9)) + 9$$

$$31280 := (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \times T(2 \times 8) + 0$$

$$31281 := (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \times T(2 \times 8) + 1$$

$$31282 := (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \times T(2 \times 8) + 2$$

$$31283 := (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \times T(2 \times 8) + 3$$

$$31284 := (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \times T(2 \times 8) + 4$$

$$31285 := (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \times T(2 \times 8) + 5$$

$$31286 := (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \times T(2 \times 8) + 6$$

$$31287 := (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \times T(2 \times 8) + 7$$

$$31288 := (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \times T(2 \times 8) + 8$$

$$31289 := (T(T(T(3))) - 1) \times T(2 \times 8) + 9$$

$$32340 := T(T(3)) \times T(T(2 \times 3 + 4)) + 0$$

$$32341 := T(T(3)) \times T(T(2 \times 3 + 4)) + 1$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32342 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(2 \times 3 + 4)) + 2 \\ 32343 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(2 \times 3 + 4)) + 3 \\ 32344 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(2 \times 3 + 4)) + 4 \\ 32345 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(2 \times 3 + 4)) + 5 \\ 32346 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(2 \times 3 + 4)) + 6 \\ 32347 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(2 \times 3 + 4)) + 7 \\ 32348 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(2 \times 3 + 4)) + 8 \\ 32349 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(2 \times 3 + 4)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32490 &:= T(T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(T(4) + 9) + 0 \\ 32491 &:= T(T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(T(4) + 9) + 1 \\ 32492 &:= T(T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(T(4) + 9) + 2 \\ 32493 &:= T(T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(T(4) + 9) + 3 \\ 32494 &:= T(T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(T(4) + 9) + 4 \\ 32495 &:= T(T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(T(4) + 9) + 5 \\ 32496 &:= T(T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(T(4) + 9) + 6 \\ 32497 &:= T(T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(T(4) + 9) + 7 \\ 32498 &:= T(T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(T(4) + 9) + 8 \\ 32499 &:= T(T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(T(4) + 9) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32640 &:= T(T(T(3)) + T(2)) + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + 0 \\ 32641 &:= T(T(T(3)) + T(2)) + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + 1 \\ 32642 &:= T(T(T(3)) + T(2)) + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + 2 \\ 32643 &:= T(T(T(3)) + T(2)) + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + 3 \\ 32644 &:= T(T(T(3)) + T(2)) + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + 4 \\ 32645 &:= T(T(T(3)) + T(2)) + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + 5 \\ 32646 &:= T(T(T(3)) + T(2)) + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + 6 \\ 32647 &:= T(T(T(3)) + T(2)) + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + 7 \\ 32648 &:= T(T(T(3)) + T(2)) + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + 8 \\ 32649 &:= T(T(T(3)) + T(2)) + T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33150 &:= (T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) - 1 \times T(5) + 0 \\ 33151 &:= (T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) - 1 \times T(5) + 1 \\ 33152 &:= (T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) - 1 \times T(5) + 2 \\ 33153 &:= (T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) - 1 \times T(5) + 3 \\ 33154 &:= (T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) - 1 \times T(5) + 4 \\ 33155 &:= (T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) - 1 \times T(5) + 5 \\ 33156 &:= (T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) - 1 \times T(5) + 6 \\ 33157 &:= (T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) - 1 \times T(5) + 7 \\ 33158 &:= (T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) - 1 \times T(5) + 8 \\ 33159 &:= (T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) - 1 \times T(5) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34320 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3 + 2)) + 0 \\ 34321 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3 + 2)) + 1 \\ 34322 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3 + 2)) + 2 \\ 34323 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3 + 2)) + 3 \\ 34324 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3 + 2)) + 4 \\ 34325 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3 + 2)) + 5 \\ 34326 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3 + 2)) + 6 \\ 34327 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3 + 2)) + 7 \\ 34328 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3 + 2)) + 8 \\ 34329 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3 + 2)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34420 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^{T(2)}) + 0 \\ 34421 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^{T(2)}) + 1 \\ 34422 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^{T(2)}) + 2 \\ 34423 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^{T(2)}) + 3 \\ 34424 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^{T(2)}) + 4 \\ 34426 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^{T(2)}) + 5 \\ 34427 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^{T(2)}) + 6 \\ 34428 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^{T(2)}) + 7 \\ 34429 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^{T(2)}) + 8 \\ 34440 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) + 0 \\ 34440 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(4^{T(2)}) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34441 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) + 1 \\ 34442 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) + 2 \\ 34443 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) + 3 \\ 34444 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) + 4 \\ 34445 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) + 5 \\ 34446 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) + 6 \\ 34447 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) + 7 \\ 34448 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) + 8 \\ 34449 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(4) \times T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34450 &:= T(-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + 0 \\ 34451 &:= T(-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + 1 \\ 34452 &:= T(-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + 2 \\ 34453 &:= T(-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + 3 \\ 34454 &:= T(-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + 4 \\ 34455 &:= T(-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + 5 \\ 34456 &:= T(-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34457 &:= T(-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + 7 \\ 34458 &:= T(-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + 8 \\ 34459 &:= T(-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34650 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 6 \times 5 + 0 \\ 34651 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 6 \times 5 + 1 \\ 34652 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 6 \times 5 + 2 \\ 34653 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 6 \times 5 + 3 \\ 34654 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 6 \times 5 + 4 \\ 34655 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 6 \times 5 + 5 \\ 34656 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 6 \times 5 + 6 \\ 34657 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 6 \times 5 + 7 \\ 34658 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 6 \times 5 + 8 \\ 34659 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 6 \times 5 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34840 &:= (-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(8)) + 4) + 0 \\ 34841 &:= (-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(8)) + 4) + 1 \\ 34842 &:= (-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(8)) + 4) + 2 \\ 34843 &:= (-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(8)) + 4) + 3 \\ 34844 &:= (-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(8)) + 4) + 4 \\ 34845 &:= (-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(8)) + 4) + 5 \\ 34846 &:= (-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(8)) + 4) + 6 \\ 34847 &:= (-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(8)) + 4) + 7 \\ 34848 &:= (-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(8)) + 4) + 8 \\ 34849 &:= (-3 + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(8)) + 4) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34860 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8) - T(6))) + 0 \\ 34861 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8) - T(6))) + 1 \\ 34862 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8) - T(6))) + 2 \\ 34863 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8) - T(6))) + 3 \\ 34864 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8) - T(6))) + 4 \\ 34865 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8) - T(6))) + 5 \\ 34866 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8) - T(6))) + 6 \\ 34867 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8) - T(6))) + 7 \\ 34868 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8) - T(6))) + 8 \\ 34869 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8) - T(6))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35190 &:= (35 - 1) \times T(T(9)) + 0 \\ 35191 &:= (35 - 1) \times T(T(9)) + 1 \\ 35192 &:= (35 - 1) \times T(T(9)) + 2 \\ 35193 &:= (35 - 1) \times T(T(9)) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35194 &:= (35 - 1) \times T(T(9)) + 4 \\ 35195 &:= (35 - 1) \times T(T(9)) + 5 \\ 35196 &:= (35 - 1) \times T(T(9)) + 6 \\ 35197 &:= (35 - 1) \times T(T(9)) + 7 \\ 35198 &:= (35 - 1) \times T(T(9)) + 8 \\ 35199 &:= (35 - 1) \times T(T(9)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35280 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) \times (T(T(2)) + 8) + 0 \\ 35281 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) \times (T(T(2)) + 8) + 1 \\ 35282 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) \times (T(T(2)) + 8) + 2 \\ 35283 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) \times (T(T(2)) + 8) + 3 \\ 35284 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) \times (T(T(2)) + 8) + 4 \\ 35285 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) \times (T(T(2)) + 8) + 5 \\ 35286 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) \times (T(T(2)) + 8) + 6 \\ 35287 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) \times (T(T(2)) + 8) + 7 \\ 35288 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) \times (T(T(2)) + 8) + 8 \\ 35289 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) \times (T(T(2)) + 8) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35340 &:= T(T(3) \times 5) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) + 0 \\ 35341 &:= T(T(3) \times 5) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) + 1 \\ 35342 &:= T(T(3) \times 5) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) + 2 \\ 35343 &:= T(T(3) \times 5) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) + 3 \\ 35344 &:= T(T(3) \times 5) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) + 4 \\ 35345 &:= T(T(3) \times 5) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) + 5 \\ 35346 &:= T(T(3) \times 5) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) + 6 \\ 35347 &:= T(T(3) \times 5) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) + 7 \\ 35348 &:= T(T(3) \times 5) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) + 8 \\ 35349 &:= T(T(3) \times 5) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35640 &:= 3 \times (-T(5) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4)) + 0 \\ 35641 &:= 3 \times (-T(5) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4)) + 1 \\ 35642 &:= 3 \times (-T(5) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4)) + 2 \\ 35643 &:= 3 \times (-T(5) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4)) + 3 \\ 35644 &:= 3 \times (-T(5) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4)) + 4 \\ 35645 &:= 3 \times (-T(5) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4)) + 5 \\ 35646 &:= 3 \times (-T(5) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4)) + 6 \\ 35647 &:= 3 \times (-T(5) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4)) + 7 \\ 35648 &:= 3 \times (-T(5) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4)) + 8 \\ 35649 &:= 3 \times (-T(5) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36270 &:= T(T(3) + 6) \times T(2 + T(7)) + 0 \\ 36271 &:= T(T(3) + 6) \times T(2 + T(7)) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36272 &:= T(T(3) + 6) \times T(2 + T(7)) + 2 \\ 36273 &:= T(T(3) + 6) \times T(2 + T(7)) + 3 \\ 36274 &:= T(T(3) + 6) \times T(2 + T(7)) + 4 \\ 36275 &:= T(T(3) + 6) \times T(2 + T(7)) + 5 \\ 36276 &:= T(T(3) + 6) \times T(2 + T(7)) + 6 \\ 36277 &:= T(T(3) + 6) \times T(2 + T(7)) + 7 \\ 36278 &:= T(T(3) + 6) \times T(2 + T(7)) + 8 \\ 36279 &:= T(T(3) + 6) \times T(2 + T(7)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36450 &:= 3^6 \times T(4) \times 5 + 0 \\ 36451 &:= 3^6 \times T(4) \times 5 + 1 \\ 36452 &:= 3^6 \times T(4) \times 5 + 2 \\ 36453 &:= 3^6 \times T(4) \times 5 + 3 \\ 36454 &:= 3^6 \times T(4) \times 5 + 4 \\ 36455 &:= 3^6 \times T(4) \times 5 + 5 \\ 36456 &:= 3^6 \times T(4) \times 5 + 6 \\ 36457 &:= 3^6 \times T(4) \times 5 + 7 \\ 36458 &:= 3^6 \times T(4) \times 5 + 8 \\ 36459 &:= 3^6 \times T(4) \times 5 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36480 &:= T(T(T(T(3))) - T(6 + T(4))) \times 8 + 0 \\ 36481 &:= T(T(T(T(3))) - T(6 + T(4))) \times 8 + 1 \\ 36482 &:= T(T(T(T(3))) - T(6 + T(4))) \times 8 + 2 \\ 36483 &:= T(T(T(T(3))) - T(6 + T(4))) \times 8 + 3 \\ 36484 &:= T(T(T(T(3))) - T(6 + T(4))) \times 8 + 4 \\ 36485 &:= T(T(T(T(3))) - T(6 + T(4))) \times 8 + 5 \\ 36486 &:= T(T(T(T(3))) - T(6 + T(4))) \times 8 + 6 \\ 36487 &:= T(T(T(T(3))) - T(6 + T(4))) \times 8 + 7 \\ 36488 &:= T(T(T(T(3))) - T(6 + T(4))) \times 8 + 8 \\ 36489 &:= T(T(T(T(3))) - T(6 + T(4))) \times 8 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36750 &:= T(3) \times T(T(6) + T(7)) \times 5 + 0 \\ 36751 &:= T(3) \times T(T(6) + T(7)) \times 5 + 1 \\ 36752 &:= T(3) \times T(T(6) + T(7)) \times 5 + 2 \\ 36753 &:= T(3) \times T(T(6) + T(7)) \times 5 + 3 \\ 36754 &:= T(3) \times T(T(6) + T(7)) \times 5 + 4 \\ 36755 &:= T(3) \times T(T(6) + T(7)) \times 5 + 5 \\ 36756 &:= T(3) \times T(T(6) + T(7)) \times 5 + 6 \\ 36757 &:= T(3) \times T(T(6) + T(7)) \times 5 + 7 \\ 36758 &:= T(3) \times T(T(6) + T(7)) \times 5 + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$36759 := T(3) \times T(T(6) + T(7)) \times 5 + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36840 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(4)) + 0 \\ 36841 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(4)) + 1 \\ 36842 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(4)) + 2 \\ 36843 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(4)) + 3 \\ 36844 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(4)) + 4 \\ 36845 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(4)) + 5 \\ 36846 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(4)) + 6 \\ 36847 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(4)) + 7 \\ 36848 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(4)) + 8 \\ 36849 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(4)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37260 &:= T(3) \times T(T(7 + 2)) \times 6 + 0 \\ 37261 &:= T(3) \times T(T(7 + 2)) \times 6 + 1 \\ 37262 &:= T(3) \times T(T(7 + 2)) \times 6 + 2 \\ 37263 &:= T(3) \times T(T(7 + 2)) \times 6 + 3 \\ 37264 &:= T(3) \times T(T(7 + 2)) \times 6 + 4 \\ 37265 &:= T(3) \times T(T(7 + 2)) \times 6 + 5 \\ 37266 &:= T(3) \times T(T(7 + 2)) \times 6 + 6 \\ 37267 &:= T(3) \times T(T(7 + 2)) \times 6 + 7 \\ 37268 &:= T(3) \times T(T(7 + 2)) \times 6 + 8 \\ 37269 &:= T(3) \times T(T(7 + 2)) \times 6 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37840 &:= (-T(3) + T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(4)) + 0 \\ 37841 &:= (-T(3) + T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(4)) + 1 \\ 37842 &:= (-T(3) + T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(4)) + 2 \\ 37843 &:= (-T(3) + T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(4)) + 3 \\ 37844 &:= (-T(3) + T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(4)) + 4 \\ 37845 &:= (-T(3) + T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(4)) + 5 \\ 37846 &:= (-T(3) + T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(4)) + 6 \\ 37847 &:= (-T(3) + T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(4)) + 7 \\ 37848 &:= (-T(3) + T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(4)) + 8 \\ 37849 &:= (-T(3) + T(7) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(4)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37920 &:= T(3) \times T(79) \times 2 + 0 \\ 37921 &:= T(3) \times T(79) \times 2 + 1 \\ 37922 &:= T(3) \times T(79) \times 2 + 2 \\ 37923 &:= T(3) \times T(79) \times 2 + 3 \\ 37924 &:= T(3) \times T(79) \times 2 + 4 \\ 37925 &:= T(3) \times T(79) \times 2 + 5 \\ 37926 &:= T(3) \times T(79) \times 2 + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$37927 := T(3) \times T(79) \times 2 + 7$$

$$37928 := T(3) \times T(79) \times 2 + 8$$

$$37929 := T(3) \times T(79) \times 2 + 9$$

$$38430 := T(T(3)) \times T(T(8-4)) \times T(3) + 0$$

$$38431 := T(T(3)) \times T(T(8-4)) \times T(3) + 1$$

$$38432 := T(T(3)) \times T(T(8-4)) \times T(3) + 2$$

$$38433 := T(T(3)) \times T(T(8-4)) \times T(3) + 3$$

$$38434 := T(T(3)) \times T(T(8-4)) \times T(3) + 4$$

$$38435 := T(T(3)) \times T(T(8-4)) \times T(3) + 5$$

$$38436 := T(T(3)) \times T(T(8-4)) \times T(3) + 6$$

$$38437 := T(T(3)) \times T(T(8-4)) \times T(3) + 7$$

$$38438 := T(T(3)) \times T(T(8-4)) \times T(3) + 8$$

$$38439 := T(T(3)) \times T(T(8-4)) \times T(3) + 9$$

$$38760 := T(3) \times (-8 + T(7) \times T(T(6))) + 0$$

$$38761 := T(3) \times (-8 + T(7) \times T(T(6))) + 1$$

$$38762 := T(3) \times (-8 + T(7) \times T(T(6))) + 2$$

$$38763 := T(3) \times (-8 + T(7) \times T(T(6))) + 3$$

$$38764 := T(3) \times (-8 + T(7) \times T(T(6))) + 4$$

$$38765 := T(3) \times (-8 + T(7) \times T(T(6))) + 5$$

$$38766 := T(3) \times (-8 + T(7) \times T(T(6))) + 6$$

$$38767 := T(3) \times (-8 + T(7) \times T(T(6))) + 7$$

$$38768 := T(3) \times (-8 + T(7) \times T(T(6))) + 8$$

$$38769 := T(3) \times (-8 + T(7) \times T(T(6))) + 9$$

$$38880 := (-T(3) + T(8)) \times T(8) \times T(8) + 0$$

$$38881 := (-T(3) + T(8)) \times T(8) \times T(8) + 1$$

$$38882 := (-T(3) + T(8)) \times T(8) \times T(8) + 2$$

$$38883 := (-T(3) + T(8)) \times T(8) \times T(8) + 3$$

$$38884 := (-T(3) + T(8)) \times T(8) \times T(8) + 4$$

$$38885 := (-T(3) + T(8)) \times T(8) \times T(8) + 5$$

$$38886 := (-T(3) + T(8)) \times T(8) \times T(8) + 6$$

$$38887 := (-T(3) + T(8)) \times T(8) \times T(8) + 7$$

$$38888 := (-T(3) + T(8)) \times T(8) \times T(8) + 8$$

$$38889 := (-T(3) + T(8)) \times T(8) \times T(8) + 9$$

$$38910 := -T(3) + T(8) \times T(T(9) + 1) + 0$$

$$38911 := -T(3) + T(8) \times T(T(9) + 1) + 1$$

$$38912 := -T(3) + T(8) \times T(T(9) + 1) + 2$$

$$38913 := -T(3) + T(8) \times T(T(9) + 1) + 3$$

$$38914 := -T(3) + T(8) \times T(T(9) + 1) + 4$$

$$38915 := -T(3) + T(8) \times T(T(9) + 1) + 5$$

$$38916 := -T(3) + T(8) \times T(T(9) + 1) + 6$$

$$38917 := -T(3) + T(8) \times T(T(9) + 1) + 7$$

$$38918 := -T(3) + T(8) \times T(T(9) + 1) + 8$$

$$38919 := -T(3) + T(8) \times T(T(9) + 1) + 9$$

$$38940 := (-3 + T(T(8)) + T(9)) \times T(T(4)) + 0$$

$$38941 := (-3 + T(T(8)) + T(9)) \times T(T(4)) + 1$$

$$38942 := (-3 + T(T(8)) + T(9)) \times T(T(4)) + 2$$

$$38943 := (-3 + T(T(8)) + T(9)) \times T(T(4)) + 3$$

$$38944 := (-3 + T(T(8)) + T(9)) \times T(T(4)) + 4$$

$$38945 := (-3 + T(T(8)) + T(9)) \times T(T(4)) + 5$$

$$38946 := (-3 + T(T(8)) + T(9)) \times T(T(4)) + 6$$

$$38947 := (-3 + T(T(8)) + T(9)) \times T(T(4)) + 7$$

$$38948 := (-3 + T(T(8)) + T(9)) \times T(T(4)) + 8$$

$$38949 := (-3 + T(T(8)) + T(9)) \times T(T(4)) + 9$$

$$39270 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)) + T(7)) + 0$$

$$39271 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)) + T(7)) + 1$$

$$39272 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)) + T(7)) + 2$$

$$39273 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)) + T(7)) + 3$$

$$39274 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)) + T(7)) + 4$$

$$39275 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)) + T(7)) + 5$$

$$39276 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)) + T(7)) + 6$$

$$39277 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)) + T(7)) + 7$$

$$39278 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)) + T(7)) + 8$$

$$39279 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)) + T(7)) + 9$$

$$39690 := (-3 + T(9)) \times T(6) \times T(9) + 0$$

$$39691 := (-3 + T(9)) \times T(6) \times T(9) + 1$$

$$39692 := (-3 + T(9)) \times T(6) \times T(9) + 2$$

$$39693 := (-3 + T(9)) \times T(6) \times T(9) + 3$$

$$39694 := (-3 + T(9)) \times T(6) \times T(9) + 4$$

$$39695 := (-3 + T(9)) \times T(6) \times T(9) + 5$$

$$39696 := (-3 + T(9)) \times T(6) \times T(9) + 6$$

$$39697 := (-3 + T(9)) \times T(6) \times T(9) + 7$$

$$39698 := (-3 + T(9)) \times T(6) \times T(9) + 8$$

$$39699 := (-3 + T(9)) \times T(6) \times T(9) + 9$$

$$41400 := T(T(T(4) - 1)) \times 40 + 0$$

$$41401 := T(T(T(4) - 1)) \times 40 + 1$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41402 &:= T(T(T(4) - 1)) \times 40 + 2 \\ 41403 &:= T(T(T(4) - 1)) \times 40 + 3 \\ 41404 &:= T(T(T(4) - 1)) \times 40 + 4 \\ 41405 &:= T(T(T(4) - 1)) \times 40 + 5 \\ 41406 &:= T(T(T(4) - 1)) \times 40 + 6 \\ 41407 &:= T(T(T(4) - 1)) \times 40 + 7 \\ 41408 &:= T(T(T(4) - 1)) \times 40 + 8 \\ 41409 &:= T(T(T(4) - 1)) \times 40 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41580 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(1 + 5) \times T(8) + 0 \\ 41581 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(1 + 5) \times T(8) + 1 \\ 41582 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(1 + 5) \times T(8) + 2 \\ 41583 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(1 + 5) \times T(8) + 3 \\ 41584 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(1 + 5) \times T(8) + 4 \\ 41585 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(1 + 5) \times T(8) + 5 \\ 41586 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(1 + 5) \times T(8) + 6 \\ 41587 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(1 + 5) \times T(8) + 7 \\ 41588 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(1 + 5) \times T(8) + 8 \\ 41589 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(1 + 5) \times T(8) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41850 &:= T(4) \times (-1 + T(T(8 + 5))) + 0 \\ 41851 &:= T(4) \times (-1 + T(T(8 + 5))) + 1 \\ 41852 &:= T(4) \times (-1 + T(T(8 + 5))) + 2 \\ 41853 &:= T(4) \times (-1 + T(T(8 + 5))) + 3 \\ 41854 &:= T(4) \times (-1 + T(T(8 + 5))) + 4 \\ 41855 &:= T(4) \times (-1 + T(T(8 + 5))) + 5 \\ 41856 &:= T(4) \times (-1 + T(T(8 + 5))) + 6 \\ 41857 &:= T(4) \times (-1 + T(T(8 + 5))) + 7 \\ 41858 &:= T(4) \times (-1 + T(T(8 + 5))) + 8 \\ 41859 &:= T(4) \times (-1 + T(T(8 + 5))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41860 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-1 + 8 + 6)) + 0 \\ 41861 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-1 + 8 + 6)) + 1 \\ 41862 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-1 + 8 + 6)) + 2 \\ 41863 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-1 + 8 + 6)) + 3 \\ 41864 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-1 + 8 + 6)) + 4 \\ 41865 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-1 + 8 + 6)) + 5 \\ 41866 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-1 + 8 + 6)) + 6 \\ 41867 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-1 + 8 + 6)) + 7 \\ 41868 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-1 + 8 + 6)) + 8 \\ 41869 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-1 + 8 + 6)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42180 &:= T(4) \times T(T(2)) \times T(1 + T(8)) + 0 \\ 42181 &:= T(4) \times T(T(2)) \times T(1 + T(8)) + 1 \\ 42182 &:= T(4) \times T(T(2)) \times T(1 + T(8)) + 2 \\ 42183 &:= T(4) \times T(T(2)) \times T(1 + T(8)) + 3 \\ 42184 &:= T(4) \times T(T(2)) \times T(1 + T(8)) + 4 \\ 42185 &:= T(4) \times T(T(2)) \times T(1 + T(8)) + 5 \\ 42186 &:= T(4) \times T(T(2)) \times T(1 + T(8)) + 6 \\ 42187 &:= T(4) \times T(T(2)) \times T(1 + T(8)) + 7 \\ 42188 &:= T(4) \times T(T(2)) \times T(1 + T(8)) + 8 \\ 42189 &:= T(4) \times T(T(2)) \times T(1 + T(8)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42240 &:= (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4)) + 0 \\ 42241 &:= (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4)) + 1 \\ 42242 &:= (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4)) + 2 \\ 42243 &:= (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4)) + 3 \\ 42244 &:= (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4)) + 4 \\ 42245 &:= (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4)) + 5 \\ 42246 &:= (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4)) + 6 \\ 42247 &:= (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4)) + 7 \\ 42248 &:= (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4)) + 8 \\ 42249 &:= (T(T(T(4)))/2 - 2) \times T(T(4)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42750 &:= T(T(4)/2) \times T(75) + 0 \\ 42751 &:= T(T(4)/2) \times T(75) + 1 \\ 42752 &:= T(T(4)/2) \times T(75) + 2 \\ 42753 &:= T(T(4)/2) \times T(75) + 3 \\ 42754 &:= T(T(4)/2) \times T(75) + 4 \\ 42755 &:= T(T(4)/2) \times T(75) + 5 \\ 42756 &:= T(T(4)/2) \times T(75) + 6 \\ 42757 &:= T(T(4)/2) \times T(75) + 7 \\ 42758 &:= T(T(4)/2) \times T(75) + 8 \\ 42759 &:= T(T(4)/2) \times T(75) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42770 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times T(7) - T(T(7)) + 0 \\ 42771 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times T(7) - T(T(7)) + 1 \\ 42772 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times T(7) - T(T(7)) + 2 \\ 42773 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times T(7) - T(T(7)) + 3 \\ 42774 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times T(7) - T(T(7)) + 4 \\ 42775 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times T(7) - T(T(7)) + 5 \\ 42776 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times T(7) - T(T(7)) + 6 \\ 42777 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times T(7) - T(T(7)) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$42778 := (T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times T(7) - T(T(7)) + 8$$

$$42779 := (T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times T(7) - T(T(7)) + 9$$

$$42780 := T(4) \times T(2^7 - T(8)) + 0$$

$$42781 := T(4) \times T(2^7 - T(8)) + 1$$

$$42782 := T(4) \times T(2^7 - T(8)) + 2$$

$$42783 := T(4) \times T(2^7 - T(8)) + 3$$

$$42784 := T(4) \times T(2^7 - T(8)) + 4$$

$$42785 := T(4) \times T(2^7 - T(8)) + 5$$

$$42786 := T(4) \times T(2^7 - T(8)) + 6$$

$$42787 := T(4) \times T(2^7 - T(8)) + 7$$

$$42788 := T(4) \times T(2^7 - T(8)) + 8$$

$$42789 := T(4) \times T(2^7 - T(8)) + 9$$

$$42840 := (T(4) + 2) \times T(84) + 0$$

$$42841 := (T(4) + 2) \times T(84) + 1$$

$$42842 := (T(4) + 2) \times T(84) + 2$$

$$42843 := (T(4) + 2) \times T(84) + 3$$

$$42844 := (T(4) + 2) \times T(84) + 4$$

$$42845 := (T(4) + 2) \times T(84) + 5$$

$$42846 := (T(4) + 2) \times T(84) + 6$$

$$42847 := (T(4) + 2) \times T(84) + 7$$

$$42848 := (T(4) + 2) \times T(84) + 8$$

$$42849 := (T(4) + 2) \times T(84) + 9$$

$$42900 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 00$$

$$42901 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 01$$

$$42902 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 02$$

$$42903 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 03$$

$$42904 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 04$$

$$42905 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 05$$

$$42906 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 06$$

$$42907 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 07$$

$$42908 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 08$$

$$42909 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 09$$

$$42910 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 10$$

$$42911 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 11$$

$$42912 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 12$$

$$42913 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 13$$

$$42914 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 14$$

$$42915 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 15$$

$$42916 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 16$$

$$42917 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 17$$

$$42918 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 18$$

$$42919 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 19$$

$$42920 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 20$$

$$42921 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 21$$

$$42922 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 22$$

$$42923 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 23$$

$$42924 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 24$$

$$42925 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 25$$

$$42926 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 26$$

$$42927 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 27$$

$$42928 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 28$$

$$42929 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 29$$

$$42930 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 30$$

$$42931 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 31$$

$$42932 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 32$$

$$42933 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 33$$

$$42934 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 34$$

$$42935 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 35$$

$$42936 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 36$$

$$42937 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 37$$

$$42938 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 38$$

$$42939 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 39$$

$$42940 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 40$$

$$42941 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 41$$

$$42942 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 42$$

$$42943 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 43$$

$$42944 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 44$$

$$42945 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 45$$

$$42946 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 46$$

$$42947 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 47$$

$$42948 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 48$$

$$42949 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 49$$

$$42950 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 50$$

$$42951 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 51$$

$$42952 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 52$$

$$42953 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 53$$

$$42954 := T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 54$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42955 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 55 \\ 42956 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 56 \\ 42957 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 57 \\ 42958 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 58 \\ 42959 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 59 \\ 42960 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 60 \\ 42961 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 61 \\ 42962 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 62 \\ 42963 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 63 \\ 42964 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 64 \\ 42965 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 65 \\ 42966 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 66 \\ 42967 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 67 \\ 42968 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 68 \\ 42969 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 69 \\ 42970 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 70 \\ 42971 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 71 \\ 42972 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 72 \\ 42973 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 73 \\ 42974 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 74 \\ 42975 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 75 \\ 42976 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 76 \\ 42977 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 77 \\ 42978 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 78 \\ 42979 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 79 \\ 42980 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 80 \\ 42981 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 81 \\ 42982 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 82 \\ 42983 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 83 \\ 42984 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 84 \\ 42985 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 85 \\ 42986 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 86 \\ 42987 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 87 \\ 42988 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 88 \\ 42989 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 89 \\ 42990 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 90 \\ 42991 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 91 \\ 42992 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 92 \\ 42993 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 93 \\ 42994 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 94 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42995 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 95 \\ 42996 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 96 \\ 42997 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 97 \\ 42998 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 98 \\ 42999 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) + 99 \\ 43120 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(3) + 1)^2 + 0 \\ 43121 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(3) + 1)^2 + 1 \\ 43122 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(3) + 1)^2 + 2 \\ 43123 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(3) + 1)^2 + 3 \\ 43124 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(3) + 1)^2 + 4 \\ 43125 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(3) + 1)^2 + 5 \\ 43126 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(3) + 1)^2 + 6 \\ 43127 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(3) + 1)^2 + 7 \\ 43128 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(3) + 1)^2 + 8 \\ 43129 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(3) + 1)^2 + 9 \\ 43540 &:= T(4 + 3) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) + 0 \\ 43541 &:= T(4 + 3) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) + 1 \\ 43542 &:= T(4 + 3) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) + 2 \\ 43543 &:= T(4 + 3) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) + 3 \\ 43544 &:= T(4 + 3) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) + 4 \\ 43545 &:= T(4 + 3) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) + 5 \\ 43546 &:= T(4 + 3) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) + 6 \\ 43547 &:= T(4 + 3) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) + 7 \\ 43548 &:= T(4 + 3) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) + 8 \\ 43549 &:= T(4 + 3) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) + 9 \\ 44220 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) \times 2 + 0 \\ 44221 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) \times 2 + 1 \\ 44222 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) \times 2 + 2 \\ 44223 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) \times 2 + 3 \\ 44224 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) \times 2 + 4 \\ 44225 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) \times 2 + 5 \\ 44226 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) \times 2 + 6 \\ 44227 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) \times 2 + 7 \\ 44228 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) \times 2 + 8 \\ 44229 &:= T(4) \times T(T(-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) \times 2 + 9 \\ 44250 &:= T(4 + T(T(4))) \times 25 + 0 \\ 44251 &:= T(4 + T(T(4))) \times 25 + 1 \\ 44252 &:= T(4 + T(T(4))) \times 25 + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44253 &:= T(4 + T(T(4))) \times 25 + 3 \\ 44254 &:= T(4 + T(T(4))) \times 25 + 4 \\ 44255 &:= T(4 + T(T(4))) \times 25 + 5 \\ 44256 &:= T(4 + T(T(4))) \times 25 + 6 \\ 44257 &:= T(4 + T(T(4))) \times 25 + 7 \\ 44258 &:= T(4 + T(T(4))) \times 25 + 8 \\ 44259 &:= T(4 + T(T(4))) \times 25 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44550 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(4)) \times T(5) - T(5)) + 0 \\ 44551 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(4)) \times T(5) - T(5)) + 1 \\ 44552 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(4)) \times T(5) - T(5)) + 2 \\ 44553 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(4)) \times T(5) - T(5)) + 3 \\ 44554 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(4)) \times T(5) - T(5)) + 4 \\ 44555 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(4)) \times T(5) - T(5)) + 5 \\ 44556 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(4)) \times T(5) - T(5)) + 6 \\ 44557 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(4)) \times T(5) - T(5)) + 7 \\ 44558 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(4)) \times T(5) - T(5)) + 8 \\ 44559 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(4)) \times T(5) - T(5)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44650 &:= T(4) \times T(4 + 6 \times T(5)) + 0 \\ 44651 &:= T(4) \times T(4 + 6 \times T(5)) + 1 \\ 44652 &:= T(4) \times T(4 + 6 \times T(5)) + 2 \\ 44653 &:= T(4) \times T(4 + 6 \times T(5)) + 3 \\ 44654 &:= T(4) \times T(4 + 6 \times T(5)) + 4 \\ 44655 &:= T(4) \times T(4 + 6 \times T(5)) + 5 \\ 44656 &:= T(4) \times T(4 + 6 \times T(5)) + 6 \\ 44657 &:= T(4) \times T(4 + 6 \times T(5)) + 7 \\ 44658 &:= T(4) \times T(4 + 6 \times T(5)) + 8 \\ 44659 &:= T(4) \times T(4 + 6 \times T(5)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45100 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(5) + T(10)) + 0 \\ 45101 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(5) + T(10)) + 1 \\ 45102 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(5) + T(10)) + 2 \\ 45103 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(5) + T(10)) + 3 \\ 45104 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(5) + T(10)) + 4 \\ 45105 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(5) + T(10)) + 5 \\ 45106 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(5) + T(10)) + 6 \\ 45107 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(5) + T(10)) + 7 \\ 45108 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(5) + T(10)) + 8 \\ 45109 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-T(5) + T(10)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45360 &:= T(T(4) + 5) \times T(T(3) + T(6)) + 0 \\ 45361 &:= T(T(4) + 5) \times T(T(3) + T(6)) + 1 \\ 45362 &:= T(T(4) + 5) \times T(T(3) + T(6)) + 2 \\ 45363 &:= T(T(4) + 5) \times T(T(3) + T(6)) + 3 \\ 45364 &:= T(T(4) + 5) \times T(T(3) + T(6)) + 4 \\ 45365 &:= T(T(4) + 5) \times T(T(3) + T(6)) + 5 \\ 45366 &:= T(T(4) + 5) \times T(T(3) + T(6)) + 6 \\ 45367 &:= T(T(4) + 5) \times T(T(3) + T(6)) + 7 \\ 45368 &:= T(T(4) + 5) \times T(T(3) + T(6)) + 8 \\ 45369 &:= T(T(4) + 5) \times T(T(3) + T(6)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45430 &:= T(T(4)) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(43)) + 0 \\ 45431 &:= T(T(4)) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(43)) + 1 \\ 45432 &:= T(T(4)) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(43)) + 2 \\ 45433 &:= T(T(4)) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(43)) + 3 \\ 45434 &:= T(T(4)) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(43)) + 4 \\ 45435 &:= T(T(4)) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(43)) + 5 \\ 45436 &:= T(T(4)) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(43)) + 6 \\ 45437 &:= T(T(4)) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(43)) + 7 \\ 45438 &:= T(T(4)) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(43)) + 8 \\ 45439 &:= T(T(4)) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(43)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45930 &:= (T(T(T(4))) \times 5 - T(9)) \times T(3) + 0 \\ 45931 &:= (T(T(T(4))) \times 5 - T(9)) \times T(3) + 1 \\ 45932 &:= (T(T(T(4))) \times 5 - T(9)) \times T(3) + 2 \\ 45933 &:= (T(T(T(4))) \times 5 - T(9)) \times T(3) + 3 \\ 45934 &:= (T(T(T(4))) \times 5 - T(9)) \times T(3) + 4 \\ 45935 &:= (T(T(T(4))) \times 5 - T(9)) \times T(3) + 5 \\ 45936 &:= (T(T(T(4))) \times 5 - T(9)) \times T(3) + 6 \\ 45937 &:= (T(T(T(4))) \times 5 - T(9)) \times T(3) + 7 \\ 45938 &:= (T(T(T(4))) \times 5 - T(9)) \times T(3) + 8 \\ 45939 &:= (T(T(T(4))) \times 5 - T(9)) \times T(3) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46200 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 20 + 0 \\ 46201 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 20 + 1 \\ 46202 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 20 + 2 \\ 46203 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 20 + 3 \\ 46204 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 20 + 4 \\ 46205 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 20 + 5 \\ 46206 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 20 + 6 \\ 46207 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 20 + 7 \\ 46208 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 20 + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$46209 := T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 20 + 9$$

$$46380 := (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times (-T(3) + T(8)) + 0$$

$$46381 := (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times (-T(3) + T(8)) + 1$$

$$46382 := (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times (-T(3) + T(8)) + 2$$

$$46383 := (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times (-T(3) + T(8)) + 3$$

$$46384 := (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times (-T(3) + T(8)) + 4$$

$$46385 := (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times (-T(3) + T(8)) + 5$$

$$46386 := (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times (-T(3) + T(8)) + 6$$

$$46387 := (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times (-T(3) + T(8)) + 7$$

$$46388 := (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times (-T(3) + T(8)) + 8$$

$$46389 := (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times (-T(3) + T(8)) + 9$$

$$46560 := T(4) \times T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) + 0$$

$$46561 := T(4) \times T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) + 1$$

$$46562 := T(4) \times T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) + 2$$

$$46563 := T(4) \times T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) + 3$$

$$46564 := T(4) \times T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) + 4$$

$$46565 := T(4) \times T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) + 5$$

$$46566 := T(4) \times T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) + 6$$

$$46567 := T(4) \times T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) + 7$$

$$46568 := T(4) \times T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) + 8$$

$$46569 := T(4) \times T((T(6) - 5) \times 6) + 9$$

$$46660 := T(4) - 6 + 6^6 + 0$$

$$46661 := T(4) - 6 + 6^6 + 1$$

$$46662 := T(4) - 6 + 6^6 + 2$$

$$46663 := T(4) - 6 + 6^6 + 3$$

$$46664 := T(4) - 6 + 6^6 + 4$$

$$46665 := T(4) - 6 + 6^6 + 5$$

$$46666 := T(4) - 6 + 6^6 + 6$$

$$46667 := T(4) - 6 + 6^6 + 7$$

$$46668 := T(4) - 6 + 6^6 + 8$$

$$46669 := T(4) - 6 + 6^6 + 9$$

$$46830 := T(4) \times (T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(T(3)) + 0$$

$$46831 := T(4) \times (T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(T(3)) + 1$$

$$46832 := T(4) \times (T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(T(3)) + 2$$

$$46833 := T(4) \times (T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(T(3)) + 3$$

$$46834 := T(4) \times (T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(T(3)) + 4$$

$$46835 := T(4) \times (T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(T(3)) + 5$$

$$46836 := T(4) \times (T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(T(3)) + 6$$

$$46837 := T(4) \times (T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(T(3)) + 7$$

$$46838 := T(4) \times (T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(T(3)) + 8$$

$$46839 := T(4) \times (T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(T(3)) + 9$$

$$46920 := T(T(4) + 6) \times T(T(9)) / T(2) + 0$$

$$46921 := T(T(4) + 6) \times T(T(9)) / T(2) + 1$$

$$46922 := T(T(4) + 6) \times T(T(9)) / T(2) + 2$$

$$46923 := T(T(4) + 6) \times T(T(9)) / T(2) + 3$$

$$46924 := T(T(4) + 6) \times T(T(9)) / T(2) + 4$$

$$46925 := T(T(4) + 6) \times T(T(9)) / T(2) + 5$$

$$46926 := T(T(4) + 6) \times T(T(9)) / T(2) + 6$$

$$46927 := T(T(4) + 6) \times T(T(9)) / T(2) + 7$$

$$46928 := T(T(4) + 6) \times T(T(9)) / T(2) + 8$$

$$46929 := T(T(4) + 6) \times T(T(9)) / T(2) + 9$$

$$47520 := (-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 0$$

$$47521 := (-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 1$$

$$47522 := (-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 2$$

$$47523 := (-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 3$$

$$47524 := (-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 4$$

$$47525 := (-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 5$$

$$47526 := (-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 6$$

$$47527 := (-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 7$$

$$47528 := (-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 8$$

$$47529 := (-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 9$$

$$47530 := T(4) \times T(7 + T(5) \times T(3)) + 0$$

$$47531 := T(4) \times T(7 + T(5) \times T(3)) + 1$$

$$47532 := T(4) \times T(7 + T(5) \times T(3)) + 2$$

$$47533 := T(4) \times T(7 + T(5) \times T(3)) + 3$$

$$47534 := T(4) \times T(7 + T(5) \times T(3)) + 4$$

$$47535 := T(4) \times T(7 + T(5) \times T(3)) + 5$$

$$47536 := T(4) \times T(7 + T(5) \times T(3)) + 6$$

$$47537 := T(4) \times T(7 + T(5) \times T(3)) + 7$$

$$47538 := T(4) \times T(7 + T(5) \times T(3)) + 8$$

$$47539 := T(4) \times T(7 + T(5) \times T(3)) + 9$$

$$47740 := T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + 7 - 4) + 0$$

$$47741 := T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + 7 - 4) + 1$$

$$47742 := T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + 7 - 4) + 2$$

$$\begin{aligned} 47743 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + 7 - 4) + 3 \\ 47744 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + 7 - 4) + 4 \\ 47745 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + 7 - 4) + 5 \\ 47746 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + 7 - 4) + 6 \\ 47747 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + 7 - 4) + 7 \\ 47748 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + 7 - 4) + 8 \\ 47749 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + 7 - 4) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 47880 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) - 8)) \times T(8) + 0 \\ 47881 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) - 8)) \times T(8) + 1 \\ 47882 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) - 8)) \times T(8) + 2 \\ 47883 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) - 8)) \times T(8) + 3 \\ 47884 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) - 8)) \times T(8) + 4 \\ 47885 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) - 8)) \times T(8) + 5 \\ 47886 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) - 8)) \times T(8) + 6 \\ 47887 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) - 8)) \times T(8) + 7 \\ 47888 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) - 8)) \times T(8) + 8 \\ 47889 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) - 8)) \times T(8) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48450 &:= (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \times T(5) + 0 \\ 48451 &:= (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \times T(5) + 1 \\ 48452 &:= (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \times T(5) + 2 \\ 48453 &:= (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \times T(5) + 3 \\ 48454 &:= (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \times T(5) + 4 \\ 48455 &:= (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \times T(5) + 5 \\ 48456 &:= (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \times T(5) + 6 \\ 48457 &:= (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \times T(5) + 7 \\ 48458 &:= (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \times T(5) + 8 \\ 48459 &:= (-T(4) + T(8 \times T(4))) \times T(5) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48720 &:= (4 + T(8)) \times T(T(7)) \times T(2) + 0 \\ 48721 &:= (4 + T(8)) \times T(T(7)) \times T(2) + 1 \\ 48722 &:= (4 + T(8)) \times T(T(7)) \times T(2) + 2 \\ 48723 &:= (4 + T(8)) \times T(T(7)) \times T(2) + 3 \\ 48724 &:= (4 + T(8)) \times T(T(7)) \times T(2) + 4 \\ 48725 &:= (4 + T(8)) \times T(T(7)) \times T(2) + 5 \\ 48726 &:= (4 + T(8)) \times T(T(7)) \times T(2) + 6 \\ 48727 &:= (4 + T(8)) \times T(T(7)) \times T(2) + 7 \\ 48728 &:= (4 + T(8)) \times T(T(7)) \times T(2) + 8 \\ 48729 &:= (4 + T(8)) \times T(T(7)) \times T(2) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48840 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8)) / T(T(T(8/4))) + 0 \\ 48841 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8)) / T(T(T(8/4))) + 1 \\ 48842 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8)) / T(T(T(8/4))) + 2 \\ 48843 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8)) / T(T(T(8/4))) + 3 \\ 48844 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8)) / T(T(T(8/4))) + 4 \\ 48845 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8)) / T(T(T(8/4))) + 5 \\ 48846 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8)) / T(T(T(8/4))) + 6 \\ 48847 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8)) / T(T(T(8/4))) + 7 \\ 48848 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8)) / T(T(T(8/4))) + 8 \\ 48849 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(8)) / T(T(T(8/4))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 49280 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) + 8 + 0 \\ 49281 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) + 8 + 1 \\ 49282 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) + 8 + 2 \\ 49283 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) + 8 + 3 \\ 49284 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) + 8 + 4 \\ 49285 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) + 8 + 5 \\ 49286 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) + 8 + 6 \\ 49287 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) + 8 + 7 \\ 49288 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) + 8 + 8 \\ 49289 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) + 8 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 49560 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9) - 5)) \times T(6) + 0 \\ 49561 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9) - 5)) \times T(6) + 1 \\ 49562 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9) - 5)) \times T(6) + 2 \\ 49563 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9) - 5)) \times T(6) + 3 \\ 49564 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9) - 5)) \times T(6) + 4 \\ 49565 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9) - 5)) \times T(6) + 5 \\ 49566 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9) - 5)) \times T(6) + 6 \\ 49567 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9) - 5)) \times T(6) + 7 \\ 49568 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9) - 5)) \times T(6) + 8 \\ 49569 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9) - 5)) \times T(6) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 49780 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(9) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) + 0 \\ 49781 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(9) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) + 1 \\ 49782 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(9) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) + 2 \\ 49783 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(9) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) + 3 \\ 49784 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(9) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) + 4 \\ 49785 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(9) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) + 5 \\ 49786 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(9) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) + 6 \\ 49787 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(9) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) + 7 \\ 49788 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(9) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$49789 := T(T(T(4))) + T(9) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) + 9$$

$$49830 := T(T(4)) \times (9 + T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) + 0$$

$$49831 := T(T(4)) \times (9 + T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) + 1$$

$$49832 := T(T(4)) \times (9 + T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) + 2$$

$$49833 := T(T(4)) \times (9 + T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) + 3$$

$$49834 := T(T(4)) \times (9 + T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) + 4$$

$$49835 := T(T(4)) \times (9 + T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) + 5$$

$$49836 := T(T(4)) \times (9 + T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) + 6$$

$$49837 := T(T(4)) \times (9 + T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) + 7$$

$$49838 := T(T(4)) \times (9 + T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) + 8$$

$$49839 := T(T(4)) \times (9 + T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) + 9$$

$$49920 := (T(T(4)) + 9) \times T(T(9) - T(T(2))) + 0$$

$$49921 := (T(T(4)) + 9) \times T(T(9) - T(T(2))) + 1$$

$$49922 := (T(T(4)) + 9) \times T(T(9) - T(T(2))) + 2$$

$$49923 := (T(T(4)) + 9) \times T(T(9) - T(T(2))) + 3$$

$$49924 := (T(T(4)) + 9) \times T(T(9) - T(T(2))) + 4$$

$$49925 := (T(T(4)) + 9) \times T(T(9) - T(T(2))) + 5$$

$$49926 := (T(T(4)) + 9) \times T(T(9) - T(T(2))) + 6$$

$$49927 := (T(T(4)) + 9) \times T(T(9) - T(T(2))) + 7$$

$$49928 := (T(T(4)) + 9) \times T(T(9) - T(T(2))) + 8$$

$$49929 := (T(T(4)) + 9) \times T(T(9) - T(T(2))) + 9$$

$$49950 := T(4 \times 9) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 0$$

$$49951 := T(4 \times 9) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 1$$

$$49952 := T(4 \times 9) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 2$$

$$49953 := T(4 \times 9) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 3$$

$$49954 := T(4 \times 9) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 4$$

$$49955 := T(4 \times 9) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 5$$

$$49956 := T(4 \times 9) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 6$$

$$49957 := T(4 \times 9) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 7$$

$$49958 := T(4 \times 9) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 8$$

$$49959 := T(4 \times 9) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 9$$

$$51840 := (T(5) + 1) \times T(8 \times T(4)) + 0$$

$$51841 := (T(5) + 1) \times T(8 \times T(4)) + 1$$

$$51842 := (T(5) + 1) \times T(8 \times T(4)) + 2$$

$$51843 := (T(5) + 1) \times T(8 \times T(4)) + 3$$

$$51844 := (T(5) + 1) \times T(8 \times T(4)) + 4$$

$$51845 := (T(5) + 1) \times T(8 \times T(4)) + 5$$

$$51846 := (T(5) + 1) \times T(8 \times T(4)) + 6$$

$$51847 := (T(5) + 1) \times T(8 \times T(4)) + 7$$

$$51848 := (T(5) + 1) \times T(8 \times T(4)) + 8$$

$$51849 := (T(5) + 1) \times T(8 \times T(4)) + 9$$

$$52650 := T(5) \times (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(5) + 0$$

$$52651 := T(5) \times (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(5) + 1$$

$$52652 := T(5) \times (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(5) + 2$$

$$52653 := T(5) \times (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(5) + 3$$

$$52654 := T(5) \times (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(5) + 4$$

$$52655 := T(5) \times (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(5) + 5$$

$$52656 := T(5) \times (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(5) + 6$$

$$52657 := T(5) \times (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(5) + 7$$

$$52658 := T(5) \times (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(5) + 8$$

$$52659 := T(5) \times (T(2) + T(T(6))) \times T(5) + 9$$

$$52680 := -T(5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(8)) + 0$$

$$52681 := -T(5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(8)) + 1$$

$$52682 := -T(5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(8)) + 2$$

$$52683 := -T(5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(8)) + 3$$

$$52684 := -T(5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(8)) + 4$$

$$52685 := -T(5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(8)) + 5$$

$$52686 := -T(5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(8)) + 6$$

$$52687 := -T(5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(8)) + 7$$

$$52688 := -T(5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(8)) + 8$$

$$52689 := -T(5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(8)) + 9$$

$$52920 := T(5) \times T(2) \times T(T(9) + T(2)) + 0$$

$$52921 := T(5) \times T(2) \times T(T(9) + T(2)) + 1$$

$$52922 := T(5) \times T(2) \times T(T(9) + T(2)) + 2$$

$$52923 := T(5) \times T(2) \times T(T(9) + T(2)) + 3$$

$$52924 := T(5) \times T(2) \times T(T(9) + T(2)) + 4$$

$$52925 := T(5) \times T(2) \times T(T(9) + T(2)) + 5$$

$$52926 := T(5) \times T(2) \times T(T(9) + T(2)) + 6$$

$$52927 := T(5) \times T(2) \times T(T(9) + T(2)) + 7$$

$$52928 := T(5) \times T(2) \times T(T(9) + T(2)) + 8$$

$$52929 := T(5) \times T(2) \times T(T(9) + T(2)) + 9$$

$$53130 := T(T(T(5))/T(3)) \times T(1 + T(T(3))) + 0$$

$$53131 := T(T(T(5))/T(3)) \times T(1 + T(T(3))) + 1$$

$$53132 := T(T(T(5))/T(3)) \times T(1 + T(T(3))) + 2$$

$$53133 := T(T(T(5))/T(3)) \times T(1 + T(T(3))) + 3$$

$$\begin{aligned}53134 &:= T(T(T(5))/T(3)) \times T(1 + T(T(3))) + 4 \\53135 &:= T(T(T(5))/T(3)) \times T(1 + T(T(3))) + 5 \\53136 &:= T(T(T(5))/T(3)) \times T(1 + T(T(3))) + 6 \\53137 &:= T(T(T(5))/T(3)) \times T(1 + T(T(3))) + 7 \\53138 &:= T(T(T(5))/T(3)) \times T(1 + T(T(3))) + 8 \\53139 &:= T(T(T(5))/T(3)) \times T(1 + T(T(3))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53220 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(T(T(3)))^2 - T(T(T(2))) + 0 \\53221 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(T(T(3)))^2 - T(T(T(2))) + 1 \\53222 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(T(T(3)))^2 - T(T(T(2))) + 2 \\53223 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(T(T(3)))^2 - T(T(T(2))) + 3 \\53224 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(T(T(3)))^2 - T(T(T(2))) + 4 \\53225 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(T(T(3)))^2 - T(T(T(2))) + 5 \\53226 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(T(T(3)))^2 - T(T(T(2))) + 6 \\53227 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(T(T(3)))^2 - T(T(T(2))) + 7 \\53228 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(T(T(3)))^2 - T(T(T(2))) + 8 \\53229 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(T(T(3)))^2 - T(T(T(2))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53280 &:= T(T(5))/3 \times 2 \times T(T(8)) + 0 \\53281 &:= T(T(5))/3 \times 2 \times T(T(8)) + 1 \\53282 &:= T(T(5))/3 \times 2 \times T(T(8)) + 2 \\53283 &:= T(T(5))/3 \times 2 \times T(T(8)) + 3 \\53284 &:= T(T(5))/3 \times 2 \times T(T(8)) + 4 \\53285 &:= T(T(5))/3 \times 2 \times T(T(8)) + 5 \\53286 &:= T(T(5))/3 \times 2 \times T(T(8)) + 6 \\53287 &:= T(T(5))/3 \times 2 \times T(T(8)) + 7 \\53288 &:= T(T(5))/3 \times 2 \times T(T(8)) + 8 \\53289 &:= T(T(5))/3 \times 2 \times T(T(8)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53460 &:= T(5) \times (-T(3) + T(4 \times T(6))) + 0 \\53461 &:= T(5) \times (-T(3) + T(4 \times T(6))) + 1 \\53462 &:= T(5) \times (-T(3) + T(4 \times T(6))) + 2 \\53463 &:= T(5) \times (-T(3) + T(4 \times T(6))) + 3 \\53464 &:= T(5) \times (-T(3) + T(4 \times T(6))) + 4 \\53465 &:= T(5) \times (-T(3) + T(4 \times T(6))) + 5 \\53466 &:= T(5) \times (-T(3) + T(4 \times T(6))) + 6 \\53467 &:= T(5) \times (-T(3) + T(4 \times T(6))) + 7 \\53468 &:= T(5) \times (-T(3) + T(4 \times T(6))) + 8 \\53469 &:= T(5) \times (-T(3) + T(4 \times T(6))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53550 &:= T(5) \times T(-T(3 + 5) + T(T(5))) + 0 \\53551 &:= T(5) \times T(-T(3 + 5) + T(T(5))) + 1 \\53552 &:= T(5) \times T(-T(3 + 5) + T(T(5))) + 2 \\53553 &:= T(5) \times T(-T(3 + 5) + T(T(5))) + 3 \\53554 &:= T(5) \times T(-T(3 + 5) + T(T(5))) + 4 \\53555 &:= T(5) \times T(-T(3 + 5) + T(T(5))) + 5 \\53556 &:= T(5) \times T(-T(3 + 5) + T(T(5))) + 6 \\53557 &:= T(5) \times T(-T(3 + 5) + T(T(5))) + 7 \\53558 &:= T(5) \times T(-T(3 + 5) + T(T(5))) + 8 \\53559 &:= T(5) \times T(-T(3 + 5) + T(T(5))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53640 &:= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(T(6) \times 4)) + 0 \\53641 &:= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(T(6) \times 4)) + 1 \\53642 &:= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(T(6) \times 4)) + 2 \\53643 &:= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(T(6) \times 4)) + 3 \\53644 &:= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(T(6) \times 4)) + 4 \\53645 &:= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(T(6) \times 4)) + 5 \\53646 &:= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(T(6) \times 4)) + 6 \\53647 &:= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(T(6) \times 4)) + 7 \\53648 &:= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(T(6) \times 4)) + 8 \\53649 &:= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(T(6) \times 4)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53820 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8)))/2 + 0 \\53821 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8)))/2 + 1 \\53822 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8)))/2 + 2 \\53823 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8)))/2 + 3 \\53824 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8)))/2 + 4 \\53825 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8)))/2 + 5 \\53826 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8)))/2 + 6 \\53827 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8)))/2 + 7 \\53828 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8)))/2 + 8 \\53829 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8)))/2 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54340 &:= T(T(5) + 4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) + 0 \\54341 &:= T(T(5) + 4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) + 1 \\54342 &:= T(T(5) + 4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) + 2 \\54343 &:= T(T(5) + 4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) + 3 \\54344 &:= T(T(5) + 4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) + 4 \\54345 &:= T(T(5) + 4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) + 5 \\54346 &:= T(T(5) + 4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) + 6 \\54347 &:= T(T(5) + 4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) + 7 \\54348 &:= T(T(5) + 4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) + 8\end{aligned}$$

$$54349 := T(T(5) + 4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) + 9$$

$$54450 := T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) + 0$$

$$54451 := T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) + 1$$

$$54452 := T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) + 2$$

$$54453 := T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) + 3$$

$$54454 := T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) + 4$$

$$54455 := T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) + 5$$

$$54456 := T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) + 6$$

$$54457 := T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) + 7$$

$$54458 := T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) + 8$$

$$54459 := T(5) \times T(T(4)) \times T(-4 + T(5)) + 9$$

$$54670 := T(T(5) + T(T(4))) \times (-6 + T(7)) + 0$$

$$54671 := T(T(5) + T(T(4))) \times (-6 + T(7)) + 1$$

$$54672 := T(T(5) + T(T(4))) \times (-6 + T(7)) + 2$$

$$54673 := T(T(5) + T(T(4))) \times (-6 + T(7)) + 3$$

$$54674 := T(T(5) + T(T(4))) \times (-6 + T(7)) + 4$$

$$54675 := T(T(5) + T(T(4))) \times (-6 + T(7)) + 5$$

$$54676 := T(T(5) + T(T(4))) \times (-6 + T(7)) + 6$$

$$54677 := T(T(5) + T(T(4))) \times (-6 + T(7)) + 7$$

$$54678 := T(T(5) + T(T(4))) \times (-6 + T(7)) + 8$$

$$54679 := T(T(5) + T(T(4))) \times (-6 + T(7)) + 9$$

$$55320 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 0$$

$$55321 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 1$$

$$55322 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 2$$

$$55323 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 3$$

$$55324 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 4$$

$$55325 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 5$$

$$55326 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 6$$

$$55327 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 7$$

$$55328 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 8$$

$$55329 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 9$$

$$55350 := T(5) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) + 0$$

$$55351 := T(5) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) + 1$$

$$55352 := T(5) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) + 2$$

$$55353 := T(5) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) + 3$$

$$55354 := T(5) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) + 4$$

$$55355 := T(5) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) + 5$$

$$55356 := T(5) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) + 6$$

$$55357 := T(5) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) + 7$$

$$55358 := T(5) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) + 8$$

$$55359 := T(5) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) + 9$$

$$55440 := T(55) \times T(4 + 4) + 0$$

$$55441 := T(55) \times T(4 + 4) + 1$$

$$55442 := T(55) \times T(4 + 4) + 2$$

$$55443 := T(55) \times T(4 + 4) + 3$$

$$55444 := T(55) \times T(4 + 4) + 4$$

$$55445 := T(55) \times T(4 + 4) + 5$$

$$55446 := T(55) \times T(4 + 4) + 6$$

$$55447 := T(55) \times T(4 + 4) + 7$$

$$55448 := T(55) \times T(4 + 4) + 8$$

$$55449 := T(55) \times T(4 + 4) + 9$$

$$55560 := T(T(5)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6)) + 0$$

$$55561 := T(T(5)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6)) + 1$$

$$55562 := T(T(5)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6)) + 2$$

$$55563 := T(T(5)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6)) + 3$$

$$55564 := T(T(5)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6)) + 4$$

$$55565 := T(T(5)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6)) + 5$$

$$55566 := T(T(5)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6)) + 6$$

$$55567 := T(T(5)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6)) + 7$$

$$55568 := T(T(5)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6)) + 8$$

$$55569 := T(T(5)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6)) + 9$$

$$55680 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(-6 + T(8)) + 0$$

$$55681 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(-6 + T(8)) + 1$$

$$55682 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(-6 + T(8)) + 2$$

$$55683 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(-6 + T(8)) + 3$$

$$55684 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(-6 + T(8)) + 4$$

$$55685 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(-6 + T(8)) + 5$$

$$55686 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(-6 + T(8)) + 6$$

$$55687 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(-6 + T(8)) + 7$$

$$55688 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(-6 + T(8)) + 8$$

$$55689 := -T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(-6 + T(8)) + 9$$

$$55920 := T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(9 + T(T(T(2)))) + 0$$

$$55921 := T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(9 + T(T(T(2)))) + 1$$

$$55922 := T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(9 + T(T(T(2)))) + 2$$

$$55923 := T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(9 + T(T(T(2)))) + 3$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55924 &:= T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(9 + T(T(T(2)))) + 4 \\ 55925 &:= T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(9 + T(T(T(2)))) + 5 \\ 55926 &:= T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(9 + T(T(T(2)))) + 6 \\ 55927 &:= T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(9 + T(T(T(2)))) + 7 \\ 55928 &:= T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(9 + T(T(T(2)))) + 8 \\ 55929 &:= T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \times T(9 + T(T(T(2)))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55980 &:= (T(5) + T(T(T(-5 + 9)))) \times T(8) + 0 \\ 55981 &:= (T(5) + T(T(T(-5 + 9)))) \times T(8) + 1 \\ 55982 &:= (T(5) + T(T(T(-5 + 9)))) \times T(8) + 2 \\ 55983 &:= (T(5) + T(T(T(-5 + 9)))) \times T(8) + 3 \\ 55984 &:= (T(5) + T(T(T(-5 + 9)))) \times T(8) + 4 \\ 55985 &:= (T(5) + T(T(T(-5 + 9)))) \times T(8) + 5 \\ 55986 &:= (T(5) + T(T(T(-5 + 9)))) \times T(8) + 6 \\ 55987 &:= (T(5) + T(T(T(-5 + 9)))) \times T(8) + 7 \\ 55988 &:= (T(5) + T(T(T(-5 + 9)))) \times T(8) + 8 \\ 55989 &:= (T(5) + T(T(T(-5 + 9)))) \times T(8) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 56520 &:= T(T(5)) \times (6 + T(T(5) \times 2)) + 0 \\ 56521 &:= T(T(5)) \times (6 + T(T(5) \times 2)) + 1 \\ 56522 &:= T(T(5)) \times (6 + T(T(5) \times 2)) + 2 \\ 56523 &:= T(T(5)) \times (6 + T(T(5) \times 2)) + 3 \\ 56524 &:= T(T(5)) \times (6 + T(T(5) \times 2)) + 4 \\ 56525 &:= T(T(5)) \times (6 + T(T(5) \times 2)) + 5 \\ 56526 &:= T(T(5)) \times (6 + T(T(5) \times 2)) + 6 \\ 56527 &:= T(T(5)) \times (6 + T(T(5) \times 2)) + 7 \\ 56528 &:= T(T(5)) \times (6 + T(T(5) \times 2)) + 8 \\ 56529 &:= T(T(5)) \times (6 + T(T(5) \times 2)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 56640 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) + T(4)) + 0 \\ 56641 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) + T(4)) + 1 \\ 56642 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) + T(4)) + 2 \\ 56643 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) + T(4)) + 3 \\ 56644 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) + T(4)) + 4 \\ 56645 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) + T(4)) + 5 \\ 56646 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) + T(4)) + 6 \\ 56647 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) + T(4)) + 7 \\ 56648 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) + T(4)) + 8 \\ 56649 &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) + T(4)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 57330 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(3) + 0 \\ 57331 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(3) + 1 \\ 57332 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(3) + 2 \\ 57333 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(3) + 3 \\ 57334 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(3) + 4 \\ 57335 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(3) + 5 \\ 57336 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(3) + 6 \\ 57337 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(3) + 7 \\ 57338 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(3) + 8 \\ 57339 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(3) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 57420 &:= T(5) \times T(T(7 + 4) + T(T(T(2)))) + 0 \\ 57421 &:= T(5) \times T(T(7 + 4) + T(T(T(2)))) + 1 \\ 57422 &:= T(5) \times T(T(7 + 4) + T(T(T(2)))) + 2 \\ 57423 &:= T(5) \times T(T(7 + 4) + T(T(T(2)))) + 3 \\ 57424 &:= T(5) \times T(T(7 + 4) + T(T(T(2)))) + 4 \\ 57425 &:= T(5) \times T(T(7 + 4) + T(T(T(2)))) + 5 \\ 57426 &:= T(5) \times T(T(7 + 4) + T(T(T(2)))) + 6 \\ 57427 &:= T(5) \times T(T(7 + 4) + T(T(T(2)))) + 7 \\ 57428 &:= T(5) \times T(T(7 + 4) + T(T(T(2)))) + 8 \\ 57429 &:= T(5) \times T(T(7 + 4) + T(T(T(2)))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 58320 &:= 5 \times (T(8) \times 3)^2 + 0 \\ 58321 &:= 5 \times (T(8) \times 3)^2 + 1 \\ 58322 &:= 5 \times (T(8) \times 3)^2 + 2 \\ 58323 &:= 5 \times (T(8) \times 3)^2 + 3 \\ 58324 &:= 5 \times (T(8) \times 3)^2 + 4 \\ 58325 &:= 5 \times (T(8) \times 3)^2 + 5 \\ 58326 &:= 5 \times (T(8) \times 3)^2 + 6 \\ 58327 &:= 5 \times (T(8) \times 3)^2 + 7 \\ 58328 &:= 5 \times (T(8) \times 3)^2 + 8 \\ 58329 &:= 5 \times (T(8) \times 3)^2 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 58740 &:= T(5) \times T(8 \times (7 + 4)) + 0 \\ 58741 &:= T(5) \times T(8 \times (7 + 4)) + 1 \\ 58742 &:= T(5) \times T(8 \times (7 + 4)) + 2 \\ 58743 &:= T(5) \times T(8 \times (7 + 4)) + 3 \\ 58744 &:= T(5) \times T(8 \times (7 + 4)) + 4 \\ 58745 &:= T(5) \times T(8 \times (7 + 4)) + 5 \\ 58746 &:= T(5) \times T(8 \times (7 + 4)) + 6 \\ 58747 &:= T(5) \times T(8 \times (7 + 4)) + 7 \\ 58748 &:= T(5) \times T(8 \times (7 + 4)) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$58749 := T(5) \times T(8 \times (7 + 4)) + 9$$

$$58830 := T(5) \times (T(88) + T(3)) + 0$$

$$58831 := T(5) \times (T(88) + T(3)) + 1$$

$$58832 := T(5) \times (T(88) + T(3)) + 2$$

$$58833 := T(5) \times (T(88) + T(3)) + 3$$

$$58834 := T(5) \times (T(88) + T(3)) + 4$$

$$58835 := T(5) \times (T(88) + T(3)) + 5$$

$$58836 := T(5) \times (T(88) + T(3)) + 6$$

$$58837 := T(5) \times (T(88) + T(3)) + 7$$

$$58838 := T(5) \times (T(88) + T(3)) + 8$$

$$58839 := T(5) \times (T(88) + T(3)) + 9$$

$$58950 := (T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 0$$

$$58951 := (T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 1$$

$$58952 := (T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 2$$

$$58953 := (T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 3$$

$$58954 := (T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 4$$

$$58955 := (T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 5$$

$$58956 := (T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 6$$

$$58957 := (T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 7$$

$$58958 := (T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 8$$

$$58959 := (T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5))) + 9$$

$$59280 := (5 + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) + 0$$

$$59281 := (5 + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) + 1$$

$$59282 := (5 + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) + 2$$

$$59283 := (5 + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) + 3$$

$$59284 := (5 + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) + 4$$

$$59285 := (5 + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) + 5$$

$$59286 := (5 + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) + 6$$

$$59287 := (5 + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) + 7$$

$$59288 := (5 + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) + 8$$

$$59289 := (5 + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) + 9$$

$$59400 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 00$$

$$59401 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 01$$

$$59402 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 02$$

$$59403 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 03$$

$$59404 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 04$$

$$59405 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 05$$

$$59406 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 06$$

$$59407 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 07$$

$$59408 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 08$$

$$59409 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 09$$

$$59410 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 10$$

$$59411 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 11$$

$$59412 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 12$$

$$59413 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 13$$

$$59414 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 14$$

$$59415 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 15$$

$$59416 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 16$$

$$59417 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 17$$

$$59418 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 18$$

$$59419 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 19$$

$$59420 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 20$$

$$59421 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 21$$

$$59422 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 22$$

$$59423 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 23$$

$$59424 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 24$$

$$59425 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 25$$

$$59426 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 26$$

$$59427 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 27$$

$$59428 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 28$$

$$59429 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 29$$

$$59430 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 30$$

$$59431 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 31$$

$$59432 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 32$$

$$59433 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 33$$

$$59434 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 34$$

$$59435 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 35$$

$$59436 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 36$$

$$59437 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 37$$

$$59438 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 38$$

$$59439 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 39$$

$$59440 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 40$$

$$59441 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 41$$

$$59442 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 42$$

$$59443 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 43$$

$$59444 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 44$$

$$59445 := T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 45$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59446 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 46 \\ 59447 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 47 \\ 59448 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 48 \\ 59449 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 49 \\ 59450 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 50 \\ 59451 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 51 \\ 59452 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 52 \\ 59453 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 53 \\ 59454 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 54 \\ 59455 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 55 \\ 59456 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 56 \\ 59457 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 57 \\ 59458 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 58 \\ 59459 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 59 \\ 59460 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 60 \\ 59461 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 61 \\ 59462 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 62 \\ 59463 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 63 \\ 59464 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 64 \\ 59465 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 65 \\ 59466 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 66 \\ 59467 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 67 \\ 59468 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 68 \\ 59469 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 69 \\ 59470 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 70 \\ 59471 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 71 \\ 59472 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 72 \\ 59473 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 73 \\ 59474 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 74 \\ 59475 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 75 \\ 59476 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 76 \\ 59477 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 77 \\ 59478 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 78 \\ 59479 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 79 \\ 59480 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 80 \\ 59481 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 81 \\ 59482 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 82 \\ 59483 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 83 \\ 59484 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 84 \\ 59485 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 85 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59486 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 86 \\ 59487 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 87 \\ 59488 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 88 \\ 59489 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 89 \\ 59490 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 90 \\ 59491 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 91 \\ 59492 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 92 \\ 59493 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 93 \\ 59494 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 94 \\ 59495 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 95 \\ 59496 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 96 \\ 59497 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 97 \\ 59498 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 98 \\ 59499 &:= T(T(5)) \times 9 \times T(T(4)) + 99 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59520 &:= T(T(5)) \times T(-9 + T(T(5))/T(2)) + 0 \\ 59521 &:= T(T(5)) \times T(-9 + T(T(5))/T(2)) + 1 \\ 59522 &:= T(T(5)) \times T(-9 + T(T(5))/T(2)) + 2 \\ 59523 &:= T(T(5)) \times T(-9 + T(T(5))/T(2)) + 3 \\ 59524 &:= T(T(5)) \times T(-9 + T(T(5))/T(2)) + 4 \\ 59525 &:= T(T(5)) \times T(-9 + T(T(5))/T(2)) + 5 \\ 59526 &:= T(T(5)) \times T(-9 + T(T(5))/T(2)) + 6 \\ 59527 &:= T(T(5)) \times T(-9 + T(T(5))/T(2)) + 7 \\ 59528 &:= T(T(5)) \times T(-9 + T(T(5))/T(2)) + 8 \\ 59529 &:= T(T(5)) \times T(-9 + T(T(5))/T(2)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59820 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(9) \times T(T(8)) \times 2 + 0 \\ 59821 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(9) \times T(T(8)) \times 2 + 1 \\ 59822 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(9) \times T(T(8)) \times 2 + 2 \\ 59823 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(9) \times T(T(8)) \times 2 + 3 \\ 59824 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(9) \times T(T(8)) \times 2 + 4 \\ 59825 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(9) \times T(T(8)) \times 2 + 5 \\ 59826 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(9) \times T(T(8)) \times 2 + 6 \\ 59827 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(9) \times T(T(8)) \times 2 + 7 \\ 59828 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(9) \times T(T(8)) \times 2 + 8 \\ 59829 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(9) \times T(T(8)) \times 2 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59840 &:= (T(T(5)) \times 9 + 8) \times T(T(4)) + 0 \\ 59841 &:= (T(T(5)) \times 9 + 8) \times T(T(4)) + 1 \\ 59842 &:= (T(T(5)) \times 9 + 8) \times T(T(4)) + 2 \\ 59843 &:= (T(T(5)) \times 9 + 8) \times T(T(4)) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59844 &:= (T(T(5)) \times 9 + 8) \times T(T(4)) + 4 \\ 59845 &:= (T(T(5)) \times 9 + 8) \times T(T(4)) + 5 \\ 59846 &:= (T(T(5)) \times 9 + 8) \times T(T(4)) + 6 \\ 59847 &:= (T(T(5)) \times 9 + 8) \times T(T(4)) + 7 \\ 59848 &:= (T(T(5)) \times 9 + 8) \times T(T(4)) + 8 \\ 59849 &:= (T(T(5)) \times 9 + 8) \times T(T(4)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59850 &:= (T(T(T(5)) - T(9))) \times (T(8) - T(5)) + 0 \\ 59851 &:= (T(T(T(5)) - T(9))) \times (T(8) - T(5)) + 1 \\ 59852 &:= (T(T(T(5)) - T(9))) \times (T(8) - T(5)) + 2 \\ 59853 &:= (T(T(T(5)) - T(9))) \times (T(8) - T(5)) + 3 \\ 59854 &:= (T(T(T(5)) - T(9))) \times (T(8) - T(5)) + 4 \\ 59855 &:= (T(T(T(5)) - T(9))) \times (T(8) - T(5)) + 5 \\ 59856 &:= (T(T(T(5)) - T(9))) \times (T(8) - T(5)) + 6 \\ 59857 &:= (T(T(T(5)) - T(9))) \times (T(8) - T(5)) + 7 \\ 59858 &:= (T(T(T(5)) - T(9))) \times (T(8) - T(5)) + 8 \\ 59859 &:= (T(T(T(5)) - T(9))) \times (T(8) - T(5)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 61620 &:= (T(6) - 1) \times T(T(6 \times 2)) + 0 \\ 61621 &:= (T(6) - 1) \times T(T(6 \times 2)) + 1 \\ 61622 &:= (T(6) - 1) \times T(T(6 \times 2)) + 2 \\ 61623 &:= (T(6) - 1) \times T(T(6 \times 2)) + 3 \\ 61624 &:= (T(6) - 1) \times T(T(6 \times 2)) + 4 \\ 61625 &:= (T(6) - 1) \times T(T(6 \times 2)) + 5 \\ 61626 &:= (T(6) - 1) \times T(T(6 \times 2)) + 6 \\ 61627 &:= (T(6) - 1) \times T(T(6 \times 2)) + 7 \\ 61628 &:= (T(6) - 1) \times T(T(6 \times 2)) + 8 \\ 61629 &:= (T(6) - 1) \times T(T(6 \times 2)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 63140 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(T(T(4))) + 0 \\ 63141 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(T(T(4))) + 1 \\ 63142 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(T(T(4))) + 2 \\ 63143 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(T(T(4))) + 3 \\ 63144 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(T(T(4))) + 4 \\ 63145 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(T(T(4))) + 5 \\ 63146 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(T(T(4))) + 6 \\ 63147 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(T(T(4))) + 7 \\ 63148 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(T(T(4))) + 8 \\ 63149 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(T(T(4))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 63750 &:= -6 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) - 5) + 0 \\ 63751 &:= -6 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) - 5) + 1 \\ 63752 &:= -6 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) - 5) + 2 \\ 63753 &:= -6 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) - 5) + 3 \\ 63754 &:= -6 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) - 5) + 4 \\ 63755 &:= -6 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) - 5) + 5 \\ 63756 &:= -6 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) - 5) + 6 \\ 63757 &:= -6 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) - 5) + 7 \\ 63758 &:= -6 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) - 5) + 8 \\ 63759 &:= -6 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7) - 5) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64260 &:= T(T(6) \times 4) \times T(2) \times 6 + 0 \\ 64261 &:= T(T(6) \times 4) \times T(2) \times 6 + 1 \\ 64262 &:= T(T(6) \times 4) \times T(2) \times 6 + 2 \\ 64263 &:= T(T(6) \times 4) \times T(2) \times 6 + 3 \\ 64264 &:= T(T(6) \times 4) \times T(2) \times 6 + 4 \\ 64265 &:= T(T(6) \times 4) \times T(2) \times 6 + 5 \\ 64266 &:= T(T(6) \times 4) \times T(2) \times 6 + 6 \\ 64267 &:= T(T(6) \times 4) \times T(2) \times 6 + 7 \\ 64268 &:= T(T(6) \times 4) \times T(2) \times 6 + 8 \\ 64269 &:= T(T(6) \times 4) \times T(2) \times 6 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64680 &:= T(6 + 4) \times T(6 \times 8) + 0 \\ 64681 &:= T(6 + 4) \times T(6 \times 8) + 1 \\ 64682 &:= T(6 + 4) \times T(6 \times 8) + 2 \\ 64683 &:= T(6 + 4) \times T(6 \times 8) + 3 \\ 64684 &:= T(6 + 4) \times T(6 \times 8) + 4 \\ 64685 &:= T(6 + 4) \times T(6 \times 8) + 5 \\ 64686 &:= T(6 + 4) \times T(6 \times 8) + 6 \\ 64687 &:= T(6 + 4) \times T(6 \times 8) + 7 \\ 64688 &:= T(6 + 4) \times T(6 \times 8) + 8 \\ 64689 &:= T(6 + 4) \times T(6 \times 8) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64740 &:= 6 \times (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) + 0 \\ 64741 &:= 6 \times (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) + 1 \\ 64742 &:= 6 \times (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) + 2 \\ 64743 &:= 6 \times (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) + 3 \\ 64744 &:= 6 \times (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) + 4 \\ 64745 &:= 6 \times (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) + 5 \\ 64746 &:= 6 \times (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) + 6 \\ 64747 &:= 6 \times (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$64748 := 6 \times (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) + 8$$

$$64749 := 6 \times (T(T(T(4))) \times 7 + T(4)) + 9$$

$$64890 := T(6) \times (T(T(4+8)) + 9) + 0$$

$$64891 := T(6) \times (T(T(4+8)) + 9) + 1$$

$$64892 := T(6) \times (T(T(4+8)) + 9) + 2$$

$$64893 := T(6) \times (T(T(4+8)) + 9) + 3$$

$$64894 := T(6) \times (T(T(4+8)) + 9) + 4$$

$$64895 := T(6) \times (T(T(4+8)) + 9) + 5$$

$$64896 := T(6) \times (T(T(4+8)) + 9) + 6$$

$$64897 := T(6) \times (T(T(4+8)) + 9) + 7$$

$$64898 := T(6) \times (T(T(4+8)) + 9) + 8$$

$$64899 := T(6) \times (T(T(4+8)) + 9) + 9$$

$$65520 := 6 \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(5) - 2) + 0$$

$$65521 := 6 \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(5) - 2) + 1$$

$$65522 := 6 \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(5) - 2) + 2$$

$$65523 := 6 \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(5) - 2) + 3$$

$$65524 := 6 \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(5) - 2) + 4$$

$$65525 := 6 \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(5) - 2) + 5$$

$$65526 := 6 \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(5) - 2) + 6$$

$$65527 := 6 \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(5) - 2) + 7$$

$$65528 := 6 \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(5) - 2) + 8$$

$$65529 := 6 \times T(T(5)) \times T(T(5) - 2) + 9$$

$$66150 := T(6) \times T(T(6) - 1) \times T(5) + 0$$

$$66151 := T(6) \times T(T(6) - 1) \times T(5) + 1$$

$$66152 := T(6) \times T(T(6) - 1) \times T(5) + 2$$

$$66153 := T(6) \times T(T(6) - 1) \times T(5) + 3$$

$$66154 := T(6) \times T(T(6) - 1) \times T(5) + 4$$

$$66155 := T(6) \times T(T(6) - 1) \times T(5) + 5$$

$$66156 := T(6) \times T(T(6) - 1) \times T(5) + 6$$

$$66157 := T(6) \times T(T(6) - 1) \times T(5) + 7$$

$$66158 := T(6) \times T(T(6) - 1) \times T(5) + 8$$

$$66159 := T(6) \times T(T(6) - 1) \times T(5) + 9$$

$$66360 := T((6 + T(T(6)))/3) \times T(6) + 0$$

$$66361 := T((6 + T(T(6)))/3) \times T(6) + 1$$

$$66362 := T((6 + T(T(6)))/3) \times T(6) + 2$$

$$66363 := T((6 + T(T(6)))/3) \times T(6) + 3$$

$$66364 := T((6 + T(T(6)))/3) \times T(6) + 4$$

$$66365 := T((6 + T(T(6)))/3) \times T(6) + 5$$

$$66366 := T((6 + T(T(6)))/3) \times T(6) + 6$$

$$66367 := T((6 + T(T(6)))/3) \times T(6) + 7$$

$$66368 := T((6 + T(T(6)))/3) \times T(6) + 8$$

$$66369 := T((6 + T(T(6)))/3) \times T(6) + 9$$

$$67320 := T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(T(3+2)) + 0$$

$$67321 := T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(T(3+2)) + 1$$

$$67322 := T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(T(3+2)) + 2$$

$$67323 := T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(T(3+2)) + 3$$

$$67324 := T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(T(3+2)) + 4$$

$$67325 := T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(T(3+2)) + 5$$

$$67326 := T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(T(3+2)) + 6$$

$$67327 := T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(T(3+2)) + 7$$

$$67328 := T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(T(3+2)) + 8$$

$$67329 := T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(T(3+2)) + 9$$

$$68040 := T(6) \times T(8 \times T(04)) + 0$$

$$68041 := T(6) \times T(8 \times T(04)) + 1$$

$$68042 := T(6) \times T(8 \times T(04)) + 2$$

$$68043 := T(6) \times T(8 \times T(04)) + 3$$

$$68044 := T(6) \times T(8 \times T(04)) + 4$$

$$68045 := T(6) \times T(8 \times T(04)) + 5$$

$$68046 := T(6) \times T(8 \times T(04)) + 6$$

$$68047 := T(6) \times T(8 \times T(04)) + 7$$

$$68048 := T(6) \times T(8 \times T(04)) + 8$$

$$68049 := T(6) \times T(8 \times T(04)) + 9$$

$$69300 := T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 00$$

$$69301 := T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 01$$

$$69302 := T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 02$$

$$69303 := T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 03$$

$$69304 := T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 04$$

$$69305 := T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 05$$

$$69306 := T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 06$$

$$69307 := T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 07$$

$$69308 := T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 08$$

$$69309 := T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 09$$

$$69310 := T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 10$$

$$69311 := T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 11$$

$$69312 := T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 12$$

$$69313 := T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 13$$

69314 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 14$
69315 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 15$
69316 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 16$
69317 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 17$
69318 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 18$
69319 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 19$
69320 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 20$
69321 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 21$
69322 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 22$
69323 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 23$
69324 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 24$
69325 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 25$
69326 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 26$
69327 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 27$
69328 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 28$
69329 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 29$
69330 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 30$
69331 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 31$
69332 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 32$
69333 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 33$
69334 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 34$
69335 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 35$
69336 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 36$
69337 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 37$
69338 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 38$
69339 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 39$
69340 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 40$
69341 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 41$
69342 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 42$
69343 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 43$
69344 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 44$
69345 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 45$
69346 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 46$
69347 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 47$
69348 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 48$
69349 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 49$
69350 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 50$
69351 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 51$
69352 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 52$
69353 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 53$

69354 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 54$
69355 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 55$
69356 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 56$
69357 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 57$
69358 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 58$
69359 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 59$
69360 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 60$
69361 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 61$
69362 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 62$
69363 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 63$
69364 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 64$
69365 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 65$
69366 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 66$
69367 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 67$
69368 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 68$
69369 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 69$
69370 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 70$
69371 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 71$
69372 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 72$
69373 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 73$
69374 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 74$
69375 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 75$
69376 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 76$
69377 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 77$
69378 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 78$
69379 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 79$
69380 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 80$
69381 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 81$
69382 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 82$
69383 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 83$
69384 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 84$
69385 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 85$
69386 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 86$
69387 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 87$
69388 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 88$
69389 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 89$
69390 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 90$
69391 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 91$
69392 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 92$
69393 := $T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 93$

$$\begin{aligned} 69394 &:= T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 94 \\ 69395 &:= T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 95 \\ 69396 &:= T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 96 \\ 69397 &:= T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 97 \\ 69398 &:= T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 98 \\ 69399 &:= T(T(6)) \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) + 99 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 70560 &:= T(7) \times T(T(05)) \times T(6) + 0 \\ 70561 &:= T(7) \times T(T(05)) \times T(6) + 1 \\ 70562 &:= T(7) \times T(T(05)) \times T(6) + 2 \\ 70563 &:= T(7) \times T(T(05)) \times T(6) + 3 \\ 70564 &:= T(7) \times T(T(05)) \times T(6) + 4 \\ 70565 &:= T(7) \times T(T(05)) \times T(6) + 5 \\ 70566 &:= T(7) \times T(T(05)) \times T(6) + 6 \\ 70567 &:= T(7) \times T(T(05)) \times T(6) + 7 \\ 70568 &:= T(7) \times T(T(05)) \times T(6) + 8 \\ 70569 &:= T(7) \times T(T(05)) \times T(6) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 71050 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(10) + T(T(5))) + 0 \\ 71051 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(10) + T(T(5))) + 1 \\ 71052 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(10) + T(T(5))) + 2 \\ 71053 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(10) + T(T(5))) + 3 \\ 71054 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(10) + T(T(5))) + 4 \\ 71055 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(10) + T(T(5))) + 5 \\ 71056 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(10) + T(T(5))) + 6 \\ 71057 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(10) + T(T(5))) + 7 \\ 71058 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(10) + T(T(5))) + 8 \\ 71059 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(10) + T(T(5))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 72450 &:= T(T(7+2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5)) + 0 \\ 72451 &:= T(T(7+2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5)) + 1 \\ 72452 &:= T(T(7+2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5)) + 2 \\ 72453 &:= T(T(7+2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5)) + 3 \\ 72454 &:= T(T(7+2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5)) + 4 \\ 72455 &:= T(T(7+2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5)) + 5 \\ 72456 &:= T(T(7+2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5)) + 6 \\ 72457 &:= T(T(7+2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5)) + 7 \\ 72458 &:= T(T(7+2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5)) + 8 \\ 72459 &:= T(T(7+2)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 72870 &:= T(7 \times 2) \times (T(T(8)) + T(7)) + 0 \\ 72871 &:= T(7 \times 2) \times (T(T(8)) + T(7)) + 1 \\ 72872 &:= T(7 \times 2) \times (T(T(8)) + T(7)) + 2 \\ 72873 &:= T(7 \times 2) \times (T(T(8)) + T(7)) + 4 \\ 72874 &:= T(7 \times 2) \times (T(T(8)) + T(7)) + 4 \\ 72875 &:= T(7 \times 2) \times (T(T(8)) + T(7)) + 5 \\ 72876 &:= T(7 \times 2) \times (T(T(8)) + T(7)) + 6 \\ 72877 &:= T(7 \times 2) \times (T(T(8)) + T(7)) + 7 \\ 72878 &:= T(7 \times 2) \times (T(T(8)) + T(7)) + 8 \\ 72879 &:= T(7 \times 2) \times (T(T(8)) + T(7)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 72930 &:= T(7 + T(2)) \times T(T(9) + T(3)) + 0 \\ 72931 &:= T(7 + T(2)) \times T(T(9) + T(3)) + 1 \\ 72932 &:= T(7 + T(2)) \times T(T(9) + T(3)) + 2 \\ 72933 &:= T(7 + T(2)) \times T(T(9) + T(3)) + 3 \\ 72934 &:= T(7 + T(2)) \times T(T(9) + T(3)) + 4 \\ 72935 &:= T(7 + T(2)) \times T(T(9) + T(3)) + 5 \\ 72936 &:= T(7 + T(2)) \times T(T(9) + T(3)) + 6 \\ 72937 &:= T(7 + T(2)) \times T(T(9) + T(3)) + 7 \\ 72938 &:= T(7 + T(2)) \times T(T(9) + T(3)) + 8 \\ 72939 &:= T(7 + T(2)) \times T(T(9) + T(3)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 73920 &:= T(T(7+3)) \times (T(9) + T(2)) + 0 \\ 73921 &:= T(T(7+3)) \times (T(9) + T(2)) + 1 \\ 73922 &:= T(T(7+3)) \times (T(9) + T(2)) + 2 \\ 73923 &:= T(T(7+3)) \times (T(9) + T(2)) + 3 \\ 73924 &:= T(T(7+3)) \times (T(9) + T(2)) + 4 \\ 73925 &:= T(T(7+3)) \times (T(9) + T(2)) + 5 \\ 73926 &:= T(T(7+3)) \times (T(9) + T(2)) + 6 \\ 73927 &:= T(T(7+3)) \times (T(9) + T(2)) + 7 \\ 73928 &:= T(T(7+3)) \times (T(9) + T(2)) + 8 \\ 73929 &:= T(T(7+3)) \times (T(9) + T(2)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74480 &:= T(7) \times (-4 + 4 \times T(T(8))) + 0 \\ 74481 &:= T(7) \times (-4 + 4 \times T(T(8))) + 1 \\ 74482 &:= T(7) \times (-4 + 4 \times T(T(8))) + 2 \\ 74483 &:= T(7) \times (-4 + 4 \times T(T(8))) + 3 \\ 74484 &:= T(7) \times (-4 + 4 \times T(T(8))) + 4 \\ 74485 &:= T(7) \times (-4 + 4 \times T(T(8))) + 5 \\ 74486 &:= T(7) \times (-4 + 4 \times T(T(8))) + 6 \\ 74487 &:= T(7) \times (-4 + 4 \times T(T(8))) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$74488 := T(7) \times (-4 + 4 \times T(T(8))) + 8$$

$$74489 := T(7) \times (-4 + 4 \times T(T(8))) + 9$$

$$74550 := T(7 \times T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(5)) + 0$$

$$74551 := T(7 \times T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(5)) + 1$$

$$74552 := T(7 \times T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(5)) + 2$$

$$74553 := T(7 \times T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(5)) + 3$$

$$74554 := T(7 \times T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(5)) + 4$$

$$74555 := T(7 \times T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(5)) + 5$$

$$74556 := T(7 \times T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(5)) + 6$$

$$74557 := T(7 \times T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(5)) + 7$$

$$74558 := T(7 \times T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(5)) + 8$$

$$74559 := T(7 \times T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(5)) + 9$$

$$74880 := T(7 \times 4 + T(8)) \times T(8) + 0$$

$$74881 := T(7 \times 4 + T(8)) \times T(8) + 1$$

$$74882 := T(7 \times 4 + T(8)) \times T(8) + 2$$

$$74883 := T(7 \times 4 + T(8)) \times T(8) + 3$$

$$74884 := T(7 \times 4 + T(8)) \times T(8) + 4$$

$$74885 := T(7 \times 4 + T(8)) \times T(8) + 5$$

$$74886 := T(7 \times 4 + T(8)) \times T(8) + 6$$

$$74887 := T(7 \times 4 + T(8)) \times T(8) + 7$$

$$74888 := T(7 \times 4 + T(8)) \times T(8) + 8$$

$$74889 := T(7 \times 4 + T(8)) \times T(8) + 9$$

$$75440 := (-T(7) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(4) \times 4) + 0$$

$$75441 := (-T(7) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(4) \times 4) + 1$$

$$75442 := (-T(7) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(4) \times 4) + 2$$

$$75443 := (-T(7) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(4) \times 4) + 3$$

$$75444 := (-T(7) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(4) \times 4) + 4$$

$$75445 := (-T(7) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(4) \times 4) + 5$$

$$75446 := (-T(7) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(4) \times 4) + 6$$

$$75447 := (-T(7) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(4) \times 4) + 7$$

$$75448 := (-T(7) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(4) \times 4) + 8$$

$$75449 := (-T(7) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(4) \times 4) + 9$$

$$77140 := T(T(7)) \times T(T(7) + 1 - T(4)) + 0$$

$$77141 := T(T(7)) \times T(T(7) + 1 - T(4)) + 1$$

$$77142 := T(T(7)) \times T(T(7) + 1 - T(4)) + 2$$

$$77143 := T(T(7)) \times T(T(7) + 1 - T(4)) + 3$$

$$77144 := T(T(7)) \times T(T(7) + 1 - T(4)) + 4$$

$$77145 := T(T(7)) \times T(T(7) + 1 - T(4)) + 5$$

$$77146 := T(T(7)) \times T(T(7) + 1 - T(4)) + 6$$

$$77147 := T(T(7)) \times T(T(7) + 1 - T(4)) + 7$$

$$77148 := T(T(7)) \times T(T(7) + 1 - T(4)) + 8$$

$$77149 := T(T(7)) \times T(T(7) + 1 - T(4)) + 9$$

$$78540 := T(7) \times (T(8) + T(5)) \times T(T(4)) + 0$$

$$78541 := T(7) \times (T(8) + T(5)) \times T(T(4)) + 1$$

$$78542 := T(7) \times (T(8) + T(5)) \times T(T(4)) + 2$$

$$78543 := T(7) \times (T(8) + T(5)) \times T(T(4)) + 3$$

$$78544 := T(7) \times (T(8) + T(5)) \times T(T(4)) + 4$$

$$78545 := T(7) \times (T(8) + T(5)) \times T(T(4)) + 5$$

$$78546 := T(7) \times (T(8) + T(5)) \times T(T(4)) + 6$$

$$78547 := T(7) \times (T(8) + T(5)) \times T(T(4)) + 7$$

$$78548 := T(7) \times (T(8) + T(5)) \times T(T(4)) + 8$$

$$78549 := T(7) \times (T(8) + T(5)) \times T(T(4)) + 9$$

$$82890 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8)) \times T(9) + 0$$

$$82891 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8)) \times T(9) + 1$$

$$82892 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8)) \times T(9) + 2$$

$$82893 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8)) \times T(9) + 3$$

$$82894 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8)) \times T(9) + 4$$

$$82895 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8)) \times T(9) + 5$$

$$82896 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8)) \times T(9) + 6$$

$$82897 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8)) \times T(9) + 7$$

$$82898 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8)) \times T(9) + 8$$

$$82899 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 8)) \times T(9) + 9$$

$$83160 := T(8) \times T(3 + 1) \times T(T(6)) + 0$$

$$83161 := T(8) \times T(3 + 1) \times T(T(6)) + 1$$

$$83162 := T(8) \times T(3 + 1) \times T(T(6)) + 2$$

$$83163 := T(8) \times T(3 + 1) \times T(T(6)) + 3$$

$$83164 := T(8) \times T(3 + 1) \times T(T(6)) + 4$$

$$83165 := T(8) \times T(3 + 1) \times T(T(6)) + 5$$

$$83166 := T(8) \times T(3 + 1) \times T(T(6)) + 6$$

$$83167 := T(8) \times T(3 + 1) \times T(T(6)) + 7$$

$$83168 := T(8) \times T(3 + 1) \times T(T(6)) + 8$$

$$83169 := T(8) \times T(3 + 1) \times T(T(6)) + 9$$

$$83250 := T(T(8)) \times (3 + 2 + T(T(5))) + 0$$

$$83251 := T(T(8)) \times (3 + 2 + T(T(5))) + 1$$

$$83252 := T(T(8)) \times (3 + 2 + T(T(5))) + 2$$

$$\begin{aligned}83253 &:= T(T(8)) \times (3 + 2 + T(T(5))) + 3 \\83254 &:= T(T(8)) \times (3 + 2 + T(T(5))) + 4 \\83255 &:= T(T(8)) \times (3 + 2 + T(T(5))) + 5 \\83256 &:= T(T(8)) \times (3 + 2 + T(T(5))) + 6 \\83257 &:= T(T(8)) \times (3 + 2 + T(T(5))) + 7 \\83258 &:= T(T(8)) \times (3 + 2 + T(T(5))) + 8 \\83259 &:= T(T(8)) \times (3 + 2 + T(T(5))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}84260 &:= (-8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(-2 + 6)) + 0 \\84261 &:= (-8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(-2 + 6)) + 1 \\84262 &:= (-8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(-2 + 6)) + 2 \\84263 &:= (-8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(-2 + 6)) + 3 \\84264 &:= (-8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(-2 + 6)) + 4 \\84265 &:= (-8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(-2 + 6)) + 5 \\84266 &:= (-8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(-2 + 6)) + 6 \\84267 &:= (-8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(-2 + 6)) + 7 \\84268 &:= (-8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(-2 + 6)) + 8 \\84269 &:= (-8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(-2 + 6)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}85140 &:= (8 + T(T(T(5 - 1)))) \times T(T(4)) + 0 \\85141 &:= (8 + T(T(T(5 - 1)))) \times T(T(4)) + 1 \\85142 &:= (8 + T(T(T(5 - 1)))) \times T(T(4)) + 2 \\85143 &:= (8 + T(T(T(5 - 1)))) \times T(T(4)) + 3 \\85144 &:= (8 + T(T(T(5 - 1)))) \times T(T(4)) + 4 \\85145 &:= (8 + T(T(T(5 - 1)))) \times T(T(4)) + 5 \\85146 &:= (8 + T(T(T(5 - 1)))) \times T(T(4)) + 6 \\85147 &:= (8 + T(T(T(5 - 1)))) \times T(T(4)) + 7 \\85148 &:= (8 + T(T(T(5 - 1)))) \times T(T(4)) + 8 \\85149 &:= (8 + T(T(T(5 - 1)))) \times T(T(4)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}85920 &:= T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9) + T(T(2)) + 0 \\85921 &:= T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9) + T(T(2)) + 1 \\85922 &:= T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9) + T(T(2)) + 2 \\85923 &:= T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9) + T(T(2)) + 3 \\85924 &:= T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9) + T(T(2)) + 4 \\85925 &:= T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9) + T(T(2)) + 5 \\85926 &:= T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9) + T(T(2)) + 6 \\85927 &:= T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9) + T(T(2)) + 7 \\85928 &:= T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9) + T(T(2)) + 8 \\85929 &:= T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9) + T(T(2)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}86240 &:= 8 \times T(6) / T(2) \times T(T(T(4))) + 0 \\86241 &:= 8 \times T(6) / T(2) \times T(T(T(4))) + 1 \\86242 &:= 8 \times T(6) / T(2) \times T(T(T(4))) + 2 \\86243 &:= 8 \times T(6) / T(2) \times T(T(T(4))) + 3 \\86244 &:= 8 \times T(6) / T(2) \times T(T(T(4))) + 4 \\86245 &:= 8 \times T(6) / T(2) \times T(T(T(4))) + 5 \\86246 &:= 8 \times T(6) / T(2) \times T(T(T(4))) + 6 \\86247 &:= 8 \times T(6) / T(2) \times T(T(T(4))) + 7 \\86248 &:= 8 \times T(6) / T(2) \times T(T(T(4))) + 8 \\86249 &:= 8 \times T(6) / T(2) \times T(T(T(4))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}86940 &:= T(T(8)/6) \times T(T(9)) \times 4 + 0 \\86941 &:= T(T(8)/6) \times T(T(9)) \times 4 + 1 \\86942 &:= T(T(8)/6) \times T(T(9)) \times 4 + 2 \\86943 &:= T(T(8)/6) \times T(T(9)) \times 4 + 3 \\86944 &:= T(T(8)/6) \times T(T(9)) \times 4 + 4 \\86945 &:= T(T(8)/6) \times T(T(9)) \times 4 + 5 \\86946 &:= T(T(8)/6) \times T(T(9)) \times 4 + 6 \\86947 &:= T(T(8)/6) \times T(T(9)) \times 4 + 7 \\86948 &:= T(T(8)/6) \times T(T(9)) \times 4 + 8 \\86949 &:= T(T(8)/6) \times T(T(9)) \times 4 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}87360 &:= T(T(8) + T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(6)) + 0 \\87361 &:= T(T(8) + T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(6)) + 1 \\87362 &:= T(T(8) + T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(6)) + 2 \\87363 &:= T(T(8) + T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(6)) + 3 \\87364 &:= T(T(8) + T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(6)) + 4 \\87365 &:= T(T(8) + T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(6)) + 5 \\87366 &:= T(T(8) + T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(6)) + 6 \\87367 &:= T(T(8) + T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(6)) + 7 \\87368 &:= T(T(8) + T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(6)) + 8 \\87369 &:= T(T(8) + T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(6)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}87660 &:= (T(8) \times T(T(7)) - 6) \times 6 + 0 \\87661 &:= (T(8) \times T(T(7)) - 6) \times 6 + 1 \\87662 &:= (T(8) \times T(T(7)) - 6) \times 6 + 2 \\87663 &:= (T(8) \times T(T(7)) - 6) \times 6 + 3 \\87664 &:= (T(8) \times T(T(7)) - 6) \times 6 + 4 \\87665 &:= (T(8) \times T(T(7)) - 6) \times 6 + 5 \\87666 &:= (T(8) \times T(T(7)) - 6) \times 6 + 6 \\87667 &:= (T(8) \times T(T(7)) - 6) \times 6 + 7 \\87668 &:= (T(8) \times T(T(7)) - 6) \times 6 + 8\end{aligned}$$

$$87669 := (T(8) \times T(T(7)) - 6) \times 6 + 9$$

$$88290 := (-T(T(8)) + T(T(8) \times 2)) \times T(9) + 0$$

$$88291 := (-T(T(8)) + T(T(8) \times 2)) \times T(9) + 1$$

$$88292 := (-T(T(8)) + T(T(8) \times 2)) \times T(9) + 2$$

$$88293 := (-T(T(8)) + T(T(8) \times 2)) \times T(9) + 3$$

$$88294 := (-T(T(8)) + T(T(8) \times 2)) \times T(9) + 4$$

$$88295 := (-T(T(8)) + T(T(8) \times 2)) \times T(9) + 5$$

$$88296 := (-T(T(8)) + T(T(8) \times 2)) \times T(9) + 6$$

$$88297 := (-T(T(8)) + T(T(8) \times 2)) \times T(9) + 7$$

$$88298 := (-T(T(8)) + T(T(8) \times 2)) \times T(9) + 8$$

$$88299 := (-T(T(8)) + T(T(8) \times 2)) \times T(9) + 9$$

$$89100 := T(8) \times T(9) \times T(10) + 0$$

$$89101 := T(8) \times T(9) \times T(10) + 1$$

$$89102 := T(8) \times T(9) \times T(10) + 2$$

$$89103 := T(8) \times T(9) \times T(10) + 3$$

$$89104 := T(8) \times T(9) \times T(10) + 4$$

$$89105 := T(8) \times T(9) \times T(10) + 5$$

$$89106 := T(8) \times T(9) \times T(10) + 6$$

$$89107 := T(8) \times T(9) \times T(10) + 7$$

$$89108 := T(8) \times T(9) \times T(10) + 8$$

$$89109 := T(8) \times T(9) \times T(10) + 9$$

$$89460 := T(8) \times T((T(9) + 4 + T(6))) + 0$$

$$89461 := T(8) \times T((T(9) + 4 + T(6))) + 1$$

$$89462 := T(8) \times T((T(9) + 4 + T(6))) + 2$$

$$89463 := T(8) \times T((T(9) + 4 + T(6))) + 3$$

$$89464 := T(8) \times T((T(9) + 4 + T(6))) + 4$$

$$89465 := T(8) \times T((T(9) + 4 + T(6))) + 5$$

$$89466 := T(8) \times T((T(9) + 4 + T(6))) + 6$$

$$89467 := T(8) \times T((T(9) + 4 + T(6))) + 7$$

$$89468 := T(8) \times T((T(9) + 4 + T(6))) + 8$$

$$89469 := T(8) \times T((T(9) + 4 + T(6))) + 9$$

$$91350 := T(9) \times T(T(1 + T(3))) \times 5 + 0$$

$$91351 := T(9) \times T(T(1 + T(3))) \times 5 + 1$$

$$91352 := T(9) \times T(T(1 + T(3))) \times 5 + 2$$

$$91353 := T(9) \times T(T(1 + T(3))) \times 5 + 3$$

$$91354 := T(9) \times T(T(1 + T(3))) \times 5 + 4$$

$$91355 := T(9) \times T(T(1 + T(3))) \times 5 + 5$$

$$91356 := T(9) \times T(T(1 + T(3))) \times 5 + 6$$

$$91357 := T(9) \times T(T(1 + T(3))) \times 5 + 7$$

$$91358 := T(9) \times T(T(1 + T(3))) \times 5 + 8$$

$$91359 := T(9) \times T(T(1 + T(3))) \times 5 + 9$$

$$92430 := (9 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4 \times 3)) + 0$$

$$92431 := (9 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4 \times 3)) + 1$$

$$92432 := (9 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4 \times 3)) + 2$$

$$92433 := (9 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4 \times 3)) + 3$$

$$92434 := (9 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4 \times 3)) + 4$$

$$92435 := (9 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4 \times 3)) + 5$$

$$92436 := (9 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4 \times 3)) + 6$$

$$92437 := (9 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4 \times 3)) + 7$$

$$92438 := (9 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4 \times 3)) + 8$$

$$92439 := (9 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4 \times 3)) + 9$$

$$92730 := -T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) + 0$$

$$92731 := -T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) + 1$$

$$92732 := -T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) + 2$$

$$92733 := -T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) + 3$$

$$92734 := -T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) + 4$$

$$92735 := -T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) + 5$$

$$92736 := -T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) + 6$$

$$92737 := -T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) + 7$$

$$92738 := -T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) + 8$$

$$92739 := -T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) + 9$$

$$93150 := T(T(9)) \times T(3) \times 15 + 0$$

$$93151 := T(T(9)) \times T(3) \times 15 + 1$$

$$93152 := T(T(9)) \times T(3) \times 15 + 2$$

$$93153 := T(T(9)) \times T(3) \times 15 + 3$$

$$93154 := T(T(9)) \times T(3) \times 15 + 4$$

$$93155 := T(T(9)) \times T(3) \times 15 + 5$$

$$93156 := T(T(9)) \times T(3) \times 15 + 6$$

$$93157 := T(T(9)) \times T(3) \times 15 + 7$$

$$93158 := T(T(9)) \times T(3) \times 15 + 8$$

$$93159 := T(T(9)) \times T(3) \times 15 + 9$$

$$93690 := T(9) \times (3 + T(T(6)) \times 9) + 0$$

$$93691 := T(9) \times (3 + T(T(6)) \times 9) + 1$$

$$93692 := T(9) \times (3 + T(T(6)) \times 9) + 2$$

$$93693 := T(9) \times (3 + T(T(6)) \times 9) + 3$$

$$\begin{aligned} 93694 &:= T(9) \times (3 + T(T(6)) \times 9) + 4 \\ 93695 &:= T(9) \times (3 + T(T(6)) \times 9) + 5 \\ 93696 &:= T(9) \times (3 + T(T(6)) \times 9) + 6 \\ 93697 &:= T(9) \times (3 + T(T(6)) \times 9) + 7 \\ 93698 &:= T(9) \times (3 + T(T(6)) \times 9) + 8 \\ 93699 &:= T(9) \times (3 + T(T(6)) \times 9) + 9 \\ \\ 93870 &:= T(9) \times (T(3) + T(T(8) + T(7))) + 0 \\ 93871 &:= T(9) \times (T(3) + T(T(8) + T(7))) + 1 \\ 93872 &:= T(9) \times (T(3) + T(T(8) + T(7))) + 2 \\ 93873 &:= T(9) \times (T(3) + T(T(8) + T(7))) + 3 \\ 93874 &:= T(9) \times (T(3) + T(T(8) + T(7))) + 4 \\ 93875 &:= T(9) \times (T(3) + T(T(8) + T(7))) + 5 \\ 93876 &:= T(9) \times (T(3) + T(T(8) + T(7))) + 6 \\ 93877 &:= T(9) \times (T(3) + T(T(8) + T(7))) + 7 \\ 93878 &:= T(9) \times (T(3) + T(T(8) + T(7))) + 8 \\ 93879 &:= T(9) \times (T(3) + T(T(8) + T(7))) + 9 \\ \\ 94240 &:= T(T(9)) \times T(T(4) + T(2)) + T(T(4)) + 0 \\ 94241 &:= T(T(9)) \times T(T(4) + T(2)) + T(T(4)) + 1 \\ 94242 &:= T(T(9)) \times T(T(4) + T(2)) + T(T(4)) + 2 \\ 94243 &:= T(T(9)) \times T(T(4) + T(2)) + T(T(4)) + 3 \\ 94244 &:= T(T(9)) \times T(T(4) + T(2)) + T(T(4)) + 4 \\ 94245 &:= T(T(9)) \times T(T(4) + T(2)) + T(T(4)) + 5 \\ 94246 &:= T(T(9)) \times T(T(4) + T(2)) + T(T(4)) + 6 \\ 94247 &:= T(T(9)) \times T(T(4) + T(2)) + T(T(4)) + 7 \\ 94248 &:= T(T(9)) \times T(T(4) + T(2)) + T(T(4)) + 8 \\ 94249 &:= T(T(9)) \times T(T(4) + T(2)) + T(T(4)) + 9 \\ \\ 95220 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(5) \times T(T(2)) + 2) + 0 \\ 95221 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(5) \times T(T(2)) + 2) + 1 \\ 95222 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(5) \times T(T(2)) + 2) + 2 \\ 95223 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(5) \times T(T(2)) + 2) + 3 \\ 95224 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(5) \times T(T(2)) + 2) + 4 \\ 95225 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(5) \times T(T(2)) + 2) + 5 \\ 95226 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(5) \times T(T(2)) + 2) + 6 \\ 95227 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(5) \times T(T(2)) + 2) + 7 \\ 95228 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(5) \times T(T(2)) + 2) + 8 \\ 95229 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(5) \times T(T(2)) + 2) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 95490 &:= T(9) \times T(T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) - T(T(9)) + 0 \\ 95491 &:= T(9) \times T(T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) - T(T(9)) + 1 \\ 95492 &:= T(9) \times T(T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) - T(T(9)) + 2 \\ 95493 &:= T(9) \times T(T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) - T(T(9)) + 3 \\ 95494 &:= T(9) \times T(T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) - T(T(9)) + 4 \\ 95495 &:= T(9) \times T(T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) - T(T(9)) + 5 \\ 95496 &:= T(9) \times T(T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) - T(T(9)) + 6 \\ 95497 &:= T(9) \times T(T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) - T(T(9)) + 7 \\ 95498 &:= T(9) \times T(T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) - T(T(9)) + 8 \\ 95499 &:= T(9) \times T(T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) - T(T(9)) + 9 \\ \\ 95760 &:= T(-T(9) + 5 \times T(7)) \times T(6) + 0 \\ 95761 &:= T(-T(9) + 5 \times T(7)) \times T(6) + 1 \\ 95762 &:= T(-T(9) + 5 \times T(7)) \times T(6) + 2 \\ 95763 &:= T(-T(9) + 5 \times T(7)) \times T(6) + 3 \\ 95764 &:= T(-T(9) + 5 \times T(7)) \times T(6) + 4 \\ 95765 &:= T(-T(9) + 5 \times T(7)) \times T(6) + 5 \\ 95766 &:= T(-T(9) + 5 \times T(7)) \times T(6) + 6 \\ 95767 &:= T(-T(9) + 5 \times T(7)) \times T(6) + 7 \\ 95768 &:= T(-T(9) + 5 \times T(7)) \times T(6) + 8 \\ 95769 &:= T(-T(9) + 5 \times T(7)) \times T(6) + 9 \\ \\ 96720 &:= (9 + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(2)) + 0 \\ 96721 &:= (9 + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(2)) + 1 \\ 96722 &:= (9 + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(2)) + 2 \\ 96723 &:= (9 + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(2)) + 3 \\ 96724 &:= (9 + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(2)) + 4 \\ 96725 &:= (9 + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(2)) + 5 \\ 96726 &:= (9 + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(2)) + 6 \\ 96727 &:= (9 + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(2)) + 7 \\ 96728 &:= (9 + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(2)) + 8 \\ 96729 &:= (9 + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(2)) + 9 \\ \\ 97290 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(7) + T(2 + 9)) + 0 \\ 97291 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(7) + T(2 + 9)) + 1 \\ 97292 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(7) + T(2 + 9)) + 2 \\ 97293 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(7) + T(2 + 9)) + 3 \\ 97294 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(7) + T(2 + 9)) + 4 \\ 97295 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(7) + T(2 + 9)) + 5 \\ 97296 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(7) + T(2 + 9)) + 6 \\ 97297 &:= T(T(9)) \times (T(7) + T(2 + 9)) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$97298 := T(T(9)) \times (T(7) + T(2+9)) + 8$$

$$97299 := T(T(9)) \times (T(7) + T(2+9)) + 9$$

$$99360 := T(T(9)) \times (-T(9) \times 3 + T(T(6))) + 0$$

$$99361 := T(T(9)) \times (-T(9) \times 3 + T(T(6))) + 1$$

$$99362 := T(T(9)) \times (-T(9) \times 3 + T(T(6))) + 2$$

$$99363 := T(T(9)) \times (-T(9) \times 3 + T(T(6))) + 3$$

$$99364 := T(T(9)) \times (-T(9) \times 3 + T(T(6))) + 4$$

$$99365 := T(T(9)) \times (-T(9) \times 3 + T(T(6))) + 5$$

$$99366 := T(T(9)) \times (-T(9) \times 3 + T(T(6))) + 6$$

$$99367 := T(T(9)) \times (-T(9) \times 3 + T(T(6))) + 7$$

$$99368 := T(T(9)) \times (-T(9) \times 3 + T(T(6))) + 8$$

$$99369 := T(T(9)) \times (-T(9) \times 3 + T(T(6))) + 9$$

$$99450 := T(T(9)) + 9^4 \times T(5) + 0$$

$$99451 := T(T(9)) + 9^4 \times T(5) + 1$$

$$99452 := T(T(9)) + 9^4 \times T(5) + 2$$

$$99453 := T(T(9)) + 9^4 \times T(5) + 3$$

$$99454 := T(T(9)) + 9^4 \times T(5) + 4$$

$$99455 := T(T(9)) + 9^4 \times T(5) + 5$$

$$99456 := T(T(9)) + 9^4 \times T(5) + 6$$

$$99457 := T(T(9)) + 9^4 \times T(5) + 7$$

$$99458 := T(T(9)) + 9^4 \times T(5) + 8$$

$$99459 := T(T(9)) + 9^4 \times T(5) + 9$$

$$99540 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 0$$

$$99541 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 1$$

$$99542 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 2$$

$$99543 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 3$$

$$99544 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 4$$

$$99545 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5$$

$$99546 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6$$

$$99547 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 7$$

$$99548 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 8$$

$$99549 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 9$$

$$99630 := T(9) \times (T(T(9) + T(6)) + 3) + 0$$

$$99631 := T(9) \times (T(T(9) + T(6)) + 3) + 1$$

$$99632 := T(9) \times (T(T(9) + T(6)) + 3) + 2$$

$$99633 := T(9) \times (T(T(9) + T(6)) + 3) + 3$$

$$99634 := T(9) \times (T(T(9) + T(6)) + 3) + 4$$

$$99635 := T(9) \times (T(T(9) + T(6)) + 3) + 5$$

$$99636 := T(9) \times (T(T(9) + T(6)) + 3) + 6$$

$$99637 := T(9) \times (T(T(9) + T(6)) + 3) + 7$$

$$99638 := T(9) \times (T(T(9) + T(6)) + 3) + 8$$

$$99639 := T(9) \times (T(T(9) + T(6)) + 3) + 9$$

2.2 General Representations: Up To Four Digits Numbers

$$15 := T(1 \times 5)$$

$$21 := T(T(2+1))$$

$$23 := 2 + T(T(3))$$

$$24 := T(T(2)) \times 4$$

$$34 := -T(T(3)) + T(T(4))$$

$$36 := T(3) \times 6$$

$$39 := -T(3) + T(9)$$

$$45 := T(4+5)$$

$$49 := 4 + T(9)$$

$$55 := T(5+5)$$

$$63 := T(6) \times 3$$

$$66 := T(T(T(6)))/T(6)$$

$$105 := T(-1 + T(05))$$

$$132 := (1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(2))$$

$$135 := T(-1 + T(3)) + T(T(5))$$

$$136 := T(T(1+3)) + 6$$

$$147 := T(T(-1+4)) \times 7$$

$$152 := -1 + T(T(5) + 2)$$

$$153 := T(-1 + T(5) + 3)$$

$$154 := T(T(T(-1+5)))/T(4)$$

$$167 := -1 + 6 \times T(7)$$

$$168 := 1 \times T(6) \times 8$$

$$171 := T(17+1)$$

$$176 := 1 + T(T(7)) - T(T(6))$$

$$185 := (1 + T(8)) \times 5$$

$$186 := -T(1+8) + T(T(6))$$

$$205 := T(20) - 5$$

$$\begin{aligned} 210 &:= T(2 \times 10) \\ 221 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2) + 1) \\ 222 &:= T(T(2))^{T(2)} + T(T(2)) \\ 223 &:= -2^{T(2)} + T(T(T(3))) \\ 224 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(2) - 4 \\ 225 &:= T(2 + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ 226 &:= -2 - T(2) + T(T(6)) \\ 227 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2) - 7 \\ 228 &:= T(T(2)) \times (2 + T(8)) \\ 229 &:= -2 + T(T(-T(2) + 9)) \\ 231 &:= T(T(2 \times 3 \times 1)) \\ 232 &:= -2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(2) \\ 233 &:= 2 + T(T(3 + 3)) \\ 234 &:= T(2) \times T(3 \times 4) \\ 236 &:= 2 + 3 + T(T(6)) \\ 237 &:= T(T(2)) + T(3 \times 7) \\ 240 &:= T(T(2)) \times 40 \\ 241 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4 \times 1) \\ 242 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4) + T(T(T(2))) \\ 243 &:= T(2)^4 \times 3 \\ 244 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 4 \\ 245 &:= (-T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 5 \\ 248 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times 8 \\ 252 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times 2 \\ 253 &:= T(25 - 3) \\ 254 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + 5 \times T(T(4)) \\ 255 &:= (2 + T(5)) \times T(5) \\ 256 &:= 25 + T(T(6)) \\ 264 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(6) \times 4 \\ 268 &:= T(2 + T(6)) - 8 \\ 273 &:= T(2) \times T(7 + T(3)) \\ 274 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(7) \times T(4) \\ 275 &:= T(T(2) + 7) \times 5 \\ 276 &:= T(2 + 7) + T(T(6)) \\ 279 &:= (T(2) + T(7)) \times 9 \\ 285 &:= T(T(2) \times 8) - T(5) \\ 286 &:= T(2 + 8) + T(T(6)) \\ 287 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + 8 \times 7 \\ 294 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(9) + 4) \\ 295 &:= T(-T(T(T(2)))) + T(9) - 5 \\ 297 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 9/7 \\ 315 &:= 3 \times T(-1 + T(5)) \\ 324 &:= -T(3) + T(T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 325 &:= T((3 + 2) \times 5) \\ 336 &:= T(3 \times T(T(3)))/6 \\ 342 &:= T(3) \times (T(T(4)) + 2) \\ 345 &:= T(3) \times T(T(4)) + T(5) \\ 346 &:= T(T(3)) + T(4 + T(6)) \\ 348 &:= -3 + T(-T(4) + T(8)) \\ 351 &:= T(T(T(3))) + 5 \times 1 \\ 355 &:= 3 \times T(T(5)) - 5 \\ 360 &:= T(3) \times 60 \\ 364 &:= -T(T(T(3))) + T(-T(6) + T(T(4))) \\ 369 &:= -T(36) + T(T(9)) \\ 372 &:= T(T(3)) + T(T(7) - 2) \\ 375 &:= (-3 + T(7)) \times T(5) \\ 385 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(-8 + T(5))) \\ 392 &:= T(3 + T(9))/T(2) \\ 396 &:= T(3) \times (T(9) + T(6)) \\ 399 &:= -T(3) + 9 \times T(9) \\ 416 &:= T(4) + T(T(1 + 6)) \\ 417 &:= T(4) + 1 + T(T(7)) \\ 427 &:= T(4 + 2) + T(T(7)) \\ 433 &:= T(T(4)) + T(3^3) \\ 435 &:= T(4 \times T(3) + 5) \\ 437 &:= T(4) + T(T(3)) + T(T(7)) \\ 442 &:= T(-4 + T(T(4)))/T(2) \\ 455 &:= -T(4) + T(T(5) + T(5)) \\ 456 &:= 4 \times (T(T(5)) - 6) \\ 461 &:= T(T(4)) + T(T(6 + 1)) \\ 462 &:= 4 \times T(T(6))/2 \\ 465 &:= T(4 + T(6) + 5) \\ 466 &:= 4 + T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) \\ 467 &:= T(T(4)) + 6 + T(T(7)) \\ 469 &:= 4 + T(T(6) + 9) \\ 475 &:= T(T(4)) + T(7) \times T(5) \\ 485 &:= -T(T(4)) + T(8) \times T(5) \\ 492 &:= T(T(4)) \times 9 - T(2) \\ 495 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(9)/5 \\ 496 &:= T(T(4) + T(T(9 - 6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$497 := T(4+9) + T(T(7))$$

$$525 := 5 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 5$$

$$528 := T(T(T(5))/T(2) - 8)$$

$$556 := T(5 \times 5) + T(T(6))$$

$$561 := T(5 + T(6 + 1))$$

$$564 := (T(T(5)) + T(6)) \times 4$$

$$572 := (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 2$$

$$573 := -T(5) + T(7) \times T(T(3))$$

$$629 := -T(T(T(6)/T(2))) + T(T(9))$$

$$630 := T(6) \times 30$$

$$637 := T(T(6)) + T(T(T(3)) + 7)$$

$$638 := -T(T(6)/3) + T(T(8))$$

$$647 := T(T(6)) + T(4) + T(T(7))$$

$$658 := T(T(6) + T(5)) - 8$$

$$663 := T(6 \times 6) - 3$$

$$666 := T(-6 + T(6) + T(6))$$

$$672 := (T(T(6)) - 7) \times T(2)$$

$$687 := T(6) + T(8 + T(7))$$

$$693 := (T(T(6)) \times (9/3))$$

$$696 := T(T(6)) + T(9 + T(6))$$

$$697 := -6 + T(9 + T(7))$$

$$722 := -7 + T(2)^{T(T(2))}$$

$$728 := T(7 + T(T(2))) \times 8$$

$$735 := (T(7) + T(T(3))) \times T(5)$$

$$741 := T(T(7) + T(4 \times 1))$$

$$742 := (-T(7) + T(T(T(4))))/2$$

$$756 := T(-7 + T(5)) \times T(6)$$

$$758 := -T(7) + T(T(5)) + T(T(8))$$

$$759 := -T(T(7) - 5) + T(T(9))$$

$$774 := T(7) \times T(7) - T(4)$$

$$777 := T(7) \times T(7) - 7$$

$$784 := T(7)^{8/4}$$

$$812 := T(T(8-1)) \times 2$$

$$825 := T(8+2) \times T(5)$$

$$826 := T(T(8) - 2) + T(T(6))$$

$$842 := T(T(8)) - T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$861 := T(T(8) + 6 - 1)$$

$$864 := T(8) \times 6 \times 4$$

$$867 := -T(8) + T(6 \times 7)$$

$$874 := -T(T(8)) + T(7) \times T(T(4))$$

$$882 := T(T(8)) + T(8) \times T(T(2))$$

$$897 := T(T(8)) + T(T(T(T(9-7))))$$

$$903 := T(T(9) - 03)$$

$$915 := T(T(9)) - T(15)$$

$$924 := T(T(9 - T(2))) \times 4$$

$$945 := T(9) \times T(T(T(T(4)/5)))$$

$$946 := T(T(9) + 4 - 6)$$

$$957 := T(T(9)) - T(5 + 7)$$

$$966 := T(9) \times T(6) + T(6)$$

$$969 := T(T(9)) - T(6) - T(9)$$

$$972 := T(T(9) - 7) + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$977 := T(T(9)) - T(T(7))/7$$

$$1024 := 1 \times 02^{T(4)}$$

$$1025 := -10 + T(T(2) \times T(5))$$

$$1029 := -T(1 + 02) + T(T(9))$$

$$1035 := T(10 + 35)$$

$$1036 := 1 + T(T(03 + 6))$$

$$1039 := 1 + 03 + T(T(9))$$

$$1045 := 10 + T(45)$$

$$1049 := 10 + 4 + T(T(9))$$

$$1056 := T(10) \times T(5) + T(T(6))$$

$$1069 := T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9))$$

$$1081 := T(1 + T(08 + 1))$$

$$1088 := -T(T(10)) + T(T(8) + T(8))$$

$$1122 := T(11 \times T(2)) \times 2$$

$$1125 := (-T(T(1 + 1)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 5$$

$$1128 := T(-1 + 12 + T(8))$$

$$1129 := 1 + T(1 \times 2 + T(9))$$

$$1134 := -1 \times T(T(1 + T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$1144 := (T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) + T(T(4))) \times 4$$

$$1149 := 114 + T(T(9))$$

$$1152 := T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) \times 5 - T(2)$$

$$1153 := -1 - 1 + 5 \times T(T(T(3)))$$

$$1154 := -1 + T(1 + 5) \times T(T(4))$$

$$1155 := T(T(1 + 1) \times T(5)) + T(T(5))$$

$$1156 := 1 + 1 \times 5 \times T(T(6))$$

$$1165 := (1 + 1 + T(T(6))) \times 5$$

$$1174 := -1 - 1 + T(-7 + T(T(4)))$$

$$1176 := T((1 \times 1 + 7) \times 6)$$

$$1177 := 1 + T(-1 + 7 \times 7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1182 &:= T(T(1+1)) + T(8 \times T(T(2))) & 1329 &:= 1 \times 3 + T(T(T(2)) + T(9)) \\ 1188 &:= (-T(1+1) + T(8)) \times T(8) & 1332 &:= (-1+3) \times T(T(3)^2) \\ 1197 &:= T((1+1) \times 9) \times 7 & 1337 &:= T(T(T((1+3)))) - T(T(T(3))) + T(7) \\ 1210 &:= (1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(10) & 1338 &:= (-1+3) \times (3 + T(T(8))) \\ 1217 &:= -1 + T(2) \times T(T(1 \times 7)) & 1339 &:= 13 + T(T(3) + T(9)) \\ 1218 &:= (1+2) \times T(T(-1+8)) & 1342 &:= (1 + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \\ 1222 &:= T((1 + T(T(2)))^2) - T(2) & 1343 &:= -1 + T(T(3)) \times 4^3 \\ 1224 &:= -1 + T(T(T(2)^2) + 4) & 1345 &:= T(-1 \times T(3) + T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) \\ 1225 &:= T(-1 + 2 \times 25) & 1349 &:= -1 + 3 \times T(4) \times T(9) \\ 1226 &:= 1 + T(T(T(2+2)) - 6) & 1356 &:= T(1 \times 3) \times (-5 + T(T(6))) \\ 1227 &:= (1+2) \times (T(2) + T(T(7))) & 1362 &:= (-1 - 3 + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 1235 &:= (T(1 + T(T(T(2)))) - T(3)) \times 5 & 1364 &:= T(T(T(1+3))) - T(T(6)) + T(T(4)) \\ 1237 &:= 1 + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(T(7))) & 1365 &:= 13 \times T(6) \times 5 \\ 1239 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) - T(3) + T(T(9)) & 1366 &:= 1 + T(3) \times T(T(6)) - T(6) \\ 1243 &:= T(1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 + T(T(T(3))) & 1368 &:= T(1 \times 3 \times 6) \times 8 \\ 1245 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(45) & 1372 &:= (1+3) \times 7^{T(2)} \\ 1246 &:= T(T(1+2)) + T(T(T(4)) - 6) & 1374 &:= -1 + (-3 + T(7)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 1247 &:= -1 + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(T(7))) & 1377 &:= -1 + T(3 + 7 \times 7) \\ 1248 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)) - 8) & 1378 &:= T(-1 - 3 + 7 \times 8) \\ 1249 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) + 4 + T(T(9)) & 1379 &:= 1^3 + T(7 + T(9)) \\ 1254 &:= -T(T(1+2)) + T(5 \times T(4)) & 1384 &:= -T(T(-1 + T(3))) - T(8) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 1259 &:= -1 + T(2+5) \times T(9) & 1385 &:= -1 + T(3) \times T(T(8) - T(5)) \\ 1272 &:= T(T(12) - T(7)) - T(2) & 1386 &:= T(1 \times 3 + 8) \times T(6) \\ 1273 &:= T(T(1 + T(2))) + T(T(7)) \times 3 & 1389 &:= -1 \times T(T(T(3))) + T(8) \times T(9) \\ 1274 &:= -1 + T((-2 + 7) \times T(4)) & 1392 &:= (1 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (9 - T(2)) \\ 1275 &:= T((1 + 2 + 7) \times 5) & 1395 &:= 1 \times 3 \times T(T(9) - T(5)) \\ 1276 &:= 1 + T(2 \times T(7) - 6) & 1396 &:= 1 + 3 \times T(9 + T(6)) \\ 1284 &:= -1 \times 2^8 + T(T(T(4))) & 1421 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(2)) - 1)) \\ 1291 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9) + 1) & 1422 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(2) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 1295 &:= -1 + T(T(2) + T(9)) + T(T(5)) & 1423 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4)) + 2) - T(T(T(3))) \\ 1296 &:= T(-1 + T(T(2)) + T(9)) + T(6) & 1424 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(T(2)) - T(T(4)) \\ 1297 &:= -1 + T(T(T(2)) + T(9)) - T(7) & 1425 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(2)) - T(T(5)) \\ 1310 &:= 1 - T(T(T(3))) + T(T(10)) & 1426 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4)) - 2) - 6 \\ 1322 &:= -1 + T(T(3))^2 \times T(2) & 1428 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(8) \\ 1323 &:= T(T(1 \times 3)) \times T(2) \times T(T(3)) & 1429 &:= -1 - T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2))) \times 9 \\ 1324 &:= T(1 + T(3)) + T(T(2))^4 & 1431 &:= T((-1 + T(4)) \times T(3) - 1) \\ 1325 &:= -1 + T(T(3)^2 + T(5)) & 1432 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4)) - T(3)/T(2)) \\ 1326 &:= T(-13 + 2^6) & 1434 &:= 1 + T(T(4)) + T(-3 + T(T(4))) \\ 1327 &:= 1 + T(T(3) + T(2 + 7)) & 1435 &:= T(T(T(1 \times 4))) - T(T(3)) \times 5 \\ 1328 &:= (-1 + 3) \times (-2 + T(T(8))) & 1442 &:= 1 + T(4) + T(T(T(4)) - 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1443 &:= T(1 + T(T(4))) - T(-4 + T(T(3))) \\1445 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) + T(5) \\1446 &:= T(-1 + 4) \times (T(4) + T(T(6))) \\1447 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(4) - T(7) \\1448 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) - T(8) \\1449 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(4) \times 9 \\1455 &:= T(14) \times T(5) - T(T(5)) \\1456 &:= (1 + T(T(4))) \times (5 + T(6)) \\1457 &:= T(-T(1 + T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(7) \\1462 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(6) - 2 \\1463 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(6 + T(3)) \\1464 &:= T(T(T(1 \times 4))) - T(6) - T(T(4)) \\1470 &:= T(T(-1 + 4)) \times 70 \\1472 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 7 - T(T(2)) \\1474 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 7 - 4 \\1479 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(T(-7 + 9)) \\1482 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(8 - T(T(2))) \\1483 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 8 + T(3) \\1484 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8 - 4)) \\1485 &:= T(1 + 48 + 5) \\1486 &:= 1 + T(48 + 6) \\1487 &:= T(T(1 \times 4) + T(8)) + T(T(7)) \\1489 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) + T(8)/9 \\1492 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9) - 2 \\1493 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9) - 3 \\1494 &:= T(T(T(1 \times 4))) + 9 - T(T(4)) \\1495 &:= T(T(T(1 \times 4))) - 9 \times 5 \\1496 &:= 1 + T(4) + T(9 \times 6) \\1497 &:= 1 + T(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + T(T(7)) \\1498 &:= T(1 + T(T(4))) - 98 \\1499 &:= 14 + T(9 + T(9)) \\1506 &:= T(1 \times 50) + T(T(6)) \\1512 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(1 + T(T(2))) \\1519 &:= -T(1 + 5) + T(T(1 + 9)) \\1520 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - 20 \\1522 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(2) \times T(T(2)) \\1524 &:= 1 - T(5) - 2 + T(T(T(4))) \\1525 &:= -15 + T(T(2 \times 5)) \\1526 &:= 1 - T(5) + T(T(T(-2 + 6))) \\1527 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(T(2)) - 7\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1529 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - 2 - 9 \\1532 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(3) - 2 \\1533 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(T(3))/3 \\1534 &:= -1 - 5 + T(T(T(3) + 4)) \\1535 &:= T(T(T(1^5 + 3))) - 5 \\1537 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(T(3))/7 \\1538 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(3) - 8 \\1539 &:= T((1 + 5) \times 3) \times 9 \\1552 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(5) - T(2) \\1554 &:= -1^5 + T(5) + T(T(T(4))) \\1555 &:= 15 + T(55) \\1556 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - 5 + T(6) \\1561 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(6 \times 1) \\1564 &:= (-1 + 5) \times 6 + T(T(T(4))) \\1567 &:= -1 + T(56) - T(7) \\1573 &:= (1 + T(T(5))) \times (7 + T(3)) \\1574 &:= -1 + 5 \times 7 + T(T(T(4))) \\1575 &:= T(1 + 5) \times 75 \\1576 &:= 1 + T(5) \times T(-7 + T(6)) \\1579 &:= (-1 + 5) \times T(T(7)) - T(9) \\1582 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(8) + T(T(2)) \\1593 &:= T(1 + T(T(-5 + 9))) - 3 \\1594 &:= (1 + 5) \times 9 + T(T(T(4))) \\1595 &:= T(T(-1 + 5)) + T(T(T(9 - 5))) \\1596 &:= T(1 \times 5 + T(9) + 6) \\1616 &:= -1 + T(T(6)) \times (1 + 6) \\1617 &:= 1 \times T(T(6)) \times 1 \times 7 \\1618 &:= 1 + T(T(6)) \times (-1 + 8) \\1623 &:= (1 + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3))) \\1624 &:= (-1 - T(T(6))) \times (T(2) - T(4)) \\1625 &:= (-1 + 6) \times T(25) \\1632 &:= T(16) \times T(3) \times 2 \\1637 &:= -1 + (T(T(6)) + 3) \times 7 \\1638 &:= -T(-1 + 6) + T(T(T(3)) + T(8)) \\1639 &:= 1 + T(6) \times T(3 + 9) \\1645 &:= (-1 + 6 \times T(T(4))) \times 5 \\1648 &:= (T(-1 + T(6)) - 4) \times 8 \\1652 &:= -1 + T(-T(6) + T(T(5) - T(2))) \\1653 &:= T(T(1 \times 6) + T(5 + 3)) \\1654 &:= -1 \times 6 + T(T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))\end{aligned}$$

- 1656** := $T(T(1+6) - 5) \times 6$
1657 := $1 + 6 \times T(-5 + T(7))$
1661 := $1 - T(T(6)) + T(61)$
1665 := $T(-1+6) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))$
1668 := $T(-1+6) + T(T(6) + T(8))$
1711 := $T(-1 - 7 + T(11))$
1712 := $1 + T((T(7) + 1) \times 2)$
1722 := $T(-1 + 7 \times T(T(2))) \times 2$
1728 := $(-1 + 7^2) \times T(8)$
1755 := $T(T(-1+7) + 5) \times 5$
1763 := $-1 + T(7) \times 63$
1764 := $T(-1+7) \times T(6) \times 4$
1769 := $-1 + T(-7 + T(6) + T(9))$
1782 := $(-1 + T(7)) \times T(8 + T(2))$
1785 := $(-1 + T(7 + 8)) \times T(5)$
1823 := $-1 + 8 \times (-T(2) + T(T(T(3))))$
1824 := $T(18) + T(2 + T(T(4)))$
1825 := $T(-T(18) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) - 5$
1826 := $-1 + 8 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(6)$
1827 := $(1 + 8) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(7))$
1829 := $-1 + T(T(8 - T(2)) + T(9))$
1844 := $(T(T(-1+8)) + T(T(4))) \times 4$
1846 := $-T(1+8) + T(T(T(4)) + 6)$
1847 := $-1 + 8 \times T(T(T(-4+7)))$
1848 := $T(T(T(1+8/4))) \times 8$
1850 := $(1 + T(8)) \times 50$
1853 := $-1 - T(T(8)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))$
1864 := $(1 + T(T(8) - 6)) \times 4$
1875 := $T(T(1+8)) + 7 \times T(T(5))$
1883 := $-1 + T(8) + 8 \times T(T(T(3)))$
1892 := $1 + T(T(T(T(8)/9)) + T(T(2)))$
1895 := $(1 + T(T(8) - 9)) \times 5$
1896 := $(1 + T(8)) \times T(9) + T(T(6))$
1899 := $-T(18) + T(T(9)) + T(T(9))$
1912 := $1 + 91 \times T(T(T(2)))$
1922 := $-T(1 + T(9)) + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2))$
1925 := $-T(T(1+9)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(5)$
1928 := $(-1 + T(9))^2 - 8$
1932 := $(1 + T(9)) \times T(T(3)) \times 2$
1937 := $-1 + T(T(9)) + T(T(3) \times 7)$
1938 := $T(T(1 \times 9)) + T(T(3) + T(8))$
1939 := $1 + T(T(9)) + T(-3 + T(9))$
1944 := $-T(1 + T(9)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(4))$
1946 := $T(1+9) + T(T(T(4)) + 6)$
1947 := $1 + T(T(9) + T(4)) + T(T(7))$
1952 := $-1 + T(T(9) + T(5) + 2)$
1953 := $T(1 \times 9 + 53)$
1962 := $1 \times 9 + T(62)$
1967 := $T(T(1+9)) + T(6) + T(T(7))$
1975 := $-T(1+9) + T(T(7)) \times 5$
1978 := $(1 + T(9)) \times (7 + T(8))$
1992 := $T(T(-1+9)) + T(T(9) + T(T(2)))$
1995 := $19 \times T(9+5)$
1997 := $-19 + T(9 \times 7)$
1998 := $T(1+9/9) \times T(T(8))$
2016 := $T((T(2) \times T(0 \times 1 + 6)))$
2022 := $T(T(2)) + T(T(02) \times T(T(T(2))))$
2036 := $20 + T(3 \times T(6))$
2065 := $(T(2^{06}) - T(5))$
2078 := $-2 + T(T(07) + T(8))$
2079 := $T(T(2) \times 07) \times 9$
2082 := $2 + T(08^2)$
2100 := $T(T(T(2))) \times 100$
2122 := $T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(1+T(2)))) + T(T(2))$
2124 := $-T(T(T(2))) + T(T(1+T(2))) + T(T(4))$
2135 := $(T(T(T(2))) + T(T(1+T(3)))) \times 5$
2136 := $T(T(T(T(2)) - 1)) + T(3 \times T(6))$
2139 := $-T(T(2)) + T(-1 + T(T(3)) + T(9))$
2142 := $T(T(T(2) + 1) + T(T(4))) - T(2)$
2143 := $-2 + T(1 + 4^3)$
2144 := $-2 + 1 + T(T(4) + T(T(4)))$
2145 := $T(-2 + 1 + T(-4 + T(5)))$
2147 := $2 + T(-1 + T(4 + 7))$
2148 := $-T(2) + T(-1 + T(T(4))) + T(T(8))$
2156 := $-T(T(T(2) + 1)) + T(T(5 + 6))$
2162 := $2 \times T(1 + T(6 + T(2)))$
2165 := $T(T(T(2))) - 1 + T(65)$
2166 := $T(2)^{1+6} - T(6)$
2169 := $(T(T(2) + 1) + T(T(6))) \times 9$
2175 := $T(2 - 1 + T(7)) \times 5$

- 2177** := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1) \times 7 + T(T(7))$
2178 := $T(T(T(T(2) + 1))) - T(7) + T(T(8))$
2183 := $-T(T(T(2)) + 1) + T(T(8 + 3))$
2184 := $T(T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(8 + 4)$
2196 := $-T(T(T(2)) - 1) + T(T(9) + T(6))$
2198 := $2 \times T(1 + T(9)) + T(8)$
2205 := $-T(T(2)) + T(T(T(T(2)) + 05))$
2208 := $T(T(2) + 20) \times 8$
2209 := $-2 + T(T(2 + 09))$
2211 := $T(T(2 - 2 + 11))$
2221 := $T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) + T(T(2) + 1)$
2222 := $(T(T(2))^{T(T(2))} + T(T(2)))/T(T(T(2)))$
2223 := $T(2) \times T(2 + T(2^3))$
2224 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(2)) \times T(2) + T(T(T(4)))$
2226 := $T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(2) \times T(6))$
2227 := $T(2^{T(T(2))}) + T(T(T(2))) \times 7$
2229 := $T(T(T(2))) - T(2) + T(T(2 + 9))$
2231 := $T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) + T(T(3)) - 1$
2232 := $T(T(T(2))) + T(T(2 + T(3) + T(2)))$
2233 := $T(T(T(2 + 2))) + 3 \times T(T(T(3)))$
2234 := $2 + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(T(3)) - T(4)))$
2235 := $T(2) + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3) + 5))$
2237 := $-2 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(3)))) + T(7)$
2238 := $T(T(T(2))) + T(T(2)) + T(T(3 + 8))$
2239 := $T(T(T(T(2)))/T(2)) + T(T(T(3)) + T(9))$
2242 := $T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) + T(4) + T(T(T(2)))$
2243 := $T(T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 4 + T(T(T(3)))$
2244 := $T(T(2) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times 4$
2245 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2))) \times T(4) - 5$
2246 := $-2^{T(T(2))} + T(4) \times T(T(6))$
2247 := $T(2 + T(T(2))) + T(T(4 + 7))$
2248 := $T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8))$
2250 := $T(T(2)^2) \times 50$
2252 := $T(T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))) + 5 + T(T(T(T(2))))$
2253 := $T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(5 + T(3)))$
2254 := $-T(T(T(2) + T(2))) + T(T(5) + T(T(4)))$
2256 := $T(T(2) + T(T(2))) + T(T(5 + 6))$
2259 := $T(2) + T(T(T(T(2)) + 5)) + T(9)$
2262 := $T(T(2)^{T(2)}) \times 6 - T(T(2))$
2264 := $T(T(2)^{T(2)}) \times 6 - 4$
2265 := $T(T(2 + T(2))) + T(65)$
2266 := $T(T(2 + 2)) + T(66)$
2267 := $-T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))) + T(67)$
2268 := $-T(T(T(2)) + T(T(2))) + T(68)$
2269 := $T(T(2) + 2^6) - 9$
2271 := $T(2) + T(T(2)) \times T(T(7) - 1)$
2274 := $T(T(2)) \times (-T(T(2)) + 7 \times T(T(4)))$
2275 := $(2 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 7) \times 5$
2277 := $2 + T(-T(2) + T(7)) \times 7$
2278 := $T(T(T(2))) - T(2) + T(7) + T(8)$
2279 := $2 + T(-T(T(2)) + T(7)) \times 9$
2281 := $T(2) + T(T(T(2) + 8) + 1)$
2283 := $2^{T(T(2))} \times T(8) - T(T(3))$
2284 := $T(2) + T(2 + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))$
2286 := $T(2) \times (T(T(2)) + T(8) \times T(6))$
2288 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2 + 8)) \times 8$
2289 := $T(T(T(2))) + T(T(2)) \times T(T(8) - 9)$
2292 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - 2) \times 9 + T(T(T(T(2))))$
2295 := $T(2^{T(2)} + 9) \times T(5)$
2299 := $T(T(T(T(2)))) - 2 + T(T(9)) + T(T(9))$
2304 := $(T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(04)$
2324 := $2 \times (-T(3^{T(2)}) + T(T(T(4))))$
2325 := $(2 + 3) \times T(2 \times T(5))$
2328 := $-T(T(2) + T(T(3))) + T(2 \times T(8))$
2331 := $T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(3) - 1)))$
2332 := $T(2^{T(3)}) + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2)))$
2334 := $-T(T(2)) + (3 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)$
2338 := $-2 + 3 \times T(3 + T(8))$
2343 := $T(2 \times 34) - 3$
2352 := $T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3) + 5) + 2)$
2354 := $-T(T(2)) + (T(T(T(3))) + 5) \times T(4)$
2355 := $(T(T(2)) + T(T(3) \times 5)) \times 5$
2358 := $T(2) \times (T(3 \times 5) + T(T(8)))$
2364 := $-T(T(2)) + (T(3) + T(T(6))) \times T(4)$
2365 := $T(2^{T(3)} + 6) - T(T(5))$
2372 := $-2^{T(3)} + T(T(7)) \times T(T(2))$
2373 := $(T(T(2 + 3)) - 7) \times T(T(3))$
2374 := $-T(2)^3 + 7^4$
2375 := $(2 + T(T(3)) \times (-7 + T(T(5))))$
2376 := $(-T(-2 + T(3)) + T(T(7))) \times 6$

$$\begin{aligned} 2377 &:= T(T(2^3)) + T(T(T(7)))/7 \\ 2378 &:= 2 \times (T(T(T(3)) + T(7)) - T(8)) \\ 2379 &:= -T(2) + T(3) \times (T(T(7)) - 9) \\ 2382 &:= T(-T(2) + T(T(3))) + T(T(8 + T(2))) \\ 2384 &:= -T(T(2)) + (T(T(T(3))) + 8) \times T(4) \\ 2385 &:= T(2) \times (T(3 + T(8)) + T(5)) \\ 2387 &:= T(T(2) + T(3 + 8)) - T(7) \\ 2388 &:= 2 \times T(T(3) \times 8) + T(8) \\ 2394 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)) \times (9 + T(4)) \\ 2397 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(3) \times (T(9) - T(T(7))) \\ 2398 &:= -2 + T(-T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 8 \\ 2400 &:= T(T(2)) \times 400 \\ 2410 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)) \times 10 \\ 2412 &:= -T(2) + T(T(T(4) + 1) + T(2)) \\ 2413 &:= -2 + T(T(T(4) + 1) + 3) \\ 2415 &:= T(T(2) + T(-4 + 15)) \\ 2417 &:= 2 + T(41 + T(7)) \\ 2421 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1 \\ 2422 &:= T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))^2 \\ 2428 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4) - T(2))) - 8 \\ 2430 &:= T(2)^4 \times 30 \\ 2432 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(4))) \times 32 \\ 2433 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T((4 + 3))) - 3 \\ 2435 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(4)) - T(3)) - T(5) \\ 2436 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(4 - 3 + 6)) \\ 2437 &:= -T(2) + 4 + T(3) \times T(T(7)) \\ 2438 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - 4 + T(T(3 + 8)) \\ 2439 &:= -T(T(2 \times 4)) + 3 \times T(T(9)) \\ 2440 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 40 \\ 2442 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(4 + 4 + T(2))) \\ 2443 &:= -T(2 + T(T(4))) + 4^{T(3)} \\ 2444 &:= (T(T(2 \times 4)) - T(T(4))) \times 4 \\ 2445 &:= T(24) + T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \\ 2446 &:= T(2^4) + T(4) \times T(T(6)) \\ 2448 &:= T(2^4) \times (T(4) + 8) \\ 2450 &:= (-T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 50 \\ 2452 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4) + T(T(5 + T(T(2)))) \\ 2454 &:= -T(T(T(2))) - T(4) + T(T(5) + T(T(4))) \\ 2455 &:= T(2) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(5))) - 5 \\ 2457 &:= T(T(2 + 4) + 5) \times 7 \\ 2458 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))/5 \times 8 \\ 2462 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)) - 6)) \times 2 \\ 2463 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(T(-T(4) + T(6))) + T(T(T(3))) \\ 2464 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(4 + T(T(6) - T(4))) \\ 2465 &:= (-T(2) + T(T(4) + T(6))) \times 5 \\ 2467 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(4) + 6 \times T(T(7)) \\ 2469 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(4 + 6) \times T(9) \\ 2472 &:= T(T(2)) + T(4 \times 7) \times T(T(2)) \\ 2473 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(T(4) \times 7) - T(3) \\ 2474 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(4) + T(7 \times T(4)) \\ 2475 &:= -T(T(2) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(7) - T(5))) \\ 2476 &:= -T(2) + T(T(4) \times 7) - 6 \\ 2478 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(4 + 7)) + T(8) \\ 2479 &:= T(2) + T(T(4) \times 7) - 9 \\ 2480 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times 80 \\ 2481 &:= T(T(2)) + T(T(4)) \times T(8 + 1) \\ 2482 &:= -T(2) + T(4 + T(8 + T(2))) \\ 2483 &:= -2 + T(4 + T(8 + 3)) \\ 2485 &:= T(-T(2 + 4) + T(8 + 5)) \\ 2487 &:= 2 + T(T(T(4)) + 8 + 7) \\ 2488 &:= T(2) + T(T(4 + 8) - 8) \\ 2489 &:= -T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(4)) + T(T(T(8)))/9 \\ 2492 &:= T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9) - 2) \\ 2493 &:= -T(2) + T(T(4)) \times T(9) + T(T(3)) \\ 2494 &:= -T(2)^4 + T(T(9)) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 2495 &:= (-T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(9))) \times 5 \\ 2496 &:= T(T(T(2)) + 4) \times T(9) + (T(6)) \\ 2497 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(T(4)) \times T(9) + T(7) \\ 2499 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times (4 + T(T(9)))/9 \\ 2505 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) - T(05) \\ 2510 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) - 10 \\ 2513 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) - 1 - T(3) \\ 2514 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) - T(-1 + 4) \\ 2515 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) - 1 \times 5 \\ 2517 &:= -T(2) + T(T(5)) \times T(-1 + 7) \\ 2519 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) - 1^9 \\ 2532 &:= T(T(2)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(3)) + T(T(2)) \\ 2534 &:= T(T(T(2)) \times T(5)) - T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4))) \\ 2535 &:= T(T(2) + T(5 + T(3))) + T(T(5)) \\ 2536 &:= T(25) + T(T(T(T(3)))/T(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2541 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times (T(5 + T(4)) + 1) & 2626 &:= -2 + T(6 \times 2 \times 6) \\ 2543 &:= 2 + (T(5) - 4) \times T(T(T(3))) & 2628 &:= T(2 + 62 + 8) \\ 2544 &:= -T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(5) + 4 + T(T(4))) & 2634 &:= 2 \times (T(6) + T(3)^4) \\ 2545 &:= 2 \times T(5 \times T(4)) - 5 & 2638 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(6) \times T(T(3)) - 8 \\ 2546 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + 5 + T(4) \times T(T(6)) & 2640 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(6) \times 40 \\ 2547 &:= T(T(-T(T(2)) + T(5))) + T(T(T(4))) - T(7) & 2643 &:= T(T(2 + 6)) \times 4 - T(T(3)) \\ 2548 &:= T(2 + 5) \times (T(T(4)) + T(8)) & 2644 &:= T(2 + T(6)) \times 4 + T(T(T(4))) \\ 2549 &:= -T(T(T(2))) - 5 + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9)) & 2646 &:= T(T(2) + T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(6)) \\ 2550 &:= (-T(2) + 5) \times T(50) & 2648 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(6) + 4)) \times 8 \\ 2552 &:= (T(T(2))^5 - T(T(5)))/T(2) & 2649 &:= -T(T(T(T(2)))) + 64 \times T(9) \\ 2553 &:= -T(2) + T(5 + T(5 + T(3))) & 2652 &:= 2 \times T(T(6) + T(5) \times 2) \\ 2554 &:= -2 + T(5 + T(T(5) - 4)) & 2662 &:= 2 \times (T(T(6))/T(6))^{T(2)} \\ 2555 &:= T(T(T(2)) \times T(5)) - T(55) & 2664 &:= T(T(2 + 6)) \times (-6 + T(4)) \\ 2556 &:= T(-T(2 + 5) + T(T(5)) - T(6)) & 2667 &:= (T(2) + T(T(6) + 6)) \times 7 \\ 2561 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times T(6) - 1 & 2672 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 6)) - T(T(7)) - T(2) \\ 2562 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6/2)) & 2673 &:= T(T(2)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(7)) \times T(3) \\ 2563 &:= -2 + T(5) \times T(6 \times 3) & 2674 &:= T(T(T(-2 + 6))) - T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 2565 &:= T((-2 + 5) \times 6) \times T(5) & 2681 &:= T(T(2) \times T(6)) + T(T(8)) - 1 \\ 2568 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(5) \times T(6)) \times 8 & 2682 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(6)) + T(8)^2 \\ 2569 &:= T(T(2 \times 5)) - 6 + T(T(9)) & 2685 &:= (T(T(2) \times 6) + 8) \times T(5) \\ 2571 &:= T(2) \times 5 + T(71) & 2688 &:= 2 \times T(6) \times 8 \times 8 \\ 2572 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 5) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(2)) & 2691 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(9 - 1))) \\ 2574 &:= 2 \times (-T(T(5) + 7) + T(T(T(4)))) & 2694 &:= -T(T(2)) + 6 \times T(9) \times T(4) \\ 2577 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(T(5) + T(7) + T(7)) & 2695 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(T(T(6) - 9)) - 5 \\ 2579 &:= -2 - T(T(5)) + T(T(7) + T(9)) & 2697 &:= 2 - 6 + T(T(9) + T(7)) \\ 2582 &:= 2 \times (-5 + T(8)^2) & 2701 &:= T(2 + 70 + 1) \\ 2583 &:= (T(2) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)/T(3)) & 2703 &:= 2 + T(70 + 3) \\ 2584 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times (-T(8) + T(T(4))) & 2708 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(70) - 8 \\ 2585 &:= T(25) \times 8 - T(5) & 2709 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 70) \times 9 \\ 2586 &:= -T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 + T(86) & 2712 &:= (T(T(T(2)) \times 7) + 1) \times T(2) \\ 2589 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 5)) + T(T(8) - 9) & 2722 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7) + T(T(2) + T(T(2)))) \\ 2595 &:= (T(2^5) - 9) \times 5 & 2723 &:= (2 \times 7)^{T(2)} - T(T(3)) \\ 2596 &:= T(T(2 \times 5)) + T(T(9)) + T(6) & 2728 &:= (-2 + 7^{T(2)}) \times 8 \\ 2597 &:= T(2 + T(T(5)) - T(9)) - T(T(7)) & 2730 &:= T(T(T(2)) + 7) \times 30 \\ 2598 &:= -2 \times T(5) + T(9 \times 8) & 2734 &:= (2 \times 7)^3 - T(4) \\ 2617 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 6 - 1)) + T(T(7)) & 2736 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(7)) + T(3 + T(6)) \\ 2619 &:= -T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(6 - 1))) - T(9) & 2738 &:= -T(T(2)) + 7^3 \times 8 \\ 2622 &:= T(2 \times 6^2) - T(T(2)) & 2742 &:= 2 \times (-7 + T(T(T(4)) - T(2))) \\ 2624 &:= T(2 \times 6^2) - 4 & 2744 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(74) - T(4) \\ 2625 &:= -T(2) + T(6 + T(T(T(2)) + 5)) & 2745 &:= (2^7 + T(T(4))) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

- 2747** := $-T(T(T(2))) + T(74) - 7$
2748 := $T(2) \times T(7) + 4 \times T(T(8))$
2749 := $T(2) \times T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4))) - 9$
2750 := $T(T(2) + 7) \times 50$
2754 := $-T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7 + 5) - 4)$
2756 := $2 \times T(7 + T(T(5) - 6))$
2758 := $-2 \times T(T(7)) + T(T(T(5)) - T(8))$
2759 := $-T(T(T(2)) + 7) + T(T(T(5)) - T(9))$
2764 := $T(2) \times T(7 \times 6) + T(T(4))$
2768 := $(T(-T(2) + T(7)) + T(6)) \times 8$
2771 := $-T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(77) - 1$
2772 := $-T(2) + T(77 - T(2))$
2773 := $-2 + T(77 - 3)$
2774 := $T(T(2)) - 7 + T(74)$
2775 := $T(2 + 77 - 5)$
2778 := $T(T(2)) + 77 \times T(8)$
2779 := $(-T(T(T(2))) + T(7)) \times (T(T(7)) - 9)$
2781 := $T(T(2)) + T(-7 + 81)$
2782 := $T(2)^7 + T(T(8) - 2)$
2783 := $T(-T(T(2)) + T(7)) \times (8 + 3)$
2784 := $(2 + T(7)) + T(T(8)) \times 4$
2786 := $-T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(7)) \times 8 - T(T(6))$
2787 := $T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(78 - 7)$
2789 := $2 \times 7 + T(T(T(8)) / 9)$
2790 := $(T(2) + T(7)) \times 90$
2793 := $(-T(2) + T(7 + 9)) \times T(T(3))$
2794 := $-T(T(2)) + T(7) \times (T(9) + T(T(4)))$
2795 := $-T(T(2) + 7) + T(-T(9) + T(T(5)))$
2796 := $T(2 \times (T(7) + 9)) + T(6)$
2797 := $T(T(2)) \times T(T(7)) - T(9) + T(T(7))$
2805 := $T(-T(2) + T(8)) \times 05$
2808 := $(-2 + 80) \times T(8)$
2812 := $2 \times T(T(8) + 1) \times 2$
2814 := $2 + T(T(8) + 1) \times 4$
2823 := $2 \times T(8)^2 + T(T(T(3)))$
2824 := $-2^8 + 2 \times T(T(T(4)))$
2825 := $-2^8 + T(T(-T(2) + T(5)))$
2826 := $T(2) \times (T(T(8)) + T(2 + T(6)))$
2828 := $2 \times (T(8^2) - T(T(8)))$
2829 := $-T(T(T(2))) + T(T(8) - T(T(2)) + T(9))$
2835 := $(T(T(2)) + T(T(8) - 3)) \times 5$
2838 := $T(T(2)) \times (T(T(8) - T(3)) + 8)$
2842 := $T(28) \times (T(4) - T(2))$
2845 := $T(-T(2) + T(8 + 4)) - 5$
2847 := $-T(2) + T(-8 + T(T(4)) + T(7))$
2862 := $T(T(2)) \times (T(8) + T(6)^2)$
2872 := $2 \times T(T(8)) + T(T(7 + T(2)))$
2874 := $-T(2) + T(T(8)) + T(T(7 + 4))$
2877 := $(-T(2) + 8 + T(T(7))) \times 7$
2878 := $T(28) \times 7 + T(8)$
2883 := $T(T(2)) + T(T(8)) + T(T(8 + 3))$
2884 := $(T(2 + 8) + T(T(8))) \times 4$
2886 := $T(T(T(T(2)))) - 8 \times T(T(8)) / T(6)$
2887 := $T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7)$
2889 := $T(2) \times (-T(8) - T(8) + T(T(9)))$
2892 := $2 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(9) - T(T(2))))$
2894 := $-T(T(T(2))) + (8 + T(9)) \times T(T(4))$
2895 := $T(2 + 8 \times 9) + T(T(5))$
2898 := $2 \times T(8 + T(9)) + T(8)$
2918 := $T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(9 + 1) - 8$
2922 := $(T(T(2)) \times 9)^2 + T(T(2))$
2923 := $T(-2 + T(9 + T(2))) - 3$
2924 := $-2 + T(T(9 + 2) + T(4))$
2925 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times 9 + T(T(2))) \times T(5)$
2926 := $T(-2 + T(9 - T(2) + 6))$
2927 := $2 + 9 \times T(-T(2) + T(7))$
2928 := $(T(T(T(2))) + T(T(9)) / T(2)) \times 8$
2932 := $T(T(2)) + T(T(9 + 3) - 2)$
2937 := $T(2) \times T(T(9)) - T(3) \times T(7)$
2952 := $T(2) \times T(T(9)) - T(T(5) + 2)$
2953 := $-2^9 + T(5) \times T(T(T(3)))$
2955 := $T(T(T(2))) \times 9 \times T(5) + T(T(5))$
2957 := $T(2) \times T(T(9)) - T(T(5)) - T(7)$
2958 := $(T(T(2)) + T(9)) \times 58$
2961 := $T(T(T(2) + 9)) - T(T(6 - 1))$
2962 := $T(-2 + T(9)) + T(T(6) \times T(2))$
2964 := $(-T(T(2)) + T(9)) \times (T(6) + T(T(4)))$
2965 := $2 \times T(9 \times 6) - 5$
2973 := $2 \times T(T(9)) + T(7 \times T(3))$
2974 := $-2^9 + T(T(7) + T(T(4)))$

$$\begin{aligned} 2975 &:= T(T(2) \times 9 + 7) \times 5 \\ 2976 &:= T(T(T(2) + 9)) - T(-7 + T(6)) \\ 2977 &:= T(2) \times T(9) + T(T(7)) \times 7 \\ 2978 &:= -T(T(2)) \times T(9) + T(T(7)) \times 8 \\ 2982 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(98 - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2985 &:= T(2) \times T(T(9)) - 8 \times T(5) \\ 2988 &:= (2 + T(9) + T(8)) \times T(8) \\ 3003 &:= T(T(T(T(3)))/003) \\ 3033 &:= 30 + T(T(T(T(3)))/3) \\ 3075 &:= -T(3) + T(T(07 + 5)) \\ 3078 &:= -3 + T(078) \\ 3081 &:= T(T(3 + 08 + 1)) \\ 3084 &:= 3 + T(T(08 + 4)) \\ 3102 &:= T(T(3)) + T(T(10 + 2)) \\ 3112 &:= 31 + T(T(12)) \\ 3122 &:= (T(T(T(3 + 1))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 2 \\ 3123 &:= T(T(3)) + T(T(12)) + T(T(3)) \\ 3129 &:= 3 + T(T(12)) + T(9) \\ 3135 &:= (T(T(T(3))) - 1 - T(T(3))) \times T(5) \\ 3136 &:= T(T(3 + 1)) + T(T(T(3) + 6)) \\ 3139 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(1 + T(3 + 9)) \\ 3142 &:= T(3) + (1 + T(T(4)))^2 \\ 3145 &:= T(T(3 + 1)) \times T(T(4)) + T(T(5)) \\ 3163 &:= 3 + T(1 + T(6 + T(3))) \\ 3164 &:= -T(T(T(3) + 1)) + T(T(6) \times 4) \\ 3165 &:= (-T(T(3)) + 1 + T(T(6))) \times T(5) \\ 3166 &:= T(3) + T(1 + T(6 + 6)) \\ 3174 &:= T(3) \times (1 + T(T(7) + 4)) \\ 3185 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(-1 + 8))) \times 5 \\ 3189 &:= 3 \times (T(-1 + 8) + T(T(9))) \\ 3197 &:= T(31) + T(T(9) + T(7)) \\ 3213 &:= T(T(3) \times T(2) - 1) \times T(T(3)) \\ 3224 &:= T(T(T(T(3)))/T(2)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4) \\ 3225 &:= T(T(T(3) + T(T(2))) + 2) - T(5) \\ 3227 &:= -T(T(3)) + 2^{T(2)} \times T(T(7)) \\ 3228 &:= -T(3) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(2)) + 8) \\ 3232 &:= T(T(T(3))) - 2 + T(T(T(T(3)))/T(2)) \\ 3234 &:= -T(3) + T(2 + T(3 \times 4)) \\ 3235 &:= T(T(T(T(3)))/T(2) + 3) - 5 \\ 3237 &:= 3 + 2 \times T(T(T(3))) \times 7 \\ 3252 &:= T(T(T(3)) - T(2)) + T(T(T(5) - T(2))) \\ 3255 &:= -T(T(T(3))) + T(T(-T(2) + T(5)) + 5) \\ 3258 &:= T(3) \times (T(2) + T(5) \times T(8)) \\ 3264 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(2)) \times T(6 + T(4)) \\ 3272 &:= (T(3) + 2) \times (T(T(7)) + T(2)) \\ 3276 &:= T(3)^2 \times T(7 + 6) \\ 3277 &:= T(T(T(3) \times 2)) + 7 \times T(7) \\ 3278 &:= T(3) + (T(2) + T(T(7))) \times 8 \\ 3279 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times 2 \times 7 + T(9) \\ 3282 &:= (3 + T(2)^8)/2 \\ 3283 &:= -T((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(-8 + T(T(3)))) \\ 3285 &:= (-3^2 + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\ 3288 &:= -T(3) + T(2 \times T(8)) + T(T(8)) \\ 3289 &:= -32 + T(T(8) + T(9)) \\ 3297 &:= (T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 9) \times 7 \\ 3298 &:= -T(T(3)) - 2 + T(T(9) + T(8)) \\ 3312 &:= T(T(3 + 3)) + T(T(12)) \\ 3313 &:= T(T(T(3) + T(3))) + 1 + T(T(T(3))) \\ 3315 &:= -T(3) + T(3^{-1+5}) \\ 3321 &:= T((3 \times 3)^2) \times 1 \\ 3324 &:= 3 + T(3 + T(2 + T(4))) \\ 3327 &:= T(3) + T(3 \times 27) \\ 3333 &:= T(T(T(3))) + T(T(3)) + T(T(T(3) + T(3))) \\ 3336 &:= 3 \times T(T(3 \times 3)) + T(T(6)) \\ 3339 &:= -T(T(T(3))) + T(T(3) + T(3 + 9)) \\ 3341 &:= T(T(3)) + T(3^4) - 1 \\ 3342 &:= T(T(3)) + T(3 + T(T(4) + 2)) \\ 3345 &:= 3 \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) - T(T(5)) \\ 3348 &:= 3 \times (T(T(3)) + T(4)) \times T(8) \\ 3355 &:= (T(T(3) \times T(3)) + 5) \times 5 \\ 3357 &:= -3 + T(3 \times 5) \times T(7) \\ 3358 &:= T(T(T(3)))/3 + 5 \times T(T(8)) \\ 3363 &:= T(33) \times 6 - 3 \\ 3366 &:= T(3^3 + 6) \times 6 \\ 3372 &:= T(3) \times T(T(T(T(3)))/7) + T(T(2)) \\ 3375 &:= T(3 \times 3) \times 75 \\ 3382 &:= -T(3 + 3) + T(82) \\ 3384 &:= 3 \times T(T(T(3)) + T(8) - T(4)) \\ 3385 &:= (T(T(T(3)))/T(3) + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\ 3387 &:= -T(T(3)) \times T(T(3)) + T(87) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3388 &:= T(T(T(3)))/3 \times (8 + T(8)) \\ 3391 &:= T(T(T(3))) + T(T(3+9)) + 1 \\ 3396 &:= T(3^3) \times 9 - 6 \\ 3397 &:= -T(3) + T(T(3) \times 9 + T(7)) \\ 3398 &:= T(T(T(3)))/3 + (T(T(9) + T(8))) \\ 3399 &:= -3 + T(3 \times 9) \times 9 \\ 3403 &:= T(T(3) + T(T(4)) + T(T(03))) \\ 3405 &:= (T(T(T(3))) - 4) \times T(05) \\ 3417 &:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(17) \\ 3421 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times 2 - 1 \\ 3422 &:= T(T(3) \times T(4) - 2) \times 2 \\ 3423 &:= (3 \times T(T(4)) - 2) \times T(T(3)) \\ 3424 &:= T(T(3)) + T(4 + T(2 + T(4))) \\ 3431 &:= T(T(3) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3+1))) \\ 3432 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(3) \times 2 \\ 3434 &:= 3 + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(3) + T(T(4))) \\ 3435 &:= T(3^4) - T(3) + T(T(5)) \\ 3436 &:= T(-T(3) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(6))) \\ 3437 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 3 - T(7) \\ 3438 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times 4 \times 3 + T(T(8)) \\ 3441 &:= -3 + 4 \times T(41) \\ 3442 &:= (T(3 + T(T(4))) + T(4)) \times 2 \\ 3444 &:= T(-3 + 44) \times 4 \\ 3445 &:= T(3^4) + 4 + T(T(5)) \\ 3453 &:= T(3 \times 4) + T(5)^3 \\ 3462 &:= 3 \times T(T(4)) \times T(6) - T(2) \\ 3465 &:= T(T(3)) \times (-T(4) + T(6)) \times T(5) \\ 3471 &:= T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4) \times (7 + 1)) \\ 3472 &:= (3 + 4) \times T(T(7) + T(2)) \\ 3474 &:= T(3^4) + T(7 + T(4)) \\ 3475 &:= -T(3) + T(T(T(4)) + T(7)) - 5 \\ 3478 &:= T(T(T(3) + 4) + T(7)) - 8 \\ 3483 &:= -T(T(3) - 4) + T(83) \\ 3484 &:= (-3 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \times 4 \\ 3485 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(4) + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\ 3486 &:= T(-T(T(3) - 4) + 86) \\ 3487 &:= T(T(-T(3) + T(4) + 8)) + T(T(7)) \\ 3489 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(4 + 8) \times T(9) \\ 3492 &:= T(3^4) + T(9 \times 2) \\ 3495 &:= T(3 \times 4) \times T(9) - T(5) \\ 3497 &:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(9) - T(7) \\ 3498 &:= T(T(T(3)) - T(4)) \times (T(9) + 8) \\ 3510 &:= T(T(T(3)) + 5) \times 10 \\ 3515 &:= T(T(3 + 5) + 1) \times 5 \\ 3518 &:= 3 + 5 \times T(1 + T(8)) \\ 3522 &:= T(T(-3 + T(5))) + (T(T(T(2))))^2 \\ 3525 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 25 \\ 3528 &:= (T(3) + T(5))^2 \times 8 \\ 3534 &:= (-T(3) + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(4)) \\ 3542 &:= (T(T(3) + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2 \\ 3543 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times T(5) + T(4 \times 3) \\ 3546 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(5) \times (4 + T(T(6)))) \\ 3549 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(T(5)) + 49) \\ 3552 &:= T(T(T(3))) + T(T(5) + T(5 + T(T(2)))) \\ 3555 &:= T(-T(3 + 5) + T(T(5))) - T(5) \\ 3557 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times T(5) + T(T(5)) - T(7) \\ 3558 &:= 3 - T(5) + T(T(T(5)) - T(8)) \\ 3564 &:= -T(3) + T((T(5) + 6) \times 4) \\ 3565 &:= T(T(-3 + T(5)) + 6) - 5 \\ 3567 &:= -3 + T(56 + T(7)) \\ 3568 &:= (T(T(3)) - 5) \times (T(T(6)) - 8) \\ 3582 &:= T(3) + T(T(T(5)) - T(8)) + T(T(2)) \\ 3583 &:= T(T(3) \times T(5)) - 8^3 \\ 3584 &:= -T(T(3)) + 5 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(4))) \\ 3585 &:= (T(T(3) + T(5)) + 8) \times T(5) \\ 3587 &:= (3 + (T(T(5)) + 8) \times T(7)) \\ 3591 &:= T(T(3)) + T(T(T(5)) - T(9 - 1)) \\ 3597 &:= -T(T(T(3))) + T(59 + T(7)) \\ 3600 &:= T(3) \times 600 \\ 3612 &:= (T(T(T(3)) + T(6))) \times (1 + T(2)) \\ 3624 &:= (3 + T(T(6) \times 2)) \times 4 \\ 3627 &:= (3 + 6) \times (-T(2) + T(T(7))) \\ 3634 &:= T(T(T(3))) + T(T(6) + T(3) + T(T(4))) \\ 3642 &:= T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(6))) + T(T(T(4)) - 2) \\ 3645 &:= -3^6 \times (T(4) - T(5)) \\ 3647 &:= 3 \times T(-6 + T(T(4))) - T(7) \\ 3648 &:= T(3) \times (T(6) + T(T(4))) \times 8 \\ 3649 &:= -T(3) + T(-6 + T(4 + 9)) \\ 3652 &:= -3 + T(-6 + T(T(5) - 2)) \\ 3654 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(6) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3655 &:= T(3 \times 6 \times 5 - 5) & 3837 &:= T(T(T(3))) + T(8) + T(3 \times T(7)) \\ 3657 &:= 3 + (-6 + T(5)) \times T(T(7)) & 3843 &:= T(3) \times T(T(8)) - T(-4 + T(T(3))) \\ 3658 &:= 3 + T(-6 + T(5 + 8)) & 3846 &:= (-T(T(3)) + T(T(8)) - 4) \times 6 \\ 3672 &:= 3 \times T(T(6) + T(7)) - T(2) & 3849 &:= T(T(3)) + T(T(8 + 4)) + 9 \\ 3675 &:= 3 \times T(6 + T(7) + T(5)) & 3855 &:= (T(T(3)) \times T(8) + T(5)) \times 5 \\ 3676 &:= T(T(3)) + T(-6 + T(7 + 6)) & 3856 &:= -T(T(T(3))) - 8 + T(T(5) \times 6) \\ 3688 &:= 3 - T(T(6)) + T(88) & 3858 &:= T(3) \times (-8 - T(5) + T(T(8))) \\ 3696 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(6) + T(T(9)))/6 & 3864 &:= T(T(T(3)) + T(8)) + T(T(T(6) - T(4))) \\ 3699 &:= T(T(3) + T(6)) + T(9 \times 9) & 3865 &:= (-T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 6 - 5 \\ 3724 &:= -3 + T(T(7)) + T(T(2)^4) & 3877 &:= T(T(3)) + T(87) + T(7) \\ 3725 &:= -T(T(T(3)) + T(7)) + T(-T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(5)) & 3879 &:= T(3) + T(87) + T(9) \\ 3727 &:= T(T(3 + 7)) + T(2)^7 & 3882 &:= 3 \times (T(8) \times T(8) - 2) \\ 3729 &:= T(T(3)) + (T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) \times 9 & 3884 &:= 3 \times T(8) \times T(8) - 4 \\ 3732 &:= T(3) \times (T(T(7)) + T(3))^{T(2)} & 3885 &:= (T(38) + T(8)) \times 5 \\ 3735 &:= -T(3) + T(T(7 + T(3)) - 5) & 3886 &:= T(-3 + 88) + T(T(6)) \\ 3738 &:= T(3 \times T(7)) + T(T(3)) \times 8 & 3888 &:= 3 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(8)) - T(8)) \\ 3739 &:= 3 + T(73) + T(T(9)) & 3898 &:= T(3) \times T(T(8)) - 98 \\ 3741 &:= T(T(T(3)) + T(7 + 4) - 1) & 3906 &:= T(T(3)) \times (-T(9) + T(T(06))) \\ 3745 &:= T(3 \times T(7)) + T(T(4)) + T(T(5)) & 3909 &:= -T(T(T(3))) + T(90) + T(9) \\ 3746 &:= T(3 \times T(7)) - T(T(4)) + T(T(6)) & 3913 &:= -3 + T(91 - 3) \\ 3751 &:= (3 + T(7)) \times (T(T(5)) + 1) & 3916 &:= T(3 + 91 - 6) \\ 3759 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(7) \times T(5) \times 9 & 3922 &:= T(3) + T(T(9) \times 2 - 2) \\ 3762 &:= (-T(3) + T(7)) \times T(T(6) - T(2)) & 3927 &:= T(3 \times (9 + 2)) \times 7 \\ 3773 &:= T(T(T(3))) - T(7) + T(T(7) \times 3) & 3942 &:= T(3) \times (-9 + T(T(4 \times 2))) \\ 3774 &:= -T(3) - (T(7) - T(T(7))) \times T(4) & 3944 &:= (T(3) + T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times 4 \\ 3775 &:= T(T(T(3) + 7)) - T(T(7)) - 5 & 3948 &:= T(3) \times (T(9 \times 4) - 8) \\ 3784 &:= T(37) + T(T(8 + 4)) & 3951 &:= 3 \times (-9 + T(51)) \\ 3792 &:= (3 - T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(2)) & 3954 &:= -T(T(T(3))) + 9 \times T(T(T(5)))/4 \\ 3795 &:= 3 \times T(7) \times T(9) + T(5) & 3960 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 60 \\ 3797 &:= T(T(T(3))) + T(79) + T(T(7)) & 3963 &:= T(T(3)) \times 9 \times T(6) - T(3) \\ 3798 &:= T(3 + T(7)) \times 9 - T(T(8)) & 3964 &:= 3 + T(T(9)) + T(T(6) + T(T(4))) \\ 3807 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(80 + 7) & 3966 &:= -3 + 9 \times T(6) \times T(6) \\ 3816 &:= (T(3) + T(T(8) - 1)) \times 6 & 3968 &:= T((T(T(T(3))) - T(9))/6) \times 8 \\ 3819 &:= T(T(3) + 81) - 9 & 3969 &:= T(-3 + 9) \times T(6) \times 9 \\ 3822 &:= T(T(T(3)) + T(8 + T(2))) - T(T(2)) & 3970 &:= T(T(3) \times 9) + T(70) \\ 3824 &:= T(T(T(3)) + T(8 + T(2))) - 4 & 3975 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(-9 + T(7)) - T(5) \\ 3825 &:= -3 + T(82 + 5) & 3978 &:= (T(3) + T(9)) \times 78 \\ 3828 &:= T(-3 + 82 + 8) & 3984 &:= T(-3 + T(9)) + T(T(8 + 4)) \\ 3834 &:= T(3) + T(83 + 4) & 3988 &:= (-3 + 9) \times T(T(8)) - 8 \\ 3835 &:= T(T(T(T(3)) - 8)) - T(T(T(3)) + 5) & 3993 &:= -T(3 \times 9) + T(93) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3996 &:= T(3 \times 9 + 9) \times 6 \\ 3997 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(9 + 9) + T(T(7)) \\ 4065 &:= (40 + T(T(6))) \times T(5) \\ 4075 &:= T(4) \times T(T(07)) + T(5) \\ 4092 &:= T(T(4) \times 09) - T(2) \\ 4095 &:= T(40 + T(9) + 5) \\ 4099 &:= 4 + T(T(09) + T(9)) \\ 4125 &:= T(T(4)) \times (-1 + T(T(2))) \times T(5) \\ 4131 &:= -T(T(4)) + T(T(13 \times 1)) \\ 4134 &:= (4 - 1) \times T(-3 + T(T(4))) \\ 4136 &:= 4 \times (-1 + T(T(3 + 6))) \\ 4164 &:= (T(T(T(4) - 1)) + 6) \times 4 \\ 4175 &:= -T(4) - 1 + T(T(T(7) - T(5))) \\ 4176 &:= -T(4) + T(T(-1 - 7 + T(6))) \\ 4178 &:= T(T(-4 + 17)) - 8 \\ 4182 &:= -4 + T(T(-1 + 8 + T(T(2)))) \\ 4183 &:= T(T(4 + 1 + 8)) - 3 \\ 4185 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(1 + T(8))) \times 5 \\ 4186 &:= T(4 + 1 + 86) \\ 4190 &:= 4 + T(1 + 90) \\ 4191 &:= 4 + 1 + T(91) \\ 4192 &:= T(T(T(4)) + T(-1 + 9)) + T(T(2)) \\ 4194 &:= T(T(4)) - 1 + T(T(9)) \times 4 \\ 4196 &:= T(4) + T(T(19 - 6)) \\ 4215 &:= T(T(T(4) + T(2)) - 1) + T(T(5)) \\ 4216 &:= 4^{T(T(2))} + T(T(-1 + 6)) \\ 4218 &:= (4 + 2) \times T(1 + T(8)) \\ 4222 &:= T(T(T(4) + T(2))) + T(2 + T(T(2))) \\ 4223 &:= -T(T(4)) + T(T(2 + T(T(T(2))))/3) \\ 4224 &:= T(42) + T(T(2)^4) \\ 4225 &:= (T(4) + T(2)) \times T(25) \\ 4228 &:= T(T(T(4) + T(2))) + T(T(2)) + T(8) \\ 4229 &:= T(T(T(4) + T(2))) - 2 + T(9) \\ 4232 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))/3 - T(2) \\ 4233 &:= (T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(3))/3 \\ 4235 &:= T(T(4))^2 \times T(T(3))/T(5) \\ 4236 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3) + 6)) \\ 4238 &:= T(T(4)) - T(2) + T(T(T(T(3)) - 8)) \\ 4239 &:= (T(T(4) \times T(2)) + T(3)) \times 9 \\ 4241 &:= T(T(4)) + T(T(-2 + T(4 + 1))) \\ 4243 &:= T(T(4)) + 2 + T(T(T(4) + 3)) \\ 4246 &:= T(T(T(4) + T(2))) + T(4) \times 6 \\ 4252 &:= T(T(T(4) + T(2))) + T(5 + T(T(2))) \\ 4256 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 56 \\ 4257 &:= -T(4 + 2) + T(T(T(5)) - T(7)) \\ 4258 &:= T(4) + (-2 + T(T(5))) \times T(8) \\ 4263 &:= (-T(T(4) - T(2)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 4265 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(2 + 6) \times T(T(5))) \\ 4267 &:= 4 + T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(7)) \\ 4269 &:= T(4 \times (2 + T(6))) - 9 \\ 4282 &:= T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 4286 &:= T(4)^2 + T(T(-8 + T(6))) \\ 4288 &:= 4 \times (T(28) + T(T(8))) \\ 4289 &:= -4 + (T(2) \times T(8 + T(9))) \\ 4312 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3))) \times 12 \\ 4323 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(2))) \times 3 \\ 4324 &:= 4 \times T(T(3)^2 + T(4)) \\ 4326 &:= (-T(4) + T(3)^{T(2)}) \times T(6) \\ 4327 &:= 4^{T(3)} + T(T(2) \times 7) \\ 4330 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(3) \times T(30) \\ 4333 &:= 4^{T(3)} + T(3) + T(T(T(3))) \\ 4334 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times 3 - T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4)) \\ 4335 &:= (T(T(4)) + 3 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) \\ 4345 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(3)) \times 4 - 5) \\ 4348 &:= 4 \times (T(3) + T(T(4) + T(8))) \\ 4350 &:= T(4) \times T(-T(T(3)) + 50) \\ 4352 &:= -4 + T(T(3) + 5)^2 \\ 4355 &:= -T(T(4)) + T(T(3)) \times T(5 + T(5)) \\ 4356 &:= T(-T(4) + T(T(3))) \times T(5 + 6) \\ 4362 &:= (T(T(4) + T(T(3))) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 4365 &:= (T(4) \times T(3) + T(T(6))) \times T(5) \\ 4367 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times 3 - T(-6 + T(7)) \\ 4368 &:= T(T(4) + 3) \times 6 \times 8 \\ 4371 &:= T(T(T(4)) + 37 + 1) \\ 4378 &:= (-T(4) + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7)) - 8) \\ 4379 &:= (T(4) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(7) - 9) \\ 4385 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 3 - T(T(8))) \times 5 \\ 4386 &:= (-T(4) + T(38)) \times 6 \\ 4388 &:= -T(T(T(4))) + T(38) \times 8 \\ 4392 &:= T(4 \times T(T(3)) + 9) + T(T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4395 &:= -T(T(4)) \times 3 + T(95) \\ 4396 &:= 4^{T(3)} + T(T(9) - T(6)) \\ 4398 &:= 4 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(9))) - T(T(8)) \\ 4412 &:= -T(4) + T(T(T(4) + 1)) \times 2 \\ 4422 &:= T(T(4 + 4 + T(2))) \times 2 \\ 4425 &:= T(4 + T(T(4))) / T(T(2)) \times T(5) \\ 4427 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4))) \times T(2) - T(7) \\ 4432 &:= T(4) + T(T(-T(4) + T(T(3)))) \times 2 \\ 4437 &:= T(T(4) \times T(4) - T(3)) - T(7) \\ 4442 &:= 4^4 + T(T(T(4) + T(2))) \\ 4443 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(T(4)))) - 4 \times 3 \\ 4445 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(4)) - T(T(5)) \\ 4446 &:= T(T(T(T(4))) / T(T(4)) + T(4)) \times 6 \\ 4455 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(-4 + T(5)) + T(5)) \\ 4462 &:= T(T(4) \times T(4) - 6) - T(2) \\ 4463 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4)) + (T(6))) - 3 \\ 4465 &:= T(T(T(4) + 4) - 6 - 5) \\ 4466 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(4) + 66) \\ 4468 &:= 4 \times (T(46) + T(8)) \\ 4469 &:= 4 + T(T(T(4)) - 6 + T(9)) \\ 4473 &:= (4 \times T(T(4)) - 7) \times T(T(3)) \\ 4476 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(4) + T(76) \\ 4482 &:= (-T(4) + T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) \times T(2) \\ 4484 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(48)) \times 4 \\ 4485 &:= (T(T(-4 + T(4))) + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\ 4488 &:= (-4 + T(T(4))) \times 88 \\ 4495 &:= -T(4) - T(T(4)) + T(95) \\ 4497 &:= -4^4 + T(97) \\ 4526 &:= -T(T(4) + T(5)) + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(6)) \\ 4532 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(5 + T(3)))) \times 2 \\ 4536 &:= (T(4 \times 5) + T(3)) \times T(6) \\ 4543 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) - 43 \\ 4545 &:= T(T(T(4)) - T(5) + T(T(4))) - T(5) \\ 4555 &:= T(-T(4) - T(5) + T(T(5))) - 5 \\ 4556 &:= -4 + T(5 + T(5)) \times 6 \\ 4575 &:= T(4 + T(-T(5) + T(7))) + T(5) \\ 4584 &:= (4 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 4 \\ 4585 &:= T(T(4) + T(T(5)) - T(8)) + T(T(5)) \\ 4589 &:= -T(T(T(4))) + T(5) + T(T(8)) \times 9 \\ 4595 &:= (4 - T(T(5)) + T(T(9))) \times 5 \\ 4596 &:= -T(T(4)) - 5 + T(96) \\ 4602 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - 6) \times T(02) \\ 4615 &:= (4 \times T(T(6)) - 1) \times 5 \\ 4616 &:= -4 + T(T(6)) \times (-1 + T(6)) \\ 4632 &:= (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(3)) \times 2 \\ 4634 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times 3 - 4 \\ 4635 &:= (T(T(4)) \times 6 - T(T(3))) \times T(5) \\ 4638 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times T(-T(3) + 8) \\ 4639 &:= T(T(T(4))) - 6 + 3 \times T(T(9)) \\ 4641 &:= (-T(4) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4 - 1)) \\ 4642 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(6) + T(T(T(4) + 2)) \\ 4644 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times 4 - T(T(T(4))) \\ 4646 &:= -T(4) + T((6 + T(4)) \times 6) \\ 4648 &:= T(4 \times 6 \times 4) - 8 \\ 4662 &:= (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(6)) \times 2 \\ 4675 &:= T(T(4)) \times (-6 + T(T(7) - T(5))) \\ 4678 &:= T(4) + 6 + 7 \times T(T(8)) \\ 4679 &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(6) + T(79) \\ 4682 &:= (-T(4) + T(68)) \times 2 \\ 4683 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(6) \times 8) \times T(T(3)) \\ 4687 &:= (4 + T(6) + T(T(8))) \times 7 \\ 4690 &:= T(T(T(4)) - T(6)) + T(90) \\ 4692 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(6) + T(9)) \times T(2) \\ 4694 &:= -T(T(T(4))) + 6 \times T(T(9)) + 4 \\ 4696 &:= T(T(T(4)) - 6 + T(9)) + T(T(6)) \\ 4697 &:= (-T(T(T(4))) + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times 7 \\ 4698 &:= -T(-4 + T(6)) + T(98) \\ 4704 &:= 4 \times T(-7 + T(T(04))) \\ 4717 &:= T(T(4)) + 7 \times T(T(1 + 7)) \\ 4722 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + T(7) + T(T(2))) \times T(2) \\ 4725 &:= (-T(4) + T(T(7) - T(2))) \times T(5) \\ 4726 &:= T(4) \times T(T(7)) + T(T(2 + 6)) \\ 4728 &:= T(4) \times T(T(7)) + 2 + T(T(8)) \\ 4729 &:= 4 + T(7 \times 2) \times T(9) \\ 4732 &:= (T(T(T(4)) + 7 \times T(3))) - T(T(T(2))) \\ 4733 &:= -T(T(4)) + T(7) \times T(3 \times T(3)) \\ 4738 &:= T(T(4)) + 7 \times (3 + T(T(8))) \\ 4743 &:= (T(T(4) + 7)) \times (T(4) + T(T(3))) \\ 4744 &:= (T(4) + T(-7 + T(T(4)))) \times 4 \\ 4746 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(7) - T(4))) \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4749 &:= -4 + T(7 + T(4) \times 9) & 4927 &:= T(T(4)) + (9 + T(2)) \times T(T(7)) \\ 4752 &:= (-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times (T(5) - T(2)) & 4935 &:= -T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \\ 4753 &:= T(T(T(4) + T(7 - 5)) + T(3)) & 4937 &:= -T(T(T(4))) + 9 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(7) \\ 4759 &:= -T(4) - T(T(7)) + 5 \times T(T(9)) & 4942 &:= (T(T(4)) \times T(9) - 4) \times 2 \\ 4762 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(7)) \times 6) \times 2 & 4943 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(-9 + T(T(4) + 3)) \\ 4763 &:= T(4) + T(T(7 + 6) + T(3)) & 4945 &:= T(T(4)) \times 9 \times T(4) - 5 \\ 4779 &:= T(-T(4) + T(7)) \times T(7) - 9 & 4946 &:= -4 + T(T(T(9 - 4)) - T(6)) \\ 4780 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(7) + T(80) & 4962 &:= (T(T(4)) \times T(9) + 6) \times 2 \\ 4782 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(7)) \times 8 - T(T(2)) & 4965 &:= T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5))) \\ 4784 &:= -4 + T(7) \times T(8 + T(4)) & 4972 &:= (T(4) \times T(T(9)) - T(T(7)))/2 \\ 4785 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-7 + T(8))/5 & 4973 &:= -T(T(T(4))) + T(9) + T(7) \times T(T(T(3))) \\ 4788 &:= (T(T(4)) + 78) \times T(8) & 4985 &:= (-T(4) + T(T(9)) - T(8)) \times 5 \\ 4792 &:= 4 + T(7) \times T(9 \times 2) & 4987 &:= T(4) + (T(9) + T(T(8))) \times 7 \\ 4795 &:= T(T(T(4))) + 7 \times T(T(9) - T(5)) & 4992 &:= (T(T(4)) + 9) \times T(9 + T(2)) \\ 4796 &:= -T(T(4)) + T(T(T(-7 + 9))) \times T(T(6)) & 4995 &:= (-4 \times 9 + T(T(9))) \times 5 \\ 4832 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(8) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(2))) & 4999 &:= 49 + T(99) \\ 4833 &:= (-T(4) - 8 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(3))) & 5112 &:= T(5 + T(11)) \times 2 \\ 4837 &:= (4 + T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) \times 7 & 5133 &:= T(T(T(5 - 1)) + 3) \times 3 \\ 4842 &:= -T(4) + T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4) + T(2))) & 5147 &:= 5 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) - T(7) \\ 4847 &:= -4 + T(T(8) + T(T(4)) + 7) & 5159 &:= -T(5) - 1 + 5 \times T(T(9)) \\ 4848 &:= 4 \times (T(8) + T(48)) & 5166 &:= (T(5) + T(T(1 \times 6))) \times T(6) \\ 4851 &:= T(T(T(4)) - 8 + 51) & 5175 &:= 5 \times T(T(1 - 7 + T(5))) \\ 4852 &:= T(T(T(4)) + T(8)) + T(T(5 + T(2))) & 5195 &:= (5 - 1 + T(T(9))) \times 5 \\ 4855 &:= T(T(4)) + 8 \times 5 \times T(T(5)) & 5196 &:= 5 \times T(T((1 \times 9))) + T(6) \\ 4859 &:= -T(T(4)) + (T(T(8)) - T(T(5))) \times 9 & 5226 &:= T(T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(2 + T(6)) \\ 4863 &:= 4 + 8 + T(T(6)) \times T(T(3)) & 5235 &:= (T(T(5)) - 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) \\ 4866 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(8) \times T(6)) \times 6 & 5236 &:= T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(3)))/6 \\ 4871 &:= (4 + 8) \times T(T(7)) - 1 & 5244 &:= (T(5) + T(T(2))^4) \times 4 \\ 4872 &:= T(T(T(4)) + T(8) + 7) + T(T(T(2))) & 5248 &:= (5 + T(2)) \times (-T(4) + T(T(8))) \\ 4875 &:= T(4 \times 8 - 7) \times T(5) & 5250 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 50 \\ 4882 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 8 - T(T(2)) & 5259 &:= -T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(5)) \times T(9) \\ 4884 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 8 - 4 & 5262 &:= T(5) \times T(26) - T(2) \\ 4888 &:= T(T(T(4)) + T(8)) + T(T(8)) + T(8) & 5265 &:= 5 \times T(2) \times T(T(6) + 5) \\ 4889 &:= T(T(T(4)) + T(8)) + T(-8 + T(9)) & 5272 &:= (T(5) - 2) \times T(T(7)) - T(T(2)) \\ 4892 &:= T(T(4)) \times 89 - T(2) & 5274 &:= (T(5) - 2) \times T(T(7)) - 4 \\ 4895 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(8))/9 + T(5)) & 5280 &:= T(5 + T(T(2))) \times 80 \\ 4897 &:= 4 \times T(8) + T(97) & 5287 &:= -5 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(8) \times 7 \\ 4898 &:= T(T(4)) - 8 + T(98) & 5288 &:= (-T(5)/T(2) + T(T(8))) \times 8 \\ 4914 &:= -T(4 + 9) \times (1 - T(T(4))) & 5292 &:= T(T(T(5) - T(2))) + T(T(9 + 2)) \\ 4924 &:= (T(49) + T(T(2))) \times 4 & 5295 &:= T(5)/T(2) \times T(T(9)) + T(T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5297 &:= 5 + T(T(T(2))) \times 9 \times T(7) & 5726 &:= T(T(-T(5) + T(7))) + T(T(T(-2 + 6))) \\ 5313 &:= T(T(5) + T(3) + 1) \times T(T(3)) & 5733 &:= (-T(5) + T(7)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 5324 &:= (5 + T(3))^{T(2)} \times 4 & 5745 &:= -T(5) + (-7 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(5)) \\ 5328 &:= (5 - 3)^{T(2)} \times T(T(8)) & 5747 &:= T(5) \times 7 \times T(T(4)) - T(7) \\ 5368 &:= (5 + T(36)) \times 8 & 5775 &:= T(5) \times 77 \times 5 \\ 5375 &:= 5^3 \times (T(7) + T(5)) & 5795 &:= (-5 + T(7) \times T(T(9)))/5 \\ 5382 &:= (T(T(5) + T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(2)) & 5796 &:= T(-5 + T(7)) \times T(T(9 - 6)) \\ 5385 &:= (T(5 + T(T(3))) + 8) \times T(5) & 5824 &:= (T(T(5)) - 8) \times (-T(2) + T(T(4))) \\ 5395 &:= T(5 \times 3) \times T(9) - 5 & 5832 &:= ((-5 + 8) \times T(3))^{T(2)} \\ 5415 &:= T(T(5)) \times T(T(4) - 1) + T(5) & 5845 &:= T(T(5)) \times T(8) + T(T(T(4))) - T(5) \\ 5423 &:= 5 + T(42) \times T(3) & 5848 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times 8 \\ 5432 &:= (T(T(5) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 2 & 5852 &:= T(T(5 + 8) - T(5)) \times 2 \\ 5433 &:= T(T(5)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 3 & 5865 &:= 5 \times T(8 \times 6) - T(5) \\ 5434 &:= (T(5) + 4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) & 5868 &:= (-5 + 8 \times T(6)) \times T(8) \\ 5445 &:= T(54) \times T(T(4))/T(5) & 5894 &:= (-5 + T(T(8))) \times 9 - T(T(4)) \\ 5448 &:= (T(5) + T(T(4 + 4))) \times 8 & 5895 &:= (T(5) + T(T(8) - 9)) \times T(5) \\ 5475 &:= T(5) \times (-T(T(4)) + T(7) \times T(5)) & 5922 &:= (-T(T(5)) + T(T(9 + T(2)))) \times 2 \\ 5485 &:= T(5 + T(T(4))) + T(85) & 5925 &:= T(T(5) + T(9)) + T(T(T(2)) \times T(5)) \\ 5487 &:= (T(5) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(8)) \times 7 & 5928 &:= T(-5 + T(9) - 2) \times 8 \\ 5488 &:= 5 \times 4 + T(T(8)) \times 8 & 5929 &:= (T(T(T(5) - 9)))^2/9 \\ 5497 &:= -T(5) + 4 \times T(T(9) + 7) & 5949 &:= (-5 + T(9 \times 4)) \times 9 \\ 5523 &:= T(T(5))/5 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(3)) & 5955 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(9) \times (T(T(5)) + T(5)) \\ 5525 &:= T(5 \times 5) \times (2 + T(5)) & 5976 &:= T(5) \times (-9 + T(T(7))) + T(6) \\ 5534 &:= T(T(5))/5 \times T(T(T(3))) - T(4) & 5982 &:= -T(5) + 9 \times T(T(8)) + T(2) \\ 5535 &:= (T(T(5)) \times 5 - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) & 5983 &:= -5 + 9 \times T(T(8)) - T(3) \\ 5537 &:= T(T(5))/5 \times T(T(T(3))) - 7 & 5995 &:= 5 \times T(T(9)) + T(T(9) - 5) \\ 5544 &:= T(T(5))/5 \times T(T(-4 + T(4))) & 5998 &:= -5 + 9 + 9 \times T(T(8)) \\ 5568 &:= (T(T(5) + T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times 8 & 5999 &:= 5 + 9 \times T(T(9) - 9) \\ 5597 &:= (5 + T(T(5))) \times T(9) - T(7) & 6125 &:= T((6 + 1)^2) \times 5 \\ 5616 &:= T(5 + T(6)) \times 16 & 6132 &:= (61 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 5625 &:= 5 \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(2))) \times 5 & 6135 &:= (T(T(6 + 1)) + 3) \times T(5) \\ 5640 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(6)) \times 40 & 6154 &:= -6 + (-1 + 5) \times T(T(T(4))) \\ 5655 &:= 5 \times T(T(6)) \times 5 - T(T(5)) & 6162 &:= T(T(6 \times 1 + 6)) \times 2 \\ 5658 &:= (T(5) + T(T(6))) \times (T(5) + 8) & 6192 &:= -6 \times (1 - T(T(9)) + 2) \\ 5664 &:= (5 + T(T(6))) \times 6 \times 4 & 6194 &:= 6 \times (-1 + T(T(9))) - T(4) \\ 5665 &:= T(5) \times T(T(6) + 6) - 5 & 6195 &:= 6 \times T(T(1 \times 9)) - T(5) \\ 5676 &:= T(T(5) + T(6) + 7) \times 6 & 6197 &:= 6 \times (-1 + T(T(9))) - 7 \\ 5688 &:= (T(T(5) - 6) + T(T(8))) \times 8 & 6216 &:= (T(T(6 + T(2))) + 1) \times 6 \\ 5720 &:= (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 20 & 6222 &:= (-6 + T(2^{T(T(2))})) \times T(2) \\ 5724 &:= T(T(-T(5) + T(7))) - 2 + T(T(T(4))) & 6225 &:= 6 \times T(T(T(2)^2)) + T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6227 &:= T(T(T(T(6))/T(T(T(2)))) \times T(2) - T(T(7))) \\ 6228 &:= (T(T(6) - T(2)) + 2) \times T(8) \\ 6229 &:= T(6) - 2 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(9)) \\ 6234 &:= 6 \times (T(T(T(2) \times 3)) + 4) \\ 6237 &:= T(T(6)) \times (2 - 3 + T(7)) \\ 6244 &:= (T(T(6/2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 4 \\ 6249 &:= (-T(6) + T(T(2)) \times (T(4) + T(T(9)))) \\ 6258 &:= 6 \times (T(T(2) \times T(5)) + 8) \\ 6272 &:= (6 + 2) \times T(7)^2 \\ 6279 &:= T(T(6)) + T(2) \times T(7 \times 9) \\ 6285 &:= T(6) \times T(T(2) \times 8) - T(5) \\ 6288 &:= 6 + T(T(2) + T(8)) \times 8 \\ 6295 &:= T(6) \times T(-T(T(T(2)))) + T(9) - 5 \\ 6300 &:= T(6) \times 300 \\ 6321 &:= T(T(6) + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(2)) + 1) \\ 6324 &:= T(T(T(6))/3) + T(T(2)^4) \\ 6327 &:= 6 + T(T(T(3)) \times 2) \times 7 \\ 6336 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3 \times 3))) \times 6 \\ 6342 &:= T(6) \times (T(T(3) \times 4) + 2) \\ 6363 &:= T(6) \times (3 + T(T(6) + 3)) \\ 6374 &:= (T(T(6)) - 3) \times T(7) - T(4) \\ 6375 &:= T(T(6 + T(3)) - T(7)) \times 5 \\ 6377 &:= (T(T(6)) - 3) \times T(7) - 7 \\ 6384 &:= T(6) \times (T(3 \times 8) + 4) \\ 6391 &:= T(T(6)) \times T(T(3)) + T(T(9 + 1)) \\ 6399 &:= (T(6 \times T(3)) + T(9)) \times 9 \\ 6426 &:= T(T(6) - 4) \times 2 \times T(6) \\ 6435 &:= T(6 + 4) \times (-3 + T(T(5))) \\ 6437 &:= -T(6) - T(4) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(7) \\ 6447 &:= -T(6) + T(T(-4 + T(4))) \times T(7) \\ 6453 &:= (6 + T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) \times 3 \\ 6459 &:= T(6) \times T(T(T(4)))/5 - 9 \\ 6468 &:= T(6) \times (T(4 \times 6) + 8) \\ 6472 &:= -6 + T(4) + T(7) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 6474 &:= 6 \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7)) - T(T(4))) \\ 6480 &:= (6 - 4) \times T(80) \\ 6483 &:= 6 \times T(T(4) + T(8)) - 3 \\ 6484 &:= -T(T(6)) + T(4) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(4)) \\ 6486 &:= 6 \times T(4 + T(8) + 6) \\ 6489 &:= (T(6 + 4) + T(T(8))) \times 9 \\ 6492 &:= (T(T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(9))) \times 2 \\ 6496 &:= (T(T(6)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(9)) \times 6 \\ 6517 &:= T(6) + (T(5) + 1) \times T(T(7)) \\ 6524 &:= -T(6) + 5 \times (-T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 6525 &:= T(T(6) + 5 + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ 6528 &:= T(T(6) - 5) \times T(T(2)) \times 8 \\ 6534 &:= -T(T(6)) + (T(T(5)) + 3) \times T(T(4)) \\ 6545 &:= (-T(6 + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5 \\ 6549 &:= -6 + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(4)) - T(9)) \\ 6552 &:= (6 + T(T(5))) \times 52 \\ 6567 &:= -T(6) + T(T(5)) + T(T(6)) \times T(7) \\ 6573 &:= T(6) \times 5 + T(7) \times T(T(T(3))) \\ 6574 &:= T(-T(6) + T(T(5))) + T(T(7)) \times 4 \\ 6579 &:= -T(T(6) + T(5)) + 7 \times T(T(9)) \\ 6594 &:= -6 + T(T(5)) \times (T(9) + T(4)) \\ 6615 &:= T(6) \times T(6) \times 15 \\ 6624 &:= 6 \times T(T(6) + 2) \times 4 \\ 6633 &:= T(66) \times (-3 + T(3)) \\ 6642 &:= (T(T(6) + 6 \times T(4))) \times 2 \\ 6645 &:= T(6 \times 6) \times T(4) - T(5) \\ 6648 &:= -6 - 6 + T(4) \times T(T(8)) \\ 6654 &:= -6 + T(T(6) + T(5)) \times T(4) \\ 6657 &:= (T(T(6)) + 6 \times T(T(5))) \times 7 \\ 6678 &:= -T(6) + T(T(6)) \times (-7 + T(8)) \\ 6696 &:= 6 \times (T(T(6)) - T(9)) \times 6 \\ 6699 &:= T(T(6)) \times (6 + T(T(9))/T(9)) \\ 6721 &:= T(T(6)) \times T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1) \\ 6727 &:= T(T(6)) \times T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(7) \\ 6732 &:= T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(3) \times 2 \\ 6742 &:= -6 + T(7) \times (T(4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 6744 &:= 6 \times (-T(T(7)) - T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 6754 &:= -T(T(6)) + (7 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 6756 &:= 6 \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(5)) \times 6) \\ 6762 &:= (T(T(6)) + T(7 + 6)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 6783 &:= T(6) \times (T(T(7)) - 83) \\ 6804 &:= T(6) \times T(80)/T(4) \\ 6819 &:= -T(6) + T(8) \times T(19) \\ 6825 &:= T(6) \times T((8 - T(2)) \times 5) \\ 6828 &:= T(T(6)) + T(8) + T(2)^8 \\ 6843 &:= T(T(6) + T(8)) \times 4 + T(T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6844 &:= T(6 \times 8 + T(4)) \times 4 & 7332 &:= (T(T(7) + T(T(3))) - 3) \times T(T(2)) \\ 6855 &:= (T(6) + T(8)) \times T(T(5)) + T(5) & 7335 &:= (T(T(7) + T(T(3)))) \times T(3) - T(5) \\ 6864 &:= -6 + (T(T(8)) + T(6)) \times T(4) & 7343 &:= -7 - (-T(3) \times T(T(T(4)) - T(3))) \\ 6873 &:= -T(T(6) + T(8)) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(3)) & 7350 &:= 7 \times T(T(3)) \times 50 \\ 6888 &:= (T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) - T(8)) \times 8 & 7353 &:= (T(T(7)) \times T(3) + T(5)) \times 3 \\ 6891 &:= T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) \times (9 + 1) & 7355 &:= -T(T(7)) + T(3)^5 - T(5) \\ 6894 &:= 6 + 8 \times T(T(9) - 4) & 7362 &:= (T(T(7)) + 3) \times (T(6) - T(2)) \\ 6925 &:= T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(T(2)))) - 5 & 7365 &:= 7 \times T(T(3 + 6)) + T(T(5)) \\ 6948 &:= (T(6) \times 9 + 4) \times T(8) & 7391 &:= 7 \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(9))) - 1 \\ 6954 &:= 6 \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(5)) + 4) & 7392 &:= T(7) \times (T(3) \times T(9)) - T(T(2)) \\ 6966 &:= 6 \times (T(T(9)) + 6 \times T(6)) & 7394 &:= -T(T(7)) + T(39) \times T(4) \\ 6972 &:= (-6 + T(T(9))) \times 7 - T(T(T(T(2)))) & 7395 &:= (T(7) + T(T(T(3)) + 9)) \times T(5) \\ 6978 &:= -T(T(6)) + T(T(9)) \times 7 - T(8) & 7410 &:= (T(T(7) + T(4))) \times 10 \\ 6987 &:= -6 + (T(T(9)) - T(8)) \times 7 & 7420 &:= T(7) \times (T(T(4)) + T(20)) \\ 6993 &:= T(6) \times (-T(9) + T(9 \times 3)) & 7425 &:= T((T(7) - T(4)) \times T(2)) \times 5 \\ 7112 &:= T(7) \times (1 + T(1 + T(T(T(2)))))) & 7427 &:= T(7 \times T(4)) \times T(2) - T(7) \\ 7129 &:= T(7) \times T(1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(9) & 7428 &:= (T(7) + 4) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(8) \\ 7182 &:= 7 \times T(18) \times T(T(2)) & 7435 &:= T(7 \times T(4)) + T(-T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \\ 7189 &:= 7 \times (-1 \times 8 + T(T(9))) & 7438 &:= T(7) + T(4) \times T(38) \\ 7196 &:= 7 \times (-1 + T(T(9)) - 6) & 7442 &:= (T(T(7)) \times T(T(4)) - 4) / T(2) \\ 7203 &:= 7^{T(2)} \times T(T(03)) & 7443 &:= (T(7 \times T(4)) - 4) \times 3 \\ 7223 &:= (T(7) + T(2)) \times (2 + T(T(T(3)))) & 7452 &:= (-T(7) + T(T(4)) \times T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 7224 &:= T(7 \times T(T(2))) \times 2 \times 4 & 7455 &:= T(7 \times T(4)) \times T(5) / 5 \\ 7245 &:= 7 \times T(T(2) \times T(4) + T(5)) & 7462 &:= T(T(7)) + (4 \times T(6))^2 \\ 7248 &:= T(7) \times T(T(T(2))) + (T(4) \times T(T(8))) & 7482 &:= T(T(7) + T(T(4))) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 7252 &:= (T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times T((5 + 2)) & 7483 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(8)) - T(T(T(3))) \\ 7259 &:= 7 \times (2 + T(5 \times 9)) & 7485 &:= (-7 + T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) \times 5 \\ 7266 &:= (T(T(7) - T(2)) + T(6)) \times T(6) & 7514 &:= -T(T(7)) + T(T(5)) \times T(1 + T(4)) \\ 7273 &:= (T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times T(7) + T(T(3)) & 7532 &:= -T(7) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(2) \\ 7279 &:= T(7) + T(T(2)) + 7 \times T(T(9)) & 7548 &:= T(7) + 5 \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) \\ 7280 &:= T(7 + T(T(2))) \times 80 & 7567 &:= T(T(T(7) - 5) / 6) \times 7 \\ 7288 &:= (T(7 \times T(T(2))) + 8) \times 8 & 7568 &:= T(7 + T(5) + T(6)) \times 8 \\ 7293 &:= 7 \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + T(3) & 7595 &:= 7 \times (T(T(5)) \times 9 + 5) \\ 7294 &:= 7 \times (T(2) + T(T(9)) + 4) & 7596 &:= T(T(7 - 5)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(6))) \\ 7296 &:= (T(7^2) - 9) \times 6 & 7599 &:= T(-T(7) + T(T(5))) + T(9 \times 9) \\ 7298 &:= -T(7) + (2 + 9) \times T(T(8)) & 7623 &:= T(T(7)) \times T(6) - T(2 \times T(T(3))) \\ 7299 &:= T(T(7)) \times 2 \times 9 - 9 & 7627 &:= (T(7) + T(T(6))^2) / 7 \\ 7308 &:= (-T(7) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(08) & 7653 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(65)) \times 3 \\ 7326 &:= (T(T(7)) \times 3 + T(2)) \times 6 & 7672 &:= T(7) \times (T(6) + T(T(7) - T(T(2)))) \\ 7329 &:= 7 \times (T(3) \times 2 + T(T(9))) & 7714 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(7) + 1 - T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7728 &:= T(7) \times T(7+2 \times 8) & 8292 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(9) + T(T(T(2))) \\ 7735 &:= (7 + T(T(7+3))) \times 5 & 8293 &:= 8 \times (2 + T(T(9))) - 3 \\ 7749 &:= T(-7-7 + T(T(4))) \times 9 & 8294 &:= 8 \times (T(2) + T(T(9))) - T(4) \\ 7784 &:= (7+7) \times T(T(8)) - T(T(T(4))) & 8295 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(-9 + T(5)) \\ 7819 &:= 7 \times (T(8) + T(1 + T(9))) & 8297 &:= 8 \times (T(2) + T(T(9))) - 7 \\ 7826 &:= -T(7) + (T(8) - 2) \times T(T(6)) & 8298 &:= T(8)/2 + T(T(9)) \times 8 \\ 7833 &:= (T(T(7)) - T(8) + 3) \times T(T(3)) & 8308 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) - 08 \\ 7839 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(8) - T(3))) \times 9 & 8312 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) - 1 - T(2) \\ 7845 &:= (-7 + T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5 & 8313 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) - 1 \times 3 \\ 7847 &:= (-7 + T(-8 + T(T(4)))) \times 7 & 8315 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) - 1^5 \\ 7848 &:= (T(7) + T(-T(8) + T(T(4)))) \times T(8) & 8316 &:= T(8) \times T(3 \times (1 + 6)) \\ 7867 &:= 7 - T(T(8)) + T(6) \times T(T(7)) & 8317 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + 1^7 \\ 7893 &:= (T(7 \times 8) + T(T(9))) \times 3 & 8321 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(2)) - 1 \\ 7896 &:= 7 \times T(8 + T(9) - 6) & 8322 &:= T(8) \times T(T((3 \times 2))) + T(T(2)) \\ 7918 &:= 7 \times (T(T(9)) + 1) + T(T(8)) & 8323 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2)))/3 \\ 7924 &:= 7 \times (T(T(9) + 2) + 4) & 8324 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + 2 \times 4 \\ 7963 &:= 7 + T(T(9) + 6) \times T(3) & 8325 &:= (T(T(8) - 3) - T(T(2))) \times T(5) \\ 7965 &:= 7 \times T(T(9)) + 6 \times T(T(5)) & 8326 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(-2 + 6) \\ 8028 &:= (-8 + T(T(T(T(02)))) \times T(8) & 8328 &:= T(8)/3 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8) \\ 8120 &:= T(T(8-1)) \times 20 & 8331 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(3) - 1) \\ 8127 &:= (8+1) \times T(T(T(2))) \times 7 & 8337 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + 3 \times 7 \\ 8136 &:= T(8) \times (1 - T(3) + T(T(6))) & 8343 &:= -T(T(8)) + T(3) \times T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3))) \\ 8214 &:= T(T(8))^2 / (-1 + T(T(4))) & 8344 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) / T(T(4)) \\ 8223 &:= T(T(8)) \times 2 \times T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3))) & 8345 &:= T(T(8)) - T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4))) \times 5 \\ 8225 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(-2 + T(5)) & 8348 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + 4 \times 8 \\ 8228 &:= T(8) + 2^{T(T(T(2))) - 8} & 8352 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(5 + T(2)) \\ 8232 &:= (8 + T(T(2)))^3 \times T(2) & 8364 &:= -T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)) + T(6)) \times T(4) \\ 8234 &:= T(8) \times (-2 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(4) & 8372 &:= T(T(8) + T((3+7))) \times 2 \\ 8235 &:= (T(T(8) + T(2)) - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) & 8379 &:= (T(T(8) + T(3)) + T(7)) \times 9 \\ 8237 &:= T(8) \times (-2 + T(T(T(3)))) - 7 & 8382 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(8 + T(2)) \\ 8238 &:= -T(T(8)/T(2)) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) & 8385 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(T(3))) \times (8 + 5) \\ 8244 &:= T(8) \times (-2 + T(T(-4 + T(4)))) & 8388 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + ((T(8) + T(8))) \\ 8245 &:= (T(T(8) + T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \times 5 & 8415 &:= T(8 \times 4 + 1) \times T(5) \\ 8256 &:= 8 \times (-T(2) + T(T(T(5) - 6))) & 8423 &:= 8^4 \times 2 + T(T(T(3))) \\ 8258 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 58 & 8424 &:= T(T(8) - T(4)) \times 24 \\ 8265 &:= 8 \times T(T(T(2) + 6)) - T(5) & 8436 &:= T(T(8)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(3)))/6 \\ 8267 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(6) - T(7) & 8458 &:= 8 - T(T(T(4))) + T(5) \times T(T(8)) \\ 8268 &:= -8 \times T(T(2)) + T(T(6)) \times T(8) & 8496 &:= T(8) \times (-4 + 9 + T(T(6))) \\ 8275 &:= 8 \times T(T(2+7)) - 5 & 8523 &:= T(T(-8 + T(5))) \times T(T(T(2))) - 3 \\ 8279 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(7) - 9 & 8526 &:= (T(T(8) - 5 - T(2))) \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8532 &:= T(8) \times (T(T(5) + T(3)) + T(T(2))) \\ 8544 &:= -T(8) + T(T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) \times 4 \\ 8567 &:= T(8) + 5 + T(6) \times T(T(7)) \\ 8568 &:= (T(8) + T(5)) \times T(6) \times 8 \\ 8572 &:= (8 + T(T(T(5)) - T(7))) \times 2 \\ 8574 &:= -T(T(8)) + T(T(-5 + 7)) \times T(T(T(4))) \\ 8592 &:= 8 \times (T(T(5)) \times 9 - T(T(2))) \\ 8624 &:= 8 \times (-T(T(6)) \times 2 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 8637 &:= T(T(8))/6 + T(T(3)) \times T(T(7)) \\ 8640 &:= T(8) \times 6 \times 40 \\ 8646 &:= T(8) \times T(T(6)) + T(T(4)) \times 6 \\ 8648 &:= 8 \times T(6 + 4 + T(8)) \\ 8658 &:= T(T(8)) \times (6 + T(5) - 8) \\ 8673 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(-6 + T(7))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 8674 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(6)) \times T(7)) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 8679 &:= -T(8) + T(6) \times (T(T(7)) + 9) \\ 8694 &:= T(8) \times T(69)/T(4) \\ 8739 &:= (8 + T(T(7))) \times T(T(3)) + T(9) \\ 8742 &:= -T(T(8)) + (T(7) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 8745 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(7) - T(T(4))) \times T(5) \\ 8749 &:= (T(T(8)) + 7) \times (4 + 9) \\ 8764 &:= 8 \times T(7 \times 6) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 8784 &:= 8 \times (-T(T(7)) - T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 8824 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(8 + 2))) \times 4 \\ 8827 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(8) - 2)) \times 7 \\ 8834 &:= -T(-8 + T(8)) + T(3) \times T(T(T(4))) \\ 8844 &:= T(T(8 + T(8/4))) \times 4 \\ 8848 &:= 8 \times (8 \times T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \\ 8856 &:= T(8) \times (T(8) + 5) \times 6 \\ 8895 &:= T(8 + T(8)) \times 9 - T(5) \\ 8925 &:= T((8 + 9) \times 2) \times T(5) \\ 8928 &:= (8 + 9 + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times T(8) \\ 8955 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(T(9))/T(5)) \times T(5) \\ 8991 &:= (-T(8) + T(T(9))) \times 9 \times 1 \\ 9129 &:= (T(9) - 1) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9)) \\ 9195 &:= 9 \times T(T(1 \times 9)) - T(T(5)) \\ 9222 &:= T(T(9 + T(2))) \times T(2) - T(T(T(2))) \\ 9225 &:= T(T(9)) + 2 \times T(T(T(2))) \times T(5) \\ 9227 &:= T(T(9)) + 2^{T(T(2))+7} \\ 9231 &:= -9 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(3 + 1))) \\ 9233 &:= -T(9 - 2) + T(T(3))^3 \\ 9234 &:= -9 + T(2) \times T(T(3 \times 4)) \\ 9252 &:= -9 + (T(T(2)) + T(5))^{T(2)} \\ 9264 &:= T(9) - T(T(T(2))) + 6 \times T(T(T(4))) \\ 9276 &:= T(T(9) + T(T(2))) \times 7 - 6 \\ 9279 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(2) - 7) \times 9 \\ 9282 &:= (T(T(9 - 2)) + T(8)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 9285 &:= (-T(9) - 2 + T(T(8))) \times T(5) \\ 9288 &:= (-9 + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(8)) \times T(8) \\ 9294 &:= (-T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9)) \times T(4) \\ 9312 &:= (T(T(9)) \times 3 - 1) \times T(2) \\ 9315 &:= 9 \times T(3 \times 15) \\ 9333 &:= (T(T(9)) \times 3 + T(3)) \times 3 \\ 9336 &:= 9 \times T(T(3 \times 3)) + T(6) \\ 9339 &:= T(9) \times T(T(T(3))) - T(T(3)) - T(T(9)) \\ 9355 &:= T(9 + 3) \times T(T(5)) - 5 \\ 9369 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(-3 + 6)) \times 9 \\ 9387 &:= T(9) \times T(T(T(3))) - T(8) \times T(7) \\ 9396 &:= 9 \times (3 + T(T(9)) + 6) \\ 9397 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(3)) \times 9 + T(7) \\ 9424 &:= (9 + T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4) \\ 9426 &:= -T(9) + T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(6)) \\ 9435 &:= (T(T(9)) - T(T(4 + 3))) \times T(5) \\ 9444 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(-4 + T(T(4)))) \times 4 \\ 9445 &:= T(9) \times T(T(4) + T(4)) - 5 \\ 9462 &:= -9 + T(T(T(4))) \times 6 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 9465 &:= T(9) \times T(4) \times T(6) + T(5) \\ 9471 &:= (T(9) - 4) \times T(T(7 - 1)) \\ 9485 &:= T(T(9)) - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8)) \times T(5) \\ 9495 &:= T(9) \times (T(4 + 9) + T(T(5))) \\ 9522 &:= (((T(T(9))/T(5))^2) \times 2) \\ 9546 &:= 9 \times T(T(5 + 4)) + T(T(6)) \\ 9567 &:= 9 \times (T(T(T(5) - 6)) + T(7)) \\ 9576 &:= (T(9) + 5 + T(T(7))) \times T(6) \\ 9585 &:= (T(9) \times T(5) - T(8)) \times T(5) \\ 9586 &:= T(9) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(-8 + T(6))) \\ 9594 &:= 9 \times (-T(5) + T(-9 + T(T(4)))) \\ 9613 &:= -T(T(9)) + (T(6) + 1)^3 \\ 9624 &:= -T(T(-9 + T(6))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4)) \\ 9639 &:= 9 \times T(6) \times (T(3) + T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9648 &:= (T(T(9)) - T(T(6))) \times (4 + 8) & 9837 &:= 9 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) \\
 9672 &:= (T(9) - T(6)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(2)) & 9852 &:= (-9 + T(T(8))) \times T(5) - T(2) \\
 9693 &:= 9 \times (T(6) + T(T(9)) + T(T(3))) & 9882 &:= (T(9 \times 8) + T(T(8))) \times T(2) \\
 9724 &:= -T(T(9)) + 7 \times (-T(2) + T(T(T(4)))) & 9884 &:= (T(T(9)) + 8) \times 8 + T(T(T(4))) \\
 9728 &:= (T(9) - 7) \times 2^8 & 9927 &:= -T(T(9)) + 9 \times T(2) \times T(T(7)) \\
 9729 &:= 9 \times T(T(7) + 2 \times 9) & 9936 &:= T(T(T(9)) / T(9)) \times 36 \\
 9742 &:= -T(T(9)) + 7 \times T(T(T(4))) - T(2) & 9945 &:= -T(9) + T(9 \times 4) \times T(5) \\
 9747 &:= (-T(9) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(7)) & 9963 &:= T(9 \times 9) \times (6 - 3) \\
 9765 &:= T(T(9)) \times 7 + T(6) \times T(T(5)) & 9981 &:= 9 \times T(T(9)) + T(T(8 \times 1)) \\
 9795 &:= T(T(9)) + (T(7) + T(9)) \times T(T(5)) & 9985 &:= T(T(9) / 9) \times T(T(8)) - 5 \\
 9825 &:= (-9 + T(T(8)) - 2) \times T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 2.1. From now onwards the results are with unnecessary extra brackets, such as, "...". After simplifications, these can be removed easily.

2.3 General Representations: Five Digits Numbers

$$\begin{aligned}
 10125 &:= ((T((10 - 1))^2) \times 5) & 10462 &:= ((10^4) - (T(T(6)) \times (-2))) \\
 10128 &:= ((-T(T((10 - 1)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-8) & 10465 &:= ((10^4) + T((6 \times 5))) \\
 10164 &:= (((10 + 1) \times T(T(6))) \times 4) & 10484 &:= ((T(T(10)) + T((T(4) + T(8)))) \times 4) \\
 10219 &:= (T(10) - (T(T(T(2)))) \times (1 - T(9))) & 10536 &:= (((T(T(10)) - (T(5))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 6) \\
 10224 &:= (T((-T(10)) - (T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(2)))) \times 4) & 10584 &:= ((T(T(10)) - T(T((5 + 8)))) \times (-4)) \\
 10230 &:= ((1 + T(T(T(02)))) \times T(30)) & 10623 &:= (((T(T(10)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2))) - 3) \\
 10237 &:= (T((T(10) + T(2))) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(7)))) & 10626 &:= (T((1 + T(06))) \times (2 \times T(6))) \\
 10239 &:= (((T(T(10)) - T(T(2))) \times T(3)) + T(T(9))) & 10632 &:= (((T(T(10)) + T(T(6))) \times T(3)) + T(T(2))) \\
 10263 &:= ((T((T(10) + T(2))) \times 6) - 3) & 10633 &:= (((T(T(10)) - (T(6))) \times T(T(3))) / 3) \\
 10266 &:= (T(((T(10) - T(2)) + (6))) \times 6) & 10639 &:= (((1 + T(06))^3) - 9) \\
 10269 &:= (((T(T(10)) \times T(T(2))) - (6)) + T(T(9))) & 10648 &:= ((1 + T(06))^{T(T(4)-8)}) \\
 10288 &:= (((-T(10)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(8))) - 8) & 10656 &:= ((10 + 6) \times T((T(5) + T(6)))) \\
 10329 &:= (-T((-T(10) + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9)) & 10662 &:= (((T(T(10)) + T(T(6))) + (6)) \times T(T(2))) \\
 10335 &:= ((10 \times T(T(3 \times 3))) - (T(5))) & 10674 &:= (-106) + (7 \times T(T(T(4)))) \\
 10349 &:= (-1) + (T(((0 \times 3) + 4)) \times T(T(9))) & 10675 &:= ((T(T(10)) + T((6 + T(7)))) \times 5) \\
 10365 &:= ((10 \times T(T(3 + 6))) + (T(5))) & 10714 &:= ((T(T(10)) \times 7) - T((1 + T(4)))) \\
 10374 &:= (((T(T(10)) \times T(3)) - T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) & 10725 &:= ((T(T(10)) \times 7) - T((2 \times 5))) \\
 10384 &:= (T(T(10)) + (T(T((3 + 8))) \times 4)) & 10729 &:= (((T(T(10)) \times 7) - T(T(2))) - T(9)) \\
 10392 &:= (((T(10) \times T(T(3))) \times 9) - T(2)) & 10731 &:= ((T(T(10)) - (7)) \times (T(3) + 1)) \\
 10393 &:= (1 + ((T(T(T(03))) \times T(9)) - 3)) & 10735 &:= ((T(T(10)) \times 7) - (3 \times T(5))) \\
 10394 &:= (-1) + (((0 - T(T(3))) \times (-9)) \times T(T(4))) & 10738 &:= ((T(T(10)) \times 7) - (T(3) + T(8))) \\
 10395 &:= ((T(10) \times T(T(3))) \times (T(9) / 5)) & 10740 &:= ((T(T(10)) \times 7) - 40) \\
 10396 &:= (1 + (T(((0 \times 3) + 9)) \times T(T(6)))) & 10744 &:= ((T(T(10)) \times 7) - T((4 + 4))) \\
 10416 &:= (T(-((10 - 41))) \times T(6)) & 10745 &:= ((1 \times 07) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 5)) \\
 10426 &:= (10 + (T((T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(6))) & 10746 &:= (((T(T(10)) \times 7) - T(T(4))) + (T(6))) \\
 10427 &:= (((10^4) + T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7)))) & 10748 &:= ((T(T(10)) \times 7) - (4 \times 8)) \\
 10437 &:= (((T(T(10)) - T(T(4))) + (T(3))) \times 7) & 10752 &:= ((T(T(10)) \times 7) - T((5 + 2))) \\
 10449 &:= (-1) - ((0 - T(T(4))) \times T((T(4) + 9))) & 10755 &:= ((T(T(10)) \times 7) - (5 \times 5))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 10757** := $((T(T(10)) \times 7) - (-5) + T(7))$
10759 := $((T(T(10)) \times 7) - T((5) - 9))$
10762 := $((T(T(10)) \times 7) - (T(6) - T(2)))$
10764 := $((T(T(10)) \times 7) - (6 + T(4)))$
10765 := $((T(T(10)) \times (T(7) - T(6))) - (T(5)))$
10767 := $((T(T(10)) \times 7) - (6 + 7))$
10773 := $((T(T(10)) \times 7) - T(7) + T(T(3)))$
10774 := $((T(T(10)) \times 7) - T((7 - 4)))$
10775 := $((T(10) \times T(7)) \times 7) - (5)$
10780 := $(T(T(10)) \times (7 + (8 \times 0)))$
10782 := $((T(T(10)) \times 7) + 8) - T(T(2))$
10783 := $(T(T(10)) - (T(78) \times (-3)))$
10784 := $((T(T(10)) \times 7) + (8 - 4))$
10786 := $((T(T(10)) \times 7) + (T(8)/6))$
10787 := $((T(10) - T((7 \times 8))) \times (-7))$
10789 := $((T(T(10)) \times 7) - ((T(8) - T(9))))$
10792 := $((T(T(10)) \times 7) + (9 + T(2)))$
10794 := $(-10) + (T((T(7) + T(9))) \times 4)$
10797 := $((T(T(10)) \times 7) + (T(9) - T(7)))$
10810 := $(10 \times T((T(8) + 10)))$
10815 := $((T(10) + T(T(8))) \times 15)$
10816 := $((10 + T(T(8))) \times 16)$
10836 := $((T(T(10)) + 8)/3) \times T(6)$
10855 := $(T(10) + (T(8) \times T((T(5)/5))))$
10856 := $((10 + T(8)) \times (5 + T(T(6))))$
10857 := $((T(10) - 8) \times T(T(T(-((5 - 7))))))$
10863 := $((T(10) - 8) \times T(T(6))) + (T(3))$
10864 := $((T(T(10)) + T((8 \times 6))) \times 4)$
10865 := $(-T(10)) + (T((-8) + T(6))) \times T(T(5))$
10879 := $((T(T(10)) \times 8) - T(T(7))) - T(T(9))$
10889 := $((T(T(10)) \times 8) - T((8 + T(9))))$
10925 := $(-10) + ((9^{T(2)}) \times T(5))$
10927 := $((T(T(10)) + T((9 - T(2)))) \times 7)$
10934 := $((T(T(10)) \times 9) - T((T(3) + T(4))))$
10935 := $(T((1 \times 09)) \times (3^5))$
10945 := $(-T(10)) \times (-9) - T((4 + T(5)))$
10972 := $(10 + ((-9) \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(2)))$
10975 := $((T(T(10)) + T(9)) \times 7) - T(T(5))$
10979 := $((10 \times T(T(9))) - T(T(7))) + T(T(9))$
10984 := $((T((T(10) + 9)) + T(T(8))) \times 4)$
10985 := $((T(T(10)) - 9) + T(T(8))) \times 5)$
11025 := $((T(T(11)) - T(T(02))) \times 5)$
11052 := $((T(T(11)) \times 05) - T(2))$
11055 := $(T(T(11)) \times ((0 \times 5) + 5))$
11105 := $((T(T(11)) + 10) \times 5)$
11137 := $(-((T(T(T((1 + 1)))) - ((T(1 + T(3))) \times T(T(7))))))$
11165 := $((T(T(11)) + (1 + T(6))) \times 5)$
11172 := $((1 + T(T((1 + 1)))) \times T((T(7) \times 2)))$
11199 := $((T(T(T(T((1 + 1)))))) \times (-1) + T(9)) + T(T(9))$
11220 := $(T((11 \times T(2))) \times 20)$
11235 := $((T(T(11)) + T((2^3))) \times 5)$
11242 := $(11 \times ((2^{T(4)}) - 2))$
11243 := $((11 \times (2^{T(4)})) - T(T(3)))$
11250 := $((T(T((1 + 1))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-50))$
11253 := $((T(T(11)) + T(T((2 \times 5)))) \times 3)$
11256 := $((T(T(11)) - T(T(2))) \times 5) + T(T(6))$
11265 := $((T(T(11)) + (2 \times T(6))) \times 5)$
11277 := $(-T((1 + 12))) - (-T(7) \times T(T(7)))$
11286 := $((T(11) \times T(2)) \times (T(8) + T(6)))$
11289 := $(-T(T(11)) + (T((T(2) \times 8)) \times (-T(9))))$
11292 := $((T(11) \times T((2 \times 9))) + T(T(2)))$
11295 := $((T(T(11)) + (T(2) + T(9))) \times 5)$
11319 := $(11 \times (-T(3)) + T(T((1 \times 9))))$
11322 := $((11 + T(3)) \times T(T((2^{T(2)})))$
11329 := $(-11) - ((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(9)))$
11339 := $(-1) + (T((-1) + T(T(3))) \times (T(3) \times 9))$
11341 := $(1 + (T((-1) + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) - 1))$
11343 := $((T(T((1 + 1))) \times T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) - 3)$
11345 := $((T(T(11)) + 3) + T(T(4))) \times 5)$
11346 := $(T(T((1 + 1))) \times T((T(3) + T((4 + 6))))$
11347 := $(-T(T(T((1 + 1)))) + (T(T((3 + 4))) \times (-T(7))))$
11352 := $(11 \times (-3) + T((T(5) \times T(2))))$
11357 := $((11 \times T((3 \times T(5)))) - T(7))$
11364 := $(T(T((1 + 1))) \times (3 + T((6 + T(T(4))))$
11367 := $(-1) + (T((1 + T(3))) \times T((T(6) + (7))))$
11372 := $(1 + ((T((1 + T(3))) \times T(T(7))) + T(2)))$
11373 := $(-1) + ((T((1 + T(3))) \times T(T(7))) + (T(3)))$
11374 := $((T(T(T(T((1 + 1)))))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(7))) + (T(T(4)))$
11377 := $((-1) + T((1 + 3))) - (-T(7) \times T(T(7)))$
11379 := $(-T(T((1 + 1))) + (T(-((T(3) - T(7)))) \times T(9))$
11384 := $(-1) + (T((1 + T(T(3)))) \times T((T(8)/4)))$
11385 := $(11 \times T(T((3 \times (8 - 5))))$
11392 := $(1 + ((T((1 + T(T(3)))) \times T(9)) + T(T(2)))$
11394 := $(-1) + ((T((1 + T(T(3)))) \times T(9)) + T(4))$
11395 := $((1 + T((1 + T(T(3))) + T(9))) \times 5)$
11396 := $(11 - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(9))))/T(6))$
11424 := $(T(T(T((1 + 1)))) \times (4 \times T((2^4)))$
11427 := $((T(T((1 + 1))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(2)^7))$
11429 := $(11 \times ((T(4) - T(T(2))) + T(T(9))))$
11433 := $(T(T(11)) + ((T(T(T(4))) - 3) \times T(3)))$
11435 := $((T(T(11)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(3))) \times 5)$
11439 := $((-1) + T(T((1 \times 4))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(9))$
11440 := $((T(T(T(T((1 + 1)))))) + (T(T(4)))) \times 40$
11445 := $(T(T(T((1 + 1)))) \times ((T(4) \times T(T(4))) - (5)))$

- 11448** := $(T(((1+1) + T(T(4))) - (4))) \times 8$
11451 := $(T(T(11)) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-5+1)))$
11452 := $((1+1) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T((T(5) - 2))))$
11462 := $(T(T(11)) - (T(4) - (T(6)^{T(2)})))$
11466 := $(T(-((1-14))) \times (T(6) \times 6))$
11472 := $((T(T(11)) \times 4) + (T(72)))$
11473 := $((T(T(11) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 7) + T(T(T(3))))$
11475 := $(T((T(T(T((1+1)))) - 4) \times 75)$
11477 := $(-T((1+1))) + ((4 + T(T(7))) \times T(7))$
11484 := $(T((1+1)) \times T((T(T(4)) + (8 \times 4))))$
11492 := $((11 \times (T(4) + T(T(9)))) - T(2))$
11494 := $(-1) + ((1 + T(4)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(4)))$
11495 := $(11 \times (T(4) + T(9 \times 5)))$
11529 := $((T(11) - 5) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times 9$
11544 := $-((T(T((1+1))) + (-T((5 \times 4))) \times T(T(4))))$
11545 := $(T((-1) + T((1+5))) \times T(T(4))) - (5)$
11550 := $(T(T((1 \times 1) + 5))) \times 50$
11557 := $(T(-((1+1)) + T(5))) \times (T(T(5)) + (7))$
11564 := $((T(T(T(T((1+1)))))) + 5) \times (-6) + T(T(4)))$
11572 := $(11 \times ((T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 2))$
11577 := $(-1) - ((1 + T(57)) \times (-7))$
11583 := $(T((11 + T(5))) \times (T(8) - 3))$
11592 := $((T(T((1+1))) + T(T(5))) \times 92)$
11594 := $(11 \times ((T(5) + T(T(9))) + (4)))$
11616 := $(T((11 + T(6))) \times (1 + T(6)))$
11643 := $((T(T((1+1)))^6)/4 - T(T(3)))$
11647 := $(-1) + ((T(T((1+6))) + T(4)) \times T(7))$
11648 := $((T(T(T(T((1+1)))))) + T((-6) + T(T(4)))) \times 8$
11649 := $(11 \times ((6 \times 4) + T(T(9))))$
11650 := $((1+1) + T(T(6))) \times 50$
11655 := $((T((11 \times 6)) + T(T(5))) \times 5)$
11674 := $(-((1+1)) - (6 \times (-T(T(7))) - T(T(T(4))))))$
11676 := $((T((11 + T(6))) + T(7)) \times T(6))$
11682 := $(-T(11)) \times (-6 - T((T(8)/2)))$
11684 := $((1 + T((1 + T(6)))) \times (T(8) + T(4)))$
11704 := $(T((T(T((1+1))) + 70)) \times 4)$
11715 := $((11 \times 71) \times T(5))$
11736 := $((T((1+1))^7 - T(T(T(3)))) \times 6)$
11739 := $((T(T((1+1))) + (7)) \times T((-3) + T(9)))$
11742 := $((11 + T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(2))$
11748 := $(T((1+1)) \times T(((7+4) \times 8)))$
11749 := $(-T(11)) + ((7 \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(9)))$
11755 := $((T(T(11)) + (T(7) \times 5)) \times 5)$
11757 := $(-T((1+1)) - ((T(7) \times T(5)) \times T(7)))$
11764 := $(-1) - (-((1 + (7^6)))/T(4))$
11767 := $(T(T(T(T((1+1)))))) - ((T(T(7)) + (6)) \times (-T(7)))$
11768 := $(-T(T((1+1))) + (T(T(7)) \times (-T(6) + 8)))$
11771 := $(-T((1+1))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(7) + 1))$
11772 := $((1 + T((1 \times 7))) \times T(T(7))) - 2$
11773 := $(-1) + ((1 + T(7)) \times T((7 + T(T(3))))))$
11774 := $((1 + T((1 \times 7))) \times T((7 \times 4)))$
11775 := $((1 - ((-1) \times T(7)) \times T(7)) \times T(5))$
11777 := $(T((1+1)) - ((-T(7)) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(7)))$
11781 := $(11 \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) - 1))$
11782 := $(1 + (T(-((1-7))) \times T((T(8) - T(2))))$
11786 := $((11 \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(8)))) - (6))$
11792 := $((T(T(11)) \times (-7+9))/(-T(2)))$
11814 := $(-T(11)) - (-8) \times T((-1) + T(T(4)))$
11823 := $((1+1) + T((T(8) - T(2)))) \times T(T(3))$
11824 := $(-1) + ((-1) + (T(8) \times T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4))$
11832 := $((T(T(11)) - 8) - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(2))$
11855 := $((T(11) \times T(8)) - (5)) \times 5$
11856 := $(T(((1+1) + T(8))) \times (-5) + T(6))$
11862 := $((T((1+1)) \times T(T(8))) - (T(6))) \times T(T(2))$
11869 := $(-11) + (8 \times T((6 \times 9)))$
11885 := $((T(T(11) - 8)) + T(T(8))) \times 5$
11888 := $((1 + T((18 + T(8)))) \times 8)$
11889 := $((-11) + T(T(8))) + T(T(8)) \times 9$
11891 := $(11 \times T((T(8) + (9 + 1))))$
11894 := $(-T(11)) + (8 \times (-T(9)) + T(T(T(4))))$
11895 := $((T((1+1)) \times T(89)) - T(T(5)))$
11912 := $((11 \times T((T(9) + 1))) + T(T(T(2))))$
11924 := $(11 \times ((T(T(9)) - T(T(2))) + T(T(4))))$
11925 := $(T(11) + (9^{T(2)})) \times T(5)$
11928 := $((T(-1) + T((1+9))) + T(T(2))) \times 8$
11934 := $(T((T((1+1)) + 9)) \times T((T(T(3)) - (4))))$
11946 := $(-T(11)) \times (-T(9) - T((T(4) + (6))))$
11949 := $((T(T(11)) + T(T(9))) \times 4) - T(T(9))$
11957 := $(11 \times ((9 \times T(T(5))) + (7)))$
11964 := $((T(11) \times T(9)) + T(6)) \times 4$
11968 := $((-11) - T((9 \times 6))) \times (-8)$
11970 := $(T(((1+1) \times 9)) \times 70)$
11973 := $((11 \times T(T(9))) - (-T(7)) \times T(T(3)))$
11977 := $((T((T(11) - 9)) \times 7) + T(T(7)))$
11979 := $((11^{T(9-7)}) \times 9)$
11982 := $((1+1) \times 9) \times T(T(8)) - T(T(2))$
11984 := $((1+1) \times 9) \times T(T(8)) - (4)$
11985 := $((T(T(T(T((1+1)))))) - T((9 \times 8))) \times (-5)$
11988 := $((1 \times 1) + 9) + 8) \times T(T(8))$
11989 := $(1 + ((T(T(-((1-9)))) + (T(T(8)))) \times 9))$
12096 := $(T(((1 + T(T(2))) \times 09)) \times 6)$
12097 := $(1 - (T(T(2)) \times (0 - T((9 \times 7))))$
12104 := $(T(T(12)) - T(T(10))) \times 4$
12144 := $((T(T(12)) - T((-1) + T(4))) \times 4)$

- 12149** := $(-1) + ((T(T(2)) \times T((-1) + T(4))) \times T(9))$
12154 := $(-1) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(-((1 - 5)))) \times T(T(4)))$
12165 := $((-1) - (-2 \times T(T((1 + 6)))) \times T(5))$
12167 := $((1 + T(T(T(2)))) + 1)^{T(6)/7}$
12168 := $(T(12) \times (T(T(-((1 - 6)))) + T(8)))$
12175 := $((-1) - (-T((2 + 1))) \times T(T(7))) \times 5$
12177 := $(-((1 + 2)) - (T((1 + T(7))) \times (-T(7))))$
12184 := $((T(T(12)) - (-1) + T(8))) \times 4$
12185 := $((1 + (T(T(2)) \times T(T(-((1 - 8)))))) \times 5)$
12189 := $(-1) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1) \times (8 + T(9)))$
12192 := $((1 + T((T(T(T(2))) + 1))) \times (T(9) + T(2)))$
12222 := $((T((T(T(1 + 2))) \times T(2))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(2))$
12223 := $(1 + (T(T(2)) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T((T(2) \times T(T(3))))))$
12225 := $((T(T((1 + T(T(2)))) \times 2) + T(2)) \times T(5))$
12253 := $(T((1 + T(2))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 53))$
12254 := $(-1) + (T(2) \times (T((T(T(2)) \times T(5))) - T(4)))$
12255 := $(-((T((1 + 2^{T(T(2))})) - (T(T(5)) \times T(T(5))))$
12257 := $((1 + 2) \times T((T(T(2)) \times T(5))) - (T(7)))$
12258 := $((T((1 + 2)) \times T(2)) \times (T(5) + T(T(8))))$
12259 := $(1 + (T(2) \times (T((T(T(2)) \times T(5))) - 9)))$
12263 := $(-1) + ((T(T(T(2)))^{T(2)} + T((T(T(6))/3)))$
12264 := $((T(T(12)) + T(T(2))) - (T(6))) \times 4$
12265 := $(T(T((1 + T(2)))) \times ((-T(2)) + T(T(6))) - (5)))$
12275 := $((-1) - (T(T(2)) \times (T(2) + T(T(7)))) \times (-5))$
12276 := $((T(T(12)) - T(T((2 + 7)))) \times 6)$
12279 := $((T(T(12)) \times (-T(2) - (7))) - T(9))$
12282 := $((-1) + (2^{T(2)+8}) \times T(T(2)))$
12283 := $((T(T(T(1 + T(2)))) - 2) \times 8) - (T(T(3)))$
12284 := $((-1) - T(2)) - (T(2) \times (-8^4))$
12285 := $(1 + 2) \times T((-((2 - 8)) \times T(5)))$
12286 := $(1 + (T(2) \times T((T(2) \times (T(8) - (6))))))$
12288 := $(T((1 + 2)) \times ((2^8) \times 8))$
12290 := $(-1) + (T(2) \times (2 + T(90)))$
12292 := $(1 + ((2 + T(2 \times T(9))) \times T(2)))$
12293 := $(-1) + ((T(2) + T(2 \times T(9))) \times 3)$
12294 := $(-1) + ((T(2) \times T(2 \times T(9))) + T(4))$
12296 := $((-1) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times ((-2) - T(9)) - (6))$
12297 := $((T((1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times (2 + T(9))) + (T(T(7))))$
12298 := $(T(T((1 + T(2)))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(9) + 8)))$
12299 := $((1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times (2^9)) + T(T(9))$
12312 := $((T(T(12)) - 3) \times (1 + T(2)))$
12314 := $((T(T(12)) \times (3 + 1)) - T(4))$
12315 := $((1 + T(2 \times (T(T(3)) - 1))) \times T(5))$
12317 := $((T(T(12)) \times (3 + 1)) - (7))$
12318 := $(-((1 \times 2)) + (T(T(T(3 + 1)))) \times 8)$
12319 := $(-1) - (-((2^3) \times T(T((1 + 9))))$
12320 := $(T(T(T((1 + T(2)))) \times (T(3) + (2 + 0)))$
12321 := $((T(T(T((1 + T(2)))) \times (T(3) + 2)) + 1)$
12322 := $((T(T(12)) \times (T(3) - 2)) - 2)$
12323 := $(-1) + ((-2) + T(3)) \times T(T((2 \times T(3))))$
12324 := $(12 \times (3 + (2^{T(4)})))$
12325 := $((T(T(T((1 + T(2)))) \times (T(3) + 2)) + 5)$
12326 := $(-1) + ((T(T(2)) \times T((T(T(3)) \times T(2)))) + T(T(6)))$
12327 := $(-((T(T((1 + 2))) - ((T(T(3))^2) \times T(7))))$
12328 := $((1 + T(T(((2^3) + 2))) \times 8)$
12329 := $(-1) + ((T(23) - 2) \times T(9))$
12332 := $((1 + T(2)) \times (T(T((T(3) + T(3)))) + 2))$
12333 := $((-1) - T((T(2) \times T(T(3)))) \times (-T(3))) + T(T(T(3)))$
12334 := $((1 + T(2)) \times T(T((T(3) + T(3)))) + T(4))$
12336 := $(T(T(12)) + ((T(T(3))^3) - (6)))$
12339 := $((T((1 + T(2)))) \times (T(T(3)) \times T(T(3))) - 9)$
12341 := $((1 + T((T(2) + T(T(3)))) \times 41)$
12342 := $((T(T(12)) + 3) \times 4) + T(T(2))$
12343 := $(T(T((1 + T(2)))) + (3 \times (4^{T(3)})))$
12344 := $((-1) + T(T(2))) + T(T((3 \times 4))) \times 4$
12345 := $(T((-1) + T(T(2))) \times (3 + T((T(T(4)) - (T(5))))))$
12346 := $(1 + ((T(T((2 \times T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(6))))$
12347 := $((T(T(T((1 + 2)))) - T(3)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(7))$
12348 := $((T(T(12)) + T(3)) \times (-4 - 8))$
12349 := $(1 + (T(2) \times (T(T(3)) + T((T(4) \times 9))))$
12350 := $((T((1 + T(T(T(2)))) - T(3)) \times 50)$
12354 := $(-((T(T((-1) + T(T(2)))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (-54))))$
12359 := $(-1) + ((2 \times T(3)) \times (-5) + T(T(9)))$
12363 := $((T(T(12)) + T(T(3))) + (T(6)^3))$
12364 := $((T((1 + T(2))) + T(T((T(3) + (6)))) \times 4)$
12366 := $((T((T((1 + T(2))) \times T(3))) + T(T(6))) \times 6)$
12368 := $((T(T(T(((1^2) + 3)))) + 6) \times 8)$
12369 := $((1 + T(2)) \times T(T((T(3) + (6)))) + T(9))$
12372 := $((1 + T(2))^{T(3)} + T(7)) \times T(2)$
12373 := $((1 - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) - 3)$
12374 := $(-1) - ((T(T(2)) - T((3 \times 7))) \times T(T(4)))$
12375 := $((-T(12)) + T((T(3) \times 7))) \times T(5)$
12376 := $(T((1 + T(2 + 3))) \times T(7 + 6))$
12377 := $(1 + ((T(2^3)) + T(T(7))) \times T(7))$
12378 := $((1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(T(T(3)))/7)) + T(8))$
12383 := $((T(T((1 + T(2)))) + (T(T(3)))) \times (8 + T(T(3))))$
12384 := $((T(T(12)) + T(-((3 - 8)))) \times 4)$
12385 := $((T(T((1 + T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(3)) - 8)) + (T(T(5))))$
12389 := $((T(T(T((1 + T(2)))) + 3) \times 8) + T(9))$
12392 := $(-((T((1 + T(T(2)))) + ((-T(3)) \times T(T(9))) \times 2))$
12393 := $((-1) + (T(2) \times T(3))) \times (9^3)$
12394 := $((12 \times (-3) + T(T(9))) + T(4))$

- 12396** := (((-1) + T(23)) × T(9)) + T(6)
12397 := (T((1 + T(T(T(2)))))) × ((-3) + T(9)) + (7))
12399 := (T(T(12)) + 3) - (T(T(9)) × (-9))
12405 := (((1 + T(T(2))) + (T(40))) × T(5))
12415 := ((12 × T(T((T(4) - 1)))) - 5)
12419 := (-1) + (T((24 - 1)) × T(9))
12422 := (((1 - T(T(T(T(2)))))) × (-T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2)
12424 := (-1) + ((T(T(2)) × T((4^{T(2)}))) - T(T(4)))
12425 := ((-1) + T(T(2))) × T((T(4) × (2 + 5)))
12426 := (T((1 + 2)) × (T(T(4)) + T((T(2) × T(6))))
12428 := (((-1 + 2) + T(T(4))) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 8))
12429 := (1 + (2 × (4 + (T(T(2)) × T(T(9))))))
12432 := (((-1 + 2) + T((T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))))) × T(T(T(2)))
12433 := (1 + ((-T(2) + T((T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))))) × T(T(3)))
12435 := (((-1) + T(T((T(2) + T(4)))))) × 3 - (T(T(5)))
12437 := (-1) + (T(T(2)) × (T((4³)) - (7)))
12438 := (((1 - 2) + T(T(4))) × T(T(T(3)))) - T(8)
12439 := (-1) + (2 × (T(4) - (-T(3)) × T(T(9))))
12442 := -(((T(1 + T(T(T(2)))))) + T(4)) + (-T(T(4)) × T(T(T(T(2))))))
12445 := ((T(((1 + T(T(2))) × T(4))) + 4) × 5)
12446 := -((T(T(T(1 + T(2)))) - (T(T((4 + 4))) × T(6))))
12447 := ((-1) + T((T(2) + 4))) × (T(T(4)) + T(T(7)))
12448 := (((1 × 2)⁴) + T(T(T(4)))) × 8
12449 := (-1) + (T(2) × (T(T(4)) + T((T(4) × 9))))
12450 := ((T((1 + T(T(T(2)))) - 4) × 50)
12452 := ((1 + T(T(T(2)))) - (-T(T(4)) × (-5) + T(T(T(T(2))))))
12453 := (((-1) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4)) × (-T(5)))) × T(T(3)))
12454 := (((T(T(12)) × 4) + T(T(5))) + T(4))
12455 := ((T((1 + 2)) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5)))))) × 5
12459 := ((T(T(12)) × 4) + (T(5) × 9))
12462 := (-T(12)) + (T(T(4)) × (T(T(6)) - T(2)))
12464 := (((1 - 2) + T(T(4))) × T(T(6))) - T(4)
12465 := (((T(T(12)) × 4) + (T(6))) + T(T(5)))
12467 := ((1 + T((2⁴))) × T((6 + 7)))
12468 := (((1 + T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(6) × T(T(8))))
12472 := ((1 + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(4)) - T(7)))) × (-2))
12473 := (-1) + (-((T(2) × (T(4) - T(7))) × T(T(T(3))))
12474 := (((-1) - T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)))) × T((-T(7)) + T(T(4)))
12475 := ((T((1 + T(2))) + T((T(4) × 7))) × 5)
12479 := (-1) + (T(T(2)) × T((4 × (7 + 9))))
12480 := (((1 - T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-8 + 0))
12481 := (((1 - T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-8)) + 1
12482 := (((1 - T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-8)) + 2
12483 := ((-1) + (2^{T(4)+8})/T(T(3)))
12484 := ((T(T(12)) + (4 + T(8))) × 4)
12485 := (T(T((1 + T(2)))) × (-4) + T((T(8) - T(5))))
12486 := ((1 + T((2 × 4) × 8)) × 6)
12487 := (-1) + ((T(T(2)) + (T(T(4)) × 8)) × T(7))
12488 := (((1 - T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-8)) + 8
12489 := (((1 - T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-8)) + 9
12492 := (12 × ((4 + T(T(9))) + 2))
12493 := (1 + ((2 + T(4)) × (T(T(9)) + (T(3))))
12495 := (T(T((1 + 2))) × T((T(4) + 9) + T(5)))
12496 := (1 + (T(-(2 - (4 × 9))) × T(6)))
12497 := (((1 - T(T(T(T(2)))))) × (-T(T(4)))) - T((T(9) - T(7)))
12513 := ((1 + 2) × (-T(5) + T(T(13))))
12516 := ((1 + T(-(T(T(T(2))) - T(T(5 - 1)))))) × T(6)
12522 := ((12 - T(T((T(5) - 2)))) × (-T(2)))
12523 := -((T(T(12)) - ((5^{T(2)}) - T(T(3))))
12524 := (((-1) + T(T(2)))⁵ + T(T(2))) × 4
12525 := ((T((-1) + T(T(2)))) + T((T(T(5))/T(2)))) × T(5)
12527 := (((-1) + T(T((-2) + T(5)))) × T(2)) - (T(7))
12528 := ((T((1 + 25)) - T(2)) × T(8))
12534 := -((T(T(12)) - ((5^{T(3)}) - T(4))))
12536 := (-1) + ((T(T((-2) + T(5)))) × 3) - (T(6))
12537 := -((T(T(12)) - ((5^{T(3)}) - (7))))
12542 := ((-1) + ((T(T(2)) - T(T(5))) × T(T(4)))) × (-2)
12543 := (((-1) + T(T((-2) + T(5)))) - 4) × 3
12544 := -((T(T(12)) - ((5^{-4+T(4)}))))
12545 := (((-1) + T(T(2))) × T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5))))
12546 := ((T(T((-1) + T(T(2)))) - T(T((T(5) - 4)))) × (-6))
12547 := (1 - (T(T(2)) × (T(T(5)) - T(T((4 + 7))))))
12549 := -((T(T(T(1 + 2)))) + ((T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4)))) × 9))
12552 := (((1 + T(T((T(T(2)) + 5)))) - (T(T(5)))) × T(T(2)))
12553 := (T((1 + T(T(T(2)))) - (-T(5) × T((T(5)/3))))
12555 := ((-1) + T((2 + 5))) × T((T(5) + T(5)))
12557 := (-1) + ((T(T(2)) - (T(T(5)) × T(5))) × (-7))
12558 := ((1 + 2) × T((55 + T(8))))
12564 := -(((T(T(1 + 2))) + T(T(5))) - (T(T(6)) × T(T(4))))
12565 := (((-1) - T(T(2))) - (T(T(5)) × (-T(6)))) × 5
12572 := -((T((1 + T(T(2)))) - (T(T(5)) × T((7 × 2))))
12573 := (((1 + T(T(T(2)))) × T((5 + T(7)))) + T(T(T(3))))
12576 := ((1 + 2) × (T(T(-(T(5) - T(7)))) + 6))
12578 := (((-1) - (2⁵)) × T(T(7))) - 8
12579 := ((T(12) × (T(T(5)) + T(7))) + T(T(9)))
12582 := ((T(T((-1 × 2) + T(5))) + 8) × T(2))
12583 := (1 + ((T(T((-2) + T(5)))) + 8) × 3)
12585 := (-1) + (T(T((2 + 5))) × (T(8) - 5))
12586 := (T(T((1 + T(T(2)))) × ((-T(5)) + T(T(8)))/T(6))
12587 := (1 + ((T(2) + T((T(5) - 8))) × T(T(7))))
12594 := -((T(T(12)) + (-T(5)) × (T(T(9)) + T(4))))
12595 := ((1 - T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)) × T((9 + 5))))
12597 := ((12 + 5) × T((T(9) - 7)))

- 12599** := $(-1) + ((T(25) - T(9)) \times T(9))$
12617 := $((T((1 + T(2))) + (T(6))) \times (1 + T(T(7))))$
12622 := $((-1) + T(T(2)))^6 - T((T(T(T(2))))/T(2)))$
12624 := $((T(T(1 + T(2)))) \times T(T(6))) - (T(2)^4)$
12627 := $(-T(12)) + (T(T(6)) \times T((T(2) + (7))))$
12628 := $((-1) + T((2 \times T(6)))) \times (T(T(2) + 8))$
12635 := $(-1) + (T(26) \times T((3 + 5)))$
12636 := $((-1) \times T(26)) \times (-36)$
12639 := $((T(T(1 + T(2)))) \times T(T(6))) - (T(T(3)) + T(9))$
12650 := $(T(((1^2) + T(6))) \times 50)$
12653 := $(-1) + ((-2) + T(6)) \times T(T((5 + 3)))$
12654 := $(T(T((1 \times 2) + 6))) \times (T(5) + (4))$
12655 := $(T(T(1 + T(2)))) + ((-T(6)) \times T(T(5))) \times (-5))$
12656 := $((1 - T(T(2))) + T(T(6))) \times 56$
12657 := $(1 + (2 \times ((T(T(6)) - 5)) \times T(7)))$
12658 := $(1 + T(T(T(2)))) + (T((T(6) + 5)) \times T(8))$
12660 := $((1 - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(6))) \times 60$
12663 := $((T(T(1 + T(2)))) \times T(T(6))) - (T(6) + T(T(3)))$
12664 := $((T((1 + T(2 \times 6)))) + (6)) \times 4$
12668 := $(-1) + ((T(T(-(2 - 6)))) \times T(T(6))) - T(8))$
12672 := $(12 \times (T(6) + T(T(7 + 2))))$
12677 := $-((T((1 + T(T(2)))) - (T(T(6)) \times T(T((T(7)/7))))))$
12682 := $(1 + (T(2) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(2)))))$
12684 := $-((T(T(1 + 2))) - (T(T(6)) \times T(T((8 - 4))))$
12690 := $((T(T((-1) + T(T(2)))) + (T(6))) \times 90)$
12693 := $((T(T(1 + (2 \times 6)))) + T(9)) \times 3$
12695 := $-((T((1 + T(2))) - (T(T(6)) \times T(T((9 - 5))))))$
12696 := $((-1) - T((2 + T(6)))) \times (-T(9)) + T(T(6))$
12704 := $(-1) + (T((T(2) \times 7)) \times T(T(04)))$
12705 := $(T(T(T(1 + 2))) \times (70 - T(5)))$
12706 := $(1 + (T((T(2) + 7))) \times T(T(06)))$
12713 := $(1 + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(13))))$
12720 := $((-1) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7)))) \times 20$
12723 := $((T(T(1 + T(2)))) + T(T((7 + T(T(2))))) \times 3$
12724 := $((12 + 7) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
12725 := $((-1) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(5))$
12726 := $(T(T(1 + 2))) + (T((7 + T(2))) \times T(T(6)))$
12728 := $((1 - T(T(2))) + T((T(7) \times 2))) \times 8$
12733 := $(T((1 + T(T(2)))) + (T((7 + 3)) \times T(T(T(3))))$
12734 := $((1^2) + T(7)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
12735 := $((-1) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) - 5$
12738 := $((1 - T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7)))) \times (-3) + T(8))$
12742 := $(1 - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7)))) \times (-T(4)))) \times 2$
12743 := $((T((1 + T(2))) + T(7)) - (-T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
12744 := $((-1) - T((T(2) \times T(7)))) \times (-4) - T(T(T(4)))$
12745 := $((1 + T((T(2) \times 7))) \times T(T(4))) - (T(5))$
12746 := $((-1) + (T(T(2)) \times 7)) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(6)))$
12747 := $((T((1 + T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 7$
12748 := $((1 + T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times 8))$
12749 := $(-1) + ((T((T(2) \times 7)) \times T(T(4))) + T(9))$
12750 := $((1 + 2) + 7) \times T(50)$
12752 := $((-1) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(7))) - (T(T(5))) \times 2$
12755 := $((T((T(12) - 7)) - 5) \times 5)$
12756 := $(12 \times (T(7) + T(T((T(5) - 6))))$
12761 := $(1 + (T((T(2) + 7))) \times (T(T(6)) + 1))$
12767 := $(-1) + (T(T(2)) \times (76 \times T(7)))$
12768 := $(T(T(1 + 2))) \times (76 \times 8)$
12769 := $(1 + (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(7)) + (T(6)) - T(T(9))))$
12772 := $((-T((1 + 2))) - T(T(7))) \times (-T(7) + T(2))$
12773 := $(1 + ((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times (T(7) + 3))$
12775 := $((-1) + T(-((T(T(2)) - 77))) \times 5)$
12778 := $(T((1 + T(2))) + (T((T(7) + T(7))) \times 8))$
12782 := $((1 + T(2 \times T(7))) \times 8) + T(T(2))$
12784 := $((-1) + T((2 + T(7))) - (-8) \times T(T(T(4))))$
12785 := $((1 + T(-((T((T(T(2)) + T(7)) - (T(T(8))))))) \times 5)$
12787 := $((12 + 7) \times (T(T(8)) + 7))$
12788 := $((-1) + T(T(T(2)))) + (T((7 \times 8)) \times 8)$
12789 := $((T((1 + T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(7))))/(-8)) \times 9$
12792 := $(T(12) \times (-7) + T(9 \times 2))$
12795 := $-((T((-1) + T(T(2))) - (7 \times T((T(9) + T(5))))))$
12796 := $(T((1 + T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(7)) + ((T(9) + 6))))$
12797 := $(1 + ((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) + T(9)) \times T(7))$
12798 := $((T(1 + T(2))) - T(7)) \times (-T(9) - T(T(8)))$
12817 := $(1 + T(-((T(T(T(2))) - 81))) \times 7)$
12824 := $(T((1 + T(T(2)))) \times ((T(T(8)) \times T(2)) - T(T(T(4))))$
12825 := $((-1) + T(T(2))) \times T((T(8)/2)) \times T(5)$
12826 := $(1 + ((T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) \times (-T(T(2)) - T(T(6))))$
12827 := $((T((1 + T((T(T(T(2))) - 8))) \times T(2)) - 7$
12831 := $(T(T(1 + 2))) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T((3 + 1))))$
12832 := $(1 + (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T((3 - 2))))$
12834 := $((1 + 2) \times T((8 - (T(T(3)) \times (-4))))$
12840 := $(T((-1) + T(T(2)))) \times (T(8) + T(40))$
12842 := $((1 + T(2 \times 8)) - (-T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
12843 := $(12 + ((T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(3)))$
12844 := $(-T((-1) - (-2) \times T(8))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T(4))$
12845 := $(-1) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(8)) - T(T(4)))) - T(5))$
12846 := $(T((-1) + T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times T(6))$
12848 := $((T(1 + T((2 + 8)))) + T(4)) \times 8$
12851 := $(-1) + ((T(2) \times T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) - 1))$
12852 := $(T(T(1 + 2))) \times (T(8) \times (T(5) + 2))$
12853 := $(1 + (T(2) \times (-T(T(8))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(T(3))))$
12854 := $-((T(T(1 + T(T(2)))) + (T((T(8) + T(5))) \times (-T(4))))$
12855 := $((-1) - T(2)) + T((T(8) + 5)) \times T(5)$
12857 := $((1 - T((T(2) \times 8))) \times (-T(5) + T(7)))$

- 12865** := ((T((-1) + T((T(2) + 8)))) × 6) - 5
12868 := (((T(T((1 + T(T(2)))))) × T(T(8)))/T(6)) - 8
12869 := (-1) - (-286 × T(9))
12871 := (1 + (T(T(2)) × T(((T(8) + T(7)) + 1))))
12872 := ((-1) - T(2)) + ((T(T(8)) × T(T(7)))/T(T(T(2))))
12873 := (-((1 + 2)) + ((T(T(8)) × T(T(7)))/T(T(3))))
12874 := ((12 × (T(T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + T(4))
12875 := (((1 - T(T(T(2)))) × (-8 × 7)) - 5)
12876 := ((T(T(((1²) × 8))) × T(T(7)))/T(6))
12878 := (((-1) + T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(8))) - (T(T(7)) + T(8))
12879 := (T(-((1 + 2) - (8 × 7))) × 9)
12884 := ((-1) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8)) × (-T(8)) + T(T(4))))
12886 := (T(T((1 + T(T(2)))) + (T(8 × 8)) × 6)
12887 := (1 + ((T(T(2)) × T(8 × 8)) + T(T(7))))
12888 := ((T((-1) + T(T(T(2)))) × T(8)) - (-8 × T(T(8))))
12899 := ((-1) + T(T(T(2)))) + (T((8 + T(9))) × 9)
12903 := (T((1 + T(T(T(2)))) × (T(9) + T(03)))
12915 := ((T(12) + T(9)) × T((-1) + T(5)))
12924 := (-1) + (((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(9))))/(-T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4))))
12925 := ((-1) + T((T(2) + T(9))) × (T(T(2)) + (5)))
12928 := ((-1) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × (9 - 2))) × 8
12934 := (((1 + T(T(T(T(2)))) - 9) × (3 + T(T(4))))
12935 := (-1) + (T((T(2) + T(9))) × (T(3) + (5)))
12936 := ((-1) + (T((2 × 9)/3)) × T(T(6)))
12937 := (1 + ((2 × T(T((9 - 3)))) × T(7)))
12942 := (((1 + T(T((2 + 9))) - T(T(4))) × T(T(2)))
12943 := ((1 + T(T(2))) × (T((9 + T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(3))))
12945 := (((1 × 2) + T((T(9) - 4))) × T(5))
12946 := ((1 + T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-9) - (T(T(4)) × T(T(6))))
12947 := ((-1) - T((T(2) + T(9))) × (-4 + 7))
12948 := ((12 × T(T(9))) + T((4 × 8)))
12955 := (((12 × 9) × T(T(5))) - 5)
12957 := ((T(T((1 + 2))) + T((T(9) + T(5)))) × 7)
12959 := (-1) + ((-((T(2) + 9)) × T(T(5))) × (-9))
12964 := ((1 + T((2 + T((-9) + T(6)))) × 4)
12968 := ((1 - (T(T(2)) × (T(9) × (-6)))) × 8)
12969 := ((1 - (T(T(2)) × (-9) - T(T(6)))) × 9)
12972 := ((-1) - (T(2) × (T(T(9)) + T(T(7)))) × (-T(2)))
12979 := (T((1 + T(2))) + ((T(T(9)) + T(T(7))) × 9))
12984 := (12 × ((T(T(9)) - 8) + T(T(4))))
12985 := ((1 + T(T(2))) × (T(T(9)) + T(8 × 5)))
12986 := -((T(T((1 + T(2)))) - ((T(9) - T(T(8))) × (-T(6))))
12988 := (T((1 + T(T(2)))) + (T(9) × T(8)) × 8)
12992 := ((-1) - T(T(T(T(2)))) × ((-9) - T(9)) - 2)
12996 := ((T(T(((1 × 2) + 9))) - T(9)) × 6)
12997 := (T((1 + T(T(2)))) + (9 × (T(T(9)) + T(T(7))))
13021 := (1 + (T(30) × T((T(T(2)) + 1)))
13034 := (-1) - ((T(3) + T(T(T(03)))) × (-T(T(4))))
13048 := ((-T(13)) - T(T(T(04)))) × (-8)
13074 := ((-1) + (T(30) × T(7)) + T(T(4)))
13079 := (-((1 - 30)) × (T(T(7)) + T(9)))
13113 := (T((T(13) + (1 + 1))) × 3)
13122 := (((1 × 3)^{1+T(T(2))}) × T(T(2)))
13123 := (1 - ((3^{1+T(T(2))}) × (-T(3))))
13124 := (-1) + (T(T(3)) × ((-1) + T(T(2)))⁴)
13127 := (-1) + (T(3) × (1 + (T(2)⁷)))
13145 := ((1 + T((T(3) + T((1 + T(4)))))) × 5)
13146 := ((1 + ((T(3) - 1)⁴) × T(6))
13167 := ((T((1 + T(T(3 + 1)))) × (-T(T(6)))/(-T(7)))
13168 := (1 + (T(T(T(3))) × (T((1 × 6)) + T(8))))
13169 := (13 × ((-1) - T(6)) + T(T(9)))
13182 := (13 × (T(T((1 + 8))) - T(T(T(2))))
13194 := -((T(T(((1 + T(3)) + 1))) - (9 × T(T(T(4))))))
13211 := -((T(T((1 + 3))) - (T(T(2)) × T(T(11))))
13222 := (((1 - T(T(T(3))))/(-2))²) - T(2)
13223 := ((T(T(13)) × 2) + (T(T(T(2))) × T(T(T(3))))
13224 := ((T(T(13)) × T(2)) + T(T((2 × 4)))
13225 := ((1 + T(32)) × 25)
13229 := (-1) + (-T(3)) × (T(T(2)) - T(T((2 + 9))))
13242 := (((13^{T(2)}) + T(4)) × T(T(2)))
13243 := (((1 + T(3)) × T((T(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) + T(3))
13244 := ((-T((1 + 3))) + T((T(2)⁴))) × 4
13245 := (((T(T(13)) + T(2)) - T(T(T(4)))) × 5)
13246 := ((((-1) + T(T(T(3))))²/4) + (T(6)))
13247 := (-1) + (-T(3)) × (T(2) - T(T((4 + 7))))
13248 := ((T(((1 × 3)^{T(2)})) - T(4)) × T(8))
13252 := (1 + ((T(T(T(3))) + T(T((-2) + T(5)))) × T(2)))
13253 := (-13) + (T(T(2)) × T(T((5 + T(3))))
13254 := (-1) + ((T(T(T(3))) + (2 × 5)) × T(T(4)))
13255 := ((T((1 + 3)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × 55)
13256 := (-T((1 + 3))) + (T(T(2)) × T(T((5 + 6))))
13258 := ((T((1 × 3)) × T(T((T(T(2)) + (5)))) - 8)
13260 := ((-T((1 + 3))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × 60)
13261 := (((-1) + T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))))) × 6) + 1)
13262 := (((-1) + T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))))) × 6) + 2)
13263 := ((T(T((13 - 2))) × 6) - 3)
13264 := ((1 - 3) - (-T(T(2))) × T(T((T(6) - T(4))))
13265 := (-1) + ((3 × 2) × T(T((6 + 5))))
13266 := (((1 × 3) × 2) × T(66))
13267 := (1 + (T(3) × T((T(2) × (-6) + T(7))))
13268 := (((-1) + T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))))) × 6) + 8)
13269 := ((1 × 3) + (T(T(2)) × T((T(6) + T(9))))
13272 := (((1 + T(T(3) × 2)) × T(7)) × T(T(2)))

- 13278** := $-((T(T((-1) + T(3))) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(7) + T(8))))))$
13279 := $(-1) + (32 \times (T(T(7)) + 9))$
13292 := $((1 + 3) \times (2 + T(9^2)))$
13293 := $((T(T(1 + T(3))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(9)) \times T(T(3))$
13294 := $(1 + (T(T(3)) \times (T(2) + T((T(9) - T(4))))))$
13295 := $(-1) + (T(3) \times (T(T((2 + 9))) + (5)))$
13296 := $((-1) + T(3)) + T(T((2 + 9))) \times 6$
13299 := $(13 \times ((-T(2) + T(T(9))) - 9))$
13318 := $((1 - 3) + ((T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(T(8))))$
13332 := $((T(T(13) + 3) - T(T(3))) \times T(2))$
13334 := $(-1) + (((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(3))))/4)$
13335 := $((-1) + T(T(3))) \times T((T(3) \times T(3))) + (T(5))$
13338 := $((1 \times 3) \times T(3)) \times T(38)$
13339 := $(1 - (T(3 \times T(3))) \times (-T(3 + 9)))$
13355 := $(-1) + (T(3) \times (T(T((T(3) + 5)))) + T(5))$
13356 := $((T(1 \times 3)) + T(35)) \times T(6)$
13357 := $(1 + (T(T(3)) \times (T(3) + T((5 \times 7))))$
13359 := $((1 + 3) \times T(T((-3) + T(5)))) + T(T(9))$
13364 := $(-1) + (((T(3) + T(3)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4)))$
13365 := $(T(T(1 + 3))) \times (-((3 - 6)^5))$
13367 := $(-T(1 + 3)) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7))))$
13370 := $-((T(T(T(1 + 3))) - (T(3) \times T(70))))$
13371 := $((T(T(1 + 3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T((7 + 1)))$
13372 := $((1 - T(3)) + ((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(7))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
13373 := $(-((1 + 3) - ((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(7))) \times (-T(T(3))))$
13374 := $(1 + ((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(7)))) - 4)$
13375 := $((T(T((1 + 3) \times 3)) - T(T(7))) \times 5)$
13376 := $(-1) + ((33 \times T(T(7))) - (T(6)))$
13377 := $(T(13) \times ((3 \times 7) \times 7))$
13378 := $(T(T(13)) + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(8))))$
13392 := $(T(1 \times 3) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(9 + 2))))$
13393 := $(1 + ((T(T(3)) + T((T(T(3)) + T(9)))) \times T(3))$
13394 := $(-1) - ((3 - T(3)) \times T(94))$
13395 := $(T(T(13) + 3) \times (T(9)/T(5)))$
13397 := $(-1) + ((T(3) + ((3 \times 9))) \times T(T(7)))$
13398 := $((-1) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(3)) + (T(9) - 8))$
13419 := $((T(1 \times 3)) + T((T(T(4)) - 1))) \times 9$
13423 := $(T(T(13)) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(2)))) + 3)$
13425 := $((T((-1) + T(3))) \times T(42)) - T(T(5))$
13426 := $(T(1 + T(3))) + ((T(T(4)) + T(2)) \times T(T(6)))$
13427 := $(1 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(2))) + (T(7))))$
13428 := $((-1) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(4))) + (2 + T(T(8)))$
13429 := $(13 \times (-((4 - 2) + T(T(9))))$
13432 := $(T(T(13)) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(3)) + T(T(2))))$
13433 := $(-1) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(4))) + (3^{T(3)}))$
13435 := $((T((-1) + T(T(3)))) \times (4^3)) - 5$
13439 := $((-1) - T(T(T(3)))) - ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(3)))) \times (-9))$
13442 := $((-1) - T(T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T((4 \times 2))))$
13446 := $(T(T(T(1 + T(3))) + T(4))) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(6))))$
13447 := $((T((1 + 3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T((T(T(4)) + (7))))$
13452 := $((13 \times T(45)) - T(2))$
13454 := $(-1) + ((3 + T(4)) \times T(T((5 + 4))))$
13455 := $(13 \times T(((4 + 5) \times 5))$
13456 := $(1 + ((3 + T(4)) \times T(T((5) - (6))))$
13462 := $(T(T(13)) - ((T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times (-T(T(2))))$
13464 := $(T(-((1 - 34))) \times (6 \times 4))$
13465 := $((T(1 + 3))^4 + (T(T(6)) \times T(5))$
13467 := $(-1) + ((-3) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(7))$
13474 := $(-1) + (T((-T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times (7 + 4))$
13475 := $((-1) - T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times (-7 \times 5)$
13476 := $(1 + ((T(T(3)) - T(4)) \times T((T(7) + T(6))))$
13479 := $((-1) \times T(T(3))) - (T((-4) + T(7))) \times (-T(9))$
13482 := $((T(T(13) - 4)) + T(T(8))) \times T(2)$
13483 := $(1 + (((T(3) \times (-4)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3))))$
13485 := $(T(1 + T(3 + 4))) \times (T(8) - 5)$
13486 := $(1 + ((T(T(3)) + T(4)) \times T((8 + T(6))))$
13492 := $((1 + T(T(T(3)))) - (-T(4)) \times T((T(9) + T(T(2))))$
13493 := $(-1) + ((T(T(3) \times 4)) \times T(9)) - (T(3))$
13495 := $((-1) + ((T(3) \times T(4)) \times T(9))) \times 5$
13497 := $(-1) + (34 \times (-9) + T(T(7)))$
13499 := $(-1) + ((3 + T(4)) \times T(T(9)) + T(9))$
13523 := $((-1) - T(T(3))) - (-T(5)) \times T((2 \times T(T(3))))$
13524 := $((-1) \times T(3)) - (T(5)^{T(2)}) \times (-4)$
13525 := $((T(T(1 + 3))) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(2)))) - 5)$
13528 := $(T(T(T(1 + 3))) + ((T(5) + T(2)) \times T(T(8))))$
13542 := $(-((1 \times 3)) + (T(5) \times T(42)))$
13545 := $(T((-1) + T(3))) \times T(T((5 \times 4)/5))$
13546 := $((T(T(13)) + T(T(5))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times 6)$
13552 := $((1 - ((T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(5))) \times (-T(T(5)))) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
13555 := $((-1) - T(3)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(5)) - 5$
13557 := $(-((1 \times 3)) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(5)) - 7)))$
13559 := $(13 \times ((T(T(5))/T(5)) + T(T(9))))$
13560 := $((T(T(T(1 \times 3)))) - 5) \times 60$
13564 := $((T(1 + T((-3) + T(5)))) + T(T(6))) \times 4$
13566 := $((1 - T(T(3))) + T((T(5) + T(6)))) \times T(6)$
13567 := $((1 + T(T(3))) + ((T(5) \times T((6 \times 7))))$
13572 := $((1 + T(T(T(3)))) - (-5) \times T(T(7))) \times T(T(2))$
13573 := $(T(1 + T(3))) - (-T(5)) \times T((7 \times T(3)))$
13575 := $(T((-1) + T(3))) + ((T(T(5)) - 7) \times T(T(5)))$
13584 := $((T(1 + T(3))) \times T(T(5))) + T(8) \times 4$
13587 := $((T(T(1 + 3)) \times 5) + T(T(8))) \times 7$
13592 := $((-1) - T(T(T(3)))) + (((T(5) + 9)^{T(2)}))$
13593 := $((-1) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (((T(5) + 9)^3))$
13596 := $((T(T((-1) + T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - (T(T(9)) - T(T(6))))$

- 13608** := $((-1) \times T((T(3) + T(6)))) \times (0 - T(8))$
13612 := $((1 + 3) \times T((61 + T(T(2))))$
13628 := $((-1) - T(T(T(3)))) - (T(6) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(8))))$
13629 := $((-1) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(T(6 - 2)))) \times (-9)$
13632 := $((T((1 + T((T(T(3))/T(6)))) - T(3)) \times T(T(2)))$
13635 := $((T((-((1 - 3)) \times T(6))) + (T(3))) \times T(5)$
13636 := $(T(T(T((1 + 3)))) - (T(63) \times (-6)))$
13644 := $((-1) - T((T(3) + T(6)))) \times (-T((4 + 4)))$
13649 := $(-T(13)) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(9)))$
13662 := $(T((1 + T(T(3)))) \times ((T(6) + (6)) \times 2))$
13664 := $(((-1) - T(3)) + T(T(6))) \times (6 + T(T(4)))$
13665 := $((T((-1) + T(3))) \times T((T(6) + T(6)))) + T(T(5))$
13667 := $((1^3) - (-6) \times T(67))$
13668 := $(T((1 + T((T(T(3))/T(6)))) \times T(T(-(6 - 8))))$
13671 := $(T((-1) + (3 \times T(6)))) \times (7 \times 1)$
13672 := $(1 + ((T(3) \times T(67)) + T(2)))$
13673 := $(-1) + ((T(3) \times T(67)) + T(3))$
13679 := $(-1) + (3 \times T((T(T(6)) - T((7 + 9))))$
13680 := $(T(((1 \times 3) \times 6)) \times 80)$
13684 := $((T((1 + T(T(3)))) \times (6 \times 8)) + T(T(T(4))))$
13685 := $(T((13 + T(6))) \times (8 + T(5)))$
13686 := $(-T(((1 + 3) \times 6)) + (T(T(8)) \times T(6)))$
13688 := $(T((T((1 + 3)) + ((6 \times 8)))) \times 8$
13689 := $((13 + 6) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(9))$
13692 := $((T(T(T((1 + 3)))) - (T(6))) \times 9) + T(T(T(2)))$
13694 := $(-1) - ((T(T(3)) - (6 \times T(9))) \times T(T(4)))$
13695 := $(-T((T((1 + 3)) \times 6)) - (T(T(9)) \times T(5)))$
13698 := $((T((1 + T(T(3)))) \times (6 \times 9)) + T(8))$
13713 := $((-13) + T(T((7 + 1))) \times T(T(3)))$
13725 := $(T((-1) + T(3)) \times (T(T((7 + 2))) - T(T(5))))$
13728 := $((-1) + (T(37)^2)/T(8))$
13729 := $(1 + ((T(37) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9))))$
13735 := $((-1) + T(T(T(3)))) - (T(73) \times (-5))$
13736 := $(((-1) + T(3)) \times T(73)) + T(T(6))$
13739 := $(-1) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T((7 + 3))) + T(T(9)))$
13749 := $((T((1 + T(3))) \times T((T(7) + (4)))) - T(T(9)))$
13755 := $(((-1) + T((T(3) \times 7))) + (T(5)) \times T(5))$
13756 := $(1 + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T((-7) + T(5)))) - T(T(6))))$
13762 := $(T(13) - (-7) \times T(62))$
13768 := $((T(T((1 + T(3)))) \times (T(7) + (6))) - T(8))$
13771 := $(1 - (-((T(3) + T(7)) \times (T(T(7)) - 1)))$
13773 := $((1 - T(T(T(3) + 7))) - (T(T(7))) \times (-3))$
13775 := $(-1) - (3 \times (-T(T(7))) - T(T((T(7) - T(5))))$
13776 := $((T(T(13)) + T(T(7)))/7) \times T(6)$
13777 := $(1 + (((T(3) + T(7)) \times T(T(7))) - T(7)))$
13779 := $(-1) + ((3 + 7) \times T((7 + T(9))))$
13780 := $(T((1 + 3)) \times T(-(T(7) - (80))))$
13782 := $((-1) - T(T(3))) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(8) - 2))$
13783 := $((-1) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (-T(7) - (T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))))$
13784 := $((T(T((1 \times 3))) \times (-7) + T(T(8))) - T(T(4)))$
13785 := $((T((1 + (3 \times 7))) + T(T(8))) \times T(5))$
13788 := $((-1) + (T(3) \times (T(7) + T(8)))) \times T(8)$
13789 := $(1 - ((T(T(3 + 7))) - 8) \times (-9))$
13794 := $(-T(((1 + 3) + 7)) + (9 \times T(T(T(4))))$
13795 := $((T((1 + 3)) \times T((7 + T(9)))) + (T(5)))$
13797 := $((T(T(13) - T(7))) - T(9)) \times 7$
13798 := $(1 + ((3 \times 7) \times (-9) + T(T(8))))$
13817 := $(-1) - (T(T(3)) \times (8 - T(T((1 + 7))))$
13818 := $(T(T((1 \times 3))) \times (-8) + T(T((1 \times 8))))$
13819 := $(13 \times (T((8 - 1)) + T(T(9))))$
13822 := $((1 \times 3) \times 8)^{T(2)} - 2$
13823 := $(-1) + ((3 + T((8 - 2)))^3)$
13824 := $((1 \times 3) \times 8)^{T(-2+4)}$
13832 := $((T(13) \times 8) \times (T(T(3)) - 2))$
13833 := $(((-1) - T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3)) - (T(3))$
13834 := $((1 \times 3) \times 8)^3 + T(4)$
13839 := $(((-1) - T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times T(-(3 - 9))$
13842 := $((1^3) + 8) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 2)$
13845 := $((1 + T(3)) \times T(8)) \times T(T(4)) - (T(5))$
13846 := $((-1) - T((3 \times 8))) \times (-46)$
13847 := $(-13) - ((T(8) \times T(T(4))) \times (-7))$
13848 := $(((-1) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(8))) + T((4 \times 8))$
13849 := $(-((1 \times 3) + 8)) + (T(T(T(4))) \times 9)$
13851 := $(1 + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) - T((T(5) + 1))))$
13853 := $(-T((1 + T(3))) - ((T(T(8)) - 5) \times T(T(3))))$
13858 := $((T(T((1 \times 3))) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(5))) - 8$
13859 := $(-1) - (T(((3 + 8) \times 5)) \times (-9))$
13872 := $((1 - 3) + T(8)) \times (T(T(7)) + 2)$
13873 := $(13 - (-T(8)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(3))))$
13874 := $(-1) - ((3 - 8) \times T(74))$
13875 := $((1 - ((3 - T(8)) \times T(7))) \times T(5))$
13878 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((T(T(8)) \times 7) - T(8)))$
13879 := $((T(((1 - T(3)) + T(8))) \times T(7)) - 9)$
13882 := $((1 + T(T(3))) \times (T(8) + T((T(8) - 2))))$
13887 := $(-1) - (T(((3 + T(8)) - 8) \times (-T(7))))$
13888 := $((1 + (T(3) \times T(8))) \times (8 \times 8))$
13893 := $((T(T((1 \times 3))) \times T(T(8))) - 93)$
13894 := $(-1) + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) - T((9 + 4))))$
13895 := $(-T(13)) + (T(T(8)) \times T((-9) + T(5)))$
13896 := $(((-1) + T(3)) \times T((T(T(8))/9))) + (T(6))$
13912 := $((T((1 + T(T(3)))) \times T((9 + 1))) - T(2))$
13914 := $((T(T(T((1 + 3)))) \times 9) + (-1) + T(T(4)))$
13915 := $(T((1 + T(T(3)))) \times T((9 + (1^5))))$
13922 := $(-1) + ((T((T(3) + T(9)))/2) \times T(T(T(2))))$

- 13923** := $(T(13) \times T((9 + (2^3))))$
13924 := $(T((1 + 3)) - (9 \times (-T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))))$
13925 := $(-1) + ((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(2)) + (5)))$
13926 := $((((-1) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))/(-T(6))$
13928 := $((-13) - T(9)) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(8)))$
13934 := $(-1) + (3 \times ((T(T(9)) \times 3) + T(T(T(4)))))$
13937 := $-((T(T(T((1 + 3)))) + (T((T(9) + T(T(3)))) \times (-7)))$
13938 := $((-(1 \times 3)) - T(9)) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(8)))$
13940 := $((T((1 + T(3))) - T(9)) \times (-T(40)))$
13941 := $((T(T(T((1 + 3)))) + 9) \times (T(4) - 1)$
13942 := $(T(T(T((1 + 3)))) - (-9 \times T((T(T(4)) - T(2))))$
13944 := $(T(((1 + T(3 + 9))) + (4))) \times 4$
13949 := $(-1) + ((T(-((T(T(3)) - T(9)))) + T(4)) \times T(9))$
13951 := $(T(13) - (-9 \times T(T(T((5 - 1))))))$
13952 := $((1 + (T((T(T(3)) + 9)) \times T(5))) \times 2)$
13953 := $((T(13) + T(95)) \times 3)$
13955 := $((-1) - (T(3) \times T((T(9) - T(5)))) \times (-5))$
13956 := $((T((-1) + T(3))) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(5)))) + T(T(6))$
13957 := $-((T(T(T((1 + 3)))) + ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(5))) + T(7)))$
13958 := $-((T((1 + T(3))) - (T((-9) + T(5))) \times T(T(8))))$
13959 := $((T((-1) + (T(3) \times 9))) + T(T(5))) \times 9$
13962 := $((1 - 3) + T(96)) \times T(2)$
13963 := $(1 - ((-3) \times T(96)) + T(3))$
13964 := $((1 \times 3) \times T(96)) - (4)$
13965 := $((T(T(T((1 + 3)))) \times 9) - (T(6) \times (-5)))$
13967 := $(-1) + ((T(T(3)) \times (-T(96)))/(-7))$
13968 := $((1 \times 3) \times T((-9) + T((6 + 8))))$
13969 := $(1 + (3 \times T(((T(9) + (6)) + T(9))))$
13975 := $(T(((1 - T(T(3))) + T(9))) \times (T(7) + T(5)))$
13982 := $(-1) + ((T(-((3 - 9))) \times T(T(8))) - T(2))$
13983 := $((T(-((1 \times 3) - 9)) \times T(T(8))) - 3)$
13984 := $((1 + T(3)) + 9) \times (-T(T(8))) + T(T(T(4))))$
13985 := $-((T(T(T((1 + 3)))) + (T((9 + T(8))) \times (-T(5))))$
13986 := $(T((1 + ((3 \times 9) + 8))) \times T(6))$
13987 := $(1 + (T(T(3)) \times T(T((9 - 8) + 7))))$
13992 := $((T(T((1 \times 3))) \times T((T(9) - 9))) + T(T(2)))$
13993 := $(1 + ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(9) - 9))) + T(3)))$
13994 := $((T((-1) + T(3))) \times T(T(9))) + 9 - T(T(T(4)))$
13995 := $((T(T(T((1 + 3)))) \times 9) + (9 \times T(5)))$
13996 := $(1 - (3 \times (-9) - T(96)))$
14028 := $(T(T(-((1 - 4)))) \times (02 + T(T(8))))$
14049 := $((T(T(-((1 - 4)))) + T(T(T(04)))) \times 9)$
14057 := $((-1) + (T(40) \times T(T(5))))/7$
14076 := $(T(((1 \times 40) + T(7))) \times 6)$
14079 := $((-1 - 40)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(9))$
14092 := $((1 - (T(T(T(4))) \times (0 - 9))) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
14112 := $((1 - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(11)))) \times T(T(T(2)))$
14124 := $(T((1 + T(4))) \times (T((-1) + T(T(T(2)))) + 4))$
14134 := $(-1) + ((4 + T((1 + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4))))$
14144 := $((T(14) - 1) \times T((4 \times 4)))$
14146 := $((T((1 + T(T((4 - 1)))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(6)))$
14152 := $((1 - T(4)) + ((-1) + T(T(5))))^2$
14162 := $((1 + T(T(4))) \times T((1 + T(6))) - T(T(2)))$
14164 := $((1 + T(T(4))) \times T((1 + T(6))) - (4))$
14167 := $(-1) + ((T(T(4)) + 1) \times T((-6) + T(7)))$
14168 := $(((-1) + T(T(T(4)))) - (-1 - T(T(6)))) \times 8$
14175 := $(T(14) \times ((1 - T(7)) \times (-5)))$
14184 := $((-1) + T(4)) \times (T((1 \times 8)) + T(T(T(4))))$
14196 := $((1 + (T((4 + 1)) \times T(9))) \times T(6))$
14211 := $(-T(T((-1) + T(4))) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(11))))$
14217 := $(T(T(T(-((1 - 4)))) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T((1 + 7))))))$
14224 := $((T(T((1 \times 4))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4))))$
14226 := $((1 + (T(4) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times 6)$
14228 := $((-1) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(2)) \times T((2 \times T(8))))$
14229 := $((T(T((1 + 4)))^2 - T((2 \times 9)))$
14234 := $((1 + T(4)) \times (-2) + (T(3)^4))$
14235 := $((T((1 + 42)) + 3) \times T(5))$
14238 := $(((-1) + T(T(4))) \times T(23)) - T(T(8))$
14239 := $(1 + ((T(T(T(4))) + (2 \times T(T(3)))) \times 9))$
14242 := $((T(T((1 \times 4))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(2)))$
14243 := $((T(T(T((1 \times 4)))) - 2) - (-T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(3))))$
14244 := $(-1) - (T(T(4)) \times (-T(2) + (4^4)))$
14245 := $((-1) + T((T(T(4)) + (2 \times T(4)))) \times 5)$
14246 := $(1 + (T(T(4)) \times (T((T(2) + 4))) + T(T(6))))$
14247 := $((T(T((1 + 4)))^2 - T((T(4) + 7)))$
14248 := $((1 + T(4)) \times (T(T(2))^4) - 8)$
14262 := $((1 + T((T(T(4)) + (2 \times T(6)))) \times T(2))$
14264 := $((T(T((1 + 4)))^2 - T((6 + T(4))))$
14265 := $(T((-1) + T(4)) \times (2 + (T(6) \times T(5))))$
14267 := $(1 + (((T(4) \times T(T(2))) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(7))))$
14272 := $((1 \times 4) \times (-2) + T((T(7) \times T(2))))$
14273 := $(-1) + ((4 \times T((T(2) \times T(7)))) - (T(3)))$
14274 := $((-1) + T(4)) \times (T((2 \times T(7))) - T(4))$
14275 := $((1 \times 4) \times T((T(2) \times T(7))) - (5))$
14279 := $(((-1) - T((T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \times (-7)) + T(T(9)))$
14292 := $((T(T((1 + T(4)))) + T((2 \times 9))) \times T(T(2)))$
14295 := $((T(T((1 + 4)))^2 - (T((9 + 5))))$
14310 := $(T(((1 + T(T(4))) - 3)) \times 10)$
14319 := $((T((1 + T(T(4)))) - (T(3) - 1)) \times 9)$
14321 := $((1 + T(T(4))) + (T(3))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1$
14322 := $((1 + T(T(4))) + (T(3))) \times T(T((2 \times T(2))))$
14323 := $(1 - (-((4^3) - 2)) \times T(T(T(3))))$
14328 := $((T((1 + T(4))) \times T(3)) + 2) \times T(8)$

- 14334** := $(-1) + ((-4) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(3) - T(T(4)))$
14336 := $((1 \times 4)^{T(3)} \times T(T(3))) / 6$
14337 := $(1 - ((4^3)) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 7))$
14343 := $((1 - 4) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(4)) \times (-T(T(3)))$
14344 := $(1 + T((4 + T(T(3)))) \times 44$
14349 := $-((T(T(1 + T(4)))) - ((T(3) + T(4)) \times T(T(9))))$
14350 := $((1 + 4)^{T(3)} - T(50))$
14352 := $(T((-1) + (4 \times T(3))) \times 52$
14354 := $((T(1 + T(T(4)))) \times (-T(3) - T(5))) - T(4)$
14355 := $(T((-1) + T(4)) \times (-T(3) - T(5 \times 5)))$
14356 := $(1 + (T(T(4)) \times ((T(3) \times 5) + T(T(6))))$
14357 := $((T(1 + T(T(4)))) \times (-T(3) - T(5))) - 7$
14362 := $((T(1 + T(T(4)))) \times (3 + 6)) - 2$
14363 := $(-1) + ((4 \times T(T(3))) \times T((6 \times 3)))$
14364 := $(T((-1 - 4) \times T(3)) \times (T(6) \times 4))$
14365 := $((-1) \times T(4) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 65$
14373 := $((-1) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (T(T(3)) + 7))) / 3$
14374 := $((-1) + T(T(T(4)))) / 3 \times T(7) + T(4)$
14375 := $(1 + T(T(T(4)))) - (-3) \times T((-T(7)) + T(T(5)))$
14379 := $(-1) + (T(4) \times ((-3) + T(T(7))) + T(T(9)))$
14382 := $(-T((-1) + T(4))) - (-((T(T(3)) + T(T(8)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
14383 := $(-1) + (T((T(4) + T(T(3)))) \times (8 + T(T(3))))$
14385 := $(T(T((14 - 3))) + T(T(8))) \times 5$
14386 := $(1 + ((T(T((4 + 3))) \times T(8)) - T(T(6))))$
14387 := $(-((1 + 4) + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(7))))$
14388 := $-((T(1 + T(T(4)))) + ((-3) \times T(T(8))) \times 8)$
14391 := $((T(1 + T(T(4)))) + 3) \times (9 \times 1)$
14393 := $(-1) + ((T((4 + T(T(3)))) \times T(9)) - T(T(T(3))))$
14395 := $((-1) - ((4^3) \times T(9))) \times 5$
14398 := $((14 \times (-T(3)) + T(T(9))) - 8)$
14399 := $(-1) + (T(4) \times (T(T(3) \times 9)) - T(9))$
14412 := $((1 + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(41))) \times T(T(2))$
14415 := $((T(T(1 + 4))) \times T(T((4 + 1)))) + (T(5))$
14416 := $((1 + T((T(4) + 4))) \times T(16))$
14418 := $((-1) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(T(4 - 1)))) + T(8)$
14419 := $(T(T(1 \times 4))) + (T((T(T(4)) + 1) \times 9))$
14425 := $((1 + T(4))^4 - T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5))$
14426 := $(-1) + ((T(T((4 + 4))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(6))$
14427 := $((T(1 + T(T(4)))) + (T((T(4) \times T(2)))) \times 7$
14428 := $(1 + (T((-4) + T(4))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8))))$
14429 := $(-1) + ((T(4) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(T(2)))) - 9))$
14431 := $((1 + T(4))^4 - T((T(T(3)) - 1))$
14432 := $((1 + T(4)) \times ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) + T(2))$
14433 := $(T(T((-1) + T(4))) - (-((T(T(4)) + 3) \times T(T(T(3))))$
14443 := $((1 + T(4)) \times ((T(T(T(4))) + 4) - T(T(T(3))))$
14444 := $((T((-1) + T(T(4)))) \times T(4) - T((T(T(T(4)))) / T(T(4))))$
14445 := $(T((-1) + T(4)) \times (-4) + T((T(4) + T(5))))$
14446 := $((T(T((-1) + T(4))) \times T(4)) + (4^6))$
14448 := $((T(1 + T(T(4)))) + T((T(4) + T(4)))) \times 8$
14452 := $((1 + T(T(4))) - 4) + (T(T(5))^2)$
14454 := $((-1) + (4 \times T(T(4)))) \times T((T(5) - 4))$
14455 := $(T(T(1 \times 4))) + (T((T(4) + 5)) \times T(T(5)))$
14458 := $(-1) + (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(4))) \times 5) - T(T(8)))$
14460 := $((T(T(T(-(1 - 4)))) + T(4)) \times 60$
14464 := $((-1) + T(T(T(4)))) + ((4 + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4)))$
14465 := $(T((-1) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(6)) + 5))$
14466 := $((-1) - (T(4) \times (T(4) + T(T(6)))) \times (-6))$
14468 := $((14 \times T(46)) - T(T(8)))$
14472 := $(T(-(1 - 4))) \times ((-4) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(2)))$
14473 := $((1 + T(4))^4 - (T(7) \times T(3))$
14475 := $(T(T((-1) + T(4))) - ((-4) \times T(7)) \times T(T(5)))$
14476 := $((1 - T((-T(4)) + T(T(4)))) \times (7 - T(6))$
14477 := $(T((-1) + T(T(4)))) + ((4 + T(7)) \times T(T(7)))$
14478 := $(T(-(1 - 4))) + ((4 - T(T(7))) \times (-T(8)))$
14482 := $(T((T(T(-(1 - 4)))) + T(4))) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(2))))$
14483 := $(-1) + (((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(8)))) \times T(3))$
14484 := $(T(-(1 - 4))) \times ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(8)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
14485 := $((1 + T(4))^4 - T(8) - T(T(5))$
14489 := $(-1) + ((T(4) + 4) \times T((T(8) + 9)))$
14505 := $(T(14) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(05))))$
14515 := $(-((1 + 4) + ((T(T(5)) + 1) \times T(T(5))))$
14532 := $(14 \times (T((T(5) \times 3)) + T(2))$
14534 := $((-1) + T((4 \times T(5)))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
14535 := $((T(-(1 - 45))) - T(T(3))) \times T(5)$
14552 := $(-1) - (-((T(T(4)) + (T(T(5)) / T(5)))) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$
14553 := $((-1) + (4^{T(5)/5}) \times T(T(T(3))))$
14559 := $-((T(1 + T(4))) - ((T(5 \times 5)) \times T(9)))$
14562 := $((T(T(1 + T(4)))) + (-T(5) + T(T(6)))) \times T(T(2))$
14564 := $((1 + T(4)) \times ((T(5) - T(T(6))) + T(T(T(4))))$
14567 := $((1 + T(((T(4) / 5)^6)) \times 7$
14568 := $((T(T(1 + 4))) \times T(T(5))) + (T(6) \times 8)$
14569 := $-((T(T(-(1 - 4)))) - ((5^6) - T(T(9))))$
14573 := $(-1) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(5))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(3))))$
14574 := $(-1) + (T(T(4)) \times (-T(5) - (T(7) \times T(4))))$
14575 := $((T((T(1 + T(4))) + (T(5)))) - (T(T(7)))) \times 5$
14576 := $((1 - T(T(4))) + (5 \times T(76)))$
14583 := $((1 + T(4)) \times (T(T(5) + T(8))) - 3$
14584 := $(-1) + ((T((4 \times T(5))) \times 8) - T(T(4)))$
14585 := $(-1) + ((-4) + T(5)) \times T((T(8) + T(5)))$
14586 := $(T(1 + T(4))) \times (5 + (T(8) \times 6))$
14587 := $((-14) - T(5)) + (T(8) \times T(T(7)))$
14589 := $((-1) - (45 \times T(8))) \times (-9)$
14595 := $((1 - T((T(4) + T(5)))) \times (-T(9))) + (T(5))$
14597 := $((T(((1 + 4) \times 5)) \times T(9)) - T(7))$

- 14598** := $((-1) \times (T(5) + T(98)))$
14608 := $((1 \times 4) - T(60)) \times (-8)$
14616 := $(T((14 - 6)) \times T(T((1 + 6))))$
14625 := $((-1) \times T(25))$
14626 := $(1 + (T((4 + T(6))) \times T((T(2) + (6))))))$
14627 := $((1 + T(4)) + ((6^2) \times T(T(7))))$
14631 := $(1 + (T((T(T(4)) + (T(6)))) \times (T(3) - 1)))$
14632 := $((1 - T((T(4) \times 6))) \times (-T(3) + 2))$
14634 := $((-1) + T(T(4))) \times ((6^3) + T(T(4)))$
14635 := $((1 + T((T(T(4)) + T(T((6 - 3)))))) \times 5)$
14636 := $((-1) + ((4 + (T(T(6)) \times 3)) \times T(6)))$
14637 := $((-1) \times ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(3))) + T(7)))$
14639 := $((-1) + (T(4) \times (-T(6)) + T((T(3) \times 9))))$
14652 := $((-1) - T(4)) \times (T((T(6) + T(5))) \times (-2))$
14655 := $((T(T(1 + T(4)))) - (-6 \times T(T(5)))) \times 5$
14656 := $((1 + T((T(T(4)) + (T(6)))))) \times 5 + (T(6))$
14657 := $((-1) + ((T((T(T(4)) + (T(6)))) \times 5) + (T(7))))$
14664 := $((T(T(1 + 4))) - (T(T(6)) \times 64))$
14665 := $((-1) - T((T(T(4)) + (T(6)))) - 6) \times (-5)$
14672 := $((1 + T(T(4))) + ((6 \times T(T(7))) \times T(T(2))))$
14676 := $((T((1 \times 4)) + (6 \times T(T(7)))) \times 6$
14678 := $((1 + T(T(4))) + (6)) + (T(T(7)) \times T(8))$
14679 := $((-14) + (T(T(6)) \times (-7))) \times (-9)$
14682 := $((T(T(1 \times 4))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(8))) - T(2)$
14683 := $(1 + ((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(8))) - 3))$
14684 := $((1^4) + ((T(T(6)) + T(8)) \times T(T(4))))$
14685 := $((1 + T(4)) \times ((T(T(6)) + T(8)) \times 5))$
14686 := $(1 + (T((4 + 6)) \times (T(8) + T(T(6))))$
14688 := $(T(-((1 - 4))) \times (68 \times T(8)))$
14697 := $((T((1 + T(4))) - (T(6) \times T((9 + T(7))))))$
14700 := $(T(T(-((1 - 4)))) \times 700)$
14718 := $(T((1 + T(4))) \times (T(T((7 - 1))) - 8))$
14724 := $((-1) + T(T(7))) \times T((2 \times 4))$
14727 := $((-1) + ((T((4 + T(7))) - 2) \times T(7)))$
14728 := $((1 + T(T(4))) \times (7 + (2^8)))$
14735 := $((T((1 + 4)) + T(T(7))) \times 35)$
14736 := $(T(T(1 + 4))) + (T(T(7)) \times 36)$
14738 := $(14 + ((T(T(7)) + 3) \times T(8)))$
14739 := $((-T((1 + T(4)))) \times (7 - T(T(T(3)))) - T(9))$
14742 := $((-1) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(7)) \times 42$
14743 := $(1 - ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(7)))) \times (-T(4) + 3)))$
14749 := $((1 + T((-4) + T(7))) \times 49)$
14752 := $((1 - T(T(4))) + T(T(7))) + (T(T(5))^2)$
14756 := $((-1) \times 4) \times (T(T(7)) - T((T(5) \times 6)))$
14759 := $((-1) + (-((T(4) - T(7))) \times T((-5) + T(9))))$
14763 := $(T((-1) + T(4)) + T(7)) \times T(T((6 - 3)))$
14764 := $((T(T(1 + T(4))) - 7) \times 6) + T(T(T(4)))$
14766 := $((1 + ((4 + T(T(7))) \times 6)) \times 6)$
14767 := $((1 \times 4)^7 + (T(T(6)) \times (-7)))$
14774 := $((T(((1 \times 4) + T(7))) \times T(7)) - T(4))$
14777 := $((T(((1 \times 4) + T(7))) \times T(7)) - 7)$
14778 := $((T((-1) + T(4)) \times 7) \times 7) + T(T(8))$
14782 := $((T((1 + T(4))) \times (T(7) \times 8)) - 2)$
14783 := $((-1) + ((T(4) + T(7)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3)))$
14784 := $((1 \times 4) \times 7) \times T((8 \times 4))$
14785 := $(1 + (T((4 + T(7))) \times T((-8) + T(5))))$
14787 := $((-1) - (4^7)) - T((8 \times 7))$
14788 := $((1 + 4) + T(T(7))) \times T(8) - 8$
14795 := $((-1) \times T(T(4))) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(9) \times T(5)))$
14796 := $(1 + (T(T(4)) \times ((-7) + T(9)) + T(T(6))))$
14797 := $((-1) - ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(7)) \times (-9))) \times 7))$
14812 := $((1 + T((4 \times 8))) \times T((1 + T(T(2))))$
14819 := $((-1) + (T((4 + 8)) \times T(19)))$
14822 := $((-1) + (-T(4)) \times T((T(8) + 2))) \times (-2)$
14823 := $((-1) + T(4)) \times (T((T(8) + T(T(2)))) - T(3))$
14825 := $((1 + (4 \times T((T(8) + 2)))) \times 5)$
14826 := $((T(((1^4) + T(8))) + T(2)) \times T(6))$
14827 := $((-1) + 4) + (T(8) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))))$
14829 := $((T(T(T(-((1 - 4)))))) \times (8^2)) + T(9))$
14835 := $((-1) + T((4 \times (8 + 3)))) \times T(5)$
14837 := $((1 + 4) + (T(8) \times (T(3) + T(T(7))))$
14838 := $((-1) + T(T(4))) + ((-8) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-8))$
14844 := $((-1) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((8^4) \times 4)$
14845 := $((T((-1) + T(T(4)))) \times T((8 - 4))) - 5$
14847 := $(T(T((1 + T(4)))) + (-T(8)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(7))))$
14849 := $((-1) + (T(4) \times T(((T(8)/4) + T(9))))$
14852 := $((1 - (-4) \times T(85))) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
14853 := $((1 + T(-((T(T(T(T(4) - 8)))) - (T(T(5)))))) \times 3)$
14859 := $((-1) + T(T(4))) \times T((8 + T(5))) - T(9)$
14861 := $((1 + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(8)) \times (-T(6) - 1)))$
14865 := $((1 + T(-((4 - (8 \times 6)))))) \times T(5)$
14868 := $(T(T(-((1 - 4)))) \times (T(T(8)) - (-6 - T(8))))$
14872 := $((T((1 \times 4)) + T(T(8))) \times (T(7) - T(T(2))))$
14873 := $(1 + ((T(4) + T(T(8))) \times (T(7) - T(3))))$
14874 := $((1^4) + T(8)) \times (T(T(7)) - 4)$
14875 := $((T((-1) + T((4 + 8)))) - T(7)) \times 5$
14877 := $((-1) + T(4)) \times T((8 + (7 \times 7)))$
14883 := $((1 + T(4)) \times ((T(T(8)) + T(T(8))) + T(T(3))))$
14894 := $((-1) + (((T(T(T(4))) \times 8) + T(T(9))) + T(T(T(4))))$
14895 := $((-1) + T(T(4))) \times T(8) + T(T(9)) \times 5$
14896 := $(14 \times ((8 + T(T(9))) + T(6)))$
14916 := $(T(T(1 + T(4)))) + (T((9 + 1)) \times T(T(6)))$
14922 := $((1 + T(T(T(4)))) + (T((T(9) - 2))) \times T(T(2)))$
14924 := $((14 \times T((T(9) + T(2)))) - T(T(T(4))))$

- 14925** := $((1 + 4) \times ((T(T(9)) \times T(2)) - T(T(5))))$
14927 := $((14 + T(9)) \times T(-((T(T(2)) - T(7))))$
14928 := $((T(T(1 + T(4)))) + (T(T(9)) / (-T(2)))) \times 8$
14937 := $((T((1 + 4)) \times T(T(9))) + (T(T(3)) \times (-T(7))))$
14939 := $(-1) + (T(4) \times (9 + T((T(3) \times 9))))$
14951 := $(1 + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) \times T((5 - 1))))$
14952 := $((1 - ((T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) \times (-5))) \times 2$
14954 := $(14 - (9 \times (-T(T(5))) - T(T(T(4))))$
14955 := $((14 \times T(T(9))) + T((T(5) + T(5))))$
14963 := $(-1) + (4 \times T((9 - (T(T(6)) / (-3))))$
14964 := $((1 \times 4) \times T((96 - T(4))))$
14972 := $(-1) + ((T(4) + T((9 + T(7)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
14973 := $((T((1 \times 4)) + T((9 + T(7)))) \times T(T(3)))$
14977 := $-((T((-1) + T(4)) - ((9 + T(7)) \times T(T(7))))$
14982 := $((1 - 4) + ((T(9) \times T(T(8))) / 2)$
14984 := $(-1) + (((T(4) \times 9) \times T(T(8))) / 4)$
14985 := $((T(((1 + 4) \times 9)) - T(8)) \times T(5))$
14986 := $(T(T((1 \times 4))) + ((-T(9) - T(T(8))) \times (-T(6))))$
14987 := $((14 \times (T(T(9)) + T(8))) - 7)$
14993 := $((T((1 + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9)))) / (-3))$
14994 := $(14 \times (T(T(9)) + (9 \times 4)))$
15124 := $(-1) + ((-5) \times T(T((1 + T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
15125 := $((-1) - T(T(5))) \times (-125)$
15126 := $((1 + (T(T(5)) \times T(T((1 + 2)))) \times 6$
15128 := $(T((1 + (5 \times 12))) \times 8$
15136 := $((1 + T(5)) \times T(((1 + T(T(3))) + (T(6))))$
15148 := $((-1) + T(5)) \times (1 + T((T(4) + T(8))))$
15177 := $(1 - ((T((T(5) + 1)) + T(T(7))) \times (-T(7))))$
15195 := $((-1) - T((5 + 1))) + T(T(9)) \times T(5)$
15196 := $(1 - (-T(5)) \times ((-1) + T(T(9))) - (T(6))))$
15209 := $(-1) - (T(5) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(09))))$
15217 := $(-1) + (((5^{T(T(2))}) - 1) - T(T(7)))$
15218 := $((-1) + (5^{T(T(2))}) - T(T(-((1 - 8))))$
15224 := $((-1) - (-T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
15225 := $((1 + T((T(5) \times T(2)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(5)$
15226 := $(1 + ((T((5 + T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(6))))$
15228 := $((T(15) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(2) \times T(8)))$
15232 := $((1 - T(T(5))) \times ((2^{T(3)}) \times (-2)))$
15236 := $(-T(-((1 - 5))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(T(T(3))) / T(6))))$
15238 := $((1 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(2))) \times T(T(3)) - 8$
15239 := $(-1) + (-T(5)) \times ((-2) + T(T(3))) - T(T(9))))$
15241 := $((-1 \times 5) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(4) + 1))))$
15242 := $((1 - 5) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((-T(4) + T(T(T(2))))))$
15243 := $((T(T(1 + 5))) \times T((T(T(T(2))) - T(4)))) - 3$
15244 := $(-T((1 + T(5))) - ((-2) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(4)))$
15245 := $(-1) + (T(T(T(5 - 2))) \times T((-4) + T(5)))$
15246 := $((-1) - T(T(5))) \times (T((2 + 4)) \times (-6))$
15247 := $((1 \times 5)^{T(T(2))} - T((T(T(4)) - T(7))))$
15248 := $((15 + T((T(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) \times 8$
15252 := $((-1) + (5^{T(2)})) \times (T(T(5)) + T(2))$
15255 := $((1 + T(T(5))) + T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) + (T(5))$
15256 := $(T((1 + T(5))) + ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(5))) \times T(6)))$
15262 := $((1 + T(5)) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(T(6)) / T(T(T(2))))))$
15264 := $(-T((1 + T(5))) - (-T(-((2 - 6)))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
15266 := $(-1) + ((T((5 + T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6))) + (T(6)))$
15274 := $((1 \times 5)^{T(T(2))} - T(T(7))) + T(T(4))$
15286 := $((1 + T(T(5)))^2 + T(T(8))) - (T(6))$
15287 := $(-1) + ((T((5 \times T(2))) - T(T(8))) \times (-T(7)))$
15288 := $((T((1 + 5)) \times T((T(T(T(2))) - 8))) \times 8$
15293 := $((-1) - ((-5) \times T(2)) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(T(3)))$
15295 := $((1 - T(T(T(5 - 2)))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(5))))$
15298 := $((1 + T(T(5)))^2 - 9) + T(T(8))$
15299 := $(-1) + (-T(5)) \times ((T(T(2)) + 9) - T(T(9)))$
15312 := $(T(((1 \times 5) + T(3))) \times (1 + T(T(T(T(2))))))$
15313 := $(1 + (T((5 + T(3))) \times (1 + T(T(T(3))))))$
15318 := $((T((1 + 5)) + (3 - 1)) \times T(T(8)))$
15323 := $((-1) + T(5)) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(2)^{T(3)}))$
15324 := $(-1) + ((5^{T(3)}) - T(24))$
15325 := $((-1) - T(5)) + T(T((T(3) \times 2))) \times 5$
15326 := $((1 + (5^{T(3)})) - T((T(2) + T(6))))$
15328 := $(T(-((1 - 5))) + ((T(T(3)) + 2) \times T(T(8))))$
15335 := $((1 - T(5)) + T(T((T(3) + T(3)))) \times 5$
15336 := $(T((-1) + ((T(5) - 3) \times T(3))) \times 6$
15337 := $((T((1 + 5)) \times (3^{T(3)})) + T(7))$
15352 := $((1 + ((T(T(5)) + (T(3))) \times T(T(5)))) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
15354 := $(-1) - (-5) \times (T(T((-3) + T(5))) - T(4))$
15355 := $((-T(-((1 - 5))) + T(T((-3) + T(5)))) \times 5$
15357 := $(-T(15)) - (T(T((T(3) + 5))) \times (-7))$
15359 := $(-1) - (-T(5)) \times (-((T(3) + 5)) + T(T(9)))$
15364 := $((T((1 + 5)) \times (3^6)) + T(T(4)))$
15365 := $(-1) + ((T((5 + T(3))) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(5)))$
15366 := $(T(15) + (T(T(T(3))) \times 66))$
15367 := $((1 + (5^{T(3)})) - T(T(6))) - T(7)$
15368 := $((-1 \times 5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 68$
15372 := $((1 + 5) \times ((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(2))))$
15373 := $((1 + (5^{T(3)})) - T((T(7) - T(3))))$
15375 := $((-1) - T(53)) + (7^5)$
15378 := $((1 + 5) + ((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) \times T(8)))$
15382 := $(T((1 + T(5))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T((8 + T(2))))))$
15384 := $((1 + 5) - (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(8))) / (-T(4)))$
15386 := $((1 \times 5)^{T(3)} - 8) - T(T(6))$
15389 := $(-T((1 + T(5))) - (T(-((3 - 8))) \times T(T(9))))$
15390 := $(T(((1 + 5) \times 3)) \times 90)$

- 15392** := $((-1) + (T((T(5) + 3)) \times (-T(9)))) \times (-2)$
15393 := $((-1) + (5^{T(3)})) - T(T((9 - 3)))$
15394 := $(-1) + ((5 \times T(T((3 + 9)))) - T(4))$
15395 := $-((T(-(1 - 5))) + (T(T((3 + 9))) \times (-5)))$
15396 := $((1 + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))) + T(9))) \times 6)$
15397 := $(-1) + ((5 \times T(T((3 + 9)))) - (7))$
15398 := $(1 + ((5 \times T(T((3 + 9)))) - 8))$
15399 := $(T(((1 + T(5)) - 3) + T(9))) \times 9$
15506 := $((1 - T(T(5))) + (5^{06}))$
15509 := $((-1) - T(5)) - ((-T(5)) \times T(T(09)))$
15518 := $(((-1) + T(T(5))) \times T((T(5) + 1))) - T(T(8))$
15519 := $((-1 + 5)) - ((-T(5)) \times T(T((1 \times 9))))$
15520 := $-((T((-1) + T(5))) - (5^{T(T(2+0))}))$
15521 := $-((T((-1) + T(5))) - ((5^{T(T(2))}) + 1))$
15522 := $((15 \times T((T(5) \times T(2)))) - T(2))$
15523 := $(1 + ((T(5) \times T((T(5) \times T(2)))) - 3))$
15524 := $(-1) + (T(5) \times T((T((5 \times 2)) - T(4))))$
15525 := $(T((15 \times (5 - 2))) \times T(5))$
15526 := $(1 + (T(5) \times T(T(((5 - 2) + 6))))$
15527 := $(1 + ((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(2)))) + T(T(7))))$
15528 := $-((T((-1) + T(5))) - ((5^{T(T(2))}) + 8))$
15529 := $(1 + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(5))) + T((2 + T(9))))$
15532 := $(1 + ((T(5) \times T((T(5) \times 3))) + T(T(2))))$
15534 := $(-1) + ((T(5) \times T((T(5) \times 3))) + T(4))$
15535 := $(T(-(1 - 5))) - ((-T(5)) \times T((3 \times T(5))))$
15539 := $((-1) + T(5)) - ((5 \times 3) \times T(T(9)))$
15541 := $(1 - (-T(5)) \times (T(T((5 + 4)) + 1)))$
15544 := $(-1) + ((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(4))) - T(T(4)))$
15545 := $((T(-(1 - 5))) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) - 5)$
15546 := $((15 \times T(T((5 + 4)))) + (T(6)))$
15547 := $((T(T(((1 + 5) + 5))) + T(4)) \times 7)$
15548 := $((-1) + (T(T(5))/5)) \times (T(4) + T(T(8)))$
15555 := $(((-1) + T(5)) - (5^5)) \times (-5)$
15556 := $((1 + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(5)))) + (5 \times T(T(6))))$
15564 := $((-1) + (5^6)) - T(T(4))$
15565 := $-((T(T(-(1 - 5)))) - ((5^6 - 5)))$
15567 := $(-1) - ((556) \times T(7))$
15568 := $-(((T(1 + 5)) - (5^6)) + T(8))$
15569 := $(-1) + ((T((5 \times 5)) + T(6)) \times T(9))$
15579 := $((T((1 + T(5))) \times T(T(5))) - T((-7) + T(9)))$
15582 := $((1 + T(((T(5) + T(5)) + 8))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
15588 := $(-1) + ((5^{T(-5+8)}) - T(8))$
15593 := $(-1) + ((-T(5)) \times (-5 - T(T(9)))) - T(3))$
15594 := $((-1) + T(5)) - ((-T(5)) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(4))$
15595 := $((-1 \times 5)) - ((5 + T(T(9))) \times (-T(5)))$
15597 := $((1 \times 5)^{T(5-9)} - T(7))$
15599 := $((-1) + T(T(5))) - ((-T(5)) \times T(T(9))) + T(9))$
15603 := $((-1 - (5^6)) - T(T(03)))$
15608 := $(((-1) - T(T(5))) - T(60)) \times (-8)$
15610 := $(T(-(1 - 5))) \times (T(6) + T(T(10)))$
15614 := $((-1 - (5^6)) - T((1 \times 4)))$
15615 := $((1 \times 5)^6 - T(-(1 - 5)))$
15620 := $((1 + (5^6)) - T(T((2 + 0))))$
15625 := $((1 \times 5)^{T(6+2-5)})$
15627 := $((1 + (5^6)) - T(T(2))) + (7)$
15628 := $((-1 - 5)) - (T(62) \times (-8))$
15629 := $((1 + (5^6)) - T(T(2))) + 9$
15641 := $((1 + (5^6)) + T((4 + 1)))$
15643 := $((1 + ((5^6) - 4)) + T(T(3)))$
15644 := $((-1 - (5^6)) + T(4)) + T(4)$
15646 := $((1 \times 5)^{T(6-4)} + (T(6)))$
15647 := $((1 + (5^6)) + T(T(-(4 - 7))))$
15652 := $((-1 - (5^6)) + T((5 + 2)))$
15653 := $(T(((1^5) + 6)) + (5^{T(3)}))$
15654 := $((-1 - (5^6)) + (T(T(5))/4))$
15657 := $((-1 - ((5^6) + 5)) + T(7))$
15659 := $(-1) + ((-T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) - T((5 + T(9))))$
15664 := $((-1 - 5)) \times T((T((6 + 6)) + T(4)))$
15665 := $((T(-(1 - 5))) + T(T(6))) \times 65$
15666 := $((-1 - (5^6)) + T(6)) + T(6)$
15668 := $((1 + ((5^6) + 6)) + T(8))$
15673 := $((-1 - (5^6)) + T(7)) + T(T(3))$
15674 := $((1 + ((5^6) - 7)) + T(T(4)))$
15675 := $((-1) + T((T(T(5))/6))) \times 75$
15682 := $((1 + T(T(5))) - ((-T(6)) \times T((T(8) + 2))))$
15683 := $((1 + (5^6)) + T(8)) + T(T(3))$
15687 := $((T((-1) + T(5))) \times T(6)) + T(8)) \times 7$
15692 := $((1 + (5^6)) + T((9 + 2)))$
15695 := $((1 + (5^6)) - (T(T(9))/(-T(5))))$
15697 := $((-1 - (5^6)) + T(9)) + T(7)$
15707 := $(-1) - (T((5 + T(7))) \times (0 - T(7)))$
15718 := $((-1 - 5)^7 - T(T((1 \times 8)))$
15725 := $((-1) + T((5 \times 7))) \times 25$
15729 := $-((T((-1) + T(5))) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(2)) - T(9))))$
15731 := $(1 - ((T(T(5)) - T(T(7))) \times T(T((3 + 1))))$
15732 := $((T(15) - T(7)) \times T((T(3) \times T(2))))$
15733 := $(1 + ((T(T(5)) - T(7)) \times T((3 \times T(3))))$
15736 := $(T(-(1) + T(5))) - ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))))/(-6))$
15745 := $((1 \times 5)^{T(7-4)} + T(T(5)))$
15747 := $((-1) - ((T(T((1 + 5))) + T(T(7))) - (4^7)))$
15749 := $(-1) - ((-1 - (5 \times 7)) \times T(4)) \times T(9))$

- 15750** := $(T((1+5)) \times 750)$
15752 := $((T(15) + (7)) + (5^{T(T(2))}))$
15753 := $((1 + T(T(5))) - (-7) - (5^{T(3)}))$
15755 := $((-1) - (5 \times T((7 \times 5))) \times (-5))$
15756 := $((T(T((1 + T(5)) - (7)))) \times T(5) + T(T(6)))$
15762 := $((-1) + T(((5 + 7) \times 6))) \times T(T(2))$
15785 := $((T((1 + 5)) - T(T(7))) \times (-T(8) + (5)))$
15792 := $((1 - T(5)) + T(7)) \times T((T(9) + 2))$
15793 := $(-1) - ((-5) \times T(79)) + T(3))$
15794 := $(-1) + (-T(5)) \times ((-T(7)) - T(T(9))) + T(4))$
15795 := $((1^5) - T(79)) \times (-5)$
15801 := $(1 - (-5) \times T((80 - 1)))$
15823 := $(T(T(-(1 - 5))) + (T((T(8) \times 2)) \times T(3)))$
15824 := $((1 + T(T((5 + 8)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4)$
15825 := $((-1) - T(T(5))) + T((8 \times T(T(2)))) \times T(5)$
15827 := $((-1) + T(T(5))) - (T((T(8) - T(2))) \times (-T(7)))$
15834 := $((-1) - (5 \times 8)) \times T(T((3 + 4)))$
15839 := $(-1) - (T(T(5)) \times (T((T(8) + T(3))) - T(T(9))))$
15842 := $((-1) - (T(5) \times T((8 \times 4))) \times (-2))$
15846 := $(1 + (5 \times T((8 \times 4))) \times 6)$
15848 := $((1^5) + (T(8) \times T(T(4)))) \times 8)$
15855 := $(T((-1) + T(5))) \times ((T(8) - (5)) + T(T(5)))$
15856 := $(T((-15) + T(8))) + (5^6)$
15862 := $((1 - T(5)) + (T(8) \times (T(6)^2)))$
15863 := $(-1) - ((5 - T(T(8))) \times (T(6) + 3))$
15864 := $((-1) \times 5) + T(T(8)) \times (6 \times 4)$
15866 := $(-T(-(1 - 5))) - ((T(8) \times T(6)) \times T(6))$
15868 := $((T((1 + 5)) \times T(8)) \times T(6)) - 8)$
15872 := $(-((1 - 5) \times 8)) \times T((T(7) + T(2)))$
15876 := $(T((1 + 5)) \times ((8 + T(7)) \times T(6)))$
15879 := $((-1) - (5 \times 8)) \times T(T(7)) + T(9)$
15884 := $((-1 - 5) \times (T(88) + T(T(4))))$
15897 := $(-((T(T(1 + 5))) + (-8) \times T((9 \times 7))))$
15904 := $((1 - T(T(5))) + (T(90))) \times 4)$
15912 := $(T(((1 + 5) + T(9))) \times 12)$
15917 := $(1 + ((T(5) \times (T(T(9)) - 1)) + T(T(7))))$
15924 := $(-15) - (-9) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
15925 := $((-1) - 5) + T(9) \times T(25)$
15927 := $(-1) - (((-T(5)) \times T(T(9))) + T(2)) - T(T(7)))$
15929 := $(-1) + ((59 \times T(T(2))) \times T(9))$
15931 := $((15 \times T(T(9))) + T(T((T(3) + 1))))$
15932 := $((1 - (-T(5)) \times T(T(9))) + T(T((T(3))/T(2))))$
15933 := $((-1) - (T(59) \times 3)) \times (-3)$
15934 := $((-1) \times 5) - (-9) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))))$
15935 := $((1 - 5) + ((-T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(3))))/(-T(5)))$
15937 := $((15 \times T(T(9))) + (T(3))) + T(T(7))$
15939 := $(T(T((1 + 5))) \times (-9) + T((3 + 9)))$
15943 := $(-((1 - 5)) - (-9) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3))))$
15944 := $((-1) + T(5)) - (-9) \times T((4 + T(T(4))))$
15945 := $((T((1 + T(T(-(5 - 9)))))) \times T(4)) - T(5)$
15948 := $((-1) + ((T(T(5)) - 9) \times 4)) \times T(8)$
15953 := $((-1) - T((T(5) + 9))) \times (-53)$
15966 := $((15 \times T(T(9))) + (T(6) \times T(6)))$
15968 := $((-1) - T(5)) - ((T(9) - T(6)) \times T(T(8)))$
15972 := $((-1) - T(T(5))) \times (-T(T(9)) + T((7 \times T(T(2))))$
15974 := $(-T(T(T(-(1 - 5)))) - (9 \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4))))$
15977 := $((-1) + (-((5 - 9)^7)) - T(T(7)))$
15982 := $((15 + 9) \times T(T(8))) - 2)$
15983 := $(-1) + ((-5 - 9) \times T(T(8))) \times T(3)$
15984 := $((T(15) - 9) \times T(8)) \times 4)$
15994 := $((1 + T(59)) \times 9) + T(T(4))$
16128 := $((-1) \times T((61 + 2))) \times (-8)$
16169 := $(-1) - (T(T(6)) \times (-1 + 69))$
16170 := $((-1) \times T(T(6))) \times (-1 \times 70)$
16171 := $(1 - (T(T(6)) \times (1 - 71)))$
16192 := $(T((1 + T(6))) \times ((1 - 9)^2))$
16195 := $((1 - T(6)) - (T((1 + T(9))) \times (-T(5))))$
16199 := $(-1) - (T((6 - 1)) \times (-T(9) - T(T(9))))$
16215 := $(T((1 + T(((6 + 2) + 1)))) \times T(5))$
16224 := $(T((-1) + T(6))) - 2 \times T((2 + T(4)))$
16228 := $(T((1 + T(6))) \times (2^{T(T(2))})) + T(8)$
16233 := $((T((1 + 6))^2 \times T(T(3))) - T(T(T(3))))$
16235 := $(-1) + (T((T(T(6))/T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(5)))$
16236 := $((-1) + T((T(6) \times 2))) \times (3 \times 6)$
16240 := $(T(T(-(1 - 6) - 2))) \times 40$
16244 := $((1 - (T(T(T(6)/T(2)))) \times (-T(4))) \times 4)$
16250 := $(T(((1 + T(6)) + T(2))) \times 50)$
16253 := $(-1) + (T((T(6) \times 2)) \times (T(5) + 3))$
16254 := $((1 + T((T(6) + T(2)))) \times 54)$
16272 := $((1 + T(T(6))) - T(T(2))) \times 72$
16275 := $((1 + (6^{T(2)})) \times 75)$
16282 := $(T(T((1 + 6))) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(8))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
16291 := $((1 - 6)^{T(T(2))} + T(T((9 - 1))))$
16296 := $((T((1 + T(6))) + T(T(2))) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(6))$
16297 := $(1 + (-T(6)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(9)) - T(7))))$
16315 := $((T(16) \times T(T((T(3) - 1)))) - 5)$
16318 := $(1 - ((T(6) \times T(T(3))) \times (-1 - T(8))))$
16334 := $(-1) + ((T((T(6) + 3)) - 3) \times T(T(4)))$
16335 := $((T(16) \times T((-T(3)) + T(T(3)))) + T(5))$
16338 := $(T((-1) + T(6))) + (T((3 \times T(T(3)))) \times 8)$
16340 := $((1 - T(6)) \times (3 - T(40)))$
16344 := $((-16^3) + T(4)) \times (-4)$
16347 := $(-1) - ((6 \times T(3)) - (4^7))$

- 16348** := $((16^3) \times 4) - T(8)$
16349 := $(-1) + ((T(6) - T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(9))))$
16364 := $(-T(16)) + (T((3 + T(6))) \times T(T(4)))$
16365 := $((T((-1) + T(6))) \times T((T(3) + (6)))) - (T(5))$
16368 := $((1 + T(6)) \times (T((T(3) + (6)))) + T(T(8)))$
16374 := $((1^6 + 3^7) - T(4))$
16379 := $(-1) + (T(6) \times T(((3 \times T(7)) - T(9))))$
16395 := $((T((1 \times 6)) \times T(39)) + T(5))$
16396 := $(16 + (T(39) \times T(6)))$
16412 := $(T((1 + 6)) + (4^{1+T(T(2))}))$
16422 := $((1 + 6) \times T((T(4^2))/2))$
16423 := $((T((1 + T(6))) \times (4^{T(2)})) + T(T(T(3))))$
16432 := $((16 \times T(T((4 \times 3))))/T(2))$
16434 := $((T((1 + T(6))) - 4) \times T((T(T(3)) - T(4))))$
16435 := $((T((1 + T(6))) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(5))))$
16442 := $((-1) + T((6 \times 4)) \times T(T(4))) - T(2)$
16444 := $(-1) - ((-T((6 \times 4)) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(4)))$
16445 := $(-((T((1 + T(6))) \times (T(T(4)) - T((T(4) + (5))))))$
16450 := $((-1) - (-6 \times T(T(4)))) \times 50$
16455 := $((1 + T((6 + T(4)))) \times T(T(5))) + (T(5))$
16456 := $(T(16) \times (T(T(4)) + (T((5 + 6))))$
16464 := $((-1) + T(6)) + (4^6) \times 4$
16469 := $(-1) + (T(((6 + 4) \times 6)) \times 9)$
16471 := $((T((1 + T(6))) \times T(T(4))) + (T(71)))$
16478 := $((1 + T(6)) \times ((T(T(4)) + T(7)) + T(T(8))))$
16479 := $((1 + T((-6) + T((4 + 7)))) \times 9)$
16480 := $((T((-1) + T(6))) - 4) \times 80$
16482 := $((1 + T(64)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(2))$
16491 := $(-((T((1 + T(6))) - 4) \times T(91)))$
16492 := $((1 + (T((6 \times T(4)) \times 9)) + T(T(T(2))))$
16493 := $((16 \times (-4) + T(T(9))) - 3)$
16495 := $((1 - 6) + (T(T(4)) \times T((9 + T(5))))$
16496 := $(16 \times ((-T(4)) + T(T(9))) + (6))$
16497 := $(-1) + ((T((6 \times T(4))) \times 9) + T(7))$
16529 := $(1 - ((T(6) - 5) \times (2 - T(T(9))))$
16534 := $(-T(T((1 + 6)))) + ((5 + T(3)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
16539 := $((-1) \times T(6)) + ((-5) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(9))$
16544 := $((1 - T(T((-6) + T(5)))) \times (-4 \times 4))$
16545 := $((16 \times T(T((5 + 4))) - T(5))$
16551 := $((T(16) \times T(T(5))) + T(T((5 + 1))))$
16552 := $((1 + (T((T(6) - 5))) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
16556 := $((T(16) \times T(T(5))) + 5) + T(T(6))$
16559 := $(-1) + ((T(6) - 5) \times T((5 \times 9)))$
16573 := $((T(16) \times T(T(5))) + T((T(7) - T(3))))$
16575 := $((-1) - T((6 + T(5)))) + (7^5)$
16576 := $((-1 - 65) \times (T(7) + T(T(6))))$
16584 := $(((-1) - T(T(6))) \times T(5) - T(T(8))) \times (-4)$
16585 := $((-T((1 + T(6)))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(8)))) \times 5$
16587 := $(-1) + ((T(6) + 5) \times (T(T(8)) - T(7)))$
16589 := $(-16) + (5 \times T((T(8) + T(9))))$
16592 := $(16 \times (T((5 \times 9)) + 2))$
16596 := $((T(16) \times T(T(5))) + T(9)) + T(T(6))$
16598 := $((-1) + 6) + (5 \times T((T(9) + T(8))))$
16599 := $((-1 \times 6) + (5 \times T((9 \times 9)))$
16605 := $((-1) \times T((T(6) + (60)))) \times (-5)$
16624 := $(16 \times (T(T((6 + T(2)))) + 4)$
16625 := $((-1) + T((6 \times 6))) \times 25$
16626 := $((-1) + (T(T(6)) \times (6 \times 2))) \times 6$
16632 := $((-1) + T((6 + 6))) \times (T(3)^{T(2)})$
16633 := $(1 + (T(T(6)) \times ((6^3)/3))$
16638 := $((1 \times 6) - ((-T(T(6))) - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(8))$
16639 := $((((-1 - 6)^6) - T(T(3))) + T(T(9)))$
16645 := $((T((1 + 6)) \times T((-T(6) + T(T(4)))) - T(5))$
16648 := $((1^6) + T(64)) \times 8$
16655 := $((-1) + (T((6 \times 6)) \times (-5))) \times (-5)$
16656 := $(16 \times (6 + T(T((5) - (6))))$
16668 := $((1 + (T(6) \times T(6)) + T(6)) \times T(8))$
16675 := $(((-1) - T(6)) \times 6) + (7^5)$
16684 := $((T((1 + 66)) \times 8) - T(T(T(4))))$
16692 := $((T((1 + T(6))) \times (T(6) + T(9))) - T(T(2)))$
16694 := $((T((1 + T(6))) \times (T(6) + T(9))) - 4)$
16695 := $((T(((1 \times 6) + 6)) + T(T(9))) \times T(5))$
16698 := $(T((1 + T(6))) \times (-6 - (9 \times 8)))$
16716 := $(((-1) + T(T(6))) + (T(71))) \times 6$
16724 := $(((-1) - T(T((6 + 7)))) + T(T(2))) \times (-4)$
16757 := $(((-1) - T(6)) + (7^5)) - T(7)$
16764 := $((1 + T((-6) + T(7))) \times T((T(6) - T(4))))$
16769 := $(-((T(16) - (7 \times T(69))))$
16775 := $(1 - ((T(T(6))/7) - (7^5)))$
16779 := $((-1) \times T(T(6))) + ((T(7) - T(T(7))) \times (-T(9)))$
16786 := $((-1) - T(6)) \times (-7 - (T(8) \times T(6)))$
16815 := $(T((-1) + T(6))) + (T(81) \times 5)$
16822 := $(1 + ((T(6) + T((T(8) + T(2)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
16824 := $((T((-1) + T(6))) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(2)))) \times 4$
16825 := $((1 + 6) + T(T(8))) \times 25$
16827 := $((-1) - ((-6) - T((T(8) - 2))) \times T(7))$
16835 := $((1 - (-6) \times T((T(8) - 3))) \times 5)$
16836 := $((T(16) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3))) - 6$
16839 := $((-T(16) \times T(8)) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(9))))$
16842 := $((T(16) + T(T(8))) \times T((4 + 2)))$
16843 := $(1 - (-T(6)) \times (T(T(8)) + T((T(4) + T(3))))$
16845 := $((1 - 6) + T((-8) + T(T(4)))) \times T(5)$
16847 := $((-1) - ((6 \times 8) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(7))))$

- 16848** := $((1 \times 6) \times T(8)) \times T((4 + 8))$
16862 := $((-1) + T(T(6))) + ((-T(8)) \times T(T(6))) \times (-2))$
16863 := $((T(16) + T(T(8))) \times T(6)) + T(T(3))$
16864 := $(T(16) \times (T((T(8) - T(6))) + 4))$
16865 := $(-1) - (-6) \times (T(T(8)) + T(65))$
16877 := $((T((1 + 68)) \times 7) - T(7))$
16884 := $(T((1 + 6)) \times ((-8) + T(T(8))) - T(T(4)))$
16896 := $((-1) - T(6)) \times (-8 \times 96)$
16905 := $((1 + 6) \times T((T(9)/T(05))))$
16912 := $((1 + T(69)) \times (1 + T(T(2))))$
16952 := $((1 + T((6 + T(9)))) + 5^{T(T(2))})$
16965 := $((((-1) + T(6)) \times T(9)) + T(T(6))) \times T(5)$
16967 := $(-1) + (T(6) \times (T((T(9) - 6))) + T(7))$
16968 := $((T((-1) + T(6)) \times 9) + T(T(6))) \times 8$
16972 := $((16 \times T(T(9))) + T(T(7))) + T(T(2))$
16982 := $(-1) - (((-6) - T(9)) \times T(T(8)))/2)$
16983 := $(T(-((T(1 + 6)) - T(9))) \times (T(T(8))/T(3)))$
16986 := $((T((1 + T(6))) + T(9)) \times (T(8) + T(6)))$
16989 := $((-1) \times T(6)) - (-T(9) \times T((T(8) - 9)))$
16992 := $((1 - (T(6) \times T(9))) \times (-9 \times 2))$
16994 := $(-1) - (T(-((T(6) - T(9)))) + 9) \times (-T(T(4)))$
16995 := $((-1) + (T(6) \times (9 + T(9)))) \times T(5)$
17073 := $((1 + T(T(7))) + T(T(07))) \times T(T(3))$
17108 := $(T((1 \times 7)) \times (-T(10)) + T(T(8)))$
17136 := $((T((17 - 1)) \times T(3)) \times T(6))$
17168 := $((1 + T((71 - 6))) \times 8)$
17172 := $((-1) + T(7)) \times ((-1) + T(T(7))) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
17185 := $(T((-1) + T(7)) + ((-1 - 8)^5))$
17196 := $((1 - T((T(7) - 1))) \times (-T(9))) + T(T(6))$
17198 := $((T(T(1 \times 7))) \times (-1) + T(9)) - T(T(8))$
17220 := $(T(-((1 - 7))) \times T((2 \times 20)))$
17224 := $(-1) - (T((T(7) - T(2))) \times (2 - T(T(4))))$
17226 := $((1 + T(T(7))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(2)) + T(6)))$
17235 := $((T(17) \times T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5)$
17238 := $((T((1 \times 7)) - 2) \times (-3) + T(T(8)))$
17239 := $(1 - ((-7) - T(T(2))) \times T((T(3) + T(9))))$
17243 := $((1 + T(T(7))) - T(T(2))) \times 43$
17247 := $(-1) - ((T(T(7)) + T((2 \times T(4)))) \times (-T(7)))$
17248 := $((T(T((1 + 7) + T(2)))) - (T(T(4)))) \times 8$
17254 := $(-1) + (7 \times ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(4))))$
17255 := $((1 + T((T(7) \times T(2)))) - T(T(5))) \times 5$
17262 := $((-1) + T(T(7))) + T(T(2)) \times (T(6) \times 2)$
17276 := $((-1) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(2)))) \times 7 + T(T(6))$
17279 := $(-1) - (((T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) - T(7)) \times (-T(9)))$
17280 := $((-1 - 7)^{T(2)}) \times 80$
17282 := $((-1) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(2)) + T(8)))) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
17283 := $((T(T(1 \times 7))) \times (T(T(2)) + T(8))) + T(T(T(3)))$
17284 := $((T((1 + (T(7) \times T(2)))) + T(T(8))) \times 4)$
17287 := $(-1) + (((T(7) - 2) \times T(T(8))) - T(7))$
17295 := $((T((-1) + T(7))) + T(T(2))) \times T(9) + T(5))$
17296 := $((T((1 \times 7))^{T(2)}) - T(96))$
17297 := $((T(T((1 \times 7))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9) - T(7))$
17298 := $((-((1 + 7)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-9)) + T(T(8)))$
17316 := $(T(T((1 + 7))) \times ((T(3) - 1) + T(6)))$
17322 := $((-1) - ((T(7) - 3)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(2))$
17324 := $(-1) - ((-7) \times T((3^2))) \times T(T(4))$
17325 := $((-1) + ((T(7) + T(3))^2) \times T(5))$
17326 := $(1 - ((73 + 2)) \times T(T(6)))$
17328 := $((T((1 + T(7))) + T(T(3))) \times (2 + T(8)))$
17329 := $((T(T((1 \times 7))) - 3) \times (-2) + T(9))$
17334 := $((-17) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (3^4)$
17342 := $((1 + T(7)) \times (T(34) + T(2)))$
17343 := $((T((1 + T((7 + T(3)))) \times 4) + T(T(T(3))))$
17346 := $(T(-((1 - 7))) \times (T(34) + T(T(6))))$
17352 := $(-T(T((1 + 7))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(5) - T(2))))$
17354 := $((1 + T(7)) + ((T(T(3)) \times T(5)) \times T(T(4))))$
17355 := $((T((-1) - (T(7) \times (-3))) - T(5)) \times 5)$
17372 := $((1 + (7 \times T(3))) \times (T(T(7)) - 2))$
17373 := $(-1) - ((7 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-73))$
17374 := $((1 \times 7) \times (-3) + T((7 \times T(4))))$
17375 := $((1 + T(7)) \times T((T(3) + T(7))) + T(T(5)))$
17385 := $((-17) + T((T(3) \times 8))) \times T(5)$
17387 := $((1 - T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(8))) - T(7))$
17388 := $(T((-1) + T(7)) \times (38 + 8))$
17389 := $(1 - ((-7) - T(T(3))) \times (T(T(8)) - T(9)))$
17394 := $(-1) - ((-7) \times T((T(T(3)) + (T(9) + 4))))$
17415 := $((-T((1 + T(7))) + T((T(T(4)) + 1))) \times T(5))$
17424 := $((T(((1 \times 7) + 4))^2) \times 4)$
17425 := $(17 \times (-T(4)) + T((T(2) \times T(5))))$
17431 := $(1 - (T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) \times (-T(3) - 1)))$
17435 := $((T(T((1 \times 7))) + T(T((4 \times 3)))) \times 5)$
17436 := $((1 - T(T(7))) \times (-43)) + T(6)$
17437 := $((T(((1 \times 7) \times T(4))) + T(3)) \times 7)$
17442 := $(T(17) \times (4 - (T(T(4)) \times (-2))))$
17445 := $((-1) + T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) + 4) \times 5$
17446 := $((-1 - 7) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(6)))$
17448 := $((T((1 + 7)) + T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) \times 8)$
17452 := $(1 - ((T(T(7) + T(T(4)))) \times (-5)) - T(T(T(2))))$
17455 := $((T(T((1 \times 7)) + T(T(4)))) + 5) \times 5$
17456 := $((-1) - T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) \times (-5)) + T(6))$
17457 := $(-1) + (T((7 \times 4)) \times (T(5) + T(7)))$
17458 := $((1 + T((T(7) - 4))) \times 58)$
17459 := $(1 - (T(T(7)) \times ((T(4)/5) - T(9)))$
17465 := $(1 - (-74) \times (T(T(6)) + 5))$

- 17469** := (((1 + T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) - 6) × 9
17472 := ((T(17) + T(T(4))) × (T(7) × T(2)))
17473 := (1 - ((T(T(7)) + T(4)) × (-7) × T(3)))
17478 := ((T((-1) + T(7))) × (T(T(4)) - (7)) - T(T(8)))
17484 := (((1 + T(7)) × (-T(4)) + T(T(8)))) - T(T(T(4)))
17492 := (-1) - ((-7) - T(4)) × (T(T(9)) - T(T(2))))
17493 := ((17 × 49) × T(T(3)))
17495 := (((1 + 7) × T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(9)) × (-5)))
17528 := (T((1 × 7)) × ((T(T(5)) / (-T(2))) + T(T(8))))
17532 := (((1 - T(T(7))) × (-T(5))) - T(T(T(3)))) × T(2)
17535 := ((1 × 7) × ((T(T(5)) × T(T(3))) - (T(5))))
17540 := ((T(17) × T(T(5))) - (T(40)))
17542 := ((1 × 7) × (T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(2))))))
17543 := (1 + (7 × (T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(3))))))
17547 := (-((1 - (7⁵))) + T((T(4) + T(7))))
17550 := (T((T(-((1 - 7))) + (5))) × 50)
17556 := (-(((1 - 7) - 5) × T(56))
17562 := ((T((1 + 75)) × 6) + T(T(2)))
17564 := (((-1) - (-7) × T(T(5))) × T(6)) - T(T(4)))
17567 := ((17 × T(T((T(5) - (6)))))) - (T(7)))
17568 := (((T((1 + T(7))) × 5) + (T(6))) × 8)
17583 := (T(17) + (5 × T(83)))
17585 := (((-1) - T(75)) - T(T(8))) × (-5)
17592 := ((17 × T((5 × 9))) - T(2))
17593 := (1 + (((T(T(7)) - (T(5))) × T(9)) - 3))
17595 := (17 × T(T((5 × 9) / 5)))
17612 := ((-1) × T(T(7))) - (T(T(6)) × (-T(12)))
17622 := ((T((1 + 7)) + T(T(6))) × T((T(T(T(2)))) / T(T(T(2))))))
17625 := ((-1) - ((T(7) × T(6)) × (-2))) × T(5)
17629 := (17 × ((6 / T(2)) + T(T(9))))
17631 := (-1) - (-76) × (T(T(T(3))) + 1))
17635 := ((1 - ((T(7) × T(6)) × T(3))) × (-5))
17639 := (-1) - ((-7) × T(6)) × T((T(3) + 9))
17640 := (T(-((1 - 7))) × (T(6) × 40))
17641 := (1 + (T(7) × T(-((6 - 41))))))
17643 := ((-1) - ((T(7) × T(6)) × T(4))) × (-3)
17644 := (((1 + T(T(7))) - (6)) × 44)
17647 := (((1 - T(T(7))) + T((T(6) + T(T(4)))))) × 7)
17648 := ((T(T((1 + 7))) + T(T((6 + 4)))) × 8)
17649 := ((T((T(-1) + T(7)) / 6)) - (T(T(4)))) × 9
17652 := (((1 + T(76)) + T(5)) × T(T(2)))
17655 := ((T(((1 + 7) × 6)) × T(5)) + T(5))
17657 := (17 - ((-T(6)) × T(T(5))) × 7)
17664 := (T((17 + 6)) × 64)
17667 := (-1) - (((T(T(7)) - (6)) + T(T(6))) × (-T(7)))
17682 := ((T(T((17 - 6))) × 8) - T(T(2)))
17684 := ((T(T((17 - 6))) × 8) - (4))
17685 := ((-1) + T(7)) × ((-6) + T(T(8)) - (5))
17688 := ((1 + 7) × T(((6) + T(8)) + T(8)))
17709 := (-1) - (-7) × (T(70) + T(9))
17714 := (17 × (7 + T(T((-1) + T(4))))))
17724 := ((-T((1 + 7))) × T(T(7))) + (T(T(T(2))) × T(T(T(4))))
17729 := ((-1) × T(T(7))) - ((T(T(7)) - T(2)) × (-T(9)))
17739 := ((1 - T(7)) × (-73 × 9))
17745 := (((1 × 7) + T((-7) + T(T(4)))) × T(5))
17748 := ((-1) - T(7)) × ((-7) - T(4)) × T(8))
17766 := ((-17) - T(T(7))) × (-T(6) + T(6))
17769 := -((T(T(-1 - 7))) + ((T(T(7)) - (6)) × (-T(9))))
17777 := (((-1) - T((7 × 7))) × T(T(7))) / (-T(7))
17784 := ((-1) + T((7 + 7))) × T((8 + T(4)))
17786 := (-1) - (-77) × T(T((8 / 6)))
17793 := ((T(T((1 + 7))) - (7)) × (9 × 3))
17794 := ((T(T((1 × 7))) + T(7)) × (T(9) - (4)))
17832 := (((-1) + T(7)) × (T(T(8)) + 3)) - T(T(T(T(2))))
17835 := ((-1) + T(T(7))) - (T(83) × (-5))
17837 := (1 - ((7 × T((-8) + T(T(3)))) × (-T(7)))
17841 := (T(17) - (-8) × T(T((4 + 1))))
17845 := ((1 - T((7 × (8 + 4)))) × (-5))
17846 := (((-1) + T(7)) × T(T(8))) - T((T(4) + (6)))
17847 := ((T((17 + 8)) × T(T(4))) - T(7))
17849 := ((1 + T(7)) - ((T(8) × T(T(4))) × (-9))
17850 := (-((1 - 7) - 8) × T(50))
17853 := ((T((1 + 7)) × T((T(8) - (5)))) - 3)
17855 := ((1 + T((-7) + T((8 + 5)))) × 5)
17856 := ((T((1 + T(7))) × (T(8) + (5))) + (T(6)))
17862 := ((1 × 78) × (T(T(6)) - 2))
17863 := (-1) + (T(T(7)) × (8 + (6 × T(3))))
17864 := (T(T((1 × 7))) × ((8 × 6) - 4))
17865 := (((-1) + T(T(7))) - 8) × T((-6) + T(5))
17867 := (17 × ((T(T(8)) - (T(6))) + T(T(7))))
17869 := (1 - ((-T(7)) × T(T(8))) + T((-6) + T(9)))
17873 := (17 - (-T(8)) × T((T(7) + 3)))
17874 := (((T((1 + 7)) + 8) × T(T(7))) + T(4))
17877 := (((-1) + T(7)) × T(T(8))) - (T((7 + 7)))
17885 := ((1 + T(7)) - (-T(8)) × T((T(8) - (5))))
17886 := (1 + ((T(T(7)) × (8 + T(8))) + (T(6))))
17891 := (-1) - (-7) × T(((8 × 9) - 1))
17892 := (((-1) + T(7)) × T(T(8))) + (T(9) × (-2))
17893 := (1 + (T(7) × (T(T(8)) - (9 × 3))))
17895 := (((-1) × T(T(7))) + 8) × (-T(9)) - (T(5))
17913 := (-1) + (T((7 + T(9))) × 13)
17927 := ((1 + T((7 + T(9)))) × (T(T(2)) + (7)))
17928 := ((T(T((1 × 7))) + (92)) × T(8))
17934 := ((T((-1) + T(7))) × T(9)) - (T(T(T(3))) × (-4))

- 17944** := ((T(-(1-7))) + (T(94))) × 4
17945 := ((T(T((1 × 7))) × T(9)) - T((T(4) + T(5))))
17946 := (1 - ((T(T(7)) × (-T(9))) + T((4 + T(6))))
17952 := ((T(-(1-7))) + T(T(9))) × (T(5) + 2)
17955 := (T(((1 - T(7)) + T(9))) × (T(T(5)) - (T(5))))
17956 := (1 - ((T(T(7)) × (-T(9))) + (T(5) × T(6))))
17964 := (T((1 + 7)) × (-((T(T(9)) + (6))) + T(T(T(4))))
17968 := (((-1) + T((7 × 9))) + T(T(6))) × 8
17969 := ((-1) - (T(T(7)) × (-T(9)))) - T(-((T(6) - T(9))))
17972 := (((1 + T(T(7))) × T(9)) - ((7^{T(2)})))
17973 := ((1 - T(7)) - (-T(9)) × (T(T(7)) - (T(3))))
17975 := (1 - (-((T(7) - 9) × T((T(7) + T(5)))))
17976 := ((T(17) + T((9 + T(7)))) × T(6))
17981 := ((T(T((1 + 7))) × (-9) + T(8)) - 1)
17982 := ((-1) + T(7)) × T(((9 × 8)/2))
17983 := ((1⁷) - ((-9) × T(T(8))) × 3)
17986 := (((1 - T(T(7))) × (-T(9))) - 8) - T(T(6))
17988 := (-((1 - 7)) - ((9 - T(8)) × T(T(8))))
17993 := ((-1) + ((T(T(7)) × T(9)) - T(9))) - T(T(T(3)))
18195 := (((-1) - T(T(8 - 1))) × (-T(9))) - T(T(5))
18197 := (((1 - T(T(8 - 1))) × (-T(9))) - T(7))
18216 := ((T((1 × 8)) × 2) × T((1 + T(6))))
18222 := (((-1) + T((8 × 2)))² - T(2))
18223 := (-1) - (-8) × T((T(2) + (2^{T(3)})))
18224 := ((1 × 8) × T(((2 × T(T(2))) + T(T(4))))
18225 := (((1 + 8)^{T(2)}) × 25)
18226 := ((T((1 + T(8))) - 2) × 26)
18227 := (-1) + ((T(T(8)) - T((2 + T(2)))) × T(7))
18228 := -((T(-(1 - 8)) × (T((2 + T(2))) - T(T(8))))
18233 := (-1) + ((T(8) + T((T(T(T(2))))/3)) × T(3))
18234 := ((1 + 8) × (T((T(2) × T(T(3)))) + T(4)))
18244 := ((-1) × T(T(8))) + (T((T(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) × T(4))
18245 := (((-1) - (T(T(8)) / (-2))) × T(T(4))) - (T(5))
18248 := ((T(((1 - 1) + T(8)) + T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) × 8
18252 := ((-1) + T((T(8) × 2))) + (5^{T(T(2))})
18253 := (T((T((1 × 8)) × 2)) + (5^{T(3)}))
18255 := ((T((1 + 8)) × T(T((2 + 5)))) - (T(5))
18265 := ((T(T(-(1 - 8))) × T((T(2) + (6)))) - 5)
18269 := ((T((1 + T(8))) × 26) - 9)
18284 := (T(-(1 - 8)) × ((-T(2)) + T(T(8))) - T(4))
18285 := ((T((1 + 8)) × T(28)) + T(5))
18286 := ((1 × 82) × (-8) + T(T(6)))
18288 := ((T((1 + T((8 + T(2)))) + 8) × 8)
18296 := ((-1) - T(T(8))) + (T(-((T(2) - T(9)))) × T(6))
18297 := (T(18) × ((T(2) × T(9)) - T(7)))
18314 := (-1) + ((T(T(8)) / (3 - 1)) × T(T(4)))
18324 := (-18) × (T(3) - (2^{T(4)}))
18333 := ((1 + 8) × (T(T(3)) + T((3 × T(T(3)))))
18342 := (-1) + (83 × (-T(4)) + T(T(T(T(2))))))
18343 := ((1 × 83) × (-T(4)) + T(T(T(3))))
18345 := ((-1) + (T(8) × 34)) × T(5)
18346 := (((1 + T(8)) × T((T(T(3)) + T(4)))) - 6)
18352 := ((1 + T(8)) × T((3 + T((5 + 2))))
18356 := ((T((1 + T(8))) + 3) × (5 + T(6)))
18359 := (-1) - (-T(8)) × (T((T(3) × 5)) + T(9))
18361 := ((-1) - T((8 × 3))) × (-61)
18365 := (-1) - ((T(T((T(8)/3))) × (-6)) + (T(T(5))))
18366 := (((1 + T(T((T(8)/3))) - (T(6))) × 6)
18369 := (((1 + 83) × T(T(6))) - T(T(9)))
18373 := (((1 + T(8)) × T((3 + T(7)))) + T(T(3)))
18375 := ((1 + (T(8) × (T(3) + T(7)))) × T(5))
18376 := (1 - (-T((8 - 3))) × T((T(7) + T(6))))
18377 := ((T((1 + 8)) × (3 + T(T(7)))) - T(7))
18378 := (-((T((1 + 8)) × T(3))) - (-T(7) × T(T(8))))
18379 := ((1 - (T(8) × (-3))) - (T(T(7)) × (-T(9))))
18384 := (((1 + 8) + 3) × (-8) + T(T(T(4))))
18388 := ((-((1 - (8³))) × T(8)) - 8)
18396 := (-((1 - 8) × T((3 + 9) × 6))
18397 := (((-1) + (T(T(8)) × (-3))) × (-9)) + T(T(7))
18417 := ((T(T((1 + 8))) + T((T(T(4)) + 1))) × 7)
18424 := (-1) - (((T(T(8)) + (4)) / (-2)) × T(T(4)))
18426 := ((-((1 + 8)) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-2))) × 6)
18433 := (1 + (8 × ((T(4) × T(T(T(3)))) - T(3))))
18435 := (-T((1 + 8)) + (T(T(T(4))) × (-3) + T(5)))
18438 := ((-1) - (-8) × T(T(4))) × (T(3) + T(8))
18440 := ((T(T(-(1 - 8))) + (T(T(4)))) × 40)
18443 := ((-1) - T(8)) + (T(T(T(4))) × (4 × 3))
18445 := ((1 - T(8)) - ((T(T(T(4))) / (-T(4))) × T(T(5))))
18449 := (-1) - ((T(T(8)) - (4⁴)) × (-T(9)))
18452 := (-T(-(1 - 8))) + (T(T(T(4))) × (T(5) - T(2)))
18453 := ((18 × (4⁵)) + T(T(3)))
18455 := (((-1) - T(84)) - T(T(5))) × (-5)
18456 := ((T(T((1 × 8) + 4)) - (5) × 6)
18462 := (-18) + (T(T(T(4))) × (6 × 2))
18463 := ((1 + T(8)) × (T((T(4) + T(6))) + 3))
18465 := ((T((T((1 + 8)) + (4))) + (6)) × T(5))
18466 := (1 - ((T(T((8 + 4))) × (-6)) + (T(6))))
18468 := ((T(T((1 × 8))) - T((-4) + T(6))) × T(8))
18472 := (-1) - (((T(8) + T(T(4))) × T(T(7))) / (-2))
18473 := (T(((1 + 8) + 4) × (-T(7)) + T(T(T(3))))
18475 := ((1 + (T((8 × 4)) × (-7))) × (-5))
18478 := ((1 - T((8 + T(4)))) - (-T(7) × T(T(8))))
18479 := (-1) - ((-T(8)) × T(T(T(4))) / T(-(7 - 9)))

- 18492** := $((-1) - T(T((8+4))) \times (-9) + T(2))$
18495 := $((1 \times 8) + T(49)) \times T(5)$
18496 := $(1 - T((8 \times T(4)))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(6)))$
18500 := $(1 + T(8)) \times 500$
18507 := $(-1) + ((T(T(8)) - 5) \times T(07))$
18508 := $(T(-((1-8))) \times (-5) + T(T(08)))$
18522 := $(T(((1^8) + 5))^{T(2)} \times 2)$
18523 := $(1 - ((-T(T(8) + 5)))) - T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(3)))$
18527 := $(-1) - (8 \times (T(T(5)) - (T(T(2)) \times T(T(7))))))$
18532 := $(T((1 \times 8)) + (T((-5) + T(T(3))))^2)$
18533 := $(-1) - ((8 + T(T((T(5) - 3)))) \times (-T(3)))$
18537 := $((1 + T(8)) \times (5 + T((3 + T(7)))))$
18539 := $(-1) - ((T(T((-8) + T(5)))) + T(3)) \times (-T(9)))$
18545 := $((-1) + T(85)) + T(T(4)) \times 5$
18546 := $((T(T(-((1-8) - 5)))) + T(4)) \times 6$
18564 := $(-((1-85)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(4)))$
18574 := $((T(18) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(7))) - T(T(T(4)))$
18583 := $((1 + T(8)) \times T((-5) + T(8))) + T(T(T(3)))$
18585 := $(T(((1-8) + T(8)) + T(5))) - T(8) \times T(5)$
18595 := $((-1) - (-8 \times T(-((T(5) - T(9)))))) \times 5$
18615 := $((-1) + T(T(8))) \times T((6+1)) - (5)$
18620 := $((-1) + T(T(8))) \times T((T(6)/T((2+0))))$
18640 := $(1 + T((T(8) - 6))) \times 40$
18642 := $((1 \times 8) + T(T(6))) \times T((T(4) + 2))$
18643 := $(1 - ((8 + T(T(6))) \times (-T((4 \times 3))))$
18645 := $(18 + T((-6) + T(T(4)))) \times T(5)$
18647 := $(-1) - (T(T(8)) \times ((-6) + T(4)) \times (-7))$
18648 := $(1 + 8) \times (T(64) - 8)$
18649 := $(1 + ((-8) + T(64)) \times 9)$
18654 := $(T(T((1+8))) \times T(6)) - T(T((T(5)/T(4))))$
18657 := $(1 + 8) - (T((T(6) + T(5))) \times (-T(7)))$
18659 := $(-1) + ((T(86) \times 5) - T(9))$
18673 := $((1 + T(T(8))) \times (T(6) + (7))) - 3$
18675 := $((-1) - T(86)) + (7) \times (-5)$
18676 := $(1 + T(T(8))) \times T(((6 \times 7)/6))$
18677 := $(1 + ((T(T(8)) - ((6-7))) \times T(7)))$
18678 := $((T((1 \times 8)) - 6) - (-T(7) \times T(T(8))))$
18683 := $((-1) + T(T(8))) + (T(T(6)) \times T((T(8)/3)))$
18684 := $(T(T((1 \times 8))) - (T(T(6)) \times (-T((8+4))))$
18685 := $(1 - (T(8) \times (T(6) - (T(8) \times T(5))))$
18687 := $((T((1+8)) - 6) - (T(T(8)) \times (-T(7))))$
18696 := $((-1) + T(8)) + T(T((T(6) - 9))) \times 6$
18697 := $(T(T(-((1-8)))) - (-T(6)) + (-T(9)) \times T(T(7)))$
18704 := $(1 + ((T(T(8)) \times T(7)) + T(T(04))))$
18705 := $(T(-((1-87))) \times 05)$
18714 := $((T(T((1 \times 8))) \times T(7)) + T((1 + T(4))))$
18719 := $(-1) - (T((8 \times (7+1))) \times (-9))$
18722 := $((1 + T(8)) \times T((T(7) - T(T(2)))) \times 2)$
18723 := $((-1) - (T((T(8) + T(7))) \times T(2))) \times (-3)$
18724 := $((T(T((1 \times 8))) \times T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)))$
18725 := $((-1) + T(8)) \times (7 + T((2^5)))$
18726 := $((T(T((1 \times 8))) \times T(7)) + (T((2 \times 6))))$
18728 := $((-1) + T(T(8))) \times T(7) + ((T(2) \times T(8)))$
18729 := $((1 + T(-((8-72)))) \times 9)$
18731 := $((1 + T(T(8))) \times T(7)) + T(T(3+1))$
18732 := $((T((1+8)) \times T(T(7))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-2)))$
18734 := $((1 + T(T(8))) \times T(7) + 3) + T(T(4))$
18735 := $((T((1+8)) \times T(T(7))) + T((T(3) \times 5)))$
18738 := $((-1) - (T(T(8)) \times (-T(7)))) + T((T(T(3)) - 8))$
18739 := $(1 - ((T(T(8)) + T(7)) \times (-3 \times 9)))$
18742 := $((1 + T(T(8))) \times T(7)) + T((-T(4) + T(T(T(2))))$
18749 := $(1 - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(7))) - T(T(4)) - T(9)))$
18752 := $((-1) - (T(T(8)) \times (-T(7)))) + (5 \times T(T(T(2))))$
18753 := $((T(T((1 \times 8))) \times T(7)) - (-5 \times T(T(3))))$
18754 := $((1 + T(T(8))) \times T(7)) + T((T(T(5))/T(4)))$
18755 := $((-1) + T(T(8))) \times T(7) + (T(5)) + T(T(5))$
18756 := $((-1) + T(T(8))) \times T(7) + T((-5) + T(6))$
18759 := $((T(T((1 \times 8))) \times T(7)) + T(T(5))) - 9$
18765 := $(T((1+8)) \times (T(T(7)) + (6+5)))$
18767 := $((-1) + T(T(8))) \times T(7) + (T(6) \times 7)$
18768 := $((1 \times 8) \times T((76-8)))$
18769 := $(1 - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(7))) - (T((6+9))))$
18774 := $((T((-1) + T(8))) \times T(7)) - T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))$
18775 := $((T(T((1 \times 8))) \times T(7)) + (7)) + T(T(5))$
18782 := $((T((1+8)) \times T(T(7))) + (8^{T(2)}))$
18786 := $((1 - (87 \times T(8))) \times (-6))$
18792 := $((T((1+8)) - 7) \times (9 \times T(2)))$
18795 := $((1-8) + (T(7) \times T(9))) \times T(5)$
18796 := $((1 + T(T(8))) \times T(7)) + (T((9+6)))$
18816 := $(T(-((1-8))) \times (T(T(8)) + (1 \times 6)))$
18822 := $((T(-((1-8))) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(2)))) + T(T(2)))$
18823 := $((T(-((1-8))) \times (T(T(8)) - 2)) + T(T(T(3))))$
18824 := $((1 + T((8+8)))^2) + T(T(4))$
18828 := $((T(T((1+8))) - (8^{T(2)})) \times T(8))$
18829 := $(1 - (T(8) \times ((8^{T(2)}) - T(T(9))))$
18833 := $((1 + T(8)) \times ((8^3) - 3))$
18836 := $(-1) + ((-T(T(8))) - T(T((T(8)/T(3)))) \times (-T(6)))$
18837 := $((T(18) + T(8)) \times T((T(3) + 7)))$
18838 := $(T(T(-((1-8)))) + ((8^3) \times T(8)))$
18844 := $((1 - T(T(8)) - 8) \times T(T(T(4)))) / (-T(T(4)))$
18845 := $(-T(T((1+8))) + (8 \times T((T(T(4)) + T(5))))$
18847 := $(T(18) - (-((T(8) + T(4))) \times T(T(7))))$
18855 := $(-T(T((1+8))) + (T((T(8) + T(5))) \times (-T(5))))$

- 18871** := (((1 × 8) + T(T(8))) × T(7)) - 1
18872 := (((1 × 8) + T(T(8))) × (7 + T(T(T(2))))
18873 := (1 + ((8 + T(T(8))) × (7 + T(T(3))))
18874 := (T(18) + ((T(T(8)) × T(7)) + T(T(4))))
18879 := ((T(-(1 - 8))) × T(T(8))) + T(T(T(T(-(7 - 9))))))
18885 := ((-1) + ((T(8) × T(8)) - T(8))) × T(5)
18895 := ((T(-(1 - 8))) × (T(T(8)) + 9)) - (5)
18907 := (T((1 + (8 × 9))) × 07)
18915 := (((T(-(1 - 8))) × T(9)) + 1) × T(5)
18924 := ((T((1 + T(8))) - T(T(9))) × (-2 - T(T(4))))
18926 := ((-1) - T(8)) - (T((T(9) - T(2))) × (-T(6)))
18928 := (((1 + T(T(8))) + 9) × 28)
18936 := ((T(T(-(1 - 8)))) × T(9)) + T(36)
18937 := (1 - (-T(8)) × (T(9 + T(3))) + T(T(7)))
18942 := (((1 + T(8)) + T(9)) × T(T(4 + 2)))
18943 := (1 + (((8 × 9) + T(4)) × T(T(T(3))))
18944 := ((T(T((1 × 8)))/9) × (4⁴))
18950 := ((-1) - T((T(8) - 9))) × (-50)
18954 := (T(((1 - 1) + T(8)) - 9)) × 54
18955 := ((18 × T(T(9))) + (T((5 × 5))))
18959 := (-1) + (8 × (T((T(T(9)))/T(5))) - T(9))
18962 := (((1 + T(8)) - T(T(9))) × (-T(6) - 2))
18963 := (T((T((1 × 8)) + T(9 - 6))) × T(T(3)))
18973 := ((18 × T(T(9))) + ((7³)))
18975 := ((1 - (T(T(8)))/(-9)) × T((7 + T(5))))
18981 := (T((1 + T(8))) × (-9) + T((8 × 1)))
19125 := (T(((1 - 1) + T(9)) + T((1 + 2))) × T(5))
19145 := ((-1) - T((91 - 4))) × (-5)
19152 := (T((1 + T((9 + 1)))) × (T(5) - T(2)))
19162 := (T(T(-(1 - 9))) + (T(16)²))
19172 := (-1) - (-((T(9 + 1)) + T(7))) × T(T(T(T(2))))
19173 := (-(((1 - 91) + 7)) × T(T(T(3))))
19216 := (1 - (-T(9)) × (T(T(T(2))) + T(T((1 + 6))))
19224 := (((-1) × T(9)) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(T(2)))))) × 4
19225 := (1 + (9 × (T((T(2) × T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(5))))))
19228 := ((-1) + T(9)) × (2 + T((T(T(T(2))) + 8)))
19236 := (((1 + T(T(9))) - T(T((2 + 3)))) × T(6))
19245 := (((T(-(1) + T(9))) × T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) - 5
19256 := (-1) - (((T(T(9)) + 2) - T(T(5))) × (-T(6)))
19259 := ((-1) - ((T(9)^{T(2)})/(-5))) + T(T(9))
19264 := ((-1) - T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) × (-64)
19266 := (19 × (T(T((T(2) + 6)))) - (T(6)))
19269 := (((T((1 + T(9))) × 2) - (T(6))) × 9)
19272 := ((T(-(1 - (9²))) - T(7)) × T(T(2)))
19274 := ((1 + T(9)) × ((T(2) + T(T(7))) + T(4)))
19277 := ((T((1 + 9)) × T((-2) + T(7))) - T(7))
19279 := (1 + (9 × ((T(2)⁷) - T(9)))
19280 := (((1 + 9) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) × 80
19293 := ((T(T(-(1 - 9)))) × 29) - (T(T(3)))
19295 := (-1) - ((-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × (9 + T(5)))
19296 := ((-((1 - 9)) × T(2)) × (T(T(9)) - T(T(6))))
19297 := ((19 × (2 + T(T(9)))) - T(T(7)))
19305 := (T((1 + 9)) × T((T(T(3)) + 05)))
19320 := (-((1 - 93)) × T(20))
19322 := (-1) - (((T(T(9)) × (-T(3))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(2))
19323 := (((T(T((1 × 9))) × T(3)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × 3
19328 := ((1 + T((T(T(9)))/T((3 + 2)))) × 8
19329 := ((1 + T((9 × 3))) × (T(T(2)) + T(9)))
19332 := (((T((1 + T(9))) × 3) - T(T(3))) × T(T(2)))
19339 := (1 - ((T(T(9)))/3) - ((3⁹)))
19343 := (-1) + ((T(9) - T(3)) × T((T(4) + T(T(3))))
19356 := ((T(((1 - 1) + T(9)) + T(3))) × T(5)) + T(T(6))
19358 := ((-1) - T(9)) - (T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(5)) - T(8)))
19362 := ((19 + T((T(T(3)) + (T(6)))) × T(T(T(2))))
19364 := (((1 + 9) - (T(T(3)) × T(T(6)))) × (-4))
19365 := (((T((1 + T(9))) - T(T(3))) + T(T(6))) × T(5))
19368 := (((-1) + T(T(9))) × T(T(3))) - (T(68))
19378 := ((1 + (9³)) - (-T(7)) × T(T(8)))
19382 := ((-1) - T(T(9))) + ((T(3) × T(82)))
19384 := (-1) - ((-T(9)) × T(-(T(3) - T(8)))) + T(T(T(4)))
19385 := (-19) + (T(T(T(3))) × (-T(8)) + T(T(5)))
19398 := ((19 × (T(T(3)) + T(T(9)))) - T(T(8)))
19422 := ((T(-(1 - 9)) × T(4)) - T(2)) × T(T(2))
19423 := (19 + ((4 × T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(T(3))))
19425 := (-((1 - ((9 × 4)²))) × T(5))
19426 := (1 - ((T(T(9)) + (T(T(4)) × (-2))) × (-T(6)))
19434 := (-1) + ((T(9) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-3 - T(4)))
19435 := ((T(-(1 - 9)) × T(4)) × T(3)) - (5)
19446 := (((1 + T(T(9))) - T(T(4))) - T(T(4))) × T(6))
19448 := ((-1) + T(9)) × (T((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)))) + T(8))
19458 := (T((1 + T(9))) × (-T(4)) + T((T(5) - 8)))
19467 := ((T((19 + T(T(4)))) + 6) × 7)
19475 := (((1 + 9) × (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(7)))) + T(5))
19476 := ((T(T((1 × 9))) + T(T((4 + 7)))) × 6)
19479 := (((-1) + T(9)) + (4) × T(T(7))) - 9
19485 := ((-1) × T(T(9))) + (T((T(4) + 8)) × T(T(5)))
19486 := ((1 + T(9)) + (T((T(4) × 8)) × 6))
19487 := (-1) - ((-T(9)) - T((T(4) - 8))) × T(T(7))
19488 := (((-1) + T(9)) + (4) × T((-8) + T(8)))
19494 := (((-1) - T(T(9))) + T(4)) × (-9) - T(4))
19496 := ((19 × (-T(4)) + T(T(9))) + (T(6)))
19522 := ((1 + T(T(9))) + (T(T((T(5) - T(2)))) × T(T(2))))
19525 := (T((1 + 9)) × ((T(T(5)) × T(2)) - (5)))
19529 := (-1) - (T((T(9) - T(5))) × (T(2) - T(9)))

- 19530** := ((T(T(-(1-9)))) - T(5)) × 30
19532 := ((1 + (T((T(9) - T(5))) × T(T(3)))) × 2)
19536 := ((-1) + T(9)) × (T((5 × T(3))) - T(6))
19537 := ((-1) - (T((T(9) - T(5))) × T(3))) × (-7)
19545 := ((T(T((1 × 9))) × (T(5) + (4))) - T(T(5)))
19548 := (T(-(1-9))) × (T(5) + T((4 × 8)))
19565 := ((1 + T((9 + T(5)))) × 65)
19572 := (((1 + T((T(9) - T(5)))) × 7) × T(T(2)))
19574 := (-1) - (-T(9)) × T(((5 + T(7)) - (4)))
19575 := ((1 - T((95 - 7))) × (-5))
19576 := (1 + (T(9) × T(((5 × 7) - 6)))
19584 := ((1 + (9 × T(5))) × (T(8) × 4))
19588 := (-((1 - 9)) + (5 × T(88)))
19596 := ((T(((1-1) + T(9)) - T(5))) × T(9)) + (T(6))
19619 := -((T((1 + T(9))) - ((T(6) - 1) × T(T(9))))
19624 := ((T((1 + 9)) - (-T(T(6))) × T(T(T(2)))) × 4)
19626 := ((T(19) + T(T((6 × 2)))) × 6)
19628 := (-1) - ((T(T(9)) × (-T(6) - 2)) + T(8))
19629 := (-((1 × 9) × 6) + (T(2)⁹))
19634 := ((-1) + (T(9) × T(T(6)))) + (T(3) × T(T(T(4))))
19635 := ((T(T((1 + 9))) - T(T(6))) × (3 × 5))
19637 := ((19 × T(T((6 + 3))) - T(7))
19638 := (T(-(1) + T(9))) + (T((T(6)/3)) × T(T(8)))
19639 := ((1 - T(9)) + (((6 - 3)⁹))
19642 := ((1 + T(9)) × (T(6) + T(T((T(4) - T(2))))))
19645 := ((1 + 9) - ((-T(T(6))) + T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(5)))
19646 := ((-1) + T(T(9))) × (T(6) + ((4 - 6)))
19647 := ((1 × 9) × (T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) - T(7)))
19648 := (((T(T(-(1-9))) × 6) - T(T(T(4)))) × 8)
19656 := (T(-(1-9))) × ((T(6) + (5)) × T(6))
19664 := (-1) + (T(9) × ((T(6) × T(6)) - (4)))
19665 := (19 × T(-(T(6) - T((6 + 5))))
19668 := ((-1) + T(9)) × (T(T(6)) + (6 × T(8)))
19678 := (T(19) - ((6 × T(T(7))) × (-8)))
19682 := (-1) + (((9 - 6)⁸) × T(2))
19684 := (1 + ((9 - 6)^{T(8)/4})
19694 := ((1 + ((9 - 6)⁹)) + T(4))
19695 := ((T(-(1-9)) + T(6)) × T(9)) + T(T(5))
19712 := ((1 + T((9 + T(7)))) × T((1 + T(T(2))))
19722 := (19 × (T(T((7 + 2))) + T(2)))
19725 := ((T(-(1) + T(9))) + T((T(7) - T(2)))) × T(5))
19734 := ((1 - (-9) × T(7)) × T((3 × 4)))
19747 := (((1 + T(9)) + T(74)) × 7)
19748 := (T(T(-(1-9))) + (T(T(7)) × (T(T(4) - 8)))
19754 := (-1) - ((-T(9)) × T(T(7))) - (T(54)))
19759 := (-1) - ((-9) + T(7)) × (-5 - T(T(9)))
19768 := (((-1) - T((T(9) + T(7)))) + T(T(6))) × (-8))
19776 := ((T((1 + 9)) - (7)) × (T(T(7)) + (6)))
19779 := (((-1) + T(T(9))) + (7)) × (T(7) - 9))
19784 := (T((1 + T(9))) + ((T(7) × T(T(8))) + T(T(4))))
19785 := ((T(-(1) + T(9))) × (T(7) - 8)) - (T(5))
19792 := ((19 × (7 + T(T(9)))) - T(T(2)))
19794 := ((19 × (7 + T(T(9)))) - (4))
19795 := (T(T((1 + 9))) - ((T(T(7)) × (-T(9))) + T(5)))
19797 := (-1) - ((T(T(9)) + (7)) × (9 - T(7)))
19798 := (19 × (7 + T((9 + T(8))))
19799 := (((-1) + T(9)) × (T(T(7)) + T(9))) - T(9))
19812 := ((-19) + T(81)) × T(T(2))
19823 := (-1) + ((T(T(9)) - T((-8) + T(T(T(2)))))) × T(T(3))
19824 := ((-T((1 + 98))) - T(T(2))) × (-4)
19826 := (-1) - (9 × (8 - T(T((T(T(T(2))))/T(6))))))
19828 := (1 - (9 × (8 - T(T((T(2) + 8))))))
19836 := (19 × (T(T(8)) + T((T(3) + T(6))))
19837 := (1 - (-9) × (T(T((8 + 3))) - (7)))
19842 := (((1 + T(9)) - (T(T(8)) × T(4))) × (-T(2)))
19844 := ((-1) + T(9)) - (-((T(8) × T(4)) × T(T(4))))
19845 := ((T(((1-1) + T(9)) + 8)) - T(T(4))) × T(5))
19846 := (1 - ((T(T(9)) - (T(8) × T(T(4)))) × T(6)))
19847 := (((1 × 9) × (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) - 7)
19854 := ((T(T((1 + 9))) + T(T(8))) × (5 + 4))
19855 := (T((1 + 9)) × (T(8) + T((5 × 5))))
19866 := ((1 - (-9) × T((8 + 6))) × T(6))
19870 := (-((1 + 9)) + (8 × T(70)))
19872 := (-((1 - 9)) × ((8 + T(T(7))) × T(T(2))))
19874 := (T(T(-(1-9))) + (8 × (7⁴)))
19875 := ((((-1) + T(9)) + T(T(8))) × T(7)) - (5))
19876 := ((1 + 9) - (T((T(8) + (7))) × (-T(6))))
19886 := (-1) - ((T(T(9)) - (88)) × (-T(6)))
19888 := ((T(19) + T(8)) × 88)
19893 := ((T(T((19 - 8))) × 9) - (T(3)))
19894 := (T(((1-9) + T(8))) × (T(9) + (4)))
19896 := ((19 × T((T(8) + 9))) + T(T(6)))
19898 := (-1) - (-9) × T(((T(T(8))/9) - 8)))
19899 := (T(T(((1 + 98)/9))) × 9)
19931 := (((1 + T(9 × 9))) × T(3)) - 1)
19932 := ((1 + T((9 × 9))) × (3 × 2))
19933 := (1 + ((T(9 × 9)) × T(3)) + T(3))
19934 := (-1) + (9 × (T((T(9) + T(T(3)))) + 4))
19935 := (((-1) + T(9 × 9)) × T(3)) + T(5))
19943 := ((-1) + T(9)) + (9 × T(T((-T(4)) + T(T(3))))))
19945 := ((1 + T(9)) - (-9) × T(T((-4) + T(5))))
19962 := ((T(((1 × 9) × 9)) + (6)) × T(T(2)))
19963 := (1 + ((T(9 × 9)) + (6)) × T(3))
19965 := (((T(-(1) + T(9))) - T(9)) × T(6)) + T(T(5))

- 19968** := (((T((1+9)) × T(9)) + T(6)) × 8)
19972 := (((1 - T(9)) × T(9)) + (T(7)^{T(2)}))
19975 := ((T((1+9)) × (-T(9)) + T(T(7)))) + T(T(5))
19982 := (1 + (T((T(9)/9)) × T(T(8)))) × 2
19985 := (T(((1 - T(9)) + T(9)) - 8) × 5)
19986 := (((1+9) + T((T(9) + T(8)))) × 6)
19988 := ((-1) - T(T(9))) + (T((9 × 8)) × 8)
19989 := (19 × T(T(9))) + (T(8) × 9)
19992 := (-((1 - 9) - 9) × T((T(9) + T(2))))
20197 := (20 - 1) × (T(T(9)) + T(7))
20244 := (-T(T(T(2)))) × ((T(T(T(02)))) + T(4)) × (-4))
20252 := (2 - (T(T(02)) × (-T(5)^{T(2)})))
20253 := (T(2) - (T(T(02)) × (-T(5)³)))
20286 := ((-T(20)) + T((T(T(2)) × 8))) × T(6)
20295 := ((-20) × (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9)))) + T(5)
20328 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) × ((T(T(T(03)))/T(T(T(2)))) × 8))
20349 := (T(T(T(2))) × ((T(T(T(03))) × 4) + T(9))
20358 := (T((20 + T(3))) × 58)
20382 := (T(T(2)) × ((0 - T(3)) + T(82)))
20385 := (((T(2) × T(T(T(03)))) + (T(T(8)))) × T(5))
20439 := -(((T(T(2))⁰⁴) - (T(T(3)) × T(T(9))))
20448 := (T(((T(2))⁰⁴) - T(4)) × 8)
20465 := ((T(2) - (04⁶)) × (-5))
20469 := (((2^{T(04)}) × T(6)) - T(T(9)))
20475 := (T((20 - (T(4) × (-7)))) × 5)
20476 := (T((T(T(T(2))) - (0 - T(T(4)))) × 7) - 6)
20478 := (T((T(T(2)) × T(04)) - (-T(7)) × T(T(8))))
20485 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(04)) × 85)
20495 := (20 + (T((T(4) × 9)) × 5))
20518 := (-2) + ((0 - T(T(5))) × (-T(18)))
20522 := (2 - ((0 - T(T(5))) × T((T(2) × T(T(2))))))
20523 := (T(2) + (T(T(05)) × T((T(2) × T(3))))
20526 := (T(T(2)) + (T(T(05)) × T((T(2) × 6))))
20592 := (T((2⁰⁵)) × (T(9) - T(T(2))))
20595 := ((-20) × (5 - T(T(9)))) - (5)
20646 := (T(T((2+06))) × (T(4) + T(6)))
20648 := (2 + ((T(06) + T(4)) × T(T(8))))
20664 := (T((20 + T(6))) × (6 × 4))
20728 := (-20) + (T(7) × T((2 + T(8))))
20745 := (T(2) × (((0 - T(T(7))) - T(T(4))) × (-T(5))))
20790 := (T((T(2) × 07)) × 90)
20825 := ((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(((0 - 8) + T(T(T(2))))))) × (-5))
20826 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(08)) × T((2 × 6)))
20855 := ((T(T((T(T(T(2))) - 08))) - T(5)) × 5)
20897 := (T(-((T(T(2)) - T(08))) × T(9)) - T(7))
20915 := ((T(2) - T(091)) × (-5))
20916 := ((T(T(2)) + T((T(09) - 1))) × T(6))
20925 := (T(((2 × 0) + 9) × T((2 × T(5))))
20927 := (2 + (T(09) × T((2 + T(7))))
20928 := (T(2) - ((0 - T(9)) × T(-((T(T(2)) - T(8))))))
20931 := ((20 × T(T(9))) + T(T(T(3 × 1))))
20937 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (((0 - T(9)) - T(3)) × T(T(7))))
20945 := ((T(2) + T(T((09 + 4))) × 5)
20976 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(09)) × 76)
20982 := ((T(T(T(2))) × (T(T(09)) - T(8))) + T(2))
20988 := ((20 × T(T(9))) - (-8) × T(8))
21000 := (T(T(T(2))) × 1000)
21021 := (T((T(2) + 10)) × T(21))
21023 := (2 - (-T((10 + T(2)))) × T(T(T(3))))
21035 := ((T(T(T(2))) + T(T((10 + 3)))) × 5)
21063 := (((2¹⁰) - T(6)) × T(T(3)))
21069 := -((T(T(-(2 - 10))) + (-T(6)) × T(T(9))))
21112 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1) × T((1 + 12)))
21114 := (T((2 + T(11))) × (-1) + T(4))
21133 := (((T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1) × T(13)) + (T(T(3))))
21147 := (T(T(T(2))) × (T(T((-1) + T((1 × 4)))) - T(7)))
21154 := -((T(T((T(T(2)) + 1))) + ((1 - T(5)) × T(T(T(4))))))
21159 := ((T((2 + T(11))) + (5)) × 9)
21168 := ((21 × T((1 + 6))) × T(8))
21175 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-11) × T(T(7))) × (-5))
21184 := ((T(T(T(2))) + 11) × (T(T(8)) - (4))
21195 := ((T((T(2))^{T(1+1)}) + T(T(9))) × T(5))
21196 := (T(T((T(T(2)) + 1))) + (T((-1) + T(9))) × T(6))
21216 := ((2 × T(12)) × T(16))
21223 := ((T((T(T(2)) + 1))^{T(2)}) - ((T(2))^{T(3)}))
21228 := (T(T(2)) × (T(T(T((1 + T(2)))) - (-T(2)) × T(T(8))))
21229 := (T(T(T(T(2) + 1))) + ((T(T(2)) + ((T(2))⁹))))
21239 := -((T(T(T(2) + 1))) - (T(T(T(2))) × (-T(T(3)) - T(T(9))))))
21245 := -((T(T(T(T(2) + 1))) + ((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4))) × T(5))))
21246 := -((T(T(2)) + ((-1) - T((T(2) + T(4)))) × T(T(6))))
21251 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (1 + T((-2) + T(5)))) - 1)
21252 := (T(21) × ((T(T(2)) × T(5)) + 2))
21253 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-1) - (T((-2) + T(5)) × T(T(T(3))))))
21255 := ((T(T(T(T(2) + 1))) - (T(2) + T(T(5)))) × T(5))
21257 := ((T(T(2)) - 1) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(5)) - T(7))))
21258 := (T(T(2)) - (T((1 + T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(5)) - T(8))))
21264 := ((T(2) - (T((1 + T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(6)))) × 4)
21273 := (T(T(T(2))) × ((-1) + T(T((2 + 7)))) - T(T(3)))
21274 := -((T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T((-1) + T(T(2))) - (T(T(7)))) × T(T(4))))
21279 := (T(2) × ((T((1 + T(T(T(2)))) × T(7)) + 9))
21283 := ((T((T(T(2)) + 1))^{T(2)}) - (T(T(8)) + 3))
21284 := (((T(T(T(2))) × T((1 + T(T(T(2)))))) + 8) × 4)
21285 := (T(T(T(2) + 1)) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(8) + T(T(5))))

- 21288** := $((-T(2)) + ((1 + T(2)) \times T(T(8)))) \times 8$
21292 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T((1 + 2))) - T(T(9)))) - 2)$
21293 := $((-((2 - 1)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(9)) - T(T(3))))))$
21294 := $((T(2) \times T(12)) \times T(9 + 4))$
21296 := $(2 - ((T(T((1 + 2))) - T(T(9))) \times T(6)))$
21297 := $(T(2) \times (1 - ((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9))) \times 7)))$
21315 := $((T((T(T(2)) + 1) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T((-1) + T(5))))$
21318 := $(T(T(2)) - ((1 + 31) \times T(T(8))))$
21329 := $(-T(T((21/3))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(9))))$
21336 := $((T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(T((T(3) + T(3)))) - T(T(6)))$
21337 := $((-T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-1) + (T(T((T(3) + T(3))) \times (-7))))$
21342 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-13) + T(4 \times T(T(T(2))))))$
21343 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((-1) - T(T(T(3)))) \times T((T(4) + 3)))$
21345 := $((T(2) - T(T((-1) + T(3)))) + T(T(T(4))) \times T(5))$
21346 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(13)) + (T(4 + T(6))))$
21348 := $((-2) + T(1 \times 34)) \times T(8)$
21350 := $((T(T(T(2))) + T(T((1 + T(3)))) \times 50)$
21357 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (((1 + 3)^5 - 7))$
21364 := $((-T(T(T(2))) + (-T(13)) \times (T(T(6)) + 4))))$
21372 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(13)) + (T(T(7) - 2)))$
21375 := $((T(2) - T((1 + T((T(3) + 7)))) \times (-5))$
21378 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((1 + T(3 \times T(7))) - 8))$
21379 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-1) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(7) - T(T(9))))))$
21384 := $((-T((2 + 1)) \times (T(3) - T(84))))$
21385 := $((T(2) + 1) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T((8 + 5))$
21390 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1) \times (3 + 90))$
21392 := $(2 + ((-1) + T(3)) \times T(92))$
21393 := $(T(2) - ((1 - T(T(3)))) \times 93)$
21399 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (((-1) - T(3)) + T(T(9))) - 9)$
21414 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-1) + T((T(T(4 - 1))) \times 4))$
21432 := $((2 + T((14 \times T(3)))) \times T(T(2)))$
21434 := $((T(T((T(T(2)) + 1))) \times (T(T(4)) - (T(3)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
21435 := $((T((21 \times 4)) \times T(3)) + T(5))$
21439 := $(T(T(T((T(2) + 1)))) + (T(T((-T(4)) + T(T(3)))) \times 9))$
21441 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (-14) + T(T((T(4) - 1))))$
21444 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-1) - ((-T(4)) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(4))))$
21445 := $((T((T(2) + 1)) \times T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) - 5)$
21448 := $(T((T(T(2)) + 1)) \times ((T(4) \times T(4)) + T(T(8))))$
21462 := $((T(T(2)) + 1) + T(4 \times T(6))) \times T(T(2))$
21465 := $(T((-2) + T((1 \times 4) + 6))) \times T(5)$
21468 := $((2^{T(1 \times 4)}) \times T(6)) - T(8)$
21472 := $((T(T((T(T(2)) - 1))) \times (-4)) + ((T(7)^{T(2)}))$
21476 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(T(1 \times 4)))) \times (7 - T(6)))$
21483 := $(T(21) \times (T(4) + 83))$
21488 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (1 - (-4) \times T(T(8)))) \times 8)$
21492 := $((-T(2)^{1+4}) - (-T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
21493 := $((-T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((1 + T(4)) - (T(T(9)) \times T(T(3))))))$
21494 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times ((-1) - T(4)) + T(T(9)))) - T(4)$
21495 := $((T(T(T(2))) + T((1 + T((4 + 9)))) \times 5)$
21497 := $((-21) \times (T(4) - T(T(9)))) - T(7)$
21505 := $(T((T(T(T(2))) + 1)) \times (T(50)/T(5)))$
21518 := $((-2) + T(T((-1 - 5)))) \times T(T(-(1 - 8)))$
21524 := $(T(T(2)) - ((-1) + T(5)) \times (T(2) - T(T(T(4))))))$
21525 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (-T((-1 - 5)) - T((T(2) \times T(5))))))$
21528 := $((T(T(2)) - 1) \times T(T(5)) - 2) \times T(8)$
21532 := $((T(T(2)) + 1) \times (-5) + T(T((T(3) \times 2))))$
21542 := $(T(2) - (((1 - T(5)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(2))))))$
21544 := $(-T(T(2)) - ((1 - T(5)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(4))$
21545 := $((-((2 - 1)) + T(5)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(5)$
21546 := $((T(T(2)) \times T((-1) + T(5) + 4)) \times T(6))$
21547 := $(-T(T(2)) - ((1 - T(5)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + 7)$
21549 := $((-T(T(2)) + ((-1) - (T(T(5)) \times (-4)) \times (-T(9))))$
21554 := $((-T(T(2))) - (((1^5) - T(5)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
21558 := $((-T(T(2)) + ((-1) - (T(T(5)) \times (-5)) \times (-T(8))))$
21559 := $((2^{-1+T(5)}) + (5 \times T(T(9))))$
21562 := $(2 - ((1 - T(5)) \times T(T(T(6 - 2))))))$
21567 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T((1 + 5)))) \times T((6 + 7)))$
21571 := $((-2) + T(T((-1 - 5)))) \times (T(T(7)) + 1)$
21572 := $(2 \times ((T(T(T(-1 - 5)))) \times 7) + T(T(2)))$
21573 := $((T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(T(5 + 7))) + T(3))$
21575 := $(((-2) \times T(T(T(-1 - 5)))) \times (-7) + T(5))$
21577 := $(T(2) - ((1 + T(T(5 + 7))) \times (-7)))$
21582 := $((T(T(T(2))) + 1) \times ((T(T(5)) \times 8) + T(T(T(2))))$
21585 := $((T(2) - (T(15) \times T(8))) \times (-5))$
21592 := $((T(2) + 1) \times ((T(T(5)) \times T(9)) - 2))$
21593 := $((-T(T(2)) + T((1 + T(5)))) - (T(T(9)) \times T(T(3))))$
21594 := $((-T(2 + 1)) - (T(T(5)) \times (T(9) \times (-4))))$
21595 := $((T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(T(5)) \times T(9)) - 5)$
21596 := $((-T(2) - T((1 + T(5)))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(6))))$
21598 := $(2 \times (-1) + (T((T(5) + 9)) \times T(8)))$
21609 := $((-21) \times (6 - T(T(09))))$
21624 := $((-T(T(2) \times T(16))) \times (2 - T(T(4))))$
21629 := $(T(T(T(2))) + (-1) - (T(6) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(9))))))$
21635 := $((-(((T(2) + 1)^6) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-5))$
21636 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(-1 - 6))^3) + T(T(6)))$
21637 := $((T((T(2) + 1)) + T(T((6 + T(3)))) \times 7)$
21639 := $((T(T(2)) \times (-16)) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(9))))$
21644 := $((T(T(T(T(2) + 1)))) + 6) \times (T(4) + 4))$
21648 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (-1) + T(6)) \times T((4 \times 8)))$
21649 := $((-2) + (T((1 \times 6)) \times (-4) + T(T(9))))$
21658 := $((T(T(2)) + 1) + T(T(6))) \times T((5 + 8))$
21669 := $((T(2) \times (-1) - T(6)) - (-T(6)) \times T(T(9)))$
21672 := $((T(T(2)) + 1) \times T((6 \times 7))) \times T(T(2))$
21673 := $(T((T(T(T(2))) + 1)) + (6 \times T(T(7) \times 3)))$

- 21690** := $((T((T(2) + 1)) + T(T(6))) \times 90)$
21692 := $((-((2 - 1) - (-T(6) \times (T(T(9)) - 2)))$
21693 := $((-2) + T(T((1^6 \times 9))) \times T(T(3)))$
21694 := $((-((T(T(T(2))) + (-1) + (T(T(6)) \times (-94))))$
21695 := $((-((T(T((T(2) + 1))) + ((-T(6) \times T(T(9))) - T(5))))$
21696 := $((T(T(2)) - 1) - T(T(6))) \times (-96)$
21697 := $((-((T((T(2) + 1)) + ((-T(6) \times T(T(9))) + T(7))))$
21698 := $((-((2 - 1) - ((-T(6) \times T(T(9))) + T(8)))$
21699 := $((T(2) + 1) - T(69)) \times (-9)$
21714 := $(T(21) \times (T(7) + T((1 + T(4))))$
21720 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (1 - (T(7)^{T(2+0)})))$
21721 := $((T(21) - (T(7)^{T(2)})) \times (-1))$
21722 := $((2 - 1) + (T(7)^{T(2)}) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
21723 := $((2 + (T((1 \times 7))^{T(2)})) - T(T(T(3))))$
21724 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-1) + T(T(7 + 2)))) + T(4)$
21725 := $(T(T((T(2) + 1))) \times ((T(T(7)) - T(T(2))) - 5))$
21726 := $((T(T(2)) - (1 - (T(7)^{T(2)}))) - T(T(6)))$
21727 := $((-((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (1 - ((T(7)^{T(2)} + 7))))$
21728 := $(T((T(T(2)) + 1)) \times ((T(7)^2 - 8))$
21729 := $((-T((2 + 1))) - ((-7) \times T(2)) \times T(T(9)))$
21732 := $((T(T(((2 \times 1) + 7))) \times T(T(3))) - T(2))$
21733 := $((-2) + (T(-((1 - 7))) \times T(T(3 \times 3))))$
21735 := $(21 \times T(T((7 - 3) + 5)))$
21736 := $(T((T(T(2)) - 1)) - (-((T(7)^3) + T(T(6))))$
21739 := $((T(2) + 1) - (-((7 \times 3) \times T(T(9))))$
21741 := $(T(T(2)) - (-T(-((1 - 7))) \times T(T((T(4) - 1))))$
21742 := $((-((T((T(T(T(2))) - 1)) - ((T(7)^{T(4-2)})))$
21749 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (1 + 7)) \times T((4 + 9)))$
21750 := $(T(((2 - 1) + T(7))) \times 50)$
21755 := $((-((T(T((T(T(2)) - 1))) - ((7 \times 5^5))))$
21756 := $((T(T(2)) + 1) \times ((-T(7) - T(T(5))) \times (-T(6))))$
21758 := $(T((T(T(T(2))) + 1)) \times (T(7) + 58))$
21762 := $(T((-2) + T((1 \times 7))) \times 62)$
21763 := $((T(T(2)) + 1) \times (T(7) + T(T((6 + T(3)))))$
21769 := $((2 \times 17) - (-T(6) \times T(T(9))))$
21777 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((1 + T(T(7))) + T((T(7) + 7))))$
21792 := $((-((T(T(2)) - (T(-((1 - 7))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(2))))$
21793 := $((2 \times (1 + T(7))) + (T(T(9)) \times T(T(3))))$
21798 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(-((1 - 7))) \times (T(T(9)) - 8)))$
21825 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T((1 + 8)))) + (T(T(2)) \times T(5)))$
21835 := $(T(2) + ((T(-((1 - 8)))^3) - T(T(5))))$
21837 := $((-T(2)) + (T((T((1 \times 8) + 3)) \times T(7)))$
21838 := $((-2) + (T(-((1 - 8))) \times T(3 + T(8))))$
21840 := $((T(T((T(T(2)) - 1))) - (T(T(8)))) \times (-40))$
21842 := $((T(2) + 1)^8 - T(4)) / T(2)$
21845 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T((1 + 8)))) - (T(4) - T(T(5))))$
21847 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T((1 + 8)))) - (-4) \times T(7))$
21852 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T((1 + 8)))) + (T(T(5)) - T(2)))$
21854 := $((-((T(T(T(2))) - ((-1) + T(8)) \times (5^4))))$
21855 := $((2 + T((1 + 8))) \times T((T(5) + T(5))))$
21861 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T((1 + 8)))) \times T((6 \times 1)))$
21863 := $(2 + ((T(T((1 + 8))) + 6)) \times T(T(3)))$
21872 := $((T((T(2) + 1)) \times (-8)) + ((T(7)^{T(2)}))$
21874 := $(T((T(T(T(2))) - 1)) - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) \times T(T(4))))$
21875 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T((1 + 8)))) + (T(7) \times 5))$
21876 := $((-((T(T(2)) - ((T(T((1 + 8))) + 7)) \times T(6))))$
21879 := $((T(2) \times 18) \times T(T(7))) - T(9)$
21882 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T((1 + 8))) + 8)) - T(T(T(2))))$
21884 := $((-T(T(2))) - ((T(T(-((1 - 8)))) - 8) \times (-T(T(4))))$
21885 := $((-T(2)) + (T(18) \times (8 + T(T(5))))$
21888 := $((-2) \times T(18)) \times (-8 \times 8)$
21889 := $((T((T(T(T(2))) + 1)) - (T(T(8)))) \times (-8 - T(9)))$
21893 := $((-((T(T(2) + 1)) + ((-8) - T(T(9))) \times T(T(3))))$
21896 := $((-((T(T(2)) + 1) - ((8 + T(T(9))) \times T(6))))$
21897 := $((T(T(T(2))) + 1) \times T(T(8))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-7))$
21912 := $((T(T(T(2))) + 1) \times (T((T(9) - 1)) + T(T(2))))$
21918 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-1 - (-9) \times T(T(-((1 - 8))))))$
21922 := $((T(T((T(T(2)) + 1))) \times (9 \times T(T(2)))) - 2)$
21923 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - (1 - ((T(T(9)) - 2) \times T(T(3))))$
21924 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-1) + T((9^2) + 4))$
21927 := $(T(2) - ((-((1 \times 9)) \times T(T(2))) \times T(T(7))))$
21930 := $(T(T(2)) \times T((T((1 + 9)) + 30)))$
21934 := $((T(T((T(T(2)) + 1))) \times (9 \times T(3))) + T(4))$
21935 := $((-2) + (19 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times 5)$
21937 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - (1 - ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(3))) - T(7))))$
21942 := $((21 \times (T(T(9)) + T(4))) - T(2))$
21943 := $((-2) - ((-19) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(3)))$
21945 := $(T(21) \times ((9 + T(4)) \times 5))$
21946 := $((2 - 1) - ((T(T(9)) + T(4)) \times (-T(6))))$
21948 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T((1 + T(9))) \times 4) - T(T(8))))$
21951 := $((T((T(T(2)) + 1))^{T(9)/T(5)} - 1)$
21952 := $((2 \times ((1 \times 9) + 5))^{T(2)})$
21954 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-1 - ((T(T(9)) - T(T(5))) \times (-4))))$
21957 := $((-((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(-((1 - 9)))) \times (-5) - T(7))))$
21960 := $((2 + 1) + 9) \times T(60)$
21962 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - (1 + ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(6))) + T(2))))$
21963 := $((21 \times T(T(9))) + T(T(6))) - 3$
21965 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - (1 + (T(T(9)) \times (-6) - T(5))))$
21966 := $((T(T(((2 - 1) \times 9))) \times T(6)) + T(T(6)))$
21967 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-1) + T(T(9))) + (T((-6) + T(7))))$
21969 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-1) + T((T(9) + T(6)))) \times 9)$
21972 := $((2 \times (1 + 9)) + (T(7)^{T(2)}))$

- 21973** := $((2 + 19) + (T(7)^3))$
21974 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(-(1-9))))/7) - 4$
21975 := $((T(T(2)) - 1) \times (T(T(9)) + (T(7) \times T(T(5))))$
21977 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(-(1-9)))) + 7)/(-7))$
21978 := $((-(T(2)) + T(-(1-9))) \times T((T(7) + 8)))$
21984 := $((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(-(1-9)))) \times (8 \times 4))$
21985 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 19) + 8) \times 5$
21987 := $((21 \times T(T(9))) - (T(8) \times (-7)))$
21996 := $((T(T(2)) \times (T(-(1) + T(9))) - T(96)))$
21998 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((1 + T(9)))) - (T((T(9) - 8))))$
22029 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((20 - T(T(2))) + T(T(9))))$
22035 := $((T(2) + (-T(20)) \times T(T(3))) \times (-5))$
22044 := $((T(T(2)) + (-T(20)) \times T((T(4) + (4)))))$
22048 := $((2 \times T((-T(2)) + T(T(04)))) \times 8)$
22065 := $((T(2) + (T(20) \times T(6))) \times 5)$
22072 := $((T(T(2)) \times 20) + ((T(7)^{T(2)}))$
22080 := $(T((T(2) + (20))) \times 80)$
22085 := $((-(T(T(T(T(2)))) - T((T(T(T(2))) - 08)))) \times (-5))$
22088 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (20)) \times 88)$
22092 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((20 + T(T(9))) - T(2)))$
22095 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(20)) + 9) \times 5$
22104 := $((-T(T(2))) + (T(T(T(T(2))) - 10)) \times T(4))$
22105 := $((T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \times 10) - 5)$
22123 := $(T((T(2) \times T(T(2)))) + (T((1 + T(T(2))))^3))$
22125 := $((T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \times T((1 + T(2)))) + T(5))$
22127 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(T(2)) + 1)^{T(2)} + (T(T(7))))))$
22128 := $((2 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1) \times (T(T(2)) \times 8))$
22139 := $((-2) + T(T((T(T(2)) + 1))) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(9))))$
22140 := $((T(2)^{T(2)}) \times T((1 \times 40)))$
22147 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(-(1) + T(4)))) + (T(T(7))))$
22154 := $((T((2 \times T(T(T(2)))) + 1) + (-T(5)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
22155 := $((T((T(T(2+2)) - 1)) \times T(5)) - (T(T(5))))$
22162 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(T(2))) - ((T((1+6))^{T(2)})))$
22165 := $((T((T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 1) \times (6 + 5))$
22168 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(2)) \times 16)) - 8)$
22173 := $(221 + (T(7)^3))$
22176 := $((T(2) \times ((T(2) + 1) + T(7))) \times T(T(6)))$
22178 := $(2 + ((T(T(T(2))) + 1) \times (T(7) \times T(8))))$
22179 := $(T(2) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(-(1-7)) + T(T(9))))$
22182 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T(T(T(2))) + T(T((1+8)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
22183 := $(T(T((2 \times T(2)))) + ((T(-(1-8)))^3))$
22185 := $((T(T(2)) - T((T(2) \times 18))) \times (-T(5)))$
22194 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T((T(T(2)) - 1)) \times (-T(9) + T(T(T(4))))))$
22196 := $((2 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - (1 + (T(T(9)) \times (-T(6))))$
22197 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((-T((2+1)) + T(T(9))) + T(7)))$
22213 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 2) \times (T(T(2)) + (T(13))))$
22214 := $((-T(T(2))) - ((-2) + T(T((T(T(2)) + 1)))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
22218 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(2))) - (-2 - T(T((1+8))))$
22224 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(2))) - T(2)) \times (-2^4))$
22225 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(2))) - T(T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2)))) \times 5)$
22230 := $(T((2 + T(2^{T(2)}))) \times 30)$
22231 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T((T(2)^2))) + (T(31)))$
22239 := $(T((2 \times T(2))) \times ((T(2) + T(T(3))) + T(T(9))))$
22242 := $((T(T(2)) + T((T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \times (-T(4) + T(T(T(2))))$
22243 := $((T(2) + T((2+2))) \times T((T(T(4)) + 3)))$
22245 := $((-2) - ((T(2)^{T(2)})) \times T(T(4))) \times T(5)$
22246 := $((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times (-4) + T(T(6))))$
22247 := $((T(2)^{T(2)}) - ((2 - T(T(4))) \times T(T(7))))$
22248 := $(T(2) \times (((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) - T(4)) \times T(8)))$
22249 := $((2 - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T((2^4)) - T(T(9))))$
22252 := $(T((T(2) + T(T(T(2)))) + ((T((2+5))^{T(2)})))$
22254 := $((-T(T(T(2))) + (T((2+T(2))) \times (-T(54))))$
22264 := $(T(22) \times (T((2 \times 6)) + T(4)))$
22267 := $((-T(T(2))) - T(T((T(2)^2))) \times (-T(6)) + (T(T(7))))$
22269 := $((-T(T(2)) + (T((2+T(2))) \times (-T((6 \times 9))))$
22272 := $((2^{T(2)}) \times (-T(2) + T((T(7) - 2))))$
22273 := $(T((T(2) + T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(T(2))) + ((T(7)^3))))$
22274 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(2) \times T(27))) - T(T(T(4))))$
22275 := $((T(2) \times T((2 \times 27))) \times 5)$
22277 := $(T(2) + (-2) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-T(7)) \times T(T(7))))$
22278 := $((-T(2) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(7)) + T(T(8))))$
22279 := $((-T(T(2)) - ((T(T((2+2))) \times T(T(7))) - T(9)))$
22284 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(2)^{T(2)}) - (T(T(8))) \times 4)$
22287 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(8)) + T(T(7))))$
22294 := $((-T((2^{T(2)})) - (T(T(-(2-9)))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
22295 := $((T(T(2)) - T((2 \times (2 + T(9)))) \times (-5))$
22296 := $((-T(T(2)) + ((-T(2)^{T(2)}) - T(T(9))) \times T(6)))$
22299 := $((2 - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T((T(2) + T(9)))) - T(9))$
22308 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-2) + (T(30) \times 8))$
22315 := $((T((T(2)^2)) \times T(31)) - 5)$
22319 := $((2/2) + (T(31) \times T(9)))$
22323 := $((T(T((T(2)^2))) + T((T(T(3))/T(2)))) \times T(T(3)))$
22324 := $((-T(T(2)) - (T(T((2+3)+2))) \times T(T(4))))$
22325 := $(T((2 \times (2 + T(3^2)))) \times 5)$
22326 := $((T(2) - (2^{T(3)}))^2 \times 6)$
22327 := $((-T(2)) + (T(((2^3) + 2)) \times T(T(7))))$
22328 := $((-2) - (T(T((-2) + T(3))) \times (-T(28)))$
22329 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)))) + (T(2)^9))$
22341 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-T((-2) + T(3))) \times T(T((T(4) + 1))))$
22342 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))/3)) \times T(T(4)) + T(T(2))))$
22343 := $(2 + ((T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + T(T(T(3))))$

- 22344 := (T(T(T(2))) × ((T(23) - T(4)) × 4))
22345 := ((T(T(2+2))) × T(T((3+4)))) + (T(5))
22347 := ((2 + T((2+3))) + (T(T(4)) × T(T(7))))
22348 := ((T((2 + T(T(T(2)))))) × (3⁴)) - 8
22350 := (((T(T(T(2))))² + T(3)) × 50)
22351 := (T(T(T(2))) - (T(T((T(T(T(2)))/3))) × (-T(T((5-1))))))
22356 := (T(T(2)) × ((2 + T(T(T(3)))) × T(5)) + T(T(6)))
22358 := ((T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2)))³ + (T(T((T(5) - 8))))))
22359 := ((T(2)^{T(T(2))}) - (T(T(3)) × (5 - T(T(9))))))
22365 := (((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) - 3) × (T(6) × 5))
22368 := (2 × ((2 + T(T(T(3)))) × (6 × 8)))
22372 := ((T(T(T(2)))²) - ((T(T(3)) - ((T(7)^{T(2)}))))))
22373 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T((-2) + T(T(3)))) + ((T(7)³)))
22374 := ((2 + (2 × T(T(3)))) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(4))))
22375 := ((T(T(2+2))) × (3 + T(T(7)))) - T(T(5))
22382 := ((2 - T(T(T(2)))) × (-T((T(3) × 8)) + 2))
22386 := -((T(T(2)) × (T((-2) + T(3))) - T(86)))
22387 := ((T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2)))³ + T((T(8) - (7))))))
22389 := (((2 - T(T(T(2)))) × (-T((T(3) × 8)))) + T(9))
22392 := ((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) - (-((T(T(3)) + T(T(9)))) × T(T(T(2))))))
22395 := (((2^{T(2)}) + T((T(3) × 9))) × T(5))
22397 := (-T((2+2)) - (T(T(T(3))) × (-97)))
22398 := (-T(2) - ((-T((2 × 3))) × T(T(9))) - T(T(8)))
22407 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))/T(2)) - (T(T(4)) × (0 - T(T(7))))))
22422 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(2)) × T((T(4) × T(T(2)))))) × 2)
22425 := ((T((T(2)²) - T(T(T(4)))) × (T(2) × (-5)))
22427 := ((-2) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(4)) × (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))))))
22428 := (((2 + T(2))⁴) - 2) × T(8)
22434 := (T(2) × (-2) + (T(T(4)) × T((T(3) + T(4))))))
22435 := ((T(T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2)))) × T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)) × 5))
22438 := ((T(T(2)) × T((2 × 43))) - 8)
22439 := ((2 × T((-T(2) + T(T(4)))) + ((3⁹)))
22450 := ((T(T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2)))) × T(T(4))) + (T(T((5+0))))))
22451 := ((T(T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2)))) × T(T(4))) + ((T(T(5)) + 1)))
22452 := ((T(T(2)) × T(((T(2)⁴) + (5)))) + T(T(2)))
22453 := ((T(T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2)))) × T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) + 3))
22454 := ((T(T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2)))) × T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) + 4))
22455 := -(((T(2) + (T(24) × (-5))) × T(5)))
22456 := ((T(T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2)))) × T(T(4))) + ((T(T(5)) + (6))))
22457 := ((-T(T(2)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(T(4))) × (-T(5))) + (T(T(7))))))
22458 := (T(T(2)) × (2 + T(((T(4) × 5) + T(8))))))
22459 := ((T(T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2)))) × T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) + 9))
22461 := -((T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(2) × (-4)) × T(61))))
22464 := (T((2 + 24)) × 64)
22465 := -((T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(T(2))) × T(46)) - 5)))
22470 := ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(24))) × 70)
22472 := (2 × ((T((2 + T(4))) + T(7))²))
22473 := (-22) + (T(T(4)) × (T(T(7)) + 3))
22474 := ((T(T(2)) × 24) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(4))))
22476 := (T(2) × ((2^{T(4)}) - (-T(7) × T(T(6))))))
22477 := ((T(T(T(2))) - 2) × (T((T(T(4)) - (7)) + 7))
22478 := (2 - (((-2) - T(T(4))) × T(T(7))) + T(T(8))))
22481 := ((T(T(2)) × (T(T((2 + T(4)))) + (T(T(8)))))) - 1
22482 := ((T(T((2 × (2 + 4)))) + T(T(8))) × T(T(2)))
22484 := ((T((22 + T(T(4)))) × 8) - T(T(T(4))))
22485 := (((2 + T(2))⁴) × T(8)) - T(5)
22488 := ((T(2) + (T((2 + T(4))) × T(8))) × 8)
22489 := (-2) - (T((2 + 4)) × (-T(8) - T(T(9))))
22491 := (T((2 × T(2))) × (-T(4) + T((T(9) + 1))))
22493 := (2 - ((-T((2 × 4))) - T(T(9))) × T(T(3)))
22494 := (T(2) + (T(T(T(2))) × (-T(4) + T((-9) + T(T(4))))))
22495 := ((T(2) + T(T((T(2) + (4)))))) × T(T((9 - 5)))
22500 := (T((T(2)²) × 500)
22502 := (2 + ((T(2) × 50)²))
22512 := (((T(T(T(2)))²) × 51) + T(T(T(2))))
22515 := (((T((T(2) + T(T(T(2)))))) × 5) + 1) × T(5)
22524 := -((T(T((2^{T(2)}))) + (T(5) × (-T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4))))))
22527 := (-T(T(2)) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(5)))) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(7))))))
22528 := ((-T(2) + T((-2) + T(5))) × (2⁸))
22533 := ((T(22) + T((T(T(5))/3))) × T(T(3)))
22536 := ((T((T(2) × T(T(2)))) × T(T(5))) + (T((3 × T(6))))))
22539 := (((2 + 2)⁵) × T(T(3))) + T(T(9))
22540 := (T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2))) × (-T(5) - T(40)))
22542 := ((2 × T(T(T(2)))) + (((T(5) × T(4))²))
22544 := -((T(T(2)) - ((T(T((2 + 5))) + (4)) × T(T(4))))))
22545 := (((T(2) × T(T(2))) + (T(54))) × T(5))
22547 := (-T(2) - (T((2 × 5)) × (-4) - T(T(7))))
22548 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(T(2)) × (5⁴) + 8))
22554 := (T(T(T(2))) × (-T(T(2)) + (T(T(5)) × (-5 + 4))))
22555 := (((T(T(2)) × T(T(T(T(2)))))) + (5⁵)) × 5
22556 := ((T((T(2) + T((-2) + T(5)))) × 5) + T(T(6)))
22561 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-T((2 × 5))) × T(T((6 + 1))))
22563 := ((T((T(T(T(2)) - 2)) × T(T(5))) - (T(T(6)) + (T(3))))
22564 := ((T(2) + (T((-2) + T(5))) × T(T(6))) + T(T(T(4))))
22566 := (((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(2)) × (T(T(5)) - (T(6)))) - 6)
22568 := ((T(22) - 5) × T((T(6) - 8)))
22569 := ((T((T(T(T(2)) - 2)) × T(T(5))) - T(T(T(-(6 - 9))))))
22572 := (T((2^{T(2)})) × (T((5 × 7)) - T(2)))
22573 := (-2) - (-25) × T((7 × T(3)))
22574 := ((2 × (2 + T(T(5)))) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(4))))
22575 := -(((T(2) - T(2⁵)) × (T(7) + T(5))))
22576 := ((-2) + T(T((T(2) + (5)))) × (T(7) + (6)))

- 22577** := $((T(T((2+2))) \times (5 + T(T(7)))) - T(7))$
22578 := $(T(T(2)) - ((T(2) - T((5 \times 7))) \times T(8)))$
22584 := $(-((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) - (-T(T(5))) \times T((-T(8)) + T(T(4))))))$
22593 := $-((T(T(2)) + ((T(2)^5) \times (-93)))$
22594 := $(-2) - (T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(T(5)) \times (-9)) + (4)))$
22596 := $((T(T(2^{T(2)})) + (5) + T(T(9))) \times T(6))$
22598 := $(2 - (T(T(T(2))) \times ((-5) - T(T(9))) - T(8)))$
22599 := $((T(2)^{T(T(2))}) \times ((-5) + T(9)) - 9)$
22625 := $(2 + T((2 \times T(6)))) \times 25$
22629 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(6))/T(2)))) - 9)$
22632 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(6))/3))) - T(T(2)))$
22634 := $(2 \times (-2) - (T(T(6)) \times (T(3) - T(T(4))))))$
22635 := $((T(2) - T(T(2))) \times (T(T(6)) - ((T(3)^5))))$
22636 := $(-2) - ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(6))/3)) \times (-T(T(6))))$
22638 := $-((T(T(2)) + ((2 - (6 \times T(3))) \times T(T(8))))$
22642 := $(2 \times (2 + (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(2))))))$
22644 := $((-2) + T((2+6))) \times T(T((4+4)))$
22645 := $((T(T(T(T(T(2))/T(2)))) + 6) \times T(T(4)) - T(5))$
22646 := $(2 + (T(T((2+6))) \times (T(T(4)) - (T(6))))$
22648 := $(2+2) + ((-T(6)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(8)))$
22649 := $((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(6)) + T((T(T(4)) + 9)))$
22653 := $((T(2)^2) \times ((T(6) \times T(T(5))) - 3))$
22655 := $((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) \times T(6) - (5)) \times 5$
22656 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (T(2) \times (-((6^5)) + T(T(6))))$
22659 := $(T(T(2)) - ((-T(2)) - (-T(6)) \times T(T(5)))) \times (-9))$
22662 := $-((T(T(2^{T(2)})) - ((6^6)/2))$
22665 := $-((T(T(2)) + ((2 - T(T(6))) \times (-T(6)) + T(T(5))))$
22672 := $((T(T((2+T(2)))) \times 6) + ((T(7)^{T(2)}))$
22674 := $(-T(T(2))) - (-((T(T(2)) - (T(6))) \times (T(7) - T(T(T(4))))))$
22675 := $((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) \times T((T(6) - (7))) - (5))$
22677 := $(-T(2)) - (-T((2+6))) \times T((T(7) + (7)))$
22678 := $(-2) - (T(((2 \times T(6)) - (7))) \times (-T(8)))$
22691 := $(-T((2+2))) + (T(6) \times T((T(9) + 1)))$
22692 := $(T((-2) + (T(2) \times T(6)))) \times (9 + T(2))$
22693 := $((-T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T((T(T(T(2))))/T(6))) \times T(T(9)))/3)$
22694 := $((T(T(T(2)))/(-T(2))) - (-T(6)) \times T((-9) + T(T(4))))$
22695 := $((-2) - T(2)) \times (T(6) - T(95))$
22698 := $(T(2) \times (T(T(2)) - ((T(6) \times T(9)) \times (-8))))$
22699 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (2 - (-T(6)) \times (-T(9)) - T(T(9))))$
22701 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times T((T((2+7)) + 01)))$
22714 := $(-22) + (T(T(7)) \times (1 + T(T(4))))$
22715 := $((T(T(T(2)))/T(2)) + (T(T(7))) \times T(T(-(1-5))))$
22719 := $(T(2) \times (T(T(2)) - (-7) \times T((1+T(9))))$
22722 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(-((T(2) - ((7^2)))))) + T(T(T(2))))$
22724 := $((2^{T(T(2))}) + ((T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))))$
22725 := $((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) \times 7) + T(2) \times T(5)$
22726 := $((T(T((2+2))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(2))) + T(T(6)))$
22727 := $(-((T(2)^2)) + (T(T(7)) \times (2 \times T(7))))$
22728 := $((T(2)^{T(T(2))}) - T((T(7) \times T(2)))) \times (-8)$
22729 := $(T(2) + ((T(T(2)) - T(7)) \times (2 - T(T(9))))$
22732 := $(2 \times (-2) + (T(T(7)) \times T((T(T(3))/T(2))))$
22733 := $(-T(2)) - ((-2) \times T(T(7))) \times T((T(T(3))/3))$
22734 := $(-2) - ((2 \times T(T(7))) \times (-T((3+4))))$
22735 := $(T((2 \times T(T(T(2)))) - (-((T(7)^3)) + T(T(5))))$
22736 := $((T((T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(7)))/36)$
22737 := $-((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-T(T(2))) \times T(((T(T(7)) \times T(3))/T(7))))$
22738 := $(T(T((2+T(2)))) + ((T(7)^3) + T(T(8))))$
22741 := $((2 + T(2)) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) + 1)))$
22742 := $(T(T(2)) - ((-2) \times T(T(7))) \times T((T(4) - T(2))))$
22743 := $((2 + T((2 \times T(7)) - T(4))) \times T(T(3)))$
22744 := $-(((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) - (T(7) \times T((T(4) + 4))))$
22746 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T((T(2) \times T(7))) - T(4)) + T(T(6))))$
22747 := $(-T(2)) - (T(-((T(2) - T(7)))) \times (T(4) \times (-7)))$
22748 := $((T(2 \times T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7)))) \times (T(T(4)) - 8)$
22749 := $(T(T(2)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times ((7 - T(T(4))) - T(T(9))))$
22750 := $((2 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 7) \times 50)$
22752 := $(T(2^{T(2)})) \times (T((7 \times 5)) + 2)$
22754 := $-(((T(T(T(2))) + T(-((T(2) - T(7)))) + (-T(5)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
22755 := $((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) \times 7) + (5) \times T(5)$
22757 := $((T(T(T(2))) - T(T((T(2) + (7)))) \times (-T(5)) - (T(7)))$
22758 := $(T(T(2)) - ((-2) - T((7 \times 5))) \times T(8))$
22759 := $((T(T(T(T(2))))/(-T(T(2)))) + ((7 + T(5)) \times T(T(9))))$
22764 := $-((T(T(2)) + (((-2) - T(T(7))) - (6)) \times T(T(4))))$
22765 := $((T(T((T(2)^2))) \times (T(7) - (6))) - 5)$
22767 := $(-T(2)) - (T(T((2+7))) \times (6 - T(7)))$
22769 := $(-(2/2) - (-((T(7) - (6)) \times T(T(9))))$
22771 := $-((T(T(T(2))) + ((-2) \times T(7)) \times (T(T(7)) + 1)))$
22772 := $(2 - ((T(T(2)) - T(7)) \times T(T((7+2))))$
22773 := $(T(2) + (T(T((2+7))) \times (T(7) - T(3))))$
22774 := $((2 \times (T(T(T(2)))) - (-T(7)) \times T(T(7)))) - 4$
22776 := $(T(T(2)) + (T(T((2+7))) \times (T(7) - (6))))$
22778 := $(T(T(2)) - ((2 \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(7)) - T(8)))$
22779 := $(-2) - ((2 \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(7)) - T(9))$
22782 := $(-T(2)) + ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(7))) \times T((T(8) - T(T(2))))$
22783 := $(-2) + ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(7))) \times T((T(8) - T(3))))$
22785 := $(((-2) + (T(2)^7)) - T(T(8))) \times T(5)$
22788 := $((T(2) + T((27+8))) \times T(8))$
22789 := $(-T(2)) - ((T(T((T(2) + (7)))) \times (-T(T(8))))/T(9))$
22791 := $(T(T(T(2))) - ((T(T(2)) - T(7)) \times T(T((9 \times 1))))$
22792 := $(22 \times ((7 + T(T(9))) - T(T(2))))$
22793 := $(2 - (((T(T(2)) - T(7)) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(3))))$
22794 := $(-T(T(2))) - (T(T(-((2-7))) \times (-T((9+T(4))))))$

- 22795** := ((T(T(2+2))) × T(T(7))) + T((T(9) – T(5))))
22797 := ((T(T(2+2))) × (T(T(7)) + 9)) – T(7))
22798 := (–2) – (T((2 + T(7)) + T(9))) × (–8))
22815 := (((T(T(T(T(2))) – 2)) × 8) + 1) × T(5))
22824 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T((T(T(2)) + 8))) – (T(–(2) + T(T(4))))))
22825 := ((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) × (T(8²) – (5)))
22827 := (T(T(T(2))) × (T(T(2)) + T(((T(8)/2) + T(7))))))
22833 := (((T(2)^{T(2)}) × T(T(8))) + (T(T(T(3))) × T(T(3))))
22834 := (T((T(T(T(2))) – 2)) – (T(T(8)) × (–34)))
22836 := ((T((T(T(T(2))) – 2)) + (T(T(8)) × (–T(3)))) × (–6))
22838 := ((T(T(2)) + T(–(2) + T(8))) × 38)
22839 := ((2 + T(T(T(2)))) × (–((T(8) + T(3))) + T(T(9))))
22842 := ((T(T(T(2))) – (T((T(2) + (84)))))) × (–T(T(2))))
22844 := ((T(T(T(2))) × (T((2 × T(8))) – T(T(T(4)))))) – 4)
22845 := ((–(((T(2)²) + 8)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(5))
22846 := (–2) + ((T(T(2)) + T(T(8))) × (T(T(4)) – (T(6))))
22848 := (T(T(T(2))) × ((–2) + T(8)) × (4 × 8))
22851 := (T(2) – (T(T(T(2))) × (–(8 × T((T(5) + 1))))))
22854 := (–((T(T(T(2))) + (T(–((T(2) – 8)) × (T(5) – T(T(T(4))))))))
22855 := (T(T((2 + 2))) + (8 × T((5 × T(5))))))
22857 := ((2 + T((2 + 8))) × (–5) + T(T(7)))
22863 := ((–((T(2) × (T(2) – T(8)))) × T(T(6))) – (T(3)))
22866 := (–(T(2)) – ((T(T(2)) – (T((8 + 6)))) × T(T(6))))
22867 := (–2) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × (8 + T((6 + 7))))
22869 := (((T(T(2)) – ((T(2) – 8)) × T(T(6))) × 9)
22872 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) – (T(2) – (T(T(8)) × (T(7) + T(T(2))))))
22873 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) – (2 – (T(T(8)) × (T(7) + T(3))))
22874 := (–((T(T(2)) + ((–(2 + 8)) – T(T(7))) × T(T(4))))
22875 := (–(T(2)) – (T(T(2)) × (–(T(87) – T(5))))
22877 := (–(T(T(2))) – ((T(T(T(2))) + (8 × T(T(7)))) × (–7)))
22878 := (–2) – (–((T(2) + 8)) × T((T(7) + T(8))))
22880 := ((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) × T(((8 × 8) + 0)))
22881 := (((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) × T((8 × 8))) + 1)
22882 := (2 + ((T(2) + 8) × T(8²)))
22883 := (((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) × T((8 × 8))) + 3)
22884 := (((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) × T((8 × 8))) + 4)
22885 := ((2 + T(T(T(2)))) × (T((8 + T(8))) + (5)))
22886 := (((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) × T((8 × 8))) + 6)
22887 := (((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) × T((8 × 8))) + 7)
22888 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (2 + T((T(8) + T(8)))) × 8)
22889 := (((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) × T((8 × 8))) + 9)
22890 := (T(T(T(2))) × (T((2 + 8)) + T(T((9 + 0))))
22891 := ((T(T(T(2))) × (T((2 + 8)) + T(T(9)))) + 1)
22892 := ((T(T(T(2))) × (T((2 + 8)) + T(T(9)))) + 2)
22893 := (T(2) – ((–(T((2 + 8))) – T(T(9))) × T(T(3))))
22894 := ((T(T(T(2))) × (T((2 + 8)) + T(T(9)))) + 4)
22895 := ((T(T(T(2))) × (T((2 + 8)) + T(T(9)))) + 5)
22896 := (T(T(2)) – ((–(T((2 + 8))) – T(T(9))) × T(6)))
22897 := ((T((2 × T(2))) × (T(8) + T(T(9)))) + T(T(7)))
22898 := (2 – ((2 × 8) × T((T(9) + 8))))
22899 := ((T(T(T(2))) × (T((2 + 8)) + T(T(9)))) + 9)
22902 := (22 × (T(T(9)) + T(T(02))))
22904 := ((–(T(T(2))) × (T(T(T(2))) – (T(90)))) – T(T(T(4))))
22911 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) – (T(T(T(2))) × (–(T((T(9) + 1)) – 1))))
22914 := (T(2) – (T(T(T(2))) × (–((T(T(9)) + 1) + T(T(4))))))
22923 := ((22 × (T(T(9)) + T(T(2)))) + T(T(3)))
22924 := (22 × (T(T(9)) + (T(2) + (4))))
22926 := (((T(T(T(2)))²) × T(9)) + T(T((2 × 6))))
22928 := ((T(T(T((2 + 2)))) + T((T(9) + T(T(2)))) × 8)
22929 := (–((T(T(T(2))) + (–((2⁹) – 2)) × T(9))))
22932 := ((T((T(2) × 29)) – (T(3)) × T(T(2))))
22935 := (((T(T(2))^{T(2)}) + T(93)) × 5)
22938 := ((22 × T(T(9))) – (T(T(3)) × (–8)))
22944 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(–(2) + T(9))) + T(4)) × 4)
22945 := (((22 × T(T(9))) + T(T(4))) + T(T(5)))
22946 := ((22 × T(T(9))) – T(T(4))) + T(T(6)))
22947 := ((T(T(T(2))) × T((2 + T(9)))) – T((T(4) + T(7))))
22962 := ((T(T(2)) × T((T((2 + 9)) + T(6)))) – T(T(2)))
22964 := ((T(T(2)) × T((T((2 + 9)) + T(6)))) – (4))
22965 := (((T(T(T(2))) × (–T(2))) + T(96)) × 5)
22966 := (–2) – (T((T((2 + 9)) + T(6))) × (–6))
22967 := (((T(2) + (T(2)⁹))/6) × 7)
22968 := (T(T(2)) × T(((T(2) × T(9)) – ((6 × 8))))
22972 := (–(((T((2 + T(2))) – T(T(9))) – ((T(7)^{T(2)}))))
22973 := ((22 × T(T(9))) – T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))
22974 := (T(T(2)) + (T(T(2)) × T((97 – T(4))))
22975 := ((T(–(–2) – T(2)) + T(9)) × T(7)) + (T(5))
22978 := (((2 + T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(9)) – (7))) – (T(T(8))))
22983 := ((2 + T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(9)) – T(8))) + T(3)
22984 := ((T(T(2)) + T(–((2 – 9)))) × (T(T(8)) + T(4)))
22985 := ((2 + T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(9))) – T((8 × 5))
22986 := (T(T(2)) × ((2 × T(9)) + T(86)))
22989 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(2)) + (98))) – T(T(9)))
22992 := (((T(T(T(T(2))))/(-T(2))) + T(T(9))) × (T(9) – T(T(T(2))))))
22994 := (–((T(T(2)) × (T(T(2)) – T((T(9) + T(9)))))) – T(T(T(4))))
22995 := ((22 × T(T(9))) – (T(9) × (–5)))
22997 := (2 – ((T(T(T(2))) × (–T(T(9)))) – ((T(9) × T(7))))
22998 := (T(T(2)) × (2⁹) + T((T(9) + T(8))))
23045 := (–((T(T(–(2) + T(3)))) + (T(T(T(04))) × (–T(5))))
23094 := (–((T(T(2)) – ((T(30) – T(9)) × T(T(4))))
23115 := ((T(T(T((2 + 3) – 1))) + 1) × T(5))
23119 := (–2) – (T(T(3)) × (–(T(11)) – T(T(9))))
23121 := (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(T((3 + 1)))) × T((T(T(2)) – 1))))
23124 := ((T(2) + T(T(3))) + (T(–(1) + T(T(2)))) × T(T(T(4))))

- 23128** := $((T((-2) + T(T(3)))) - T(T(12))) \times (-8)$
23135 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(13))) \times 5$
23142 := $(T(T((2^3) - 1))) \times (T(T(4)) + 2)$
23143 := $(-2) + (T((T(3) - 1)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 3))$
23145 := $((T(2) \times T(31)) + T(T(4))) \times T(5)$
23148 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(3) + 1))) + (T(T(4)))) \times T(8)$
23150 := $((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + 1) \times 50$
23154 := $((T(T((-2) + T(3))) - 1) - (-T(5)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
23155 := $(T(T((-2) + T(3))) + (T(T(T(-1 - 5)))) \times T(5))$
23157 := $(2 - (T(T(3 + 1))) \times (-T(5) - T(T(7))))$
23163 := $(-T(2)) \times (T(T(T(3 + 1)))) - (T(6)^3)$
23164 := $(2^{T(3)} + (T(-1 - 6)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
23166 := $(T(((T(2)^3) - 1)) \times 66)$
23172 := $((-T(T(2))) - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(17)^2)$
23175 := $((-T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-17 + T(T(5)))$
23177 := $((T((T(2) + T(T(3)))) + 1) \times 77)$
23178 := $((2 + T(T(3 + 1))) \times T(T(7))) + T(8)$
23184 := $(T(23) \times (1 \times 84))$
23190 := $(-T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (1 + T(90)))$
23193 := $((T(T(2))^{T(3)-1}) - T(9)) \times 3$
23194 := $(-T(T(2))) + ((T(T(T(3))) + 1) \times (T(9) + T(T(4))))$
23197 := $(T(T(T(2))) + (((T(T(3)) + 1) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(7))))$
23199 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(3)) + 1) \times (-9 - T(T(9))))$
23205 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(20))) \times 5$
23212 := $((T(T(2))^{T(3)} - T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1) / 2)$
23226 := $((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(T(3))) / (-T(2)))) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(6))))$
23232 := $((T(2)^{T(3)} - T(2)) \times 32)$
23235 := $(-((T(T(T(2))) - (T((T(3) \times T(2))) \times T((T(T(3)) - 5))))))$
23237 := $((T(T(2))^{T(3)} / 2) - T((T(3) + 7)))$
23238 := $(T(T(2)) \times (3 - (T(T(2)) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(8))))))$
23241 := $(-((T(T(2)) - (3^{T(2)}) \times T(41))))$
23244 := $(-T(T(2))) + (T(3 + 2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(4))$
23245 := $(T(T((-2) + T(3))) + ((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5)))$
23247 := $(T(((2 \times 3) / 2^4)) \times 7)$
23248 := $((T(T(2))^{T(3)} / 2) + (T(4) \times (-8)))$
23249 := $(2 - (-((3^{T(2)}) \times T((-4) + T(9))))$
23250 := $(T(-((2 - 32))) \times 50)$
23253 := $(-T(2)) + (T((T(3) \times T(2))) \times T((-5) + T(T(3))))$
23254 := $((-T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times T(T(T(4))))$
23255 := $((T((T(2) \times 32)) - 5) \times 5)$
23256 := $(T((T(2) \times T(3))) \times T(((2 \times 5) + 6)))$
23259 := $(-T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(3) - T(2^5)) \times T(9)))$
23262 := $((T(T(2))^{T(3)} / 2) - T((T(T(6)) / T(T(T(2))))))$
23264 := $((T(T(2))^{T(3)} / 2) - (64))$
23265 := $(-T(T(2)) \times (T(3 \times 2) - (6^5)))$
23268 := $(T(T(T(2))) + (((T(T(3))^{T(2)} + (T(6) \times T(T(8))))))$
23269 := $(T(T(T((-2) + T(3)))) - (T(T(2)) + (-T(6)) \times T(T(9))))$
23272 := $((T(T(2))^{T(3)} / 2) - (T(7) \times 2))$
23273 := $((T(T(2))^{T(3)} / 2) - (T((7 + 3))))$
23274 := $((-T(2)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(2) + T(T(7)))) / (-4))$
23275 := $((-2) + T(T(3))) \times T((T(T(2)) + (T(7) + T(5))))$
23276 := $((T(23) / T(2)) \times T((T(7) - 6)))$
23277 := $(2 - ((T(T(3)) - 2) \times (-T((7 \times 7))))$
23283 := $((-T(2)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(8))) \times T(3))$
23286 := $((T(T(2))^{T(3)} / 2) - ((T(8) + 6)))$
23289 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T((3^2))) - (T(T(8)) / (-9)))$
23294 := $(-((T(T(2)) - ((T(T(3)) + T(2)) \times T(T(9)))) - T(T(T(4))))$
23295 := $((-T(2)) - T((T(3) - (-2) \times T(9)))) \times (-5)$
23296 := $(T(T(T((-2) + T(3)))) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(9))) - (T(6))))$
23298 := $(-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T((T(T(2)) \times 9)) \times 8))$
23317 := $(-T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((-3) - T(T(3 + 1))) \times T(T(7)))$
23319 := $((T(2) \times (T(3)^{T(3)-1}) - 9)$
23321 := $(-T(T(2)) - (((T(3)^{T(3)} / 2) - 1))$
23322 := $(T(2) \times ((T(3)^{3+2} - 2))$
23323 := $(-2) + (((T(3)^{T(3)} / 2) - 3))$
23324 := $((T(2)^{T(3)} \times 32) - 4)$
23325 := $(2 + (((T(3)^{T(3)} / 2) - 5))$
23326 := $(-2) + (((T(3)^{T(3)} \times T(2)) / 6)$
23327 := $(T(T(2)) - ((T(3)^{T(3)} / (-2)) + 7))$
23331 := $(T(2) + ((T(3)^{T(3)} / (3 - 1)))$
23332 := $((-2) + T(3) - ((T(3)^{T(3)} / (-2)))$
23334 := $(2 \times (3 - ((T(3)^{T(3)} / (-4))))$
23335 := $(-2) - (3 \times (-3) - (T(3)^5))$
23342 := $((T(T(2))^{T(3)} + T((3 + 4))) / 2)$
23344 := $((T(T(2) \times T(3))^3 + 4) \times 4)$
23346 := $(T(2) \times (T(3) + ((T(3)^4) \times 6))$
23349 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (-3) \times (T(3)^{-4+9}))$
23352 := $((2^3) + (T(3)^5) \times T(2))$
23354 := $((23 + T(T(T(3)))) - (-T(5)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
23355 := $(-T(T(2)) \times (T(3) - ((T(3)^5) + T(5))))$
23358 := $(T(T(2)) - (-3) \times ((T(3)^5) + 8))$
23364 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(3) + (3 \times (6^4))))$
23367 := $(-T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))) / T(T(3)))) - ((3 \times T(6)) \times T(T(7))))$
23373 := $((T(2) \times (T(3^3) - 7)) \times T(T(3)))$
23379 := $(-T(T(T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(3)) \times (-T(7) \times T(9))))$
23382 := $((T(2) \times T(3)) \times (3 + (T(8)^2)))$
23385 := $((T(2 \times T(3))) \times T((3 \times 8)) - T(5))$
23387 := $(-T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(T(T(3))) / 3) \times (-8)) + (T(T(7))))$
23388 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((-3) \times T(3) + T(88)))$

$$\begin{aligned} 23389 &:= (-2) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(8)) \times T(9))) \\ 23394 &:= -((T(T(2)) - ((3 \times T(39)) \times T(4))) \\ 23395 &:= ((T((T(2) + T(T(3)))) \times T((3 + 9))) - 5) \\ 23406 &:= ((T(T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(40))) \times 6) \\ 23408 &:= (2^3) \times T((40 + T(8))) \\ 23411 &:= (2 + (T((T(T(3)) - (4)))^{1+1})) \\ 23412 &:= (T(2) + (T(((T(3) + T(4)) + 1)^2)) \\ 23413 &:= (-2) - ((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T((-1) + T(3)))) \\ 23415 &:= (((2 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(4)) \times T((-1) + T(5))) \\ 23418 &:= (2 - ((T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + 1) \times (-8))) \\ 23421 &:= (T(T(2)) - ((-T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times T((T(T(2)) - 1))) \\ 23424 &:= ((2 + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) \times (2 \times 4)) \\ 23425 &:= ((T((2 + 3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(25))) \\ 23427 &:= (T((T(2) \times T(3))) \times ((T(T(4)) \times T(2)) - T(7))) \\ 23428 &:= ((T(2^{T(3)})) \times T(4)) + T((2 \times T(8))) \\ 23432 &:= ((T(2) + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) \times (T(3) + 2)) \\ 23436 &:= (T(2) \times (((T(3)^4) + T(3)) \times 6)) \\ 23438 &:= (2 - (((T(T(3)) + T(4)) \times T(T(3))) \times (-T(8)))) \\ 23439 &:= ((T(T(2)) + (T(34))) \times 39) \\ 23444 &:= (((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T((3 + 4)))) - T(4))/4) \\ 23445 &:= ((T((2 \times 34)) \times T(4)) - T(5)) \\ 23447 &:= (T(T(T(2))) - (T((-3) + T(T(4)))) \times (-T(4) + (7))) \\ 23448 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (T((T(3 \times 4)) + T(4)) - 8)) \\ 23452 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(3))) + T(4)) \times 52) \\ 23454 &:= (-T(T(2))) - (T(((3 - T(T(4))) + T(T(5)))) \times (-T(4))) \\ 23455 &:= (((T(T(2) + T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(5)) - 5) \\ 23457 &:= (-T(2)) - ((T(3) \times T(4)) \times (T(5) - T(T(7)))) \\ 23463 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) + T(3 \times 4)) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(3)))) \\ 23464 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) - (((T(T(3 + 4))) + (T(6))) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 23467 &:= (-((T(2) \times T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(6) + T(T(7)))) \\ 23468 &:= (2^3) + (T(4) \times T(68)) \\ 23472 &:= ((T(2) \times T(T(3))) + (T((T(4) + (7)))^2)) \\ 23473 &:= ((-2) \times T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(3)))) \\ 23474 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(3^4) \times 7) - (4))) \\ 23475 &:= (((-T(2)) + T(T((T(3) + (4)))) + (T(7))) \times T(5)) \\ 23476 &:= ((-2) + (T((3^4) \times 7)) + T(T(6))) \\ 23478 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (-3) + T(((4 + 7) \times 8))) \\ 23481 &:= ((T((T(2) \times T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + (T(81))) \\ 23484 &:= ((-T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (48 + T(T(4))) \\ 23485 &:= ((T((T(2) \times 3)) - T(4)) \times (T(T(8)) + (5))) \\ 23488 &:= (((2 + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + 8) \times 8) \\ 23490 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (3 \times T(4))) \times 90) \\ 23492 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(9))))/T(2) \\ 23493 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times T((-3) + T((4 + 9)))) - 3) \\ 23494 &:= (-T(T(2))) - ((T(T(T(3))) + 4) \times (-T(9) - T(T(4)))) \\ 23495 &:= -((T(2^{T(3)})) - (T(T(4)) \times T((T(9) - T(5)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23496 &:= (T(T(2)) \times T((34 + (9 \times 6)))) \\ 23497 &:= ((T((2 + 3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (-9) + T(T(7))) \\ 23498 &:= (2 - (-T(3)) \times T(-(T(4) - 98))) \\ 23499 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times (-T(3)) + T((T(4) \times 9))) - T(T(9))) \\ 23513 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(5)))) + T(T(13)))) \\ 23520 &:= ((-2^3) + T(T(5))) \times T(20) \\ 23523 &:= (T((T(T(T(T(2))))/3) + ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(2) \times T(3)))))) \\ 23525 &:= ((-T(2)) \times T(T((-3) + T(5)))) + (2^{T(5)}) \\ 23526 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (-T(3)) - ((T(5) + 2) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 23527 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) + ((-3) - T((5 \times 2))) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 23528 &:= ((2 + T((3 + T(5)))) \times T((2 \times 8))) \\ 23529 &:= (((T(T(2)) \times T((T(3) \times T(5)))) - T(T(2))) - T(T(9))) \\ 23532 &:= ((T((-2) + (T(3) \times T(5)))) + (T(3))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 23534 &:= ((T(T((2 \times 3))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T((3 + T(4)))) \\ 23535 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times T((T(3) \times T(5)))) - T((3 \times T(5)))) \\ 23537 &:= (T(2) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(5)))) + T(T((T(3) + (7)))))) \\ 23538 &:= (T(2) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(5)) - T(T(3)))) - (T(T(8)))) \\ 23541 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(3))) + (T(5) \times T(T(T(4 \times 1)))))) \\ 23544 &:= ((T(T(2)^3) \times (54 + T(T(4)))) \\ 23545 &:= ((T((-2) + T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(5)) + (4)) - T(5)) \\ 23547 &:= ((T(2)^3) + (T(5) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(7)))) \\ 23548 &:= ((T(T(2))^{T(3)} + ((-T(5)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - 8) \\ 23550 &:= ((T(T(2)) + T((T(3) \times 5))) \times 50) \\ 23554 &:= ((-2) + T(T(T(3)))) + (T(5) \times (T(5) + T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 23556 &:= -((T(T(2)) + ((3 + T(5)) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 23559 &:= ((T(2) \times (T(3)^5)) + T(T((T(5) - 9)))) \\ 23561 &:= (((-T(2) \times T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6)) - 1) \\ 23562 &:= (T(2) \times ((T(3)^5) + T((6 \times 2)))) \\ 23564 &:= (2 + ((3 + T(5)) \times (-T(T(6)) + T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 23565 &:= (((-T(T(2))) - T(T(T(3)))) + T((T(T(5)) - (T(6)))) \times 5) \\ 23568 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times 5) - (T(6) + T(T(8)))) \\ 23574 &:= (-2) + ((T(3) \times T(T(-(T(5) - T(7)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 23576 &:= -((T(T(T((-2) + T(3)))) + (T(T(-(T(5) - T(7)))) \times (-6))) \\ 23578 &:= (2 \times ((T(T(3)) \times T((5 + T(7)))) + 8) \\ 23583 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times 5) - (T(T(8)) + (T(3)))) \\ 23585 &:= -((T(2^{T(3)})) - ((T(58) \times T(5)))) \\ 23586 &:= (T(2) \times ((T(3)^5) + (86))) \\ 23588 &:= (2 + (T(3) \times (T(5) + T(88)))) \\ 23589 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times ((T(3) - T(T(5))) \times (-T(8)))) - T(T(9))) \\ 23594 &:= (-T(T(2))) - ((T(T(T(3))) + 5) \times (-T(9) - T(T(4)))) \\ 23595 &:= ((-2) + (35 \times T(9))) \times T(5) \\ 23597 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(3) \times T(5)) + T(T(9)))) - T(7)) \\ 23598 &:= (T((T(2) \times T(3))) \times (-T(5) - T((9 + 8)))) \\ 23625 &:= (T((T(2) \times 3)) \times (T(6) \times 25)) \\ 23627 &:= (2 - ((T(3) - T(T(6))) \times T((2 \times 7)))) \\ 23628 &:= (T(2) - ((T(3) - T(T(6))) \times T((T(T(2)) + 8)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 23634** := ((T(2) + T((3 + T(6)))) × T((3 × 4)))
23635 := (2 + ((-T(3)) + T(T(6))) × T(T(3))) × 5)
23642 := (2 + T(T(T(3)))) + (T((T(6) - (4)))²)
23644 := (-T(T(2))) + ((T(T(T(T(3)))/T(6))) × T(4) + T(T(T(4))))
23645 := (((T(T(T(2))) × (-T(3)) + T(T(6)))) + 4) × 5)
23646 := (((T(T(2)) × T(36)) - T(T(4))) × 6)
23649 := -((T(2) + T(((3 × 6) × 4)) × (-9)))
23652 := ((T(2) × 3) × T(((T(6) + T(5)) × 2)))
23654 := (-((T(T(2)) + ((T(T(3)) - T(T(6))) × T(T(5)))) - T(T(T(4))))
23655 := (((T((2 × 3)) × T(T(6))) - T(T(5))) × 5)
23664 := ((T(2) + T((3 × 6))) × T((6 + T(4))))
23667 := ((23 × T(6)) × (T(6) + T(7)))
23674 := ((2^{T(3)}) × T(6)) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(4)))
23679 := ((T(T(2³))) × (6 + T(7))) + T(T(9))
23682 := (T(T(T(2))) - (((T(3)⁶) + T(T(8)))/(-2)))
23684 := ((2 - T(3)) - (-T(6)) × T((-8) + T(T(4))))
23685 := (-T(2)) + (T(T(3)) × T(((6 + T(8)) + (5))))
23686 := (-2) + (T(T(3)) × T((68 - T(6))))
23688 := ((T((2 × 3) × 6) - 8) × T(8))
23692 := ((-2) + T(3)) - (-T(6)) × T((T(9) + 2))
23694 := (T(T(2)) × ((-T(3)) - T(T(6))) + T(T((9 + 4))))
23695 := (T(2^{T(3)}) - ((-T(6)) × T(T(9))) + T(T(5)))
23712 := ((T(23) + T(7)) × T(12))
23715 := (T((T(2) × 3)) × ((T(T(7)) + 1) + T(T(5))))
23716 := (((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(3))) + (T(T(7)))) × T((1 + 6)))
23722 := (((T(T(2)) × T(T(3))) + T(7))²) + T(T(2))
23723 := (T(T(T((-2) + T(3)))) - (-T(7)^{T(2)}) - T(T(T(3))))
23724 := ((T(T(2³))) - 7) × T((2 × 4))
23725 := ((T((T(2) × 3)) + T(7)) × T(25))
23728 := (-2) + (3 × (-T(T(7))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(8)))
23729 := ((T(T(T(T(2))))/3) - (T(72) × (-9)))
23730 := (T(T(2)) × (T(T((T(3) + (7)))) - T(T(T(3 + 0))))
23731 := ((T(T(2)) × (T(T((T(3) + (7)))) - T(T(T(3)))) + 1)
23732 := (2 - ((T(T(T(3))) - T(T((7 + T(3)))) × T(T(2))))
23733 := (T(2) - ((T(T(T(3))) - T(T((7 + T(3)))) × T(3)))
23734 := ((T(T(2)) × (T(T((T(3) + (7)))) - T(T(T(3)))) + 4)
23735 := ((-T(T(2))) + T((T(3) + T((7 + T(3)))) × 5)
23736 := (T(T(2)) - ((T(T(T(3))) - T(T((7 + T(3)))) × 6)
23737 := ((T(T(2)) × (T(T((T(3) + (7)))) - T(T(T(3)))) + 7)
23738 := ((T(T(2)) × (T(T((T(3) + (7)))) - T(T(T(3)))) + 8)
23739 := ((T(T(2)) × (T(T((T(3) + (7)))) - T(T(T(3)))) + 9)
23742 := (((T((2 × T(3))) × T(7)) - T(T(T(4)))) - 2)
23743 := (T(T(T(2))) - ((-3) - T(T(7))) × (T(T(4)) + 3))
23744 := ((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(7)) × (-4) - T(T(4))))
23745 := ((T((T(2) × 3)) × T((T(7) + (4)))) - (T(5)))
23747 := (T(2) - ((T((T(3) × 7)) - T(T(4))) × (-T(7))))
23749 := (-2) + (T(T(3)) × (T((-7) + T(T(4)))) - T(9))
23750 := ((T(T(T(2))) - (T((3 + T(7)))) × (-50))
23751 := (((T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(T(7))))/(-5 - 1))
23752 := (-((2³) × (T(T(7)) - ((T(5)^{T(2)}))))
23753 := (2 - ((T(T(T(3))) - T(7)) × (-T(T(5)) - 3))
23754 := -((T(T(2)) - (((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) + 5) × T(T(4))))
23755 := ((-2) + T((T(3) + T((T(7) - T(5)))) × 5)
23757 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(7) × T(T(5))) × 7)
23758 := (-2) - ((-T(3)) + T(T((-7) + T(5)))) × (-T(8))
23759 := (23 × (-((7 - 5) + T(T(9))))
23760 := ((T((-2) + T(3)) - T(T(7))) × (-60))
23765 := ((2 + 3) × T((7 - (-6 × T(5))))
23766 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(3) + T(T((7 + 6)))) - T(T(6))))
23768 := ((T((T(2) × 3)) + (T(76))) × 8)
23769 := (T(2) - (-T(3)) × (T(76) + T(T(9))))
23772 := (((T(23) + 7) × T(7)) × T(2))
23775 := ((-T(T(2)) × T(T(3))) + T((T(T(7))/7)) × T(5))
23777 := ((-2) + T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(7))/7) × T(T(7)))
23778 := (((T(2) × T(T(3))) × (-T(7)) + T(T(7))) - T(8))
23779 := -((T(T(T(2))) + ((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(7))) × T((7 + 9))))
23784 := (2 - ((T(3) - T(7)) × T((T(8) + T(4))))
23785 := ((-T(2)) - (T((T(3) + T(7))) × (-8)) × 5)
23788 := ((2^{T(3)}) - ((-7) + T(T(8))) × (-T(8)))
23793 := (((T(T(2)) × T(T(3))) - T(7)) + T(T(9))) × T(T(3))
23794 := (-T(T(2))) - ((T(T(T(3))) + 7) × (-T(9) - T(T(4))))
23795 := (2 + (T(T(T(3))) × ((T(7) - T(9)) + T(T(5))))
23796 := (T(2) + (T(T(T(3))) × (7 + 96))
23797 := (-T(2)) - ((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(7))) × T((9 + 7)))
23799 := -((T(T(2)) + ((T(3) - T(7)) × T(T(9))) - T(T(9))))
23805 := (T(T((T(2) × 3)) × (8 + T(05)))
23814 := ((T(2) × T(T(3))) × T(((T(8) + 1) - T(4))))
23815 := ((-2) + T((T(T(3)) + 8)) × T(-((1 - 5))))
23821 := ((T(T(T(2)))/3) × T((82 × 1))
23822 := ((T(2) + (T(T(3)) × T(82)))/T(2))
23823 := (2 - ((T(T(3)) × T(82)))/(-3))
23824 := ((T(T(T(2))) × (T(T(T(3))) + T((T(8) + T(T(2)))))) + T(4))
23826 := (((T(2)^{T(3)}) × (T(8) - T(2))) - T(T(6)))
23827 := ((2 × 3) + (T(82) × 7))
23829 := ((T(T((-2) + T(3))) - T(T(8))) × (T(T(2)) - T(9))
23832 := (((2 - T(3)) + T(T(8))) × (T(3)²)
23834 := (((T(2) × T(T(T(3)))) + 8) × 34)
23835 := ((T((2 + 3)) + T(T(8))) × 35)
23838 := (T((2 × T(3))) + ((T(T(8)) - T(3)) × T(8))
23842 := (-2) × (T(T(T(3))) + (-8) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2))))
23844 := ((T(T(T(2))) - ((-3) × T(8)) × T(T(4))) × 4)
23848 := ((T((2 × 38)) + T(T(4))) × 8)
23850 := (((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(3))) + T(8)) × 50)

- 23853** := $((T(T(2^3)) \times T(8)) - T(T(5))) - 3$
23854 := $((-2) - (T(T(3)) \times (-T(8))) - (-T(5) \times T(T(4))))$
23856 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(3)) + T(T(8+5))) - T(T(6))))$
23859 := $((T(2) \times T(3)) \times T((T(8) + T(5)))) - 9$
23862 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(3) \times T(T(8))) - (T(6) - 2)))$
23864 := $((T(T(2)) \times ((-3) + T(T(8))) \times 6) - 4)$
23865 := $((T(T(2^3)) \times T(8)) - T(T(6))) + T(T(5))$
23866 := $(-2) - ((-3) + T(T(8))) \times (-6 \times 6))$
23868 := $(T((2 + (3 \times 8))) \times 68)$
23871 := $(T(2) + ((-3) + T(T(8))) \times T(7 + 1))$
23872 := $(2^{T(3)}) \times ((-T(8)) + T(T(7))) + T(2)$
23874 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(3) \times T(T(8))) - (7 + T(4))))$
23877 := $((T(T(T(2)))^3) - ((-8) - T(7)) \times T(T(7)))$
23883 := $((T(T(2)) / (-3)) + T(T(8))) \times T(8) - T(T(3))$
23884 := $(T(T(2)) + ((-3) + T(T(8))) \times T(8) + T(4))$
23885 := $((T(T(2^3)) \times T(8)) - (T(8 + 5)))$
23886 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(3) \times T(T(8))) - (T(8) - T(6))))$
23888 := $((T(T(2^3)) \times T(8)) - 88)$
23889 := $((-2) \times T(T(3)) - (T(T(8)) \times (-T(8))) + T(9))$
23892 := $((-23) + T(89)) \times T(T(2))$
23894 := $(2 - (T(T(3)) + (T(T(8)) \times (-9))) \times 4)$
23895 := $-(((T(2^3)) - (T(8) \times T(9))) \times T(5))$
23897 := $-(((T(T(2)) \times (T(T(3)) - (T(89)))) + (7))$
23898 := $(T(23) \times 89) - T(T(8))$
23899 := $((T(T(T(2)))) / (-3)) - (T(T(8)) \times (9 - T(9)))$
23922 := $((T(T(2^3)) + T(9^2)) \times T(T(2)))$
23924 := $((2 - T(T(3))) + (T(T(9)) \times T(T(2)))) \times 4$
23925 := $(T((2 + (3 \times 9))) \times T(2 \times 5))$
23928 := $(T(23) - (-9) \times T(2 \times T(8)))$
23935 := $(T(2^{T(3)}) - (T(93) \times (-5)))$
23937 := $((T(2) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(9))) - T((T(3) \times 7))$
23938 := $(-2) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(9)) + T((T(3) + 8))))$
23952 := $(((-2) \times T(T(3))) - T(T(9))) \times (5 - T(T(T(2))))$
23954 := $(T(T((T(T(T(2)))) / 3)) \times (9 + (5 \times T(4))))$
23955 := $((T(T(2 \times 3)) + (T(95))) \times 5)$
23957 := $(T(2) - (((T(3) \times (-9)) - 5) \times T(T(7))))$
23958 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-3) - ((9 - T(T(5))) \times T(8)))$
23972 := $((23 \times (T(T(9)) + (7))) + T(T(2)))$
23973 := $((23 \times T(T(9))) + (T(7) \times T(3)))$
23974 := $-((T(T(2)) - ((T(T(3)) + 9) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(4))))$
23975 := $(((-2) \times T(T(3))) - (T(97))) \times (-5)$
23976 := $(T(T(2^3)) \times T((9 - 7) + 6))$
23978 := $(2 - (T((T(3)^{9-7})) \times (-T(8))))$
23979 := $(((-2) \times T(T(3))) \times (-T(9) + (7))) - T(9)$
23982 := $((T((2 - 3) + 9)) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(2))$
23983 := $(T(2^{T(3)}) + ((T(T(9)) + 8) \times T(T(3))))$
23984 := $((2^3) - ((-9) \times T(T(8))) \times 4)$
23985 := $-(((T(2 \times 3)) - (T(9) \times T(8))) \times T(5))$
23988 := $(T(T(2)) - ((T(T(3 + 9))) \times (-8)) + T(T(8)))$
23989 := $((2 + T(-((3 - 9))) \times (8 + T(T(9))))$
23991 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(3)) - T(9)) \times T((T(9) - 1))))$
23994 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-T(3)) + T((99 - T(4))))$
23997 := $((T(2) - T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(9))) \times (9 - T(7))$
24000 := $(T(T(2)) \times 4000)$
24024 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) \times ((T(4)^{02}) + 4))$
24045 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (T(40) + T((T(4) + T(5))))$
24048 := $((2 + T((40 - 4))) \times T(8))$
24066 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((-40) + T(T(6))) \times T(6))$
24079 := $((T(2) + T(40)) \times T(7)) + T(T(9))$
24100 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)) \times 100)$
24124 := $(2^{T(4)}) + (T((-1) + T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(4)))$
24128 := $((T(2) + T(4)) \times ((-1) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-8))$
24129 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T((4 - 1))) + T((2 + T(9))))$
24135 := $((T((-T(2)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T((1 \times 3)))) \times T(5))$
24138 := $(T(2) \times (T((T(T(4)) - 1)) + (3^8)))$
24144 := $(-T(T(2))) - (-T(4) \times T((14 + T(T(4))))$
24145 := $((T(T(2) + T(T(4) + 1))) \times T(4)) - 5$
24147 := $(-T(2)) - (-T(4) \times T((-1) - (T(4) \times (-7))))$
24148 := $(-2) - (-T(4) \times T((T(14) - T(8))))$
24156 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)) \times T(-((1 - (5 \times 6))))))$
24157 := $((T(T(T(T(2))) \times 4) + (1 - T(T(5)))) \times 7$
24163 := $(T(T((T(T(T(2))) - T(4))) + ((T((1 + 6))^3)))$
24164 := $((T(-((T(T(2)) - T(T(4)))) - 1) \times T(6)) - T(T(T(4))))$
24165 := $(((-T(T(2))) + T((T(T(4)) + 1))) + (T(6))) \times T(5)$
24168 := $((2 - T(T(4))) \times (T((-1) + T(6))) - T(T(8)))$
24174 := $((2 + T(41)) \times T(7)) + T(4)$
24184 := $((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(4))) \times (-1) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(T(4)))$
24188 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4)) + ((1 + T(T(8))) \times (-T(8))))$
24192 := $((T(2) + T(41)) \times T((9 - 2)))$
24194 := $-((T(T(2)) + (T(T(4)) \times ((1 - T(9)) \times T(4))))$
24198 := $(-2) - (T(T(4)) \times (T((1 + 9)) \times (-8)))$
24213 := $((-2) + (T(T(4)) \times 21)) \times T(T(3))$
24218 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (1 + T(8)))$
24219 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(-((1 - 9)))$
24221 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (-T(T(4))) \times ((T(T(T(2)))^2) - 1))$
24222 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(2))^{T(2)}))) \times 2$
24224 := $(2 \times (((T(T(4))^2) + T(2)) \times 4))$
24225 := $((T(T(2)) - T(((T(4)^2) - 2))) \times (-5))$
24227 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(2)))) - 7$
24228 := $(T(T(2)) \times (42 + (T(T(2)) \times T(T(8))))$
24232 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(3)) + 2))$
24234 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((-4) + T(2)) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))))$

- 24235** := $((-2) \times T(4) - ((T(T(2))) \times T(T(3)))) \times (-5))$
24236 := $(2 - (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(2)))) \times (-T(3)))) + (T(6)))$
24238 := $(-((T(T(2))) - 4) - (T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T((T(3) + 8))))$
24242 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(4) + T(2))$
24243 := $(-T(2) - ((4^{T(2)}) - T(T(4))) \times (-T(3)))$
24244 := $((T((2 + T(T(4))))/T(2)) \times 44)$
24245 := $((-2) + T((-T(T(4))) + T((T(T(2))) - 4))) \times 5$
24246 := $((-((2^4)^{T(2)})) + T(T(4))) \times (-6)$
24248 := $(2 + ((T(T(4)))^2 + (4))) \times 8$
24249 := $(-((T(T(2))) + ((T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))) \times (-9)))$
24261 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (6 \times 1)$
24262 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(6)/T(2))$
24263 := $(2 - (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(2)))) \times (-T(6))) - T(3))$
24264 := $(T((2 \times 4) \times ((T(2)^6) - T(T(4))))$
24265 := $(2 + (T((4 + 2) \times T(T(6)))) \times 5$
24266 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(6))/T(6))$
24267 := $(T(2) \times (4 - (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(6) - T(T(7))))))$
24268 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(6) - 8)$
24272 := $((T(T(T(2))) - 4) - (T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T((7 \times 2))))$
24273 := $(T(2) \times (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times 7) + T(3)))$
24274 := $((-2) + T(T(4))) \times ((-T(2)) + T(T(7))) + T(T(4)))$
24275 := $(2 \times T(4) - (T(T(T(2)))) \times (-7 \times T(5)))$
24276 := $((T(T(2 + 4))) \times T((2 \times 7))) + (T(6))$
24278 := $(-((T(2) - (4^{T(2)})) \times (T(T(7)) - 8))$
24279 := $(T(2) \times (-T(4) - (-T(2)) \times T((T(7) + T(9))))$
24282 := $((T(T(2)) + (T((4^2)))) \times T((T(8)/2))$
24283 := $((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-2 \times 8)) - (T(T(3)))$
24284 := $(2 \times (((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 8) - T(4))$
24285 := $((2^{T(4)} + T((-2) + T(8))) \times T(5))$
24286 := $((T(T(T(2))) + T(4) - (T((T(T(2)) + 8)) \times (-T(T(6))))$
24288 := $((2^{T(4)} \times T(2)) - T(8)) \times 8$
24291 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(9 - 1))$
24292 := $(2 \times (-4 - (T(T(2)) \times (-T(9)^2)))$
24294 := $(-((T(T(2)) \times (T((T(4) + T(2))) - (T(T(9)) \times 4)))$
24295 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(9) - 5))$
24297 := $(T(2) \times ((T(42) \times 9) - T(7)))$
24298 := $(-2) - (T((T(4)/2)) \times (-T(9) \times T(8)))$
24300 := $((T(2)^4) \times 300)$
24304 := $((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(3) + T(04)))$
24309 := $(T((-T(2)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(3))) \times 09$
24310 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(4)) \times T(T(3)))) + (T(10)))$
24314 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(4))) \times (-T(31))) + T(4)$
24315 := $((T(2)^4 + T(T(T(3) + 1)))) \times T(5)$
24318 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((-4) + T(31)) + T(T(8)))$
24320 := $((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(4))) \times 320)$
24321 := $((T(T(T(2))) - T(4)) \times T(T((T(3) \times 2) - 1)))$
24322 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(-T(4) + T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(2)))/T(T(T(2))))$
24323 := $(2 + ((T(T((-T(4) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(2))))/T(T(3))))$
24324 := $((T(2) - (T((4 \times 3)^2)) \times (-4))$
24325 := $(T(T(T(2))) + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(2))) - 5))$
24327 := $((-2) + T(T(4))) \times (-T(3) + T((2 + T(7))))$
24328 := $((2 \times T((4 \times 3))^2) - 8)$
24329 := $(-((T(T(T(2)))) - (-T(4) + (T(3) \times T((2 \times T(9))))))$
24331 := $(T(T(T(2))) + ((T(T(4)) \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(3)) + 1)))$
24332 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(4)) \times T(T(3)))) - (T(T(T(3)))/(-T(2))))$
24333 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(4)) \times T(T(3)))) + (T((T(3) + T(3))))$
24334 := $((T(2) + 43)^3)/4$
24335 := $((2^4) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)))) \times 5$
24336 := $((-T(2) + T(T(4))) \times T(3) \times T((T(3) + 6)))$
24338 := $(2 - ((T(4) + T((T(3) \times T(3)))) \times (-T(8)))$
24339 := $(T((2^4) \times T(3)) + ((3^9)))$
24342 := $(T(T(2)) - (-4 \times (T((3 \times 4)^2)))$
24343 := $((2 + T(T((-T(4) + T(T(3)))))) \times (-T(4) + T(T(3))))$
24344 := $((T(2) - T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T((4 \times 4))$
24345 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(4)) \times T(T((3 + 4))) - (T(5)))$
24346 := $(T((T(2) + T(4))) + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) \times T(6)))$
24347 := $(-((T(2) + T(4))) + ((T(3) \times T(4)) \times T(T(7))))$
24348 := $(-T(24) + (T(T((3 \times 4))) \times 8))$
24349 := $((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(3) + T(4))) + T(9)$
24352 := $((2^{T(4)} + ((T(3)^5) \times T(2)))$
24354 := $(-((T(T(2)) + (T(T((4 + 3))) \times (T(5) \times (-4))))$
24355 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(3))) + (5))) - 5)$
24357 := $(-T(2) - ((T(T(4)) + 3) \times (-T(5) \times T(7))))$
24358 := $(-2) - ((T(4) \times T(3)) \times T(T((T(5) - 8))))$
24360 := $(T((-2) + (T(4) \times 3)) \times 60)$
24362 := $(-T(2) - (T(T(4)) \times ((T(T(3)) \times (-T(6))) - 2))$
24363 := $((T(2) + (4^{T(3)})) \times 6) - T(T(T(3)))$
24365 := $((2 \times T(T(4))) - ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(6))) \times (-5))$
24366 := $((T(T(2)) \times (4^{T(3)})) + (T(6))) - T(T(6))$
24368 := $((T((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)))) + (T(-((T(3) - T(6)))))) \times 8)$
24369 := $((2 \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (-6 - T(T(9)))$
24371 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (T(4) \times ((-T(3)) \times T(T(7)) + 1))$
24372 := $((T(2) \times T(4))^3 - T(72))$
24373 := $((T(T(2)) \times (4^{T(3)})) + T(7) - T(T(T(3))))$
24375 := $((-T(2) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(3))) \times (-7) + T(T(5))$
24381 := $((T(2)^4) \times (T((3 \times 8) + 1))$
24382 := $(T(2) - T(4) + ((T(T(3)) + 8)^{T(2)}))$
24383 := $((T(2) + T(T(4)))^3/8) - (T(3))$
24384 := $(T(T(2)) \times (4^{T(3)} - (8 \times 4)))$
24385 := $((T(T(T(2))) - 4)^3 - T(8)) \times 5$
24387 := $(T(2) \times (T(T(T(4))) + ((3^8) + T(7))))$

- 24388** := (((T(2) + T(T(4)))³ - 8)/8)
24390 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(4) × (-3)) + T(90)))
24392 := (T(2) + -(T(4) - 39)^{T(2)})
24394 := -(T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4)) + (T(3) × T((9 × T(4))))))
24396 := (T(T(2)) × (((4^{T(3)}) - 9) - T(6)))
24397 := ((T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) × (T(39) + (7)))
24398 := (-2) + ((T(T(4)) - (3 × T(T(9)))) × (-8))
24399 := (((T(2) × T(T(T(4)))) × T(3)) - (T((9 × 9))))
24400 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) × 400)
24416 := ((T(-(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4)))))) × 41) + (T(6))
24420 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(44))) × 20)
24422 := (2 + (-T(T(4)) × (-T((T(4) × T(2)))) + T(T(T(2))))))
24423 := (T(2) + (T(T(4)) × (T((T(4) × T(2))) - T(T(3))))))
24424 := ((T(T((2 + T(4)))) + (T(T(4))²)) × 4)
24426 := (T(T(2)) × (T(44) + T(T(2 × 6))))
24427 := (-T(2)) + (T(4) × (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(2)) × 7))))
24428 := (2 × ((T(4) × T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) - T(8)))
24429 := -(T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(4) × T(T(4))) - 2) × T(9)))
24432 := ((-24) + (4^{T(3)})) × T(T(2))
24433 := (T(2) + (T(4) × (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(3))))))
24435 := (((T(2) × T(4)) × T(T(4))) - T(T(3))) × T(5))
24436 := (T(T(2)) - (-T(4) × (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(3)) + (T(6))))))
24437 := ((T(T(T(2))) × (T(4) + (T(T(4)) × T(T(3)))) - (T(7)))
24438 := (T(2) × ((T(T(4)) × T((T(4) + T(3)))) + T(T(8))))
24440 := ((T(T(2 × 4)) - T(T(4))) × 40)
24444 := (T(T(T(2))) × (T(((T(4) × T(4)) - (4))/4))
24445 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T((T(4) + (4)))) + T((4 + T(5))))
24447 := ((T((T(2) × T(4))) × T(T(4))) - (T(47)))
24448 := (((24 - T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-8))
24453 := ((T((T(T(T(2))) - 4) - T(4)) × T((T(5) + 3)))
24454 := -(T(T(T(2))) + (-445) × T(T(4))))
24456 := ((T(T(T(2) + T(4))) + (T(4) - T(T(5)))) × 6)
24462 := ((T(2)⁴) × (T((4 × 6)) + 2))
24463 := (-2) - ((-T(4)) - (T(T(4)) × T(6))) × T(T(3))
24464 := ((T(2) + T((4 × 4))) × (T(T(6)) - T(T(4))))
24465 := ((T((T(2) + T(4))) + T(T((4 + 6)))) × T(5))
24466 := ((-2) × T(T(4))) + ((4⁶) × 6)
24468 := (T(T(2)) × (-T(4) - (((4⁶) - 8))))
24469 := -(T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-T(4)) × (T(T(4)) + (T(69))))
24471 := (((-T(T(2 × 4))) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(7)) - 1)
24472 := (((4⁴) × T(T(T(4)))) - (T(7) × T(T(2))))
24475 := ((T(T(T(2))) + 4) × (T(T(T(4))) - T((T(7) + (5))))
24476 := ((T(2) + T(T(4))) × ((T(4) + T(T(7))) + (6)))
24478 := (T(2) - (T(T(4)) × (-T(4)) - T((-7) + T(8))))
24479 := -(T(T(2)) + ((-4) - T(T(4))) × (T(T(7)) + 9))
24480 := (T(T(2)) × ((-4) + T(T(4))) × 80)
24481 := ((2 × ((T(4) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-8))) + 1)
24482 := (2 - ((T(4) - T(T(T(4)))) × (8 × 2)))
24483 := (-T(2)) - ((T(4) - T(48)) × T(T(3)))
24484 := ((-T(2)) - ((T(T(T(4))) × (-4)) + T(8))) × 4)
24485 := (((-T((T(2)⁴))) - T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) × (-5))
24486 := -(T((2 + 4)) × (T(4) - T((8 × 6))))
24487 := ((2 × ((T(4) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-8))) + 7)
24488 := (((-2) × T(4)) + T(T((4 + 8))) × 8)
24489 := (((2 + T(T(4))) - (-4) × T(T(8))) × 9)
24492 := ((-T(2) + T(4)) + T((T(4) × 9))) × T(T(2))
24493 := ((2⁴) × (T(T(T(4))) - 9) - 3)
24494 := -(T(T(2)) + (-T(T(4) + T(4))) × T((T(9) + (4))))
24495 := (((T(2⁴)) × 4) × T(9)) + T(5)
24497 := (((T(2) + (4)) + T(4)) × (T(T(9)) + T(T(7))))
24498 := (T(T(2)) × ((-4) + T((T(4) × 9))) - 8)
24500 := ((T(T(2)) - T(T(4))) × (-500))
24516 := (T(T(2)) × (-T(4) - ((5 - 1)⁶)))
24519 := -(T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)) × (-T((5 - 1) × T(9))))
24522 := ((-2 × 4) + T((T(5) × T(T(2)))) × T(T(2))
24523 := (((T(T(2)) - T(T(T(4)))) × (5 - T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(3))))
24524 := ((T((T(T(2)) × T(4)) × T(5)) - T((T(T(2)) + (T(T(4))))))
24525 := (((-2) + T(T(4))) × T((T(5) × 2))) - T(T(5))
24527 := (-T(2)) + (T(T(4)) × ((T(T(5))/T(2)) + T(T(7))))
24528 := (T(2) × (((4⁵) - 2) × 8))
24531 := (T((-2) + T(T(4))) + (T(5) × T(T(T(3 + 1))))
24532 := (2 - (T(T(4)) × (-5) - (T(T(3))²)))
24533 := (T(2) - (T(T(4)) × (-5) - (T(T(3)) × T(T(3))))
24534 := (T(T(2)) × ((4 + T((T(5) × T(3)))) - T(4))
24536 := (T(T(2)) - (T(T(4)) × (-5) - (T(T(3)) × T(T(6))))
24537 := (-T(2)) - ((4 × T(5)) × (-3) - T(T(7)))
24538 := ((T(T(2)) × (-4) + T((T(5) × T(3)))) - 8)
24540 := (T(T(2)) × (-T(4) - (5 × T(40))))
24544 := ((T(T(2)) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-((5 × 4) - 4))
24545 := (((T(T(2)) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))) - 5)
24547 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T((-4) + T(5)))) + ((T(T(4)) × T(T(7))))
24549 := (T(T(T(2))) × ((T(4) + T(T(5))) + (4)) + T(T(9)))
24550 := ((T((T(T(T(2))) + T(4))) - 5) × 50)
24552 := ((T(2) × (4 + T(T(5)))) × T((5 + T(T(2))))
24555 := ((T((2 + T(T(4)))) × T(5)) - ((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))))
24557 := (((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)))) × (-T(5))) - (T(7))
24558 := (-2) - ((T(T(4)) - (5⁵)) × 8)
24562 := ((-2 × 4) + (T((T(5) × 6)) × T(T(2))))
24563 := (((T(T(2)) - T((T(4) + T(5)))) × T(T(6)))/(-3))
24564 := ((T(2) - ((4⁵) × 6)) × (-4))
24565 := ((T((2 × 45)) × 6) - 5)
24566 := ((T(T(2)) - T(4)) + (T((T(5) × 6)) × 6))

- 24567** := $(-T(2) - ((-T(4) \times T((5 + T(6)))) \times 7))$
24568 := $((-((2^{T(4)})) + T((T(5) \times 6))) \times 8)$
24569 := $(-((T(T((T(2) + T(4)))) - ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(9))))))$
24582 := $(T(2) \times (((4^5) \times 8) + 2))$
24583 := $((T(2) + T(4)) \times T((58 + 3)))$
24584 := $((T((T(2) + T(T(4)))) \times T(5)) - T((T(8) + T(4))))$
24585 := $((T(2) \times T(4)) \times T((5 \times 8))) - T(5)$
24587 := $(2 - (T(T(4)) \times ((-5) - T(8)) - T(T(7))))$
24588 := $((-((2 - 4) + T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times T(8))$
24589 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)))) \times (-T(T(8))))/T(9)))$
24591 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (((T(4) + T(T(5))) \times 9) + 1))$
24592 := $((-T(2) + T(T(T(4)))) \times ((5 + 9) + 2))$
24594 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(((T(4)/5) \times T(9))) + (4)))$
24595 := $((T(2) \times T(4)) \times T((-5) + T(9))) - (5)$
24598 := $((T(T(T(2)))) + (4 \times 5)) \times 98$
24599 := $(-((T(T(T(2)))) + (T(4) - ((T(5) + 9) \times T(T(9))))))$
24609 := $(-((T(T(T(2)))) - ((4 \times 6) \times T(T(09)))))$
24612 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((4^6) + T((1 + 2))))$
24615 := $((T((-2) + T(T(4)))) + (T((T(6) - 1)))) \times T(5)$
24618 := $(T(T(2)) \times (((4^6) - 1) + 8))$
24619 := $(-((T(T(T(2)))) + (-((T(4) + (6))) \times T(T((1 + 9))))))$
24620 := $((T(T(2)) + T((T(T(4)) - (6)))) \times 20)$
24622 := $((T(T(2))^4) \times (T(6) - 2)) - 2$
24624 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((4^6) + (2 \times 4)))$
24625 := $((2^4) \times T(T(T((6 - 2)))) - T(5))$
24628 := $((-2) \times T(4) + (T(T((6 \times 2))) \times 8))$
24631 := $((T(T(2)) \times (4^6)) + T(T((3 + 1))))$
24632 := $((2 \times 4) \times (T(T((6 + T(3)))) - 2))$
24633 := $((T((2 + 46)) - 3) \times T(T(3)))$
24634 := $((T(2) + ((4^6) \times T(3))) + T(T(4)))$
24635 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(3)))) \times 5)$
24636 := $(2 \times ((4 \times T(T((6 + T(3)))) - 6))$
24637 := $(-T(2)) - (-((T(4) + (6))) \times T(T((3 + 7))))$
24638 := $((-T(2) - T(T(4))) + (T(6) \times T((T(3) \times 8))))$
24639 := $((T(2) + (4^6)) \times T(3)) + T(9)$
24640 := $((2^4) \times T(T((6 + 4) + 0)))$
24641 := $((2^4) \times T(T((6 + 4))) + 1)$
24642 := $(T(T((2 \times 4))) \times (T(6) + ((4^2))))$
24643 := $((2^4) \times T(T((6 + 4))) + 3)$
24644 := $((2^4) \times T(T((6 + 4))) + (4))$
24645 := $((-2) + T(T(4))) \times ((T(6) + T(4)) \times T(5))$
24646 := $((2^4) \times T(T((6 + 4))) + (6))$
24647 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(4))) + T((T(6) \times 4))) \times 7$
24648 := $(T(T(2)) \times (((4^6) + 4) + 8))$
24649 := $((2^4) \times T(T((6 + 4))) + 9)$
24650 := $((-T(2) + T((T(4) + T(6)))) \times 50)$
24652 := $(T(T(2)) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(6) - (5)))) - T(T(2)))$
24654 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((4 + T((6 \times T(5)))) + T(4)))$
24655 := $((-2) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))) + T(5)))$
24657 := $(-T(2)) - ((T(4) \times 6) \times (-5) - T(T(7)))$
24658 := $((T(T(2)) \times ((4^6) + T(5))) - 8)$
24661 := $((T(2) + T(4)) \times (6 + T(61)))$
24665 := $((-2) + ((4 + T(T(6))) \times T(6))) \times 5$
24666 := $(T(T(2)) \times (((4^6) + T(6)) - (6)))$
24667 := $((T(T(2)) \times (4^6)) + (T((6 + 7))))$
24668 := $((2 \times T(4)) + (T(T((6 + 6))) \times 8))$
24669 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(4)) - (6)))) - (T(6) + T(T(9))))$
24672 := $(-T(2)) - ((4 + T(T(6))) \times (-T((7 \times 2))))$
24673 := $(-2) - ((-4) - T(T(6))) \times T((-7) + T(T(3))))$
24675 := $((T(T(2)) - T(4)) - T(T(6))) \times (-7 \times T(5))$
24676 := $(-2) \times (T(4) - ((T(6) \times T(7)) \times T(6)))$
24677 := $(2 - ((4 + T(T(6))) \times (-T((7 + 7))))$
24679 := $(-((T(T(T(2))) + (T(4) \times (T(T(6)) - T((T(7) + T(9)))))))$
24682 := $((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T((4 + 6))) \times (-8))) \times 2)$
24683 := $(-((T(2) + T(4))) + (T(6) \times T((8 \times T(3))))$
24684 := $(T(T(2)) \times (((4^6) + 8) + T(4)))$
24685 := $((-2) \times T(T(4))) + (T((T(6) + T(8))) \times T(5))$
24686 := $(-((T(T(2)) - (-4) + (T(6) \times T((8 \times 6))))))$
24688 := $((T((2 + 4)) \times T((6 \times 8))) - 8)$
24690 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(4)) - (6)))) - T(T((9 + 0))))$
24691 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(4)) - (6)))) - (T(T(9)) - 1))$
24692 := $((T(T(2)) - T(4)) + (T(6) \times T((T(9) + T(2))))$
24693 := $(-T(2)) + (T((4 \times (T(6) - 9))) \times T(T(3)))$
24694 := $(-((T(T(2)) + ((T(T(4)) + (T(69))) \times (-T(4))))))$
24695 := $((2 \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((-T(6)) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(5)))$
24696 := $(T((2 + 4)) \times T(((6 \times 9) - 6)))$
24697 := $(-T(2)) - (T(4) \times (T(T(6)) - T((T(9) + T(7))))))$
24698 := $(2 - (-4) \times ((6 \times T(T(9))) - T(8)))$
24699 := $(-((T(T(2)) + ((T(T(4)) + (6)) \times (T(9) \times (-9))))))$
24702 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(4)) - (7)))) + T(T(02)))$
24709 := $(-((T(T(T(2)))) - (T(4) \times (T(70) + 9))))$
24716 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(4)) - (7)))) + (-1) + T(6))$
24717 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(4)) - (7)))) + (T(-((1 - 7))))$
24732 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(4) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(3)))) + 2))$
24733 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7))) - 33$
24734 := $((2 + T((T(T(4)) - (7)))) \times T(T(3))) - 4$
24735 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(4)) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(3)))) + (T(5))$
24736 := $((2^4) \times (T(T((7 + 3))) + (6)))$
24737 := $((T((T(T(T(2))) \times 4)) \times 7) - (T(-((T(3) - T(7))))))$
24738 := $((T(2) + (4)) \times (T((T(7) \times 3)) - T(8)))$
24739 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7))) - (3 \times 9)$
24741 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(4)) - (7)))) + T((T(4) - 1)))$

- 24742** := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(7))) - (4 × T(T(2))))
24743 := (((T(2)⁴) + T(7)) × (-4) + T(T(T(3))))
24744 := -((T(T(2)) + ((-T(4)) + T(7 × T(4)))) × (-T(4)))
24745 := ((T(T(2)) - T(T(4))) × ((-7) × T(T(4))) - T(T(5)))
24746 := ((-2) × T(4)) + (T(T(7)) × (T(T(4)) + (6)))
24748 := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(7))) - (T(4) + 8))
24749 := ((T(2)^{T(4)}) - (T(7) × T(49)))
24772 := (((T(T(2)) × T(4)) × T(T(7))) + T(T(7))) + T(T(2)))
24773 := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(7))) + T(7)) - T(T(3)))
24774 := -((T(T(2)) + ((T(T(4) × 7)) - (7)) × (-T(4))))
24775 := (((T(T(2)) × T(4)) × (T(T(7)) + (7))) - (5))
24781 := ((-T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) + (7 × T(81))
24782 := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(7))) + (8 × 2))
24783 := (T(2) × (-T(T(4))) + ((T(7) + 8) × T(T(T(3))))))
24784 := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(7))) + (8 + T(4)))
24785 := ((T(T(T(2)))) - ((-T(4)) × T(T(7))) - T(T(8)))) × 5
24786 := -((T(T(2)) × (T(T(4)) - T(T((78/6))))))
24787 := ((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(4)) × (-T(7) + T(8)))) × 7)
24788 := ((2 × T((4 × 7))) - (T(T(8)) × (-T(8))))
24789 := (T(2) × (-((T(4) + (7))) - (-8) × T(T(9))))
24791 := ((T(T(T(2)))) × (4 × T(7))) - T((T(9) + 1))
24792 := ((T(T(2)) - ((T(4) - T(7)))) × (T(T(9)) - 2))
24793 := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(7))) + (9 × 3))
24794 := -(((T(T(2)) - T(T(4))) × ((T(T(7)) + T(9)) + T(T(4))))
24795 := (T(-((2 + 4) - (7 × 9))) × T(5))
24796 := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(7))) + (9 + T(6)))
24798 := -((T(T(2)) + (((4 - T(7)) × T(T(9))) + T(8))))
24799 := (T(2) + ((T(T(4)) × (T(T(7)) + T(9))) - 9))
24800 := ((T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) × 800)
24804 := (T((-T(2)) + T(T(4))) × (8 + T(04)))
24813 := (-T(2)) - (T((T(T(4)) - 8)) × (-1) - T(T(3)))
24815 := ((T(T(T(2))) × T(48)) - (1 - T(T(5))))
24816 := (T(T((2 + T(4)))) - (T(T((8 + 1))) × (-T(6))))
24818 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(8)) × (1 + T(8))))
24819 := -((T(T(T(2))) + ((4 - T((8 - 1))) × T(T(9))))
24821 := ((T(T(T(2))) × (T(48) + T(T(2)))) - 1)
24822 := ((T(T(2)) + T(48)) × T((2 × T(2))))
24823 := (((-T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) × (8 × 2)) + T(T(T(3)))
24824 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-T(T(4))) + (8 × T(T((2 + T(4))))))
24825 := ((T((T((2 + 4)) + T(8))) + 2) × T(5))
24827 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) × (T((8 + T(T(2)))) - (T(7))))
24828 := (T(T(2)) × (T((T(T(4)) + T(8))) - (T(T(2)) × 8)))
24829 := (T(T(T(2))) - (-4) × (-8) + (T(T(2)) × T(T(9))))
24832 := (((2 × T(T(4))) + T(T(8))) × 32)
24834 := (T(T(2)) × (-((T(T(4)) - 8)) + T(T((3 + T(4))))))
24837 := (T(T(T(2))) - (T((T(T(4)) - 8)) × (T(3) - T(7))))
24839 := ((T(2) - 4) + ((8 × 3) × T(T(9))))
24852 := ((T((2 × T(4))) + 8) × (T(T(5)) - T(T(2))))
24853 := (T(2) - (-T(4)) × T((-8) + T((T(5) - 3))))
24854 := ((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(4)))) × (-((T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(4))))
24855 := (((-T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) - (-8) × T(5)) × T(5)
24856 := (T(T(2)) - (-T(4)) × T(((8 + 5) - T(6))))
24857 := -((T(T(2)) + (T((T(4) + T(8))) × (5 - T(7))))
24864 := ((2 + T(4)) × (-8) + T(64))
24867 := (-T(2)) × (T(T(4)) - ((T(8) × T(T(6))) + T(7)))
24868 := (T((2⁴)) + ((T(T(8)) + (T(6))) × T(8)))
24869 := (-T(2)) - (-4) × (8 + (6 × T(T(9))))
24871 := (((2 × T(T(T(4)))) × 8) + (T(T((7 - 1))))
24872 := (((T(T(2 + T(4)))) × 8) - 7) + T(T(T(T(2))))
24874 := (((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-4)) + T(8)) × (-T(7))) + T(4)
24875 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (4 - (8 × T(T((7 + 5))))))
24876 := (T(T(2)) × ((-4) - T(8)) + T(T((7 + 6))))
24878 := (T(T(2)) - ((T(T((4 + 8))) + T(7)) × (-8)))
24879 := ((T(T((2 + T(4)))) × 8) + T(T(T(T(-((7 - 9))))))
24880 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(4) × 8)) × 80)
24882 := ((T((T(2) + 4)) - T(T(8))) × (-T(8) + T(2)))
24883 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (4 + (8 × T(T((8/3))))))
24884 := (((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)))) - 8) × 8) + T(T(T(4)))
24885 := ((T(2) + ((T(4) + T(8)) × T(8))) × T(5))
24888 := (((T(T(2)) - T(T((4 + 8)))) - T(8)) × (-8))
24892 := ((-T(2)) + T(T(4))) + ((-8) × T(T(9))) × (-T(2))
24893 := ((-2) + T(T(4))) + ((-8) × T(T(9))) × (-3))
24894 := ((T(2)^{T(4)}) - ((T(T(8)) - T(9)) × T(T(4))))
24895 := (T(-((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(4)))))) + (((T(8) × T(9)) × T(5))))
24899 := -(((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)))) - (T((T(T(8))/9)) × 9))
24912 := (T(T(2)) × ((4 × T(T(9))) + 12))
24915 := ((T(2) + (T(4) × T(9))) × T(T(-((1 - 5))))
24920 := ((T(T(T(2))) + T(49)) × 20)
24922 := (-2) + (4 × ((T(T(9)) × T(T(2))) + T(T(T(2))))))
24923 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-4) + (T((T(9) + T(2))) × T(T(3))))
24924 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(T(4)) + T((T(9) × 2))) + (4)))
24925 := ((T(-((T(T(2)) - T(T(4)))) - (T(T(9)) × T(T(2)))) × (-5))
24926 := ((T(T(2)) × T(T((4 + 9)))) - T((-2) + T(6)))
24927 := (T(2) × ((T((4 + 9))²) + T(7))
24928 := ((T(T(T(2))) + (-T(4)) + (T(T(9)) × T(2))) × 8)
24929 := (((T(T(T(2))) + 4) × T(T(9))) - (T((-2) + T(9))))
24932 := -(((T(T(2)) - T(T(4))) - T(T(9))) × (T(T(3)) + 2))
24933 := ((24 × (T(T(9)) + 3)) + T(T(3)))
24934 := (T((T(2) + T(4))) × ((T(9) × T(3)) + (4)))
24935 := ((2 × T(T(T(4)))) - (T(93) × (-5)))
24936 := (((T(T(2)) - T(4)) - T(T(9))) × (-3 - T(6)))
24938 := (2 - ((4 + T(T(9))) × (-3 × 8)))
24939 := ((T(T((2 × 4))) × (T(9) - T(3))) - T(T(9)))
24942 := (T(T(2)) - ((4 + T(T(9))) × (-4)) × T(T(2)))

- 24944** := $((T(T(2))^{-4+9}) - T(T(T(4)))) \times 4$
24945 := $((T((2 + T(4)) + T(9))) + T(4)) \times T(5)$
24948 := $(T(T((2 + 4))) \times (9 \times (4 + 8)))$
24949 := $((T(T((T(2) + (4)))) \times (9 + T(T(4)))) - T(T(9)))$
24950 := $((-T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(9))) \times 50$
24954 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((4 \times T(T(9))) + (T(5) + (4))))$
24955 := $((24 \times T(T(9))) - (5)) + T(T(5))$
24957 := $(-T(2)) - (T((T(4) + 9)) \times (-5 + 7))$
24958 := $(-2) - (-T(4) \times (T((T(9) + T(5))) + T(T(8))))$
24971 := $(2 + (T((-4) + T(9))) \times (T(7) + 1))$
24972 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((4 \times T(T(9))) + T(7)) - T(T(2)))$
24973 := $((T(T(2)) \times T((T(4) \times 9))) + T(T(7))) - 3$
24974 := $((T(2) - 4) - (-9 \times T(74)))$
24975 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(9)) \times (-7)) - T(T(5))))$
24976 := $((T(T(2)) \times T((T(4) \times 9))) + T((7 + T(6))))$
24978 := $(T(2) \times (-T(4) + ((T(T(9)) + 7) \times 8)))$
24979 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (4 + T(T(9)))) + (T(79)))$
24982 := $(-2) \times ((T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) - (T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(2)))))$
24983 := $((2 \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(9)) + 8) \times T(T(3))))$
24984 := $((24 \times T(T(9))) + (T(8) \times 4))$
24985 := $((2 \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(9)) \times 8 - T(5)$
24987 := $(T(2) - (-((4 \times 9) \times (T(T(8)) + T(7))))$
24993 := $(T(2) \times (((4 \times T(9)) \times T(9)) + T(T(T(3))))$
24994 := $(-T(T(2)) - ((T(4)^{T(9)/9})/4))$
24995 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(4))) - (T(99))) \times (-5)$
24996 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T((4 + 9)))) - (T((9 + 6))))$
24997 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(9) \times T(9))) \times 7$
25029 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(50) \times (-2))) \times 9$
25031 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) + (50 \times T(31)))$
25074 := $(-T(T(2)) + ((-50) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(4))))$
25086 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-5) + T(T((0 - 8) + T(6))))$
25110 := $(T((2 \times T(5))) \times (-1) + T(10))$
25113 := $(-T(2)) + ((5 + 1) \times T(T(13)))$
25116 := $(T(T(2)) \times T(T(((5 + 1) + 1) + 6)))$
25121 := $((T(T((-2) + T(5))) + 1) \times T(T(2))) - 1$
25122 := $((T(T((-2) + T(5))) + 1) \times (2 \times T(2)))$
25124 := $(-T(T(T(2)))) - ((-T(T(5))) \times T((-1) + T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4))))$
25125 := $((T(T((-2) + T(5))) - 1) \times T(T(2))) + T(5)$
25128 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(5))) - 1) - T(T(T(2))) \times T(8)$
25132 := $(T(T(T(2))) + (-5) + (T(T(13)) \times T(T(2))))$
25133 := $((2 + T(5)) + (T(T(13)) \times T(3)))$
25137 := $((T((T(2) + T(5))) \times T(T((1 \times 3)))) \times 7$
25138 := $((T(T(2)) \times (5 + T(T(13)))) - 8$
25143 := $((2 + T(5)) \times (T((-1) + T(T(4)))) - T(3))$
25146 := $((T(T((-2) + T(5)))) + (1 + 4)) \times 6$
25152 := $((T(T((-2) + T(5)))) + (1 + 5)) \times T(T(2))$
25155 := $((-T(2)) + (T(T(5)) \times (-1) + T(5))) \times T(5)$
25158 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(51) - T(T(5))) - 8))$
25164 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) - T((16 + T(T(4))))$
25168 := $((T(T(T(2))) + ((5^{-1+6}))) \times 8$
25172 := $((T(T(2) + T(T(5))) + 1) \times T(T(7)))/2$
25176 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T((5 - 1)) + T(T((7 + 6))))$
25179 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T((T(5) + 1)) + T(7)) + T(T(9))))$
25182 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(5)) \times (-1) + T(8))) - T(2))$
25185 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(5))) \times (-1) + T(8)) - (T(5))$
25188 := $(-T((T(2) \times 5)) - (T((1 + T(8))) \times T(8)))$
25194 := $(-T(T(2)) - (T(T(5)) \times T(((1 + 9) + T(4))))$
25195 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(5)) \times (1 + 9))) - 5$
25197 := $(T(2) + (T(51) \times (-9) + T(7)))$
25212 := $(T(T(2)) - ((-T(T(5))) \times T((T(T(2))) - 1))) - T(T(2))$
25215 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(5)) \times T((T(2) + 1)))) + T(5)$
25218 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-T(5) + (T(T(2)) \times T((1 + T(8))))$
25221 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(T(5)) \times T((2 + 2))) + 1)$
25223 := $(2 - ((-T(T(5))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(T(2)))))) - (T(T(3))))$
25224 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(5) + T(2)) + T(T((T(2) + T(4))))$
25225 := $(25 + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))))$
25227 := $(T(2) \times (-T(T(5)) - T(2)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(7))))$
25228 := $(T((2 + 5)) \times (-2) + T((T(T(2)) + T(8))))$
25230 := $((T(T(T(2))) + T((T(T(5))/T(2)))) \times 30$
25234 := $((-T(T(2))) + T((T(T(5))/T(2)))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(4))$
25235 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) - T((2 \times 35)))$
25236 := $((T(T(2)) \times T((T(5) \times T(T(2)))) + T(36))$
25237 := $(2 + (((-T(T(5))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(7))))$
25238 := $(2 - ((T((T(5) \times T(T(2)))) \times (-T(3))) - (T(T(8))))$
25239 := $(-T(T(2)) + ((-T(5) + 2) \times T((T(3) \times 9))))$
25242 := $((T(2) \times T((T(5) + 2))) \times T(T(4))) - T(2)$
25243 := $(-2) - ((T((T(5) + 2)) \times T(T(4))) \times (-3))$
25245 := $((T(2) \times T(5)) \times T((T(2) \times (-4) + T(5))))$
25246 := $((-2) + T(5)) \times (T((T(2) + T(T(4)))) + T(T(6)))$
25247 := $(2 + (T(5) \times (T((T(2) + T(T(4)))) - (T(7))))$
25248 := $((T(2^5)) - 2) \times 48$
25249 := $(-T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((5 + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4)) - T(T(9))))$
25252 := $(T((T(T(T(2))) - 5)) - (-T(T(2))) \times T(T((T(5) - 2))))$
25254 := $((-2) - T(T(5))) \times (T(2) - T((5 \times 4)))$
25257 := $(-T(2)) - ((T(T(5))/2) \times (-T(5)) - T(T(7)))$
25263 := $((T((2 + 5)) \times T((2 \times T(6)))) - T(T(3)))$
25267 := $((-2) - T(5)) + (T((2 \times T(6))) \times T(7))$
25269 := $(-T(T(T(2))) + ((5 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(6)))) - T(T(9)))$
25272 := $((-T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times (T(2) \times 72)$
25273 := $(T(((T(2)^5)/T(2))) + ((T(7)^3)))$
25274 := $((T(((T(2) \times T(5)) - T(2))) \times T(7)) - T(4))$
25275 := $((T(-T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(5)))) + T((2 \times 7))) \times 5$
25277 := $((T(((T(2) \times T(5)) - T(2))) \times T(7)) - 7)$
25278 := $(-2) - (T((-5) + (T(2) \times T(7))) \times (-8))$

- 25281** := $(T(2) \times (-T(T(5))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(8) + 1)))$
25282 := $((T((2+5)) \times T((T(T(2)) + T(8)))) - 2)$
25284 := $(T((2+5)) \times T((2+T(8)) + (4)))$
25286 := $(2^{T(5)} + (-2) \times T(86))$
25287 := $(T(2) - (T((T(5-2)) + T(8))) \times (-T(7)))$
25288 := $(2 \times (((-T(T(5))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(8))) + 8))$
25308 := $(T(((2+5) + 30)) \times T(8))$
25311 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (T((T(T(3)) - 1)) - 1)))$
25320 := $((-T((T(2) \times T(5)))) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-20)$
25322 := $(2 - (-T(T(5))) \times (T((T(3) - 2)) + T(T(T(2))))))$
25323 := $(T(2) - (-T(T(5))) \times (T(T(3)) + T((-2) + T(T(3))))))$
25326 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-((T(5) - (T(3)^{T(2)})) \times T(6))))$
25327 := $((-T(2)) + T((T(T(5))/3))) \times (T(2) + T(7)))$
25328 := $((T((2^5)) \times T(3)) - 2) \times 8$
25329 := $((T((2+5)) \times T((T(T(3)) \times 2))) + T(9))$
25332 := $((T(T((-2) + T(5))) \times T(3)) + ((T(3)^{T(2)}))$
25335 := $((T(25) \times T((T(3) + T(3)))) - T(5))$
25341 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(5)) \times ((T(T(3)) \times (-T(4)) - 1)))$
25342 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-5) + (T(3) \times T(T((T(4) + T(2))))))$
25343 := $((T(T((-2) + T(5))) \times T(3)) - 4) + T(T(T(3)))$
25344 := $(T((2^5)) \times ((3 \times 4) \times 4))$
25345 := $((T(25) \times T((3 \times 4))) - 5)$
25346 := $(2 + ((T((5 \times T(3))) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(6))))$
25347 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T((5 \times 3)) \times T(4)) + (7)))$
25348 := $(2 \times (5 - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + T(8))))$
25362 := $((T(T(T(2)) \times T((5+3))) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)))$
25364 := $((2 - T(T(5))) \times (3 - T(T(6)))) - T(T(T(4)))$
25365 := $((-T(25)) + T((3 \times T(6)))) \times T(5)$
25368 := $(T((2+5)) \times (3 + T((6+T(8))))$
25372 := $((-T(2)) - ((-5^3) \times T(T(7)))/2)$
25373 := $((-2) - (5^3) \times (T(7) - T(T(T(3))))))$
25374 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) - T(-((T(3) - 74)))$
25375 := $((T(T(2)^5) \times T(T(3))) - T(7)) \times 5$
25383 := $((T(T((-2) + T(5))) \times T(3)) + T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))$
25386 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(5) \times 3) + T(T((-8) + T(6))))))$
25389 := $((T((2^5)) \times T(3)) \times 8) + T(9)$
25392 := $(T(((2+T(5)) + T(3))) \times 92)$
25395 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) - (T((T(T(3)) + 9)) \times 5))$
25398 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(5) + (T(3) \times T((T(9) - 8))))))$
25405 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4))) - 05)$
25410 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(T(5)) \times T(4)) + 10))$
25411 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4))) + (1 \times 1))$
25412 := $((T((T(T(2)) + T(5))) \times T(T(4))) + 1) \times 2$
25413 := $(T(2) - (-((T(T(5)) - T(4))) \times T(T(T(1 \times 3))))))$
25414 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4))) + (1 \times 4))$
25415 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4))) + (1 \times 5))$
25416 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T(T(5)) - T(4)) \times T(T((1 \times 6))))))$
25417 := $((T((T(T(2)) + (5))) \times T(T(4))) + 1) \times 7$
25418 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4))) + (1 \times 8))$
25419 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4))) + (1 \times 9))$
25420 := $(2 \times (5 - (-T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(T(2+0))))))$
25421 := $((T(T(2)) + (5)) \times ((T(4) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1))$
25422 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)) + (4^{T(T(2))}))) \times T(T(2)))$
25423 := $((-2) + T(5)) + ((T(T(4)) \times 2) \times T(T(T(3))))$
25424 := $((T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times (T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(2)) - T(T(4))))))$
25425 := $((T((2+T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))) + 2) \times T(5)$
25426 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (5 - ((T(T(4)) \times 2) \times T(T(6))))$
25427 := $(T(2) + ((5 + T(42)) \times T(7)))$
25428 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(5)^4)))/(-T(T(2)) - 8))$
25429 := $(2 \times (5 - (-T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) + 9$
25431 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(5)) \times T(4))) + T(T(T(3 \times 1))))$
25432 := $((T(T(2)) + (5)) \times ((T(4) \times T(T(3)))) + 2)$
25433 := $((2 - ((T(T(5)) \times (-T(4))) \times T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(3))))$
25434 := $((-((T(T(2))^5) - ((T(4) \times T(3^4))))))$
25435 := $(2 \times (5 - (-T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(5))$
25436 := $(2 - ((-T(5)) \times T((T(T(4)) + 3))) + T(T(6)))$
25438 := $((-2) - (T(T(5)) \times (4 - (T(3) \times T(8))))$
25439 := $((-T((T(T(T(2))) - 5)) - (T(T(4)) \times T((T(T(3)) + 9))))$
25442 := $(2 - ((T(T(5)) \times (-4)) \times (T(T(4)) - 2)))$
25443 := $(T(2) \times (((T(5) \times T(4)) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3))))$
25444 := $((-T(T(T(2))) + ((T(5) \times (-T(T(4))) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(4))))))$
25445 := $((T((2 \times T(5))) \times T(T(4))) - T(4) - T(T(5)))$
25446 := $(T((T(2) + (5))) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(6))))$
25448 := $((T(T(-((T(2) - T(5)))) + (T(4) \times T(4))) \times 8)$
25449 := $((T(T(T(2))) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(4)))) \times 4) - T(T(9)))$
25452 := $((T((2 \times T(5))) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(5))) - T(2)$
25453 := $((-2) - T(T(5))) + (T(T(4)) \times T((5 \times T(3))))$
25454 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) + (-T(T(4))) - T(T((T(5) - (4))))))$
25455 := $((T(T((2+5))) \times T(T(4))) + (5^5))$
25458 := $(T(2) \times ((5 \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(8))))$
25462 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (5 + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(6)))) \times 2)$
25464 := $((-T(2)) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(6)))) \times 4$
25465 := $((T(T(2)) + (5)) \times ((T(4) \times T(T(6))) + (5)))$
25466 := $((2 + T(5)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(6) + T(6))))$
25469 := $((-T(T((2+5))) + ((-4) - T(6)) \times T(T(9))))$
25472 := $((T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times (-4 + T((T(7) \times 2))))$
25473 := $((((-2) - T(T(5))) \times (-T(4))) - (7)) \times T(T(3))$
25475 := $((T((-2) + T(5))) \times (T(4) \times T(7))) - (5)$
25476 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(5) \times 4) + T(T((7+6))))$
25477 := $((-T(2)) - ((T(T(5)) + T(4)) \times (-7 \times T(7))))$
25479 := $(T((T(2) + T(5))) \times (-4) + T(-((T(7) - T(9))))))$
25480 := $((-T(2) + (5)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(80)))$
25482 := $((T((T(T(2)) + T(5))) \times T(T(4))) + T(8)) \times 2$

- 25484** := (((T((2 × T(5))) × T(T(4))) - T(8)) - T(T(4)))
25485 := (((-2) + T(T((5 + 4)))) + T(T(8))) × T(5)
25487 := -((T((-2) + T(5))) - ((T(T(4)) + 8) × T(T(7))))
25488 := (((T(T(2)) × T(T(5))) - (4 + 8)) × T(8))
25494 := (T(T(T(2))) × (-((T(5) - T(49)) - (4))))
25495 := (((T(T(T(2))) + 5) × (-T(T(4) - T(T(9)))) + T(5))
25502 := (2 + ((T(T(5)) × T(50))/T(T(2))))
25503 := (T(2) + ((T(T(5)) × (-T(50)))/(-T(3))))
25506 := (T(T(2)) + ((T(T(5)) × (-T(50)))/(-6)))
25512 := (((T(2)⁵) × T((T(5) - 1))) - T(2))
25514 := -((T(T(2)) - ((T((T(5) + T(5))) - 1) × T(T(4))))
25515 := (((T(2)⁵) × 5) × T((1 + 5)))
25522 := (T(T((2 + 5))) - (T(T((T(5) - 2))) × (-T(T(2))))
25523 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(5))) - ((T(5) - 2)³))
25524 := ((T(2) + T(5)) × (-((T(T(5)) + 2) + T(T(T(4))))
25525 := (T(25) + (T((T(T(5))/T(T(2)))) × T(T(5))))
25533 := (-((T(T(2)) - T(T(5))) × (-5) + T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(3))))
25536 := (((T(2)⁵) × 5) × T(T(3))) + T(6))
25537 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(5))) - (T(T((5 + T(3)))) - (T(7))))
25538 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5) × (5 - (-3) × T(8)))
25542 := (-T(2) - T(T(5))) + (T(5) × T((T(T(4)) + T(2))))
25543 := ((-2) - T(T(5))) + (T(5) × T((T(T(4)) + 3)))
25544 := -((T(T(T(2))) - ((T((T(5) + T(5))) × T(T(4))) - T(4))))
25545 := ((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(5))) + ((5 - T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(5))))
25546 := ((T((-2) + T(5))) + (T(5))) × (T(4) + T(T(6))))
25547 := ((T((25 + 5)) × T(T(4))) - T(7))
25548 := (2 × (T(T(5)) + ((T(5) + 4) × T(T(8))))
25551 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(5)) × (T((5 + T(5))) + 1)))
25554 := -(((T(T(2)) + T(5)) - (T((T(5) + T(5))) × T(T(4))))
25555 := (((T(2) + T((5 + T(5)))) × T(T(5))) - (5))
25559 := -((T((-2) + T(5))) + (T((5 × T(5))) × (-9)))
25562 := (2 - (T(T(5)) × ((T(5) - T(T(6))) + T(2))))
25563 := (T(2) - (T(T(5)) × ((T(5) - T(T(6))) + 3)))
25564 := -(((T(T(2)) + 5) - (T((5 × 6)) × T(T(4))))
25568 := (T((T(T(T(2))) - 5)) × (T(T(5)) + (68)))
25569 := (((-T(2)) + T((5 × T(5)))) - (6)) × 9)
25572 := (-T(2)) - (-55) × T((T(7) + 2)))
25573 := (-2) - (T((T(5) + T(5))) × (-T((7 + 3))))
25574 := ((T(T(T(2))) × ((T(5)/5) × T(T(7)))) - 4)
25575 := (T((2 × 5)) × T(((5 × 7) - 5)))
25576 := (-2) - (((T(5)/(-5)) × T(T(7))) × T(6))
25577 := (2 - (-T((T(5) + T(5)))) × T(T((T(7)/7))))
25578 := (T(T((2 + 5))) × (-T(5) - 78))
25584 := ((T(2) + T((5 × 5))) × T((8 + 4)))
25585 := -(((T(2) - (5 + 5)) × T(85)))
25593 := (((T(T(2)) - T((5 × T(5)))) × (-9)) - 3)
25594 := -((T(T(2)) + (-5) × ((5 × T(T(9))) - T(T(4))))
25596 := (-((T(2) × T(5))) + ((T(T(5)) - 9) × T(T(6))))
25598 := (2 - (T((T(T(5))/T(5))) × (-T(9)) - T(T(8))))
25599 := -((T(T(2)) + ((T((5 × T(5))) × (-9)) + T(9)))
25605 := (((T(2) + T(T(5))) - T(60)) × (-T(5)))
25613 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(5)) - T(T(6)))) - T((1 + T(3))))
25615 := ((2 + T(T(5))) × T((T(6) - 1))) - (5))
25617 := -((T(2) + ((T(5) × (-61)) × T(7)))
25631 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(5)) - T(T(6)))) - T((3 + 1)))
25632 := ((T((2 - (T(5) × (-6)))) - (T(3))) × T(T(2)))
25633 := (-2) - (((T(T(5)) - T(T(6))) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(3))
25634 := (T(2) - ((T(T(5)) - T(T(6))) × T(T(T(3)))) + T(4))
25635 := ((-2) + T(-((5 - 63))) × T(5))
25637 := (T(2) + ((-((T(T(5)) - T(T(6)))) × T(T(T(3)))) - 7))
25638 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(5)) - T(T(6)))) - T(-((T(3) - 8)))
25639 := (-2) - ((T(T(5)) - T(T(6))) × T(T(-((3 - 9))))
25640 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(5))) - T((64 + 0)))
25641 := (T(T(T(2))) × ((5 × T(T(6))) + T((4 + 1))))
25642 := (2 + ((T(T(5)) × T(T(6))) - T((4^{T(2)}))))
25643 := (T(2) + ((T(T(5)) × T(T(6))) - T((4³))))
25644 := (T(2) - ((T(T(5)) - T(T(6))) × T(T((-4) + T(4))))
25645 := ((2 × (T(T(5)) + (T(T(6)) × T(T(4)))) - (5))
25646 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(5))) - (T(64) - (6)))
25647 := -(((T(T(2)) - (T(5) × T(6))) × (T(T(4)) + T(7)))
25648 := (T((2 + 5)) × ((T(T(6)) × 4) - 8))
25649 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(5))) - (T(64) - 9))
25651 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(5)) - T(T(6)))) + T((5 - 1)))
25652 := (2 - ((T(T(5)) - 6) × (-T(5)²)))
25653 := (-((T(2) - T(5))) - (-((T(T(6)) - T(T(5))) × T(T(T(3))))
25656 := ((T(2) × 5) + ((T(T(6)) - T(T(5))) × T(T(6))))
25657 := (-((T(T(2)) + 5)) - (-6) × T((T(T(5)) - T(7))))
25658 := (((2^{T(5)}) - (6⁵) + T(T(8)))
25659 := ((T(2) + T(5)) + (T(T(6)) × (T(T(5)) - 9)))
25661 := (T(T(T(2))) - (((T(T(5)) - T(T(6))) × T(T(6))) + 1))
25662 := ((-2) + T(5)) × (T(6) + T(62))
25664 := ((T((2 - (T(5) × (-6)))) × 6) - (4))
25665 := (T(-((2 - (5 × (6 + 6)))) × T(5))
25667 := (-2) - (((T(T(5)) - T(T(6))) × T(T(6))) - T(7))
25668 := (T(2) + (T(5) × T((66 - 8))))
25672 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(5)) - T(T(6)))) + (T(7) + T(2)))
25673 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(5))) + (-T(67) + T(T(T(3))))
25674 := -((T(T(2)) - (T(T(5)) × (T(T(6)) - (7 + T(4))))
25675 := (-((2^{T(5)})) + (T(T(6)) × T((7 + T(5))))
25677 := (T(2) × (5 + ((T(6) × T(T(7))) + T(7))))
25678 := ((T(T(T(2))) + (-5) + T(6)) × (T(7) + T(T(8))))
25679 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(5)) - T(T(6)))) + (-7) + T(9))
25680 := ((T(T(2)) + (T(5) × T(6))) × 80)
25682 := (2 - (T(T(5)) × ((-6) × T(8) + 2)))

- 25683** := $((T((2 + T(5))) \times (T(6) \times 8)) - T(T(3)))$
25686 := $((T(2) + T((56 + T(8)))) \times 6)$
25689 := $-((T(T(T(2)))) + ((5 - T(6)) \times T(8)) \times T(9)))$
25692 := $(-T(2) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))) - ((T(9)^2))))$
25694 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T((-5) + T(6)) \times 9)) - T(4))$
25695 := $((T((2 \times 5)) \times T((T(6) + 9))) + T(T(5)))$
25697 := $((25 \times (-6) + T(T(9)))) - T(7)$
25698 := $(T(T(2)) \times (5 + T(-(6 - 98))))$
25704 := $((2 + T(5)) \times (-T(7) + T(T(T(04)))))$
25719 := $((T(T(2)) \times (T((T(T(5)) - T(7)) + 1)) + T(9))$
25722 := $((T(T(2 + T(5))) \times T(7)) + T(2)) \times T(T(2))$
25723 := $(-2) - (-((5 \times 7^2) \times T(T(3))))$
25724 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + 5) \times (T((7 \times 2) + (4))))$
25725 := $(T(2) \times (((5 \times 7)^{T(2)})/5))$
25726 := $(T(T(2)) + (-5) + (T(7^2) \times T(6)))$
25727 := $(2 + (T(T(T(-(5 - 7)))) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + (T(7))))))$
25728 := $(2^5) \times ((T(T(7)) \times 2) - 8)$
25732 := $(2 + 5) + (T((T(7) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
25733 := $((T(2) + 5) - (T((T(7) + T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(3))))$
25734 := $-((T(T(2)) + (-((T((5 + 7)) \times T(3))) \times T(T(4))))$
25735 := $((-2) - (T(5) \times (7^3))) \times (-5)$
25736 := $((T(T(2)) + 5) - (T((T(7) + T(T(3)))) \times (-T(6))))$
25738 := $(-2) - ((-5 - T(7)) \times T((3 + T(8))))$
25739 := $-((T((T(T(T(2))) - 5)) - ((T(7) - 3) \times T(T(9))))$
25752 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(5)) - T(T(7))) \times (-T(5)) + 2))$
25753 := $(T((-2) + T(5)) \times ((T(T(7)) - T(T(5))) - 3))$
25754 := $((T(T(2)) \times (T(5) + T((-T(7) + T(T(5)))))) - 4)$
25755 := $((T(T(2)) + T(((T(5) + T(7)) + T(5)))) \times T(5)$
25756 := $(-2) - ((T(5) + T((-T(7) + T(T(5)))) \times (-6))$
25758 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(5) + T(-(T(7) + (T(5) \times (-8))))))$
25759 := $-((T(T(-(T(2) - T(5)))) + (T(7) \times (5 - T(T(9))))$
25762 := $(-2) + ((T(T(5)) - 7) \times (T(T(6)) - T(2)))$
25764 := $((-T(2)) \times (T(T(5)) - 7)) \times (-T(6) - T(T(4)))$
25765 := $((T(-(T(T(T(2))) - T(T(5)))) - (T(7) - T(T(6)))) \times 5)$
25767 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (-((5 - 7) + T((T(6) + T(7))))$
25772 := $(-2) - ((T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times (-7^2))$
25773 := $((T(T(2)) \times T((T(T(5)) - T(7))) + T((-7) + T(T(3))))$
25774 := $((-T(2) - T(T(5))) \times (-T(7)) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(4))))$
25776 := $(2 - ((T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times (-T(7) + T(6))))$
25777 := $(T(2) - ((T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times (-7 \times 7)))$
25779 := $-((T(T(T(2))) + (-T(5) \times (T((T(T(7))/7) + 9))))$
25781 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(-(T(5) - T(7)))) + (T(T(8)) - 1))$
25782 := $(2 \times (T(5) - (-((T(T(7)) \times T(T(8)))/T(T(T(2))))))$
25784 := $((T(T(2)) \times T((T(5) + 7))) \times T(8)) - T(T(T(4)))$
25785 := $((T(T(2) + T(T(5))) + T((7 \times 8))) \times T(5)$
25788 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) + T(8)) + T(T(8)))$
25794 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(5)) - 7) + T(T((9 + 4))))$
25795 := $((T(25) \times 79) + T(T(5)))$
25797 := $(2 - (-5) \times (T(T(7)) + T(97)))$
25798 := $(-2) - (T(T(5)) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(9)) - T(T(8))))$
25815 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(5))) \times T(8) - T((-1) + T(5)))$
25821 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(5)) \times ((-T(8)) \times T(T(2)) + 1)))$
25823 := $((2 + T(5)) \times (T(T((8 + 2))) - T(T(3))))$
25824 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(5)) \times T(8)) - 2^4))$
25825 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(5) \times 82)) - 5)$
25827 := $(-T(2) - (T((5 + T(8))) \times (-2) - T(7)))$
25828 := $(-2) - (T((5 + T(8))) \times (T(T(2)) - T(8)))$
25829 := $-((T(T(-(2) + T(5))) + ((8 + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(9))))$
25840 := $(T((T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times T((-T(8) + T(T((4 + 0))))))$
25841 := $((T((T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times T((-T(8) + T(T(4)))) + 1)$
25842 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(5))) \times T(8) - T((T(4) + 2)))$
25843 := $((T((T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times T((-T(8) + T(T(4)))) + 3)$
25844 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8)) - (T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4))))$
25845 := $((2 + T(58)) + T(4)) \times T(5)$
25846 := $((T((T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times T((-T(8) + T(T(4)))) + 6)$
25847 := $((25 \times T(T(T(8)/4))) - T(7))$
25848 := $((-2) + ((5 \times T(8)) \times 4)) \times T(8)$
25849 := $((T((T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times T((-T(8) + T(T(4)))) + 9)$
25850 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (T((-5) + T(8)))) \times 50)$
25851 := $-((T(T(T(2))) - ((T(T(5)) - 8) \times T(T((5 + 1))))))$
25852 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8)) - (T(T(5))/T(T(2))))$
25854 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(5))) \times T(8) - T((T(5) - 4)))$
25855 := $((T(T(2)) \times T((5 + T(8)))) + (5) \times 5)$
25856 := $-((T(T(T(2))) + (-5) + ((8 - T(T(5))) \times T(T(6))))$
25860 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(5))) \times T(8) - 60)$
25862 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8)) - T((6 - 2)))$
25863 := $(-T(2) + ((T(T(5)) - 8) \times T(T(6))) - T(3))$
25864 := $((-2) - T(T(5))) \times ((T(8) \times (-6)) + 4))$
25865 := $(-2) + (((T(T(5)) - 8) \times T(T(6))) - 5))$
25866 := $((T(T(T(2)) \times 5) - 8) \times T(T(6)) - 6)$
25867 := $(2 + (((T(T(5)) - 8) \times T(T(6))) - 7))$
25868 := $((2 \times 58) \times (T(T(6)) - 8))$
25869 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(5))) \times T(8) - (6 + T(9)))$
25871 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - (T(8) - T(7)))) - 1)$
25872 := $((25 + 8) \times (T(7)^2))$
25873 := $((T(T(-(T(2) - T(5)))) \times 8) + T((T(7) + T(T(3))))$
25874 := $((T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(5)) \times T(8)) - 7)) - 4)$
25875 := $(T((T(2) \times T(5))) \times ((-8) + T(7)) + 5))$
25876 := $(-2) - ((T(T(5)) \times (-T(8))) + 7) \times 6)$
25892 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(5))) \times T(8) - T((9 - 2)))$
25893 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(5))) \times T(8) - (9 \times 3))$
25894 := $((T((T(T(2)) + 5)) \times (-T(T(8)) - T(T(9)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
25896 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T((5 + 8)))) + T((T(9) - 6)))$

$$\begin{aligned} 25905 &:= ((T(T(2)) + (5 \times T(T(9)))) \times 05) \\ 25914 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (-5) + (T((T(9) + 1)) \times 4)) \\ 25915 &:= (((T(T(2)) \times T(T(5))) \times T((9 - 1))) - 5) \\ 25918 &:= (-2) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(9) + T(18))) \\ 25919 &:= (25 \times T(T(9))) + (-1) + T(9)) \\ 25920 &:= ((T(T(2))^{-5+9}) \times 20) \\ 25921 &:= (T(T((-2) + T(5)))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-21)) \\ 25922 &:= (2 + (T(5) \times ((9 + T(2))^{T(2)}))) \\ 25923 &:= (T(2) + (T(5) \times ((9 + T(2))^3))) \\ 25924 &:= (((25 \times T(T(9))) - T(T(2))) + T(T(4))) \\ 25925 &:= (2 + T((5 \times 9))) \times 25) \\ 25926 &:= (T(T(2)) - (T(T(5)) \times (-9) \times (T(2) + T(6)))) \\ 25927 &:= (((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(5)) \times T((T(9)/T(2)))) + 7) \\ 25928 &:= ((T(T((-2) + T(5)))) + (-T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times 8) \\ 25929 &:= (25 \times T(T(9))) + (T(T(2)) \times 9) \\ 25932 &:= (T(2) \times (-5 - (93^2))) \\ 25935 &:= (T((-2) + T(5)) \times (T(9) \times T(3)) + T(5)) \\ 25938 &:= -((T((T(2) + 5))) + (-T(9) - T(3)) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 25941 &:= (25 \times T(T(9))) + T((T(4) + 1)) \\ 25942 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + (((T(T(5)) + (T(9) - (4)))^2))) \\ 25944 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times T(((5 + T(9)) - (4))) \times 4) \\ 25945 &:= (((25 \times T(T(9))) + T(T(4))) + T(5)) \\ 25946 &:= (2 + ((T(5) + 9) \times T(46))) \\ 25947 &:= (25 \times (T(T(9)) + (4))) - T(7) \\ 25948 &:= ((T(T(2 + 5))) \times (9 + T(T(4)))) - T(8) \\ 25950 &:= ((T(2^5)) - 9) \times 50) \\ 25952 &:= (2^5) \times (-9) + T((T(T(5))/T(2))) \\ 25953 &:= (25 \times T(T(9))) + T((T(5) - 3)) \\ 25955 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) - ((-5) \times T(T(9))) + (5))) \times 5) \\ 25956 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (((5 - T(T(9)))/(-5)) \times T(6))) \\ 25959 &:= -((T(T(2)) - ((T(T(5)) \times (T(9) \times 5)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 25962 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (((5 - 9)^6)) \times T(T(2))) \\ 25964 &:= (((-T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times (-9) + T(T(6))) - T(4) \\ 25965 &:= (25 \times T(T(9))) - (-6 \times T(5)) \\ 25967 &:= (((-T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times (-9) + T(T(6))) - (7) \\ 25968 &:= ((T(T(2)) + T((59 + T(6)))) \times 8) \\ 25974 &:= (T(((2 + T(5)) + 9)) \times 74) \\ 25975 &:= (T(25) + (9 \times T(75))) \\ 25977 &:= ((T((2 + 5)) \times T(T(9))) - T(77)) \\ 25983 &:= (25 \times T(T(9))) - (T(8) \times (-3)) \\ 25984 &:= (((2 \times T(5)) + 9) \times T(T(8))) + T(4) \\ 25986 &:= ((-2) - T(T(5))) \times (-T(9) + (8 \times T(6)))) \\ 26028 &:= (((T(2)^6) - T(T(02))) \times T(8)) \\ 26136 &:= ((T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6)))^{-1+3}) \times 6) \\ 26139 &:= (-T(T(2))) - (-T(6)) \times (T((-1) + T(T(3)))) + T(T(9))) \\ 26142 &:= (T(T(2)) + (6 \times (T((1 + T(4)))^2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26145 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (T((T(6) - 1)) + (T(45)))) \\ 26163 &:= (T((T(2) \times 6)) \times T(-((1 - (6 \times 3)))) \\ 26166 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(6) + T((T((1 + 6)) + T(6)))) \\ 26174 &:= -((T(-((T(2) - 6)))) + (-17) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 26175 &:= ((T(T(T(-(2 - 6)))) \times 17) - 5) \\ 26187 &:= (T((2 \times T(6))) \times ((1^8) + T(7))) \\ 26188 &:= (T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6)))) - (-1) + (T(T(8)) \times (-T(8)))) \\ 26189 &:= ((T((T(T(T(2))) + 61)) \times 8) - T(T(9))) \\ 26196 &:= ((-2) + T(T((6 - 1))) \times (-9) + T(T(6))) \\ 26197 &:= ((T(T(T(-(2 - 6)))) + 1) \times (T(9) - T(7))) \\ 26199 &:= (((T(2)^6) \times T(-((1 - 9))) - T(9)) \\ 26208 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (T(6) \times 208)) \\ 26222 &:= (((-2) + T(T(6)))^2 + T(2))/2) \\ 26223 &:= (((T(2)^6) \times T(2^{T(2)})) - T(T(3))) \\ 26224 &:= (-2) + (6 \times T((2 + T((T(2) + T(4)))))) \\ 26226 &:= (T(T(2)) \times T(((6^2) \times 2) + T(6))) \\ 26228 &:= (2 + (6 \times T((T(T(T(2))) + (2 \times T(8)))))) \\ 26229 &:= (T(2) - (-6) \times T((T(2) - (-2) \times T(9)))) \\ 26232 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((6 \times (T(2)^{T(3)})) - 2)) \\ 26234 &:= (((T(2)^6) \times T(2^3)) - T(4)) \\ 26235 &:= (((2 \times 6)^{T(2)} + T(T(3))) \times T(5)) \\ 26237 &:= (((T(2)^6) \times T(2^3)) - (7)) \\ 26238 &:= -((T(T(2)) - ((6 - 2) \times (3^8)))) \\ 26240 &:= (((2^6)/2) \times T(40)) \\ 26242 &:= (((T(2)^6) \times T((2 \times 4))) - 2) \\ 26243 &:= ((T(2) \times (T(6)^{T(2)})) - T(T((4 + T(3)))) \\ 26244 &:= ((T(2)^{T(6/2)}) \times T((4 + 4))) \\ 26252 &:= (2 - ((T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-5^{T(2)}))) \\ 26253 &:= (T(2) - ((T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-5^3))) \\ 26254 &:= (((T(2)^6) \times T((T(2) + 5))) + T(4)) \\ 26256 &:= (-T((2 \times 6)) - ((T(T(2)) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 26257 &:= ((T(T(T(-(2 - 6)))) + T(T((T(T(2)) + 5)))) \times 7) \\ 26262 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((6 \times (T(2)^6)) + T(2))) \\ 26264 &:= (((T(2) \times (T(6)^{T(2)})) + T(6)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 26268 &:= ((T(2) + T(6)) + ((T(2)^6) \times T(8))) \\ 26271 &:= (T(2) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T((7 \times 1)))))) \\ 26273 &:= (2 - ((T(T(6)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(7)))) \times (-3))) \\ 26274 &:= (-T(T(2))) - (T((T((T(6) \times T(2)))/T(7))) \times (-T(4))) \\ 26275 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(6))) - (2 - T(T(7)))) \times 5) \\ 26279 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(6) - T(T(2)))) - (T(T(7)) + T(T(9)))) \\ 26292 &:= (((-2) - T(T(6))) + T((T(T(2)) \times 9))) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 26295 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T((6 + T(2)))) + (T(95))) \\ 26298 &:= ((T((-2) + T((6 \times 2))) \times 9) - T(8)) \\ 26304 &:= ((T(2)^6) - (-T(30)) \times T(T(4))) \\ 26313 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) + ((6 - T(T((T(3) - 1)))) \times T(T(T(3)))))) \end{aligned}$$

- 26319** := $((T((2 \times T(6))) \times T((T(3) + 1))) + T(T(9)))$
26322 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(3)) - 2) - 2))$
26324 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(6))) \times (T(T(3)) - 2) - T(4))$
26325 := $(T(26) \times (3 \times 25))$
26327 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(6))) \times (T(T(3)) - 2) - (7))$
26328 := $(-((2 - 6) \times (T(T(3)) + (T(2)^8)))$
26331 := $(-T(2) + (T(T(6)) \times (-T(3) + T(T((T(3) - 1))))))$
26332 := $(-2 - (T(T(6)) \times (T(3) - T(T(3 + 2))))))$
26334 := $((-2) \times T(T(6))) \times (3 - (T(3) \times T(4)))$
26335 := $((T(T(2))/6 - (T(T(3)) \times (T(3) - T(T(5))))))$
26336 := $(2 + ((T((T(6) - T(3))) - (T(3))) \times T(T(6))))$
26342 := $((T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(6) - T(3))) - (T((T(T(4)) - T(2))))))$
26344 := $((T(2) \times 6) \times T((-3) + T(T(4)))) + T(T(4)))$
26346 := $((2 - T(T(6))) + (3 \times T(T(4)))) \times 6$
26349 := $(-((T(T(2)) - (T(6)))) + (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) \times 9))$
26352 := $((T(2)^6 + 3) \times T((5 + T(2))))$
26353 := $(-2) - ((T(T(6)) \times (T(3) - T(T(5)))) - T(T(3)))$
26355 := $(T(T(2)) - ((T(T(6)) \times (T(3) - T(T(5)))) - (T(5))))$
26358 := $(-T(2) + ((T(T(6)) \times (-3) + T(T(5)))) - T(T(8)))$
26367 := $(2 + T((6 + 3))) \times T((T(6)/7))$
26375 := $((2 + 63) \times T(T(7))) - (T(5))$
26376 := $((T((-2) + T(6))) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(7)) \times 6$
26382 := $(((-2) + T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 8 \times T(T(2))$
26385 := $(((-2) - T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(8) \times (-5)$
26388 := $((-(2 + 6) + T(38)) \times T(8))$
26394 := $(-T(T(2))) \times (T((T(6)/T(3))) - (T(94)))$
26396 := $(-((T((-2) + T(6))) - (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(6))))))$
26397 := $(-((T(2) \times T(6))) - (T(T(3)) \times (-T(9) \times T(7))))$
26399 := $(2 - (-T(6)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(9)) - 9)))$
26400 := $(T((T(T(T(2))))/T(6))) \times 400$
26412 := $((T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6))) - T(4)) \times 12$
26415 := $((T((2 + T(6))) + T((T(4) - 1))) \times T(5))$
26417 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(6))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-17)))$
26418 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((-T(6) + T(T(4))) \times (1 + T(8))))$
26422 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(6)))) + (T(T(4)))/(-2) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
26424 := $((T(2) \times 6) \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(2))^4))$
26432 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + T((-T(6) + T(T(4)))) \times 32$
26433 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(6))) \times ((T(4)^3) - T(T(3))))$
26439 := $((2 \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(4)) - (T(3))) + T(T(9))$
26442 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(6) \times T((T(4) + T(4)))) - T(2)))$
26444 := $((T(T(2)) + T((-T(6) + T(T(4)))) \times 44$
26445 := $((2 \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(4))) + (T(45))$
26448 := $(2 \times T((T(6) + T((4 + 4)))) \times 8$
26449 := $((2 \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(4)) + (4)) + T(T(9))$
26454 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(6)) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T((5 + 4))))$
26455 := $((T(T(2)) \times (T(6) \times T((4 \times 5)))) - (5))$
26456 := $((T((2 + T(6))) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))))$
26457 := $(-((T(2) - ((T(6) \times 45) \times T(7))))$
26458 := $(-2) - ((-6) + T(T(4))) \times (-T(5) \times T(8)))$
26459 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(6)) + T(T(T(4)))) + (5 - T(T(9))))$
26472 := $(((-2) \times T((6 + T(T(4)))) \times (-7)) - 2)$
26474 := $((-2) \times T((6 + T(T(4)))) \times (T(7)/(-4)))$
26475 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(6))) - (T(T(4)) \times T(7))) \times (-T(5))$
26476 := $(2 - (T((6 + T(T(4)))) \times (7 - T(6))))$
26477 := $(T(2) - ((6 + T(T(4))) \times (-T(7)) - T(T(7))))$
26478 := $(T(2) \times ((6 \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(7)) + 8)))$
26479 := $((T((-2 \times 6) + T(T(4)))) \times T(7) - 9)$
26480 := $((T(T(2)) + T((T(6) + (4)))) \times 80)$
26481 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((6^4) - T(8)) + 1)$
26482 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(T(4))) \times 8) - T(T(2))$
26483 := $(2 - ((T((-T(6) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(8)))) \times (-T(T(3))))$
26484 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(T(4))) \times 8) - 4$
26488 := $(T((-2 \times 6) + T(T(4))) \times (-8) + T(8))$
26491 := $((2 \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(4))) + T((T(9) + 1))$
26495 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (T((6 + T(T(4)))) \times (-9 + 5)))$
26496 := $(T((2 + T(6))) \times ((T(4) \times 9) + (6)))$
26498 := $(2 - ((T(T(6)) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(8)))$
26499 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(6)) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(9) - T(T(9))))$
26502 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T((T(5) - 02))))$
26505 := $((-2) + T(6)) \times (T(50) + T(T(5)))$
26508 := $(-T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(6) \times T(50)) - T(8)))$
26520 := $(T((T((2 + 6) + T(5))) \times 20)$
26523 := $((-T(2) + T(T(6))) + T((T(5) \times T(2)))) \times T(T(3))$
26524 := $((T(2) \times T(T((6 + 5)))) - 2) \times 4$
26526 := $((2 \times T(T((6 + 5)))) \times T(T(2)) - (6))$
26529 := $(-T(2) - (T(T((6 + 5))) \times (-T(2) + 9)))$
26531 := $((2 \times T(T((6 + 5)))) \times T(3) - 1)$
26532 := $((2 \times 6) \times T(T((5 + (3 \times 2))))$
26534 := $(2 - (T(T((6 + 5))) \times (-3 \times 4)))$
26535 := $(T(2) - (T(T((6 + 5))) \times (3 - T(5))))$
26537 := $((2 + T(6)) \times 5 \times T(T(T(3))) - (T(7)))$
26538 := $((-2) \times T(T(6))) + ((T(5)^3) \times 8)$
26561 := $((2 + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) - (6)) - 1)$
26562 := $((2 + T(6)) \times 5 \times T(T(6)) - T(2))$
26563 := $((T(T((2 + 6))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(6)))/3$
26564 := $((-2) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) - (-6 + T(4)))$
26565 := $(T(((2^6) + 5)) \times (6 + 5))$
26567 := $(2 - ((T(6) \times (-5)) \times T((-6) + T(7))))$
26568 := $((T(2)^6 + T(5)) - (6)) \times T(8)$
26572 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-6) + T(T(5))) + 7) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
26573 := $(-(((T(T(2)) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(7))) + T(T(3))))$
26575 := $((2 - (-T(6) \times T((T(5) + (7)))) \times 5)$
26583 := $((T((T(2) \times 6)) - (T(T(5)) \times T(T(8))))/(-3))$
26585 := $((T((T(2) \times T(6))) \times T(5)) - T(85))$

- 26586** := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(6) \times (-5) + (T(8) \times 6)))$
26587 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(6))) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(8))) + T(7)))$
26588 := $(2 - (((-6) \times T(T(5))) \times T(8)) - T(T(8)))$
26589 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8)) + T(9)$
26592 := $((2 \times 6) \times (5 + T(T(9 + 2))))$
26594 := $((T(T((2 \times 6))) - T(T(5))) \times 9) - T(T(4)))$
26595 := $-(((T(2) - 6) - T(59)) \times T(5))$
26598 := $((-2) \times T(6)) + ((-5) + T(9)) \times T(T(8))$
26607 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(6) \times 60) + (7)))$
26614 := $-((T(T(2)) - ((T(T(6)) + T((T(6) + 1))) \times T(T(4))))$
26624 := $(26 \times ((6/T(2))^{T(4)}))$
26628 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (((-T(6)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2))) + 8)$
26638 := $(-2) - ((T((-6) + T(6)))/(-3)) \times T(T(8))$
26640 := $(T((T(2) \times (6 + 6))) \times 40)$
26642 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(66)) + T(T(4))) \times 2$
26648 := $((T((T(2) + T((6 + 6)))) + T(4)) \times 8)$
26649 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (((T(6) \times 6) \times T(4)) + 9))$
26652 := $-((T(T(T(2)))) + (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))) - (T(5)))/(-2)))$
26655 := $((((-T(2)) + T(T(6))) - 6) \times T(T(5))) + (T(5))$
26656 := $((T((-2) + T(6)) + 6) \times T((-5) + T(6)))$
26657 := $-((T(T((T(2) + 6)))) - ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))) - T(7)))$
26658 := $((T(2) - T(T(6))) \times (6 - T(T(5)))) + T(T(8))$
26659 := $(-26) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(9)))$
26664 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-T(6)) + T(-((T(T(6)) - T((T(6) + 4))))))$
26667 := $(-T(2)) - (-6) \times ((T(6) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(7)))$
26670 := $((T(2) + T((T(6) + 6))) \times 70)$
26671 := $((T(T(2)) \times ((T(6) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(7)))) + 1)$
26672 := $(2 - (((-T(6)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(2)))$
26673 := $(T(2) - ((T(6) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(7))) \times (-T(3)))$
26674 := $(-2) - (-((6 \times 6) \times T((T(7) + T(4))))$
26675 := $((T(T(2)) \times ((T(6) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(7)))) + (5))$
26676 := $((T(T(2)) \times T((66 - T(7)))) \times 6)$
26677 := $((T(2)^6) \times T(6)) - (-T(7)) \times T(T(7))$
26678 := $(2 - (T((66 - T(7))) \times (-T(8))))$
26679 := $(T(2) - ((6 \times 6) \times T((-7) + T(9))))$
26682 := $((T((2 + (6 \times 6))) \times T(8)) + T(T(2)))$
26684 := $((T(2) + T(6)) \times T((6 \times 8))) - T(T(T(4)))$
26685 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(6)) + T((T(6) + T(8)))) \times T(5)$
26691 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (((6 + T(T(6))) + T(T(9))) - 1))$
26694 := $(T(2) - (-T(6)) \times (T((6 + T(9))) - T(T(4))))$
26695 := $(T(T(-((2 - 6)))) + (((T(T(6)) - 9) \times T(T(5))))$
26697 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(6))) + (((T(6) \times T(9)) \times T(7)))$
26712 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (-6) + (T(71)/2))$
26715 := $((T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - 1)) - T(5))$
26724 := $-((T(T(2)) + ((-T(6)) - T((T(7) + 2))) \times T(T(4))))$
26728 := $((2 - T(T(6))) + T((T(7) \times T(2)))) \times 8$
26729 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(6)))) - 7)/(-2) + T(9)$
26732 := $(-(2^6) + (T(T(7)) \times T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))))))$
26733 := $((T((2 \times 6)) \times (7^3)) - T(T(3)))$
26734 := $(2 \times (((T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(3))) - T(4)))$
26735 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(6)))) - (T((T(7) + 3)))) \times (-5)$
26738 := $(2 \times (((T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(3))) - 8))$
26739 := $(-T((2 + 6))) + (T((T(7) + T(3))) \times T(9))$
26741 := $-((T(T(-((2 - 6)))) - (T(T(7)) \times T((T(4) + 1))))$
26745 := $((T(T((2 \times 6))) - T(T(7))) \times T(4)) - (5)$
26747 := $((T(2) + T(67)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 7$
26748 := $((2 + T((6 \times 7) - 4)) \times T(8))$
26752 := $((2^6) \times ((T(7) \times T(5)) - 2))$
26754 := $((-2) \times T(6)) + (T(T(7)) \times T((T(5) - 4))))$
26763 := $((-T(2)) + (6 \times T(T(7)))) \times (T(T(6))/T(T(3)))$
26764 := $(2 \times ((T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \times T(6))) + T(4)$
26766 := $(2 \times (((T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + 6))$
26768 := $((-((2 - 6)) \times T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) + 8))$
26769 := $((T((2 \times T(6))) \times T(7)) + (T((6 \times 9))))$
26772 := $(T(T(2)) \times (((T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \times 7) + T(2)))$
26773 := $(-2) - (-T(6)) \times T(((T(7) + T(7)) - T(3)))$
26774 := $((-2) + (6 \times T(T(7)))) \times (7 + 4)$
26775 := $((2^6) \times T(7)) - (7) \times T(5)$
26778 := $(T(2) - (-T(6)) \times T(((7 + 7) + T(8))))$
26779 := $((T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6))) \times T(T(7))) + ((T(7) - T(9))))$
26781 := $(T(T(2)) + (T((6 + T(7))) \times T((8 + 1))))$
26782 := $(2 \times (-T((6 + T(7)))) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(2))))$
26783 := $((T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6))) \times T(T(7))) - (-8) + T(T(3)))$
26784 := $((-T(2)) + (T(T(6)) \times (-7) + T(8))) \times 4$
26787 := $-((T(2) - (6 \times T((7 + 8))))$
26788 := $((2 \times T(6)) \times (-T(7)) + T(T(8))) - 8$
26817 := $((T(2) + T((6 + 81))) \times 7)$
26824 := $-((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (((-6) + T(8))^{T(2)} + T(T(4))))$
26825 := $((2 - T(T(6))) - T(T(8))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5)))$
26826 := $((T(T(2)) + T((T((T(6) - 8)) + T(2)))) \times 6)$
26829 := $((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6)) \times (-T(T(8)) - (T(2) \times T(T(9))))$
26838 := $((T(T(2)) + T(6)) - T(T(8))) \times (-T(3) + T(8))$
26844 := $-((T(T(2)) + ((T(6) - (T(T(8)) \times (-4))) \times (-T(4))))$
26847 := $(T((T(2) \times 6)) + (T(8) \times T((T(4) + T(7))))$
26853 := $((-T((2 \times T(6))) - T(8)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3))))$
26856 := $((-T((T(2) + T(6)) \times T(8))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))))$
26857 := $((-2) - T(6)) + ((8 \times T(T(5))) \times T(7))$
26859 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(T(6)) + (8 + 5)) + T(T(9))))$
26865 := $((T(((2 + T(6)) + T(8))) + (T(6))) \times T(5))$
26873 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times ((T(6) + T(8)) - T(T(7))))/(-3))$
26874 := $(-T(T(2)) - (-T(6)) \times (-((T(T(8)) - T(T(7)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
26875 := $((T(T(2)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(8)))) - (7)) \times 5$
26878 := $(-2) - (T(-((T(6) - T(8)))) \times (T(7) \times (-8)))$
26880 := $((2 \times T(6)) \times (8 \times 80))$

- 26883** := $(T(2) \times (((T(T(6)) \times T(8)) + T(T(8))) - T(T(3))))$
26884 := $((2+6) + T(8)) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(4)))$
26887 := $(T((2 \times T(6))) - ((8 \times 8) \times T(T(7))))$
26889 := $-((T(T((2 \times 6))) + (T(T(8)) \times (-T(8) + 9))))$
26891 := $((2 \times T(6)) \times T(T(8))) - T((T(9) + 1))$
26892 := $((T(T(2)) \times ((T(6) \times T(8)) - 9)) \times T(T(2)))$
26895 := $((2 + (T(6) \times T(8))) + T(T(9))) \times T(5)$
26898 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T(6) \times T(8)) - 9) \times T(8))$
26905 := $(26 \times T(T(9))) - 05$
26922 := $((26 \times T(T(9))) + T(T(2))) + T(T(2))$
26924 := $-((T(T(T(2)))) + (-((T(6) + 9)^{T(2)})) + T(T(4))))$
26925 := $-((T(2) - ((6 + T(9)) \times T(2^5))))$
26928 := $(T(2) \times ((T(6) + T(9)) \times T(2 \times 8)))$
26931 := $(26 \times T(T(9))) + T(T(3 \times 1))$
26934 := $(26 \times T(T(9))) + (T(3) \times 4)$
26936 := $(26 \times (T(T(9)) + (T(3)/6)))$
26937 := $-((T(T((T(T(T(2))))/T(6)))) + ((T(T(9)) + (T(3)) \times (-T(7))))$
26943 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (T((6 + T(9)) - 43))$
26944 := $-((T(T(2)) \times (T(T(6)) - (T(94)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
26946 := $((-26) - T(94)) \times (-6)$
26949 := $((T(T(2)) - (T(T(6)) \times 9)) \times (-4 + 9))$
26950 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(6)))/9) \times 50$
26952 := $(2 \times (T(6) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(5) - 2))))$
26955 := $-((T(2) - (T((6 + 9)) \times T(5))) \times T(5))$
26957 := $((T(2) + (6 \times T(95))) - T(T(7)))$
26962 := $(26 \times (T(T(9)) + (6/T(2))))$
26963 := $-((2^6) + (9 \times T((T(T(6))/3)))$
26964 := $((T((2 + T(6))) + T(9)) \times (T(6) \times 4))$
26965 := $(T(T(-(2 - 6))) + (T(T(9)) \times (T(6) + (5))))$
26967 := $(T((T(2) \times 6)) + ((T(9) + T(6)) \times T(T(7))))$
26973 := $-((T(2)^6) \times (-((9 + 7) - T(T(3))))$
26974 := $-((T(2 + 6)) + (T((T(9) + T(7))) \times T(4)))$
26979 := $((T(2) + T(6)) + T(9)) \times T(T(7)) - T(T(9))$
26982 := $(26 \times T(T(9))) + (T(8) \times 2)$
26985 := $((T(T(2)) + (T(6))) \times T(T(9))) - (8 \times T(T(5)))$
26992 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(9)))) + (T(T(9 - 2))))$
26994 := $-((T(T(2)) + ((6 \times T(9)) \times (-T(9) - T(T(4))))$
26995 := $((T((T(2) + T(6))) \times (T(9) + T(9))) - (5))$
26997 := $-((T(2) - ((T(6) + 9)^{T(9-7)}))$
27010 := $(T((T(2) + 70)) \times 10)$
27048 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (T(7) \times (T(04) + T(8))))$
27090 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + 70) \times 90)$
27125 := $-((T((T(T(2)) + T(7))) + (T(T(T(1 + 2)))) \times (-T(T(5))))$
27126 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) - 1) \times T((T(T(T(2))))/T(6))$
27132 := $(T(2 \times T(7))) \times (-1) + (T(3) \times T(2))$
27135 := $-((T(2 + T(7))) + ((1 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(5))))$
27147 := $(T((-2) + T(7))) + (T((1 + T(4))) \times T(T(7)))$
27153 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(7) - 1)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3))))$
27183 := $((T(T(2)) \times 7) - 1) \times (T(T(8)) - 3)$
27188 := $-((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-7) \times (-1 - T(8))))$
27189 := $((-2) + T((7 - 1))) \times T((8 + T(9)))$
27192 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T(((1 \times 9) + 2)))$
27195 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (7 \times (T(19) - (5))))$
27196 := $-((T(T(2)) - (T(T(7)) \times ((1 + T(9)) + T(6))))$
27215 := $((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(7)))) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1) \times T(T(5))))$
27216 := $((T(T(2))^{7-T(2)}) \times T((1 \times 6)))$
27222 := $((T(2) \times T((7 + T(2))))^2 - T(2))$
27223 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(2) + (2^{T(3)}))))$
27224 := $(T(((T(2) \times T(7)) - 2)) \times (2 \times 4))$
27225 := $((T(2) \times T((7 + T(2))))^{-T(2)+5})$
27228 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) + T(8))$
27231 := $((2 + T(7))^{T(2)} + T(T(T(3 \times 1))))$
27233 := $(2 + ((T(7) + 2)^3) + T(T(T(3))))$
27234 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(7)) \times T(2)) + (T(3^4))))$
27235 := $((T(T(2)) + (7)) \times (T(2^{T(3)})) + (T(5)))$
27237 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (72 + T((T(3)) + T(7))))$
27240 := $(T(T(-(2 - 7))) \times (T(T(T(2)))) - (4 + 0))$
27241 := $((T(T(-(2 - 7))) \times (T(T(T(2)))) - 4) + 1)$
27242 := $((-2) + T(7) + ((T(T(2))^4) \times T(T(T(2))))$
27243 := $(27 + ((T(T(2))^4) \times T(T(3))))$
27244 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (T(7))) \times (T(T(2)) + (T(4) \times T(T(4))))$
27245 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(4) \times 5$
27246 := $((2 + T(7)) + ((T(T(2))^4) \times T(6)))$
27247 := $(T(2) - ((7 \times 2) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(7))))$
27248 := $((T(2) + T((72 + T(4)))) \times 8)$
27249 := $((T(2) + T(7)) \times ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4) - T(9)))$
27251 := $((-2) + T((7 \times T(2)))) \times (T(T(5)) - 1)$
27252 := $((T((T(2) \times 7)) \times (-2) + T(T(5))) - T(T(2)))$
27253 := $((2 - 7) - ((2 - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
27254 := $((T((T(2) \times 7)) \times (-2) + T(T(5))) - (4))$
27255 := $(T(2) \times ((T(7) \times T(25)) - T(5)))$
27256 := $(-2) - ((-T(7)) + (T(T(2)) \times (-T(5)))) \times T(T(6))$
27257 := $((T(T(2)) \times (-T(T(7))) + T(-(T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(5)))))) - 7)$
27258 := $(T((T(2) \times 7)) \times (-2) - (T(5) \times (-8)))$
27259 := $-((T(T(T(2))) + (-T((T(7) + T(2)))) \times T(T(-(5 - 9))))$
27264 := $(2^7) \times (T(2) + (T(6) \times T(4)))$
27265 := $((T((T(2) + T(7))) \times T(T(-(2 - 6)))) - T(5))$
27268 := $((-T(2)) + T(T(7))) - 2 \times 68$
27274 := $-((T(T(2))) + (T((T(7) + (T(T(T(2)))/7))) \times T(T(4))))$
27275 := $((T((T(2) + (7))) \times T((T(2) + T(7)))) - (5))$
27277 := $-((T(2)) + (T((T(7) + T(2))) \times T(T((T(7)/7))))$
27278 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(7))^2 - T((7 + T(8))))$
27279 := $((-T(2) - T(72)) + T(T(7))) \times 9$

- 27293** := $-(((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(7)))) - (T((T(T(2)) + 9)) \times T(T(T(3))))))$
27294 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(7) \times T(2)) + T(94)))$
27295 := $((T((T(T(2)) + (7))) \times T(-((T(T(2))) - T(9)))) - 5)$
27297 := $((T((T(T(T(T(2))))/7)) \times (-T(2))) + (T(T(9)) \times T(7)))$
27300 := $(T((T(T(2)) + (7))) \times 300)$
27312 := $((-2) - T(T(7)) - (-T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T((-1) + T(T(2))))))$
27314 := $((T(T(2)) + T(7)) + (T(31) \times T(T(4))))$
27316 := $((2 - T(T(7))) - (T(T((T(3) - 1))) \times (-T(T(6))))$
27322 := $-((T(T(2)) - ((T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times (2^{T(T(2))})))$
27324 := $((T(2) \times T((T(7) - T(3)))) \times T((2 \times 4)))$
27325 := $((2 + T(7))^3 + T(25))$
27326 := $(-2) - ((T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times (-2^6))$
27328 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(7)))) \times ((T(3) + 2) \times 8))$
27329 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(7))) - (T(T((T(3) \times 2))) \times (-9)))$
27335 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(7)) - (T(T((3 + 3))) \times T(T(5))))$
27336 := $((2 \times T((73 - T(3)))) \times 6)$
27339 := $(T(2) + (-((T(7) + T(3))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(9))))$
27341 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times ((-7) - T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) - 1)$
27342 := $((2 \times 7) \times T(((T(3) \times T(4)) + 2)))$
27345 := $(T(2) \times ((7 - T((T(3) \times T(4)))) \times (-5)))$
27346 := $(((-T(2)) + T((T(7) + 3))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(6)))$
27349 := $(T(T(T(2))) + ((T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) + 9)))$
27352 := $(T(-((T(2) - T(7)))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(2))))$
27355 := $((-((T(2) - T(7 \times 3))) \times T(T(5))) - 5)$
27356 := $(T(T(T(2))) - ((T(T(7)) - T(T(3))) - (T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))))$
27357 := $(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/7)) + (T((T(3) + 5))) \times T(T(7)))$
27359 := $-((T((T(T(T(2))) + 7)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(5)))) - T(9)))$
27370 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) - T(T(3))) \times 70$
27377 := $((T(T(T(2)))^{7-3}/7) - (T(T(7))))$
27378 := $(27 \times (T(3) + (T(7) \times T(8))))$
27379 := $((-2) - (7 \times 3)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(9)))$
27384 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(7)) \times ((3 \times T(8)) + T(T(4))))$
27388 := $((T(2) - (-7) \times (3 - T(88))))$
27391 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (T((T(7) + T(3))) \times (-T(9) + 1)))$
27394 := $-(((T(T(T(2))) + (-((T(7) - 3)) \times T(T(9)))) - T(T(T(4))))$
27395 := $-((T(-((T(2) - T(7)))) - (T(T(-((3 - 9)))) \times T(T(5))))$
27397 := $((2 + T(7))^3 - 9) + T(T(7))$
27399 := $((2 - T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(9)))) + T(T(9))$
27412 := $(T(((T(2) \times T(7)) + 4)) \times (1 + T(T(2))))$
27416 := $((T((T(2) + T(7))) \times T(T(4))) + T(16))$
27418 := $(T(T(2)) + (7 \times T(((T(4) + 1) \times 8)))$
27419 := $-((T(T(T(2))) + (T(7) \times (T(4) - T((-1) + T(9))))))$
27423 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T((-T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(3))))$
27425 := $((T(2) - T(7)) + (T((T(4) \times T(T(2)))) \times T(5)))$
27426 := $((-T(2)) + T(T(7)) + T(42)) \times T(6)$
27427 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times 7) + (T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + T(7))))$
27432 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T((T(7) + T(4))) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(2))))$
27433 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (T(7) \times (-((T(4)^3) + T(T(3))))))$
27434 := $((-T((T(2) \times 7))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3)) - (T(T(4))))$
27435 := $(T((2 + T(7))) \times ((4^3) - 5))$
27436 := $((T(2) \times ((T(7) + T(4))^3)/6)$
27438 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T((T(7) + T(4))) + T(T(3))) \times T(8)))$
27442 := $((2 - T(T(7))) + (T((-4) + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
27443 := $((T(2) - T(T(7))) + (T((-4) + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3)))$
27445 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(7) - 4)) - (T(T(4)))) \times 5$
27446 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(7))) - (T((-4) + T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6)))$
27447 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(4)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 7$
27448 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(7)) - 4) \times (T(T(4)) - 8)$
27449 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-7 - ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(4))) \times (-9)))$
27462 := $(-27) + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
27463 := $((2 - T(7)) + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(3))))$
27465 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(7))) \times (-4) + T(T(6))) \times T(5)$
27467 := $(-T(2)) - ((T(T(7)) + 4) \times (-67))$
27468 := $((2 \times T(T(7))) - T(T(4)) + 6) \times T(8)$
27469 := $((T(T(2) + T(7))) \times T(T(4)) + (T(6) \times 9))$
27472 := $((-2) + T(T(7))) \times (-4 - 72)$
27473 := $((2 + (T(T(7)) \times T((4 \times 7))))/T(3))$
27482 := $((2 + T((T(7) - 4))) \times T((-8) + T(T(T(2))))$
27483 := $((2 \times T(T(7))) - T(T(4)) \times T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))$
27486 := $(-T(2)) - (((-T(7)) - T(T(4))) - T(8)) \times T(T(6)))$
27488 := $(T(T(2)) + (7 \times (T(4) + T(88))))$
27489 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (T(7))) \times T((T((4 + 8)) - T(9))))$
27492 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(7) + T((4 + 9)))) + T(2))$
27495 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(7) + T(4))) + T(T(9))) \times T(5)$
27496 := $-((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (7 + (T(T(-((4 - 9)))) \times T(T(6))))$
27498 := $(T(2) \times T(T(7))) + ((T(4) \times T((9 \times 8))))$
27500 := $(T((T(2) + 7)) \times 500)$
27510 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (T(75) - T(T(10))))$
27516 := $(27 + ((T(T(5)) - 1) \times T(T(6))))$
27517 := $((T((T(2) \times 7)) \times (T(T(5)) - 1)) + T(7))$
27520 := $((2^7) \times (5 + T(20)))$
27522 := $((T(T(T(T(2))))/7) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(T(2))))))$
27523 := $(T((T(2) + T(7))) + ((T(T(5)) - T(2)) \times T(T(T(3))))$
27524 := $((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(7)) \times (T(5) + 2))) \times (-4))$
27525 := $((-2) - 7) + T((T(T(5))/2)) \times T(5)$
27526 := $(-2) \times (T(T(7)) - ((T(T(5))^2) - T(T(6))))$
27528 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(7) + (T(T(5)) \times (2 + T(8))))$
27529 := $(-2) + ((-T(T(7))) - (-T(5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times 9$
27534 := $((T(2) \times T(7)) + (T(5) \times T((T(3) \times T(4))))$
27544 := $((-T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(T(7 - 5)))) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4))))$
27545 := $((T((T(2) \times 7)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))$
27546 := $(T(2) \times (-T(7)) + ((5 - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-6)))$
27549 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(T(7))) + (5^4) \times 9)$
27552 := $(T(2) \times T(7)) \times (T((5 \times 5)) + T(2))$

- 27555 := ((T((T(2) + T(7))) + (5)) × 55)
 27563 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(7) - (T(T(5)) × (T(T(6)) - 3))))
 27564 := ((T(2) + (T(7) × (T(5) + T(T(6)))))) × 4
 27565 := (((T(2) + T(7)) × (-5)) + (T(T(6)) × T(T(5))))
 27566 := (T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(7)) - ((T(T(5)) × T(T(6))) + T(T(6))))
 27567 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((7 + 5) × T(67)))
 27573 := ((T((T(2) × 7)) × T(T(5))) - (7 × T(T(3))))
 27574 := -((T(T(2)) + (7 × (T(T(5)) + (T(T(7)) × (-T(4))))))
 27576 := (T(2) × (T(T((-7) + T(5)))) - (T(T(7)) × (-T(6))))
 27579 := (((2 + T((T(7) + T(5)))) × T(7)) + T(T(9)))
 27582 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(T(7)) + (5)) + T(T((-8) + T(T(T(2)))))))
 27585 := (((2⁷) + T(58)) × T(5))
 27586 := (T(T((T(T(2)) + (7)))) + (T(T(5)) × (-T(8)) + T(T(6))))
 27587 := ((T(T(T(2))) × (7 + T((T(5) + T(8)))) - (T(T(7))))
 27588 := ((T(2) - T((7 × 5))) × (-8) - T(8))
 27592 := (-2) × (T(7) - ((T(5) + 9)^{T(2)}))
 27594 := -((T(T(2)) + (T((T(7) - (5))) × (-T(9)) - T(T(4))))
 27595 := (T((T(T(2)) + T(7))) + (T(T(5)) × (T(9) × 5)))
 27608 := (T((T(T(T(2))) + 7)) × (60 + 8))
 27610 := ((T((T(2) + T(7))) + (6)) × T(10))
 27615 := (T(-((2 - 7))) + ((T(T(6)) - 1) × T(T(5))))
 27624 := ((2 + T(T(7))) + (T(6) × (T(T(2))⁴)))
 27625 := ((T(T(2)) - (T((7 + 6)))) × (-T(25)))
 27629 := (T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(7)) × (-((T(6) + 2) + T(9))))
 27635 := ((T(T(2)) - (T((7 + 6)))) + (T(T(T(3))) × T(T(5))))
 27636 := -((T(2) × (T(7) - ((T(6)³) - T(6))))
 27638 := (2 + (T(7) × (T(T(6)) - (T(T(3)) × (-T(8))))))
 27642 := ((T(T(-((2 - 7)))) × T(T(6))) - T((T(4) + 2)))
 27643 := (T(T(T(2))) + ((T(T(7)) + ((6⁴) × T(T(3))))))
 27644 := (-T(T(2))) - ((T((T(7) + T(6))) + T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(4)))
 27645 := (((T(T(2)) + (7)) + T((6 × T(4)))) × T(5))
 27646 := ((T(T(2)) + T((T(7) + (6)))) × 46)
 27648 := (((2⁷) × T(T((6 - 4)))) × T(8))
 27652 := ((-2) × (T(7) + (6))) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(T(T(2))))))
 27654 := ((-2) × T(7)) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T(5))) - T(4))
 27655 := (T((T(2) + (7))) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T(5))) - T(T(5))))
 27657 := ((-2) × T(7)) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T(5))) - (7))
 27658 := (2 - T(7)) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T(5))) - T(8))
 27660 := ((T(T(-((2 - 7)))) × T(T(6))) - (60))
 27664 := (2 × (-T(7)) - (T(T(6)) × (-6 × T(4))))
 27665 := -((T(((T(2) + T(7)) - T(6))) - (T(T(6)) × T(T(5))))
 27669 := (T(2) - ((7 - T(T(6 + 6)))) × 9)
 27672 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(7) + T(67)) × 2))
 27675 := ((2 + 7) × (-6) + T(T((7 + 5))))
 27678 := ((T(T(2)) × 7) × ((T(6) - T(7)) + T(T(8))))
 27680 := ((T(-((T(2) - T(7)))) + (T(6))) × 80)
 27682 := ((T(T(-((2 - 7)))) × T(T(6))) - (T(8) + 2))
 27683 := (-2) + (7 × (T(T((T(6) - 8))) - T(T(T(3))))))
 27684 := (T(T(T(2))) - ((T(T(7)) × (-68)) - T(T(4))))
 27685 := ((T(T(T(2))) - (T(7))) × (T(T(6)) - T(T((8 + 5))))
 27686 := -(((T(T(2)) + T(7)) - (T(T(6)) × T((T(8) - T(6))))))
 27687 := ((T(T(T(T(2))))/(-7)) + (T(T(6)) × T((8 + 7))))
 27691 := (T(T(2)) + (-7) × (T(T(6)) - (T(91))))
 27692 := ((T(T(-((2 - 7)))) × T(T(6))) - T((9 - 2)))
 27693 := (-27) + (T(T(6)) × T((9 + T(3))))
 27694 := ((2 - T(7)) + (T(T(6)) × T(T((9 - 4))))
 27695 := ((T(2) - T(7)) + (T(T(T(-((6 - 9)))) × T(T(5))))
 27696 := (-T(2)) - ((7 - T((6 + T(9)))) × T(6))
 27699 := (((-2) + T(T(7))) × (T(6) + T(9))) + T(T(9))
 27714 := -((T(T(2)) - (T((-7) + T(7))) × T(T((1 + 4))))
 27715 := ((2 - 7) + (T(T((7 - 1))) × T(T(5))))
 27718 := (-2) + (T(7) × T((T((7 + 1)) + 8)))
 27719 := ((T(T(2)) - (7)) - (-T(7)) × T((-1) + T(9)))
 27732 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(T(T(T(7)/7))) × 3) + 2))
 27734 := (T(T((T(T(2)) + (7)))) - (T(T(7)) × (-3) - T(T(4))))
 27735 := ((T((2 × T(7))) + T((T(7) - T(3)))) × T(5))
 27741 := (T(T(T(2))) + (T((-7) + T(7))) × T(T((4 + 1))))
 27743 := ((-2) + (T(T(7)) × (T(T(7)) + (4))))/T(3)
 27744 := ((2 + T(T(7))) × ((7 + T(4)) × 4))
 27745 := (((T(2) + (7)) × T(74)) - (5))
 27748 := -((T(T(2)) + ((T(T(7)) × (-7) × T(4)) + T(T(8))))
 27752 := (-((T(2) - T(7)) - (7))) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(T(T(2))))))
 27753 := ((-((2 - 7)) + T(7)) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(T(3))))
 27754 := -((T(T(T(2))) - ((T((-7) + T(7))) × T(T(5))) + T(T(4))))
 27755 := ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(7)))) × ((T(7) - T(5)) × 5))
 27756 := (T(((2 × T(7))/7)) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(6))))
 27757 := ((2 + 7) × T(T((7 + 5)))) + T(7)
 27758 := (2 + ((T((-7) + T(7))) × T(T(5))) + T(8))
 27759 := ((2 + T(7)) - (T(T((7 + 5))) × (-9)))
 27762 := ((T(T(T(2)))/7) × (-7) + (T(6)^{T(2)}))
 27764 := ((2 - (-7) × T(T((7 + 6)))) - T(T(T(4))))
 27765 := ((T(T(T(2))) + T((T((T(7)/7)) × 6))) × T(5))
 27768 := ((T((T(2) + 77)) + T(T(6))) × 8)
 27773 := ((T((T(2) + T(7))) × (T(7) + T(7))) - 3)
 27774 := ((T(2) + T(T(T(T(7)/7)))) × (T(7) - T(4)))
 27775 := (T((T(2) + (7))) + (T((-7) + T(7))) × T(T(5)))
 27776 := ((2⁷) × ((T(7) × 7) + T(6)))
 27778 := (2 + ((T(7) + T(T(7))) × (T(7) + T(8))))
 27782 := ((T((T(2) + T(7))) × (7 × 8)) + T(T(2)))
 27783 := (T(2) × (T(((7 + 7) - 8))³))
 27784 := (((2 + 7) × T(78)) + T(T(4)))
 27786 := ((-((T(2) + T(7))) + (7 × T(T(8)))) × 6)
 27788 := (2 × ((7 × T((T(7) + T(8)))) - T(T(8))))
 27789 := -((T(2) - ((7 + T(78)) × 9))

- 27792 := ((2 + 7) × (7 + T(T((9 + T(2))))))
27795 := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) + T(T(7))) + T(T(9))) × T(5))
27797 := (((T(2) × T(7)) - (7)) × (-T(9) + T(T(7))))
27798 := ((T(2 × T(7))) × (-T(7) - T(9))) + T(T(8))
27804 := ((T(T(2)) × 7) × (T(T(8)) - 04))
27822 := ((T(T(T(2))) × (-7) - (T(T(8)) × (-2))) - T(2))
27823 := (-2) - (-7) × ((T(T(8)) × T(T(2))) - T(T(3))))
27825 := ((T(T(2)) + ((7 + T(8))²)) × T(5))
27828 := (((2 × T(T(7))) - (T(8) + T(2))) × T(8))
27829 := (-2) + ((T(T(7)) × T((8 + T(2)))) + T(T(9)))
27831 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-T((7 + 8)) × (T(T(T(3))) - 1)))
27832 := (2 × (-7) - (-((T(T(8)) - 3) × T(T(T(2))))))
27834 := (T(2) × (((T(T(7)) + T(8)) × T(T(3))) - (4)))
27838 := (T(T(2)) + ((-7) + T(83)) × 8)
27840 := (((2 + T(7)) + T(T(8))) × 40)
27842 := (2 + (T((-7) + T(8))) × (4^{T(2)}))
27843 := (T(2) + (T((-7) + T(8))) × (4³))
27844 := ((T(T(T(2))) + ((T(7) + T(T(8))) × T(4))) × 4)
27845 := ((T((T(T(2)) + T(7))) × (-8) + T(T(4))) - (T(T(5))))
27846 := (T((2 + (7^{8/4}))) × T(6))
27848 := (((T(T(2)) - T(T(7))) - T(T((8 + 4)))) × (-8))
27849 := (((T(T(2)) × 7) × (T(T(8)) - (4))) + T(9))
27851 := (((T(T(2)) × 7) × T(T(8))) - T(T(5))) - 1)
27852 := (((T(T(2)) × 7) × T(T(8))) - T((5 × T(2))))
27853 := -(T(T(T(2))) + (-T(7) - (T((T(8) + T(5))) × T(T(3))))))
27854 := -(T(T(2)) + ((T(T(7)) - 8) × (-T(5) - T(T(4))))))
27855 := (((T(2) × (-7) + T(T(8)))) - T(T(5))) × T(5))
27856 := ((T(2) + (7)) - (T((T(8) + T(5))) × (-T(6))))
27858 := ((T(2) × T(T(7))) + (T(T(8)) × (5 × 8)))
27861 := (T(T(T(2))) + (T((7 + 8)) × (T(T(6)) + 1)))
27862 := ((T((T(2) + (7))) - (T(T(8)) × T(6))) × (-2))
27865 := (-2) - (-7) × ((T(T(8)) × 6) - (T(5)))
27867 := (((T(T(2)) × 7) × T(T(8))) - T((T(6) - (7))))
27871 := (((-2) + T(7)) × (T(T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - 1)
27872 := ((T(T(2)) + (7)) × ((T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) × 2))
27874 := (-((2 × 7) + (8 × T((T(7) + T(T(4))))))
27876 := ((-2) + T(T(7))) × (-T(8) + T((-7) + T(6)))
27882 := (T(T(2)) × ((7 × T(T(8))) - T((8 - T(2))))
27883 := ((2 - 7) + (8 × T(83)))
27884 := (((T((T(2) × T(7))) × 8) - T(T(8))) - T(4))
27885 := ((2 × ((T(T(7)) × T(8)) - T(T(8)))) - (T(5)))
27886 := (((T(T(2)) × 7) × T(T(8))) - (86))
27887 := (((T((T(2) × T(7))) × 8) - T(T(8))) - (7))
27888 := (T(((2 - 7) + 88)) × 8)
27894 := ((T((T(2) × T(7))) × 8) - T((9 × 4)))
27898 := (-2) + (((T(T(7)) - T(T(8))) + T(T(9))) × T(8))
27900 := ((T(2) + T(7)) × 900)
27912 := ((27 × (T(T(9)) - 1)) - T(T(2)))
27914 := ((27 × (T(T(9)) - 1)) - (4))
27916 := (2 × (-T(7)) - (T(T((9 - 1))) × (-T(6))))
27917 := ((27 × T(T(9))) - T((1 × 7)))
27918 := ((T(2 × T(7))) - T(9)) × 18)
27919 := (((-2) + T(7)) × (T(T(9)) - 1)) + T(T(9))
27922 := (((27 × T(T(9))) - T(T(T(2)))) - 2)
27923 := ((T(T(2)) - T(7)) - (T(T(9)) × (-T(2)³)))
27924 := (((-T(2)) + T(T(7))) - T(9)) × T((2 + T(4)))
27926 := ((27 × T(T(9))) - (-2) + T(6))
27927 := (-T(2)) - ((T((T(7) - 9)) × T(T(T(2)))) × (-7))
27928 := ((T((T(2 × 7)) - 9)) × T(T(2))) - 8)
27930 := ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(7))) × (T(T(9)) - (T(30))))
27932 := -(((T(T(2)) + (7)) + (T(T(9)) × (-3^{T(2)}))))
27933 := ((27 × T(T(9))) - (T(3) + T(3)))
27934 := (((27 × T(T(9))) - T(T(3))) + T(4))
27935 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-((7 + 9) + (T(T(T(3))) × T(T(5))))))
27936 := (T((2 × ((7 + 9) × 3))) × 6)
27937 := (T((T(T(2)) + (7))) × (T((T(9) - T(T(3)))) + 7))
27938 := (2 × ((T(7) - T(9)) + (T(T(3)) × T(T(8))))
27939 := ((27 × T(T(9))) + ((3 - 9)))
27941 := ((27 × T(T(9))) - (4 × 1))
27942 := ((27 × T(T(9))) - T((4 - 2)))
27943 := ((27 × T(T(9))) - (-4) + T(3))
27944 := ((27 × T(T(9))) - (4/4))
27945 := (27 × T((T(9) × (-4 - 5))))
27948 := ((27 × T(T(9))) + T((T(4) - 8)))
27949 := (((-2) + T(7)) × T(T(9))) + (4) + T(T(9))
27962 := ((T((T(2) + T(7))) - T(9)) × 62)
27963 := (27 + (T(96) × T(3)))
27966 := (((2 - 7) - T(96)) × (-6))
27967 := ((27 × T(T(9))) + (-6) + T(7))
27968 := (2 × ((7 - 9) + (T(6) × T(T(8))))
27969 := ((27 × T(T(9))) - ((T(6) - T(9))))
27971 := ((-2) + T(7)) - (T(T(9)) × (-T(7) - 1))
27972 := (((T(27) - T(9)) × T(7)) × T(2))
27973 := (((27 × T(T(9))) + (7)) + T(T(3)))
27975 := (T(2) + (T(7) × (T(T(9)) - T((-7) + T(5))))))
27978 := (T(T(2)) - (T(7) × (9 - (T(7) × T(8))))
27979 := (T(T(2)) - (((-T(7)) × T(T(9))) - T(7)) + T(T(9)))
27981 := ((27 × T(T(9))) + T((8 × 1)))
27982 := (T(-((T(T(2)) - T(7))) + (9 × T(T((T(8)/T(2))))))
27984 := (2 - ((-T(7)) × (T(T(9)) - T(8))) - T(4))
27985 := ((27 × T(T(9))) + (8 × 5))
27987 := (T(-((2 - 7))) - ((T(T(9)) - T(8)) × (-T(7))))
27988 := (-2) + ((T(7) × T(T(9))) - T((8 + T(8))))
28023 := (T(2) × (80 + (T(T(T(2)))³)))

- 28035** := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((-T(8)) - T(T(T(03)))) \times (-5))$
28050 := $(T(-((T(2) - T(8)))) \times 050)$
28059 := $-((T(T(T(2))) - ((-T(80)) + T(T(5))) \times (-9)))$
28074 := $-((T(T(2)) - (80 \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(4))))))$
28119 := $-((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T((T(8) - 1)) \times T((1 \times 9))))$
28120 := $((-2) \times T((T(8) + 1))) \times (-20)$
28124 := $(2 \times (((T(T(8)) + 1) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4))))$
28125 := $((((T(T(2)) - (81)))^2) \times 5)$
28126 := $(T(28) - (T(T((-1) + T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(6))))$
28127 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) + (8 \times (T(T(12)) + T(T(7))))$
28128 := $((T((T(T(T(2))) + 8)) + T(T(12))) \times 8)$
28144 := $((T(T(2)) + (T((T(8) + 1)) \times T(4))) \times 4)$
28145 := $((2^{8+1}) \times T(T(4))) - (T(5))$
28149 := $-((T(T(T(2))) + ((T((T(8) - 1)) - (4)) \times (-T(9))))$
28152 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(8) + T(((1 + T(5)) \times T(T(2))))))$
28153 := $((-2) + T(T(8))) + ((-1) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
28154 := $-((T(T((T(T(T(2))) - 8))) + (-T((1 + 5))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
28155 := $((((T(2) \times T(T(8))) - 1) - T(T(5))) \times T(5))$
28156 := $(T((T(T(T(2))) + 8)) - (-1 - (T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))))$
28167 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) \times (-1 - (6 \times 7)))$
28175 := $(T(((T(T(2)) \times 8) + 1)) \times (T(7) - (5)))$
28176 := $(T(T(2)) \times (8 \times (-1) + (T(7) \times T(6))))$
28182 := $((T(T(2)) + T(8)) \times ((-1) + T(T(8))) + T(T(2)))$
28185 := $((T((T(T(2)) \times 8)) + T((1 + T(8)))) \times T(5))$
28188 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(8)) \times (-1 - 8)) + T(8)))$
28203 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(8)) \times 2)) + T(T(T(03))))$
28212 := $((((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2) - 12)$
28214 := $((((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2) - T((1 \times 4)))$
28215 := $((T(2) \times T((T(8)/2))) \times T(T(-((1 - 5))))$
28217 := $((((T(T(2)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(2))) - 1) \times 7)$
28221 := $((((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2) - (2 + 1))$
28222 := $(((-T(2)) + T((T(8)/2)))^2) - 2)$
28223 := $((((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2) + ((2 - 3)))$
28225 := $((((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2) + (T(T(2)) - (5)))$
28226 := $(2 - ((T(T(8)) + T(T(2))) \times (-2) \times T(6)))$
28227 := $(T(2) - (((T(T(8)) + T(T(2))) \times T(T(2))) \times (-7)))$
28228 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(8)) \times 2)) + ((2^8)))$
28242 := $(T(2) \times (((8 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(2))))$
28243 := $((-2) + T((T(8) - T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(4)) + (T(3))))$
28244 := $((((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2) + (T(4) + T(4)))$
28245 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T((8 \times 2)) \times T(4)) - T(5)))$
28246 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T((T(8)/T(2)))) \times T(T(4))))/6)$
28247 := $((T(T(2)) + T((T(8) - 2))) \times 47)$
28248 := $((((T(T(2)) \times T(T(8))) - T((T(2) \times T(4)))) \times 8)$
28249 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)) + 2)) \times (-4) + T(9))$
28251 := $(T((T(2) \times 8)) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(5)) + 1)))$
28252 := $((((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2) + T((5 + 2)))$
28253 := $((T(T(T(2))) + (8^{T(2)})) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3))))$
28254 := $((-2) + T(8)) \times (T(T(2)) - (-T(5)) \times T(T(4))))$
28255 := $((((T(T(T(T(2)))) + T((T(8) + T(T(T(2)))))) \times T(5)) - 5)$
28257 := $((((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2) + (5 + T(7)))$
28258 := $(-2) - ((T((T(8) + T(2))) + (5)) \times (-T(8)))$
28259 := $(-T(T((2 + 8))) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(5)) + 9)))$
28260 := $((T(T(2)) + T((T(8) - T(T(2)))) \times 60)$
28266 := $((2 - ((8^2) \times T(6))) \times T(6))$
28269 := $((((T(T(2)) + 8) \times T((T(2) \times T(6)))) + T(9))$
28271 := $((((T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) \times T((T(2) + T(7)))) - 1)$
28272 := $((2 + T((8 + 2))) \times T((T(7) + T(2))))$
28273 := $((((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2) + (T(7) + T(T(3))))$
28274 := $-((T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((8 \times T((T(2) \times T(7)))) - T(T(4))))$
28275 := $((T(T(2)) - T(((T(8) - T(2)) + T(7)))) \times (-T(5)))$
28278 := $(T(T(2)) - ((T(8) - T((T(2) \times T(7)))) \times 8))$
28279 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(8)^2) + (T(7) + T(T(9))))$
28284 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(T((-8) + T(T(T(2)))) + T((8 \times 4))))$
28287 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(T(8)) \times 2) + (8 + 7)))$
28288 := $((((T(T(2)) + T((T(8) + T(2)))) \times T(8)) - 8)$
28292 := $(2 - ((-82) \times T(T(9)))/T(2))$
28293 := $(T(2) - ((-82) \times T(T(9)))/3)$
28294 := $((T((T(T(2)) + T(8)))/T(2)) \times 94)$
28296 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T((T(8) + 2)) + T(9)) \times 6))$
28297 := $((((T(T(T(2))) \times 8)^2) + ((T(9) + T(7))))$
28298 := $(2 - ((T((T(8) + 2)) + T(9)) \times (-T(8))))$
28314 := $((-T(T(2))) + T((8 + T(T(3)))) \times T((1 + T(4))))$
28315 := $(T((-2) + T(8)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(15))))$
28321 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 8) \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(2))) + 1))$
28324 := $(2 \times (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4))))$
28325 := $((T(2) + (8^3)) \times T((2 \times 5)))$
28326 := $-((T((T(2) + T(8))) - ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(2))) \times T(T(6))))$
28329 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (8 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(2))) - T(9)))$
28334 := $(2 \times (((T(T(8)) + (T(3))) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(4))))$
28335 := $((T((2 \times 8)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T((-3) + T(5))))$
28337 := $((((T(T(T(2))) - 8) \times T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) - (T(T(7))))$
28342 := $((-T(T(2)) \times T(T(8))) - ((-T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(4))) + 2))$
28343 := $((-T((-2) + T(8))) - (-T(T(3)) \times T((T(4)) - 3)))$
28344 := $(2 \times ((8 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) + 4))$
28345 := $-((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (((-8) + T(T(3)))^4) + (T(5))))$
28346 := $((((T(2) + (8^3)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(6)))$
28349 := $-((T(T((2 + 8))) + (T(3^4) \times (-9)))$
28350 := $((T(T(2)) + T((T(8) - 3))) \times 50)$
28356 := $-((T(T(T(2))) + (T(8) + ((-3) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(6))))$
28357 := $(T(T(-((2 - 8))) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(5)))) - (T(T(7))))$
28358 := $(-28) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(5)))) - (T(T(8))))$

- 28359** := $((T(T(T(T(T(2)))) - 8)) - T((3 \times T(5)))) \times 9$
28364 := $((T(T(2)) + 8) \times (T((3 \times T(6))) + T(4)))$
28365 := $((T((2 + 8)) + T(3)) \times T((6 \times 5)))$
28368 := $((T(2) \times 8) \times (T(3) + T((6 \times 8))))$
28372 := $((((2 \times T(T(8))) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(7))) - T(T(2)))$
28374 := $((((2 \times T(T(8))) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(7))) - 4)$
28378 := $(-2) + ((T(8) - T(3)) \times T((7 + T(8))))$
28379 := $-(((T(-2) + T(8))) + (T(3))) - (T(7) \times T(T(9))))$
28383 := $((2 + T((T(8) + 3))) \times T(8) + T(T(T(3))))$
28386 := $((2 + T(8)) \times (T(38) + 6))$
28389 := $-((T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(8)) + ((T(3) - T(8))) \times (-T(9))))$
28391 := $((-28) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(9)))) - 1$
28392 := $((T(T(2)) + 8) \times (3 + (T(9)^2)))$
28395 := $((T(2) + ((T(8) + T(3)) \times T(9))) \times T(5))$
28397 := $(-((T(2) - 8) - ((T(T(3)) - T(T(9))) \times T(7)))$
28398 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T((8 + T(3))) \times T(9) + 8))$
28413 := $((T(2) + 8) \times T(41)) \times 3$
28416 := $(-(2^8) \times (T(T((4 + 1))) - T(T(6))))$
28419 := $-((T(T(T(2))) + (T((T((8 + 4) + 1)) \times (-9))))$
28422 := $((T(2) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(2) \times T(T(2)))$
28424 := $-((T(-((T(2) - T(8))) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
28425 := $((T(T(T(2))) - 8)^4 - T((T(T(T(2))) - 5))$
28427 := $-((T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((8^4) - 2) \times 7))$
28428 := $((2 \times T(T(8))) - T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))$
28432 := $((2 \times 8) \times ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(2)))$
28434 := $(T(2) - (T((T(8) - T(4))) \times (-3^4)))$
28435 := $((T(T(T(2))) - 8)^4 - (T(3) + T(T(5))))$
28438 := $(-2) - (T(8) \times (-T(4) - T((3 + T(8))))$
28441 := $((T(T(T(2))) - 8)^4 - (T(T((4 + 1))))$
28444 := $((T(2)^8) + (T(4) \times T(T(4)))) \times 4$
28445 := $((T(T(T(2))) - 8)^4 + (4 - T(T(5))))$
28446 := $((T(2) \times T((8 + T(4)))) \times T(T(4)) + T(T(6)))$
28448 := $(2 \times ((8 + T((4 + T(T(4)))) \times 8))$
28449 := $((T(2 \times 8)) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(4)))) \times 9$
28455 := $((T(T(2)) + T(((T(8) + T(4)) + T(5)))) \times T(5))$
28456 := $((T(T(T(2))) - 8)^4 + (-5) \times T(6))$
28462 := $(-((T(T(2)) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(6) - 2))$
28464 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(8)) \times 4) + T(64)))$
28465 := $((T((2 + T(8))) + 4) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))))$
28473 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8)))) \times (4 + T(7)) - T(T(T(3))))$
28476 := $((-2) - T(T(8)) - T(4)) \times (-7 \times 6))$
28477 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (-T(8) - ((-T(4)) \times T(T(7))) \times (-7)))$
28479 := $(T(2) - ((-T(84) + T(T(7))) \times 9))$
28482 := $((T(-((T(2) - T(8)))) + T((T(T(4)) + T(8)))) \times T(T(2)))$
28483 := $((T(T(T(2))) - 8)^4 - T((T(8)/3))$
28484 := $(-2) + (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(4))))/T(8)) - 4)$
28485 := $((T((T(T(2)) + T(T((8 - 4)))) + 8) \times T(5))$
28486 := $(2 + (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(4))))/T(8)) - 6))$
28487 := $(T(T(T(2))) - ((T(T(8)) - 4) \times (-T(8) + (7))))$
28488 := $(T(T(2)) + (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(4))))/T(8)) - 8))$
28489 := $((T(T(T(2))) - 8)^4 - ((8 \times 9))$
28494 := $-((T(T(2)) - (T((84 - 9)) \times T(4))))$
28495 := $((T(2) - 8) + (T(4) \times T((-T(9)) + T(T(5))))$
28497 := $((T(2) \times (-8)) + T((T(4) \times 9))) \times 7$
28499 := $-((T(T(T(2))) + (-8) \times (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(9) \times T(9))))$
28500 := $((T(T(T(2))) + T(8)) \times 500)$
28512 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 12))$
28514 := $((T(T(2)) \times T((-8) + T((T(5) - 1)))) - 4)$
28516 := $(-2) - (T((-8) + T((T(5) - 1))) \times (-6))$
28518 := $(T(T(2)) \times T((-8) + T(((5 + 1) + 8))))$
28524 := $-((T(T(T(2))) + ((T(8) \times T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
28527 := $((T(2) - T(8)) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 7))$
28528 := $((-T(T(2))) + T((-T(8)) + T(T(5)))) + 2) \times 8$
28533 := $(T(T(-((T(2) - 8))) + ((T(T(5)) + 3) \times T(T(T(3))))$
28534 := $(-((T(T(2)) - (8 \times (T(5)^3))) + T(T(T(4))))$
28536 := $((T(2) + T((T((8 + 5)) + T(3)))) \times 6)$
28538 := $((2 + T(8)) \times (-5) - (T(T(3)) \times (-T(8))))$
28539 := $((T((2 \times 8)) + T(5)) \times T(T(3)) \times 9)$
28540 := $((T(T(-((2 - 8)))) \times T(T(5))) + (T(40)))$
28541 := $-((T(T(T(2))) - ((8 + 5)^4 + 1))$
28542 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(8)) - 5) + (4^{T(T(2))}))$
28543 := $((T(2) + ((8 + 5)^4) - T(T(3)))$
28544 := $((2 - T((-T(8)) + T(T(5)))) \times (-4 + 4))$
28545 := $((T((2 \times 8)) \times T((5 \times 4))) - T(5))$
28546 := $(T(T(2)) + (((8 + 5)^4) - T(6))$
28547 := $-((T(T(T(2))) - (((8 + 5)^4 + 7)))$
28548 := $(((-T(2)) + T(T(8))) + T(T(5))) + T(4)) \times T(8)$
28549 := $-((T(2) - (((8 + 5)^4) - 9))$
28552 := $((-2) + T(T(8))) \times (T(5) + T((5 + 2)))$
28553 := $((2 \times (-8) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(5)))) - T(T(T(3))))$
28554 := $(-T(T(2))) + (8 \times T((T(T((5/5))) \times 4)))$
28555 := $((T((2 \times 8)) \times T((5 + T(5)))) - 5)$
28556 := $((T((2 \times 8)) - T(5)) \times (5 + T(T(6))))$
28557 := $(-T(2) - (-8) \times T(((T(5)/5) \times T(7))))$
28573 := $((-2) + T(T(8))) \times (T(5) + T(7)) + T(T(3))$
28574 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (8 - (((T(5) - T(7))^4)))$
28575 := $((2 - T(8)) \times T(T(5))) \times (-7) + (T(5))$
28576 := $((2^8) + T(T(5))) \times 76$
28579 := $(-((T(28) - 5)) + (T(7) \times T(T(9))))$
28581 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (T((T(8) + T(5))) + (T(8) - 1))$
28582 := $(T(T(T(2))) + ((8 + 5)^{8/2}))$
28583 := $(2 - ((-8) \times T((T(T(5)) - T(8)))) - (T(T(3))))$

$$\begin{aligned} 28584 &:= (((T(T(2)) \times T(8)) \times T(T(5))) - (T(T(8)) \times (-4))) \\ 28585 &:= ((T(2) + (8^5)) - T(T(8 + 5))) \\ 28586 &:= (2 \times (-8) - ((-T(5) - T(T(8))) \times T(6))) \\ 28587 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(8))) + (-T(5) + (T(8) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 28588 &:= (28 - (T((T(T(5)) - T(8))) \times (-8))) \\ 28589 &:= (((2 - T((-T(8) + T(T(5)))) \times (-8) + T(9)) \\ 28590 &:= (((T(T(T(T(2)))) + 8) \times T(T(5))) - (90)) \\ 28594 &:= (-((T(T(2)) \times T(T(8)) - (5 \times T(T(9)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 28599 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) + ((T(T(8)) + (T(5) - T(9))) \times (-T(9)))) \\ 28615 &:= ((-2) + T(T(8))) - (T(T(6)) \times (-1) - T(T(5))) \\ 28617 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)) \times (-T((6 - 1) + T(7)))) \\ 28623 &:= (T((T(T(2)) + T(8))) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(2 + 3)))) \\ 28625 &:= ((2 + T((T(8) + (6)))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 28626 &:= ((T((2 \times 8)) + T(T(6))) \times T((2 \times 6))) \\ 28627 &:= (-((T(2) - ((8 \times T(6))^2)) + T(T(7))) \\ 28629 &:= (((T((2 \times T(8))) \times (-T(6)))/(-2) + T(T(9))) \\ 28632 &:= -((T(T(2)) + (T(T(8)) \times (-T((6 + 3) - 2)))) \\ 28635 &:= ((-2) + (T((-8) + T(6))) \times T(T(3))) \times T(5) \\ 28636 &:= (-2) - ((-T(T(8))) \times T((T(6) + T(T(3))))/T(6)) \\ 28638 &:= (-((2 - ((8 \times 6) - 3))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 28642 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T((T(8) - T(6)) + 4))) - 2) \\ 28644 &:= (((T(T(2)) + T(T(8))) - (T(6))) \times 44) \\ 28645 &:= (((T(2) + T(T((-8) + T(6)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) \\ 28646 &:= (2 + ((T((T(8) - T(6))) + 4) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 28648 &:= (((T(2) + 8) + T((T(6) \times 4))) \times 8) \\ 28652 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-8 - (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(2)))) \\ 28653 &:= -((T(T(2)) - ((8 + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(3)))) \\ 28654 &:= ((2 + 8) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) + 4))) \\ 28656 &:= ((T((2 \times 8) \times 6) + T(T(5))) \times 6) \\ 28665 &:= (T(-((2 - 8))) \times (T(6) \times 65)) \\ 28667 &:= (2 - ((-T(8)) + T(T(6))) \times (T(6) \times (-7))) \\ 28672 &:= (((2^{-8+T(6)}) \times 7)/2) \\ 28674 &:= (2 \times (((T(T(8)) \times T(6)) + T(T(7))) - T(T(4)))) \\ 28677 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-((T(T(8)) + T(T(6))) - T(7)))/(-7)) \\ 28678 &:= (-2) - ((8 + T(T(6))) \times (-T((7 + 8)))) \\ 28679 &:= ((T(T(2)) + 8) - ((T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \times (-T(9)))) \\ 28692 &:= (((T(T(2)) + T(86)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 28694 &:= (-((T(T(2)) + ((T(T(8)) + (6)) \times (-T(9)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 28695 &:= -((T((T(T(2)) + 8) - ((T(T(6)) + 9) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 28696 &:= (T((2 \times 8)) \times ((T(T(6)) + T(T(9)))/6)) \\ 28704 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8)))) \times (T(7) - (0 - 4))) \\ 28722 &:= (((T(T(2)) \times (-T((8 \times 7)))) + 2) \times (-T(2))) \\ 28724 &:= ((2 + T(T(8))) \times (7 + T((2 \times 4)))) \\ 28725 &:= (((2 + T(87))/2) \times T(5)) \\ 28726 &:= (-2) - ((T((8 \times 7)) \times T(2)) \times (-6)) \\ 28728 &:= ((T(2) \times T((8 \times 7))) \times (-2 - 8)) \\ 28729 &:= -((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-T(8) - (T(7) \times (-2) + T(T(9)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28731 &:= (T(2) \times ((T((8 \times 7)) \times T(3)) + 1)) \\ 28734 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (T(8) + T(((7 \times T(3)) + T(T(4)))))) \\ 28741 &:= -((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (8 + (-T(7)) \times T(T((4) - 1)))))) \\ 28742 &:= ((T((T(T(2)) \times 8)) \times T(7)) - T(T((4) + T(2)))) \\ 28743 &:= (T(((2 + T(8)) + T(7))) \times (T(4) + 3)) \\ 28746 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((87 \times T(T(4))) + (6))) \\ 28749 &:= -((T(T(2)) + (((T(T(8)) + T(7)) - T(T(4))) \times (-T(9)))) \\ 28752 &:= (2 \times ((T(8) \times T(T(7))) + (T(T(5)) \times (-2)))) \\ 28755 &:= (T(2) \times (((T(T(8)) - T(7)) \times T(5)) + (T(5)))) \\ 28756 &:= (T((T(T(T(2))) - 8) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(5) \times (-6)))) \\ 28758 &:= (((T(T(2)) \times T(T(8))) \times 7) + T(T(5))) + T(T(8)) \\ 28764 &:= (((T(T(2)) \times T(8)) - T(7)) \times T((T(6) - 4))) \\ 28765 &:= ((2 \times ((T(8) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(6)))) - (5)) \\ 28767 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 8) \times (T((7 \times 6)/7)) \\ 28768 &:= (((T(T(2)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(7))) + (6)) \times 8) \\ 28770 &:= (-((T(2) - 8) + T(T(7))) \times 70) \\ 28771 &:= (-T((2 + 8)) + (T(T(7)) \times 71)) \\ 28774 &:= -((T(T(2)) + ((T(8) + (T(T(7)) \times 7)) \times (-T(4)))) \\ 28777 &:= -((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (((T(8) \times T(7)) + T(7)) \times T(7)))) \\ 28779 &:= ((T(2) - 8) + (T(7) \times (-7) + T(T(9)))) \\ 28782 &:= (((T(2) + T((8 \times 7))) \times T(8))/2) \\ 28783 &:= (((-2) + T(T(8))) \times (7 + T(8))) + T(T(T(3))) \\ 28784 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(8))) + (T(T(7)))) \times (8/4)) \\ 28785 &:= -((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (8 \times (T(7) - T(85)))) \\ 28786 &:= (2 \times (((T(8) \times T(T(7))) + 8) - T(T(6)))) \\ 28788 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + T((8 + 8)))) \\ 28789 &:= (-T(2) + (-8) \times (T(T(7)) - T(89))) \\ 28791 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times ((-8) + T((7 + T(9)))) + 1) \\ 28794 &:= ((28 \times (-7) + T(T(9))) + T(4)) \\ 28795 &:= (((-2) - T(T(8))) + T(7)) \times (-T(9)) - (5)) \\ 28796 &:= (-((2 \times 8) + (T(7) \times (T(T(9)) - 6)))) \\ 28797 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + (-8) + ((-7) + T(T(9))) \times T(7)) \\ 28798 &:= ((T(T(2)) + T(8)) + (T(7) \times (T(T(9)) - 8))) \\ 28799 &:= (-T((2 \times 8)) + ((T(7) \times T(T(9))) - T(9))) \\ 28809 &:= (((T(2) + T(8)) - T(80)) \times (-9)) \\ 28812 &:= (28 \times (T(T(8 + 1))) - T(T(2))) \\ 28815 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8)) \times (-8 + 1))) \times (-5)) \\ 28824 &:= ((-2) + T(T(8))) + ((8^{T(2)}) \times T(T(4))) \\ 28826 &:= (T(28) \times (8 + (T(2) \times T(6)))) \\ 28827 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) - (8 \times (T(8) + T((T(2) \times T(7)))))) \\ 28828 &:= (((T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(8)) \times (T(8) \times T(2))) - 8) \\ 28830 &:= (-((2 - (8 \times 8)) \times T(30)) \\ 28833 &:= (((T(T(2)) + T(8)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(3)))) - T(T(3))) \\ 28834 &:= (T(T((T(T(T(2))) - 8))) + (8 \times T(T((3 \times 4)))) \\ 28836 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(8)) \times (T(8) \times (-3 - 6))) \\ 28837 &:= -((T(-((T(T(2)) - T(8))) + (T(T((-8) + T(T(3)))) \times (-7)))) \\ 28839 &:= (((2 \times T(T(8))) - 8) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

- 28840** := ((T((2+8)) + T(T(8))) × 40)
28841 := ((-((T(2) - T(8))) × (-T(T(8))) + T(T(T(4)))) - 1)
28842 := (T((T(2) + 8)) × ((8 × T(T(4))) - T(2)))
28845 := ((T((2 + T(8))) + (T(T(8)) × (-4))) × (-T(5)))
28846 := (-2) + (8 × (T(8) + T((4 × T(6))))))
28847 := (T(T(T(2))) + (((8 + 8) + T(T(4))) × T(T(7))))
28848 := -((T(T(2)) + ((-T(8)) × T((T(8) + (4)))) + T(T(8))))
28851 := -((T(T(T(2))) + (-T(8)) × (T(T(8)) + T((T(5) + 1))))))
28852 := ((-2) - T(T(8))) - (-T(8)) × (T(T(5)/T(2)))
28853 := ((T((T(T(2)) + T(8))) × (T(T(8)) + (5)))/T(T(3)))
28854 := ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) × (-8) + (5 × T(4)))
28859 := -((T(T(T(2))) + (-8) × (T(85) - T(9))))
28864 := (((T(T(2)) + T(8)) × (T(T(8)) + (T(6)))) + T(4))
28867 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(8)) + (T(T((-8) + T(6)))) × (-7)))
28869 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(8)) × ((8 - 6) - T(9))))
28872 := (2 × (T(8) + (T((8 + 7)²)))
28875 := ((T(2) - T(8)) × (-875))
28887 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(8) + T(8)) × (-8) + T(T(7))))
28889 := -((T(((2 + 8) + T(8))) - (T(T(8)) × T(9))))
28905 := (((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(8)))) × (-T(9))) + (0 - T(T(5))))
28908 := ((T(2) + 8) × T((9 × 08)))
28911 := (T(2) + (T((8 × 9) × 11))
28914 := (T(T(2)) - (T((8 × 9)) × (-1) - T(4)))
28917 := ((T((2 + 8)) - T(91)) × (-7))
28922 := ((28 × (T(T(9)) - 2)) - 2)
28923 := (T(T(2)) - ((T(8) + T(T(9))) × (-T(2)³)))
28924 := (28 × (9 + (2^{T(4)})))
28925 := ((28 × T(T(9))) - T((2 × 5)))
28926 := (T(2) - ((T(8) × (-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(6)))
28927 := (T(2) - (((-8) + T(T(9))) + T(T(2))) × (-T(7)))
28928 := (-((2 × 8)) - ((-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(8)))
28929 := (((T(2) + T(T(8))) × T(9)) - T((T(2) + T(9))))
28932 := (-T(2)) - ((T(T(8)) × (-T(9))) + T(T(3²)))
28933 := (-2) - ((T(T(8)) × (-T(9))) + T(T(3 × 3)))
28934 := (((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(8)))) × (-T(9))) - T((3 + T(4))))
28935 := (((T(2) × 8) × T(T(9))) + T((T(3) × T(5))))
28936 := (-2) - ((T(8) × (-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(3)))) + 6)
28937 := (T(T(T(2))) - ((T(8) × (-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(3)))) + (T(7))))
28938 := ((28 × T(T(9))) - (T(3) + T(8)))
28939 := (-2) - (((T(T(8)) × (-T(9))) - (T(3))) + T(T(9)))
28940 := ((28 × T(T(9))) - 40)
28941 := ((T(2) + T((8 × 9))) × (T(4) + 1))
28942 := ((-2) - T(8)) + (T(T(9)) × T((T(4) - T(2))))
28944 := ((28 × T(T(9))) - T((4 + 4)))
28946 := (((28 × T(T(9))) - T(T(4))) + (T(6)))
28947 := ((T(2) - T(8)) + (T(T(9)) × (4 × 7)))
28948 := ((28 × T(T(9))) - (4 × 8))
28952 := ((28 × T(T(9))) - T((5 + 2)))
28955 := ((28 × T(T(9))) - (5 × 5))
28956 := ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)) × T(9))) - T(T((T(5) - (6))))
28957 := ((28 × T(T(9))) - (-5) + T(7))
28959 := ((28 × T(T(9))) - T((T(5) - 9)))
28962 := ((28 × T(T(9))) - (T(6) - T(2)))
28963 := (-2) - ((-T(8)) × (T(T(9)) - T(T(6)))) - T(T(3)))
28964 := ((28 × T(T(9))) - (6 + T(4)))
28965 := (T(T(2)) - ((-T(8)) × (T(T(9)) - T(T(6)))) - (T(5)))
28967 := ((28 × T(T(9))) - (6 + 7))
28968 := (T((2 × 8)) × (T(9) + (T(6) × 8)))
28970 := (-((2 + 8)) - (T(T(9)) × (-T((7 + 0))))
28971 := (((-2) - T(8)) - T(T(9))) × (-T(7) - 1))
28972 := ((T((T(2) + T(8))) × 9) + ((T(7)^{T(2)})))
28973 := (((28 × T(T(9))) - T(7)) + T(T(3)))
28974 := ((T(T(2)) + T((8 × 9))) × (7 + 4))
28975 := ((T(((T(2) - 8) × (-9))) × T(7)) - (5))
28976 := (2 - ((T((T(8) + 9)) × (-T(7))) + (6)))
28977 := (-T(2)) - (T(((8 + 9) + T(7))) × (-T(7)))
28978 := (T(T(2)) - ((T((T(8) + 9)) × (-T(7)) + 8))
28979 := (-((2 + 8)) + ((T(T(9)) × T(7)) + 9))
28992 := ((T((-2) + T(8))) + 9) × (T(9) + T(2))
28994 := ((T(T(2)) + 8) × (-9) + T((9 + T(T(4))))))
28995 := ((T(((2 × 8) - 9)) × T(T(9))) + (T(5)))
28997 := (((T(T(2)) - T(T(8))) × (-T(9))) - T((9 + T(7))))
28998 := ((-2) - (-8) × T(9)) × (T(9) + T(8))
29028 := (T(2) + (T(9) × ((0 - T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8))))))
29047 := (-T(2)) - ((T(90) + T(T(4))) × (-7))
29074 := (((T(2) + T(T(9))) × T(07)) + T(4))
29077 := ((T(T(2)) - (T(90) × (-7))) + T(T(7)))
29084 := ((T(-((T(2) - 90))) × 8) - T(T(T(4))))
29106 := (T((-2) + T(9) + T(10)) × 6)
29115 := (((T(T(2)) × (-T(9))) + T(T(11))) × T(5))
29118 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(91) + 1) + T(T(8))))
29124 := ((2 × 9) × (T(12) + T(T(T(4))))))
29127 := (T(T(T(2))) × ((T(T(9)) + 1) + T((-2) + T(7))))
29133 := ((2 - T((T(9) + 1))) × (-3³))
29139 := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) × T((1 + T(3)))) - 9)
29145 := (((T(2) × T(T(9 - 1))) - T(T(4))) × T(5))
29146 := (((2 × 9) + 1) × (T(T(T(4))) - 6))
29148 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) × T(-((1⁴) - 8)))
29158 := (-2) - (-9) × T((T(-((1 - 5))) × 8))
29166 := (T(T(2)) × ((9 + 1) - (-T(6)) × T(T(6))))
29169 := (((T(2) × T(T(9))) + T(16)) × 9)
29172 := (T((T(T(2)) + T(9))) × (1 + (7 × T(2))))
29173 := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + 1) × T(7)) - 3)
29176 := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + 1) × (7 + T(6)))

- 29178** := $(2 \times (9 - ((1 - T(T(7))) \times T(8))))$
29181 := $(T(T(T(2))) - (-9 \times T(-(1 - 81))))$
29187 := $((T(2) \times 9) \times T((18 + T(7))))$
29189 := $(2 - (T((T(9) + 1)) \times (-T(8) - 9)))$
29193 := $((T(2) \times 9) \times T((1 + T(9)))) + T(3))$
29194 := $(-T((2 + 9))) + (19 \times T(T(T(4))))$
29197 := $((T(T(2)) - (T(91) - 9)) \times (-7))$
29205 := $(T((T(T(2)) \times 9)) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(05))))$
29211 := $((T(T(T(2))) + 9)^{T(2)} + (T(T(11))))$
29213 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) - T((1 + T(3))))$
29214 := $((-T(2)) \times T(T(9))) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (1 - T(T(T(4))))))$
29216 := $((-2) - T((T(9) + T(T(2)))) \times (-1) - T(6))$
29220 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) - T(T(T(2 + 0))))$
29221 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) - T(T(T(2)))) + 1$
29222 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) + 2) - T(T(T(2)))$
29223 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) - (T(2) \times T(3)))$
29224 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(9) + T(T(2)))) + T((-T(2)) + T(T(4))))$
29225 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) - T(T(T(2)))) + 5$
29226 := $(T(T(2)) + ((T((9 \times 2))^2) - T(6)))$
29227 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) - (2 \times 7))$
29228 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) - T(T(T(2)))) + 8$
29229 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) - T(2) - 9)$
29231 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) - T((3 + 1)))$
29232 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) - (3^2))$
29234 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) - (3 + 4))$
29235 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) - T(T(3))) + T(5))$
29237 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) + ((3 - 7)))$
29238 := $(-T(2)) + (T((9 \times 2))^{-T(3)+8})$
29240 := $(2 + (9^{T(2)})) \times 40$
29241 := $(T((2 \times 9))^{-2+4 \times 1})$
29242 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) + (4) - T(2))$
29243 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) - (4) + T(3))$
29244 := $((T(T(T(2))) + ((9^{T(2)}) \times T(4))) \times 4)$
29245 := $((-2) + T((9 - T(2)))) \times T(T(T(4))) - T(5)$
29247 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) + T(-(4 - 7)))$
29248 := $(-2) + (T(9) \times (-((2^4) + T(T(8))))$
29261 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) + T(6) - 1)$
29262 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) + T(T(6/2)))$
29264 := $((-2) + T((T(9) - 2))) \times (T(6) + T(4))$
29265 := $((T((2 \times 9))^{T(2)} + T(6)) \times 5)$
29267 := $((T(T(T(2))) + 92) \times (T(T(6)) + T(7)))$
29268 := $((T(2) - (T(9) \times T(2)) \times (-6)) \times T(8))$
29272 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) + T(7) + T(2))$
29273 := $((T(T(2)) + (T(T(9)) + 2) \times T(7)) + T(T(T(3))))$
29274 := $(-((T(T(T(2))) - (T(9)/T(2)) \times T((7 + T(T(4))))))$
29275 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - (((T(T(9)) - 2) \times (-T(7))) - T(T(5))))$
29278 := $((-2) + (T(92) \times 7)) - T(T(8))$
29279 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) - (7) + T(9))$
29280 := $((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(9))/(-T(2)))) \times 80$
29283 := $((T((2 \times 9))^2) + T(8) + T(3))$
29285 := $(2 - (-((T(9) - 2)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(5))))$
29286 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(9) \times T(2)) \times T(8)) + T(6))$
29287 := $(-((T(T(2)) + 9) - (T(T((T(T(2))) - 8))) \times (-7))$
29288 := $((-2) + T(T(9))) + T((2 \times T(8))) \times 8$
29289 := $(-T(T(2)) + ((-T(9)/T(2))) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9))$
29292 := $(T(T(2)) + (T(9) + (T((2 \times 9))^2)))$
29295 := $((T(T(2)) + 9) \times T((2 + T(9) + T(5))))$
29297 := $(2 - (T((9 + T(T(2)))) \times (-9 \times 7)))$
29298 := $(T(2) - (T(9) \times ((T(T(2)) + 9) - T(T(8))))$
29315 := $((2^9) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(-(1 - 5)))$
29316 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + (T(3))) \times T((1 + 6))$
29318 := $((T((-2) + T(9))) \times 31) - 8$
29319 := $(29 \times (T(T(3)) + T((-1) + T(9))))$
29322 := $((T(T(T(2)))) + (T((93 + T(2)))) \times T(T(2)))$
29325 := $(T(2) - T((T(9) + 3))) \times (-25)$
29326 := $(T((-2) + T(9))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(-(2 - 6)))$
29328 := $(T((2 + T(9))) \times ((T(3) \times T(2)) + 8))$
29337 := $(T(T(T(2))) - ((T(T(9)) + (T(3) + T(3))) \times (-T(7))))$
29339 := $((T(2) - (T(9)^3))/(-3) - T(T(9)))$
29343 := $(T(T(2)) + ((-9) + T((T(3) + T(4)))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
29344 := $(-T(T(2))) - ((9 + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) \times (-T(4)))$
29346 := $((-2) \times T(T(9))) + (T((T(3) + T(4))) \times T(T(6))))$
29347 := $(T(2) - ((T(T(9)) + (3 + T(4))) \times (-T(7))))$
29349 := $(T(2) \times (((T(T(9)) - 3) + T(T(4))) \times 9))$
29352 := $(2 \times ((T(9) + T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5))^2)))$
29355 := $((-2) - ((-9) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5)))) \times T(5)$
29358 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((9 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (-T(5) - T(T(8))))$
29367 := $(T(2) \times (T(9) - ((-3) - T(6)) \times T(T(7))))$
29368 := $((T(T(2)) \times (T(9) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(6)))) - 8)$
29373 := $(-((T(T(2)) - ((T(T(9)) + (T(3))) \times T(7)))) + T(T(T(3))))$
29376 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T(9) + (T((3 \times 7)) \times T(6))))$
29378 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 9)/3 \times T(T(7))) - (T(T(8)))$
29379 := $((T((T(2) \times 9)) + T(T(3))) + (T(7) \times T(T(9))))$
29382 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(9)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(8))))/(-2))$
29385 := $((T(T(2)) + T(((9 \times T(3)) + 8))) \times T(5))$
29387 := $(2 - (T(9) \times ((T(3) - T(T(8))) + (7))))$
29388 := $(T(2) - (T(9) \times ((T(T(3)) - 8) - T(T(8))))$
29394 := $(-T(T(2)) + ((-T(9) + T(T(3))) \times T((T(9) + (4))))))$
29397 := $(-T(2)) - (((T(9)/(-3)) - T(T(9))) \times T(7))$
29398 := $((-29) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(9)))) - 8$
29408 := $((T(T(T(2))) + T((T(9) + 40))) \times 8)$

- 29414** := ((T(T(T(2))) + T((9 + T(T(4)))) × 14)
29415 := (((2 × (T(T(9)) - T(T(4)))) + 1) × T(5))
29424 := (((T(T(2)) × T((T(9) + (4)))) + T(T(2))) × 4)
29425 := ((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(9))) - ((T(T(T(4))) - 2) × (-5)))
29427 := (-T(2)) - ((T(T(9)) + T(T(4))) × (-27))
29428 := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + T(4)) × 28)
29432 := (2 - ((T(T(9)) + T(T(4))) × (-3^{T(2)})))
29433 := (T(2) - ((T(T(9)) + T(T(4))) × (-3³)))
29434 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((9 + T(4)) × (-3) + T(T(T(4))))))
29435 := (29 × ((T(4)³) + T(5)))
29436 := (T(T(2)) - ((T(T(9)) + T(T(4))) × (-T(3) + T(6))))
29437 := ((T(2) × T(9)) - (T(T((T(4) + 3))) × (-7)))
29439 := ((T((T(2) × 9)) × T((4 × 3))) - T(9))
29440 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(9)) - T(T(T(4)))) × 40)
29442 := (((-((T(2)⁹) + T(T(4)))/(-4)) × T(T(2)))
29444 := (-T(T(2))) - ((9 + T(4)) × (-T(4)) - T(T(T(4))))))
29445 := ((T((T(2 + 9)) - (4))) + T(4)) × T(5)
29446 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-T(9)) - (-T(4)) × T((T(T(4)) + (T(6))))))
29448 := ((-2) + T(((9 × 4) + 4))) × T(8)
29449 := ((T(T(T(2))) × 9) + (T(T(T(4))) × (T(4) + 9)))
29456 := (((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(9))) + T(T(T(4)))) × 56)
29457 := ((2 + T(T(9))) + ((T(T(4)) + (T(5))) × T(T(7))))
29458 := ((T(T(2 + 9))) + T(T(4))) × (5 + 8)
29463 := (((T((T(2) + T(9))) - (4)) + T(T(6))) × T(T(3)))
29465 := ((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(9))) - ((T(T(T(4))) + 6) × (-5)))
29466 := ((T(T((T(2) + 9))) + (T((T(4) × 6)))) × 6)
29469 := ((T(T(T(2))) × ((T(9) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(6)))) + T(T(9)))
29470 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + T((9 + T(4)))) × 70)
29472 := ((T(T(T(2))) - T(9)) × (-T(4)) + (T(T(7)) × (-T(2))))
29474 := ((T((T(2) + 9)) × T((T(T(4)) - T(7)))) - T(4))
29475 := (((T(2) + 9) + T((T(T(4)) + (7)))) × T(5))
29477 := (((-T(2)) + T(T(9 + 4))) + T(7)) × 7)
29478 := (((T(T(2)) - T(T(9))) × (-4 × 7)) + T(T(8)))
29479 := -((T(T(2)) + (((T(T(9)) + T(T(4))) × (-T(7))) + T(T(9))))))
29481 := (T(T(2)) + (T(9) × ((-T(4)) + T(T(8)) - 1)))
29482 := ((T((T(2) × 9)) × T((4 + 8))) - 2)
29484 := (T((2 × (9 + 4))) × 84)
29485 := (((2 + 9⁴) - T(T(8))) × 5)
29487 := (T(2) - ((T(T(9)) + (T(4) + 8)) × (-T(7))))
29491 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((-9) - T(4)) × T(T((9 + 1))))
29493 := (T(2) × (((T(T(9)) + T(T(4))) × 9) + T(T(3))))
29496 := (((T(T(2)) × T(T(9))) × 4) + T(96))
29499 := -((T(T(T(2))) + (T(9) × (T(4) - T((T(9) - 9))))))
29510 := (((T(T(2)) × T(T(9))) × 5) - T(T(10)))
29517 := (-T(2)) - (T((T(9) - (5))) × (-T((1 + 7))))
29518 := (-2) + (T((T(9) - (5))) × T((1 × 8)))
29520 := ((T(T(2)) × T((T(9) - (5)))) × T(T((2 + 0))))
29521 := (((T(T(2)) × T((T(9) - (5)))) × T(T(2))) + 1)
29522 := (((-((2 - (9⁵))) - T(2))/2)
29523 := (((T(2) + (9⁵))/2) - 3)
29525 := ((T((T(2) + T(9))) + (5)) × 25)
29526 := (((T(2) + (9⁵)) × T(2))/6)
29527 := (((T(T(2)) × T((T(9) - (5)))) × T(T(2))) + (7))
29528 := (((T(T(2)) × T((T(9) - (5)))) × T(T(2))) + 8)
29529 := ((T((T(2) × 9)) × T((T(5) - T(2)))) + T(9))
29532 := (((T(2)⁹) + (5)) × 3)/2)
29534 := -((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-T(T(9))) - ((T(T(5))/(-T(3))) × T(T(T(4))))))
29535 := (((T(T(2)) × T((T(9) - (5)))) × T(3)) + (T(5)))
29536 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(9)) × T((T(5) + 3)))))/6)
29537 := (-T(2)) - ((T(T(9)) + (T(T(5))/T(3))) × (-T(7)))
29538 := (2 × ((T(T(9)) × T(5)) + (T(T(3)) × (-T(8))))
29544 := -((T((T(2) + T(9))) - (T(T(5)) × (4⁴)))
29545 := ((-2) + T((-9 + T(5))) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(5)))
29547 := (T(T(T(2))) × ((-9) + T((5 × 4)) × 7))
29548 := (T(-(2 - 9)) - T((-T(5)) + T(T(4))) × (-T(8)))
29552 := ((2 + T((T(9) + T(5)))) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(T(2))))))
29553 := ((T(2) + T((T(9) + T(5)))) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(T(3))))))
29556 := ((T(T(2)) + T((T(9) + T(5)))) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(6))))
29559 := (-T(T(2))) - ((-9) + T(T((T(5))/T(5)))) × (-T(9)))
29562 := (T(T(T(2))) - ((-9) - T(T(5))) × (T(T(6)) - 2))
29563 := (((T(2) × (9⁵)) + T(T(6)))/T(3))
29564 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (9 + T(T(5)))) - (T(T(6)) + (4)))
29565 := (((2 × T(T(9))) - T(T(5))) + (T(6))) × T(5)
29566 := (-2) - (((-9) - T(T(5))) × T(T(6))) + T(T(6)))
29567 := (T(2) - ((-T(9)) × T((T(5) + T(6)))) + T(T(7)))
29568 := (T((2 + 9)) × (56 × 8))
29574 := ((2 × 9) × (T(57) - T(4)))
29575 := (T((T(T(T(2))) + (9 - 5))) × T((T(7) - T(5))))
29578 := (-2) - ((T(T(9)) - (T(5))) × (7 - T(8)))
29580 := ((T(T(2)) + T(9)) × 580)
29582 := (2 - ((T(T(9)) - (T(5))) × (8 + T(T(T(2))))))
29583 := (T(2) - ((T(T(9)) - (T(5))) × (-8 - T(T(3))))))
29586 := (((2 + T((T(9) - (5)))) × T(8)) - (6))
29589 := ((T((T(29)/5)) × 8) - T(T(9)))
29592 := (2 × ((T(T(9)) × T(5)) - ((9^{T(2)})))
29595 := ((29 × (-T(5)) + T(T(9))) + (T(5)))
29597 := ((2 + T(T(9))) - ((T(5) - T(T(9))) × T(7)))
29598 := (T((T(2) + 9)) + (T((-5) + T(9))) × T(8))
29617 := (T(T(T(2))) - ((T(T(9)) + (T(6) + 1)) × (-T(7))))
29619 := ((T(T((T(2) + 9))) + (T((T(6) - 1)))) × 9)
29624 := (((2 + T(T(9))) + (T(6))) × T((T(2) + (4))))
29625 := ((T(29) + T(T(T(6 - 2)))) × T(5))
29627 := (T(2) - ((T(T(9)) + (T(6) + 2)) × (-T(7))))

- 29628 := ((T(2) + T((T(9+6)/T(2)))) × T(8))
29629 := ((((-T(2)) + T(T(9)))/6)² + T(9))
29634 := (-T((T(2) + T(9)))) - (T(T((6 + T(3)))) × (-T(4)))
29637 := (((-T(2)) + T(T(9))) - T(T(6))) × 37
29638 := (-2) - (T((T(9) - (6))) × (-38))
29642 := (((T(2) × T(9)) × T(T(6))) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(2)
29643 := ((T(2) + T(9+6)) × (T(4) + T(T(3))))
29644 := -((T(T((T(2) + 9))) + (T((-T(6)) + T(T(4)))) × (-T(T(4))))))
29645 := (((T(T(T(2)))) + (9 × T(T(6)))) × T(T(T(4)))/T(T(5)))
29646 := ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(9 + T(6)))) × (T(T(4)) + (6)))
29647 := ((T((2 × 9))⁶⁻⁴) + T(T(7)))
29648 := ((T(-T(T(2)) - T(9))) + (T((T(6) + T(T(4)))))) × 8
29652 := (((T(2) + T(T(9))) + (T(6))) × T((5 + 2)))
29653 := ((-2) - T(9)) - (-6 × T((T(5) - T(T(3))))))
29655 := ((T(2) × T(9)) + ((T(T(6)) + (T(5))) × T(T(5))))
29657 := (2 - (-T(9)) × (T((T(6) + T(5))) - (7)))
29658 := ((2 × T(9)) + (T(T(6)) × (T(T(5)) + 8)))
29664 := (T(T(2)) × (9 + (T(6) × (T(T(6)) + (4))))))
29673 := (((T(2) + T(T(9))) + (T(6))) × T(7)) + T(T(3)))
29679 := (((T(T(2)) - T(T(9))) + (6)) × (-T(7))) + T(T(9)))
29682 := ((T(T(2)) + T(9)) × (T(6) + T((T(8) - T(2))))))
29684 := -((T(T(2)) - ((T(9) × (-6) + T(T(8)))) - T(4)))
29685 := (((2 × T(T(9))) - T((T(6) - 8))) × T(5))
29687 := -((T(T(2)) + ((T(9) × (6 - T(T(8)))) + (7))))
29688 := (-T(2)) - ((T(9) × (T(6) - T(T(8)))) - T(T(8)))
29689 := (-((2 + 9)) - ((-6) + T(T(8))) × (-T(9)))
29694 := -((T(T(2)) + (T(9) × (6 - T(9 × 4))))))
29695 := ((T(T(2)) × T((T(9) + ((6 × 9)))) - (5))
29698 := (-2) - ((T(9) + T((-6) + T(9))) × (-T(8)))
29711 := ((2 + 9) × T((7 + T(11))))
29712 := (((2 × T(T(9))) + T(T(7))) × 12)
29714 := (T(2) - (T((T(9) + T(7))) × (-1) - T(4)))
29715 := ((T(T(T(2)))) + (T(9) + (7))) × T((-1) + T(5)))
29717 := (T(T(2)) - (-((T(9) + T(7))) × (1 + T(T(7))))))
29722 := (((T(T(T(2))) × T(9)) + (T(T(7)))) × 22)
29724 := (T(T(2)) × (T((97 + 2)) + (4)))
29728 := (((T(2) + T(T(9))) × T(7)) - 2) + T(T(8)))
29732 := (((2 + 9) × T(73)) + T(T(T(2))))
29733 := (((2 + T((T(9) + T(7)))) × T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))
29734 := -((T(T(T(2))) + ((-T(9)) - T((T(7) + 3))) × T(T(4))))
29736 := ((T((2 + 97)) + T(3)) × 6)
29737 := (T(29) - (-7 × T(T(T(3) + (7))))))
29738 := ((2 + (T(T(9)) × T(7))) - (T(T(3)) × (-T(8))))
29739 := (T((2 × 9)) - (-T(7)) × (T(T(3)) + T(T(9))))
29743 := ((T(T(2)) × T(97)) + T((T(T(4)) - (T(3))))))
29744 := (((-2) + T(T(9))) × T(7)) + T((T(4) × 4))
29745 := (T(2) × (T(T(9)) + (74 × T(T(5))))))
29746 := ((T((2 × T(9))) × 7) + T(46))
29748 := (T(T(2)) × (T((9 × (7 + 4))) + 8))
29750 := (T(((T(2) × 9) + (7))) × 50)
29754 := ((2 × 9) × T((7 + (5 × T(4))))))
29755 := (((T(2) × T(9)) + T(T(7))) × 55)
29756 := (((2 + T(T(9))) × T(7)) - (T(T(5)) × (-6)))
29757 := (((T(2) × (-9)) + T((-T(7)) + T(T(5)))) × 7)
29758 := ((T(T(2)) × T(T(9))) + (T(T(7)) × 58))
29760 := (((2 × T(9)) + T(T(7))) × 60)
29761 := (-T(2)) - ((T(T(9)) + T(7)) × (-T((6 + 1))))
29762 := (-2) + ((T(T(9)) + T(7)) × T((T(6)/T(2))))
29763 := (-T(2)) - ((-T(9)) - T(T(7))) × T((T(T(6))/T(T(3))))
29764 := (-2) - ((-T(9)) - T(T(7))) × T((T(6) - T(4)))
29766 := (T(T(2)) × (((-T(9)) - T(T(7))) × T(T(6)))/(-T(6)))
29767 := (T(2) - ((T(T(9)) + T(7)) × (-T(6) + (7))))
29768 := ((T((T(T(2))) + 9)) - T(T((7 + 6)))) × (-8)
29769 := (T(2) - ((-T(9)) - T(T(7))) × (T(6) + T(9)))
29781 := ((-T(2)) × T(T(9))) + (T(T(7)) × 81))
29782 := ((-2) - (T(T(9)) × (7 - T(8)))) - T(T(T(2)))
29783 := ((-29) × T(78))/(-3)
29784 := -((T(T(2)) - (T(9) × (T((T(7) + 8)) - (4))))))
29785 := (((-2) + T(T(9))) × T(7)) + T((T(8) + (5)))
29786 := (2 - ((T(T(9)) × (7 - T(8))) + T(T(6))))
29789 := ((-2) + T(T(9))) + (T(7) × (-8) + T(T(9))))
29793 := (((T(2) + T(T(9))) × T(7)) + ((9³)))
29794 := -((T(T(T(2)))) + (((T(T(9)) × (-T(7))) - T(T(9))) - T(4)))
29796 := (T((T(2) + 9)) × (T(T(7)) - (T(9) - T(6))))
29799 := ((-2) + T(9)) × (7 × 99)
29808 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(9) - T(T(8))) × (0 - 8)))
29814 := -((T(T(T(2))) + (-T(9)) × (T(T(8)) + ((1 - 4))))))
29831 := (-T(2)) - ((-T(9)) × (T(T(8)) - 3)) + 1)
29832 := (T(2) - ((-T(9)) × (T(T(8)) - 3)) + T(T(2)))
29833 := (-2) - ((-T(9)) × (T(T(8)) - (-3) + T(3)))
29834 := (((-T(2)) × T((T(9) + T(8)))) × (-3)) - T(T(4))
29835 := ((T(2) × T(9)) × ((T(8) × T(3)) + (5)))
29837 := (T(2) - ((-T(9)) × (T(T(8)) + (T(3)))) + T(T(7)))
29838 := (T(2) - (T(9) × (T((8 - T(3))) - T(T(8))))))
29841 := ((T(T(2)) - T(T(9))) × (-8) - T(T((4 - 1))))
29842 := ((-2) + T(9)) × (T(T(8)) + T((T(4) - T(2))))
29843 := (2 + ((T((T(9) + 8)) - T(4)) × T(T(3))))
29844 := -((T(T(T(2))) + ((-T(9)) × T(T(8))) + T((T(4) + (4))))))
29845 := ((T(T(T(2))) + ((-9) × T(T(8))) + (4)) × (-5))
29847 := ((T(T(2)) × T(98)) + T((T(4) + T(7))))
29848 := ((T((T(T(2) + 9)) + 8)) - T(4)) × 8
29849 := -((T(T(T(2))) + (((-T(9)) × T(T(8))) + T(T(4))) + T(9)))
29851 := (2 - (((-T(9)) × T(T(8))) + T(T(5)) + 1))
29852 := (2 - ((-T(9)) × T(T(8))) + T((5 × T(2))))

- 29853 := (T(2) - ((-T(9) × T(T(8))) + (T((5 × 3))))))
29854 := -((T(T(2)) + (((-T(9) × T(T(8))) + T(T(5))) - T(4))))
29856 := (-T(2) - (((-T(9) × T(T(8))) - T(T(5))) + T(T(6))))
29857 := -((T(T(T(2))) + (((-T(9) × T(T(8))) + T(T(5))) - T(7))))
29858 := -((T(T(T(2))) + ((-T(9) × T(T(8))) + (T((5 + 8))))))
29859 := -((T(T(2)) + ((-T(9) × T(T(8))) + (T((5 + 9))))))
29861 := ((2 × ((-T(9) - T(T(8))) × (-T(6)))) - 1)
29862 := ((T(2) - T((T(9) + T(8)))) × (-6 - T(2)))
29864 := (2 × ((9 × T((T(8) + T(6)))) + T(T(4))))
29865 := (T(T(2)) - (((-T(9) × T(T(8))) + T(T(6))) - T(T(5))))
29867 := (2 - ((-T(9) × T(T(8))) + T((T(6) - (7))))))
29868 := (T(2) - ((-T(9) × T(T(8))) + (T((6 + 8))))))
29873 := -((T(T(2)) - ((T(9) × T(T(8))) - T((7 + T(3))))))
29874 := -((T(T(2)) + ((T(9) × (-8)) × (T(7) + T(T(4))))))
29875 := (-T(2) - (((-T(9) × T(T(8))) - T(7)) + T(T(5))))
29876 := (-T(2) - ((-T(9) × T(T(8))) + (T((7 + 6))))))
29877 := (-2) + ((T(9) × (T(T(8)) + (7))) - T(T(7)))
29878 := (((-2) + T(9)) × (T(T(8)) + T(7))) + T(8)
29879 := ((T((T(T(2)) × 9) - ((T(T(8)) × T(T(7)))))/(-9))
29882 := (2 - (T(9) × ((8 - T(T(8))) - T(T(2))))))
29883 := (T(2) - (T(9) × (-8 × 83)))
29884 := (-2) - ((-T(9) × T(T(8))) + (84))
29885 := (T(T(2)) - ((-T(9) × T(T(8))) + (T((8 + 5))))))
29886 := ((T(2) - T(9)) + (8 × T(86)))
29887 := (-2) - ((-9) × T((88 - 7)))
29888 := (((T(2) + T(9)) × T(T(8))) - T((8 × 8)))
29889 := (T(((2 - 9) + 88)) × 9)
29891 := (2 - ((-9) × T((T(8) + T((9 × 1))))))
29892 := (T(2) + ((T(9) - T(8)) × T((9²))))
29893 := (-2) - ((-9) × T((T(8) + T(9)))) - (T(3)))
29894 := (-T((2 + 9)) - ((T(T(8)) × (-T(9))) + T(4)))
29895 := ((29 × T((T(8) + 9))) - T(T(5)))
29897 := (-T((2 + 9)) - ((T(T(8)) × (-T(9))) + (7)))
29898 := (((T(2) - T((T(9) + T(8)))) × (-9)) + T(8))
29899 := (29 × ((T(8)/(-9)) + T(T(9))))
29913 := ((T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(9)) + T(T(9)))) × 13)
29918 := ((2 - 9) - (T(9) × (1 - T(T(8))))))
29919 := -((T(T(2)) + ((T((T(9) - 9) - 1) × (-T(9))))))
29922 := (T(T(2)) - ((-9) × (T(9²) + T(2))))
29923 := (((2 + T((9 + 9)))² - T(3))
29924 := ((29 × T(T(9))) - T((T(2) + T(4))))
29925 := (((-T(2)) × T((T(9) - 9))) + T(2)) × (-T(5)))
29927 := (2 + (-T((9 + 9)) × (T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(7))))))
29928 := (T(2) - ((-9) × T(9²)) - T(8))
29931 := ((T(T(2)) × T(99)) + T(T(T(3 × 1))))
29933 := ((T((T(T(2)) + T(9)) - ((T(9)³)))/(-3))
29934 := ((29 × T(T(9))) - ((3⁴)))
29937 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + ((T(T(9)) - 3) × T(7)))
29940 := (T(T(2)) × (T(99) + 40))
29942 := -((T(-((2 - 9))) + (-T(9) × T(T((4 × 2))))))
29943 := -(((T(T(2)) - ((T(9) × T((9 × 4)))) + T(T(3))))
29945 := (((29 × T(T(9))) - T(T(4))) - (T(5)))
29946 := -((T(2) - ((T(9) × T((9 × 4))) - T(6))))
29949 := -((T(-((T(2) - 9))) - ((T(9) × T((4 × 9))))))
29952 := (T(2) × ((T((T(9) - 9)) × T(5)) - T(T(2))))
29955 := (((-T(2)) × T((T(9) - 9))) × (-T(5))) - (T(5)))
29957 := (29 × (T(T(9)) + ((5 - 7)))
29958 := (T(2) × (((9 × T(T(9))) + (5)) + T(T(8))))
29963 := ((2 - 9) - ((-T(9) × T((6 × T(3))))))
29964 := -((T(T(2)) + (-T(9) × T((9 × (-6) + T(4))))))
29965 := (((-T(2) × T(9)) × (9 - T(T(6)))) - (5))
29967 := (((2 × T(T(9))) + T((T(9) + T(6)))) × 7)
29968 := (-2) - ((9 - (9 × 6)) × T(T(8)))
29972 := (2 - ((-T(9) × T(T((9 + 7)/2))))))
29973 := (((T(2) × T((9 × 9))) + T(7)) × 3)
29974 := -((T(T(T(2)))) + ((T((T(9) + T(9))) × (-7)) - T(T(T(4))))))
29975 := ((T(T(2)) × T(T(9))) - (T(97) × (-5)))
29976 := (T(T(2)) - ((-T(9) × T(T((9 - 7) + 6))))))
29978 := (((T(T(T(2))) + 9) × T(T(9))) - (T(T(7)) + T(T(8))))
29979 := (((T(2) + T((9 × 9))) + (7)) × 9)
29981 := ((2 + 9) - ((-T(9) × T(T((8 × 1))))))
29982 := ((29 × T(T(9))) - (T(8) - T(2)))
29983 := -((2 - 9) - ((-T(9) × T(T(8))) - (T(3))))
29984 := ((T((-2) + T(9)) - 9) × (8 × 4))
29985 := ((T(((2 × 9) - 9)) × T(T(8))) + (T(5)))
29986 := ((29 × T(T(9))) - (8 + T(6)))
29987 := ((29 × T((9 + T(8)))) - T(7))
29988 := ((T(T(2)) × T(99)) - ((-8) × T(8)))
29989 := (T(-((2 - 9))) - ((-T(9) × T(T(8))) + 9))
29991 := (T(T(T(2))) - ((-T(9) × T((T(9) - (9 × 1))))))
29993 := (2 - ((-T(9) × T((T(9) - 9))) - T(T(3))))
29994 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(9) + T(99)) + (4)))
29997 := (((-2 × 9) + T(T(9))) + (T(T(9)) × T(7)))
29998 := ((29 × T(T(9))) - (9 + 8))
29999 := (29 - ((-T(9) × T((T(9) - 9))))
30225 := (-T(30) × (T(T((2 + 2))) - T(T(5))))
30255 := (((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(02)))) × T(T(5))) + T(5))
30285 := ((T(T(3)) - ((0 - T(2)) × T(T(8)))) × T(5))
30324 := -((T((3 × T(T(03)))) - (T(T(T(2))) × T(T(T(4))))))
30384 := (((-30) × T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(8)))) × (-4))
30426 := ((T(30) × T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(2))) × T(T(6))))
30456 := (((-T(30)) × (T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))) + T(T(6)))
30576 := ((T((T(30)/5)) × 7) - (T(6)))
30595 := (((-30) × (T(5) - T(T(9)))) - (5))

- 30723** := $(T(T(T(3))) \times (07 \times (-2) + T(T(3))))$
30834 := $-((T(T(3)) - (T((T(08) - 3)) \times T(T(4))))$
30855 := $(T((-3) + T(08)) \times 55)$
30884 := $((T(3) + 08) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4))))$
30885 := $((T(T(3)) - T((08 \times 8))) \times (-T(5)))$
30888 := $((T(30) - T(8)) \times (T(8) + T(8)))$
30945 := $(30 \times (T(T(9)) - (4))) + (T(5))$
30975 := $(30 \times T(T(9))) - (75)$
30995 := $(30 \times T(T(9))) - T(T((9 - 5)))$
30996 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((0 - 9) + T(9 \times 6)))$
31029 := $-((T(T(3)) + ((-10) \times T(2)) \times T(T(9))))$
31031 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(10)) \times (T(T(3)) - 1)))$
31095 := $(3 \times ((10 \times T(T(9))) + (T(5))))$
31122 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T(11)) - (T(2)^{T(T(2))})))$
31143 := $((-((3 - 1)) + T((-1) + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3)))$
31144 := $((T(T(T(3))) - (1 + 1)) \times T((4 \times 4)))$
31157 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-1) + T((1 + T(5)))) - (T(7)))$
31163 := $-((T((T(T(3)) + 1)) - (T(16) \times T(T(T(3))))))$
31164 := $(T(T(3)) \times (-1) + T((-1) + T((6 + 4))))$
31182 := $(3 \times (-1) + (T((1 + 8)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))))$
31185 := $(T(T(3)) \times T(((T(1 + 1)) + T(8)) + T(5)))$
31197 := $((T(3) + T(T(11))) + (T(T(9)) \times T(7)))$
31213 := $((T(3) + 1)^{T(2)} \times T(13))$
31215 := $((T((3 + 1)^{T(2)})) + 1) \times T(5)$
31220 := $((T(T(T(3 + 1))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 20)$
31225 := $-((T(T(T(3 + 1))) + (T(2) - (2^{T(5)}))))$
31227 := $(T(T(3)) \times (-1) - (-T(2)) \times T((T(2) + T(7))))$
31228 := $-((T(T(T(3 + 1))) - (2^{T(-T(2)+8)})))$
31239 := $((T(31) \times T(2)) \times T(T(3))) - 9$
31242 := $((T(3) - 1)^{T(T(2))} - (4)) \times 2$
31245 := $((T((T(T(3)) + 1)) + T((T(T(2)) \times T(4)))) \times T(5))$
31248 := $(31 \times T((T(2) + (4)))) \times T(8)$
31252 := $(3 - 1) - (-2) \times (5^{T(T(2))})$
31253 := $(3 - ((1 \times 2)) \times (5^{T(3)}))$
31255 := $((T(3) + 1) \times T(-((T(T(T(2))) + (5 - T(T(5))))))$
31256 := $(T(3) + ((1 \times 2) \times (5^6)))$
31257 := $-((T(T(3)) + (T(12) \times (5 - T(T(7))))))$
31262 := $((T((31 - T(2))) \times T(T(6)))/T(2))$
31263 := $((3 - (T(T(1 + T(T(2)))))) \times (-T(T(6))))/3$
31269 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((1 + T(2)) + T((6 \times 9))))$
31272 := $(T((3 + 1)) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(7)))/(-T(2))))$
31275 := $(-3) - (-T(12)) \times (T(T(7)) - (5))$
31279 := $(31 \times ((2 - T(7)) + T(T(9))))$
31298 := $-((3 + 1) - ((-2) - T(9)) \times T(T(8)))$
31326 := $(T(3) \times (T(T(13)) + T(T((T(2) + (6))))))$
31328 := $(T(-((T(3) - T(13)) - T(2))) \times 8)$
31331 := $((31^3) + T(T(T((3 + 1))))$
31334 := $((31^3) + 3) + T(T(T(4)))$
31335 := $(T(T(T(3))) - ((1 + 3) \times (T(3)^5)))$
31353 := $((T(31) \times 3) + (5)) \times T(T(3))$
31365 := $((-T(T((T(3) - 1))) + T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(6)))) \times T(5))$
31374 := $(-T(((3 \times 1)^3)) \times (-T(7)) - T(T(4)))$
31375 := $((T((3 + T(13))) \times 7) + T(T(5)))$
31387 := $((31^3) + T((8 \times 7)))$
31388 := $(-T((T(3) + 1)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T((8 + 8))))$
31392 := $(-3) - ((T(T(13)) \times (-T(9)))/T(T(2)))$
31393 := $((-T(3)) - (-T(13) \times T(T(9))))/3$
31395 := $((3 + T((1 + 3))) \times T((T(T(9))/T(5))))$
31396 := $((-T(3)) + (T(T(13)) \times (-T(9))))/(-6)$
31398 := $((-31) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(9)))) - T(8)$
31413 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((1 + T((4 + 1)))) - 3)$
31416 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((1 + T(4)) \times T(16)))$
31420 := $((-31) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-20)$
31422 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(((1 \times 4)^2))) + T(T(2)))$
31423 := $((T(3) + 1) - (-T((4^2))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
31425 := $((T((T(3) - 1)) + T((4^{T(2)}))) \times T(5))$
31426 := $(T((3 + 1)) + (T((4^2)) \times T(T(6))))$
31434 := $((-T(T(3))) + T(T((-1) + T(4)))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(4))$
31436 := $((T(T(3)) - 1) + (T((T(4) + T(3))) \times T(T(6))))$
31437 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-1)) + (T((4 \times 3)) \times T(T(7))))$
31455 := $((T(3) + T(T((1 + T(4)))) - (T(T(5)))) \times T(5))$
31458 := $(-T(T(3))) \times ((1 - T(T(T(4)))) + (5 + T(8)))$
31466 := $((T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(T(T(4))) + T((6 \times 6)))$
31482 := $((T(T(3)) + 1) \times T(((T(T(4)) - 8) + T(T(2))))$
31485 := $((-T(T(3))) \times ((-1) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(8)) - (T(T(5)))$
31488 := $((T(31) - (4)) \times (8 \times 8))$
31489 := $((-T(T(3))) + T(T(T((1 \times 4)))) + (T(T(8)) \times T(9)))$
31500 := $(T(T(3)) \times 1500)$
31524 := $((-T(3)) \times T((1 + T(5)))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
31531 := $(-T(T(3))) - (-T((1 + T(5))) \times (T(T(T(3)) + 1)))$
31536 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((1 + T(5)))) + T(-((T(3) - T(6))))$
31543 := $((3 - 1)^{T(5)} - T((T(T(4)) - T(3))))$
31548 := $((-T(T(3))) \times ((1 + 5) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(8))))$
31552 := $((T(T(T(3))) + 1) \times T((-5) + T(T((5 - 2))))$
31560 := $((T(T(T(3) + 1))) + (T(T(5))) \times 60)$
31563 := $((T(31) + (5)) \times 63)$
31575 := $((T(3) - 1) \times ((-T(5)) - T(T(7))) \times (-T(5)))$
31576 := $(T(31) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(7) + T(T(6))))$
31579 := $-((T(T(3)) - (T(-((1 - 5))) \times T(79))))$
31582 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(-((1 - 5)))))) - T(8)) - 2)$
31584 := $(T((T(3) + 1)) \times T((T(5) + (8 \times 4))))$
31587 := $(3 - (T((T(T(-((1 - 5)))) - 8)) \times (-T(7))))$

- 31589** := $(-T(31) + ((-5) + T(8)) \times T(T(9)))$
31590 := $(T(31 - 5)) \times 90$
31592 := $((3 - 1)^{T(5)} - T((T(9) + T(2))))$
31593 := $(3 \times (T((1 + T(5))) + (T(9) \times T(T(3)))))$
31625 := $(T((T(T(3)) + 1)) \times (T((T(6) - T(T(2)))) + 5))$
31626 := $((T(31) + (6)) \times T(2)) \times T(6)$
31629 := $-((T(3) - (T((1 + 6^2))) \times T(9)))$
31632 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(16)) + ((T(3))^{T(2)}))$
31635 := $((T((31 + 6)) \times 3) \times T(5))$
31637 := $(-31) + (T((6 + T(3))) \times T(T(7)))$
31643 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(16)) - 4) + T(T(T(3)))$
31646 := $(T(T(T(3))) - (1 - (T(T(6)) \times T((T(4) + (6))))))$
31647 := $-((T(T(3)) - (T((16 - 4)) \times T(T(7))))$
31652 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(16)) + 5) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
31653 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (1 + T((T(6) - (5)))) + T(3))$
31662 := $(-T(3)) - (T(T((1 + 6))) \times (-T((6 \times 2))))$
31664 := $((T(T(T(3) + 1))) \times T((6 + 6))) - 4$
31668 := $((-T(3)) \times T(T((1 + 6))) \times (-T(6) - 8))$
31683 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(16)) + T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))$
31684 := $((T(T(T(3 + 1)))) \times T(6)) - ((T(T(8)) - T(4)))$
31688 := $((-((3 - 1)) - T(T(6))) \times (-T((8 + 8))))$
31692 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(16)) + T(9)) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
31694 := $(-T(3)) - ((-1) + T(6)) \times (-T(9) - T(T(T(4))))$
31723 := $(T(T((3 + 1))) + (T(T(7)) \times T((2 \times T(3))))$
31724 := $((T(T(3)) + 1) \times (-T(7))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
31725 := $(-T(T(3))) - ((-1) - T(T(7))) \times T(-((T(2) - T(5))))$
31731 := $(-T(T(3))) \times ((1 + T(7)) - T(T(T(3 + 1))))$
31735 := $(T(T((3 + 1))) \times (T(T(7)) + T((3 + T(5))))$
31742 := $(-T((3 + 1)) - ((T(7) - T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
31743 := $(-3) - ((1 + T(T(7))) \times (-T((4 \times 3))))$
31744 := $(T(31) \times (T(7) + T((4 + 4))))$
31746 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((-1) + T(7))) \times 4) - (6)$
31747 := $(-((T(3) - 1)) - ((-T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(7)))$
31749 := $(3 \times (-1) - (T((-7) + T(T(4)))) \times (-9))$
31752 := $((-3) \times T((-1) + T(7))) \times (-T((5 + 2)))$
31758 := $(T(3) + (T((-1) + T(7))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(8)))$
31764 := $(3 - (T((-1) + T(7))) \times (-T(6))) \times 4$
31773 := $((-3) \times T((-1) + T(7))) \times (-T(7)) + T(T(3))$
31774 := $((T(T(3)) + 1) - (-T(7)) \times (-T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4))))$
31779 := $(3 \times ((T((-1) + T(7))) \times T(7)) + 9)$
31782 := $((T(T(T(3))) - (T((1 + T(7))) \times (-T(8)))) \times 2)$
31784 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((-1) + T(7))) + 8) \times 4$
31788 := $((31 \times 7) + T(T(8))) \times T(8)$
31789 := $(T(31) \times (T(7) + T(8))) + T(9)$
31794 := $(-T(T(3))) \times ((17 + 9) - T(T(T(4))))$
31822 := $(T(T(T(3) + 1))) - (-T((8 \times 2))) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$
31824 := $(T((T(3) + T((1 + 8)))) \times 24$
31836 := $((T(T(T((3 + 1)))) - (8 \times 3)) \times T(6))$
31844 := $(-T(31) + (T(T(T((8/4)))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
31848 := $-((T(T(T(3) - 1))) + (T(T(8)) \times (-48)))$
31850 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(-((1 - 8)))) \times 50)$
31857 := $((T(T(T(3))) + (T((1 \times 8)) \times T(T(5)))) \times 7)$
31878 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((-1) + T(8))) - (-T(7) \times T(T(8))))$
31886 := $-((T(T(T(3) + 1))) + (-T(8) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(6))))$
31920 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T((1 + 9))) - (20)))$
31927 := $((31 \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(2)))) + T(7))$
31934 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T((1 + 9)))) - T(T((3 + 4)))$
31937 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T((1 + 9))) + 3) - T(T(7))$
31941 := $(-T(T(3))) \times (19 - T(T(T(4 \times 1))))$
31943 := $-(((T(T(T(3) + 1))) - 9) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(3))))$
31947 := $(-T(T(3))) - (T(T(-((1 - 9)))) \times (-T(T(4)) - (7)))$
31948 := $-((T(T(T(3 + 1)))) - (T(T((9 + 4))) \times 8))$
31955 := $((T(3) + 1) \times (T(95) + (5)))$
31962 := $(T(T(3)) \times (1 + ((T(9) - (6))^2)))$
31968 := $(T((3 + 1) \times 9)) \times (6 \times 8)$
31974 := $(T(3) - (T(T(-((1 - 9)))) \times (7 - T(T(4))))$
31979 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T((1 + 9)))) - T(T(7)) + T(9))$
31983 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(19) \times 8) + 3))$
31986 := $((-3) + ((1 - 9) \times T(T(8)))) \times (-6)$
31989 := $(-T(3)) - ((T((1 \times 9)) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(9)))$
31992 := $(31 \times (T(T(9)) - (9/T(2))))$
31994 := $((31 \times T(T(9))) - (T((9 + 4))))$
31995 := $((T(T(T(3))) + 1) \times 9) + T(9) \times T(5)$
31998 := $(3 - (T((1 \times 9)) \times (-T(9) - T(T(8))))$
32024 := $((T(3) + (20^{T(2)})) \times 4)$
32025 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T((20/2))) - (T(5))))$
32046 := $((T(3) - (20)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(6)$
32064 := $(-T((3 + 20))) - (-T(6) \times T(T(T(4))))$
32079 := $(-T(3)) - ((T(2) + T(07))) \times T(T(9))$
32085 := $(T(T((3^2))) \times (T(08) - (5)))$
32088 := $(-T(3)) \times (-20) + (-8) \times T(T(8))$
32103 := $(-T(3)) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(10)))) + T(T(T(3))))$
32106 := $(-3) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(10)))) + T(T(6)))$
32109 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((-2) + T(T(10))) - 9)$
32124 := $(-((T(3))^{T(2)})) - (-T(T((1 + 2))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
32131 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(2))) + 1) \times T((T(3) + 1))$
32136 := $(T((T(3) \times 2)) \times (T(T((1 + T(3)))) + 6))$
32137 := $-((T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T((1 + 3)))) + (T(7))))$
32145 := $((-T(T(3))) \times (T((T(T(2)) - 1)) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5))))$
32147 := $(T((T(3) + T(T(T(2) + 1)))) \times (T(4) + (7)))$
32148 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T(2)) \times (T(14) + T(8)))$
32154 := $(-T(T(3))) + (T((T(T(2)) - 1)) \times T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))))$
32164 := $(T(((T(T(3)) \times 2) + 1)) \times (-T(6) + T(T(4))))$
32169 := $-((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(2)) \times T(T(-((1 - 6)))) \times (-T(9))))$

- 32172** := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T((T(2) + 1)))))) - (T(7) × T(T(2))))
32175 := (T(((T(3)²) + 1) + T(7))) × T(5)
32193 := (((T(T(3)))/(-T(2))) + T(T((1 + 9)))) × T(T(3))
32212 := ((-T(T(3))) × (T(T(2)) - T(T(T((T(2) + 1)))))) - 2
32214 := -(T(T(3)) × (T(T(2)) - T(T((2 × (1 + 4))))))
32224 := ((T(T(T(3)) × T(2)) - 2) × (2⁴))
32229 := ((T(T(T(3))) × (2 × T(T(2))²)) - T(T(9)))
32232 := ((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(2))) × T((2³ × 2)))
32235 := (T(T(3)) × (T(T((2 + 2³)))) - (5))
32241 := (T(3) - (T(T(T(2))) × ((T(T(2)) - T(T(T(4)))) - 1)))
32242 := (T((T(T(3)))/T(2))) - ((T(T(2)) - T(T(T(4)))) × T(T(T(2))))
32243 := -(T(T(T(3) - 2)) + ((-2) + T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(T(3))))
32244 := (T(3) × (-2) - (T(T(T(2))) × (-4⁴)))
32245 := (T(T(3) - 2) + (T(T(T(2))) × (T(T(T(4))) - 5)))
32246 := (32 - ((T(T(2)) - T(T(T(4)))) × T(6)))
32248 := ((T(T(T(3)) × T(2)) × (2⁴)) - 8)
32249 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T(2 + 2)))) - (T((4 + 9))))
32250 := ((-T(T(3))) + T(T(2^{T(2)}))) × 50
32253 := ((T(T(T(3)) × T(2)) × (T(T(T(2))) - 5)) - 3)
32254 := ((T(T(3)) - 2) - (T(T(T(2))) × (5 - T(T(T(4))))))
32255 := -(T(32) - ((2^{T(5)}) + T(5)))
32256 := (T(3) × ((2^{T(2)+5}) × T(6)))
32259 := (-T(3)) - ((-T(2)) + (T(T(2)) × T(T(5)))) × (-T(9))
32262 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T(2 + 2)))) - T(6 × 2))
32263 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T(2 + 2)))) - (T(T(6))/3))
32264 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T(2 + 2)))) - (T(6) + T(T(4))))
32265 := ((T(3) + T((2 + (T(2) × T(6)))) × T(5))
32270 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T(2 + 2)))) - 70)
32272 := (32^{T(2)}) - T((T(7) + T(2)))
32274 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T(2 + 2)))) - T((7 + 4)))
32277 := (T(T(3)) × (-T(2) + T((27 + T(7))))
32283 := (T(3) - ((T(2) - T(T(2 + 8)))) × T(T(3)))
32284 := -(((T(T(3))²) - (T((-2) + T(8))) × T(T(4))))
32285 := (((T(T(T(3))) × (-2)) - T(T(T(2)))) + (8⁵))
32286 := (-T(3)) + (T(2^{T(2)}) × (T(T(8)) + T(T(6))))
32288 := ((T(T(T(3)) × T(2)) + 2) × (8 + 8))
32289 := ((T(T(3)) × (-2) + T(T(2 + 8)))) - 9
32292 := ((-T(3)²) × (T(T(2)) - T((T(9) - T(2))))
32294 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T(2 + 2)))) - (-9) + T(T(4)))
32295 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T(2 + 2)))) - (9 × 5))
32298 := (T(T(3)) × (-2) + T(T((2 × 9) - 8)))
32304 := ((-T(3)²) - (-T(T(3)) × T(T(T(04))))
32312 := -(((T(T(T(3)))/T(2)) - (T(T(T(3 + 1))) × T(T(T(2))))))
32313 := (-T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(T(3 + 1)))) - T(3))
32314 := ((-3 + 2) - (-T(T(3)) × (-1) + T(T(T(4))))))
32316 := ((T(T((3²))) × 31) + T(T(6)))
32319 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T(2) × T(3)))) × (1 × 9))
32320 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T((-2) + T(3)))) - (20))
32321 := (-((T(T(3)) - 2) - (-T(T(3)) × T(T(T((T(2) + 1))))))
32322 := (T(T(T(3) × 2)) + (T(T(3) × T(2))²))
32324 := ((-T(3) - T((-2) + T(3))) + (T(T(T(2))) × T(T(T(4))))
32325 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T((2³ + 2)))) - (T(5)))
32327 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T((-2) + T(3)))) - (T(T(2)) + (7)))
32328 := ((T(3) × (-2) + (T(T(3)) × T(T((2 + 8))))
32329 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T((-2) + T(3)))) - (2 + 9))
32331 := (-((3²) - (-T(T(3)) × T(T(T(3 + 1))))))
32332 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T((-2) + T(3)))) - (T(3) + 2))
32333 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T((-2) + T(3)))) - (T(T(3))/3))
32334 := (-T(3) - (T(T(T(2))) × (-T(T(((3 + 3) + 4))))))
32335 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T((-2) + T(3) + T(3)))) - 5)
32337 := (-3) - (-T((2 × 3)) × T(T((3 + 7))))
32338 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T((-2) + T(3)))) + ((T(3) - 8)))
32351 := ((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))) - (-T(T(3)) × T(T(T((5 - 1))))))
32352 := ((T(3) × 2) + (T(T(3)) × T(T(5 × 2))))
32355 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T((2 + 3) + 5))) + (T(5)))
32356 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(T((-2) + T(3)))) + (-5) + T(6))
32357 := ((32³) - 5) - T(T(7))
32359 := ((T(T(3)) - 2) + (T(T(3)) × T(T(T(-((5 - 9))))))
32361 := (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(2))) × (-T(T(((3 + 6) + 1))))))
32362 := ((32³) - T(T(T(6)/T(2))))
32364 := ((T(T(3)) + T(2)) + (T(T(3)) × T(T((6 + 4))))
32367 := (T(T(T(3))) - (T((2 × T(3))) × (-6) - T(T(7))))
32372 := (32 - (-T(T(3)) × T(T((7 + T(2))))))
32374 := -((T(T(3)) + ((T(T(2)) - T(T(3) + T(7))) × T(T(4))))
32375 := (((T(T(T(3)))/T(2)) × T(T(T(3)))) + 7) × 5
32376 := (-T(3)) - ((-2) - T(T((3 + 7))) × T(6))
32379 := (T(T(T(3))) - ((-2) - T((3 × T(7))) × 9))
32382 := (T(T(3)) × (T(T(2)) - (-3) × (8^{T(2)})))
32385 := ((3 + T((T(2)³))) × 85)
32387 := -(((T(T(T(3))) + 2) × (T(T(T(3))) + (T(8) - T(T(7))))))
32388 := -((T(T(3 + 2))) + (T(T(3) + T(8)) × (-T(8))))
32394 := (-T(3)) - (T((2 + T(3 + 9))) × (-T(4)))
32395 := ((T(T(3 + 2)) × (T(3) × T(9))) - (5))
32397 := ((T(3)^{T(2)}) + (-3) × T(97))
32403 := (((T(3)/2) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(T(03)))
32406 := (3 - ((T(2) + T(T(T(4)))) × (0 - T(6))))
32412 := (T(((T(3) × T(2)) + T(T(4)))) × 12)
32413 := ((3 - (T(T(T(2)))⁴))/(-1) × T(3))
32414 := ((-3) - (T(T(T(2)))⁴))/(-T(-((1 - 4))))
32415 := (((T(3)^{T(2)}) × T(4)) + 1) × T(5)
32416 := ((T(T(T(3)) × T(2)) + T(4)) × 16)

- 32417** := $((T(T(T(3)))/(-T(2))) \times (-T((4+1))) - T(T(7)))$
32418 := $((-T(T(3))) \times (-2) - T(T(T(4)))) + T((1 \times 8))$
32421 := $(-3) + (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(2) + 1)))$
32422 := $((T(T(3) - 2) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 2$
32423 := $(T(3) - (((T(T(T(2))))^4) + T(T(T(2))))/(-T(3)))$
32424 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T((2 \times 4) + 2))) + (4))$
32425 := $(-T(3)) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((-2) + T(5)))$
32426 := $((T(T(3)) + 2) - ((T(T(T(4))) + T(2)) \times (-T(6))))$
32427 := $(3 - (((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))) + T(2)) \times (-T(7))))$
32428 := $((-T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) - (2 + T(8))$
32429 := $((-T(T(3))) \times (-2) - T(T(T(4)))) + (2 + T(9))$
32430 := $(T(((T(3))^2) + T(4))) \times 30$
32431 := $((-T(T(3))) \times (-T(2)) - T(T(T(4)))) + T((T(3) + 1))$
32433 := $((-T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) - 33$
32434 := $((T(T(3) - 2) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(3))) + T(4)$
32435 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T((T(T(3)) - 5))))$
32437 := $(T(3) - (((T(2) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(3)))) - (T(7))))$
32439 := $(-T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T((T(3) + 9))))$
32440 := $((-((3^{T(2)})) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 40$
32442 := $((T(3) \times T(2)) - ((-4) - T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
32443 := $((T(T(3)) - 2) - ((T(T(T(4))) + 4) \times (-T(T(3))))$
32444 := $(-T(3)) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(4))))$
32445 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(2) + (T(4) \times T(4))) \times T(5)))$
32446 := $(T((T(T(3)) - 2) - ((T(T(T(4))) - 4) \times (-T(6))))$
32448 := $((T((T(3))^2) + T(4)) \times 48)$
32449 := $((-T(T(3))) \times (-T(2)) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4)) - 9)$
32451 := $(T(3) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T((T(5) - 1))))$
32452 := $((T((T(T(3)) + 2) - T(4)) \times (T(T(5)) + 2))$
32453 := $((T(3) + 2) - ((T(T(T(4))) + 5) \times (-T(T(3))))$
32454 := $(-T(3)) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T((5 + T(4))))$
32455 := $((T((3 \times 2)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5 - T(T(5))))$
32456 := $((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(T(4))) + 5) \times (-T(6))))$
32458 := $(T(3) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) - 8))$
32460 := $(-T(3)) - ((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T((6 + 0))))$
32461 := $(-T(3)) - (((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6))) - 1)$
32462 := $(-T(3)) - (((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6))) - 2)$
32463 := $(-3) + ((T(T(2)) + T(T((4 + 6)))) \times T(T(3)))$
32464 := $(T(3) - (((T(2) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6))) - (T(T(4))))$
32465 := $(-T(3)) - (((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6))) - 5)$
32466 := $((T(3) + T(T((2^4) - 6))) \times T(6))$
32467 := $(-T(3)) - (((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6))) - 7)$
32468 := $(-T(3)) - (((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6))) - 8)$
32469 := $((T(T(3) - 2) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(6)) + T(9)$
32472 := $((T(T(3))^2) + T(4)) \times 72$
32473 := $(T(T(3)) - ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(7)) + T(T(3))))$
32474 := $(-T(3)) - (((-2) \times T(4)) \times T(T(7))) \times 4$
32475 := $((T((3^{T(2)})) + T(T(4))) \times 75)$
32476 := $(-(((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(T(4))) + 7) \times (-T(6))))$
32477 := $(-3) - (((T(2) - T(T(4))) - T(7)) \times T(T(7)))$
32478 := $(-((T(3)/T(2))) + ((-T(4)) \times T(T(7))) \times (-8))$
32479 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((2^4))) + (T(7) + T(T(9))))$
32480 := $(T((32 - 4)) \times 80)$
32481 := $(-((3^{T(2)}) - ((T(4) \times T(81))))$
32482 := $(T(3) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((8 \times 2)))$
32483 := $(-T(T(3))) + (T((2^4)) \times (8 + T(T(T(3))))$
32484 := $((T((3 \times 2)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(8) \times 4)$
32485 := $((T((T(3) \times T(2))) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(8)))) - 5)$
32486 := $((T(T(T(3))) - ((T(T(T(2))))^4) + (T(T(8))))/(-6)$
32487 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(2)) - T(T(4))) + T((8 \times 7))))$
32488 := $((T(T((T(T(3))/T(2)))) \times (T(4) \times 8)) + 8)$
32489 := $((T(T((T(T(3))/T(2)))) \times (T(4) \times 8)) + 9)$
32508 := $((T(3))^2 \times T((50 - 8))$
32512 := $((-3) + (2^{T(5)})) - T((1 + T(T(T(2))))$
32516 := $((T(T(3)) - (2^{T(5)})) \times (-1)) - T(T(6))$
32521 := $((T(3) + (2^{T(5)})) - T((T(T(T(2))) + 1))$
32522 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) + (-((2^{T(5)})) + T((2 + T(2))))$
32523 := $(T(T(T(3))) - ((-T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times (-T(23)))$
32524 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) - ((2^{T(5)} - T(2)) - T(4)))$
32525 := $((T(3)/T(2))^{T(5)} - (T(2)^5))$
32526 := $((T(T(3)) - 2) + T(T(5))) \times (T(2) + T(T(6)))$
32527 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) - ((2^{T(5)} - T(2)) - 7)))$
32528 := $((-T(T(3 + 2))) + T(T((5 - 2))) \times 8)$
32529 := $(-T(3)) - (((T(T(2)) \times T(T(5))) + T(2)) \times (-T(9)))$
32531 := $(-((T(3) - (2^{T(5)})) - T(T(T(3 \times 1))))$
32532 := $((-3) + (2^{T(5)})) - T(T(T(3))) - 2$
32534 := $(T(T(T(3))) - ((2^{T(5)})) + T((3 \times T(4))))$
32535 := $(3 \times ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(5))) + 3) \times T(5))$
32536 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) - ((2^{T(5)} - T(3)/6)))$
32537 := $((T(3)/T(2))^{T(5)} - T((3 \times 7))$
32538 := $((3 + T((2 \times 5))) \times T((-3) + T(8)))$
32541 := $((T(T(T(3))) - ((2^{T(5)} + 4)) \times (-1))$
32542 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) - ((2^{T(5)} + (T(4)/2)))$
32543 := $((T(3) + (2^{5+T(4)})) - T(T(T(3))))$
32544 := $(-T(3)) - ((T(T(2)) + (T(5))) \times (-T(4)) - T(T(T(4))))$
32545 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(2 \times 5))) + T(4)) - 5)$
32546 := $((T(T(T(3))) - 25) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(6))))$
32547 := $(-3) - (T((2 \times T(5))) \times (T(4) \times (-7)))$
32549 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (((2^{T(5)} - (T(4) \times T(9))))$
32550 := $((T((T(3))^2) - T(5)) \times 50)$
32551 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) - ((2^{T(5)} + T(5)) - 1))$
32552 := $(-((T(3) - (2^{T(5)})) - T((T(T(5))/T(T(2))))$

- 32553** := $((T(T(3)) + ((2^{T(5)} - 5))) - T(T(T(3))))$
32555 := $((-3) + (2^{T(5)})) - T((5 + T(5)))$
32556 := $((T(3)^{T(2)}) + (T(55) \times T(6)))$
32557 := $((T((3 \times 2^5)) - 5) \times 7)$
32558 := $((T(T(3)) + (2^{T(5)})) - T(-((T(5) - T(8))))$
32561 := $((3 + (2^{T(5)})) - T((T(6) - 1)))$
32562 := $((-T(3)) - ((2 - T(T(5))) \times T((T(6) + 2))))$
32563 := $((-((T(3) + 2)) + ((T(T(5)) + (T(6))) \times T(T(T(3))))))$
32564 := $((T(3) + (2^{T(5)})) - (T(6) \times T(4)))$
32565 := $((-T(T(3))) - (((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)))) \times (-T(T(6)))) - T(5)))$
32566 := $((-(3 + 2)) + ((T(T(5)) + (T(6))) \times T(T(6))))$
32567 := $(3 - (((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)))) \times (-T(T(6)))) + 7))$
32568 := $((32 \times T(T(5))) + T(T(6))) \times 8$
32571 := $(T(T(3 \times 2))) \times ((5 \times T(7)) + 1)$
32572 := $((T(T(T(3))) - ((2^{T(5)} + T(T(7)))) - T(T(T(2))))$
32573 := $((T(T(T(3))) + 2) - ((-5) \times T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))))$
32574 := $(3 + ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)))) \times T(T(T(7 - 4))))))$
32577 := $(T(3) - ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)))) \times (-T((-7) + T(7))))))$
32582 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)))) + (8 + T(2)))$
32583 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)))) + (T(8)/3))$
32584 := $((T(3) + (2^{T(5)})) - T((-T(8) + T(T(4))))$
32585 := $((-3) + (2^{T(5)})) - (T(8) \times 5)$
32586 := $((T(T(3)) - T((T(T(2)) \times T(5)))) \times (-8) - 6)$
32589 := $((-((T(3) - T(2 \times 5))) \times T(T(8))) - T(9))$
32592 := $(T(3 \times 2^5)) \times (9 - 2)$
32594 := $((T(3) + (2^{T(5)})) - (T(9) \times 4))$
32595 := $((3^{T(T(2))} - 5) \times T(9)) + (T(5))$
32598 := $((-T(3)) \times (T(2) + ((T(T(5)) \times (-T(9))) - T(8))))$
32613 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(-((2 - 6)))))) + 13)$
32619 := $((-T(T(T(3))) - (((T(2)^6) + 1) \times T(9))))$
32625 := $((T((T(T(T(3)))/T(2)))/(-T(6)) + (2^{T(5)}))$
32627 := $((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(T(6))/T(2)))) - (T(T(7))))$
32628 := $((-T(3)) - ((T(T(2)) - T(T(6 - 2)))) \times T(T(8)))$
32634 := $(T((T(3)^2)) \times (T(6) + T((3 + 4))))$
32637 := $(3 + (T(T(2 + 6))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(7)))$
32652 := $((-3) - ((T(T(T(-((2 - 6)))))) + T(5)) \times (-T(T(T(2))))))$
32654 := $((-T(3)) - ((2 + T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4))))))$
32655 := $((32 + T(65)) \times T(5))$
32676 := $((T(3) \times T(2 \times T(6))) + T(7)) \times 6$
32679 := $((T((T(3)^2)) \times (T(6) + T(7))) + T(9))$
32684 := $((T(T(3)) - (2^{T(6-8)})) \times (-4))$
32685 := $((3 \times (T(2)^6) - 8) \times T(5))$
32688 := $((3 + 2) + T((6 + T(8)))) \times T(8)$
32697 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(2) - ((T(T(6)) - 9) \times (-7))))$
32704 := $((-T(T(3))) - (T((T(T(2)) + T(7))) \times (0 - T(T(4))))))$
32712 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T(-((2 - 7)))) \times (1 + T(T(T(T(2))))))$
32715 := $((T(3) - (T(2)^7)) \times (-15))$
32718 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T((T(2) + 7)))) + 18)$
32719 := $((-T(3)) - (T((T(T(2)) + T(7))) \times (-T((1 + 9))))))$
32722 := $((T(T((T(3) - 2))) \times T((T(7) + T(T(2)))) - T(2))$
32724 := $((-((T(3)/T(2))) + T(T(7))) \times (T(2)^4))$
32725 := $((-((T(3 + 2)) + T(7)) - (2^{T(5)})))$
32726 := $((-T(T(3)) - ((2^{T(7-2)} - T(6))))$
32728 := $(3 + (T((T(2) + 7))) \times T((-2) + T(8)))$
32729 := $(T(3) + ((2^{T(7-2)} - T(9)))$
32731 := $(T(3) - (T((T(T(2)) + T(7))) \times (-T(T((3 + 1))))))$
32733 := $((T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(7) + 3))) - 3)$
32734 := $((3^2) + (T((T(7) + T(3))) \times T(T(4))))$
32736 := $((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))) \times (T((T(7) + 3)) \times 6))$
32738 := $((-T((T(T(3)) - 2)) - (T(7) \times T((T(3) \times 8))))$
32739 := $(3 + ((T(2) + T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(9))))$
32742 := $((T(32) \times (7 + T(T(4)))) + T(T(2)))$
32743 := $(T(T(3)) + ((T((T(T(2)) + T(7))) \times T(T(4))) - 3))$
32745 := $((T(3)/2)^7 - 4) \times T(5)$
32746 := $((T(((3 \times 2) + T(7))) \times T(T(4))) + (T(6)))$
32747 := $((T(T(T(3))) - 2) \times (T((T(7) - T(4))) - T(7)))$
32749 := $((T((T(3) \times 2)) \times T(T(7))) + T((T(T(4)) - 9)))$
32752 := $((T(T(3)) + 2) \times (-T(T(7)) + T((T(T(5))/2))))$
32755 := $(((-3) + (T(2)^7)) \times T(5) - 5)$
32760 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((-2) + T(7)) \times 60)$
32762 := $((-3) + (2^{-7+T(6)})) \times 2$
32764 := $((T(3) \times T(2)) + T(T(7))) - ((-T(6)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
32767 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T((T(2) + 7)))) + (T(6) + T(T(7))))$
32774 := $(T(3) + (2^{T(7/7+4)}))$
32778 := $(3 \times ((27 \times T(T(7))) - T(8)))$
32779 := $(T(T(T(3))) - ((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times (-79)))$
32780 := $(T((T(T(3)) + T(2))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-80)))$
32781 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(2 \times T(7)) - (T(8) - 1)))$
32783 := $(T(T(3)) - ((2^{7+8})) + T(3))$
32784 := $((T(3) + (2^{7+8})) + T(4))$
32786 := $((-3 - (2^{7+8})) + T(6))$
32787 := $(T(3) + ((T(T(T(2))) + (7 \times T(T(8)))) \times 7))$
32793 := $((T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(2)) + T(T(7)))) \times (T(9) + T(3)))$
32795 := $((3^{T(2)}) + (-((7 - 9)^{T(5)}))$
32796 := $((-T(3)) + ((T(T(2)) + T((7 + 9))) \times T(T(6))))$
32799 := $((-T(3)) + ((T(2)^7) \times T((T(9)/9))))$
32802 := $(T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(2)) + T((8 \times 02))))$
32805 := $((T(3)/2)^8 \times 05)$
32813 := $(T((3^2)) + (8^{-1+T(3)}))$
32815 := $((3 + ((T(2)^8) - 1)) \times 5)$

- 32817** := $-(T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(2)) \times (T(8) \times T(17))))$
32823 := $((T(T(3)) + 2) + T(T((8 + 2))) \times T(T(3)))$
32824 := $(T((T(T(3)) - 2)) - (T(T(8)) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(4))))$
32825 := $(T((3 \times 2)) + T(8)) + (2^{T(5)})$
32826 := $(3 + (T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(T(8)) \times 2) + T(T(6))))$
32831 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(2)) + (8^{T(3)-1}))$
32832 := $((T(T(3)) - 2) \times ((T(8)/3)^{T(2)}))$
32835 := $((T(T(3)/2)^8 + T(3)) \times 5)$
32838 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T((2 \times 8) + T(3))) + T(8))$
32841 := $((T(T(3)) + T((T(2) + T(8)))) \times 41)$
32842 := $((-T(T(3))) \times ((T(2) \times (-8)) - T(T(T(4)))) - 2)$
32844 := $(T((32 + T(8))) \times (T(4) + (4)))$
32845 := $((T((T(3) + 28))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(5)))$
32846 := $(T((T(3) \times 2)) + (8 \times 4^6))$
32848 := $((T((T(3) - 2)) + 8^4) \times 8)$
32850 := $((-((3^2)) + T(T(8))) \times 50)$
32851 := $((-T(T(3))) + T(T((T(2) + 8)))) \times T(5) + 1)$
32852 := $((T((T(3) \times 2)) + 8^5) + T(T(2)))$
32853 := $((T(T(T(3))) + 2) \times ((8 \times T(5)) + T(T(3))))$
32854 := $((-T(T(3) - ((T(2)^8) \times 5))) + T(T(4)))$
32855 := $((-T(T(3))) + T(T((T(2) + 8)))) \times T(5) + 5)$
32856 := $((T(3) + (T(2)^8) \times 5) + T(6))$
32857 := $((-T(T(3))) + T(T((T(2) + 8)))) \times T(5) + 7)$
32858 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(2))) - (-((8^5) + T(8)))$
32859 := $((T(3) - 2) - T(85)) \times (-9)$
32865 := $((T(3) + ((T(2)^8) + 6)) \times 5)$
32867 := $(T(T(T(3))) - (-2) + (T(T(8)) \times (-T(6) + T(7))))$
32868 := $((T((T(3) - 2)) + T((T(8) + 6))) \times T(8))$
32875 := $((T(T(3)) + ((T(2)^8) - 7)) \times 5)$
32878 := $((T(3^{T(2)})) \times 87) - 8)$
32885 := $((3 \times (T(2) + T(8))) + 8^5)$
32886 := $((3 + T((T(2) + T(8)))) \times (T(8) + 6))$
32889 := $(3 + (T(28) \times (T(8) + T(9))))$
32892 := $(T(3) + (T(28) \times 9^2))$
32894 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(2))) + (8^{9-4}))$
32895 := $(3^2) \times T((8 + 9) \times 5)$
32897 := $((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(8) + T(9)) \times T(T(7))))$
32904 := $((T(T(3))^{T(2)} - T(T(9))) \times 04)$
32907 := $((T(T(3)) - (T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(07))))$
32922 := $((32 \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(2)))) - T(T(2)))$
32924 := $((32 \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(2)))) - 4)$
32925 := $((3^{T(T(2))}) \times T(9)) + T((T(2) \times 5))$
32927 := $((-((3 - 2)) + (T((T(9) + T(2)))) \times T(7))$
32928 := $(T(((T(3)/2) + T(9))) \times 28)$
32931 := $(3 + (T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T((T(3) + 1))))$
32934 := $((-T(3)) + ((2 \times 9) \times T((T(3) \times T(4))))$
32937 := $((3^2) + (T((T(9) + 3)) \times T(7)))$
32943 := $(3 + ((2 \times 9) \times T((T(4) \times T(3))))$
32944 := $((T(T(3))^{T(2)} - T(T(9))) + T(4)) \times 4)$
32945 := $((32 \times T(T(9))) - T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))$
32946 := $(T(3) + ((2 \times 9) \times T((T(4) \times 6))))$
32949 := $((T(T(3))^{T(2)} - T(T(9))) \times 4) + T(9)$
32952 := $((-T(3)) \times ((-T(2)) \times T((T(9) + T(5)))) - 2)$
32955 := $((-T(3)) + T(T((2 + 9))) \times T(5)) - T(T(5))$
32958 := $((T(3) \times T(2)) + ((T(T(9)) - T(T(5))) \times T(8)))$
32964 := $((-T(3)) + (T(T(T(2))) \times ((9 + T(6)) + T(T(T(4))))))$
32967 := $((-T(3)^2) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(6))/7)$
32970 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times 2) + 9) \times 70)$
32973 := $((3^{T(T(2))}) \times T(9)) + (T(7) \times T(3))$
32975 := $((T(T(3)) - (T(T(2)) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(7)))) \times (-5)$
32977 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-2)) + (T(97))) \times 7)$
32978 := $((-T(3)) + ((T((2 \times T(9))) + T(7)) \times 8))$
32979 := $(T(3) + ((T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(7)) + T(9)))$
32982 := $((T(T(3)) + 2) \times (T((T(9) + 8)) + T(2)))$
32985 := $((3^{T(T(2))}) \times T(9)) + (T(8) \times 5)$
32987 := $(3 + ((-T(9)) - T(T(8))) \times (-T(7)))$
32988 := $((-T(3)) + ((2 + T(9)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(8))))$
32991 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (T((2 \times T(9))) \times (9 - 1)))$
32993 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (2^{T(T(9)/9)} - T(3)))$
32994 := $((T(3)^{T(2)} - (T((9 \times 9)) \times T(4)))$
32996 := $((-3) + (2^{T(T(9)/9)} + T(T(6))))$
32999 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(T(2)) + T(9))))/9) - T(T(9))$
33033 := $((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3))) \times T((T(T(T(3))))/3))$
33048 := $((T(3) \times T((T(T(3)) - 04))) \times T(8))$
33075 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(3))) \times 075)$
33123 := $(3 + (T(T((T(3) - 1))) \times T(23)))$
33124 := $((T((3 + T((3 + 1))))^2) \times 4)$
33126 := $(T(3) + (T(T((T(3) - 1))) \times T((2 + T(6))))$
33132 := $((T(3) + T(31)) \times T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2))))))$
33135 := $((T(T(T(3))) + (3 + 1)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))))$
33137 := $((T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) \times T((-1) + T(3))) - (T(7)))$
33138 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(3 + 1)))) + 38)$
33162 := $((T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) \times T(-(1 - 6))) - T(2))$
33165 := $((-T(3)) + T(T(3))) \times T((1 + 65))$
33189 := $((-T(T(3)) - (T((3 + 1)) \times T((T(8) + T(9))))$
33198 := $((-3) + (31 \times (T(T(9)) + T(8))))$
33210 := $(T(((3 \times 3)^2)) \times 10)$
33214 := $((-T((T(3) \times T(3))) + ((T(T(T(2))) + 1) \times T(T(T(4))))$
33222 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(32) \times T(2)) - 2))$
33225 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(5))))$
33228 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(32) \times T(2))) - T(8))$

- 33234** := $(3 \times ((T(32) \times T(T(3))) - T(4)))$
33237 := $((3^3) \times (T(T(2)) + T((T(T(3)) + T(7))))$
33242 := $((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3))) \times (-T(2)) + (T(T(4))^2))$
33243 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((T(3) \times 2))) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(3)))$
33246 := $(-T(3)) \times (3 - (24 \times T(T(6))))$
33249 := $(-T(3)) + (((3^{T(T(2))}) + T(4)) \times T(9))$
33252 := $((-T(3)) - T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))))) \times (-T(5)) - T(2)$
33254 := $((T(T(3)) \times (3 \times T(2^5))) - T(4))$
33255 := $((T(3) + T(T((3 \times 2) + 5))) \times T(5))$
33257 := $((T(T(3)) \times (3 \times T(2^5))) - (7))$
33258 := $((-((T(3)^{T(3)})) - T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(8))))$
33259 := $(-((T(T(3)) + (32 \times (-5) - T(T(9))))))$
33261 := $(3 \times ((T(32) \times T(6)) - 1))$
33262 := $((3 \times T(32)) \times T(6)) - 2$
33264 := $(T(3^3)) \times (T((2 \times 6)) + T(4))$
33267 := $(3 + (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(2) - (T(6) \times 7))))$
33274 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-3) + (T(T(T(2))) \times 7)) + T(4))$
33277 := $(T(3) + (T((T(3) + T((T(T(2)) + (7)))) \times 7))$
33278 := $((T(T(3)) - T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T((T(T(2)) + (7)))) \times (-8))$
33279 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(3)^{T(2)}) \times T(-((T(7) - T(9))))))$
33282 := $(3 \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(2)) \times 8)) + T(T(2))))$
33285 := $((T((33 \times 2) + 8)) \times T(5))$
33288 := $(3 \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(2)) \times 8)) + 8))$
33294 := $(3 \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(2) + T(9))) + T(4)))$
33297 := $(33 \times ((2 + T(T(9))) - T(7)))$
33315 := $((T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) + T((3 + 1))) \times T(5))$
33324 := $(T(3) \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(2))) + T(4)))$
33327 := $((((3 \times T(T(3))) + (T(3))^2) \times 7)$
33336 := $((3 + T(T(3))) \times (3 - (-T(3)) \times T(T(6))))$
33339 := $(-T(3)) + (T(((T(T(T(3))) - 3)/T(3))) \times T(9))$
33342 := $(T(33) + ((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
33344 := $((T(T(T(3))) - 3) \times T((T(T(3)) - (4))) - T(T(T(4))))$
33345 := $(T(3 \times T(3))) \times ((3 + T(4)) \times T(5))$
33347 := $(T(T((3 \times 3))) - ((-T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(7)))$
33348 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - 8))$
33372 := $((3^3) \times ((T(3) + T(T(7))) \times T(2)))$
33375 := $(T(T((3 \times 3))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(7) \times (-5))))$
33384 := $(T((-T(3)) + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(8) \times 4))$
33387 := $(-3) + (T(T(3)) \times (-T(3) - T((8 \times 7))))$
33396 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((-T(3)) + T(T(3))) \times T((T(9) + T(6))))$
33399 := $(3 \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times (3 + T(9))) + T(9)))$
33411 := $(-T(T(3))) \times ((T(3) - T((T(T(4)) + 1))) - 1)$
33412 := $(-T(3)) + ((T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-1) - T(T(T(2))))$
33419 := $(-T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4))) \times T(19))$
33421 := $(3 + ((-T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + 1))$
33424 := $((-((T(3)^{T(3)})) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (T(2) - T(T(4))))$
33432 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(3) + T(4)))) + T((T(T(3)) \times T(2))))$
33435 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T(3)) \times T(4)) - (T(T(3))) \times T(5))$
33438 := $((T(T((T(T(3)))/3))) \times (4 \times T(T(3)))) - (T(T(8)))$
33441 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (T(3^4)) \times T((4 \times 1)))$
33442 := $((-T(T(3))) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(2)))$
33447 := $(-T(T(3))) + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(47)))$
33453 := $((-3) + T((T(3) + (T(4) \times 5))) \times T(T(3)))$
33454 := $((-T(T(3))) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(5) + T(T(T(4))))$
33456 := $(T(((T(3)/3)^4)) \times (T(5) + T(T(6))))$
33459 := $(-((T(T(3)) - ((T(T(3)) + T(4)) \times T(T(5))) \times 9))$
33462 := $((3 + T(T(T(3)))) \times ((T(T(4)) + T(T(6)))/2))$
33465 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) - ((T(3)^4) \times (T(6) + (5))))))$
33467 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - ((T(T(4)) - (6)) \times T(T(7))))$
33468 := $((T(3) + T((T(3) + T(4)))) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(8))$
33474 := $(T(T(3)) \times (3 \times T((4 + T(7)))) + T(4))$
33475 := $((-T(T((3 \times 3)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(7) - T(5))$
33480 := $((T(3) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-4))) \times T((8 + 0))$
33481 := $(-T(3)) + ((T(T((3 + T(4)))) \times 8) - 1)$
33482 := $((T(T((3 \times 3) + 4)) \times 8) - T(T(2)))$
33483 := $((T(3) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-4))) \times T(8)) + 3$
33484 := $((T(T((3 \times 3) + 4)) \times 8) - (4))$
33485 := $((T(3) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-4))) \times T(8)) + 5$
33486 := $((T(3) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-4))) \times T(8)) + 6$
33487 := $(T(3) + ((T(T((3 + T(4)))) \times 8) - 7))$
33488 := $(T(T(((3/3) + 4) + 8)) \times 8)$
33489 := $((3^{T(3)}) \times (T(4) + T(8))) - T(9)$
33491 := $(3 + (T(T((3 + T(4)))) \times (9 - 1)))$
33492 := $(3 + ((3 + (4 \times T(9)))^2))$
33495 := $(T(T((3 + 3))) \times (T(4) + (9 \times T(5))))$
33498 := $(T(3^3)) + ((4 \times T(T(9))) \times 8)$
33508 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((T(3) + (50)))) - 8)$
33516 := $(T(T(3)) \times T(((3 + 5) \times (1 + 6))))$
33522 := $(T(3) + (T(T(3)) \times T((T(5) + 2))))$
33524 := $((-T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T((T(T(5))/2)))) - (T(T(4)))$
33525 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T((T(3) + (5)))) + T(2)) \times T(5))$
33526 := $(T(T((T(T(3)))/3)) + (T(T(5)) \times T((2 + T(6))))$
33528 := $((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T((T(3) + (5)))) \times (-2))) \times (-8))$
33534 := $((3^{T(3)}) \times (T((5 + 3)) + T(4)))$
33537 := $(T(T(3)) + (T(T(3)) \times T(((5 + 3) \times 7))))$
33543 := $(T(3^3)) + (T(5) \times T(T((-T(4)) + T(T(3))))$
33544 := $((-T(T(3))) \times ((T(T(3)) - (5)) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
33550 := $((T(T(3) \times T(3))) + (5)) \times 50$
33554 := $(-T(3)) + ((T(T(T(3))) + (5^5)) \times T(4))$
33555 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T((T(3) + (5)))) + 5) \times T(5))$
33571 := $((T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) \times T(5)) + T(T((7 \times 1))))$
33572 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times ((T(3) \times 5) + T(T(7))))/T(2))$

- 33579** := $(T(T(3)) \times ((3 + T((5 + T(7)))) + T(T(9))))$
33582 := $((-3) - (T(T(T(3))) \times 5)) \times (-8) - T(T(T(2))))$
33585 := $((T(3 + T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(5)) - 8)) - T(5)$
33588 := $(-T((3^3))) - (-((T(5) + T(8))) \times T(T(8)))$
33594 := $(T(3) \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(5) + 9)) + (T(T(4)))))$
33597 := $(-3) - (((T(T(T(3))) \times (-5)) - T(9)) \times T(7))$
33598 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(5)))) + (T(T(9)) - 8))$
33607 := $((-T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(60))) + (T(7))$
33642 := $((T(3) \times T(T(3))) \times (T(T(6)) + T((4 \times 2))))$
33645 := $((T(33) \times 6) \times T(4)) - T(5)$
33648 := $(-((T(T(T(T(3))))/3) - (T(6) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)))))$
33649 := $((T(3 \times T(3))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(T(4))))/9$
33660 := $(T(((3^3) + 6)) \times 60)$
33675 := $((-33) + T(67)) \times T(5)$
33677 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(3) - (T(T(6)) \times (-7)))) - T(T(7))$
33684 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(3) + T((T(6) + T(8)))) - T(T(4))))$
33687 := $(T((3 \times T(3))) + ((T(6) \times T((8 \times 7))))$
33693 := $((33 \times (-T(6) + T(T(9)))) + T(T(T(3))))$
33696 := $(-T(3)) \times ((-3) - T(T(6))) \times (T(9) - T(6))$
33712 := $((-T(T(3))) + T((T(T(3)) + T(7)))) \times T((1 + T(T(2))))$
33718 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times ((T(T(3)) \times 7) - 1)) - 8)$
33719 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (T(T((T(3) + 7)))) \times (-1 - 9))$
33723 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(3)) \times 7) - T(2)) - T(T(T(3))))$
33726 := $((T((3 \times 3)) + T(7)) \times 2) \times T(T(6))$
33728 := $((T(3) \times T(37)) - 2) \times 8)$
33732 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 73) + T(T(2))$
33733 := $((T(3) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(3))))/3$
33738 := $(-((T(3) - ((T(37) \times T(3)) \times 8)))$
33742 := $(-T(3)) + (-((T(3) - T(7))) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(2))))$
33744 := $((3 \times T(37)) \times (4 \times 4))$
33747 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((-T(3)) + T(T(7))) \times 4) + (7))$
33750 := $(T(3 \times 3)) \times 750$
33753 := $(3 + ((3 + 7) \times (T(5)^3)))$
33754 := $((T(T(T(3))) - 3) \times (T(7) + T(T(5)))) + T(4)$
33759 := $(33 \times (-((7 + 5)) + T(T(9))))$
33761 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(3))) - (T(7))) \times (6 + 1))$
33768 := $((-3) - (T(37) \times 6)) \times (-8)$
33774 := $(T(3) \times (((T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(4))))$
33775 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (3 + T(7))) - (T(T(7)))) \times 5$
33783 := $(-T(3)) + (((T(T(T(3))) \times (-7)) + 8) \times (-T(T(3))))$
33786 := $(-3) + (((T(T(T(3))) \times (-7)) + 8) \times (-T(6)))$
33789 := $((T(3) \times T(37)) \times 8) + T(9)$
33792 := $(3 + ((T(T(T(3))) + (T((7 + T(9)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
33795 := $((T(T(3)) + ((3^7) + T(9))) \times T(5))$
33798 := $(T(3 - (-3) \times T(7))) + (T(9) \times T(T(8)))$
33814 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(8) + 1)) \times T(T(4))))$
33817 := $((T(T(T(3)) + T(T(3))) \times (T(8) + 1)) + (T(T(7))))$
33825 := $((T(T(3 \times T(T(3)))) + 8) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(5)$
33828 := $((T(T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3))) \times (8^{T(2)})) + T(8))$
33848 := $((T(T(T(3))) - ((-T(3)) \times T(T(8))) - (4))) \times 8$
33849 := $((3^{T(3)}) + ((8 \times 4) \times T(T(9))))$
33850 := $((T(T(T(3)))/(-T(T(3))) - (T(T(8)))) \times (-50))$
33852 := $((T(3) - T(T(3))) + T(T(8))) \times 52$
33864 := $((T(3) + (-3) \times T(T(8))) \times (-T(6) - (4)))$
33873 := $((T((3 \times 3)) \times T(8) - (7)) \times T(T(3)))$
33874 := $(-T(3)) + ((T(T(3)) + (8 - 7)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
33879 := $((3 - T((T(3) \times 8))) \times (-T(7))) + T(T(9))$
33885 := $((3 \times T(38)) + T(8)) \times T(5)$
33888 := $((T(T(3) \times (T(3) + 8))) + T(T(8))) \times 8$
33891 := $(33 \times (-8) + T(T(9 \times 1)))$
33892 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-T(3) - (T(8) \times T(9)))) - 2)$
33894 := $((-T(3)) \times T(T(3))) \times ((T(8) \times (-9)) + T(T(4)))$
33897 := $(T(3) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times (8 - T(T(9))))/(-7)))$
33915 := $((T(T(T(3))) + (T(3) \times 9)) \times (-1 + T(T(5))))$
33918 := $(3 - ((T(3) + T(9)) \times (1 - T(T(8))))$
33922 := $((33 \times T(T(9)) - 2) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
33924 := $((33 \times T(T(9)) - T(T(2 + 4)))$
33926 := $((33 \times T(T(9)) + 2) - T(T(6)))$
33927 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(T(2))))/7))$
33934 := $((33 \times T(T(9)) - T(T(T(3)))) + T(4)$
33936 := $((33 \times (T(T(9)) - T(3))) - (T(6)))$
33938 := $(-((T(T(T(3)))/3) - ((T(9) + T(3)) \times T(T(8))))$
33939 := $((T(T(3) \times T(3))) + (T(T(9)) \times 3)) \times 9$
33942 := $((T(3)^{T(3)} - 9) + (-T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))))$
33945 := $((33 \times T(T(9)) - (T((4 \times 5))))$
33948 := $((-3) + T((39 + 4))) \times T(8)$
33957 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(3) - (T(9) \times (-5))) \times 7))$
33963 := $((T(T(3) \times T(3))) \times (T(9) + (6))) - 3$
33966 := $((3 + 3) + T(9)) \times T((6 \times 6))$
33968 := $((T(3)/3) - (-((T(9) + (6))) \times T(T(8))))$
33969 := $((33 \times T(T(9)) - T(T(6))) + T(9))$
33975 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T(3)) \times (T((9 + 7)) + T(5)))$
33978 := $(T(T(3)) \times (((T(T(3)) \times T(9)) + (7)) + T(T(8))))$
33984 := $((33 \times T(T(9)) - T((8 + T(4))))$
33987 := $(T(T(3)) + ((T(3) + T(9)) \times T((8 + T(7))))$
33993 := $((T(T(3))^3 + T(T(9))) + T(T(9))) \times 3$
33998 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T((T(3) + T(9))))/(-9)) - T(8))$
33999 := $(-((T(T(3)) - (T(3 \times 9)) \times (T(9) + T(9))))$
34012 := $((T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (01 + T(T(T(2))))$
34026 := $(T(3) \times (T(40) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(6))))$
34056 := $(T((3 + 40)) \times (T(5) + T(6)))$
34083 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 083))$
34104 := $((T(T(3)) \times 4) \times T((T(T(10))/T(T(4))))$
34111 := $(T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-1 - T(T(T(1 + 1))))$

- 34122** := $((T(T(3)) - T(4)) \times (T(T(12)) + T(T(T(2))))$
34125 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((4 + 1) \times T(25)))$
34128 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((T(4) - 1))) + T(2)) \times T(8)$
34132 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times (1 + T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(2))))$
34136 := $(T((T(3) + T(4))) \times ((-1) + T(T(3))) + T(T(6)))$
34144 := $-((T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) \times ((1 + 4)^4)))$
34146 := $((3 \times T(4)) + T((1 + T(T(4)))) \times T(6)$
34155 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((-1) - T(T(5))) \times T(5))$
34158 := $(3 + (T((T(T(4)) - 1)) \times (T(5) + 8)))$
34167 := $(-3) + (T((4 + 1)) \times T(67))$
34174 := $((-T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T((1 + 7))) + T(T(T(4)))$
34176 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T((T(4) - 1)))) / 7) + T(6)$
34179 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-4)) \times (-1 - T(T(7)))) - 9$
34181 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(4)) + 1))) + (T(T(8)) - 1))$
34182 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(4)) - 1)) + (T(8)^{T(2)}))$
34184 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-4) \times (-1 - T(8))) - 4$
34188 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(4)) - 1) \times T(8)) + 8)$
34189 := $-((T(T(3)) - (T(T(4)) \times ((1 + T(T(8))) - T(9))))$
34197 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(4)) - 1) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(7))))$
34205 := $((T(3 + T(T(4)))) \times 20) - T(5)$
34209 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T((4 \times T(T(T(2)))))) \times 09$
34215 := $((T(3 + T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(T(2))) - 1)) - 5$
34216 := $((-3) + T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) \times T((1 + 6)))$
34218 := $(-T(3)) + (T((T(T(4)) + T(2))) + 1) \times 8$
34220 := $(T(((T(3) \times T(4)) - 2)) \times 20)$
34221 := $((T(3) + T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(T(T(2)))) / (T(T(2)) + 1)))$
34224 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T((2 + T(T(4))))))$
34227 := $(T(3) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(T(T(2)))) / 7)))$
34230 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(2) \times 30)))$
34231 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(2)) + T(T(3 + 1))))$
34234 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(2)) + T((T(3) + T(T(4))))$
34237 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(4)) - 2))) + T(T((T(3) + (7))))$
34244 := $((T((-T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - 2) \times T(T(T(4))) / T(T(4))$
34248 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((-2) + T(T(4))) \times (-T(8)))$
34251 := $(-T(T(3))) \times (-T((T(4) + T(2)))) - T(T(T(5 - 1))))$
34254 := $-((T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) \times (2 + (5^4))))$
34257 := $((-T(34)) - T(T(2))) \times (-57)$
34261 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + 61)))$
34263 := $-(((3^{T(4)}) - (2 \times (6^{T(3)})))$
34265 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(6) + (5))))$
34266 := $((T(T(3)) - 4) \times T((T(2) \times T(6)))) - 6$
34271 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-4)) \times (-2 - T(T(7)))) - 1$
34272 := $((3 \times T((4^2))) \times T(7)) \times T(2)$
34273 := $(-T(T(3))) + ((T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) \times T(7)) - T(3))$
34275 := $((T(3 + (4^{T(2)}))) + (7)) \times T(5)$
34276 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(2)) \times (T(7) - 6)$
34278 := $(T(3) + ((T((4^2)) \times 7) \times T(8)))$
34279 := $(3 + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(9))))$
34284 := $(-T((34 \times 2)) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(4))))$
34285 := $((-T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) - ((2 - (8^5)))$
34287 := $(-3) \times (T(T(4)) - ((T(2) \times T(87))))$
34293 := $((T(34) + T(2)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(3))$
34294 := $(-T(3)) + (T((T(4) - T(2))) \times T((T(9) + (4))))$
34295 := $((T((-T(3)) + T(T(4)))) \times T(-(2 - 9))) - 5$
34297 := $((T(T(3 \times 4))) \times (2 + 9)) + T(T(7))$
34299 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times ((4^2) \times 9)) + T(T(9)))$
34314 := $(-T(T(3))) \times ((-4) \times T(T((T(3) + 1))) - T(4))$
34315 := $((T((-T(3)) + T(T(4)))) \times T((T(3) + 1))) + T(5)$
34335 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((T(4) \times T(3)))) - T((T(3) \times T(5))))$
34338 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((3 - T(3)) \times T(T(8))))$
34339 := $((-T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) + ((3^{T(3)}) \times T(9))$
34341 := $(T(T(3)) + ((-T(T(4)) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T((4 + 1))))))$
34342 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(3) + ((4^2))))$
34343 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((-4) + T(T(3)))) - ((T(4)^3))$
34344 := $((T(3) \times T((43 + T(4)))) \times 4)$
34345 := $((T(T(3)) + (4)) + ((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)))) \times T(T(5))))$
34348 := $((T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T((3 + T(4)))))) - 8)$
34352 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times ((T(T(T(3))) - 5) \times 2))$
34353 := $((T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T((T(3) + (5)))) \times 3)$
34354 := $-((T(T(3)) - (T((4 + T(3))) \times (5^4)))$
34356 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T((-3) + T((5 + 6))))))$
34359 := $(-T(3)) + (((-T(T(4)) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(5)))) + T(9))$
34362 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (-T(3)) - T((T(6) \times T(2))))$
34368 := $((T(3) + (T(T(4)) \times T((T(3) + (6)))) \times 8)$
34372 := $(-3) + (T(T(4)) \times ((-3) + T(7)^2))$
34374 := $((3 + T((T(T(4)) - T(3)))) \times T(7)) - T(4)$
34377 := $(3 \times (T((T(4) + 3)) - (-T(7)) \times T(T(7))))$
34378 := $((-T(T(3))) + T((T(T(4)) - T(3)))) \times T(7) + (T(T(8)))$
34383 := $((-T(3)) \times T(T(4))) - (-T(T(3))) \times T((T(8) + T(T(3))))$
34384 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (3 \times 8))) + T(T(T(4))))$
34385 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (4 + 3)) + (8^5))$
34389 := $-((T(T(3)) - ((T((T(4) \times 3)) \times T(T(8))) / 9))$
34391 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(4)) + 3))) - T(T((9 + 1))))$
34392 := $((T(3 + T(4))) \times T((3 \times 9))) - T(T(2))$
34394 := $((T(3 + T(4))) \times T(3 \times 9)) - 4$
34395 := $((-T(3)) - (T((-4) + T(T(3)))) \times (-T(9))) \times 5$
34398 := $(T(3 + T(4))) \times T((3 \times (T(9) - T(8))))$
34412 := $((T((-T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + 4) \times T((1 + T(T(2))))$
34416 := $((T(3) + T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) \times 16)$
34418 := $((-T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) + (((T(T(4)) - 1) \times T(T(8))))$
34419 := $(T(T(T(3))) \times (T((T(4) + (4))) + (-1) + T(9)))$
34435 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T((4^3)) + T(5)))$

- 34437** := $(-3) + (T((T(4) \times 4) \times (T(3) \times 7)))$
34462 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(4)) + (6)))) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
34464 := $((-T(T(3))) + T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) - (-T(6) \times T(T(T(4))))$
34465 := $(T((-3) + T(T(4))) \times (4 + T(6))) + T(5)$
34468 := $(T((3 + 4) \times (T(T(4)) + T((6 \times 8))))$
34474 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-4) + T((T(4) + (7)))) + (T(T(4))))$
34475 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(4))) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(5))))$
34476 := $(-T(3)) \times ((T((T(4) \times 4) \times (-7)) - (6)))$
34479 := $(3 + T((T(T(4)) + (4 + T(7)))) \times 9$
34482 := $((3 \times T(4)) \times T(T(4))) - 8 \times T(T(T(2)))$
34485 := $(T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(((T(4) \times 8) - T(5)))$
34488 := $((T(T((3 + 4))) \times 4) - T(T(8))) \times T(8)$
34489 := $(T((3 + T(4))) \times (T(T(4)) + (T(8) \times 9)))$
34493 := $((T(T(3)) - (T(4) \times T(4) \times T(T(9)))) / (-3))$
34496 := $(-((T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(T(4)) - T((T(9) + T(6))))))$
34498 := $(T((-3) + T(T(4))) + ((4 \times T(T(9))) \times 8))$
34517 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T((T(5) - 1)))) - (T(7)))$
34520 := $(T((3 + T(T(4)))) + T(5)) \times 20$
34521 := $(T(T(3)) + ((T(4) \times T(5)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1)))$
34524 := $((T(T((3 + 4))) + 5) \times T(T(T(2))) \times 4$
34527 := $(T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((5 - 2)^7)$
34528 := $((-3) + T(T(4))) \times ((-5) + T(2) + T(T(8)))$
34529 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(5)) + (2^9))))))$
34536 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(5)) + T(T((T(T(T(3)))) / T(6)))$
34539 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times ((T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(3)))) - T(T(9)))$
34543 := $(3 + (T(T(4)) \times ((5^4) + 3)))$
34544 := $((T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times (-5))) \times (-T((4 \times 4)))$
34545 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((4 + T((T(5) + T(4)))) \times 5)$
34546 := $(T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) - ((T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6))))$
34551 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(((5 + 5) + 1)))$
34556 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (5 + T(T((5 + 6))))$
34559 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) - (T((T(T(4)) + (T(5)))) \times (5 + 9))))$
34566 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(5) + T(66)))$
34569 := $((T(T(3)) - (-4) \times T(T(5))) \times 69$
34573 := $((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)))) \times T(T(5))) + T((T(7) - T(3)))$
34574 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-4) + T(57)) - T(T(4)))$
34575 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(4) \times T(5))) - 75$
34584 := $((T(T(3)) - T(4)) \times ((T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 4)$
34585 := $((3 \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(T(8)))) - 5$
34587 := $(-(3^4)) \times ((T(5) - T(8)) - T(T(7)))$
34588 := $(T((3 + 4) - (T(T(5)) \times (-8) \times T(8))))$
34589 := $(-T(3)) + (-T(T(4)) \times (T(T((T(5) - 8))) - T(T(9))))$
34592 := $((T((T(T(3)) + T(4))) - (T(T(5)))) \times 92$
34595 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(4) \times T(5))) - T(T((9 - 5))))$
34596 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) \times 5 - 9) \times 6$
34605 := $((3 - (T(4) \times T(T(6)))) \times (0 - T(5)))$
34614 := $((3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(6)) + T(T((1 + T(4))))$
34626 := $(((-3) + T(T(4))) \times T((6^2))) - (6)$
34629 := $(T(T(3)) \times (-4) + T(((6 \times 2) + T(9))))$
34631 := $(((-3) + T(T(4))) \times T((6 \times T(3)))) - 1$
34632 := $((-3) + T(T(4))) \times T(((6 \times 3) \times 2))$
34635 := $((T(T(3)) + 4) \times T(T(6))) \times T(3) - (T(5))$
34638 := $(T(3) + ((46 + T(3)) \times T(T(8))))$
34644 := $(-T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times T(((T(6) + 4) + T(4))))$
34645 := $(((-3) \times T(T(4))) \times (-T(6) \times T(4))) - (5)$
34647 := $(-3) + (T(4) \times (-T(6) + T((T(T(4)) + T(7))))$
34648 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((4^6) + 4)) \times 8$
34662 := $(-T(3)) \times (((-4) - T(6)) \times T(T(6))) - 2$
34665 := $((T(3) \times (4 + T(6))) \times T(T(6))) + (T(5))$
34668 := $(3 \times ((T((4 \times 6)) + T(6)) \times T(8)))$
34671 := $(T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times T((6 + T(7) + 1))))$
34672 := $((T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)))) \times ((T(T(6)) - T(7)) - T(T(2))))$
34674 := $(T(3) \times ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(6) - 7))) + 4))$
34678 := $((T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-6) + T(7)) + (T(T(8)))$
34682 := $(-((T(T(3)) + T(4))) + (T((T(6) + T(8))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
34683 := $((-3) \times T(4)) + (T((T(6) + T(8))) \times T(T(3)))$
34684 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-4) + T((T(6) + T(8)))) + T(T(4)))$
34686 := $(-T(3)) \times ((T(T(4)) \times (-T((6 + 8)))) - (6))$
34689 := $(((-3) + T(T(4))) \times (T(6) + T(T(8))) - T(T(9)))$
34692 := $((-T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times (-T(6) - (9^{T(2)}))$
34695 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) \times 6) + 9 \times 5$
34697 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T(4)) \times (T(6) + T((9 + 7))))$
34705 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (-T(70) + T(T(5))))$
34713 := $(T(T(3)) \times T((47 + T((1 + 3))))$
34716 := $(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(-((1 - 6))))))$
34725 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(4)) + (7 - 2)) \times T(5)$
34726 := $(T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times ((T(T(7)) - T(T(2))) + T(T(6))))$
34727 := $((T((-T(3)) + T(T(4)))) \times T(7)) + T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(7)))$
34728 := $((T(T(3)) \times ((4 \times T(T(7))) - 2)) + T(T(8)))$
34731 := $((T(T(T(3))) - 4) \times T((7 + T((3 + 1))))$
34734 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((4 \times T(T(7))) + (3 \times T(4))))$
34735 := $((T((3 + T(4))) \times T(T(7))) - T(T((T(3) + 5))))$
34737 := $(-((3^{T(4)})) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T((3 \times 7))))$
34739 := $(-((T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times ((T(T(7)) - 3) - T(T(9))))))$
34741 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((7^4) \times 1))$
34742 := $((T(T(3)^4) \times T(7)) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(2))$
34744 := $((T(T(3)^4) \times T(7)) - 4) - T(T(T(4)))$
34748 := $((T(T(3)) - 4) \times (T(7) + T((T(T(4)) + 8))))$
34749 := $((T(((3^4) + 7)) - T(T(4))) \times 9$
34752 := $((3 \times (4^7)) - (T(T(5))^2))$
34754 := $(-T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times (7 + (5^4)))$
34755 := $((T((3 \times T(4))) \times 75) - T(T(5)))$
34761 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(7))) - (T(61))$

- 34762** := $(T((3 + T(4))) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(6) + T(2))))$
34764 := $((3 \times T(T(4))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(6)))) \times 4$
34765 := $((T((-T(3)) + T(T(4)))) \times T(7)) + (T((6 \times 5)))$
34768 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) - 8))$
34773 := $(3 \times (T(T(4)) - (-T(7)) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(3))))$
34775 := $((T(T(3 \times 4))) - T(T(7))) \times (T(7) - T(5))$
34776 := $(-(3 \times 4) \times (T(7) - T(76)))$
34782 := $((34 + T(7)) \times T((T(8) - T(2))))$
34783 := $((-T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T(7))) - (T(8) \times T(T(T(3))))$
34784 := $((T(T(3)^4) \times T(7)) + T(8)) - T(T(T(4)))$
34785 := $((T(T(3)) \times 4) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(8)) + (T(5))$
34793 := $((T(T(3)) - T(4)) \times (T(79) + 3))$
34794 := $(-((T(T(3)) - ((4 - T(T(7))) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(4))))$
34795 := $((T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(4)) + (-7) \times T(T(9)))) \times (-5))$
34797 := $((T(T(3)) + T(((4 + 7) \times 9))) \times 7$
34804 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (4 \times T(8))) + T(T(T(04))))$
34812 := $(-3) + (T(T(4)) \times (T((T(8) - 1)) + T(2)))$
34816 := $((T(3) - 4)^8) \times T(16)$
34822 := $((-3) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(8)) + T((T(T(T(2))) - 2))$
34823 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) \times 23))$
34824 := $(-3) + ((T(T(4)) - T(T(8))) \times (-2) - T(T(4)))$
34825 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((T((8 + 2)) + T(5)))$
34833 := $(3 + (T(4) \times (T(83) - 3)))$
34834 := $(-T(3)) + ((4 + T(T(8))) \times (-3) + T(T(4)))$
34836 := $(-3) + ((T(4) \times T(83)) - T(6))$
34839 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(4)) \times (T(8) - T(3))) + 9))$
34850 := $((T(T(3)) + T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 50$
34852 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - 8) - (-T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(2)))$
34854 := $(-T(3)) + (T((T((4 + 8)) + (5))) \times T(4))$
34855 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (-8) \times T(5))) - 5)$
34857 := $(-3) + (T(4) \times T((-8) + T(-(T(5) - T(7))))$
34859 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(8)) \times T(T(-((5 - 9))))))$
34872 := $(T(3) \times ((T(4) - T(T(8))) - (-T(7)) \times T(T(T(2))))$
34873 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 8)) + T(73))$
34875 := $(T((3 \times T(4))) \times ((8 + 7) \times 5))$
34878 := $(3 \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times 8) - (T(7) + T(T(8))))$
34881 := $(T(T(T(3))) \times ((4 \times T(8)) + (8 - 1)))$
34884 := $(34 \times (T(T(8)) + (T(8) \times T(4))))$
34885 := $(T((T(T(3)) + 4)) + ((8 \times T(8)) \times T(T(5))))$
34894 := $((-T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(8)) + T(9)) + T(T(4))$
34914 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(9)) - 1)) + T(T(T(4)))$
34915 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(9))) + T(T(T(-((1 - 5))))$
34918 := $(34 \times (T(T(9)) - (1 \times 8)))$
34923 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(4) + T((T(9 \times 2))/3)))$
34926 := $((3 + T(T(T(4)))) + T(92)) \times 6$
34935 := $(-3) \times (T(T(4)) + (T((T(9) - T(3))) \times (-T(5))))$
34937 := $((T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(9) + T(3)) - T(7))$
34938 := $((-3) \times T(4)) - (T(93) \times (-8))$
34944 := $((T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times T(9))) \times (T(4) + 4))$
34945 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T(4)) \times (-T(9)) + T((4 + T(5))))$
34947 := $(3 \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times 9) - T(T((4 + 7))))$
34952 := $(34 \times (T(T(9)) - (5 + 2)))$
34958 := $((T(T(T(3))) - 4) \times (T((T(9) - 5))) - T(T(8)))$
34959 := $((34 \times T(T(9))) - T(T((T(5) - 9)))$
34962 := $((34 \times T(T(9))) - T(T(6))) + T(2)$
34965 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T((4 \times 9))/6) \times T(5)))$
34968 := $((T(T(3)) + T(4)) \times T((T(9) - ((6 - 8))))$
34972 := $(3 + (((4 \times T(9)) + (7)^2))$
34973 := $((T((T(3) + 4)) \times T(T(9))) - ((T(7)^3))$
34974 := $((T((3 \times 4)) + 9) \times (T(T(7)) - 4))$
34977 := $(-3) + (T(T(4)) \times ((T(T(9)) + 7) - T(T(7))))$
34983 := $(3 + (T(T(4)) \times ((-9) + T(T(8))) - T(T(3))))$
34986 := $((T(3)^4) \times (-9) + T(8)) - 6$
34989 := $((-T(3)) \times (-T(4)) + (-9) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(9))$
34992 := $((T(3)^4) \times (9 + (9 \times 2)))$
34995 := $(3 \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(9) \times T(9)) \times T(5))$
34997 := $((-3) - T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(9) + T(9)) \times T(T(7)))$
35028 := $(-T(T(3))) \times (-T(5)) - T((T(T(T(02))) + T(8)))$
35049 := $(-T(T(3))) \times ((-T(T(5))) - T(T(T(04)))) - 9$
35100 := $(T((T(T(3)) + 5)) \times 100)$
35112 := $(T((T(T(3)) + T(T((5 - 1)))) \times 12)$
35124 := $((-3) + T(5)) \times (1 + T((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4))))))$
35145 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - (T((-1) + T(T(4)))) \times (-5))$
35150 := $(T((T((3 + 5)) + 1)) \times 50)$
35154 := $(-T(T(3))) \times ((-T(T(5) - 1)) - T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4))))$
35167 := $((3 + T((T(5) + 1))) \times T((-6) + T(7)))$
35169 := $(-T(T(3)) - (T(5) \times T(-(1 - 69))))$
35172 := $(-T((3 + T(5))) - (-T(17)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$
35211 := $(T(T(3)) + (T(5) \times T((2 + T(11))))$
35217 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T((T(T(5))/2)) - T(17)))$
35223 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(5) + T(2))^{T(2)}) \times T(3))$
35224 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T((5 + 2))) \times T((2^4)))$
35225 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(2))) + (2^{T(5)}))$
35226 := $((T(T(T(3))) - (5^2)) \times T((T(2) \times 6)))$
35227 := $(3 + (T((-5) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7))))$
35229 := $(-T(3)) + ((-T(T(5)) + T((2 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9)))$
35235 := $((T(3)^5) - (T(2)^{T(3)})) \times 5$
35238 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(52) + T((3 \times 8))))$
35244 := $(-((T(3) - T(5)) \times T((2 \times 44)))$
35248 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(5))/T(T(2)))) - 4) \times 8)$
35250 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 250)$
35252 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(5) + 2))) - T((T(5) - 2)))$
35253 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(5) + 2))) - (T(5) \times T(3)))$

- 35256** := $((3 \times 52) \times (-5) + T(T(6)))$
35257 := $(-3) + (T((T(T(5))/T(2))) \times (T(5) + T(7)))$
35259 := $-((T(T(3)) \times (T((T(5) - 2)) - (T(59))))$
35262 := $((3 + T(5)) \times (T(T(2)) + T(62)))$
35265 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(T(2)))) + ((6^5))$
35274 := $(-T(3)) + ((T(T(5)) + T(T(2))) \times (T(7) \times T(4)))$
35275 := $((T(35) \times 2) \times T(7)) - (5)$
35277 := $(-3) + (((T(5) \times T(2)) \times T(7)) \times T(7))$
35292 := $(-T(3)) \times ((-5) \times T((T(2) + T(9)))) - 2)$
35294 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(5) + 2))) - (T(9) + (4)))$
35295 := $((T(3) \times 5) \times T((T(2) + T(9)))) + (T(5))$
35298 := $(T((T(3) \times T((5 - 2)))) \times (T(9) + 8))$
35317 := $(-((T(T(3)) + (5))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(17)))$
35319 := $(T(T(3)) + (53 \times T(T(-(1 - 9))))$
35322 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((5 \times 3) + 2))) - T(T(T(2)))$
35324 := $((T(T(3)) + T((T(5) + 3)))^2) - T(T(T(4)))$
35325 := $((-3) - T(5)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T((2 + T(5))))$
35328 := $((-3) + T(T(5))) + T(T(3)) \times (2^8)$
35329 := $(T(T(3)) + ((5^{T(3)}) + (T(2)^9)))$
35334 := $(-T(3)) + (T((5 \times T(3))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(4))))$
35352 := $(-((T(3) - T(5))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(5) + 2))))$
35358 := $(3 \times (5 - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(5) + T(8))))$
35364 := $(T(T(3)) + (T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T((T(6) - (4))))$
35368 := $((T(T(3)) - (5)) \times T((T(T(3))/T(6)))) - 8)$
35376 := $((T(T(3)) - (5)) \times T((3 \times (T(7) - (6))))$
35379 := $(3 + (T(T((5 + T(3)))) \times (7 + 9)))$
35382 := $((T(T(3)) - (5)) \times T(T((3 + 8)))) + T(T(2))$
35385 := $((3^{T(5)-3}) - T(T(8)))/T(5)$
35394 := $((T((T(T(3)) - (5))) \times (T(3) + T(T(9))))/4)$
35397 := $(T(T(3)) + (T(T((5 + T(3)))) \times (9 + 7)))$
35415 := $((T(T(T(3))) + 5) \times T(4) + 1) \times T(5)$
35420 := $((T((T(3) + T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 20)$
35421 := $(T(T((-3) + T(5))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-21)))$
35422 := $(-((3 - 5)) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (2 + T(T(T(2))))$
35423 := $(T(-((3 - 5))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times 23))$
35424 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T(5)) \times (4 \times T((2 \times 4)))$
35425 := $((T(T(3)) \times 5) + (4)) \times T(25)$
35426 := $((T(T(3)) - (T(5))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (2 + T(6))))$
35427 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T((5 \times T(4))) + T(T(2))) + T(T(7))))$
35428 := $(-T(3)) + ((T((T(5) + (4)))^2) - T(T(8)))$
35432 := $((-3) + T(5)) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (T(T(3)) + 2))$
35433 := $((T(3) \times T(5)) + (T((-4) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
35435 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - ((T(T(T(4))) + 3) \times (-5)))$
35442 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T((T(5)/T(4)))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
35443 := $(-T(T(3))) + ((T(T(5)) + (4)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3))))$
35445 := $((3 + T((-T(5)) + T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(4))) \times T(5))$
35448 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(5)) \times (T(4) + (4))) + 8))$
35451 := $(T((T(T(3)) + (5))) \times (-4) + T((T(5) - 1)))$
35454 := $(-T(T(3))) + (T(5) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (-T(5) \times T(T(4))))$
35457 := $(-(3^5)) + (T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(7))$
35463 := $(T((3 \times 5)) - (-T((-4) + T(6)))) \times T(T(T(3)))$
35464 := $((T((3 \times 5)) + (4)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(4))))$
35466 := $((3 + T(T(5))) + (T((-4) + T(6))) \times T(T(6)))$
35472 := $((T(T(3)) - (5)) \times (T(T((4 + 7))) + T(T(2))))$
35475 := $((3 \times 5) \times T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + T(5))$
35476 := $((T(3) \times T(T(5))) + (4)) \times (T(7) + T(6))$
35478 := $(3 + ((-T(5)) \times T(T(4))) \times (-7 - T(8)))$
35483 := $((3 + 5) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(3))))$
35484 := $((T(T(T(3) + (5)))) + (T(4) \times T(T(8)))) \times 4$
35486 := $((T(3) + (5)) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(8)) - (T(6))))$
35489 := $((-T((T(3) + T(5)))) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(8) \times T(T(9)))$
35496 := $(-((T(3) - T(54)) \times (T(9) - T(6))))$
35532 := $((-T(3)) - T(T(5))) \times ((T(T(5)) + T(T(3))) \times (-2))$
35547 := $((T(T(T(3) + (5)))) - (T(T(5)))) \times (T(4) + (7))$
35558 := $((T(3) + T(55)) \times (T(5) + 8))$
35568 := $(T((3 + T(5))) \times ((5 + T(6)) \times 8))$
35574 := $(T(T(T(3))) \times ((55 \times T(7))/T(4)))$
35580 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(55)) + (T(80)))$
35583 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(5) + T(5)))) - (T(T(8))))/3$
35586 := $((T((T(T(3)) + (5))) \times T(5)) + (T(T(8)))) \times 6$
35589 := $(-T(3)) + ((T(T(5)) + (5)) + T(T(8))) \times T(9))$
35595 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T(5)) + (T(5) \times T((9 + 5))))$
35597 := $(3 + ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(5) + 9))) - T(T(7))))$
35616 := $(-((T(T(3) \times T(5))) - ((T(61) \times T(6))))$
35619 := $(-T(T(3)) - ((T(5) + T(6)) \times T((-1) + T(9))))$
35634 := $(-T(3)) + (((-T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times 3) \times T(T(4)))$
35637 := $(3 \times ((T(T(5) \times 6)) \times 3) - T(T(7)))$
35652 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6))) + T(T((T(5) - T(2))))$
35655 := $((T((T(3) + (5))) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))) + (T(5))$
35667 := $(-T(3)) + ((T(T(5)) + (T(6))) \times T((-6) + T(7)))$
35672 := $((35 + T(6)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2))))$
35673 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times T(((T(6) + (7)) - T(3))))$
35676 := $(3 + ((T(T(5)) + (T(6))) \times T((T(7) - (6))))$
35679 := $(-T(3)) - ((T((T(T(5)) - (T(6)))) \times (-7)) - T(T(9)))$
35682 := $((-T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(6)) + (82))$
35685 := $((3 + (T((5 + 6)) \times T(8))) \times T(5))$
35688 := $((T((T(3) \times 5)) + (6 \times T(T(8)))) \times 8)$
35694 := $(-T(3)) - (T((T(5) + (69))) \times (-T(4)))$
35697 := $((T(3) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(6))) \times (T(9) + T(7))$
35724 := $((T(T(3) \times 5)) - (7)) \times T((2 + T(4)))$
35728 := $((-((3 + 5)) \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(2) + 8))$
35734 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(5)) + T(7))) + T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))$
35739 := $(-T(T(3)) - (T(T(5)) \times ((7^3) - T(9))))$
35742 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(57) + T(T(4))) - T(T(2))))$

- 35745** := $((-3 - T(5) + 7^4) \times T(5))$
35748 := $((3 + (T(5) \times T((7 + 4)))) \times T(8))$
35750 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T((T(5) + T(7)))) \times (-50))$
35753 := $(3 + ((T(T(5)) - T(T(7))) \times (-5^3)))$
35763 := $(T((T(3) \times T(5))) + (T(T(7)) \times T((6 + T(3)))))$
35768 := $((T((3 \times 5)) + T(T(7))) \times 68)$
35769 := $((T(T(3)) + (T(57) \times T(6)))) + T(T(9))$
35770 := $((T(T(3)) \times 5) + T(T(7))) \times 70$
35774 := $((T((3 + T(5))) + T(T(7))) \times (7 + T(T(4))))$
35777 := $((T((T(3) \times 5)) \times 77) - T(7))$
35779 := $((T(T(3)) + T((T(5) + T(7)))) \times (T(7) + 9))$
35783 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-5 - (T(T(7)) \times 8)))/(-T(T(3))))$
35784 := $((T(3) + (T(5) \times T(7))) \times 84)$
35785 := $((3 \times 5) + T(T(7))) \times 85$
35787 := $(T((T(3) \times 5)) + (T(T(7)) \times 87))$
35791 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-5)) + (T(T(7)) \times 91))$
35794 := $-(((T(T(3)) - T(T(5))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(9))) - T(T(4)))$
35805 := $((T(3) + 5) \times (T(80) + T(5)))$
35823 := $((T(3) - T(T(5))) + (((T(8) - T(2))^3))$
35824 := $-((T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(5)) \times T((8 \times T(2)))) + T(T(4))))$
35826 := $((-3 + T(58) - 2) \times T(6))$
35828 := $((T(T(3)) + 5) \times T((T(8) + ((2 \times 8))))$
35829 := $((3 \times T((T(5) + T(8)))) + T(2)) \times 9$
35832 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-5)) + (((T(8) - 3)^{T(2)}))$
35835 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-5 + T(8))) + T(3)) \times 5$
35838 := $((3 + (T(5) \times T(8))) \times T((3 + 8)))$
35841 := $((-3 - T(T(5))) + (T(T(8)) \times (T(T(4)) - 1)))$
35844 := $-((T(3) - (T(5) + T(84)) \times T(4)))$
35847 := $(3 \times ((T(58) - 4) \times 7))$
35848 := $(((-T(3) - T(T(5))) \times (-T(8))) - T(T(4))) \times 8$
35849 := $-((T(T(3)) - ((5 + T(T(8))) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(9))))$
35852 := $(T(T((-3 + T(5)))) + ((8^5) + T(2)))$
35853 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(58)) - T((T(5) - 3)))$
35856 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - (T(8) \times (5 - T(T(6))))$
35862 := $((-3 + T(58)) \times T(6)) - T(T(2))$
35864 := $((-3 + T(58)) \times T(6)) - 4$
35865 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(58)) - T((6 + 5)))$
35868 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(58) - T(-(6 - 8))))$
35874 := $-((T(T(3)) - (T(5) \times (-8 - 7^4))))$
35875 := $((T(T(T(3))) - ((T((T(5) + T(8))) \times T(T(7)))))/(-T(5)))$
35879 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(58)) - (7 + T(9)))$
35883 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(58)) - (8 \times T(3)))$
35884 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(58)) + 8) - T(T(4))$
35885 := $(T(T((-3 + T(5)))) + (T(8) + (8^5)))$
35886 := $(T(3) + ((5 \times 8) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(6))))$
35888 := $((T(T(3)) + T((58 + T(8)))) \times 8$
35889 := $((T(3) + T(5)) \times ((8 + T(T(8))) + T(T(9))))$
35892 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(58)) - T(9)) + T(T(2))$
35898 := $((-T(3)) \times (5 + (T(T(8)) \times (-9)))) - T(8)$
35916 := $((T(-((T(T(3)) - T(T(5)))))) + (T(T(9)) + 1)) \times 6$
35917 := $((T(3) - T(T(5))) \times T(9) - 1) \times (-7)$
35922 := $((T(-((T(T(3)) - T(T(5)))))) + (T(T(9)) + 2)) \times T(T(2))$
35924 := $((-T(T(3))) + ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(9) - T(T(2)))))) - (T(T(4))))$
35925 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(-((T(5) - T(9)))))/T(2)) + (T(T(5)))$
35928 := $((-35 + T(T(9))) - 2) \times T(8)$
35931 := $(T(T(3)) \times T((T(5) + T(9)) - (3 - 1)))$
35934 := $-(((T(3)^5) - (T(93) \times T(4))))$
35937 := $((3 - T(5)) + T(9))^{T(3)/7}$
35938 := $-(((T(T(3)) + 5) + ((-9) \times T(3)) \times T(T(8))))$
35945 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((T(5) + T(9)))) - T((T(T(4)) + (T(5))))$
35949 := $-((T(T(T(3))) - ((T(T(5)) - (T(T(9)) \times 4)) \times (-9)))$
35952 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T((T(5) + T(9))) - T(T(5))) + 2))$
35955 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times T((T(9) + 5)))/5$
35958 := $(-T(3)) + ((59 - 5) \times T(T(8)))$
35962 := $((T(T((3 + 5))) \times (9 \times 6)) - 2)$
35964 := $((T((3 + 5)) \times T(T(9))) - (6^4))$
35965 := $(-35) + (T((T(9) - T(6))) \times T(T(5)))$
35972 := $((35 \times T(T(9))) - T((T(7) - T(T(2))))$
35973 := $(3 \times ((T(T(5)) + T(9)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(3)))$
35974 := $-((T(T(T(3))) - (-5) \times ((T(T(9)) \times (-7)) + 4)))$
35975 := $((35 \times (T(T(9)) - 7)) - 5)$
35977 := $(-3) - (-5) \times ((T(T(9)) - 7) \times 7)$
35979 := $-((T(T(3)) - (-5) \times ((T(T(9)) \times (-7)) + T(9))))$
35982 := $((T(T(3)) - T(5)) \times ((9 \times T(T(8))) + T(2)))$
35984 := $((-T(3)) \times (-5) + (-9) \times T(T(8))) - T(4)$
35985 := $((-35 + T(T(9))) \times T(8)) - T(5)$
35986 := $((35 \times T(T(9))) - 8) - T(T(6))$
35987 := $((-T(3)) \times (-5) + (-9) \times T(T(8))) - 7$
35989 := $-((T(T(T(3))) - (-5) - ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(8))) + T(T(9))))$
35994 := $(T(3) \times (5 - (-9) \times T(9 \times 4)))$
35997 := $(-3) + (-5) \times (T(9) + (T(T(9)) \times (-7)))$
36000 := $(T(3) \times 6000)$
36018 := $((-T(3) - 60)) \times (1 + T(T(8)))$
36036 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T((60 - T(3))) + T(T(6))))$
36057 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(60) - T(T(5))) + 7))$
36120 := $((T((3 \times 6)) + 1) \times T(20))$
36127 := $((T(T(T(3)) - T((T(6) - 1))))^2) + (T(T(7)))$
36134 := $((3 + 6) \times T(T(13))) - T(T(T(4)))$
36144 := $(T(3) \times ((-T(6)) - T((-1) + T(T(4)))) \times (-4))$
36162 := $((T(T(3)) + T(6)) \times T((-1) + (T(6) \times 2)))$
36183 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(61) + (-8) \times T(T(3))))$
36189 := $((T(T(3 + 6)) - 1) \times T(8)) - T(T(9))$
36192 := $(-T((T(3) + 6))) \times (1 - T((9 + T(T(2))))$
36195 := $((T(3) + (-6 + 1)) \times T(T(9))) \times (-5)$

- 36197** := (((36 - 1) × T(T(9))) - T(7))
36219 := (-T(3)) + (((6²) - 1) × T(T(9)))
36225 := (T(T(3+6))) × (T(2) + (2⁵))
36231 := (T(T(T(3))) + (T((T(6) + T(2))) × T(T((T(3) - 1))))))
36234 := -((T(T(T(3))) - ((T((6²) - 3) × T(T(4))))))
36240 := ((3 + T((T(6) × 2))) × 40)
36246 := (T(T(3)) × ((T(62) + (4)) - T(T(6))))
36248 := ((T(T(3)) + (6/T(2))) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(8)))
36249 := (3 + (T(6) × (T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(9))))))
36252 := ((T((3 × T(6))) - 2) × (T(5) + T(2)))
36255 := ((T((T(3) + (6))) × T((2 × T(5)))) - (T(5)))
36261 := ((T(3) + T(T(6))) × T((2 + T((6 - 1))))))
36264 := (3 + ((T(T(6)) + T(T(2))) × T((T(6) - (4))))))
36267 := (3 × ((6 × T((T(2) × T(6)))) - (7)))
36282 := ((T(T(3)) × ((6^{T(2)}) × 8)) - T(T(2)))
36284 := ((T(T(3)) × ((6^{T(2)}) × 8)) - (4))
36285 := ((T((T(3) + (6))) × T(-((T(T(2)) - T(8)))) + T(5))
36288 := ((T(3) × T(6)) × 288)
36294 := (-T(3)) × ((T((6²) × (-9)) - T(T(4)))
36315 := ((T(T(T(T(T(3))/T(6)))) + (T((T(T(3)) - 1)))) × T(5))
36324 := (-T(3)) - (-T(6) × (T((T(T(3)) - 2)) + T(T(T(4))))))
36344 := -((T(T(T(3))) - ((T((6 × T(3))) × T(T(4))) - T(T(4))))))
36345 := (((T(36) - 3) × T(T(4))) - T(T(5)))
36355 := (((3 + T((T(6) + 3))) × T(T(5))) - (5))
36369 := ((T(3) + T(6)) × (T(T(3)) + T((6 + T(9))))))
36372 := (((T(3) × T(63)) + T(7)) × T(2))
36375 := (((3 + T(63)) + T(T(7))) × T(5))
36378 := ((T(3) × T(T(6))) + ((T(3)⁷)/8))
36384 := (((T(3) - T(T(6))) - T(T(3))) + (T(T(8)) × T(T(4))))
36396 := (-T(3)) × (((T(6) + 3) - T(T(9))) × 6)
36410 := ((T(36) - (4)) × T(10))
36420 := ((T(36) × T(T(4))) - (T(20)))
36421 := -((T(T(T(3))) - ((-T(T(6))) + T(T(T(4)))) × T((T(T(2)) + 1))))
36423 := ((3 + (T(6) × T(4))) × T((T(2) × T(3))))
36424 := (((-3) + T(T(6))) × T((-4) + T(T(T(2)))))) + T(T(T(4)))
36427 := (((T(36) × T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7)))
36429 := (-T(3)) + ((T(6) × T(T(T(4)))) + (T((2 × T(9))))))
36432 := ((3 + T((T(6) - T(4)))) × T(32))
36435 := (((-((3⁶) × T(4)) + 3) × (-5))
36438 := (-((T(3) + T(6))) - (T(T(4)) × (3 - T(T(8))))))
36442 := (T(3) - ((-T(6)) × T(T(T(4)))) - (4^{T(T(2))}))
36444 := (-T(T(3))) + ((T(6) - (4)) × T((T(4) + T(T(4))))))
36448 := (((-T(3)) - T(T(6))) + T(T(4))) + (T(T(4)) × T(T(8))))
36462 := (T(3) + ((T(6) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(6) + T(2))))
36464 := (((3 + T(6)) × T(T(T(4)))) - (T((T(6) + T(4))))))
36465 := (((T(3) + T(6)) - T(4)) × T(65))
36468 := (((3 + T(T(6))) × T((-4) + T(6))) + T(T(8)))
36474 := ((((-T(3)) - T(T(6))) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(7)) - T(4))
36477 := ((3 + 6) × ((T(4) × T(T(7))) - (7)))
36492 := (((-((3⁶)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(9)) - T(2))
36495 := (((-((3⁶) × T(4)) - 9) × (-5))
36498 := ((T(T(3)) + (T(6))) × (T((-4) + T(9))) + 8))
36528 := ((T((T(T(T(3))) - T((T(6) - (5)))) + T(T(2))) × 8)
36534 := (3 + ((6 + 5) × T((3⁴))))
36537 := (-3) + (((6 × 5) × 3) × T(T(7)))
36543 := (3 + ((6 × T(5)) × T(T((4 + 3))))))
36544 := (-T(3)) + (T(((6 × 5) + T(T(4)))) × T(4))
36547 := (((T(T(3)) × (T(T(6)) + (T(5)))) + T(T(4))) × 7)
36549 := (((T(T(3)) + T((6 × T(5)))) - T(T(4))) × 9)
36555 := ((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T((6 + 5))) - (5))) × T(5))
36561 := (T(T(3)) + ((6 × T(5)) × T(T((6 + 1))))))
36564 := -((T((T(T(T(3)))/T(6))) - (T((T(5) + T(6))) × T(T(4))))))
36567 := ((T(3) + T(6)) - ((T(5) × (-6)) × T(T(7))))
36573 := (-3) - (-6) × ((T(5) × T(T(7))) + (T(3))))
36574 := ((T(T(3)) × (T(65) - T(T(7)))) + T(T(4)))
36576 := (T(-((3 - 6))) × ((T(5) × T(T(7))) + (6)))
36579 := (-T(3)) + (((6 × T(5)) × T(T(7))) + T(9))
36585 := (((3 × T(T((-6) + T(5)))) - (T(T(8)))) × T(5))
36588 := (-T(3)) - ((T(T((-6) + T(5))) × (-T(8))) + (T(T(8))))
36589 := (-((T(36) + (5))) + (T(8) × T(T(9))))
36594 := (T((3 × 6)) × (T(T(5)) + (94)))
36615 := ((T(T(T(3))) + (T(66) - 1)) × T(5))
36624 := (-T(3)) + (T((6 × T((6/2)))) × T(T(4)))
36625 := ((T(36) × T(T((6 - 2)))) - (5))
36627 := (-3) + (T((6 × 6)) × T((T(2) + (7))))
36642 := (T(3) + ((T((6 × 6)) × T(T(4))) + T(T(2))))
36645 := ((T(36) × T((6 + 4))) + T(5))
36648 := ((T(T((3 + 6))) - (T(6) - (4))) × T(8))
36651 := (T(T(3)) + (T((6 × 6)) × T(T((5 - 1))))))
36654 := ((3 + T(6)) + (T((T(6) + T(5))) × T(T(4))))
36673 := (T((T((T(3) + (6)))/6)) × (T(T(7)) - 3))
36675 := ((T(3) - T(T(6))) × ((-6) × T(7)) + (5))
36684 := (((3 + 6) × 6) + (T(T(8)) × T(T(4))))
36693 := (((T(3) × T(66)) - T(T(9))) × 3)
36723 := ((T(T(T(3))) × (T(T(6)) - 72)) - T(3))
36725 := ((T(-((T(3) - T(6)))) - 7) × T(25))
36726 := (-3) + ((T(T(6)) - 72) × T(T(6)))
36729 := (T(T(3)) × (-T(6) + T((-7) + T((2 + 9))))))
36735 := (((-T(3)) - T(T(6))) × ((T(7) + 3) × (-5)))
36744 := (-T(3)) - ((T(T(6)) - T(T(7))) × T((T(4) + T(4))))
36745 := (((-3) × T((T(6) + T(7)))) × (-T(4))) - (5))
36748 := (-T(3)) + ((6 + T(7)) × T((T(4) + T(8))))
36764 := (((3 - T(T(6))) × (T(7) × (-6))) - T(T(T(4))))

- 36765** := $((-((T(3) - T(6))) \times ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (T(5))))$
36775 := $((-T(3 \times 6)) + (T(T(7)) \times T((T(7) - T(5))))$
36784 := $((-T(3)) \times T(T(6))) - ((-T(7) - T(T(8))) \times T(T(4)))$
36789 := $((-3) + ((T(6) - 7) \times T((8 \times 9)))$
36792 := $((T(T(3)) + T(T(6))) \times ((T(7) + T(9)) \times 2))$
36795 := $((T(3) \times T((T(6) + T(7)))) + 9) \times 5$
36798 := $(T(3) + ((T(6) - 7) \times T((9 \times 8))))$
36816 := $(T((T(3) + 6))) \times (T((T(8) + 1)) - T(T(6)))$
36819 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-T(6))) + (T(8) \times T(T((1 \times 9))))$
36828 := $((((3 + T(6)) \times 8)^2) - T(8))$
36834 := $((-((T(3) \times T(6))) + ((T(T(8)) + (T(3))) \times T(T(4))))$
36852 := $((-3) - (-T((6 + 8))) \times T((5 + T(T(2))))$
36855 := $((3 + 6) \times T((85 + 5)))$
36864 := $((3 + T(6)) \times 8)^{6-4}$
36876 := $((T(3) \times T(T(6))) - T(8)) + T(T(7)) \times T(6)$
36879 := $((-T(T(3)) + (T((68 - T(7))) \times (-T(9))))$
36882 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(6))) + (T(8) \times T(8))) \times T(T(2))$
36894 := $(3 \times ((T(T(6)) \times (8 + T(9))) + T(T(4))))$
36897 := $(3 \times ((T(T(6)) \times T(T((8/9)))) - (T(T(7))))$
36909 := $((T(-(3 - 6))) + (T(90))) \times 9$
36912 := $((3 + T(6)) \times (T(T(9 + 1))) - 2)$
36918 := $((3 \times T(T(6))) + (T(T(9)) \times (-1 + T(8))))$
36924 := $((-T(3)) - (-6 \times ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(4))))$
36936 := $((T(3)^{-6+9}) \times T((3 \times 6)))$
36942 := $((-T(3)) \times (((-6) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(4))) - 2)$
36944 := $((-T(3)) - ((T(6) - T(9)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(4))$
36945 := $((3 + T(6)) \times T((T(9) + T(4)))) - (T(5))$
36947 := $((T(3)/6) + (T((9 + 4)) \times T(T(7))))$
36948 := $((-T(3)) \times ((-6) \times (T(T(9)) - T(4)) - 8))$
36951 := $(T(T(T(3))) - ((-6) \times T(9)) \times T((T(5) + 1)))$
36954 := $((-T(3)) + (T(T(6)) \times ((T(9) - 5) \times 4)))$
36955 := $((3 + T(6)) \times T(T(T(9 - 5)))) - 5$
36957 := $((-3) + ((T(6) + T(T(9))) \times (5 \times 7)))$
36966 := $((-T(3)) - (-((T(6) - 9) \times T(T((6 + 6))))$
36967 := $(T(T(3)) + (T((T((6 - 9)/6)) \times T(T(7))))$
36969 := $((-T(T(3)) - (-6 \times ((T(T(9)) \times (-6)) + T(9))))$
36972 := $((-T(3)) - T(T(6))) \times (-((T(9) + 7) \times T(2)))$
36974 := $((T((3 \times 6)/9) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4))))$
36975 := $((T(3) - T((6 + T(9)))) \times (-T(7))) + (T(5))$
36978 := $(T(3) + ((T(6) - 9) \times T(78)))$
36981 := $(T(T(3)) - ((T(6) + T(T(9))) \times (-T(8) - 1)))$
36984 := $((-T(3)) \times ((-6) \times T(T(9))) + (T(8) + T(4)))$
36987 := $((-T(T((T(3) + 6))) - (T((T(9) + 8)) \times T(7)))$
36990 := $((-T(3)) \times ((-6) \times T(T(9))) + T((9 + 0)))$
36991 := $((3^6) \times T(9)) + T(91)$
36992 := $((-T(3)) \times ((-6) \times T(T(9))) + T(9)) + 2$
36993 := $(3 + (((6 \times T(T(9))) - T(9)) \times T(3)))$
36994 := $((-T(3)) \times ((-6) \times T(T(9))) + T(9)) + (4)$
36995 := $((-T(3)) \times ((-6) \times T(T(9))) + T(9)) + (5)$
36996 := $(T(3) + (((6 \times T(T(9))) - T(9)) \times 6))$
36997 := $((-T(3)) \times ((-6) \times T(T(9))) + T(9)) + (7)$
36998 := $((-T(3)) \times ((-6) \times T(T(9))) + T(9)) + 8$
36999 := $((T(36) \times (9 + T(9))) + T(T(9)))$
37026 := $(T((T(T(T(3)))/7)) \times T((T(T(T(T(02))))/T(6))))$
37044 := $((T(T(3))^{7-04}) \times 4)$
37054 := $((-T(T(T(3))) - ((T(70) \times T(5)) + T(4))))$
37065 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(70) + (-6) \times T(T(5))))$
37092 := $((-T(3)) \times (T(7) - (T(T(09)) \times T(T(2))))$
37095 := $(((-3) + T(70)) - 9) \times T(5)$
37125 := $((-3) + T(7)) \times T((-1 + T((2 \times 5))))$
37128 := $((T((3 + 7)) + 1) \times (-T(2) + T(T(8))))$
37134 := $(T(3) + (T(7) \times T((T(T(1 + 3))) - (4))))$
37146 := $(((-3) + T(7)) \times T((-1 + T(T(4)))) + (T(6)))$
37149 := $(T(T(3)) + (T(7) \times T((T(-(1 - 4)) + T(9))))$
37164 := $(T(3) \times (-T(T(7))) + (T(T(-(1 - 6))) \times T(T(4))))$
37173 := $((3^7) \times 17) - T(3)$
37177 := $(T(T(T(3))) - (-T(((7 - 1) + 7))) \times T(T(7)))$
37188 := $((-3) + (T(7) \times (1 + T(8)))) \times T(8)$
37191 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T((7 - 1))) + T(T((9 + 1))))$
37212 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T(T((7 + T(2)))) + 1) \times T(T(T(2))))$
37213 := $((-T(3)) + ((T(T(7)) + T(2)) \times T(13)))$
37218 := $((-T(3)) - ((T(T(7 + 2)) - 1) \times (-T(8))))$
37219 := $((3 + T(T(7))) \times T((T(2) + (1 + 9))))$
37224 := $((T(T(T(3)))/7) \times T((-((2^{T(2)})) + T(T(4))))$
37225 := $(T(3) + ((T(T(7)) + T(2)) \times T((-2) + T(5))))$
37229 := $((-3) - T(7)) + (T((2^{T(2)})) \times T(T(9)))$
37233 := $((3 + T(((T(7) \times 2) + 3))) \times T(T(3)))$
37234 := $((-T(3)) + (T(7) \times ((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
37237 := $((-3) - ((7 \times T((-2) + T(T(3)))) \times (-T(7)))$
37238 := $((T(3) - T(7)) + (T(T((T(2) \times 3))) \times T(8)))$
37239 := $(3 \times (-7) + (T(23) \times T(9)))$
37243 := $(3 + (T(7) \times ((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(3))))$
37244 := $((T(3) \times ((T(7) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 4)) - T(T(T(4))))$
37246 := $((T(T(T(3)))/7)^{T(2)} + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(6))$
37247 := $((3 + T(T(7))) \times T((T(2) + T(4))) + T(7))$
37248 := $(T(((3 + 7)^2) - 4)) \times 8$
37254 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(7) \times (-2)) + T((T(5) \times 4))))$
37255 := $((T((-3) + T(7))) - (T(T(2))^5)) \times (-5)$
37257 := $((-3) + (T(T((7 + 2))) \times T((T(5) - 7))))$
37259 := $(T(37) \times ((T(2) + 5) + T(9)))$
37274 := $((T(T(3) + 7)) \times (T(2) + T(T(7)))) + T(T(4))$
37275 := $(T((-3) + T(7)) + T((2 + 7))) \times T(5)$
37281 := $(T(T(3)) - (T(T((7 + 2))) \times (T(8) \times (-1))))$

- 37284** := $((-3) - ((7 \times 2) \times T(T(8)))) \times 4$
37285 := $(-T(3) + (((T(7) \times 2) \times T(T(8))) - 5))$
37288 := $((T(3) \times T(7)) / T(2)) \times T(T(8)) - 8$
37289 := $((3 + T(7)) - 2) + (T(8) \times T(T(9)))$
37293 := $((-3) + T(T(7))) - 2 \times 93$
37296 := $(37 \times ((T(2) + T(9)) \times T(6)))$
37298 := $(-((T(3) + T(7))) + ((2 + T(T(9))) \times T(8)))$
37299 := $(-((T(3) - ((T(7)^2) + T(9)) \times T(9))))$
37317 := $(T(T(3)) \times (7 + T((31 + T(7))))$
37323 := $((T(T(T(3))) / 7)^3 - (-T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
37324 := $((-T(T(3))) + T((T(7) + T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)))$
37338 := $((T(T(3)) + T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(38)))$
37349 := $(-T((-3) + T(7))) - (T(T(3 + T(4)))) \times (-9))$
37352 := $(T((T(T(3)) + 7)) \times ((T(3) \times T(5)) + 2))$
37359 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (T(7) \times T((T(3) + (5 \times 9))))$
37362 := $(T(3) \times (-T(T(7))) + (3 \times T(T((T(6)) / T(T(T(2))))))$
37365 := $((T(3) + T((7 + (3 \times T(6)))) \times T(5))$
37368 := $((T(T(3)) / 7) + T(T(3 + 6))) \times T(8)$
37382 := $(T(3) + (73 \times (8^{T(2)})))$
37387 := $((T(T(3)) + T(7)) \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(8)) + 7))$
37392 := $((-((T(3) - T(7))) - (-T(3) \times T(T(9)))) \times T(T(2)))$
37394 := $(-((T(T(3) + 7))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(9) \times 4)))$
37395 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-T(7))) + T(T(3 + 9))) \times T(5)$
37398 := $(T(3) \times (-7) + (T(39) \times 8))$
37410 := $(T(((3 + T(7)) + T(T(4)))) \times 10)$
37416 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(7)) + T(T(4))) - 1) \times 6$
37419 := $((-3) + T(7)) \times T(T(T(4))) - T((1 + T(9)))$
37421 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times ((-T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(2))) - 1)$
37422 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T((7 + 4)) \times (T(2)^{T(2)}))$
37423 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((7 + T(4)))) + T(2^{T(3)}))$
37425 := $(3 - (T((-T(7)) + T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(5))))$
37428 := $(T(3) - ((-T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(2) - T(8)))$
37429 := $(T(T(3)) + (-T(7)) \times (-T(4)) - T((T(T(2)) + T(9))))$
37434 := $(3 \times (-7) - ((-4) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
37443 := $(3 + ((T(7) - T(4)) \times T(4^3)))$
37446 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(7)) + T(T(4))) + 4) \times 6$
37449 := $(3 \times ((-T((7 + T(4)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 9)$
37452 := $(-T(3)) \times (((T(T(7)) + T(4)) \times (-T(5))) - 2)$
37455 := $((-3) + T((7 \times T(4)))) + (T(5)) \times T(5)$
37458 := $((T(T(3)) / 7) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(T(8))))$
37464 := $(-T(3)) \times (((-T(7)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(6)) \times 4)$
37465 := $((-3) + T(7)) \times T(T(T(4))) - T(T((-6) + T(5)))$
37468 := $((T((3 + T(7))) + T(T(4))) \times 68)$
37479 := $((-3) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(4)) + (-7) + T(9))$
37482 := $((T((T(3) + T(7))) \times (T(T(4)) + 8)) - T(2))$
37485 := $(T((T(3) + T(7))) \times (48 + T(5)))$
37486 := $((T(3) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(8))) - (6)$
37488 := $((-T(3)) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(4) \times T(T(8)))) - T(8))$
37491 := $((T(3) + T(T(7))) \times T((4 + 9))) - 1$
37492 := $((T(3) + T(T(7))) \times (T(4) + (9^2)))$
37495 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(7)) + (-4) + T(T(9))) \times 5$
37498 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(7) / 4) + (T(T(9)) \times T(8))))$
37499 := $(T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(4 + 9)) \times 9)))$
37515 := $(-((T(T(3)) - (T((T(7) - 5))) \times T((1 + T(5))))))$
37524 := $((T(37) + 5) \times (-2) + T(T(4)))$
37527 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (T(T((-7) + T(5)))) \times (2 \times T(7)))$
37528 := $((T(3) + T(T(7))) \times T((T(5) - 2))) + T(8)$
37539 := $((-T(3)) \times ((T(T(7)) \times (-T(5))) + T(3))) + T(T(9))$
37542 := $(T(3) - (T((T(7) - 5))) \times (-T(4^2)))$
37548 := $((3 \times T(T(7))) - T(T(5))) - T(T(4)) \times T(8)$
37551 := $(3 + (T(7) \times (T(5) + T(51))))$
37555 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T(7)) \times (T(T(5)) + (5 \times 5)))$
37568 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T((T(7) + T((5 + 6)))) \times 8$
37569 := $((T(3) \times T(T(7))) \times T(5) - 6) + T(T(9))$
37575 := $((T(3 + T(7))) + 5) \times 75$
37576 := $((-3) + T((T(7) - T(5)))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(6))$
37577 := $(-T(3)) + (T((T(7) - T(5))) \times (T(T(7)) + 7))$
37582 := $(T(3) + (T(7) \times ((5 + T(T(8))) \times 2)))$
37583 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T((T(5) + 8))) / 3)$
37593 := $(3 \times ((T(T(T(7) - T(5)))) - 9) \times 3)$
37594 := $((T(T(T(3) + 7))) - T(5)) \times 9 + (T(T(4)))$
37596 := $((T(3) \times T(T(7))) \times T(5) + T(T(9))) + T(6)$
37597 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) - (((-7) \times T(T(5))) \times (-T(9))) + T(7))))$
37599 := $(T(3) + ((T(T(T(7) - T(5)))) - 9) \times 9)$
37625 := $((T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(7))) \times ((-T(T(6))) + T(T(T(2)))) - 5)$
37626 := $(-((T(3) + ((T(7) \times T(6)) \times (-2^6))))$
37628 := $((-37) + T(T(6)))^2 - 8$
37629 := $((-3) + T(T(7 + 6))) - 2 \times 9$
37631 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) \times (-T(3)))) - 1)$
37632 := $(T((T(3) + (7 \times 6))) \times 32)$
37638 := $((3 \times T(T(7 + 6))) \times 3) - T(8)$
37642 := $(-((T(3) - T(7))) \times T((T(6 + 4)) + T(2)))$
37650 := $((-3) + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(50))$
37653 := $(-((T(T(3)) - (T(T(7 + 6))) \times (T(5) - T(3))))$
37655 := $(-((T(T(T(3)) + T(7))) - ((6^5) \times 5)))$
37656 := $(3 + (((T(7) \times 6) - 5) \times T(T(6))))$
37657 := $(-3) + ((T((T(7) + T(6))) + T(T(5))) \times T(7))$
37659 := $(T(3) + (-7) \times (T(6) + (T(T(5)) \times (-T(9))))$
37668 := $(-T(3)) - ((7 \times 6) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(8))))$
37669 := $((3 + T(T(7))) + ((6 \times 6) \times T(T(9))))$
37674 := $((3 \times T(T(7 + 6))) \times (7 - 4))$
37675 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (T((T(7) - 6))) \times (T(7) + T(T(5))))$
37684 := $((T(3) \times 7) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(8)))) + T(4)$
37692 := $(T(T(3)) + ((T(T(7 + 6))) \times 9) - T(2))$

- 37695** := $((T(T(3)) + ((T(7) \times (-6)) \times T(9))) \times (-5))$
37716 := $(T(3) \times (T(T(7)) - ((-T(7)) \times T((-1) + T(6))))$
37723 := $((T((T(3) + (7))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(3))))$
37728 := $(T(3) \times (((T(7) \times T(7)) + 2) \times 8))$
37729 := $(T((3 + 7)) - (T(T(7 + T(T(2)))))) \times (-9))$
37737 := $(3 \times ((T(T(7)) \times (T(7) + 3)) - (7)))$
37749 := $(-T(3)) + (((T(7) \times T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times T(9))$
37752 := $(-((T(3) - T(7))) \times ((T(T(7)) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(2))))$
37755 := $(3 \times ((T((7 + 7)) \times T(T(5))) - (T(5))))$
37758 := $((-3) \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(7) - ((5 - 8)))$
37765 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(7)) - (7)) \times 65$
37779 := $-((T(T(3)) - ((T(T(7)) + T(T(7))) + T(7)) \times T(9)))$
37782 := $((((3 + T(7)) \times T(T(7))) + 8) \times T(2))$
37793 := $((T(T(3)) - (7)) \times T((T(7) + T(9)))) - T(T(3))$
37794 := $(-T(3)) + ((T(7) - T(T(7))) \times (-T(9) - T(T(4))))$
37797 := $(-3) + ((T(7) - T((7 + T(9)))) \times (-T(7)))$
37799 := $-((T((3 + T(7))) + (-T(7 + 9)) \times T(T(9))))$
37814 := $(T((37 + T(8))) \times 14)$
37815 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((7 + 8))) + 1) \times T(5)$
37818 := $((T(T(3)) + T((T(7) + T(8)))) \times 18)$
37819 := $(T((T(3) + T(7))) + (T(8) \times (-1) + T(T(9))))$
37820 := $(T(((3 + T(7)) + T(8))) \times 20)$
37822 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) - (T(7)))) + ((-T(8)) + T(T(T(T(2))))^2))$
37824 := $((T(T(3 + 7))) + T(8)) \times 24$
37828 := $((T(T(3)) + T(7)) \times (-8 + T((T(2) + T(8))))$
37830 := $((T((T(3) + T(7))) + T(T(8))) \times 30)$
37834 := $(-T(3)) + (((T(7) + T(T(8))) - (T(3))) \times T(T(4)))$
37835 := $(T(((3 + 7) + T(8))) \times 35)$
37836 := $((T(T(3)) - T(T(7))) - T(T(8))) \times (-36)$
37839 := $(-T(3)) - ((T(T(7)) + T((8 + T(T(3)))))) \times (-T(9))$
37850 := $((T((T(3) + (7))) + T(T(8))) \times 50)$
37855 := $(T((T(T(3)) + T(7))) - (T(T(8)) \times (-55)))$
37856 := $((-((3 + 7)) - T(T(8))) \times (-56))$
37857 := $-((T(T(T(3))) - (((T(T(7)) + 8) \times (T(T(5)) - T(7))))))$
37859 := $(3 + (-7) \times (-8 + (T(T(5)) \times (-T(9))))$
37860 := $((T((T(3) + T(7))) + T(8)) \times 60)$
37863 := $(3 \times (((T(T(7)) - T(8)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(3))))$
37869 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-7)) - (T(8) \times (-T(6) - T(T(9))))$
37874 := $-((T((T(T(3)) + (7))) - (T(87) \times T(4))))$
37877 := $(T(T(3)) - ((T(T(7)) + T((T(8) + (7)))))) \times (-T(7))$
37882 := $((-3) + T(T(7))) \times (88 + T(T(2)))$
37884 := $((3 \times T(T(7))) + T(8)) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(4)))$
37889 := $((-37) + T(T(8))) + (T(8) \times T(T(9)))$
37890 := $((T(T(3)) - T(T(7))) - T(8)) \times (-90)$
37891 := $(T((T(3) + T(7))) + (T(8) \times (T(T(9)) + 1)))$
37893 := $((T(T(3) \times T(7))) + T(T(8))) \times 9 - T(T(T(3)))$
37896 := $((T((3 + 7)) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(9))) + T(T(6))$
37897 := $(T((3 \times 7)) + ((T(8) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(7))))$
37898 := $-(((T(T(3)) + (7)) + ((-T(8)) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(8))))$
37905 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(7)) - T(9)) \times 05))$
37917 := $((37 \times T(T(9))) - T((-1) + T(7)))$
37932 := $((T(3) \times T(79)) + T(3)) \times 2$
37934 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(7)) \times 93) - T(T(4))))$
37935 := $((T(3) \times T(T(7))) + (93)) \times T(5)$
37941 := $-((T(T(3)) - (T((T(7) + 9)) \times (T(T(4)) - 1)))$
37944 := $((3 + T(7)) \times 9) \times T((4 \times 4))$
37946 := $((37 \times (T(T(9)) - T(4))) + (T(6)))$
37947 := $((3 + T(7)) \times T((T(9) + (4)))) - T(7)$
37953 := $(T(3) - (-7) \times ((T(9) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(3))))$
37954 := $-((T(T(T(3))) - (-7) \times ((-T(9)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(4))))$
37961 := $(T(37) \times (9 \times 6)) - 1$
37962 := $(T(37) \times 9) \times T((6/2))$
37963 := $(T(37) + (T(T(9)) \times (6 \times T(3))))$
37968 := $(T(T(3)) \times (-T(7) - ((T(9) + (6)) \times T(8))))$
37974 := $((T(T((T(3) + (7)))) \times 9) + (T((T(7) - (4))))$
37975 := $(T((T(T(3)) + T(7))) \times ((9 + 7) + T(5)))$
37978 := $((T(3) + T(7)) \times ((T(9) + T(T(7))) + T(T(8))))$
37983 := $((3 \times (T(7) - 9)) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(3))$
37989 := $((T(T(3)) + T(7)) + T(T(9))) \times T(8) - T(T(9))$
37992 := $(T(3) + T(79)) \times (9 + T(2))$
37994 := $-(((T(T(3)) \times T(T(7))) + ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(9))) + T(T(4))))$
37995 := $((37 \times T(T(9))) - T((9 + T(5))))$
37998 := $(T(37) \times (9 + T(9))) + T(8)$
38022 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T(8))^{02}) - T(2)$
38025 := $(T(T(T(3))) - T(8))^{-T(02)+5}$
38115 := $(T(T(T(3))) \times (T((8 + 1)) + T(15)))$
38133 := $((T(T(T(3))) - 8) \times T(((1 \times 3) \times T(3))))$
38136 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-8)) \times ((1 + 3) - T(T(6))))$
38139 := $(T(-((T(3) - T(8)))) + (T(T(13)) \times 9))$
38142 := $(3 \times ((8 + 1) - (-T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(T(2))))))$
38160 := $((T(3) + T((T(8) - 1))) \times 60)$
38164 := $(-T(3)) + ((T(T(8)) + T((1 + 6))) \times T(T(4)))$
38184 := $(-T(3)) \times (T(T(8)) - (T((1 + T(8))) \times T(4)))$
38193 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(8)) \times (19 \times 3)))$
38216 := $((T(T(T(3))) - (8^{T(2)})) \times (-T(16)))$
38220 := $(T((T(T(3)) - 8)) \times (2 \times T(20)))$
38223 := $(3 \times (T(8) + (T(T((2 + 2))) \times T(T(T(3))))))$
38226 := $((-((3^8)) + T((T(T(T(2))) - 2))) \times (-6))$
38229 := $(-3) + (T(8) \times ((T(2)^{T(2)}) + T(T(9))))$
38232 := $((T(3) + T((T(8)/2))) \times (T(3)^{T(2)}))$
38235 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T((8 + 2)) \times 3)) + (T(T(5))))$
38241 := $(-T(T(3))) \times ((8 - T((T(T(2)) \times T(4)))) + 1)$
38246 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T(8))^2) + (-T(4) + T(T(6)))$

- 38247** := $(T(T(T(3))) - ((T(8) \times (-2)) \times T((4 + T(7)))))$
38248 := $((T(T((T(T(3)) - 8))) + T(-((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(4)))))) \times 8)$
38249 := $((T(T(3)) + 8)^{T(2)} + (T(T(T(4))) \times 9))$
38250 := $(3 \times (8 + 2)) \times T(50)$
38255 := $((T(T((T(T(3)) - 8))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(5)))) \times 5$
38256 := $(3 \times 8) \times (-2) + T(56)$
38259 := $(3 + (T(8) \times (-2) + T(T(5)))) \times 9$
38262 := $(T(T(3)) \times (-8) + T(-((2 - 62))))$
38265 := $((3 \times T((T(8) \times 2))) - T(T(6))) \times 5$
38268 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-8)) \times (T(2) - T(T(6)))) - T(8)$
38272 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8))) \times (2^7)) / T(2)$
38274 := $(-T(3)) + ((T(T(8)) + (2 + T(7))) \times T(T(4)))$
38276 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(8)/2))) - T((T(7) + T(6))))$
38277 := $(-3) + (((T(T(8)) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(7))) / 7)$
38283 := $((T(T(3)) + T(8)) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(8)))) - T(T(3))$
38289 := $(-T(3)) + (((T(T(8)) \times (-2)) / (-T(8))) \times T(T(9)))$
38292 := $((3 + T(8) - 2) \times T(T(9))) - T(2)$
38293 := $((T(3) - ((T(T(8)) / T(T(2))) \times T(T(9)))) / (-3))$
38295 := $((3 + T(8) - 2) \times T(9 \times 5))$
38296 := $(T(3) + ((T(T(8)) / T(2)) \times T(T(9))) / 6)$
38298 := $(3 + (((T(T(8)) \times 2) \times T(T(9))) / T(8)))$
38304 := $(T(T(3)) \times (-T(8) - (T(30) \times 4)))$
38314 := $-((T(T(3)) - ((T(T(8)) + 31) \times T(T(4))))$
38322 := $((T(T(T(3))) + (T(8) \times T((T(3) \times T(2)))) \times T(T(2)))$
38324 := $((T(T(3 + 8))) / 3) \times (-T(2) + T(T(4)))$
38325 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(((T(8) - T(3)) \times 2) - (5)))$
38329 := $((3^8 \times T(3)) - 2) - T(T(9))$
38334 := $((-3) \times T(T(8))) \times (-3) - (-T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
38335 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(8))) + (((T(3))^{T(3)} - (5))))$
38338 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(83) / T(T(3)))) - 8)$
38343 := $(-3) + (T(83) \times (-T(4) + T(T(3))))$
38346 := $((-((T(3) - T(8))) + T((T(3) + T(4)))) \times T(T(6)))$
38347 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (8 \times T(T(3)))) - ((T(T(4)) + T(T(7))))$
38352 := $(T(3) + (T(83) \times (5 + T(T(2))))$
38355 := $((-3 - (8^3 \times 5)) \times T(5))$
38357 := $(3 + 8) \times (T(T((-3) + T(5))) + T(T(7)))$
38364 := $(-T((3 + 8))) + (T(T(3)) \times T((6 \times T(4))))$
38367 := $(3 + T((T(8) + 3))) \times (T(6) + T(7))$
38373 := $((-3 + T(8))^3 + (T(T(7)) \times T(3)))$
38374 := $((-T(3) + T(8)) + ((T(T(3)) - (7)^4))$
38376 := $(-T(3)) \times (((T(T(8)) - T(3))) + T(T(7))) \times (-6))$
38379 := $(3 + (T(8) \times ((3 + T(7)) + T(T(9))))$
38382 := $((T(T((T(T(3)) - 8))) + T(T((3 + 8)))) \times T(T(2)))$
38385 := $((3 \times T(T(8))) + T((-3) + T(8))) \times T(5)$
38391 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (-T(8)) \times (T(T(3)) - T((T(9) + 1))))$
38394 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(8)))) + (T(3) \times T(9))) / (-4)$
38395 := $-((T(T(3)) - ((8 + T(3))^{9-5}))$
38397 := $(T(T(3)) + (T(8) \times ((3 + T(T(9))) + T(7))))$
38408 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 - 08)$
38412 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 - 1) - T(2)$
38413 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 - (1 \times 3))$
38414 := $((-T(3)) \times ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(4)) + 1)) - T(T(T(4))))$
38415 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 - (1^5))$
38416 := $(T(3) + 8)^4 \times 1^6$
38417 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 + (1^7))$
38421 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 + T(T(2))) - 1$
38422 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 + T(2) + T(2))$
38423 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 + (T(T(T(2)))) / 3)$
38424 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 + (2 \times 4))$
38425 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 - T(T(2))) + (T(5))$
38426 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 + T(-((2 - 6))))$
38442 := $(3^8 + (T(T(T(4))) / (-T(4))) \times T(T(2)))$
38443 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(8)))) - T(4)) / (-4) - (T(T(3)))$
38444 := $((T(T(3)) + 8) \times T((-4) + T(T(4)))) - T(4)$
38445 := $(T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(8/4))) \times T(4))) + T(5)$
38447 := $((T(T(3)) + 8) \times T((-4) + T(T(4)))) - 7$
38448 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 + (4 \times 8))$
38451 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T((8 + 4) \times 5) + 1))$
38452 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 + T((5 + T(2))))$
38454 := $((-3) + T(T(8))) \times (4 + 54)$
38455 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(8)) \times T(T(4))) - (5^5)$
38459 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(8)))) + T(4)) / (5 - 9)$
38460 := $((T(T(3)) - T(T(8))) + (4)) \times (-60)$
38463 := $((-3) + T(8)) + (T((T(4) \times 6)) \times T(T(3)))$
38464 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(8)))) - T(4)) / (6 - T(4))$
38469 := $(3 + ((T(8) + T(4)) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(9)))$
38472 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 + (T(7) \times 2))$
38475 := $(3 \times T((8 + T(4)))) \times 75$
38478 := $(-T((3 + 8))) \times ((T(T(4)) + T(7)) - T(T(8)))$
38479 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 + (7 \times 9))$
38482 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 + T((8 + T(2))))$
38488 := $((T(3) + 8)^4 + T(8) + T(8))$
38493 := $(3 \times ((T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times T((9 - 3))))$
38497 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-8)) + (T(T(4)) \times T((9 + T(7))))$
38499 := $((-T(T(3)) - ((T(T(8)) + T((T(4) + 9))) \times T(9))))$
38512 := $((T(T(3)) + 8) \times (T(51) + 2))$
38514 := $((T(T(T(3))) - ((T((T(8) + 5))) \times T((-1) + T(4))))$
38524 := $(3 \times 8) - ((5^2) \times T(T(T(4))))$
38526 := $(T(38) \times 52) - (6)$
38527 := $((-T(T(3)) + (T(8) - (T(52) \times T(7))))$
38528 := $((T(3) \times T(T(8))) + T((T(T(5)) / T(2)))) \times 8$

- 38529** := $((3 + T((T((8 + T(5))/T(2)))) \times 9)$
38532 := $(-T(38)) \times ((5 + T(T(3))) \times (-2))$
38535 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(((T(8) \times 5)/3) + (5)))$
38540 := $((T(3) + T(8)) + (5)) \times T(40)$
38544 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(8)) + T(T(5))) \times 44$
38545 := $(T(-(3 - (8 \times 5))) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(5)))$
38550 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(8)) + (T(5))) \times 50$
38552 := $((T(T(T(3))) + (85)) \times (T(T(5)) + 2))$
38553 := $(-3) + ((T(8) + (T(T(5)) \times T(5))) \times T(T(3)))$
38556 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(8) \times (-5 - 56)))$
38559 := $(3 + (T(8) \times (T((T(T(5))/T(5))) + T(T(9))))$
38571 := $(T(T(T(3))) - (T(8) \times T(5)) \times (-71))$
38574 := $((T((T(T(3)) + (T(8) - (5)))) \times T(7)) - T(4))$
38577 := $(T(T(T(3))) \times (-8) + (-5) \times (-7 - T(7)))$
38586 := $((T(T(3)) + T(8)) \times (T(5) + T(T(8)))) - T(T(6))$
38589 := $(T(3) + ((T(T(8)) \times 58) - T(9)))$
38592 := $((3^8 - T(T(5))) - 9) \times T(T(2))$
38594 := $((T(T(3)) \times (8 + T((T(5) + T(9)))) - (4))$
38595 := $((T(T(3)) + T(8)) \times (T(5) \times T(9))) + T(T(5))$
38598 := $(T(T(3)) \times (8 + T((T(5) + 9) + T(8))))$
38619 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((8 \times T(T(6))) - (1 \times 9)))$
38622 := $(-T(3)) + (T(T(8)) \times (T(T((6 - 2))) + T(2)))$
38625 := $(-3) + (T(T(8)) \times ((T(6) \times T(2)) - (5)))$
38628 := $((T(3) \times 8) + T((6 - 2))) \times T(T(8))$
38634 := $(((-3 - T(T(8))) \times T(T(6))) + 3)/(-4)$
38638 := $((T(T(3)) + (-8) + T(6))^3 - T(T(8)))$
38643 := $((T(T(3)) \times 8) \times T(T(6))) + (T(T(4)) \times (-3))$
38644 := $((3 \times 8) \times (6 + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
38646 := $((T(3) \times T(8)) - (-T(6) \times T((T(4) \times 6)))$
38647 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(8)) - (-T(6) \times T(T(4)))) + T(T(7)))$
38649 := $(T(T(3)) + (T(T(8)) \times ((-6) + T(T(4)) + 9)))$
38655 := $((T(T(3)) + T((86 - T(5)))) \times T(5))$
38661 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((8 \times T(T(6))) - (6 + 1)))$
38674 := $((T(38) \times (-6)) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(4))))$
38675 := $((T(T(3)) - 8) \times T((6 + T(7)))) \times 5$
38679 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (T(8) \times ((T(T(6))/7) + T(T(9))))$
38681 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(8)) + T((6 \times 8))) - 1)$
38682 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((8 \times T(T(6))) - (8 - 2)))$
38685 := $((-3^8) - T((6 \times 8))) \times (-5)$
38694 := $(-T(3) + ((-86) \times T(9)) \times T(4))$
38715 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T(8)) \times ((T(7) + 1) \times 5))$
38724 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((8 \times T((7 \times T(2)))) - (4)))$
38736 := $((3^8) - T((-7) + T(T(3)))) \times 6$
38739 := $(-T(3)) - (T((-8) + T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times (-T(9))$
38742 := $((-3) + T(8)) \times (T((-7) + T(T(4))) - 2)$
38745 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(((8 \times 7) + 4)) + T(5)))$
38752 := $((T(T(3)) \times 8) + ((T(7) \times T(52))))$
38779 := $(T(T(T(3))) + (-T(8)) - (-T(7)) \times T((7 + T(9))))$
38793 := $(-T(T(T(3))) - (T(8) \times ((T(7) + T(T(9))) + T(T(3))))$
38794 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times 8) + (T(T(7)) \times T((9 + 4)))$
38799 := $((T(3) \times T(T(8))) + (7 \times T(9))) \times 9$
38803 := $((T(T(T(3))) - (T(8) \times T(80)))/(-3))$
38813 := $(-3) + (8 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(13))))$
38822 := $((T(3) + 8) - ((-8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
38823 := $(T(-(3 - 8)) - ((-8) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
38825 := $((T(T(3)) + ((88^2))) \times 5)$
38826 := $(-T(3)) \times (-T((8 \times 8) \times T(2)) - T(T(6)))$
38829 := $(T((T(3) + T(8))) \times (T(8) - ((2 - 9)))$
38832 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T((8 \times 8))) \times (-T(T(3)))) + T(2)$
38835 := $((T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(8)) - T(83)))) \times (-T(5))$
38837 := $(T(T(3)) + (8 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T((T(3) + (7))))))$
38838 := $(T(3) \times (-88 - (3^8)))$
38841 := $(T(T((3 + 8))) - (T(T(8)) \times T(T(4))) \times (-1))$
38848 := $((T(T((T(T(3)) - 8))) + (T(T(8)) + (4))) \times 8)$
38850 := $(T(38) + T(8)) \times 50$
38855 := $((T(3) \times T(8)) \times T(8)) - (5) \times 5$
38857 := $(T((T(T(3)) - 8)) \times ((T(8) - T(5)) + T(T(7))))$
38859 := $(-T(T(3)) + ((8 \times T(8)) \times T(5)) \times (-9))$
38865 := $((3 - ((T(8) \times T(8)) \times 6)) \times (-5))$
38866 := $(-T(3)) + (8 \times (8 - (-T(6) \times T(T(6))))$
38874 := $(-T(3) - ((T(88) - T(7)) \times T(4)))$
38875 := $(-T(T(3)) - (T((8 + 8)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(5))))$
38892 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times 8) + (T(8) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(2))))$
38894 := $(T(3) + (8 \times (T((T(8) + T(9))) + T(T(T(4))))$
38895 := $(((-3) \times T(8)) \times (-8) \times T(9)) + T(5)$
38922 := $(T(3) + (T(8) \times T((92/2))))$
38924 := $((38 \times T(T(9))) - T(T((T(2) + (4))))$
38925 := $((-3 - 8) \times (9 + (T(T(2))^5)))$
38927 := $((38 \times T(T(9))) + T(2)) - T(T(7))$
38928 := $(3 \times ((T(8) \times T(9)) + 2) \times 8)$
38934 := $(-T(3)) + ((T(T(8)) + (T(9) - 3)) \times T(T(4)))$
38937 := $(T(T(3)) + ((T(8) \times T((9 + 37))))$
38952 := $((T(T((3 + 8))) + T(T(9))) \times (T(5) - T(2)))$
38955 := $(-T(T(3))) \times (T(8) - T(((T(T(9)) - T(T(5)))/T(5))))$
38957 := $((T(T(T(3))) + 8) \times ((9 \times T(5)) + T(7)))$
38958 := $(3 \times ((8 \times T(T(T(9 - 5)))) + (T(T(8))))$
38964 := $((T(3) \times T(8)) \times T(9)) + T(6) \times 4$
38973 := $((T(T(3) + 8) - 9) \times T(T(7))) - 3$
38976 := $((T(3) + T(T(8))) \times (T(9) + (7 + 6)))$
38977 := $((T(3) + (T(8) \times T(T(9)))) + T((T(T(7))/7)))$
38979 := $(((-3) \times T(8)) \times (T(9) - T(T(7)))) - 9$
38982 := $((T(3) \times (-8)) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(8)) - T(T(2))$
38984 := $((T(3) \times (-8)) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(8)) - (4)$
38985 := $((T(3) - T(T(8))) - T(T(9))) \times (-8 - T(5))$

- 38988** := $(3 \times (((T(8) \times T(9)) \times 8) + T(8)))$
38994 := $(T(3) \times (((T(T(8)) \times 9) - T(T(9))) + T(T(T(4)))))$
38995 := $((T(3) + T((-8) + T(9))) \times T(T(9 - 5)))$
38997 := $((3^8 + T(9)) - T(T(9))) \times 7$
39084 := $-((T(T(3)) + ((-T(9) - T(T(08))) \times T(T(4)))))$
39123 := $((T(T(3)) \times 9) \times (T((-1) + T(T(T(2)))) - 3)$
39132 := $((-T(3)) - T((T(9) + 1))) \times (-T(3)^2)$
39138 := $(T(3) - ((T((T(9) + 1)) + T(3))) \times (-T(8)))$
39144 := $(T(3) \times ((-91) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-4))$
39145 := $((T(-((3 - 91))) \times T(4)) - T(5))$
39186 := $((T((T(3) \times (9 + 1))) + T(8)) \times T(6))$
39195 := $(39 \times (T((-1) + T(9))) + T(5))$
39222 := $((T(T(T(3))) - (T((T(9) + 2)) \times T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(2))))$
39225 := $((3^9 \times 2) - T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(5))$
39234 := $-(((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T((T(3) \times T(4))))))$
39243 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) - 3)$
39246 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T(9)) \times ((-2) \times T(4)) + T(T(6)))$
39248 := $((T((T(3) + 92))) + T(T(4))) \times 8$
39249 := $((T((3 - (T(9) \times (-2)))) - T(4)) \times 9$
39252 := $((3^9 \times 2) - T(T(5))) + T(T(2))$
39253 := $((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(9)) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(5)))))/(-3))$
39255 := $((T((T(T(3)) + T(9))) + (T(T((2 + 5)))) \times T(5))$
39258 := $(3 \times ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(2) - T(5))) + T(T(8))))$
39264 := $(-T(3)) + ((9 + 2) \times T((T(6) \times 4)))$
39265 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(9 \times 2)) - ((T(T(6)) + 5)))$
39267 := $(-3) + (T((9 + 2)) \times T((6 + T(7))))$
39282 := $((-((3^9) + T(T(2))) + T(8)) \times (-2))$
39284 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(9))) \times 2) - T((T(8) + T(T(4))))$
39285 := $((T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times T((-2) + T(8))) + T(5))$
39288 := $(-T(3)) + (((T(9) + T(T(2))) + 8) \times T(T(8)))$
39294 := $(T(3) \times ((-9) - T(2)) + 9^4)$
39312 := $((T(T(3)) - T(9)) \times T(T(3))) \times (-T(12))$
39318 := $(T(3) \times (9^{3+1}) - 8)$
39322 := $((-((3^9) + T(T(3))) \times (-2)) - 2)$
39324 := $((-((3^9) + T(T(3))) \times (2 - 4))$
39327 := $(-3) + (T(T(9)) \times (T(3^2) - 7))$
39333 := $((-3) \times T(93)) \times (-3) - T(3)$
39336 := $(-3) - (T(93) \times (-3 + 6))$
39339 := $(T(((3 \times 93)/3)) \times 9)$
39345 := $(T(3) - (T(93) \times (-4 + 5)))$
39347 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(9) + T((T(3) \times T(4)))) - T(7))$
39348 := $((3 + T(T(9))) + T((T(3) + 4))) \times T(8)$
39354 := $(-T(3)) + ((T(9) + 3) \times T((-T(5)) + T(T(4))))$
39375 := $((3 - T(9 \times 3)) \times (-7)) \times T(5)$
39387 := $-((T(T(T(3))) - 9 \times ((T(3) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(7))))$
39396 := $((-T(3) + T(T(9)))/T(T(3))) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(6)))$
39399 := $-((T(T(3)) + ((T(93) + 9) \times (-9)))$
39402 := $((T(3) + 9^4) \times T(T(02)))$
39417 := $((T(T(T(3))) - (-T(9)) \times T(T((4 + 1)))) \times 7)$
39421 := $((T(3) \times 9^4) + T(T((T(2) + 1))))$
39422 := $((-((3^9) - T((T(4) - T(2)))) \times (-2))$
39423 := $((T(3) + 9^4) \times T(T(2))) + T(T(3))$
39424 := $((T(3) \times 9^4) + T(2)) + T(T(4))$
39426 := $(-T(3)) \times (-((9^4) - T(-((2 - 6))))$
39427 := $((-3) \times T(T(9))) + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(7))$
39429 := $((T(3) \times (9^4) + T(2)) + T(9))$
39432 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T(9)) \times (-4 + (T(3)^{T(2)}))$
39435 := $((T(39) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(5))))$
39438 := $((T(3) + 9^4) \times T(3)) + T(8)$
39440 := $((T(3) + T(T(9))) - T(T(4))) \times 40$
39442 := $((T(3) \times 9^4) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))$
39444 := $((3 + T(T(9))) \times ((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4))) + T(4))$
39445 := $((-((T(T(3)) - T(9)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5))))$
39453 := $(-3) - ((-9^4) - T(5)) \times T(3))$
39456 := $((T(3) \times 9^4) - (T(5) \times (-6)))$
39457 := $((T(3) \times 9^4) + T(-((T(5) - T(7))))$
39459 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((T(9) + 4) + T((T(5) + T(9))))$
39462 := $((-3) + ((T(T(9)) - T(4)) \times T(T(6))))/T(T(2))$
39463 := $((3 + ((T(T(9)) - T(4)) \times T(T(6))))/T(3))$
39465 := $((T(3) \times 9^4) - T(6)) + T(T(5))$
39466 := $((T(T(3)) + ((T(T(9)) - T(4)) \times T(T(6))))/6)$
39468 := $((3 + T(9)) - 4) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(8)))$
39471 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(9)) + T(T(4))) \times T((7 + 1))))$
39474 := $(T(3) \times ((9^4) + T(7)) - T(4))$
39479 := $(-3) + ((T(T(9)) + 4) \times (-7 + T(9)))$
39482 := $((-T(3)) + T(T(9))) + T(4) \times (T(8) + 2)$
39483 := $(-3) \times (T(T(9)) - ((T(4) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(3))))$
39486 := $((T(3) \times 9^4) + T((T(8) - T(6))))$
39492 := $((T(T(3)) + 9^4) \times (9 - T(2)))$
39494 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((9 + T(T(4)))) - T(T((9 + 4))))$
39495 := $((T(3) \times 9^4) + 9) + T(T(5))$
39498 := $-(((T(T(3)) - (T(94) \times 9)) + T(T(8))))$
39522 := $((-((3^9) - T((T(5) - T(2)))) \times (-2))$
39525 := $(T((T(T(3)) + 9)) \times ((T(5) + 2) \times 5))$
39528 := $((T((3 + T(9))) - T((T(5) - T(2)))) \times T(8))$
39529 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(9 - 5)))) + T(T(T(2))))/9$
39531 := $(T(3) - (T((T(9) + 5))) \times (-31))$
39534 := $-(((T(T(3)) + T(9)) - ((T(T(5)) \times T(3)) \times T(T(4))))$
39535 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(9)) - 5))/T(3) - T(T(5)))$
39543 := $(-3) + ((-9) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(4)))) \times T(3))$
39544 := $(-T(3)) + ((T((T(T(9)))/T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(4))$

- 39546** := ((T(T(3)) - T(T(9))) × ((T(5) × (-4) + T(6)))
39549 := ((T(T(3)) × (T((T(9) + T(5))) + (4))) + T(T(9)))
39552 := ((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(9)) × (-5))) × (-5 - T(2)))
39558 := ((T(3) + T(T(9))) × ((T(5) + T(5)) + 8))
39564 := ((T(3) + T((T(9) - T(5)))) × (T(6) × 4))
39572 := (((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(9)))) + (T(57)))/(-T(T(2))))
39576 := (((-T(3)) × T(T(9))) × (-5)) - (T(T(7)) × (-T(6))))
39582 := (-T((3 × 9)) - ((T(T(5)) × T(T(8)))/(-2)))
39585 := ((T(-((T(3) - T((9 + 5)))))) × 8) - T(5)
39588 := (((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(9)) × (-5))) × (-8)) + T(8))
39594 := (-T(3)) + (((T(9) × T(5)) + T(9)) × T(T(4)))
39595 := (((T(T(T(3))) + 9) × (T(T(5)) + T(9))) - 5)
39600 := ((T(T(3)) + T(9)) × 600)
39606 := (T(3 + T(9))) + (T(60) × T(6))
39618 := ((T(T(T(3))) - T(9)) × (T(T(6)) - 18))
39622 := (T(T(3)) + ((9 + T((T(6) - 2)))²))
39624 := ((3 - T(T(9))) - (-T(T(6))) × (T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4))))
39627 := (T(T(3)) × (-T(9)) - (T((T(6) + 2)) × (-7)))
39636 := ((3 × T(9)) + (T(T(6)) × T((3 × 6))))
39642 := ((T(T(3)) - T(T(9))) - (-((T(T(6)) - T(T(4))) × T(T(T(2))))))
39644 := -((T(T(T(3))) - ((T((T(9) - 6))) - T(T(4))) × T(T(4))))
39645 := (3 × (((9 + T(T(6))) × T(T(4))) + T(5)))
39648 := ((T(3) + T((9 × (T(6) - T(4)))) × 8)
39654 := ((T(3) × 9) + ((6 × T(T(5))) × T(T(4))))
39663 := (-3) × (T(9) - (T(66) × T(3)))
39672 := (T(3) × (((T(9) × T(6)) × 7) - T(2)))
39675 := (((T(3) × T(9)) × T(6)) × 7) - T(5)
39678 := (T(3) + ((T(T(9)) + (67)) × T(8)))
39680 := (T(((T(T(T(3))) - T(9))/6) × 80)
39684 := -((T(T(T(3))) + (T(9) - ((6 × T(T(8))) × T(4))))
39685 := ((T((3 × 9)) × T((6 + 8))) - 5)
39687 := (-3) + ((9 × T(6)) × T((-8) + T(7)))
39711 := (T(T(3)) × T(((9 × 7) - 1) - 1))
39721 := ((T(T(3)) + T((9 + 7))) × T((T(T(2)) + 1)))
39724 := -((T((T(3) × 9)) - ((T(T(7))²)/4))
39726 := (((T(T(3)) × (T(9) × 7)) + T(T(2))) × 6)
39728 := ((T(39) + T(T((7 + T(T(2)))))) × 8)
39729 := -((T(T(T(3))) - (T(9) × ((-7) × T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9))))
39732 := (T(T(3)) × ((T(9) × 7) × T(3)) + 2)
39735 := (((T((3 × 9)) × 7) + 3) × T(5))
39738 := (-T(3)) × (((T(9) × (-7)) × T(T(3))) - 8)
39744 := ((T(T(T(3))) + T(9)) × (-T(T(7)) - (T(4) × T(T(4))))
39745 := (-((T(3) + 9)) - (-T(7)) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(5))))
39746 := ((T((3 + T(9))) - 7) × (T(T(4)) - T(6)))
39753 := (((-3) + T((9 × 7))) - T(T(5))) × T(T(3))
39754 := (-T(3)) + ((9 + 7) × T((T(5) + T(T(4))))
39756 := (3 + (9 × (T(T(T(7) - T(5)))) + T(T(6))))
39762 := (-T(3)) × (9 - (T(7) × (T(T(6)) + T(T(2))))))
39765 := ((T((T(3) × 9)) - (-T(7)) × T(T(6))) × 5)
39767 := ((T((T(T(3)) + 9)) - (T(7))) × T((6 + 7)))
39774 := (-T(T(3))) × (((T(9) - T(T(7))) + 7) - T(T(T(4))))
39775 := (((T(T(3)) - T(T(9))) - T(T(7))) × (-T(7))) + T(5))
39780 := ((T(3) + T(9)) × 780)
39792 := ((T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(9)) × (-T(7) - 9))) × 2)
39795 := (((-3 × 9) + T(T(7))) × T((9 + 5)))
39798 := (-T(3)) × ((-9) × T((-7) + T(9))) + T(8))
39814 := (-((T(T(3)) - (T(T(9)) × (T(8) + 1)))) + T(T(T(4))))
39816 := (T(T(3)) × (T(T(9)) + T((T(8) - (1 - 6))))
39819 := (T((-3) + T(9))) + (T(8) × T((1 + T(9))))
39822 := ((T(T((3 + 9))) × (-8) + T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(T(2))))
39825 := (((3 × 9) + T((T(8) × 2))) × T(5))
39831 := ((T(3) + T(9)) × (T((T(8) + 3)) + 1))
39834 := (-T(3)) × (-9 - ((T(T(8)) - 3) × T(4)))
39837 := (T(T(3)) × ((T(9) × (T(8) + T(3))) + 7))
39840 := (((-3) + T(T(9))) - T(8)) × 40)
39843 := (3 × ((T((T(9) + T(8))) × 4) - 3))
39844 := ((T(T(3)) × 9) + ((T(T(8)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(4))))
39846 := (((T(T(3)) + T(T(9))) × T(8)) + T((T(4) × 6)))
39849 := (3 × (T(T(9)) + (8 × (T(T(T(4)) - 9))))
39852 := ((3 + 9) × T((T(8) + (T(5) × T(2))))
39854 := ((-T(3)) + (T(T(9)) × (8 × 5))) - T(T(T(4)))
39855 := (((T(T(3)) + T((9 × 8))) × T(5)) + T(T(5)))
39856 := (((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(9))) + (T(8) + T(5)))/6)
39858 := (T(T(3)) × ((T((-9) + T(8))) × 5) + 8)
39864 := (-T(3)) + ((9 - (T(T(8)) × 6)) × (-T(4)))
39866 := (((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(9)))) + (T(T(8)))/(-6)))/(-6)
39872 := ((T(T(T(3))) - (T(9) + 8)) × (-7) + T(T(T(T(2))))
39873 := (-T(3)) + (9 × ((T(T(8)) × 7) - T(T(T(3))))
39876 := (((T(39) × 8) + T(T(7))) × 6)
39879 := (3 × (((T(T(9)) + T(8)) + T(T(7))) × 9))
39882 := (-T(3)) + ((T(T(9)) × T(8)) + T((T(8) × 2)))
39884 := (((3 × T((T(9) + T(8)))) + 8) × 4)
39885 := (T((T(T(3)) + 9)) + (T((T(8) + T(8))) × T(5)))
39886 := ((T(T(T(3))) × (T(T(9)) + (8/8)))/6)
39888 := (((T((T(3) + 9)) × T(8)) + T(T(8))) × 8)
39907 := ((T(T(T(3))) × T((9 + 9))) - (0 - T(T(7))))
39924 := (((T(3) + T((9 × 9))) × T(2)) × 4)
39933 := ((T(3) - T((9 + T(9)))) × (-3³))
39936 := (39 × (T(T(9)) + (T(T(T(3)))/(-T(6))))
39942 := (-T(3)) × ((T((T(9) - 9)) × (-T(4))) + T(2))
39944 := (((T(T(T(3))) - 9) × T(9)) - 4) × 4)
39945 := (((-T(3)) × T((T(9) - 9))) × (-T(4))) - T(5))
39947 := ((39 × (T(T(9)) - T(4))) - T(7))
39948 := ((-3) + T((9 × 9))) + (T(T(4)) × T(T(8)))

- 39954** := $(-T(3) + (T((T(9) - 9) \times (T(5) \times 4)))$
39955 := $((T((3 \times 9) - T(9)) \times T(T(5))) - (5))$
39960 := $(T(((3 \times 9) + 9) \times 60)$
39963 := $((-((T(3) - 9) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(6)))/T(3))$
39969 := $((T(3) + T(9)) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(6)))) - T(T(9)))$
39972 := $(((-3) + T(T(9))) \times T(9)) + (-T(7) \times T(T(T(2))))$
39974 := $((T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(7)))) - T(T(T(4)))$
39977 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(9))) - ((-T(9)) \times T(T(7))) + T(7))$
39978 := $((T(3) \times 9) \times T((T(9) - 7))) - T(8)$
39981 := $(T(T(3)) - ((-T(9)) - T(T(9))) \times (T(8) + 1))$
39984 := $((T(3) + (T((T(9)/9) \times T(T(8)))) \times 4)$
39987 := $(-3) \times (T(T(9)) - (9 \times T(8 \times 7)))$
39993 := $(39 \times (T(T(9)) - 9) - T(T(3)))$
40324 := $((T(40) + (T(T(3))^{T(2)})) \times 4)$
40326 := $((T(T(4)) \times (03^{T(T(2))}) + T(T(6)))$
40327 := $((T(40) + 3) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(7))))$
40339 := $((40 - T(3))^3 + T(T(9)))$
40365 := $((T(40) \times (-3)) - T(T(6))) \times (-T(5))$
40368 := $((-T(40)) - T(T(3))) \times (-6 \times 8))$
40425 := $(T(T(4)) \times ((T(T(04)) - T(T(2))) \times T(5)))$
40626 := $((40 + T(6)) \times T(T(2 + 6)))$
40639 := $(4 + ((0 - T((T(6) + T(T(3)))))) \times (-T(9)))$
40646 := $(-T(4) + ((T(T(06)) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(6))))$
40656 := $((40 + T((T(6) - 5))) \times T(T(6)))$
40662 := $(-(((T(T(4)) - T(T(06))) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(2))))$
40755 := $(T(T(4)) \times T((T(07) + (5 + 5))))$
40774 := $(-T((40 + T(7))) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(4))))$
40788 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (0 - T(T(7)))) \times T(8) - T(8))$
40796 := $(-T(T(T(4))) - (T((07 \times 9)) \times T(6)))$
40935 := $((40 \times T(T(9))) - T((T(3) \times 5)))$
40945 := $((T(4) \times T((09 \times T(4)))) - (5))$
40973 := $((40 \times T(T(9))) - T(T(7))) - T(T(3))$
41013 := $(T((-4) + T((10 + 1))) \times T(T(3)))$
41076 := $((-T(4) - T(T(10))) - T(T(7))) \times (-T(6))$
41184 := $(T((T(4) + (1 + 1))) \times T((8 \times 4)))$
41223 := $((T(4) + T((-1) + (T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \times T(T(3)))$
41248 := $((-T(41)) \times T(T(2))) + T(4) \times (-8)$
41250 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((-1) + T(T(2)))) \times 50)$
41265 := $((T(T((4 + 1))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(6))) \times T(5)$
41272 := $((T(T((T(4) + 1)))/T(2)) \times (T(7) \times 2))$
41275 := $(-T(((4 + 1)^2)) \times (-7 - T(T(5))))$
41286 := $((T(T(4)) + 1) + T(T(2))) \times T(T(8)) - (6)$
41292 := $((-T(4) - 1) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(T(2))))$
41310 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(13))) \times (-10))$
41322 := $((T(T(T(4)) - 1) \times (3^{T(2)})) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
41325 := $(T((T(T(4)) - ((1 - 3)))) \times 25)$
41328 := $(T(41) \times ((3 \times 2) \times 8))$
41332 := $((T(4) \times T(T(13))) - T(32))$
41349 := $(-T(T(T((4 - 1)))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (4 \times T(9))))$
41364 := $((T(4) \times T(T(13))) - T((T(6) + T(4))))$
41382 := $((T(4) + 1) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T((T(8)/2))$
41392 := $(-4) \times ((-T((1 + 3))) \times T(T(9))) + 2$
41395 := $((T(4) \times T(T(13))) - T((T(9) - T(5))))$
41424 := $((T(4) \times T(T((-1) + T(4)))) + T(T(2))) \times 4$
41426 := $(-T(T(T(4))) + ((-T((-1) + T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)))$
41445 := $((T((T(T(4)) - 1)/T(T(4))) \times (T(T(T(4)) - 5))$
41467 := $(T(T(4)) + ((T((-1) + T(T(4))) - 6) \times T(7)))$
41472 := $((4 - 1) \times ((-4) + T(7))^{T(2)})$
41475 := $(-T(T((4 - 1))) \times (T(T(4)) + (T(T(7)) \times (-5))))$
41479 := $(-T((T(T(4)) + 1)) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(7))) + T(9)))$
41485 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((-1) - (-4) \times T(T(8)))) \times T(5))$
41488 := $((T((T(T(4)) + 1)) \times (-T(4) - T(8))) - 8)$
41490 := $(T(4) \times ((-1) + T(T(4))) + (T(90)))$
41496 := $(-4) \times ((-1) - (T(T(4)) \times (-9))) \times (-T(6)))$
41498 := $(-T(T(4))) + ((-1) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-9) + T(8))$
41499 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (1 - 4) + 9) \times (-9))$
41524 := $(-T((T(T(4)) + 1) - (T(5 + 2)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
41525 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (-1 - T(T(5)))) \times 25)$
41538 := $((41 + 5) \times T((T(3) + T(8))))$
41553 := $((4 - 1)^5 \times T((T(5) + 3)))$
41565 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times ((1 + 5) + T(6))) - T(5))$
41568 := $((T(41) + 5) \times (6 \times 8))$
41574 := $(41 \times (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4))))$
41575 := $((T((T(4) + 1)) \times T((5 \times 7))) - (5))$
41592 := $(-4) \times ((T(T((1 + 5))) \times (-T(9))) - T(2))$
41595 := $(((-4) \times T(T((1 + 5)))) \times (-T(9))) + (T(5))$
41596 := $(-4) \times ((1 - 5) - (T(9) \times T(T(6))))$
41622 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (1 + (T(6)^2))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
41625 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((1 + T(6)))) \times T(2) - T(T(5)))$
41634 := $((T(T(4)) - 1) + ((T(6) + T(3)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
41635 := $(T(T(4)) \times (1 + (T(6) \times T((3 + 5))))$
41640 := $((T(T((T(4) - 1))) + 6) \times 40)$
41652 := $((T((T(T(4)) + 1)) + 6) \times (5 + T(T(T(2))))$
41664 := $((4 \times T((1 \times 6))) \times T((T(6) + T(4))))$
41679 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T((1 + 6))) - (T(T(7)) + T(T(9))))$
41685 := $((T(T((4 - 1))) - (T(T(6)) \times (-T(8)))) \times 5)$
41689 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T((1 + 6))) - (T((8 + T(9))))$
41692 := $(4 \times (T((1 + 6)) + (T(9) \times T(T(T(2))))))$
41716 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (-1) + T(7)) + T(16))$
41724 := $((T(T(4)) + T(17))^2 - T(T(T(4))))$
41727 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (-1) + T(7)) + (T(T(T(2))) \times 7))$
41728 := $((T(4) + T(17)) \times (2^8))$
41734 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (1 + T(7))) - T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))))$
41735 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (1 - (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(5))))))$

- 41742** := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T((1 \times 7))) - T((T(T(4)) - T(2))))$
41745 := $(T(T((4 + 1))) + (T(74) \times T(5)))$
41746 := $(4 + ((-1) + T(7)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 6))$
41748 := $(T(T((4 - 1))) \times (-T(7)) + T((T(T(4)) + 8)))$
41762 := $((T(T(T(4))) + 1) \times T(7) - ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(2))))$
41768 := $((T(T((T(4) - 1))) + T(T((7 + 6)))) \times 8)$
41769 := $((-T(4) + T(T(-((1 - 7)))))) \times (T(6) \times 9)$
41773 := $((T(T(T(T(4)) - 1)) + 7) \times T(7)) - 3$
41776 := $((T(T(T(4)) - 1) + 7) \times (7 + T(6)))$
41779 := $(-T(4) - ((-1) - T(7)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(9))))$
41788 := $((T(T(4)) + (1 \times 7)) \times (8 + T(T(8))))$
41794 := $(-T((T(4) + 1))) + (-T(7)) \times (T(9) - T(T(T(4))))$
41811 := $((T(4) + T(18)) \times T(T(T(T(1 + 1))))$
41823 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (1 + 8)) \times (T(2)^3)$
41824 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(-((1 - 8))) - ((T(T(2))^4))$
41832 := $((T((4 - 1)) \times T(83)) \times 2)$
41835 := $((T(4) \times (-1) + T(T((-8) + T(T(3)))))) - T(5)$
41845 := $((T(4) \times T(T((1 + 8) + 4))) - (T(5)))$
41875 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T((1 + 8))) \times T(7) + T(5))$
41914 := $(T(T(4)) + (-1) + (T(91) \times T(4)))$
41925 := $((T(T((4 + 1))) + 9) \times T(25))$
41929 := $-((T(T(T(4))) + (1 - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(2) - T(9))))))$
41932 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - ((-1) - (T(T(9)) \times T(T(3)))) \times (-2)))$
41934 := $((-T(41) + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(4)))$
41937 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - ((1 - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(3)))) \times 7))$
41943 := $(41 \times (T(T(9)) - (4 \times 3)))$
41948 := $(-T(4) + ((-1) - 9) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)))$
41952 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (1 - (T(T(9)) \times T(5)))) \times (-T(2)))$
41954 := $(-T(T(4)) + (19 \times T(T((5 - 4))))$
41958 := $((4 - 1) + T(9) + T(5) \times T(T(8)))$
41959 := $(T(T(4)) - (T((1 + 95)) \times (-9)))$
41962 := $(4 + (T(T(-((1 - 9)))) \times (T(6) \times T(2)))$
41967 := $((T(4) - 1) \times (T(96) + 7))$
41972 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - (((1 + T(T(9))) \times 7) \times T(T(2))))$
41974 := $((41 \times T(T(9))) - T(T(7))) - T(T(4))$
41984 := $((T(T(4)) + (1 \times 9)) \times (T(T(8)) - T(4)))$
42036 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2))) + (T(03)^6)$
42065 := $-((T(T(4)) + (-T((20 + 6))) \times T(T(5))))$
42075 := $((T(T(4)) + 20) \times T((T(7) + 5)))$
42119 := $(-T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-1) + T(19)))$
42126 := $((-T(4) + T((21 \times T(2)))) \times T(6)$
42133 := $(T((T(4) + T(2))) \times ((1 + T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(3))))$
42135 := $((T(T(4)) - 2)^{-1+3}) \times T(5)$
42147 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-1 - (4 \times 7)))$
42148 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (T((2 + T((-1) + T(4)))) \times T(8)))$
42169 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(2)) \times T((1 + 6))) - T(T(9))$
42172 := $((T(T(4)) - T(2)) \times (-1) + (T(T(7)) \times 2))$
42174 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))) + 1) \times (-T(7) + T(T(4)))$
42175 := $(T(T(4)) + (T((-2) + T((1 \times 7)))) \times T(T(5)))$
42196 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T((1 + 9))) + T(T(6))))$
42217 := $(-T(42) + (T(T(T(T(2) + 1)))) \times T(7))$
42222 := $((T((-4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T((2 + T(T(T(2)))))) - T(T(2)))$
42224 := $(T(T((T(4) - T(2)))) \times (2 \times (-T(2) + T(T(4))))$
42225 := $((T(T(4)) - 2)^2 + T(T(2))) \times T(5)$
42226 := $((T(T(4)) \times (-2) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T((T(2) \times T(6))))))$
42228 := $((T((4^2)/2)/2) \times T(8))$
42229 := $((T(T(T(4) \times 2) - 2)^2 - T(T(9)))$
42235 := $(4 + (T(T(T(2))) \times (T((T(2) \times T(T(3)))) - 5))$
42236 := $(-((T(4)^2) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T((3 \times T(6))))$
42237 := $((T(T(4)) + 2)^2) \times (T(3) + 7))$
42252 := $((-4) + T((T(2) \times (T(T(2)) + T(5)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
42255 := $((T(T(4)) - 2)^2) \times T(5) + T(5)$
42256 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(25) + T(T(6))))$
42263 := $(-T(4) + ((-T(2) + T((T(2) \times T(6)))) \times T(T(3))))$
42266 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(2)) + T((2^6))) \times T(6)))$
42269 := $(-4 - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(2)) - (T(6) \times 9)))$
42273 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times (T(2) \times T((7 \times 3))))$
42275 := $((T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(2)) - T(T(7)))) \times 5$
42276 := $((-T(4) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(7)))) \times 6$
42279 := $((-T(T(4)) + 2) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T((7 \times 9)))$
42282 := $((T(T(4)) + T(2)) \times (T(2)^{8-2}))$
42283 := $(T((4 + T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(2) \times T(T(8))) \times T(T(3))))$
42284 := $(-((T(T(4)) - T(2))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T((8 + T(T(4))))$
42285 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - ((-T(2) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(5)))$
42287 := $-((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(2) \times T(8)) \times T(T(7))))$
42288 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(T(2))/2) + (T(T(8)))) \times 8$
42292 := $(T((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(2)^9) \times (-2)))$
42295 := $(T(T(4)) \times ((T(2)^{T(T(2))}) + (T(9) - 5)))$
42299 := $-((T(T(T(4) + T(2)))) + ((-2) + T(T(9))) \times (-T(9)))$
42315 := $(T((T(4) \times T(2))) \times T((-((3 - 1) + T(5))))$
42323 := $(-T(T(4)) + ((-2) - T((T(T(3)) \times T(2)))) \times (-T(T(3))))$
42324 := $((T(4) \times T(T(T(2) \times 3))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4$
42325 := $(4 + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(3)) \times T(2)))) - T(5)))$
42326 := $(-T(4) + (T((2 \times 3)) \times T((T(2) \times T(6))))$
42328 := $((T((4 + 2)) \times T((T(T(3)) \times T(2)))) - 8$
42331 := $(-4 - ((T((T(2) \times T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(3))) + 1))$
42332 := $(-T(4) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T((3 \times T(T(3)))) + T(T(2))))$
42333 := $((T((T((4 + 2)) \times 3)) \times T(T(3))) - 3$
42335 := $-(((T(T(4))^2 - (T(3^3)) \times T(T(5))))$
42336 := $(T((4^2) \times 3)) \times 36$
42338 := $(T(4) - ((T((T(2) \times T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(3))) + 8))$
42345 := $((T(T(T(4)))/(-2) \times (-T((T(3) + 4)))) - 5$
42346 := $(T(4) + (T((T(2) + (T(3) \times T(4)))) \times T(6)))$

$$\begin{aligned} 42347 &:= ((-4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(3) + T((T(4) \times 7))) \\ 42348 &:= ((T(4) + 2) + (T(T(3)) \times T((T(4) + 8)))) \\ 42350 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(2) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times 50) \\ 42355 &:= ((4 + T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T((T(T(3)) + (5))) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 42361 &:= (4 + (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(3 \times T(6)) + 1))) \\ 42363 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) - 2) \times (-3)) + (6^{T(3)})) \\ 42364 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) + (T(T(3)))) \times (-T(6) + T(T(4)))) \\ 42365 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - ((T((-2) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(6))) + T(5))) \\ 42366 &:= ((T(4) \times T(2)) + (T((3 \times T(6))) \times T(6))) \\ 42368 &:= (-4) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(3 \times T(6)))) - T(8)) \\ 42374 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - (T(2)^3)) \times T(7)) + T(4)) \\ 42379 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(T(2)))/3)) - (T((-7) + T(9)))) \\ 42383 &:= ((-T(4)) - ((2^{T(3)}) \times T(T(8)))) - T(T(T(3))) \\ 42385 &:= ((-T(T(4))) + ((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(8))) \times 5 \\ 42388 &:= ((T(T(4)) - T(2)) + (T((T(3) \times 8)) \times T(8))) \\ 42390 &:= ((T((T(4) \times T(2))) + (T(3))) \times 90) \\ 42392 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (-T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 42394 &:= ((T(4) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(3)))) \times 94) \\ 42396 &:= ((T(4) + (T(T(2)) \times T(3 + T(9)))) \times 6) \\ 42397 &:= ((T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) - (T(T(3)) \times (-T(9 \times 7)))) \\ 42398 &:= (-T(4)) + ((-2) - T(3 + T(9))) \times (-T(8)) \\ 42399 &:= -((T((4 + 2)) \times (T(3) - (T(9) \times T(9)))) \\ 42410 &:= ((-T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2) + T(4)))) \times (-10) \\ 42416 &:= ((-T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(4) + T(T(1 \times 6)))) \\ \\ 42417 &:= (((T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-1) + T(7)) \\ 42418 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - (2 + (T((T(4) + 1)) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 42419 &:= (-((4^2) - (-41) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 42422 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + T(2)) \times (-T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(2))))/(-2) \\ 42426 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times T(T(4)))/2) + (T(6)) \\ 42427 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T((T(4) - T(2))))/T(7)) \\ 42428 &:= (((-4) + T((2 \times T(4)))^2) - 8) \\ 42432 &:= ((4 \times T((2^4))) \times T((T(3) \times 2))) \\ 42434 &:= (((T(T(T(4)))/(-2)) \times (-T(T(4)))) + (T(T(3)) \times 4) \\ 42435 &:= ((T((T(4) \times T(2))) \times T((T(4) + 3))) + T(T(5))) \\ 42438 &:= ((T(4) - (T(T(2))^4)) \times (3 - T(8))) \\ 42439 &:= (4 - ((T(2) - T(43)) \times T(9))) \\ 42448 &:= (4 \times ((T(T(2)) \times T((4 + T(T(4)))) - 8) \\ 42449 &:= (-T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (4 + (4 \times T(9)))) \\ 42455 &:= (((T(T(T(4)))/(-2)) \times (-T(T(4)))) - (T(5) - T(T(5)))) \\ 42456 &:= ((T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times ((4 - T(T(5))) \times (-6))) \\ 42458 &:= ((T(T(4)) - T((T(2))^4)) \times (-5 + 8)) \\ 42460 &:= (T(4) \times (T(T(T(2) + T(4)))) + (60)) \\ 42462 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) + (2 \times (T(4) + T(T(6)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 42464 &:= (4 \times ((T(T(2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(6)))) - T(4)) \\ 42465 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - T((T(2) \times (T(4) + T(6)))) \times (-T(5))) \\ 42466 &:= ((-4) - T(T(T(T(2) + T(4)))) + (6^6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42468 &:= (((4 \times T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(6)))) - T(8)) \\ 42475 &:= (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(4) - (T(T(7)) \times (-5)))) \\ 42476 &:= (((-4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(4) \times 7))) + T(T(6)) \\ 42477 &:= (-T(T(4))) + ((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(4)) \times T(7))) \times (-T(7))) \\ 42478 &:= ((4 \times T(T(2))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(7)) - (T(T(8)))) \\ 42479 &:= (((T(T(4)) - T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(7)) - 9)) \\ 42483 &:= (T(42) - ((T(T(4)) \times (-T(8))) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 42487 &:= (4 + (T(T(T(2))) \times (T((T(T(4)) + 8)) + 7)) \\ 42490 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(2)) + 4) \times (-T(90)))) \\ 42492 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (2 - (-T(4)) \times T((T(9) \times 2)))) \\ 42494 &:= (((4 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(4)) - 9)) - T(4)) \\ 42496 &:= (-4) \times (2 - ((T(T(4)) - 9) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 42497 &:= (((T(4)^{T(2)} - T(T(4))) \times T(9)) - T(7)) \\ 42498 &:= (((T(T(4)) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-9) + T(8)) \\ 42499 &:= ((4^{T(2)}) + ((-4) + T(9)) \times T(T(9))) \\ 42504 &:= ((4 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (50 - 4)) \\ 42524 &:= (((T(4)^{T(2)}) \times 5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4) \\ 42525 &:= ((4 + T((T(2) + T(5)))) \times (T(2)^5)) \\ 42526 &:= ((T(T(4))^2) + (T((T(5) + T(2))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 42528 &:= ((T(4) \times T((-2) + T(5))) + (2 + T(T(8)))) \\ 42529 &:= (4 + (T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(5) \times T(2)) \times T(9))) \\ 42532 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times ((5 \times T(3)) - 2)) \\ 42535 &:= (T(T(4)) + (((2 - T(T(5))) \times (-3)) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 42542 &:= (T(4) + (T((2 + 5)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2))))) \\ 42545 &:= (-T(T(4))) + (2 \times ((T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(5)))) \\ 42546 &:= ((T(4) + T((T(2) + (T(5) \times 4)))) \times T(6)) \\ 42547 &:= -((T((-4) + T(T(T(2)))) - ((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(7))) \\ 42555 &:= ((-T(4) + T(2)) + T((5 \times T(5)))) \times T(5) \\ 42560 &:= ((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 560) \\ 42562 &:= -(((T(T(T(4))) - 2) - (T((T(T(5))/6))^2)) \\ 42567 &:= ((T(4) \times T((T(T(2)) \times T(5)))) - (T(T(6)) \times (-7))) \\ 42570 &:= (-T(4)) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T((T(T(5)) - (T(7 + 0)))) \\ 42571 &:= ((-T(4)) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T((T(T(5)) - T(7)))) + 1) \\ 42572 &:= (-T(T(4))) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-5) \times T(T(7))) + T(2)) \\ 42573 &:= -(((T(T(4)) + 2) + ((-5) \times T(T(7))) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 42574 &:= ((T(4) \times T((T(T(2)) \times T(5)))) + (T(T(7)) \times 4)) \\ 42575 &:= -((T(T(4)) - (T(T((2 + 5))) \times (7 \times T(5)))) \\ 42576 &:= ((-T(4)) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T((T(T(5)) - T(7)))) + 6) \\ 42577 &:= -(((T(T(4)) - 2) + ((T(5) \times (-7)) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 42578 &:= ((-T(4)) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T((T(T(5)) - T(7)))) + 8) \\ 42579 &:= (((4^{T(2)}) \times T(T((T(5) - 7)))) - T(9)) \\ 42582 &:= -(((T((T(4) + 2)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(8)))) + T(T(2))) \\ 42584 &:= -(((T((T(4) + 2)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(8)))) + (4)) \\ 42585 &:= ((T((T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) + 5) \times 85) \\ 42588 &:= (((T(4) + T(2)) \times T((5 + 8))) \times T(8)) \\ 42592 &:= (4 \times (((-2) + T(5)) + 9)^{T(2)}) \end{aligned}$$

- 42595** := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((2 + T(5)) \times T((T(T(9))/T(5))))$
42599 := $-(((4^{T(2)}) - T(T(5))) + (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9))))$
42616 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (T(2) \times 6)) \times T((1 + 6)))$
42622 := $((4^{T(2)}) \times T((6^2))) - 2$
42624 := $((4^{T(2)}) \times T((6 \times (2 + 4))))$
42625 := $(T(T(4)) \times (T((T(2) + ((6^2)))) - (5)))$
42628 := $(4 + ((2 + 62) \times T(T(8))))$
42629 := $((4 + T((2 \times T(6)))) \times (2 + T(9)))$
42634 := $((4^{T(2)}) \times T((6 \times T(3)))) + T(4)$
42636 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(((6 + T(3)) + T(6))))$
42639 := $((T((4^{T(2)}) \times T(6)) - (T(3))) - T(T(9)))$
42640 := $(T(4) + (2 \times T(6))) \times T(40)$
42644 := $((T(T(4))^2 + (T(6))) \times (T(4) + (4)))$
42645 := $((T((4^{T(2)})) \times T(6)) - (T(45)))$
42648 := $((4 \times T(T(2))) - (-64 \times T(T(8))))$
42649 := $((T((4^{T(2)})) \times T(6)) + (4)) - T(T(9)))$
42655 := $((T(T((T(4) - T(2)))) \times T(6)) + 5) \times 5$
42656 := $(T((T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (65 + T(6)))$
42659 := $(-T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(T(6)) - (5)) \times 9))$
42669 := $((4^{T(2)}) \times T((6 \times 6))) + T(9)$
42671 := $((T((T(T(4)) - T(T(T(2)))) + 6) \times 71)$
42672 := $((4^2) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(2))))$
42675 := $(T(T(4)) + ((-2) - (-T(6) \times T(T(7)))) \times 5)$
42678 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (2 + 6)) \times T(7)) - (T(T(8)))$
42682 := $(T(T(4)) + ((2^6) \times T(T(8))) + T(2))$
42685 := $((-T(4)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(6)) \times (-T(8))) \times 5)$
42687 := $((T(T(4)) + 2) - (-T((6 + 8))) \times T(T(7)))$
42693 := $((T(T(T(4))) - 2) \times T(6)) + (T(9) \times T(T(T(3))))$
42695 := $(-T(T(4)) - (T((-2) + T(6))) \times (T(9) \times 5))$
42696 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6))) - T(9) \times 6$
42699 := $((4 \times T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(6)) \times T(9))) + T(T(9)))$
42700 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times 700)$
42714 := $((4 \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(14))))$
42715 := $((-4) + (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(7)) + 1))) \times 5$
42718 := $((T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T((7 + T((1 + 8))))$
42721 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(2))) \times T(7)) - (T(21))$
42722 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(7)) + T((T(T(T(2))) - 2))$
42723 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(2))) \times T(7)) + 2 - T(T(T(3)))$
42725 := $(-T(4)) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 5$
42727 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(2))) \times T(7)) - T((T(T(T(2))))/7))$
42728 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (2 \times 7)) \times 28)$
42732 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(2)) \times (T(7) + T(T(T(3)))) - T(2))$
42734 := $((T(T(T(4))) - 2) \times T(7)) + (-T(3)) \times T(T(4))$
42735 := $((T((4 + 2)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(3))) \times 5$
42736 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(2)) \times T(7)) - T((3 + T(6)))$
42738 := $((T(T((-T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))))) \times (-T(T(7))))/(-T(T(3))) - 8$
42739 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(2)) \times T(7)) - T((T(T(3)) + 9))$
42742 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(7)) + T((T(4) \times 2))$
42745 := $((-4) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 5)))$
42746 := $((T(T(T(4) - T(2)))) \times T(T((7 + 4)))/T(6))$
42762 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(2))) \times T(7)) - T((T(6) - 2))$
42763 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(7)) + T(T(T((6 - 3))))$
42764 := $((T(T(T(4))) - 2) \times T(7)) - (T((6 \times 4)))$
42768 := $((-T(T(4))) + T(-((T(T(2)) - T(7)))) \times (6 \times T(8)))$
42792 := $((4 - T((T(2) \times T(7)))) \times (-9 - T(2)))$
42794 := $((-4) - (T(2) \times (-T(T(7)))) - (9 \times T(T(T(4))))$
42795 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(2)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(9 + 5))))$
42796 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(2)) \times T(7)) + (-9 - T(T(6)))$
42797 := $(T(T(4)) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T((7 \times 9))) + (T(T(7))))$
42798 := $((T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times T(7)) - (T((-9) + T(8)))$
42799 := $(4 + ((-T(2) \times T(7))) + T(T(9))) \times T(9)$
42812 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (T(2) + 8)) \times T((1 + T(T(2))))$
42816 := $((-4) \times ((T(2) + T(T(8))) \times (-16)))$
42817 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T((T(2) + T(8)) - 1)) - T(7))$
42822 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times (T(T(8)) + T((2^{T(2)})))$
42823 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2))))/T(T(3))$
42824 := $((-T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) + ((T((T(8) + T(2))) \times T(T(4))))$
42825 := $((-4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T((T(8) \times 2))) \times T(5)$
42826 := $(T(4) + ((T(2) + T(T(8))) \times (2^6)))$
42827 := $((4^{T(2)}) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(7))$
42828 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + T(8)))) + (-2) \times T(8))$
42833 := $((T((4 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(8))) + (T(T(3))))/(-3))$
42834 := $((4^{T(2)}) \times T(T(8))) - (T(T(3)) \times (-T(4)))$
42835 := $((T((4 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(8)/3)) - 5)$
42850 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + T(8)))) - (50))$
42852 := $(4 \times ((T(2) \times T((-T(8)) + T(T(5)))) + T(2))$
42855 := $((T(T(T(4))) - ((-2) \times T(T(8))) + (T(5))) \times T(5))$
42856 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T((T(2) + T(8)) - 5))) + T(T(6)))$
42857 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + T(8)))) - (T(5) + T(7)))$
42864 := $((T(T(4)) + 2) \times ((T(8) \times T(6)) - (4)))$
42867 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + T(8)))) - (T(T(6))/7))$
42871 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + T(8)))) - (T(7) + 1))$
42872 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + T(8)))) - (7)) - T(T(T(2)))$
42873 := $((T((4 + T(T(T(2)))) - (T(8) \times T(T(7)))) \times (-3))$
42874 := $((T(4) - (2^8)) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(4))))$
42875 := $((-4) + T(2)) + T(8)^{T(7-5)}$
42878 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (T((T(2) + 8)) \times (7 + T(T(8))))$
42879 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + T(8)))) - T(T(T(-((7 - 9))))$
42882 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + T(8)))) - (T(8)/2))$
42883 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times T(((8 + 8) + T(T(3))))$
42885 := $((T(T((4 + 2))) + T((T(8) + T(8)))) \times T(5))$
42886 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + T(8)))) - (8 + 6))$

- 42891** := ((T(T(4)) × T((T(2) + T(8)))) - (9 × 1))
42892 := ((T(4) × T(T((T(T(2)) - 8)))) + (T(T(9)) - T(2)))
42893 := (-T(4) + (((T(2) × T(T(8))) + T(9)) × T(T(3))))
42895 := ((T(T(4)) × T(((2 - 8) + T(9)))) - (5))
42896 := (-4) + (T((2 + 8)) × T((T(9) - (6))))
42897 := ((T(T(4)) × T((T(2) + T(8)))) - T(9 - 7))
42899 := ((T(T(4)) × T((T(2) + T(8)))) - (9/9))
43065 := (T(T(4)) × (T((T(T(3)) - (0 - T(6)))) - (T(T(5)))))
43105 := ((T((4 + 3)) × T(T(10))) - (T(5)))
43107 := (-((T(4) + 3)) + (T(T(10)) × T(7)))
43110 := (-T(4) + (T((T(3) + 1)) × T(T(10))))
43113 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((T(3) + 1))) - (1 + T(3)))
43114 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((T(3) + 1))) - T(-(1 - 4)))
43115 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((T(3) + 1))) - (1 × 5))
43116 := (-4) + (T(T(T(3 + 1))) × T((1 + 6)))
43119 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((T(3) + 1))) - (1⁹))
43132 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((T(3) + 1))) + (T(3) × 2))
43134 := (T(T((4 × 3))) × ((1 + 3) + T(4)))
43135 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((T(3) + 1))) + (3 × 5))
43137 := ((-4) + T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(1 + 3))) × T(7))
43141 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((T(3) + 1))) + T(T(4 - 1)))
43142 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(3)) + 1) × T((T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))))
43144 := ((T(T((4 × 3))) × 14) + T(4))
43145 := -((T(T(4)) - ((3 × T((1 + 4))) × T(T(5))))
43147 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((T(3) + 1))) + (T(T(4)) - T(7)))
43148 := (T((4 + 3)) × (1 + T(T(T(-(4 - 8)))))
43156 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((T(3) + 1))) + (T(5) + T(6)))
43162 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((T(3) + 1))) + (T(6) × 2))
43165 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((T(3) + 1))) + T((-6) + T(5)))
43168 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((T(3) + 1))) + (6 × 8))
43172 := (T(T(4)) + ((T(T(T(3 + 1))) × T(7)) - T(2)))
43173 := ((T(4) + 3) × T(((1 - T(7)) × (-3))))
43174 := ((T((4 + T(3))) - 1) + (T(7) × T(T(T(4))))
43175 := (T(T(4)) × (T(3 + T((1 + 7)))) + (5))
43176 := ((4 + T((T(T(3)) + 1))) × (T(7) × 6))
43183 := (((T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) × T(-(1 - 8))) + T(T(T(3))))
43184 := ((4³) + (T(-(1 - 8)) × T(T(T(4))))
43185 := (((-T(4)) × T((T(3) - 1))) × (-T(8))) - T(5))
43187 := (-T(4)) + (T(T(T(3))) × 187)
43193 := (-4) + (T(T(T(3))) × (T(19) - 3))
43195 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((T(3) + 1))) + (-T(9) + T(T(5))))
43204 := ((T(T(T(4))) + 3) × T((T(2) - (0 - 4)))
43214 := (((T(T(T(4))) + 3) × T((T(T(2)) + 1))) + T(4))
43216 := (T((T(T(4)) + (T(3) × T(2)))) × 16)
43218 := (((T(T(4)) - (T(3)))²) × 18)
43225 := ((T(T(4)) + T((T(3) × 2))) × T(25))
43228 := (((T(T(4)) × T(T(3))) - 2)²) - T(8))
43229 := ((-T(4)) - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(2))) × (2 × T(T(9))))
43230 := ((T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(2)))) × 30)
43232 := ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(3) - 2)) × T((T(T(3))/T(2))))
43233 := (((T((4³)) - T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(3))) - T(3))
43239 := ((T((4³)) - T(T(T(2)))) × T(-(3 - 9)))
43240 := (T((43 + T(2))) × 40)
43243 := (4 - (T(T(3)) × (T(T(T(2))) - T((4³))))
43244 := ((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(3))^{T(2)}) + T(4))) × 4)
43245 := ((T((T(4) × 3))²) / (T(4) - (5)))
43247 := (43 + ((T(2) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(7))
43248 := ((T(T(T(4))) × 3) - ((-T(2)) - T(T(4))) × T(T(8)))
43249 := (T(4) + (T(T(3)) × ((2^{T(4)}) + T(T(9))))
43252 := ((T(T(4)) - 3) - (-T(2)) × (T(T(5))²))
43255 := (T(T(4)) + ((3 × T((T(2) × 5))) × T(T(5))))
43256 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((T(T(3))/T(2)))) + T((-5) + T(6)))
43260 := ((T(T(4)) + T((T(3))²)) × 60)
43262 := ((T((T(T(4)) + (T(3)))) × (2 + T(6))) - T(T(T(T(2))))
43263 := (T(((4 × T(3)) - 2)) × T((6 × 3)))
43264 := (((T(4) × T(T(3))) - 2)⁶⁻⁴)
43267 := (4 + (T((T(3) × T(2))) × T((-6) + T(7))))
43268 := -((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(3)^{T(T(2))}) - (T(T(6)) × 8)))
43272 := ((T((T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))) + T(T(2))) × 72)
43273 := (T(4) + (T((T(3) × T(2))) × T((T(7) - T(3))))
43274 := ((T((4³)) × T(T(T(2)))) - (T((7 × 4)))
43275 := ((T(T(4)) × T(T(3))) + (T((-2) + T(7))) × T(T(5)))
43279 := (((T(T(T(4))) + (3 × 2)) × T(7)) - 9)
43282 := (((T(T(T(4))) + T(3)) × 28) - T(T(2)))
43284 := (((T(T(T(4))) + T(3)) × 28) - 4)
43285 := (((T(T(4)) + T((T(3) - 2))) × T(T(8))) - (5))
43288 := ((T(T(T(4))) + T(3)) × T((T(T(2)) + (8/8))))
43290 := (T(4) × (T(T(T(3))) + (T(2) + T(90))))
43294 := (((T(T(T(4))) + T(3)) × 29) - T(T(T(4))))
43295 := -((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(3)) × 2) × T(T(9))) - T(T(5))))
43296 := ((-T(4) + T((T(3))²)) × (T(9) + T(6)))
43298 := (-4) + (T(T(3)) × ((2 × T(T(9))) - 8))
43316 := ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3))/3)) × T((1 + 6)))
43323 := (((T((T(4) × T(3))) + T(T(T(3)))) + 2) × T(T(3)))
43328 := ((4³) × ((T(T(T(3))/T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8)))))
43329 := ((T(T(4)) × (-T(3))) + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(T(2)))) × 9))
43332 := ((T((T(4) + T(3))) + T(T(3))) × T((T(T(3)) + 2)))
43336 := ((T(4)³) + (T(T(3)) × T((3 × T(6))))
43337 := (((T((4³)) + 3) × T(T(3))) - T(T(7)))
43343 := (T(T(4)) + (T((T(T(3))/3)) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(3))))
43344 := ((T((T(T(4)) - (T(3)))) - (T(T(3)))) × T((4 + 4)))
43345 := (T(T(4)) - (T((T(3) × T(3))) × (T(T(4)) - T(T(5))))
43347 := ((-4) + T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T((T(3) + (4)))) × T(7))

- 43348** := $(4 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(3)))) \times 48))$
43350 := $((T((4 + 3)) + T(3)) \times T(50))$
43351 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(3))/3))) + (T(T((5 + 1))))$
43355 := $((T((4^3)) \times T(T(3))) - (T((5 \times 5))))$
43356 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(3))/3))) + (5 + T(T(6))))$
43362 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) \times (T(6) + T(T(2))))$
43365 := $((T((4^3)) \times T(T(3))) - (T(6) \times T(5)))$
43371 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (3 \times 3)) \times T(7) - 1)$
43372 := $((T((4 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(3)) + ((T(7)^{T(2)}))$
43373 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(3))/3))) + T((T(7) - T(3))))$
43375 := $(T(T(4)) + ((-T(3 \times 3)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(5)))$
43378 := $((T(T(T(4))) + 33) \times T(7) - (T(T(8))))$
43379 := $((T(T(4) + 3)) - ((T(3) \times 7) \times T(T(9))))$
43385 := $((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(8))) - (T(T(5))))))$
43386 := $((T((4^3)) - T(3)) - 8) \times T(6)$
43389 := $((T((T(T(4)) - (T(3)))) - (T(T(3)))) \times T(8) + T(9))$
43392 := $((-T((4 \times 3)) + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(9))) \times 2))$
43394 := $((-T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(3)) \times T((9 + T(T(4))))))$
43395 := $(T(T(4)) \times (((3^{T(3)}) + T(9)) + T(5)))$
43396 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(3))/3))) - (-T(9) - T(T(6))))$
43397 := $((-T(T(4)) + (-T(3)) \times (-3) - (T(T(9)) \times (-7))))$
43398 := $((-4 + T(3)) \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(9))) - T(8)))$
43399 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))^3 + T((T(9) + T(9))))$
43414 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 14$
43417 := $(T((4 + T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(T(4))) - 1) \times T(7)))$
43422 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(3))))/T(4) + (T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}))$
43425 := $((-T(4) + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(5))$
43427 := $(T(T(4)) + ((3 + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(2))) \times T(7))$
43428 := $(T((-T(4) + T(T(3)))) \times (T(T((4 \times 2))) - 8))$
43432 := $(4 + (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(32))))$
43435 := $((T(T(4)) - (T(3)^4)) \times (-35))$
43436 := $((-T(T(4)) - (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T((3 \times T(6))))))$
43439 := $((-T(4)) + (-T(T(3)) \times (T(4) - (T(T(T(3))) \times 9)))$
43442 := $(T(T((4 + 3))) \times (T((T(4) + (4)) + 2))$
43445 := $((4^{T(3)}) \times T(4) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5))))$
43448 := $((T(T(4)) - (T(T(3)) \times (-4^4))) \times 8)$
43450 := $((4 \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)))) \times 50$
43452 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(3))) \times (T((T(4) \times 5) + T(2)))$
43456 := $((T(4) \times T(T((3 + T(4)))) + T(56))$
43465 := $((T((4^3)) - T(4)) \times T(6) - 5)$
43466 := $((T(T(4)) \times (-3) - T(T(4))) + (6^6))$
43467 := $((-T(4)) - T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(6))) \times T(7))$
43468 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (3 \times (-T(4) + (T(6) \times T(T(8))))))$
43471 := $(T((T(T(4)) + T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) - 1)))$
43472 := $((-T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T((T(4) + T(7))/T(2)))$
43473 := $((-4) - ((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(7)) + T(T(T(3))))))$
43474 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (3 + T(4))) \times T(7) - T(4))$
43475 := $((4 + T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(7)) + (T(T(5))))$
43477 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (3 + T(4))) \times T(7) - 7)$
43478 := $((T(T(4)) - 3) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7)) + T(8)$
43483 := $(T(T(4)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(T(4)) - 8)))/T(3)))$
43484 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times ((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) - 8)/T(T(4)))$
43485 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) + T((T(T(4)) - 8))) \times T(5)$
43486 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (3 \times (-4) + (T(T(8)) \times T(6))))$
43488 := $((4 \times T((T(3) \times 4)) + 8) \times T(8))$
43489 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T((3 + 4))) - (T(T(8)) - T(T(9))))$
43493 := $(T((T(T(4)) + T(3))) \times (-4 - (9 \times 3)))$
43495 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (-3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(9)) \times (-T(5))))))$
43498 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((3 + 4) \times 9) \times T(T(8)))$
43499 := $((-T(T(4)) - (T(T(3)) \times ((4 + T(T(9))) + T(T(9))))))$
43505 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(3)) \times T((50 + T(5))))))$
43516 := $((T(T(4)) - 3) + T(T(5))) \times T((1 + T(6)))$
43524 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T((T(T(3)) - 5))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)))$
43525 := $(T((4 + T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(2)) \times T(T(5))))$
43539 := $((4^3 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(9))$
43560 := $((-4) \times T(3)) \times (T(5) - T(60))$
43568 := $((T((T(T(4)) + T(T(3)))) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T(6)))) \times 8)$
43569 := $((-T(4) + (T(T(3)) \times T((T(5) + (6)))))) \times 9$
43572 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(3) \times 5)) - T(72))$
43575 := $((T(T(4)) + T((-3) + T((5 + 7)))) \times T(5))$
43576 := $(T(43) - ((-5) \times T(T(7))) \times T(6))$
43579 := $(4 + (T(T(3)) \times ((5 \times T(T(7))) + T(9))))$
43582 := $((-4^3) \times (-T(5) - T(T(8))) - 2)$
43584 := $((4^3) \times ((-5) - T(T(8))) - T(4))$
43587 := $((T(T(4) + T(T(3)))) + 5) \times 87$
43588 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(3)) - 5) \times T((T(8) + T(8))))$
43589 := $((-T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(5)) \times T((T(8) - 9))))$
43596 := $((T((4^3)) + ((5 - 9))) \times T(6))$
43614 := $((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - T((1 + T(4))))$
43616 := $((-43) + T(T(6))) \times (1 + T(T(6)))$
43618 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times T((6 + 1))) + (T(T(8)))$
43622 := $((-T(T(4)) + 3) - (-T(6) \times T((2^{T(T(2))})))$
43623 := $((-4) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(6)))) \times (T(2) \times 3)$
43624 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (3 \times 6)) \times T((T(2) + (4))))$
43625 := $((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - T((2 \times 5)))$
43629 := $((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - T(T(2)) - T(9))$
43635 := $((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - (3 \times T(5)))$
43638 := $((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - T(3)) - T(8)$
43640 := $((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - 40)$
43642 := $(4 - (T(T(3)) \times (-T(64) - 2)))$
43644 := $((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - T((4 + 4)))$
43646 := $((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - T(T(4))) + (T(6))$

$$\begin{aligned} 43647 &:= (-((T(T(4)) + T(3))) + ((T(6) + T(T(4)))) \times T(7)) \\ 43648 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - (4 \times 8)) \\ 43649 &:= ((-T(4)) - T(T(3))) + ((T(6)) \times T((T(4) + 9))) \\ 43652 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - T((5 + 2))) \\ 43655 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - ((5 \times 5))) \\ 43656 &:= (-4) \times ((-((3^6)) \times T(5)) + T(6)) \\ 43657 &:= (((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) + (5)) - T(7)) \\ 43659 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - T((T(5) - 9))) \\ 43662 &:= (((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - T(6)) + T(2)) \\ 43663 &:= (4 + ((3 \times T(6))) \times 63) \\ 43664 &:= (((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - (6)) - T(4)) \\ 43665 &:= ((T((4^{-3+6})) \times T(6)) - (T(5))) \\ 43667 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - (6 + 7)) \\ 43668 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) - (T(3)))) - (6 + 6)) \times T(8)) \\ 43669 &:= ((4 + T(3)) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(6) \times 9))) \\ 43670 &:= (-T(4)) + (T(T(3)) \times T(-(6 - 70))) \\ 43673 &:= (((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - T(7)) + T(T(3))) \\ 43674 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - T((7 - 4))) \\ 43675 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T(T((T(6)/7)))) - 5) \\ 43676 &:= (-4) + (T(-(3 - 67)) \times T(6)) \\ 43678 &:= ((4 - T(3)) - (-T(6)) \times T((T(7) + T(8)))) \\ 43680 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T((6 + (8 \times 0)))) \\ 43681 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T(T(T(-(6 - 8)))))) + 1) \\ 43682 &:= ((-4) + T(3)) + (T(6) \times T((8^2))) \\ 43683 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) + T((8 - T(3)))) \\ 43684 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) + (8 - 4)) \\ 43685 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T(T(T(-(6 - 8)))))) + 5) \\ 43686 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) + (T(8)/6)) \\ 43687 &:= ((4 + 3) - (-T(6)) \times T((T(8) + T(7)))) \\ 43688 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T(T(T(-(6 - 8)))))) + 8) \\ 43689 &:= (((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - T(8)) + T(9)) \\ 43692 &:= ((-4) + T(36)) \times T((9 + 2)) \\ 43693 &:= (T(T(4)) + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(6))) \times 9) - T(T(3))) \\ 43694 &:= (((T(4) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(6)))) \times 9) - T(T(4))) \\ 43695 &:= ((4 + (T(T(3)) \times T(T(6)))) \times (T(9)/5)) \\ 43697 &:= (((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) + T(9)) - T(7)) \\ 43702 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) - T(T(02))) \\ 43704 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) - 04) \\ 43708 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T((7 + (0 \times 8)))) \\ 43711 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) + T((1 + 1))) \\ 43712 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) + (1 + T(2))) \\ 43713 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) + (-1) + T(3)) \\ 43714 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) + T(-(1 - 4))) \\ 43715 &:= (T((T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(-(1 - 5)))))) \\ 43722 &:= ((T((T(4) + 3)) - ((T(7)^{T(2)})) \times (-2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43723 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) + T((2 + 3))) \\ 43724 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) + (2^4)) \\ 43725 &:= ((T(4) \times ((3^7) \times 2)) - T(5)) \\ 43726 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) + (T(2) \times 6)) \\ 43729 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) + T(-(T(2) - 9))) \\ 43732 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) + (T(T(3)) + T(2))) \\ 43735 &:= (T(T(4)) + (T(T(3)) \times T((T(7) + T((3 + 5)))))) \\ 43736 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - (-T(3)) \times T(T(7)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) / T(6) \\ 43738 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) - ((T(3) - T(8)))) \\ 43742 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) + (T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(2))) \\ 43743 &:= ((T((4^3)) + (7 - 4)) \times T(T(3))) \\ 43744 &:= (4 + ((3^7) \times (T(4) + T(4)))) \\ 43747 &:= ((-T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) - ((-T(7)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(7)))) \\ 43748 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) + (4 + T(8))) \\ 43749 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) + (-4) + T(9)) \\ 43752 &:= (-4) \times (-((3^7) \times 5)) - T(2)) \\ 43753 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) + (T(5) \times 3)) \\ 43754 &:= ((T((4 \times 3)) \times T((T(7) + (5)))) - 4) \\ 43755 &:= ((4 \times ((3^7) \times 5)) + T(5)) \\ 43756 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - 3) \times T(7)) - (T(T(5)) \times (-6))) \\ 43757 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(3)))) - 7) \times T(5) - (T(7)) \\ 43758 &:= (T((4 \times 3)) \times T(-(7 - (5 \times 8)))) \\ 43759 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) - 3)) \times T(7)) + (5 \times T(T(9)))) \\ 43762 &:= (4 + (T((T(T(T(3)))/7)) \times T((6 \times 2))) \\ 43765 &:= ((-4) + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(6)))) \times 5) \\ 43774 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) + T((7 + 4))) \\ 43782 &:= -((T(-(T(4) + T(T(3)))) - (T(T(7)) \times (T(8) \times T(2)))) \\ 43783 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(T(3)) + (7))) + (T(T(8)) - 3)) \\ 43785 &:= (T(T(T(-(4) + T(3)))) \times (T((T(7) + T(8))) + (5))) \\ 43789 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) \times T(7)) + ((T(8) + T(9)))) \\ 43792 &:= ((-4) + T(T(3))) \times (T(7) \times 92) \\ 43795 &:= ((T((4 + T(3))) + T(T(7))) \times 95) \\ 43796 &:= (-T(4)) + (T(T(3)) \times (7 + (9 \times T(T(6)))))) \\ 43798 &:= ((T(T(4)) + (T(3))) \times ((7 + T(9)) + T(T(8)))) \\ 43820 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(3) \times T(8)) \times T(20)))) \\ 43822 &:= ((T(-(T(4) + T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(8)) - 2)) - 2) \\ 43824 &:= (T(-(T(4) + T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(8)) + ((2 - 4)))) \\ 43827 &:= (T(T(T(-(4) + T(3)))) \times (T((8^2)) + (7))) \\ 43828 &:= (4 + (-T((3 + 8))) \times (2 - T(T(8)))) \\ 43834 &:= ((T((4^3)) - T(T(8))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(4))) \\ 43835 &:= (-T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(((8 \times 3) - 5))) \\ 43836 &:= ((T(-(T(4) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(8))) - T(-(T(3) - T(6)))) \\ 43837 &:= ((T(4) - T(T(3))) + ((T(8) \times 3) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 43839 &:= ((T(T((4 + 3))) \times (T(8) \times 3)) - 9) \\ 43840 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(T(3)) + 8)) - (T(40))) \\ 43844 &:= (4 \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) - (T(T(4)) \times T(T(4)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 43845** := $((T((T(T(4)) + T(T(3)))) - T((8/4))) \times T(5))$
43846 := $((T(4) - (T(3) \times T(T(8)))) \times (T(4) - T(6)))$
43847 := $(T(T(4)) + ((3 \times 8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(7))$
43848 := $(T(T((4+3))) \times (T((8/4)) \times T(8)))$
43849 := $((4^3) \times T(T(8))) + T(49)$
43850 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (-3) + T(T(8))) \times 50)$
43851 := $((T((-T(4)) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(8))) - (T((T(5) - 1)))$
43852 := $(-4) \times ((-3) \times T(85)) + 2)$
43855 := $((4 \times 3) \times T(85)) - (5)$
43856 := $-((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(3+8))) - T(T(5))) \times T(6)))$
43858 := $(T(4) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(8) \times 58)))$
43860 := $((T(4) - T(38)) \times (-60))$
43862 := $((T(4) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-8) + T((T(6) - 2)))$
43863 := $((T((T(T(4)) - (T(3)))) \times T(8)) - (T(T(6)) + (T(3))))$
43865 := $-((T((T(4) + 3)) + (T(T(8)) \times (-T((6+5))))))$
43866 := $((T((4 \times T(T(3)))) + T(86)) \times 6)$
43868 := $((-T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times ((T(T(8)) \times 6) - 8)$
43869 := $((T((T(T(4)) - (T(3)))) \times T(8)) - T(T(T(-((6-9))))))$
43872 := $((4 \times T(3)) + ((T(8) \times T(T(7))) \times T(2)))$
43873 := $(4 + (((3 \times T(8)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(3))))$
43874 := $(-4) + (3 \times ((T(8) \times T(T(7))) + T(4)))$
43875 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(8)))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(5))))$
43876 := $(T(4) + (3 \times ((T(8) \times T(T(7))) + (6))))$
43877 := $-((T(T(4)) - (3 \times ((T(8) \times T(T(7))) + T(7))))$
43878 := $((T((-T(4)) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(8))) - (78)$
43879 := $(T(4) + (T(T(3)) \times (T((T(8) + T(7))) + 9)))$
43882 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((T((T(3) \times 8)) \times T(8)) + T(T(2))))$
43884 := $((T(43) + 8) \times (T(8) + T(4)))$
43886 := $(-4) + (T(((3+8) + 8)) \times T(T(6)))$
43888 := $((-T(4)) - ((T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times (-8))) \times 8)$
43892 := $(-(4^3)) + (T(T(8)) \times T((9+2)))$
43893 := $((T((T(4) \times T(3))) \times 8) - 9) \times 3)$
43894 := $(4 + ((T(3) + T(8)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(4))))$
43895 := $((4 - ((T(T(T(3))) - T(8)) \times (-T(9)))) \times 5)$
43896 := $((-T(4) \times T(3)) + (T(T(8)) \times (T(9) + T(6))))$
43899 := $((-4) \times (3 + T(T(8)))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9)))$
43919 := $((T(4)^3) \times T(9)) - T((1 + T(9)))$
43920 := $(-T((T(4) \times T(3))) \times (-T(9)) + T(T(T((2+0))))))$
43921 := $((-T((T(4) \times T(3))) \times (-T(9)) + T(T(T(2)))) + 1)$
43922 := $((-T((T(4) \times T(3))) \times (-T(9)) + T(T(T(2)))) + 2)$
43923 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(3)) + T(9))^2) \times 3)$
43924 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(39)) + (2^{T(4)}))$
43925 := $((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(9)))/T(2))) \times 5)$
43926 := $((-T((T(4) \times T(3))) \times (-T(9)) + T(T(T(2)))) + 6)$
43927 := $((4^3) + T(9)) \times (-T(2)) + T(T(7))$
43928 := $((T(T(4)) - (T(3 \times 9))) \times (-T(2 \times 8)))$
43929 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(39)) - T(T(2))) + T(T(9))$
43932 := $((T(4) - T(T(3))) - T(T(9))) \times T(T(3)) \times (-2)$
43934 := $((-T(T(4)) - T(T(T(3)))) + ((-T(T(9)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
43935 := $(T(T(4)) \times T(39)) + T((3 \times T(5)))$
43942 := $(T(T(4)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T((9 + T(4)))) - T(2)))$
43945 := $(T(T(4)) \times ((T(39) + 4) + T(5)))$
43946 := $(-T(T(T(4)))) + (-T(T(3))) \times (T(9) - T(T(-((T(4) - T(6))))))$
43948 := $((T((-T(4)) + T(T(3)))) \times T((9 \times 4))) - 8)$
43950 := $((4 \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(9)) \times 50)$
43952 := $(-4) + ((T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times T(T((5 + T(2))))))$
43956 := $(T((-4) + T(3) + 9)) \times T((T(5) + T(6)))$
43965 := $((T(4) \times T(3)) \times T(9)) + T(T(6)) \times T(5)$
43966 := $(T(4) + ((T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times T((6 \times 6))))$
43967 := $((T(T(4)) + ((T(T(3)) + T(T(9))) \times (-6))) \times (-7)$
43968 := $((4 \times 3) - ((T(9) + T(6)) \times T(T(8))))$
43973 := $((43 \times (T(T(9)) - 7)) - T(T(T(3))))$
43974 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T((-3) + T(9))) \times (T(7) - T(4)))$
43975 := $((T(T(4)) - (-T(3) \times T(T(9)))) \times 7) + T(T(5))$
43979 := $((-T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (9 + T((T(7) - 9)))$
43983 := $((T((4 + T(T(3)))) \times T(9)) + T(8)) \times 3)$
43987 := $(T(T(4)) + ((T((-3) + T(9)) + T(T(8))) \times T(7)))$
43988 := $(-4) + (((T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times T(T(8))) + T(8))$
43989 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(3)) + (T(98) \times 9))$
43992 := $((T(4) \times 3) + 9) \times T((T(9) + 2))$
43995 := $((-T(4) \times T(3)) + T(T(9))) \times T(9) + T(T(5))$
44019 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(40)) - T((1 + T(9))))$
44065 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(40) - T(6))) + T(T(5)))$
44066 := $((T(T(4)) + ((40 - T(6)) \times T(T(6))))$
44115 := $((T((T(4) + T(4)))^{1+1}) + T(5))$
44128 := $((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4))) \times (T(T(T((1 + T(2)))) + T(8)))$
44132 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (4 \times ((1 + T(T(3)))^{T(2)}))$
44169 := $(4 - (T(T(4)) \times ((1 + T(T(6))) - T(T(9))))$
44178 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(4)) + 1) \times (T(T(7)) - 8))$
44179 := $(-4) + (((T(T(T(4))) + 1) \times T(7)) + T(T(9)))$
44183 := $((-4) + (T((T(4) + 1)) \times T(T(8)))) + T(T(T(3)))$
44215 := $(((-4) \times T(T((-T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))))) + 1) \times (-5)$
44216 := $(-4) + (T(T((-T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-1) + T(6)))$
44217 := $((-4) + T(T(4)))^2 \times 17)$
44232 := $((T(4) \times T(T((-T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))))) + T(3)) \times 2)$
44235 := $((T(44) \times T(2)) - T(T(3))) \times T(5)$
44237 := $(-T(4)) + ((T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) \times T((T(3) \times 7)))$
44239 := $((4 \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(2)))^3))) + T(T(9)))$
44243 := $(-4) + (T(42) \times (T(T(4)) - T(3)))$
44244 := $((4 + T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) \times T((4 + 4)))$
44245 := $((T((4 + T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + 4)) - 5)$
44247 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(4) \times T(2))) - T((T(T(4)) + 7)))$
44248 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(4) - T(2)))) + T((T(T(4)) - 8)))$
44262 := $((T(4) \times T(T((-T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(6))) \times 2)$

- 44265 := ((T(4) + T(T(4))) × (T(T((2+6))) + (T(5))))
44268 := ((T((T(4) + T(4)))²) + (T(6) × 8))
44272 := (4 + ((T((4^{T(2)})) + T(7)) × T(T(T(2))))
44275 := (((T((-4) + T(4)))^{T(2)}) - T(T(7))) × 5)
44281 := ((T(4) × (4^{T(T(2))})) + (T(81)))
44283 := ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(4) + T(2))) × (8 + T(T(3))))
44286 := ((T((T(4) × 4)) + (T(2)⁸)) × 6)
44288 := (((T(T(4)) × (T(4)²)) + T(8)) × 8)
44289 := ((T(T(4)) + (4 × 2)) × T((-8) + T(9)))
44292 := (T((-4) + T(T(4))) + ((T(T(T(2)))) - T(9)) × T(T(T(T(2))))
44295 := (((T(44) - T(2)) × T(9)) - T(T(5)))
44296 := (T(T(4)) + ((-T(T(4))) × (T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9)))) + (T(6)))
44297 := (-T(T(4)) + ((-T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × (9 × T(7)))
44312 := ((T(T(4)) + T((T(4) + T(3)))) × (1 + T(T(T(T(2))))
44322 := ((-T(4)) - ((4³) × T(T(T(T(2)))))) × T(2)
44324 := ((T(T(T(4))) + 43) × T((T(2) + (4))))
44325 := ((T((4 + T(T(4)))) + 3) × 25)
44328 := (4 × ((T((T(4) + T(T(3)))) × T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8))))
44336 := (-T(4)) + ((-T(4)) × T(T(T(3)))) + (T(3)⁶)
44345 := ((T(4) × T(T((T(4) + 3)))) + T((T(T(4)) + T(5))))
44346 := (((-4) + T(4))^{T(3)}) - (T(4) × T(T(6)))
44348 := (-4) + ((4 × T(T(3))) × T((4 × 8)))
44352 := (T(T((-4) + T(4))) × (T(T(3)) + T((T(5) + T(2))))
44355 := (((-4) + T(T((4 × 3)))) - T(T(5))) × T(5)
44362 := (T(4) + (((4³) × T(T(6))) × T(2)))
44368 := (-4) × (-4) - ((-T(3)) × T(T(6))) × (-8)))
44373 := (((-4) + T((T(T(4)) + 3))) + (T(T(7)))) × T(T(3))
44374 := (((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(7) × T(T(T(4))))
44378 := (4 + (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) × T(7)) + (T(T(8))))
44382 := ((T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) × T(T(3))) - (T(T(8)) - T(2)))
44384 := ((T(T(T(4))) - T((-4) + T(T(3)))) × (8 × 4))
44385 := (T(T(4)) × (-((T(4) + 3) - T((8 × 5))))
44386 := (T(T(4)) + ((T((T(T(4)) - (T(3)))) × T(8)) + T(T(6))))
44387 := (((-4) × T(T(4))) + (3⁸)) × 7)
44388 := (((T(T(T(4))) - 4) × T(T(T(3))))/8) + T(8)
44392 := (4 × (T(4) + (T(T(T(3))) × (T(9) + T(2))))
44395 := (T(4) + ((43 × T(T(9))) - T(T(5))))
44396 := (-T(T(4)) + ((-T(T(4))) × (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(9)))) + T(T(6)))
44428 := (((T(T(4)) × T((T(4) × 4))) - T(T(2))) - T(T(8)))
44429 := -((T(T((-4) + T(4))) + (T(T(T(4))) × (-29)))
44430 := (((T(T(4)) - T(T(T(4)))) + 4) × (-30))
44436 := ((T((4 + 4)) + T((4³))) × T(6))
44437 := (-T(T(4)) + ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(4)) - (T(3)))) × T(7)))
44455 := (T(T(4)) + (((T(T(T(4))))/4) - T(5)) × T(T(5)))
44457 := (T((-4) + T(4)) × (T(-((T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))) - (T(7))))
44460 := (T(((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4))) + T(4))) × 60)
44468 := ((4 + (T(T(T(4))) × T(T(T(T(-((4 - 6))))))))/8)
44472 := ((4 + T((T(4) + (4)))) × (T(T(7)) + 2))
44485 := ((T((T(4) + (4))) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(8) - (5)))
44486 := (((-4) + T(4)) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-8) - T(6))
44492 := -((T(T(4)) - ((T(44) × T(9)) - T(2)))
44495 := (T(T(4)) × (-T(4)) + (T((T(4) × 9)/5))
44496 := ((4 + T((T(4) × 4))) × (9 × 6))
44525 := -((T(T(T(4))) - ((-T(4)) + T(T((T(5) - T(2)))))) × T(5)))
44526 := -((T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) + (-T(5)) - (T(T(2))⁶)))
44529 := (-T((-4) + T(4))) + (T((T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) × 9))
44532 := (((T(44) × T(5)) - T(3)) × T(2))
44534 := ((T((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)))) × T(T(5))) - T(T((3 + T(4))))
44535 := (((T(44) × T(5)) × 3) - T(5))
44542 := (((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(4)))) × (-T(5))) + 4) × (-2))
44544 := ((T(T(T(4))) - 4) × ((T(5) + (4)) + T(4)))
44545 := ((T(44) × T((5 + 4))) - 5)
44548 := ((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4))) × ((T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(8)))
44562 := ((T((-4) - T(T(4))) + T(T(5))) + T(T(6))) × T(T(T(2)))
44565 := ((T(44) × T((T(5) - (6)))) + (T(5)))
44566 := ((T(T(4)) - T(-((T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))))) + (6⁶))
44568 := (((T(T(T(4))) × 4)/5) + 6) × T(8)
44569 := (T(T(4)) + ((-4) + T((T(T(5)) - (T(6)))) × 9))
44574 := ((4 - T(T(4))) × (T(T((T(5) - (7)))) - T(T(T(4))))
44575 := ((-T(4)) + (T((T(4) × 5)) × 7)) × 5)
44577 := -((T(T(4)) - (((-T(4)) + T(T(5))) × T(T(7))) - T(7)))
44579 := (4 + (((T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) × T(7)) + T(T(9))))
44583 := (((T(4) + T(T(4))) + T(T(5))) + 8) × T(T(T(3))))
44597 := (((T(T(4)) × (-4) + T(T(5)))) - 9) × 7)
44618 := (-4) + ((T(-((T(4) - T(6)))) + 1) × T(T(8)))
44625 := (((T(T(T(4)))/(-T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(6)))/T(2)))) × T(5)
44626 := (T(T(T(4))) - ((T((4 × T(6))) - (T(T(2))⁶)))
44635 := ((T(4) × T((T((4 + T(6))) - T(T(T(3)))))) - T(5))
44642 := ((T(T(T(4))) - (-4) + T(T(6))) × (T(T(4)) - T(T(T(2))))
44644 := (((-4) - T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T(4)))) × 4)
44645 := ((T(4) × T((4 × T(6)) + T(4))) - 5)
44646 := (-4) + (T(4) × T((T((T(6) + 4))) - T(T(6))))
44648 := ((T(T(T(4))) - ((4⁶) + T(T(4)))) × 8)
44660 := (T(T(T(4))) × (-((T(4) + T(6)) - (60))))
44665 := ((-T(4)) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T((6 + 6))) × (-T(5)))
44667 := ((T(T(T(4))) + (-T(4)) - (-T(6)) × T(T(6)))) × 7)
44672 := (-4) + ((-4) + T(6)) × T(72))
44675 := (((T(T(4)) + T(T(4))) × T((T(6) + (7)))) + (T(5)))
44679 := ((T((T(4) + 46)) × T(7)) - 9)
44682 := ((T(T(4)) - ((4 × T(T(6))) × (-8))) × T(T(2)))
44685 := ((T((-4) + T(T(4))) + (T((T(6) + T(8)))) × T(5))
44687 := (T(T(4)) + ((T(T(T(4))) × (T(6) + 8)) - (T(7))))
44688 := (T((T(4) + 46)) × (-8) + T(8))

- 44712 := (T(T(4)) + ((T(T(4))) × (T(7) + 1)) - T(2))
44714 := (((T(T(4)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(7))) - 1) + T(T(4)))
44715 := ((T((T(4) × 4)) - (7)) × T(T(-(1 - 5))))
44722 := (((T(4) + (T(T(4)) × T(T(7)))) + T(T(T(2)))) × 2)
44723 := (((T(T(4)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(7))) + (T(2) × T(T(3))))
44725 := -((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(4)) × T(T(7))) × 2) + T(T(5))))
44726 := (-4) + (T((T(4) × 7)) × (T(2) × 6))
44727 := ((-T(4)) + (T(T(T(4))) × T(7))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × 7)
44733 := ((T(T((4 + 4))) × (T(T(7)) - 3)) / T(3))
44734 := ((T(T(T(4))) - T(4)) + (-T(7)) × (-3) - T(T(T(4))))
44737 := (((T(T(T(4))) × 4) + T((7 × 3))) × 7)
44743 := (T((-T(4)) + T(T(4))) + (T(7) × (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3))))))
44744 := ((T((T(T(T(4))) / T(T(4)))) + (7 × T(T(T(4)))) × 4)
44745 := ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(4)))) + (T(7) × (T(T(T(4))) + 5)))
44748 := (44 × ((T(T(7)) - T(T(4))) + T(T(8))))
44758 := ((T(T(T(4))) - T((T(T(4)) + T(7)))) × (-T(5) + 8))
44762 := (4 + ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(7)))) × (T(6) + 2))
44765 := (((T(T(4)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(7))) - (T(6) × (-5)))
44772 := (((-T(4)⁴) + T(T(7))) × (-T(7))) / T(T(2))
44775 := (T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(7)) × (-7) × T(5)))
44776 := ((T(T(T(4))) + 4) × (T(7) + (7 - 6)))
44778 := (((-T(T(4))) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(7)) × (-T(7))) - (T(T(8))))
44782 := (((T(T(T(4))) + 4) × (-7) + T(8)) + T(T(2)))
44783 := (T(4) + ((T(T(T(4))) × T(7)) + T((T(8) + T(T(3))))))
44785 := ((-T(4)) - T(T(4))) × ((-T(7)) - T(T(8))) + (5))
44786 := (((T(4) × T(4)) × T(T(7))) + T(T((-8) + T(6))))
44795 := (((T(T(4)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(7))) + (9 × T(5)))
44796 := (T((-4) + T(T(4)))) + ((-7) × T(T(9))) × (-6))
44797 := ((-T(T(4))) × ((T(T(T(4))) / 7) - T(T(9)))) - (T(7))
44814 := ((4 + T((T(T(4)) - T(8)))) × T(T(T(-(1 - 4))))
44815 := (-T(4)) + (T(T(4)) × 815)
44824 := (((T(4) + T(T(4))) × T(T(8))) - T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4))))
44825 := (T(T(4)) × (T((4 × (8 + 2))) - (5)))
44826 := -((T((T(4) × T(T(T(4) - 8)))) - (T(T(2))⁶))
44834 := ((T(T(4)) + ((T(4) - T(8)))) × (T(3) + T(T(T(4))))
44835 := (((T(T(4)) × T(T(4))) - T(8)) × (3 × 5))
44836 := ((T(T(4)) × (T(T(4)) + (T(8) × T(T(3)))) + T(T(6)))
44840 := ((T(T(4)) - T(48)) × (-40))
44844 := ((T(T(4)) × T((4 + T(8)))) - (4⁴))
44845 := (((T(4) + T(T(4))) × T(T(8))) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(5))
44850 := ((T(T((-4) + T(4))) + (T(T(8)))) × 50)
44852 := (-4) + ((T((T(T(4)) + 8)) + (T(T(5)))) × T(T(T(2))))
44856 := (((T(T(4)) × T(T(4))) - T(8)) × T(5)) + (T(6))
44862 := -(((T(4) - (4 × T(86))) × T(2))
44863 := (((T(T(4)) × T((4 + T(8)))) - T(T(6))) - (T(3)))
44869 := ((T(T(4)) × T((4 + T(8)))) - T(T(T(-(6 - 9))))
44872 := -(((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(8)) × 72))
44874 := (((-T(T(4))) - T(T(T(4)))) - 8) × (-T(7)) - T(4)
44876 := (((T(T(4)) × T((4 + T(8)))) + (7)) - T(T(6)))
44877 := ((T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) - 8) × (-7) + T(7))
44880 := ((-4) + T(T(4))) × 880
44882 := (T(4) + ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(8)) × (-T(8)))) × (-2))
44886 := -((T((4 + T(T(4)))) - ((T(8)^{T(8-6)})))
44895 := (((T(44) + 8) × T(9)) - T(5))
44912 := ((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(4)) + 9)) × T((1 + T(T(2))))
44917 := (-4) + ((T(T(T(4))) + 9) × (1 + T(7)))
44918 := ((44 × (T(T(9)) + 1)) - T(T(8)))
44924 := ((44 × (T(T(9)) + T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4))))
44925 := ((T(T(4)) + ((T(T(4)) - T(T(9))) × (-T(2)))) × T(5))
44926 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((-4) + (T(T(9)) × 2)) × T(6))
44927 := (((4⁴) - T(9))²) + T(T(7))
44928 := (((4 × 4) × T((9 + T(2)))) × T(8))
44929 := (4 + ((T((T(4) + 9)) × T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9))))
44930 := -((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(T(4))) + 9) × (-30)))
44935 := ((T(4) - T((T(4) × 9))) × (-T(3) + (5)))
44936 := -((T(T(T(4))) - ((-4) × T(9)) + (T(3))⁶))
44937 := -((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(4)) + 9) × T(37)))
44943 := -((T(T(T(4))) - (T((T(T(4)) - 9)) × 43))
44945 := (((-4) × T(T(4))) + T(T(9))) × T(T(4)) + T(T(5))
44950 := ((T((4 × 4)) - T(T(9))) × (-50))
44954 := -((T(T(T(4))) - (T((-4) + T(9))) × 54))
44955 := ((-T(4)) + T(T(4))) × (T(T(9)) - T((T(T(5)) / T(5))))
44956 := (T((T(T(T(4))) / T(T(4)))) - (-9) × T((T(T(5)) - (T(6))))))
44968 := (44 × (T(T(9)) - (T(6) - 8))
44982 := (((T(4)⁴) × (-9)) + T(8)) / (-2)
44985 := ((-4) + T(((4) + T(9)) + T(8))) × T(5)
44995 := ((T(4) × ((T(T(4)) + T(9)) × T(9))) - (5))
44997 := ((-T(4)) - T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(9)) × (-T(9))) + T(7))
44999 := -((T(T(T(4))) - ((4 × 9)) - (T(T(9)) × (-T(9))))
45045 := (T(T(T(T(4) / 5))) × T((0 - T(T(4)) + T(T(5))))
45066 := -((T(T(T(4))) + (50 - (6⁶)))
45085 := ((T(T(4)) × T((5 × 08))) - (T(5)))
45095 := ((T(T(4)) × T((-5) + T(09))) - (5))
45115 := ((T(T(4)) × T((T(T(5)) / T((1 + 1)))) + T(5))
45116 := -((T(T(T(4))) - (((5 × 1) + 1)⁶)))
45122 := -((T(T(T(4))) + ((5 + 1)) - (T(T(2))^{T(T(2))})))
45125 := (((-T(4)) + T((T(5) - 1)))²) × 5
45126 := ((T(4) - T(T(T(5 - 1)))) + (T(T(2))⁶))
45132 := -((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(5) + 1) + (T(3))^{T(T(2))})))
45155 := ((T((T(T(4)) - (T(5)))) + 1) × 55)
45165 := ((T((T(4) + T((5 - 1)))) × T(6)) + (T(T(5))))
45175 := (T((T(4) + T(5))) × (-1) + (T(7) × 5))
45210 := (((T(T(4)) × T(5)) - T(2)) × T(10))

- 45222 := ((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(5)) + T(2))²)) × (-T(2)))
45223 := -(((T(T(4)) + (T(52))) - (T(T(2))^{T(3)})))
45225 := -(((T(4) - (T((5 × 2))²)) × T(5)))
45226 := ((T(T(4)) × T((T(T(5))/T(2)))) + (T(T(2)) × T(6)))
45227 := (-(((T(T(4)) - T(T(5))) - T(T(2)))) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7)))))
45228 := -((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(5)) + ((T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}) - 8))))
45233 := -((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) - ((T(2) - (T(3))^{T(3)}))))))
45235 := (T((4 + T(5))) + (T((T(T(T(T(2))))/3)) × T(5)))
45236 := -((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) + ((2 × 3)⁶)))
45237 := ((T(T(4)) × T((T(T(5))/T(2))) + 3) - (T(7)))
45247 := (T(T((-4) + T(5))) + ((-T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(7)))
45248 := ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) + T(T(2)))) × (4 × 8))
45255 := ((T(T(4)) × (T(5) × T((2 × 5)))) - T(T(5)))
45265 := (T(T(4)) × (T(T(5)) + T(((2 × T(6)) - (5))))))
45268 := (((T((4 + T(5))) + T(T(2))) × T(T(6))) - 8)
45272 := (-4) + (((5 + 2) × T(7)) × T(T(T(T(2))))))
45273 := (((T(T(T(4)))/(-5)) × T(T(T(2)))) × (-7)) - 3)
45276 := ((4 × ((5 + 2) × 7)) × T(T(6)))
45277 := -((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(5)) × T(27)) - T(7)))
45278 := (-T(4)) + (((T(T(5))/T(2)) + T(7)) × T(T(8))))
45282 := ((4 - T(52)) + (T(8))^{T(2)})
45284 := (((4 × (T(5) + 2)) × T(T(8))) - (4))
45288 := (((T(4) × (5)^{T(2)}) + 8) × T(8))
45295 := (T(T(4)) + ((T(T(5)) × T((T(2) × 9))) - T(T(5))))
45297 := ((T(-((T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))) × T(T(T(2)))) - (-9 × T(7)))
45320 := ((T(T(4)) + T(T((5 + T(3)))) × 20)
45324 := (4 × (-T(5)) + (T(3) × T((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))))))
45325 := ((T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) × (T(T(T(3))) + T((2 + 5))))
45326 := -((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(5)) × T((3)^{T(2)}))) + (T(6))))
45328 := (4 + ((T(T(5)) × T((3)^{T(2)}))) - T(8))
45331 := ((T(T(4)) × T((T(T(5))/3))) + T(T(T(3 × 1))))
45332 := -((T(T(T(4))) - (((5)^{T(3)}) × 3) - T(2)))
45335 := (-T(4)) + ((T(T(5)) × T((3)³)) - (T(5)))
45336 := ((4 + ((T(T(5)) × T(T(3))) × (-3))) × (-6))
45338 := (-4) + (T((5 + T(3))) × (T(T(3)) + T(T(8))))
45342 := (T((-4) + T(5)) × (T(T(3)) + T(T((4 × 2))))
45347 := (((T(T(4)) × T(5)) × T((T(3) + 4))) - T(7))
45348 := (-4) × (-T(5)) - ((T(T(3)) - 4) × T(T(8))))
45355 := ((T(((4 + 5) × 3)) × T(T(5))) - 5)
45356 := (-4) + (T(T(5)) × ((3 + T(5)) × T(6)))
45357 := -((T(-((T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))) + ((3 - T(T(5))) × T(T(7))))))
45372 := ((T(T(4)) × (T(5) × T((3 + 7)))) - T(2))
45374 := ((T((T(T(4)) + (T(5))) - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(7) × T(T(T(4))))))
45375 := (T(T(4)) × ((5 + T(3)) × 75))
45377 := (-4) + ((-T(5)) + (T(T(T(3))) × (-T(7)))) × (-7))
45384 := ((-4) - T(T(5))) × (-T(3) + (T(8) × T(4)))
45388 := ((T(T(4)) × T((T(T(5))/3))) - (-8 × T(8)))
45393 := ((T(T((-4) + T(5))) × T(T(3))) - (T(T(9)) + 3))
45394 := (4 + (T(5) × (T(T(3 + 9))) - T(T(4))))
45395 := -((T((T(T(4)) - (T(5)))) + (T(T(3 + 9))) × (-T(5))))
45396 := (-T(45)) + (T(T(3)) × T((T(9) + T(6))))
45399 := (-T((45 + 3))) - (T(T(9)) × (-T(9)))
45415 := ((T(T(4)) × ((T(5) × T(T(4)) + 1)) - (T(5)))
45419 := (((T(T(4)) × T(5)) × T(T(4))) + (-1) + T(9))
45423 := ((T(T(T(4))) + ((5⁴) - 2)) × T(T(3)))
45424 := (((T(T(4)) × T(5)) × T(T(4))) - T(T(2))) + T(T(4)))
45425 := ((T(4) × 5) - ((T(T(4))²) × (-T(5))))
45429 := (((T(T(4)) × T(5)) × T(T(4))) + (T(T(2)) × 9))
45441 := (((T(T(4)) × T(5)) × T(T(4))) + T((T(4) + 1)))
45445 := (((T(T(4)) × T(5)) × T(T(4))) + T(T(4))) + (T(5)))
45448 := (-((T(T(4)/5) - T(T(4))) × (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(8))))))
45453 := (((T(T(4)) × T(5)) × T(T(4))) + T((T(5) - 3)))
45456 := (((T(T(T(4))) × 5) + (-4) - T(T(5))) × 6)
45462 := (((T(T(T(4))) + (5⁴)) × T(6)) - T(2))
45465 := (((T(T(4)) × T(5)) × T(T(4))) - (-6 × T(5)))
45466 := ((-T(4)) × T(T(5))) + ((T(4) + (6⁶)))
45471 := (((-4) + T(T(5))) - 4) × T(T(7)) - 1)
45472 := ((4 + 54) × (T(7)²))
45476 := (-4) + (T(T(5)) × ((T(T(4)) × 7) - (6)))
45477 := ((T(4) - 5) + ((-4) × T(T(7))) × (-T(7)))
45483 := (((T(T(4)) × T(5)) × T(T(4))) - (T(8) × (-3)))
45485 := (T(T(4)) × (T((-T(5)) + T(T(4)))) + (-8) + T(5)))
45486 := (((T(T(4)) × T(5)) × T(4)) + T(T(8))) × T(6))
45488 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((T((T(5) - 4)) × T(T(8))) - 8))
45489 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (T(T(5))/4)) - ((T(T(8)) + T(9))))
45495 := ((T(T(4)) × (T(5) × (T(4) + T(9)))) + T(T(5)))
45496 := (T(4) + ((T(T((T(5) - 4)))) - T(9)) × T(6))
45497 := ((T(T(4)) × T((-T(5)) + T(T(4)))) + (-9) + T(T(7)))
45525 := ((T(4) + ((55²))) × T(5))
45527 := (T(T(4)) + ((T(T(5)) - (5 + T(2))) × T(T(7))))
45528 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (T(5) + T(5))) - (T(T(2)) + T(T(8))))
45540 := (T(T(4)) × ((T(T(5))/T(5)) + (T(40))))
45545 := -((T(T(4)) + ((-T((5 × 5))) - T(T(4))) × T(T(5))))
45574 := (((T(T(T(4)))/(-5)) × (-T(T(5)) + T(7))) - T(4))
45577 := (((T(T(T(4)))/(-5)) × (-T(T(5)) + T(7))) - 7)
45584 := (((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(5)/5)))) × T(8)) - T(T(T(4))))
45585 := (((T(T(4)) + (T(5))) × (-T(5)) + T(T(8)))) + (T(5))
45611 := -((T((T(T(4)) - (T(5)))) + (-T(6)) × T(T(11))))
45621 := -((T(45) - (6)^{T(2+1)}))
45624 := ((T(-((T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))) + (T(6))^{T(2)})) × 4)
45625 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((T((T(T(5))/6))²) - T(5)))
45626 := (-((4⁵)) + ((6)^{T(T(2))}) - (6))

- 45628** := $(T(T(T(4))) + (-T((5+6))) \times (-2) - T(T(8))))$
45631 := $(-(4^5) + ((6^{T(3)}) - 1))$
45633 := $((T(-((T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))))) + T((T(6)/3))) \times T(T(3)))$
45635 := $((T(T(4)) \times 5) + (T((T(6) + T(3))) \times T(T(5))))$
45639 := $((T(-((T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))))) - (T(6))) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(9)))$
45655 := $(T(T(4)) + ((-5) + T(6)) \times T((5 \times T(5))))$
45656 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (-T(5)) + T(T(6)))) \times (5 + T(6))$
45661 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (-5)) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T((6 \times 1))))$
45666 := $(-(T((4 \times (5+6))) - (6^6)))$
45668 := $(-(((4^5) - (6^6))) + T(8))$
45671 := $(-4) - ((-5) \times T(6)) \times T((T(7) + 1)))$
45672 := $(4 \times (T((T(T(5)) - T(6))) - (-T(7)) \times T(T(T(2))))))$
45675 := $(T(((T(4) \times 5) - T(6))) \times (7 \times T(5)))$
45679 := $(4 + (-5) \times ((T(T(6)) - T(7)) \times (-T(9))))$
45682 := $((T((T(4) \times 5)) - 6) \times T(8)) - 2$
45684 := $((4^5) + ((T(6) + 8) \times T(T(T(4))))$
45688 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(5)) + T(T((T(6) - 8)))) \times 8$
45696 := $((T(4) + T(T((5+6)))) - T(9)) \times T(6)$
45724 := $((4 \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(7)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)))$
45727 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(5)) \times T(7)) + (T(2)^7)$
45729 := $(-((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(7)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-9)$
45732 := $(-((T(T(4)) - T((T(5) + 7)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(2))$
45734 := $(-((T(T(4)) - T((T(5) + 7)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 4$
45735 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) \times 7) - T((T(3) \times 5))$
45736 := $(-(T(4)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(7))) + (T(3)^6)$
45738 := $(-4 + T(5)) \times (-T(7)) + T(T((T(3) - 8)))$
45742 := $(4 + ((T((T(5) + 7)) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
45745 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(5)) + 7) \times T(T(4)) - T(5)$
45747 := $((T(T(4)) \times 5) + (T(T(7)) \times (4 \times T(7))))$
45755 := $(-(T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times (T(7) + ((5^5))))))$
45756 := $(-4) \times (T(T(-((T(5) - T(7)))))) - (5^6))$
45762 := $((4 - ((-5) - T(7)) \times T(T(6)))) \times T(T(2))$
45764 := $(4 + ((T(5) + 7) \times T(64)))$
45765 := $((4^5) - 7) \times T((-6) + T(5))$
45768 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (-5) + T(T((7+6)))) \times 8$
45773 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) \times 7) - T(T(7)) - T(T(3))$
45775 := $((T(4) + T(5)) \times (T((T(T(7))/7)) + (T(T(5))))$
45779 := $((T(T(4)) - T(57)) \times (-T(7))) + T(T(9))$
45780 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(5)) + (7 \times T(80)))$
45782 := $(-(((T(T(T(4))) - T(T((T(5) - 7)))) - (T(8)^{T(2)})))$
45783 := $((T((-4) + T(5))) \times (T(7) + T(T(8)))) - T(T(3))$
45792 := $((T((T(T(4)) - T(5)))) + (T(7))) \times (9 \times T(T(2)))$
45793 := $(T(T(4)) + ((T(5) + 7) \times 9) \times T(T(T(3))))$
45794 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(5))) - (T(T(7)))) - (-T(9)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
45795 := $((T((T(T(4)) + T(5)))/7) \times (9 + T(T(5))))$
45798 := $(-(T((4 \times T(5))) - (T(7) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(8))))))$
45799 := $((4 + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(9))) + T(T(9))$
45808 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T((5+8)))) \times 08$
45814 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((5+T(8)))) - 1) - T(T(T(4)))$
45815 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(5) - 8)) \times (-1) + T(T(5)))$
45822 := $((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - T((2 \times T(T(2))))$
45823 := $((T(T(4)) \times (-T(5))) - 8) + (T(T(2))^{T(3)})$
45824 := $((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4)))$
45825 := $(T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (T((8 \times 2)) + 5))$
45826 := $(-(T(4) + T((5 \times 8))) + (T(T(2))^{6}))$
45828 := $((T(4) \times T(T(5))) \times T(8)) + T((2 \times T(8)))$
45831 := $((T(T(4)) \times (-T(5))) + (T(8)^3 \times 1))$
45832 := $((-4) - T((5 \times 8))) + (T(3)^{T(2)})$
45833 := $(-((T((T(T(4)) - T(5)))) - ((T(8)^3) - 3)))$
45834 := $((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - T((T(T(3)) - T(4))))$
45836 := $(-((T((T(4) - 5)) \times 8)) - (T(3)^6))$
45840 := $((4 \times T(T(5))) + T(T(8))) \times 40$
45842 := $((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - T(T(4))) - T(2)$
45845 := $((4 + (T(5) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(4)))) \times 5$
45846 := $((-4) \times T(T(5))) - ((-T(T(8)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times T(6))$
45848 := $((T(T(T(4))) + 5) + T((T(8) + T(T(4)))) \times 8$
45850 := $(T(4) \times (-5)) + (T(8) \times T(50))$
45856 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T((T(5) + T(8)))) \times (-5) + T(6))$
45857 := $((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - (T(5) + T(7)))$
45862 := $((-4) \times ((T(T(5)) - T(T(8))) \times T(6))) - 2$
45864 := $((T((T(4) + 5)) - T(T(8))) \times (T(6) \times (-4)))$
45866 := $(((-4) - T(T(5))) - T(T(8))) + (6^6)$
45867 := $((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - (T(T(6))/7))$
45871 := $((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - (T(7) + 1))$
45872 := $((T(T(4)) + 58) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(2))$
45874 := $((T(T(4)) + 58) \times T(T(7))) - 4$
45875 := $(((-4) - T(T(5))) \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - 5$
45879 := $((T(T(4)) + T(5)) \times T(T(8))) - T((-7) + T(9))$
45882 := $((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - (T(8)/2))$
45885 := $((4 + T(5)) \times T((8 \times 8) + 5))$
45886 := $((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - (8 + 6))$
45891 := $((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - (9 \times 1))$
45892 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(5)) + ((8 \times 9))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
45895 := $((T(4) - T(5)) + (T(8) \times T((T(9) + 5))))$
45897 := $((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - T((9 - 7)))$
45899 := $((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - (9/9))$
45915 := $((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T((9 - 1))) + (T(5)))$
45924 := $((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times 9) + T(T(2))) \times 4$
45925 := $(T(T(4)) \times (T((-5) + T(9))) + (T(2) \times 5))$
45926 := $(-(((T(T(4)) + T(5) \times T(9))) - (T(T(2))^{6})))$
45944 := $((4^5) \times T(9)) - T((4 \times 4))$
45950 := $((4 - T(T(5))) + T(T(9))) \times 50$

- 45955** := (((4⁵) × T(9)) – T(T(5))) – (5)
45958 := (4 + ((T((5 × 9))/T(5)) × T(T(8))))
45963 := (((T((4 + T(5))) + 9) × T(T(6))) – (T(3)))
45965 := –((T(T(4)) – ((T(59) × (T(6) + (5))))))
45966 := (((T(T(T(4))) × 5) – (T(9) – (6))) × 6)
45969 := ((T((4 + T(5))) + 9) × T(T(T(–((6 – 9))))))
45972 := (((T(T(T(4))) × 5) – (T(9) – (7))) × T(T(2)))
45974 := ((4 + T((T(T(5)) – T(9)))) + (T(7) × T(T(T(4))))))
45975 := (((4⁵) × T(9)) + (–(7) × T(5)))
45976 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (–(T(5) – T(9)))) + (7 – T(T(6))))
45985 := (((T(T(4)) + (T(5))) × (–(9) + T(T(8)))) – (5))
45990 := (((4⁵) × T(9)) – (90))
45995 := (((4 – T(T(5))) – (T(T(9)) × (–9))) × 5)
45999 := (((4⁵) × T(9)) – ((9 × 9)))
46035 := (((T(T(4)) × 60) – T(T(T(3)))) × T(5))
46065 := ((–(T(4)) + T(T((6 + 06)))) × T(5))
46089 := (((T(T(T(4))) – T(T(6))) × T(08)) – T(T(9)))
46123 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T((6 + 1))) + T((T(T(T(2))))/3))
46125 := (((T(T(T(4))) × 6) – T(–(1) + T(T(2)))) × 5)
46133 := (–(4) – (T(6) × (–(13³))))
46135 := (((T(T(T(4))) × 6) – 13) × 5)
46145 := –((T(T(4)) + ((–(6 + 1)) × T(T(4))) × T(T(5))))
46150 := (((4 × T(T(6))) – 1) × 50)
46155 := ((–(4) + T(T((6 + 1) + 5))) × T(5))
46165 := (((T(T(T(4))) × 6) – (1 + 6)) × 5)
46167 := (((T(T(T(4))) × (–(T(T(6) – 1)))) + T(T(6)))/–(7))
46185 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (–(6) + T((1 × 8)))) – T(5))
46188 := ((T((T(4) × (6 – 1))) + 8) × T(8))
46195 := (((T(T(T(4))) × 6) – (1⁹)) × 5)
46210 := (T(4) × (T(T((6 × 2))) + T(T(10))))
46215 := (T(T(((4 × 6)/2))) × 15)
46217 := (–(4) + ((6^{T(T(2))}) – T((1 + T(7))))))
46221 := ((T(T(–((T(4) – T(6)))) × T(T(T(2)))) – T((T(T(T(2))) – 1)))
46222 := (((–(T(4)) + T(T(6))) – T(T(2)))²) – T(2))
46223 := –((T(T(4)) – ((6^{T(T(2))}) – T((T(2)³))))
46224 := (((–(T(T(4))) × (–(T(T(6))) + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(2))) × 4)
46225 := (((–(T(4)) + T(T(6))) – T(T(2)))^{–T(2)+5})
46227 := (T((4 × 6)) + (T(T(T(2))) × (T(2)⁷)))
46228 := ((T(T(T(4))) + (T((T(6) × T(2)))) × (T(T(T(2))) – 8))
46230 := ((T(T(T(4))) + (6/T(T(2)))) × 30)
46233 := (((T(T(4)) × T((T(6) + 2))) + T(T(T(3)))) × 3)
46234 := –(((T(T(4)) × (T(T(6)) + 2)) – (3^{T(4)})))
46235 := ((4 – (T(T((6 × 2))) × (–3))) × 5)
46236 := (((T(4) × T(6)) × (–2)) + (T(3)⁶))
46237 := (–(T(4)) + (((6^{T(T(2))}) – 3) – T(T(7))))
46238 := ((T(T(4)) + (6)) × (2 – (T(T(3)) × (–T(8))))))
46240 := (((T(T(4)) – (T(6)))²) × 40)
46242 := ((T(T(T(4))) + (T((6²) – (4))) × T(T(T(2))))
46245 := –((T(4) + (((T(6)^{T(2)}) – T(4)) × (–5)))
46248 := ((–(4) + T((6 + T(2)))) × T((T(T(4)) – 8)))
46250 := –((T(T(4)) + ((T(6)^{T(2)}) × (–(5 + 0))))
46251 := –((T(T(4)) + (((T(6)^{T(2)}) × (–5)) – 1))
46252 := (((T(4) – (T(6)^{T(2)})) × (–5)) – T(2))
46253 := –((T(T(4)) + (((T(6)^{T(2)}) × (–5)) – 3))
46254 := ((4 – ((T(6)^{T(2)}) × (–5))) – T(T(4)))
46255 := ((T(4) – (T(6)^{–2+5})) × (–5))
46256 := –((T(T(4)) + (((T(6)^{T(2)}) × (–5)) – (6)))
46257 := (((–(4) + (T(6)^{T(2)})) × 5) – T(7))
46258 := –((T(T(4)) + (((T(6)^{T(2)}) × (–5)) – 8))
46259 := –((T(T(4)) + (((T(6)^{T(2)}) × (–5)) – 9))
46263 := (((T(T(T(4))) × T((6 – 2))) + (T(6))) × 3)
46265 := –((T(4) + (((T(6)^{T(2)}) – (6)) × (–5)))
46267 := (–(4) + (((6^{T(T(2))}) + (T(6))) – T(T(7))))
46270 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(6) – T(2)) × T(70)))
46274 := ((T((T((4 + 6)) + 2)) × T(7)) – T(4))
46275 := ((4 + T(–(6) + (T(2) × T(7)))) × T(5))
46277 := ((T((T((4 + 6)) + 2)) × T(7)) – (7))
46282 := ((4 – T((T(6) + T(T(2)))) + (T(8)^{T(2)}))
46284 := ((T(T(4)) + (T(6))) × ((–(2) + T(T(8))) – T(T(4))))
46285 := ((4 + ((T(6)^{T(2)}) – 8)) × 5)
46287 := (((T(T(T(4))) + T(T((T(6)/T(2)))) × (–T(T(8))))/–(T(7)))
46288 := ((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(6))/T(T(2)))) × (–T(T(8)))) × (–8))
46292 := –((T(T(T(4))) – ((6^{T(T(2))}) + T((T(9) + T(2))))))
46295 := –((T(4) – ((T(6)²) × T((9 + 5))))
46299 := (–(T((46/2))) – (T(T(9)) × (–T(9))))
46305 := (((T(T(T(4))) × 6) + (T(T(3)))) × 05)
46315 := (T(4) – ((T(6)³) × (–(1 × 5))))
46320 := (((T(4) × T(T(6))) + (T(3))) × 20)
46323 := ((T(T(4)) × (–6)) + ((T(3)^{T(T(2))}) – 3))
46325 := (T(4) – (((T(6)³) + 2) × (–5)))
46326 := (((T(4) × (T(6)³))/2) + T(6))
46327 := ((–(4) + (6^{T(3)})) – T(–((T(2) – T(7))))))
46331 := ((T((4 + T(6))) – (T(3)^{T(3)})) × (–1))
46332 := ((T(T(4)) + T(T(6))) × (T(3) × (3^{T(2)})))
46333 := (T(T(4)) + (((6^{T(3)}) – T((3³))))
46335 := ((T(T(–((4 – 6)))) + (T(T(3)³))) × 5)
46342 := –(((T(T(4)) × T(T(6))) – ((3^{T(4)}) – 2)))
46343 := (–(4) + ((T(T((T(T(6))/T(T(3)))) – 4) × T(T(3))))
46344 := –(((T(T(4)) × T(T(6))) – (T((T(3) – (4)))^{T(4)})))
46345 := ((4 + ((T(6)³) + (4))) × 5)

- 46346** := $-((T(4) - ((6^{T(3)}) - T((4 \times 6))))$
46347 := $((-4) \times T(6)) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T((4+7))))$
46350 := $((4 \times T(T(6))) + 3) \times 50$
46352 := $((T(4) + (T(6)^3)) \times 5) - T(2)$
46353 := $((T(T(-((T(4) - T(6)))))) \times T(T(3))) - T((T(5) - 3)))$
46354 := $((T(T(4)) - 6) \times T(((3 - T(5)) + T(T(4))))$
46355 := $(T(T(4)) - ((T(6)^3) \times (-5)) + (5))$
46356 := $-((T((4 \times 6)) - ((T(3)^5) \times 6))$
46358 := $-((T(4) - (T(63) \times (T(5) + 8))))$
46359 := $(T((-4) + T(6)) \times (3 + T((T(5) + 9))))$
46362 := $-((T((4 \times 6)) - (T(3)^6)) + T(T(2)))$
46364 := $(-4) + (-T(6) \times (3 - T(T((T(6) - T(4))))))$
46365 := $((T(4) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(3))) - (T(65))$
46366 := $((T(4) - T((T(6) + 3))) + (6^6))$
46368 := $((-46) \times T(3)) \times T(6) \times (-8)$
46371 := $((T((T(4) \times 6)) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(7) + 1))$
46372 := $(4 + ((T(6) + (3^7)) \times T(T(T(2))))$
46375 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (-T(6) \times ((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) \times (-5))))$
46376 := $-((T(T(4)) - (T(6) \times T((3 \times (T(7) - (6))))))$
46379 := $((T(T(-((T(4) - T(6)))))) \times T(T(3))) - (7 + T(9)))$
46392 := $((4 - T(T((6 + 3))) \times (-T(9))) - T(2))$
46395 := $((4 - T(T((6 + 3))) \times (-9 \times 5))$
46396 := $((T(4) + (6^{T(3)})) - (T(9) \times 6))$
46398 := $((T(4) \times 6) + T(3)) \times T((T(9) - 8))$
46399 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(T((6 - 3)))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9))))$
46410 := $((-T(4) + T(T(6))) \times T((T(4) + 10)))$
46420 := $(T(4) - ((T(T(6)) - T(4)) \times (-T(20))))$
46421 := $(-T(4) + (T(6) \times T((T(4) + (2 - 1))))$
46423 := $(T(T(4)) + ((T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) - T(2)) \times T(T(3))))$
46425 := $((-T(4) + T(T(6))) \times T((T(4) \times 2))) + (T(5))$
46427 := $(-4) + (T(6) \times T((T(4) + (2 \times T(7))))$
46429 := $((-((T(T(4)) + 6)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-29))$
46431 := $(T((T(T(4)) + (T(6) - T(4)))) \times T(T((3 \times 1)))$
46432 := $(4 + ((T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) \times T(T(3))) - T(2))$
46433 := $((4 - T(T(6))) - (-4 - (T(3)^{T(3)}))$
46435 := $(T(T(4)) + ((6 + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(3) \times 5))$
46436 := $((-4) \times T((6 + 4)) + (T(3)^6))$
46438 := $((T(4) + T(6)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(3) + T(8))))$
46441 := $(T(4) + (T(6) \times T(T((-4) + T((4 + 1))))))$
46445 := $(-T(T(4))) + (6 \times ((T(T(T(4))) + T(4) \times 5))$
46446 := $-(((T(4) \times T(6)) - ((-4) + T(4))^6))$
46448 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(6) + T(4)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 8))))$
46452 := $((-4) + T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) + 5) \times T(T(T(2)))$
46456 := $(4 + ((T(6) \times T(T((-4) + T(5)))) + (T(6))))$
46458 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T((T(6) - 4)))/5) - (T(T(8)))$
46462 := $(T(4) + ((T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) \times T(6)) + T(T(T(2))))$
46464 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(6))) \times (-4) \times T((T(6) - T(4))))$
46466 := $-((T(((T(T(4)) + (T(6)))/4) - (6^6)))$
46473 := $((-((4 - 6)) + T(T((4 + 7)))) \times T(T(3)))$
46475 := $(T(T(4)) \times (((T(T(6)) - T(T(4))) - 7) \times 5))$
46478 := $(T(T(4)) - ((-T(6)) \times T(T((4 + 7)))) + 8)$
46483 := $(T(46) \times ((4 + T(8)) + 3))$
46486 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(6) + T((4 + T(8)))) + T(T(6)))$
46488 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (-6)) + ((T(T(T(4))) + 8) \times T(8)))$
46494 := $((-((T(4) - 64)) \times T((T(9) - 4)))$
46496 := $(-4) + (6 \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(9)) \times 6)))$
46499 := $((-T(4) - T((T(6) - T(4)))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9))))$
46515 := $((4 + T(T((6 + 5))) \times T((1 + 5)))$
46522 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((T(65) - T(2)) \times T(T(T(2))))$
46525 := $((T(T(4)) \times ((T(6) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(2)))) - (5))$
46526 := $((-((4 + 6)) - T(T(5))) + (T(T(2))^6))$
46528 := $((T(T(-((T(4) - T(6)))) + 5) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 8)$
46529 := $(-46) - (T((T(5) \times T(2))) \times (-T(9)))$
46530 := $(T(T(4)) \times ((T(6) + T(T(5))) \times T((3 + 0))))$
46531 := $((T(T(4)) \times ((T(6) + T(T(5))) \times T(3))) + 1)$
46532 := $((-((T(4) - 6)) - T(T(5))) + (T(3)^{T(T(2))}))$
46533 := $((T(T(4)) \times ((T(6) + T(T(5))) \times T(3))) + 3)$
46534 := $(4 + (((T(6) + T(T(5))) \times T(3)) \times T(T(4))))$
46535 := $((T(T(4)) \times ((T(6) + T(T(5))) \times T(3))) + (5))$
46536 := $((-((4 \times 6) \times 5) + (T(3)^6))$
46537 := $((T(T(4)) \times ((T(6) + T(T(5))) \times T(3))) + (7))$
46538 := $((T(T(4)) \times ((T(6) + T(T(5))) \times T(3))) + 8)$
46539 := $((T(T(4)) \times ((T(6) + T(T(5))) \times T(3))) + 9)$
46545 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(6) - (-T(5) \times T(T(4)))) + (T(5)))$
46546 := $(T(4) + (-T(6) \times (-5 - T(T(-((T(4) - T(6)))))))$
46555 := $((T(4) \times T((T(6) - (-5) \times T(5)))) - (5))$
46556 := $-((T(4) + ((6^5) - T(5)) \times (-6))$
46572 := $((-4) \times T(6)) + (T((T(5) - 7))^{T(2)})$
46575 := $((4 \times 6) + T(T((5 + 7))) \times T(5))$
46576 := $((T(4) + 6) \times (T(5) - T(76)))$
46579 := $(4 - (T(((T(6) \times T(5))/7) \times (-T(9))))$
46582 := $((46 - T(T(5))) + (T(8)^{T(2)}))$
46585 := $(T(T(4)) \times (T((T(6) + 5)) + T((T(8) - 5))))$
46592 := $(-T(4) + (((6^5) - 9) \times T(T(2))))$
46593 := $((T((T(4) + T(6))) + 5) \times 93)$
46595 := $((4 - ((6 - T(5)) \times T(T(9)))) \times 5)$
46596 := $((T(4) \times (-6)) + ((T(5) - 9)^6))$
46597 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (6 \times 5)) + (-9) + T(T(7)))$
46599 := $((4 \times 6) + (T((5 \times 9)) \times T(9)))$
46601 := $((T(T(4)) - (6^6)) \times (0 - 1))$
46615 := $-((T(T(4)) + (-((6^6) - 1)) - T(5)))$
46616 := $-(((T(T(4)) - (6^6)) - T(-((1 - 6))))$

$$\begin{aligned} 46617 &:= -(((T(4) - ((6^6) - 1)) + T(7))) \\ 46618 &:= (-((T(4) - (6^6))) - T(-((1 - 8)))) \\ 46620 &:= (((T(4) \times T(T(6))) + (T(6))) \times 20) \\ 46621 &:= -(((T(T(4)) - (T(6))) - ((6^{T(T(2))}) - 1))) \\ 46622 &:= (-((T(4) + T(6))) + ((6^{T(T(2))}) - T(2))) \\ 46623 &:= -((T(4) - (((6^6) - 23)))) \\ 46624 &:= ((4 + (6^6)) - T((2 \times 4))) \\ 46625 &:= (-((T(4) - (6^6))) - T(T(2))) - (T(5))) \\ 46627 &:= (-((4 - (6^6))) + T(2)) - T(7) \\ 46628 &:= ((T(4) + (((6^6) - 2))) - T(8)) \\ 46629 &:= -(((T(T(4)) - (6^6)) - T(-((2 - 9)))) \\ 46631 &:= (-((4) - T(6)) - ((6^{T(3)}) \times (-1))) \\ 46634 &:= -((T(4) - (((6^6) - (3 \times 4)))) \\ 46635 &:= -((((T(4) - (6^6)) + T(3)) + (5))) \\ 46636 &:= ((4 + ((6^6) - 3)) - T(6)) \\ 46638 &:= (-((4 - (6^6))) - T(3)) - 8) \\ 46639 &:= (T(4) + (((6^6) - (3 \times 9)))) \\ 46640 &:= (T(T(4)) \times (T((T(6) + T(6))) - T(T(4)))) \\ 46641 &:= (-((4 - (6^6))) - T(4)) - 1) \\ 46642 &:= (-(((T(4) - (6^6)) + T(4))) + T(T(2))) \\ 46643 &:= (-((T(4) - (6^6))) - T(-((4) + T(3)))) \\ 46645 &:= (((4 + (6^6)) - T(4)) - (5)) \\ 46646 &:= -((T(4) - ((6 \times ((6^4) \times 6)))) \\ 46647 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T((T(6) + T(6))) - T(T(4)))) + (7)) \\ 46649 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T((T(6) + T(6))) - T(T(4)))) + 9) \\ 46653 &:= (-((4 - ((6^6) - 5))) + T(3)) \\ 46654 &:= ((T(4) + (6^6)) - (T(T(5))/T(4))) \\ 46657 &:= ((4 + (6^6)) - T(-((5 - 7)))) \\ 46658 &:= (T(4) + (((6 \times (6^5)) - 8))) \\ 46659 &:= (T(-((4 - 6))) + (6^{T(5)-9})) \\ 46672 &:= -((((T(4) - (6^6)) - T(7)) + 2)) \\ 46674 &:= -((T(4) - (((6^6) + (7 \times 4)))) \\ 46675 &:= (-((4 - (6^6))) + T(7)) - (5) \\ 46677 &:= ((T(T(-((4 - 6))))^6) + (-7) + T(7)) \\ 46679 &:= (((4 + (6^6)) + T(7)) - 9) \\ 46681 &:= -((((T(4) - (6^6)) - T(8)) + 1)) \\ 46682 &:= (T(4) + (((6^6) + (8 \times 2)))) \\ 46683 &:= (((4 + T(66)) + 8) \times T(3)) \\ 46685 &:= -(((T(T(4)) - ((6^6) - T(8))) - T(T(5)))) \\ 46686 &:= ((T(T(-((4 - 6))))^6) + (T(8) - (6))) \\ 46689 &:= (-((4 - ((6^6) - 8))) + T(9)) \\ 46691 &:= (((T(4) - (6^6)) - T(9)) \times (-1)) \\ 46693 &:= (T(4) + (((6^6) + (9 \times 3)))) \\ 46695 &:= (((4 \times 6) + T(6)) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(5))) \\ 46696 &:= ((T(4) + (((6^6) + 9))) + T(6)) \\ 46697 &:= ((4 + ((6^6) + 9)) + T(7)) \\ 46699 &:= ((4 + T((-6) + T(6))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9)))) \\ 46704 &:= ((4 \times 6) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(04)))) \\ 46711 &:= (T(T(4)) + ((6^{7 \times 1 - 1})) \\ 46713 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) \times T((6 + 7))) - 1)/3) \\ 46716 &:= ((T(4) \times 6) + ((7 - 1)^6)) \\ 46722 &:= (T((T(4) - ((6 - 7)))) + (T(T(2))^{T(T(2))})) \\ 46723 &:= (((T(4) \times 6) + (7)) + (T(T(2))^{T(3)})) \\ 46725 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(T(6))/7)) - T((T(T(2)) \times T(5)))) \\ 46726 &:= (((4 + 6) \times 7) + (T(T(2))^6)) \\ 46728 &:= (T(-((T(4) - T(6))) \times ((7 \times T(T(2))) + T(T(8)))) \\ 46732 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times (-6)) + T(T(7))) + (T(3)^{T(T(2))})) \\ 46733 &:= ((T(4) + 67) + (T(3)^{T(3)})) \\ 46740 &:= -(((T(4) - 67) \times T(40))) \\ 46744 &:= (4 \times ((6 \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(4))) \\ 46745 &:= -((T(T(4)) - (((-6) + T(T(7))) - T(4)) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 46746 &:= (((T(T(4) \times 6)) + T(T(7))) - T(4)) \times T(6) \\ 46749 &:= (((4 \times 6) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(9)) \\ 46753 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times T(7)) - (-T(5) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 46762 &:= ((4 - T(T(6))) \times ((T(T(7)) + (6))/(-2))) \\ 46766 &:= ((T(T(T(4)))/(T(6) - (7))) + (6^6)) \\ 46774 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times T(7)) + T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) \\ 46784 &:= (T((T(4) + (6))) \times (-7) + T((T(8) - T(4)))) \\ 46792 &:= (T((T(4) + (6))) + (T(T(-((7 - 9))))^{T(T(2))})) \\ 46797 &:= -((T(T(4)) - ((6 + T(7)) \times T((T(9) + (7)))) \\ 46799 &:= (T(T(T(T(-((4 - 6)))))) + (-7) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9)))) \\ 46816 &:= (T(((4 \times T(6)) - 8)) \times 16) \\ 46820 &:= (-T(4)) - ((T(T(6)) - 8) \times (-T(20))) \\ 46822 &:= (((T(T(T(4)) + (T(6)))) \times 8) + T(2)) \times 2) \\ 46824 &:= (((T((4 + T(6))) \times T(8)) + T(T(2))) \times 4) \\ 46825 &:= ((T(T(4)) - (6 - (T(8)^{T(2)})) + T(T(5))) \\ 46826 &:= -(((T(T(4)) - T(T(6))) - (((T(8)^{T(2)}) - (6)))) \\ 46827 &:= (((-4) - T(T(6))) + (T(8)^{T(2)})) + T(T(7)) \\ 46828 &:= (T((T(4) + (6))) + ((T(8)^{T(2)}) + T(8))) \\ 46844 &:= (((4 \times 6) \times T((8 + T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46847 &:= (-((4) + T(T(6))) - (T(T(8)) \times (T(4) \times (-7)))) \\ 46849 &:= (4 - ((6 + T(T(T(8)/4))) \times (-T(9)))) \\ 46852 &:= (((4 - 6) + T(8)) \times T(52)) \\ 46855 &:= (T(T(4)) + ((T(T(6)) - T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5)))) \\ 46862 &:= -((T(4) + ((T(6) \times T(8)) \times (-62))) \\ 46865 &:= ((T((4 + 6)) + T(T(8))) \times 65) \\ 46866 &:= ((T(4) \times T(6)) + ((T(8)/6)^6)) \\ 46872 &:= ((4 \times 6) \times T(((T(8) + T(7)) - 2))) \\ 46879 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - ((T(6) - ((T(8) \times T(7)) \times T(9))))$$

- 46882** := $((T(4) + (6 \times T(8))) + (T(8)^{T(2)}))$
46883 := $((4 + T(T(6))) - (8 - (T(8)^3)))$
46893 := $((T(((T(4) + T(6)) + T(8))) - T(9)) \times T(T(3)))$
46897 := $((T(4) + T(T(6))) + ((T(8)^{T(9-7)}))$
46899 := $((-T(4) + T(T((6 - 8)))) + T(T(9)) \times 9)$
46932 := $((4 \times 69) + (T(3)^{T(T(2))}))$
46933 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(6))) - (9 - (T(3)^{T(3)})))$
46934 := $((T(46) \times T(9)) - T((3 + T(4))))$
46935 := $((T((T(4) + (6))) \times T(T(9)))/3 + (T(5)))$
46936 := $((T(4) + (6 \times T(9))) + (T(3)^6))$
46938 := $((46 \times T(T(9))) - (T(3))) - T(T(8)))$
46939 := $(T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(6)) - ((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) \times T(9))))$
46942 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(6))) + ((9 \times 4)^{T(2)}))$
46944 := $((46 \times T(T(9))) - T(T((4 + 4))))$
46945 := $((T(4) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(94)))) - (T(5)))$
46948 := $((46 \times T(T(9))) + (4)) - T(T(8)))$
46949 := $(-((T(T(4)) + (T(6))) + ((T(T(9)) + T(4)) \times (-T(9))))$
46956 := $(T((4 \times 6)) + ((-9) + T(5))^6)$
46957 := $(T((T(T(4)) + (6))) + ((-9) + T(5)) \times T(T(7)))$
46962 := $((T(T(4)) - (T(6))) \times 9) + (6^{T(T(2))})$
46966 := $((T(4) + T(-((T(6) - T(9)))) + (6^6))$
46968 := $(-(((T(T(4)) + (T(6))) \times (T(T(9)) - T((T(6) + T(8))))))$
46970 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T((T(6) + T(9)))) \times (-70))$
46973 := $((46 \times T(T(9))) - T(T(7))) - T(T(T(3)))$
46975 := $(T(T(4)) + ((-((6 + 9)) + T(7))) \times T(T(5)))$
46984 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (-6) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(8)))) \times 4)$
46985 := $(-4) - (-69) \times (T(T(8)) + (T(5)))$
46988 := $(-4) + ((T(6) - 9) \times T(88))$
46989 := $((4 \times 6) + T(9)) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(9))$
46992 := $(T((T(4) + T((6 - 9))) \times (9 + T(2)))$
46994 := $(-((T(4) + T(6))) - (-T(9)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(4)))$
46995 := $(T((4 \times 6)) - ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(9))) - T(T(5))))$
46997 := $((-((4 + 6)) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(9))) - T(7)$
47040 := $(T((T(T(4)) - (7))) \times 040)$
47062 := $(T((4 \times 7)) + (06^{T(T(2))}))$
47066 := $((4 + T(T(7))) + (06^6))$
47124 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T((7 - 1)))) \times T((2 \times 4)))$
47125 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(7)) + T((-1) - (T(T(2)) \times (-T(5))))$
47128 := $(T(T(4)) + (-71) \times (T(2) - T(T(8))))$
47134 := $(T(4) + (-T((7 + 1))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))$
47135 := $(T(T(4)) \times ((T(71)/3) + (5)))$
47145 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + 1)) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5))))$
47165 := $(-((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(-(1 - 6)))) - T(5))))$
47175 := $((T(4) + (7)) \times T(-(1 - 75)))$
47183 := $(T((4 + T(7))) + (-1) + (T(8)^3))$
47196 := $(T((T(4) + (7 + 1))) \times (T(9) + T(T(6))))$
47215 := $(T((T(4) \times 7)) \times (-2) + T((1 + 5)))$
47216 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(7)) + ((T(2) + 1)^6))$
47223 := $((T(T(4)) - T(7)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(2))^{T(3)})$
47224 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + 2)) + (2^{T(4)}))$
47225 := $(-((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(7)) - T(T(2))) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(5))))$
47229 := $(T((4 + T(7))) + ((T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}) + T(9)))$
47232 := $((-4) + T(72)) \times T(3) \times T(2)$
47235 := $((T(4) + T((T(7) - T(2)))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))))$
47236 := $((T((T(4) \times 7)) \times (-2) + T(T(3))) + (T(6)))$
47245 := $(T(T(4)) \times ((T(7) + T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) \times T(5))))$
47248 := $(-(((4^7)/2) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(8))))$
47250 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T((T(7) + T(T(2)))) \times 50)$
47253 := $(T((T(T(4)) - T(7))) + ((T(2) \times (5^{T(3)})))$
47261 := $((4^7) \times T(2)) - T(61)$
47264 := $((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(7)^2)) \times T(6)) - T(T(T(4))))$
47265 := $((T((T(4) \times 7)) + T(T((2 + 6)))) \times T(5))$
47268 := $((4 + T(T(7))) + T((2 \times T(6)))) \times T(8)$
47279 := $((-4) \times T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(9))$
47280 := $((-4) + T((T(7) + T(T(2)))) \times 80)$
47283 := $((-((T(4) - T(7))) \times T((2 \times T(8)))) - T(T(3)))$
47284 := $(4 + ((T(7) + 2) \times (T(8) + T(T(T(4)))))$
47285 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(7)) - T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T((8 + 5))))$
47286 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (7^2)) \times T(T(8)))/T(6)$
47288 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(7))) \times 2) + T((T(8) + T(8)))$
47292 := $(T(47) - 2) \times (T(9) - T(2))$
47295 := $((T(T(4)) - (7)) + (T(2) \times T(T(9)))) \times T(5)$
47313 := $((T((T(4) \times 7)) - T(T(T(3)))) - 1) \times T(T(3))$
47322 := $(T(T(((4 + 7) - 3))) + (T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}))$
47324 := $((T((T(4) \times 7)) - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(4)$
47325 := $((T(T(T(4))) + ((7 \times T(T(3)))) - 2) \times T(5))$
47327 := $((T((T(4) \times 7)) - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 7$
47328 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(7))) + 3) \times (-T((2 \times 8)))$
47329 := $(-47) \times (T((T(3)/T(2))) - T(T(9)))$
47332 := $((T((T(4) \times 7)) - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(3))) - 2$
47334 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + 3)) - (T(T((3 + 4))))$
47335 := $(T(T(4)) + ((T(T(7)) - (T(3) + T(3))) \times T(T(5))))$
47337 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (7 + T(3))) \times (3 + T(7)))$
47344 := $((T(4) - T(T(7))) - (-((T(T(3)) + T(4))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
47345 := $(-((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(7)) - T(T(3))) + T(4)) \times T(T(5))))$
47348 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T((7 + T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 8)$
47352 := $((T(T(4)) \times 7) \times (3 + T(T(5)))) - T(2)$
47355 := $(T(T(4)) \times T((T(7) + ((3 + 5) + 5))))$
47362 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + 3)) - T((T(6) + T(T(2))))$
47365 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (T((T(7) - 3)) \times (T(6) + T(T(5))))$
47368 := $(T(47) \times (T(T(3)) + (T(6)))) - 8$
47373 := $((T(47) \times T(3)) \times 7) - 3$

- 47376** := (((-47) × T(3)) × T(7)) × (-6))
47379 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (T(7) + 3)) - ((T(T(7)) - T(9))))
47382 := ((T(47) × (T(3) + T(8))) + T(T(2)))
47383 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((-T(7) + T(T((3 + 8)))) × T(T(3))))
47384 := (((T(47) + T(T(T(3)))) × T(8)) - T(T(T(4))))
47385 := ((T(T(4)) - T(T(7))) × ((T(T(3)) - T(8)) - T(T(5))))
47386 := ((T(T(4)) + T((T(7) + 3))) × 86)
47392 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(7)) - ((T(3) - T(92))))
47397 := ((T(-(4 - 7))^{T(3)}) + T((T(9) - (7))))
47398 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(7)) + T(-(T(3) - 98)))
47415 := ((T((T(T(4)) + (T(7) - 4))) + 1) × T(5))
47422 := ((T((T(4) + T(7))) × (4^{T(2)})) - 2)
47424 := (T((T(4) + T(7))) × ((4²) × 4))
47428 := (-4) + (7 × (-T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(8))))
47430 := (((4 × T(7)) - T(4)) × T(30))
47432 := (((T(T(T(4))) × T(7))/T(4)) × T(T(T(3))))/T(T(T(2))))
47434 := ((T((T(4) + T(7))) × (4³)) + T(4))
47436 := ((-4) + T(T(7))) × (T(T(4)) + (3 × T(6)))
47440 := ((-T(4)) - T((-7) + T(T(4)))) × (-40)
47445 := (((T(T(T(4))) + (T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4))) × T(5))
47447 := -((T(T(4)) - ((7 + T(T(4))) + T(T(4))) × T(T(7))))
47448 := -((T(T(T(4))) - (-74) × (4 - T(T(8))))
47455 := (T(T(4)) + ((T(74 + 5)) × T(5)))
47465 := (T(T(4)) × ((T(7) × (T(4) + T(6))) - 5))
47469 := -((T((T(T(4)) - 7)) - ((T(46) × T(9))))
47475 := ((T(T(4)) × T((-7) + T(T(4))) - 7)) + (T(T(5)))
47482 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((7 + T(T(4))) × T((T(8) + 2))))
47483 := ((T(T(4)) + T(T(7))) × (T(T(4)) + (8 × T(3))))
47484 := (((4 + T(7)) × (T(T(T(4))) - 8)) - T(T(T(4))))
47492 := (-T(4)) + (T(T(7)) × (T(T(-(4 - 9)))) - T(2))
47499 := ((4 × T(T(T(7 - 4)))) - (T(T(9)) × (-T(9))))
47502 := (T((4 × 7)) × (T(T(5)) - T(02)))
47505 := (((-T(4)) + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) - T(05))
47510 := (((-T(4)) + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) - 10)
47512 := (T(4) + (T(T(7)) × (T(T(5)) - (1 + 2))))
47513 := (((-T(4)) + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) - (1 + T(3)))
47514 := (((-T(4)) + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) - T(-(1 - 4)))
47515 := (((-T(4)) + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) - (1 × 5))
47519 := (((-T(4)) + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) - (1⁹))
47541 := (((-T(4)) + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) + T(T((4 - 1)))
47542 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(7)) - (T(T((T(5) - 4)))) × (-2))
47543 := (T(T(4)) + (-T(7)) × (T(5) - T((T(T(4)) + 3))))
47544 := (-T((T(T(4)) - 7))) - (-T(T(5))) × T((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4))))
47545 := (((-T(4)) + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) + (T(4) + T(5))
47547 := (((-T(4)) + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) + T(T(4)) - T(7))
47548 := (-4) × (-7) + (T(54) × (-8))
47554 := ((T(4) - T(T((7 + 5)))) + ((T(5)⁴)))
47556 := (((-T(4)) + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) + (T(5) + T(6)))
47557 := (T(T(4)) + ((-T((7 - 5))) + T(T(5))) × T(T(7)))
47562 := (((-T(4)) + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) + (T(6) × 2))
47565 := (((-T(4)) + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) + T((-6) + T(5)))
47566 := ((T(4) × T((T(7) - T(5)))) + (6⁶))
47568 := (((-T(4)) + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) + (6 × 8))
47569 := ((4⁷) + ((T(5) × T(T(6))) × 9))
47571 := (T(T((4 + 7))) + (T(T(5)) × T((T(7) - 1))))
47575 := (T(T(4)) × (((T(T(7)) × (-T(5)))/(-7)) - 5))
47576 := ((-4) + T((7 × 5))) × 76)
47578 := ((T(T(4)) × (T(T(7)) + T(T(5)))) - (-T(7) × T(T(8))))
47580 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (T(7) + 5)) - (T(80)))
47584 := (((-4) + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) - T(T(8))) + T(4)
47585 := (((T(T(4)) × (-T(7))) + 5) × (-T(8) - 5))
47586 := ((T(47) + 5) × (T(8) + 6))
47592 := ((T((4 × 7)) × T(T(5))) - T((T(9) + 2)))
47595 := (((-T(4)) + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) - T(9)) + T(T(5))
47620 := ((T(T(4)) - (T(T(7)) × 6)) × (-20))
47622 := (((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7)))) × (T(6) × 2)) - T(T(2))
47624 := (-4) + ((T(7) × T(6)) × (T(2)⁴))
47628 := (-((4 - 7)) × ((T(6)²) × T(8)))
47629 := -(((T(T(4)) + 7) - ((6^{T(T(2))}) + T(T(9))))
47635 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(7)) + (T((T(6) + T(T(3)))) × 5))
47638 := (T(4) + (T(7) × (T(T((6 + 3))) + T(T(8))))
47642 := ((T(T(4)) + T(7)) × (T((-T(6)) + T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(2))))
47652 := (-T((4 + 7)) × ((-6) × T(T(5))) - 2)
47656 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(7)) + ((T(T(6)) - T(5)) × T(6)))
47663 := ((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(7)) × T(T(6)))))/(6/3))
47667 := -((T(-(T(4) - T(7)))) - (T(6) × T(67)))
47672 := (((4 × T(7)) + 6) × (T(T(7)) - 2))
47673 := ((T(T(4)) + (-7) × T(67)) × (-3))
47677 := (((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7))) × 6) + 7) × 7)
47682 := ((T(T(4)) × (T((7 × 6)) - T(8))) - T(2))
47685 := ((T(T(T(4)))/T(7)) × (6 + T((T(8) + 5))))
47689 := (4 + ((T(T(7)) × T(-(T(6) - T(8)))) - T(T(9))))
47691 := ((T(-(4 - 7))⁶) + T(T((9 × 1))))
47695 := (T(T(4)) + ((T((7 + T(6))) - 9) × T(T(5))))
47698 := (-((T(4) + T(7))) - (T((6 + T(9))) × (-T(8))))
47712 := (((4 × T(7)) × T(71))/T(T(2)))
47725 := ((T(T(4)) × (T(7) × (T(7) + T(2)))) - (T(5)))
47726 := (((T(T(T(4))) + 7) × (T(7) + T(2))) - T(T(6)))
47733 := (((T(T(4)) - T(T(7))) × T(T(7)))/(-3)) + T(T(T(3)))
47734 := (-T(-(4 - 7))) - (-((T(7) + 3) × T(T(T(4))))
47735 := ((T(T(4)) × (T(7) × (T(7) + 3))) - 5)
47736 := ((T(T(4)) - T(T(7))) × (-T(((7 + 3) + 6)))
47752 := ((-T(47)) × (-7 - T(T(5))))/T(2)
47754 := -((T((T(T(4)) + T(7))) - (T(7) × T((T(5) × 4))))

- 47755** := ((T(T(4)) × T(7)) - (T(T((7+5))) × (-T(5))))
47762 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((-T(7) - T(T(7))) + (6^{T(T(2))})))
47769 := (((T(T(4)) + T(7)) × (T(7) × T(6))) - T(T(9)))
47775 := (((T(T(T(4))) × 7) - (T(7 × 7))) × 5)
47781 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(7)) + ((7 × T(T(8))) - 1))
47783 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((-7) - T(T(7))) + (T(8)³))
47794 := (-(((T(4) - T(7)) - T(7))) × (T(T(9)) + (4)))
47795 := (T(T(4)) × ((7 × 7) + T((T(9) - (5)))))
47815 := (T(T(4)) - ((T(T(7)) - 8) × (-T(15))))
47817 := ((T(-((T(4) - T(7)))) + T(8)) × T(T(-(1 - 7))))
47822 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(7) × T((T(8) + T(T(2)))))) - 2))
47823 := (((T(-((T(4) - T(7)))) + T(8)) × T(T(T(2)))) + T(3))
47824 := (T(T(T(4))) + (T(7) × T((T(8) + T((2 + 4))))))
47825 := -((T(T(4)) + ((T(7 × 8)) × (-2)) × T(5)))
47826 := (T(T(T(4))) - (((T(T(7)) - T(8)) - (T(T(2))⁶)))
47829 := (T(47) + ((T(8)^{T(2)}) + T(9)))
47831 := (T((T(T(4)) - (7))) + (((T(8)³) - 1))
47832 := (T((T(T(4)) - (7))) + (((T(8) × T(3))²)))
47834 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(7) × T((T(8) + T(T(3)))))) + T(4))
47835 := ((T(T(4)) + ((T(7) × T(8)))) × (3 × T(5)))
47838 := ((4 - T(T(7))) × (-83 - T(8)))
47842 := (((T(T(4)) × T((-7) + T(8)))) - (4)) × 2)
47848 := ((T(T((4 + 7))) × (-8)) + (4⁸))
47852 := -((T(T(T(4))) + (-7) × ((-T(8) + T(T(5))²)))
47853 := -((T(T(4)) - (T(T(7)) × ((-8) + T(T(5))) + (T(3))))))
47854 := (4 + (T((-7) + T(8))) × (T(T(5)) - T(4)))
47856 := ((4 - (T(7 × 8)) × 5) × (-6))
47862 := (((T(4) × T((7 × 8))) - (6)) × T(2))
47869 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(7) × T((T(8) + T(6)))) + T(9)))
47873 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(7)) + T((-8) + T((-7) + T(T(3))))))
47879 := (T(T(4)) + (T(7) × ((T(T(8)) + (7)) + T(T(9))))
47890 := (T(4) × ((T(7) + T(T(8))) + (T(90))))
47893 := (T(T(4)) + (T((-7) - (T(T(8)) / (-9)))) × T(T(3)))
47894 := (T(T(T(4))) + (T((7 + T(8))) × (T(9) + (4))))
47895 := (((T(4) × 7) × T(T(8))) + T((T(9) + (5))))
47905 := (T(T(4)) × (T(T(7)) + T((T(9) - T(05))))))
47912 := (4 - (-T(7) × T((T(9) + 1) + T(2))))
47922 := ((4 + T(((T(7) + T(9)) - T(T(2)))))) × T(T(T(2))))
47925 := ((47 × T(T(9))) - (T(T(2)) × T(T(5))))
47926 := ((T(4) + (T(7) × T(9))) + (T(T(2))⁶))
47929 := (4 + (((T(7) + T(T(9))) + 2) × T(9)))
47935 := (T(T(4)) + (((T(7) - 9) × T(T(3))) × T(T(5))))
47938 := (T(T(T(4))) + (T((T(7) + 9)) × T((3 + 8))))
47944 := ((T(T(4)) + T(T(7))) × (94 + T(4)))
47946 := ((T((T(4) + T(7))) + T(9)) × (T(T(4)) + (6)))
47948 := (-4) + ((-((T(7) - T(9))) + T(T(4))) × T(T(8)))
47952 := ((T(T(4)) - (7)) × (T(T(9)) - T((5 + T(2))))))
47955 := ((47 × (T(T(9)) - (T(5)))) + (T(5)))
47957 := ((T(T(T(4))) + 7) × ((T(9) / T(5)) + T(7)))
47962 := (((T(T(T(4))) × T(7)) - 9) - (-T(T(6)) × T(T(T(2))))))
47971 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(7)) + T((97 + 1)))
47975 := ((-4) - T((-7) + T(9))) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(5)))
47982 := (((47 × T(T(9))) - T(T(8))) + T(2))
47988 := (((T(T(4)) - ((T(7) - T(9)))) × T(T(8))) + T(8))
47992 := -((T(T(T(4))) + (-T(T(7))) × (T(T((T(9) / 9)) + 2))))
47993 := (-T(T(4)) + (-T(7) × (-T((9 + T(9)))) - T(T(T(3))))))
47995 := ((T(T(4)) × T(7)) - ((T(T(9)) × (-T(9))) + T(T(5))))
47998 := (T(4) + ((T((7 + T(9))) - T(9)) × T(8)))
48048 := ((T(T(4)) + T(8)) × T((04 × 8)))
48055 := (T(T(4)) - ((80 × T(T(5))) × (-5)))
48125 := (T(T(4)) × ((T(8) - 1) × 25))
48128 := ((T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) × ((1 + T(2)) × 8))
48132 := ((T((T(T(4)) - T(8))) + 1) × (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2))))))
48146 := (((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(8)) - 1)) × T(T(4))) + (T(6)))
48155 := -((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(81) × T(5)) - T(T(5))))))
48156 := (4 × (-T(T(8))) + (T(T(-(1 - 5)))) × T(T(6))))
48165 := (T((T(4) + T((8 - 1)))) × 65)
48167 := (((T(4) × (T(T(8)) - 1)) + T(T(6))) × 7)
48168 := ((T(T(T(4))) - (-8) + T((-1) + T(6)))) × T(8)
48183 := (((-4) × T(T(8))) × (-18) + T(T(T(3))))
48196 := (T(T(T(4))) + (T(8)^{1×9-6}))
48199 := (4 - ((-T(8) - T(T((1 × 9)))) × T(9)))
48202 := (T(T(T(4))) - ((T(8)^{T(2)}) - T(T(02))))
48216 := (T(T(T(4))) + (((T(8)^{T(2)}) - 1) + T(6)))
48217 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(8)^{T(2)}) + T(-(1 - 7))))
48222 := (((T(T(4)) - 8) × T(T(2))) × T((T(2) × T(T(2))))))
48223 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(8)^{T(2)}) + (T(2)³)))
48224 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(8)^{T(2)}) + T((T(2) + (4))))
48225 := ((T(T(4)) + T((82 - T(2)))) × T(5))
48226 := (T(T(T(4))) + (T(8) + ((T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}) - (6))))
48227 := (T(T(T(4))) + (((T(8)^{T(2)}) + T(2)) + T(7)))
48231 := (T(T(T(4))) + (T(8) + ((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) - 1)))
48232 := (T(T(T(4))) + (T(8) + (T(2³)^{T(2)})))
48235 := (T(T(4)) × (((T(8) + T(T(2))) × T(T(3))) - (5)))
48237 := (((T(4) × T(T(8))) + T(T((2 × 3)))) × 7)
48238 := (T(T(T(4))) + (((T(8)^{T(2)}) + T(3)) + T(8)))
48241 := (T(T(T(4))) - ((-T(8)^{T(2)}) - T((T(4) - 1))))
48244 := ((4 × ((T(T(8)) × T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(4))))
48245 := (((T(T(4)) × T((T(8) + T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5))))
48246 := ((-T(4) + T((T(8) + 2))) × T(-(T(4) - T(6))))
48251 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(8)^{T(2)}) + T(T((5 - 1))))
48255 := ((T(T((4 + 8))) + T((T(T(2)) - 5))) × T(5))

- 48256** := $(4 + ((T(8)^{T(2)} + T(56)))$
48257 := $((T((T(4) \times 8) - T(T(2))) \times T(5) - (T(7)))$
48262 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (T((8 + T(2))) + (6^{T(T(2))}))$
48265 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(8) - 2) - (T((6 \times T(5))))$
48268 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (T(8) + ((T(T(2))^6 + T(8))))$
48269 := $((T(T(4) - 8) \times (-((2 + 6) + T(T(9))))$
48273 := $((T(T((T(4) - 8)))^{T(T(2))}) + (7 \times T(T(T(3))))$
48275 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - (T((T(8) + T((2 + 7)))) \times T(5)))$
48278 := $((T(T(4) + ((8^2))) \times T(T(7))) - T(8))$
48279 := $((T(T(4) \times 8) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(-((7 - 9))))))$
48282 := $((T(T(4) - ((T(T(8))/T(2)) \times (-T(8)))) \times T(T(2)))$
48285 := $((T((T(4) \times 8) - T(-((2 - 8)))) \times T(5))$
48295 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((T(8) + T(T((2 + 9)))) \times T(5)))$
48315 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (((T(8)^3) - 1) + T(T(5))))$
48316 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (T(8)^3)) + T(T(-((1 - 6))))$
48320 := $-((T((T(4) - T(8))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(20))))$
48322 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (T(8)^3) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(2))))$
48323 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T((T(8) - 3))) \times 23)$
48324 := $((-T(T(4))) \times (-T(8) + T(T(T(3)))) + (T(2)^{T(4)}))$
48334 := $((T(T(4) \times 8) - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4))))$
48336 := $((T(4) \times 8) \times T(T(3))) + (T(3)^6)$
48339 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((T(8) + T(3)))) - T((T(3) + T(9))))$
48342 := $((T((T(T(4) + 8) + T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
48344 := $((T((T(T(4) + 8) \times T(3)) - T(4)) \times 4)$
48345 := $(T(T(4)) \times ((T(8) \times T(3)) \times 4) + T(5))$
48346 := $((-T((4 + T(8)))) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-46)$
48348 := $((T(T(4) - (8 - (T(3)^4))) \times T(8))$
48355 := $((-4) - ((T(T(8) - T(T(3))) \times (-T(5)))) \times 5)$
48356 := $-((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(8) \times T(T(3))) \times (-T((5 + 6))))$
48357 := $((-((T(4) \times T(8) + 3)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))))$
48362 := $-((T(T(T(4))) + ((-((T(8) \times T(3)) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(2))))$
48363 := $((T(T(4) - 8) \times (-T(3) + T(T((6 + 3))))$
48366 := $((-4) \times T(8) - ((T(T(3) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(6))))$
48369 := $((T(T(4) - (T(8) \times T(T(3)))) \times (-69))$
48370 := $((4 + T(T(8))) + T(T(3))) \times 70$
48372 := $((T(4) \times T((T(8) + T(T(3)))) - (T(T(7)))) \times T(2))$
48374 := $((4 + 8)^3 \times T(7) - T(4))$
48375 := $((T((T(T(4) - 8) - 3) \times (T(7) + T(5))))$
48377 := $((4 + 8)^3 \times T(7) - 7)$
48379 := $(4 + (((T(T(8)) + 3) + T(T(7))) \times T(9)))$
48380 := $-((T((4 + T(8))) \times (T(T(3)) - (80)))$
48382 := $((T((T(T(4) + 8) \times (3 \times 8)) - 2)$
48384 := $((-4) \times ((T(T(8) + T(3))) \times (-8 - T(4))))$
48388 := $(4 - ((T(8) \times T(T(3))) \times (-8 \times 8)))$
48389 := $((T(4) + T((T(8) + T(3)))) \times (8 + T(9)))$
48394 := $(T(4) + ((T(8) \times T(T(3))) \times (9 + T(T(4))))$
48396 := $((T((T(4) + T(8))) - (T(3))) \times T(9) + (T(6)))$
48398 := $((-4) + ((T(8) \times T((T(3) + T(9)))) + T(T(8))))$
48412 := $((T(T(4) + T(8)) \times T((T(T(4) + 1)))/T(2))$
48416 := $((T(4) \times T(8) - 4) \times T(16))$
48424 := $(4 \times ((T((8 + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(2))) + T(4))$
48425 := $((T(4) \times T(T(8))) + (T(T(4))^2) \times 5)$
48426 := $(T((4 + T(T((8 - 4)))) + (T(T(2))^6))$
48429 := $((T((T(T(4) + 8)) \times (4 \times T(T(2)))) + T(9))$
48432 := $((-T((4 + 8))) - ((-T(4) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
48433 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((T(8) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(3))))$
48435 := $((T(4) + T((8 \times T(4)))) - T(T(3)) \times T(5))$
48439 := $(T(T(4)) + (T((8 + T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(3)) - T(9))))$
48448 := $((-((T(4) - T(8))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-4 \times 8))$
48462 := $((-48) - ((-T(4) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
48463 := $-((T(T(4) - 8) + ((-T(4) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(3))))$
48465 := $((-4) + T((T(8) + T(4)))) \times T((-6 + T(5)))$
48473 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \times T(T(4))) + ((T(T(7)) - 3))$
48475 := $((-T(T(4))) - T((-T(8) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(5))))$
48476 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \times T(T(4))) + T((7 + T(6)))$
48489 := $-((T(T(4) - ((T(T(8) - T(4)) \times T(T(8)))/9))$
48492 := $((T(T(4) - 8^4) \times (-9) - T(2))$
48495 := $((T(4) \times T((8 - (T(4) \times (-9)))) - (T(5)))$
48498 := $((-4 + 8) + (T(4) \times T(98)))$
48520 := $(T(4) - (T((T(8) - T(5))) \times (-T(20))))$
48521 := $((T(4) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T((T(5) - 2)))) + 1)$
48522 := $((T((T(4) \times 8) \times T(5)) - T((2 \times T(T(2))))$
48523 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((-T(8) - (5^{T(T(2))})) \times (-3)))$
48524 := $((T((T(4) \times 8) \times T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4))))$
48525 := $((T((T(4) \times 8) - 5) \times (T(2) \times 5))$
48526 := $((T(4) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T((T(5) - 2)))) + 6)$
48527 := $((T(T(4) - 8) - (T(T(5)) \times (2 - T(T(7))))$
48528 := $((T((T(4) \times 8) \times T(5)) + (-2) \times T(8))$
48529 := $((T(4) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T((T(5) - 2)))) + 9)$
48532 := $((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(8)))) \times ((5 + T(3)) \times 2))$
48534 := $((T((T(4) \times 8) \times T(5)) - T((T(T(3)) - T(4))))$
48536 := $((-((T(4) - T(8))) - (T((T(T(5))/T(3))) \times (-T(T(6))))$
48542 := $((T((T(4) \times 8) \times T(5)) - T(T(4))) - T(2))$
48544 := $((T(4) - T(T(8))) \times ((-T(5) - T(T(4))) - 4))$
48545 := $((-T(T(4))) + (T((-T(8) + T(T(5))) - 4)) \times T(5))$
48550 := $((T((T(4) \times 8) \times T(5)) - 50)$
48555 := $((T((T(4) \times 8) - (T(5)/5)) \times T(5))$
48556 := $((T(4) + T(8) + (T((5 + T(5))) \times T(T(6))))$
48557 := $((T((T(4) \times 8) \times T(5)) - (T(5) + T(7)))$
48563 := $((-((T(T(4) - (T(T(8)) \times (-5 + T((6 + T(3))))$
48564 := $((T(T(4) - T(8)) \times T((5 + T((T(6) - T(4))))$
48565 := $((T(T(4) \times T((8 \times 5))) + (T(T(6)) \times T(5)))$
48567 := $((T((T(4) \times 8) \times T(5)) - (T(T(6))/7))$

- 48571** := ((T((T(4) × 8)) × T(5)) - (T(7) + 1))
48572 := (((T((T(4) × 8)) × T(5)) - (7)) - T(T(T(2))))
48573 := ((-4) × T(8)) + ((T(T(5)) × T(T(7))) - 3)
48574 := -(((T(T(4)) + T(8)) - ((T(T(5)) × T(T(7))) - T(T(4))))
48576 := (((4 × 8) × T((T(5) + (7)))) × 6)
48577 := -(((T(T(4) + 8)) - ((T(T(5)) × T(T(7))) + T(7))))
48579 := (-T(48)) + ((T(T(5)) × T(T(7))) + T(T(9)))
48582 := ((T((T(4) × 8)) × T(5)) - (T(8)/2))
48585 := (((T((T(4) × 8)) × T(T(5)))/8) - (T(5)))
48586 := ((T((T(4) × 8)) × T(5)) - (8 + 6))
48590 := -((T(4) + ((T(8) × T(5)) × (-90)))
48591 := ((T((T(4) × 8)) × T(5)) - (9 × 1))
48592 := ((4 - ((T(8) × T(5)) × T(9))) × (-2))
48595 := (((T(4) × T(8)) × T(5)) × 9) - (5)
48596 := (-4) - (((T(8) × (-5)) × T(9)) × 6)
48597 := ((T((T(4) × 8)) × T(5)) - T((9 - 7)))
48598 := (-T(4)) + (T((T(8) - (5)) × 98))
48599 := ((T((T(4) × 8)) × T(5)) - (9/9))
48612 := ((T(T(4)) + (T(T(8)) × 6)) × 12)
48615 := ((T((T(4) × 8)) × T((6 - 1))) + (T(5)))
48618 := (((4 + 8) + 61) × T(T(8)))
48624 := (4 × ((T(T(8)) × T(6)) - T((T(T(2)) × T(4))))
48628 := ((T(T(4)) × T(8)) + ((6^{T(T(2))}) - 8))
48633 := ((T(T(4)) × T(8)) + ((6^{T(3)}) - 3))
48636 := ((T(T(4)) × T(8)) + (T((6 - 3)⁶))
48637 := (4 + (T(86) × (T(3) + (7))))
48642 := ((T(T(4)) × T(T(8))) + (T(T(6)) × (T(T(4)) - T(2))))
48643 := (T(4) + (T(86) × (T(4) + 3)))
48645 := -(((T(4) - T(8)) - T(6)) × T(45))
48649 := (4 + ((-8) + T((6 + 4))) × T(T(9)))
48654 := (((4 + T(T(8))) + T(T(6))) × 54)
48655 := (T(T(4)) - (((T(8) × (-6)) × T(5)) × T(5)))
48657 := ((T((T(4) - 8)) × (-T(6))) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(7))))
48660 := ((T(T(4)) + ((T(8) × T(6)))) × 60)
48662 := -((T(4) + (-8) × (T((6 + 6)²)))
48664 := (T(T(T(4))) + (-T(8)) × (T(T(6)) - T(T(6 + 4))))
48665 := -((T(T(4)) - (T(T(8 - (6/6)))) × T(T(5))))
48666 := (T((T(T(4)) + 8)) - (6 - (6⁶)))
48672 := (((-4) - T(T(8))) - (6)) × (-72)
48673 := (T(T(4)) + (T(T(8)) × (67 + T(3))))
48675 := (T(T(4)) × (-((8 - 67) × T(5)))
48679 := (4 + ((T((T(8) - T(6))) × T(T(7))) - T(9)))
48685 := ((4 + T(86)) × (8 + 5))
48692 := -((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T((-8) + T(6)))) × (-9) - T(2)))
48693 := ((48 × (-T(6) + T(T(9)))) + T(T(3)))
48695 := (((-T(4) + T(T(8))) - (T(T(6)) × T(9))) × (-5))
48696 := (((T(T(4)) - 8) × (6 + T(T(9)))) - T(T(6)))
48705 := ((T((T(4) × 8)) + (7)) × T(05))
48714 := -((T(T((T(4) - 8))) - ((T(T(7)) × T(T((1 + 4))))))
48715 := (T(4) - (((8 × T(T(7))) - 1) × (-T(5))))
48716 := (-4) - (-T((8 + 7)) × T(T((1 + 6))))
48732 := ((4 + 8) + (T(T(7)) × T(T((3 + 2))))
48735 := ((T(T((4 + 8))) + (T(7) × T(3))) × T(5))
48738 := ((T(4) + 8) - (-T(T(7)) × T(T(-(3 - 8))))
48739 := ((T(T(4)) - T(8)) + (T(T(7)) × T(T((3 + 9))))
48741 := (T(T(T((T(4) - 8)))) + ((T(T(7)) × T(T((4 + 1))))
48751 := ((4 × 8) + ((T(T(7)) × T(T(5))) - 1))
48752 := -((T(4) - T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) × T(T(5))) + T(T(2))))
48753 := ((4 + 8) + ((T(T(7)) × T(T(5))) + T(T(3))))
48754 := -((T(T(T((T(4) - 8)))) - (((T(T(7)) × T(T(5))) + T(T(4))))
48755 := ((4 + T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) × T(T(5))) - (5)))
48757 := (((4⁸) - (7⁵)) + T(7))
48758 := ((T(4) - 8) + ((T(T(7)) × T(T(5))) + T(8)))
48759 := (48 + ((T(T(7)) × T(T(5))) - 9))
48762 := (((T(4) + 8) × T((7 × 6))) × T(2))
48763 := (((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(8))) + (-7) × T(T(6))))/T(T(3))
48765 := (((T(4) × T(T(8))) × 7) + (T(65)))
48766 := ((T(4) + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) × T((-6) + T(6))))
48768 := (-((T(4) + (-8) × T(7))) × T(T(6))) - T(T(8))
48772 := (T(T(4)) + ((T((8 + 7)) × T(T(7))) - T(2)))
48775 := (T(T(4)) + (T(T((8 - 7) × 7))) × T(T(5)))
48776 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(8)) - (T(7) × (7 + T(T(6))))
48783 := ((T(T(4)) + 8) + (T(T(7)) × T(T((8 - 3))))
48785 := -((T(T(4)) - (((-8) × T(T(7))) - 8) × (-T(5))))
48795 := ((-4) - ((-8) × T(T(7))) - 9) × T(5)
48815 := -((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(8) + T(81)) × T(5)))
48824 := ((T(-((T(4) - T(8)))) + 8) × T((2⁴)))
48825 := ((T((T(4) × 8)) + T((8 - T(2)))) × T(5))
48826 := (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(8)) × (8 + (T(2) × T(6))))
48828 := ((4 + 8) × (T(82) + T(T(8))))
48832 := (((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(8))) - (8 × T(T(3))))/T(T(T(2))))
48835 := (((T(T(4)) × T(T(8))) × 8)/T(3)) - (5)
48852 := ((T((T(4) + 8)) + T(8)) × (5 + T(T(T(2))))
48853 := (((T(T(T(4))) + T(8)) × (T(8) - (5))) - 3)
48855 := (((T(T(T(4))) × (-T(T(8))))/(-T(8) - T(5))) + T(5))
48856 := ((T(T(T(4))) + T(8)) × ((T(T(8)) - (T(5)))/T(6)))
48859 := -((T(T(4)) - ((T(T(8)) × (T(T(8)) - (5)))/9))
48862 := (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(8)) + ((T(8)^{6/2})))
48864 := ((4 × 8) × ((8 - T(6)) + T(T(T(4))))
48867 := ((T((T(4) × 8)) + T(86)) × 7)
48880 := ((T(T(-((4 - 8)))) - (T(T(8))) × (-80))
48888 := (((-((T(4) - T(8))) + T(T(8))) + T(T(8))) × T(8))
48892 := ((T(T(4)) × 889) - T(2))
48895 := (-T(T(4)) × ((8 - T(T(8))) - T(T((-9) + T(5))))

- 48896** := $-((T(T(4)) - (((T(8) \times T(8)) + T(T(9))) \times T(6))))$
48898 := $((T(4) + T(8)) \times ((-8) + T(T(9))) + T(8))$
48925 := $((T(T(4)) - T(8)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(2 \times 5))))$
48927 := $((T(T(4)) - 8) \times (T(T(9)) + T((T(T(2))/7)))$
48928 := $(4 + ((T(T(8)) - ((T(9)^2)) \times (-T(8))))$
48933 := $((T(T(4)) - 8) \times (T(T(9)) + (T(3)))) + (T(3))$
48944 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(8)))) \times ((-9) + T(4)) + T(T(4)))$
48945 := $((T(T(4)) \times (89 \times T(4))) - (5))$
48946 := $((T(T(4)) - T(8)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(6)))$
48955 := $((48 \times (T(T(9)) - (T(5)))) - (5))$
48956 := $(-4) + ((8 \times T(9)) \times T((-5) + T(6)))$
48964 := $(4 + ((8 \times T(9)) \times T((6 + T(4))))$
48966 := $((-4) \times (-8 - T(9))) \times T(T(6)) - (6)$
48969 := $((4 \times T(T(8))) - ((T(T(9)) - (6)) \times (-T(9))))$
48972 := $((-4) \times (-8 - T(9))) \times T((7 \times T(2)))$
48974 := $((T(T(4)) - 8) \times (T(T(9)) + (T(7)/4))$
48975 := $((T(4) \times T(8)) \times T((9 + 7))) + T(5)$
48978 := $((T(4) \times T(8)) - (-((T(9) + T(7))) \times T(T(8))))$
48984 := $(-4) + ((T(T(8))/9) \times (T(T(8)) - (4)))$
48993 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T((8 + T(9))))/T(9) + (T(T(3))))$
48995 := $-((T((4 + T(8))) - (T(9 \times 9)) \times T(5)))$
48997 := $(T((T(T(4)) + 8)) - ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(9))) - T(T(7))))$
49085 := $-((T(T(4)) + (-90) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(5))))$
49092 := $((4 - T(90)) \times (-9) - T(2))$
49113 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(9 - 1) + 1)^3)))$
49125 := $((T((T(4) \times 9)) \times 12) - (T(5)))$
49128 := $((4 \times (T(9) + 1)) \times (T(T(T(2)))) + T(8))$
49132 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(9)) + 1) + (T(3))^{T(T(2))}$
49135 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(9)) \times (1 + (T(3) \times 5)))$
49152 := $((4^{-9+1+T(5)}) \times T(2))$
49212 := $((T((T(4) \times 9)) + T(T(2))) \times 12)$
49215 := $((T(T(4)) \times 9) - (T(T((T(2)) + 1))) \times (-T(T(5))))$
49221 := $((-4) \times T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(T(2))))^2 \times 1)$
49222 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 2)$
49223 := $(-T(T(4))) + (((-9) + T(T(T(T(2))))^2) - T(3))$
49224 := $((T(T(4) \times 9)) \times T(2)) + T(T(T(2))) \times 4$
49225 := $(T(T(4)) \times (T((9) - T(2))) - (T(2) + (5)))$
49229 := $(-T(4)) + (((-9) + T(T(T(T(2))))^2) - T(9))$
49231 := $(T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(9)) + (T(T(2))^{T(3)})) \times (-1)))$
49233 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(9)) - (-2) - (T(3))^{T(3)}))$
49234 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(3))) + T(4)$
49240 := $((-T(49)) - T(T(2))) \times (-40)$
49244 := $(4 \times (-9) - ((2 \times T(T(4))) \times (-4)))$
49248 := $((-T(4)) + T(((T(9) - T(2)) + T(4)))) \times T(8)$
49257 := $((T(T(-((4 - 9)))) - T(2)) \times (T(5) + T(T(7))))$
49262 := $((-4) - T((T(9) \times 2))) + (T(T(6))^2)$
49263 := $((T((-T(4)) + T((9 + T(2)))) \times T(6)) - 3)$
49265 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times ((9 + 2) + T(6))) - T(5))$
49266 := $(T((4 \times ((9 + 2) + 6))) \times T(6))$
49269 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(6)) + T(9)$
49272 := $((4 \times ((T(9)^2) + T(7))) \times T(T(2)))$
49273 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(9)) + 2) \times (T(7) + T(T(3))))$
49275 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T((T(9) - T(2)) - (7))) - (5))$
49277 := $((-((T(T(T(4))) - T(9))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7))))/(-7))$
49294 := $((T((4 \times 9))^2/9) + T(4))$
49295 := $-((T(T(4)) + (-((T(9) + 2) \times (T(T(9)) + (T(5))))$
49296 := $((4 + 9) + T(2)) \times T(T((-9) + T(6)))$
49328 := $((4 + (T(T((9 + 3))) \times 2)) \times 8)$
49329 := $((T((4 \times 9)/3)^2) + T(9))$
49332 := $((-4 - T(T(9))) + (T(T(3))^3)) \times T(T(2))$
49335 := $(T(T(4)) \times (T(T((9 - 3))) + T(T((3 + 5))))$
49337 := $-((T(T(4)) + (T((T(9) + 3)) \times (T(3) \times (-7))))$
49339 := $(T(T(4)) - ((9 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 9))$
49346 := $((-T(4)) + T((T(9) - 3))) \times T(T(4)) + T(T(6))$
49350 := $(T(4) \times ((T(T(9)) \times T(3)) - T(50)))$
49351 := $(T(T(4)) + (T(T((9 + 3))) \times (T(5) + 1)))$
49354 := $((T(T(4)) - T((T(9) + T(3)))) + ((T(5)^4))$
49356 := $((T(4) \times T(9)) + (T(3)^5)) \times 6$
49357 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((9 \times T(T(3))) \times T((T(5) + (7))))$
49362 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(9)) + T(T(T(3)))) + (6^{T(T(2))})$
49364 := $((-4) + T(9)) \times (-T(T(3))) + T((-6) + T(T(4))))$
49365 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times 3) + (T(6)) \times T(5)$
49368 := $((-T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(3) + (T(6)) \times 8$
49375 := $(T(T(4)) + (T((9 + T(3))) \times (T(T(7)) + (5))))$
49382 := $(-T(4)) + ((T(T(9)) - (T(3)) \times 8) \times T(T(2)))$
49383 := $((T(T(4)) \times (-T(9))) - (T(T(3)) \times T(T(8)))) \times (-3)$
49384 := $(49 + ((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(8)))) \times T(T(4))))$
49388 := $(-4) + ((T(T(9)) \times T(3)) - T(8)) \times 8$
49392 := $(T((4 \times (9 + 3))) \times (T(9) - T(2)))$
49395 := $((4 \times T((T(9) + T(T(3)))) + T(T(9))) \times 5)$
49396 := $(4 - (-((T(9) + 3)) \times (T(T(9)) - (6))))$
49420 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(9)) - (4)) \times 20$
49422 := $((4 + (9 \times T((T(4) \times T(T(2)))))) \times T(2))$
49424 := $((T(T(T(4))) + 9) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (2^4)$
49425 := $((T(4) \times T(T(9))) - T((T(4) \times T(2)))) \times 5$
49428 := $((4 - 9) + T((T(T(4)) - T(2)))) \times T(8)$
49434 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (-9) - (T(T(4)) \times (-T(3))))/T(4)$
49435 := $((T(T(4)) \times (-T(9) - T(43))) - T(T(5)))$
49442 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(9)) - T((4 \times 4))) - T(2))$
49443 := $((T((T(T(4)) - 9)) + (T(T(T(4))) \times T(4))) \times 3)$
49445 := $(T(T(4)) \times (T(T(9)) - T(-((4 - (4 \times 5))))$
49452 := $((4 + T((T(9) - T(4)))) \times T((T(5) - T(2))))$

- 49456** := ((T(T(4)) × T(T(9))) + ((T(T(T(4))) × (-5)) + T(T(6))))
49465 := ((T(4) - T(9)) - (-T(4)) × T((-T(6)) + T(T(5))))
49466 := ((T(T(4)) × (T(T(9)) - T((T(4) + (6)))))) + (T(6))
49467 := (((-4) + T(9)) - T(T(T(4)))) × (T(T(6)) / (-7))
49469 := -((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(9) + (4)) × (-6) - T(T(9))))))
49475 := -((T(T(T(4))) + ((-T(9)) × (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(7)))))) + T(5))
49476 := (-4) × (-((T(9) × T(4)) × T(7))) + T(T(6))
49477 := -((T(T(4)) + ((-94) - T(7)) × T(T(7))))
49479 := (((-4) + T(T(9))) × (T(T(4)) - (7))) - 9
49482 := (((-4) + T(T(9))) × 48) - T(T(2))
49484 := (((-4) + T(T(9))) × 48) - (4)
49485 := ((T(4) × T((T(9) + 4) + 8)) - (T(5)))
49488 := ((-4) + T(T(9))) × ((4 + 8) + T(8))
49492 := (4 - ((T(T(9)) - (4)) × (-T(9) + T(2))))
49495 := (T(4) × T((9 × T(4) + 9))) - (5)
49499 := -((T(4) - 9) - (T(4) × T(99)))
49515 := (((T(T(4)) × (T(9) + T(5))) + 1) × T(5))
49524 := (((T(T(4)) × (T(9) × 5)) + T(T(2))) × 4)
49527 := ((4 - 9) + ((T(T(5)) + 2) × T(T(7))))
49528 := (T(T(T(4))) - (((T(9) - T(52)) × T(8))))
49530 := ((T(T(T(4))) + (-9) + T(T(5))) × 30)
49533 := (((T(4) + T(T(9))) / 5) × (T(3) + T(T(T(3))))))
49535 := -(((T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) - (((T(5)³) × T(5))))
49539 := (((-T(4)) × T(T(9))) × (-5)) - T((T(T(3)) + T(9)))
49542 := -((T((T(T(4)) - 9)) - ((T(5)⁴) - 2)))
49544 := -((T((T(T(4)) - 9)) - ((5 + T(4))⁴)))
49545 := (((T(T(T(4))) × (9 + T(T(5)))) / 4) - (T(T(5))))
49549 := ((4 - T(T(9))) + (((T(5)⁴) - T(9)))
49555 := (T(T(4)) - ((-T(9)) - T(T(5))) × T((T(T(5)) / 5)))
49575 := ((T((4 × 9)) - (5)) × 75)
49576 := ((T(T(4)) × (-T(9)) + T((T(5) + T(7)))) + (T(6)))
49579 := (((T(T(T(4))) + T(T((-9) + T(5)))) × T(7)) - 9)
49580 := -(((T(T(4)) - T(T(9))) - (T(5) × T(80))))
49581 := (T((-4) + T(9))) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(8 - 1)))
49582 := (T((T((4 + 9)) - T(5))) + (T(8)^{T(2)}))
49585 := (((T(T(4)) + T(9)) × T((-5) + T(8))) - (T(5)))
49586 := (-4) - (-((T(9) - T(5)) × T((T(8) + T(6))))
49588 := ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T((-9) + T(5)))) × (-8) + T(8))
49599 := (((T(T(4)) - 9) × T(T(5))) - 9) × 9
49608 := ((4 × 9) × T((60 - 8)))
49618 := (T(4) - (T(-((9 - 61))) × (-T(8))))
49620 := (((T(T(4)) × T(9)) + (6)) × 20)
49624 := ((4 - T(9)) + (T((T(6) × 2)) × T(T(4))))
49625 := -((T(T(4)) + (T(T(9)) × (-6) × (T(2) + (5))))))
49626 := ((T(T(4)) × (9 × 6)) + (T(T(2))⁶))
49627 := ((-4) × T(T(9))) + ((T(T(6))²) + T(T(7)))
49628 := (-4) + (((T(T(9)) × 6) - T(T(2))) × 8)
49632 := ((T(T(4)) + (T(9) - (6))) × T(32))
49635 := ((T((4 × 9)) + (T(6)³)) × 5)
49637 := ((T(T(4)) × T((T(9) - (6 - 3)))) - T(7))
49638 := (((-((T(4) + 9)) + T(T(6))) × T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(8))))
49644 := ((T((T(4) × 9)) + (T(6)⁴)) / 4)
49647 := ((T(T(4)) + (-9) + T(6)) × T((T(4) + T(7))))
49648 := ((-4) + (T(T(9)) × T(T((6 - 4)))) × 8)
49662 := (((T(4) + T(9)) × T((T(6) + T(6)))) - T(2))
49664 := ((-4) + T((T(9) - (6))) × 64)
49665 := (T(T(4)) × T(((9) + T(6)) + ((6 × 5))))
49672 := ((T(T(-((4 - 9)))) × T(T(6))) + ((T(7)^{T(2)})))
49673 := (-T(T(4))) - ((9 - T(T(6))) × (-7) + T(T(T(3))))
49675 := ((T(4) + (T(9) × T(6))) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(5))))
49676 := (-4) - (T(T(9)) × (-((6 × 7) + 6)))
49678 := (((4 + T(9 + 6)) × T(T(7))) - T(T(8)))
49682 := (-4) - ((T(T(9)) × (-6 × 8)) - T(T(2)))
49683 := ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(9)) + (T(6) × T(T(8)))) × 3)
49684 := ((T(4) + 9) + (T((6 + T(8))) × T(T(4))))
49685 := (T(4) - ((T(T(9)) × (-6 × 8)) + (5)))
49686 := ((T((4 + 9))⁻⁶⁺⁸) × 6)
49692 := (-4) × ((T(T(9)) × (-T(6) - 9)) - T(2))
49695 := (((4 × T(T(9))) × (T(6) - 9)) + (T(5)))
49715 := (((T(4) × T(T(9))) - T(T(7))) - 1) × 5)
49720 := ((T((T(T(4)) + 9)) + (T(T(7)))) × 20)
49722 := ((T(T(4)) × T(T(9))) + (-((7^{T(2)}) × T(T(T(2))))))
49723 := ((T(4) + 9) × (T(T(7)) + T(T((T(T(T(2))) / T(T(3))))))
49725 := ((T(4) + (T(9) × 7)) × T((2 + T(5))))
49726 := ((T(T(4)) - 9) × T(((T(7) - T(2)) + T(6))))
49728 := (((T((4 × 9)) × T(7)) / T(2)) × 8)
49735 := (((T(T(4)) - T(T(9))) × T(T(7))) / (-3 + 5))
49736 := ((T(T(T(4))) × (9 - 7)) + (T(3)⁶))
49741 := ((T(4) × T(97)) + T(T((T(4) + 1)))
49742 := (T((-4) × (9 - T(7))) × (-4) + T(T(T(2))))
49745 := ((-T(4) + T(T(9))) - (-T((7 × 4)) × T(T(5))))
49746 := (4 - (-((T(9) - T(7)) × T((T(T(4)) + (T(6))))))
49748 := (-4) + ((T((T(9) + (7))) + (4)) × T(8))
49751 := ((-4) + T(T(9))) - ((T(T(7)) × T(T(5))) × (-1))
49752 := ((4 + T((T(9) + (7)))) × T((5 + T(2))))
49753 := ((4 + T(T(9))) + ((T(T(7)) × T(T(5))) - (T(3))))
49755 := ((-4) + T((9⁷⁻⁵))) × T(5)
49759 := (4 + (((9 + T(T(7))) × T(T(5))) - T(9))
49762 := ((T(T(4)) + (-9) × T(T(7))) + (T(T(6))²))
49764 := ((4 + 9) × T((T((7 + 6)) - (4))))
49765 := ((T(4) + T(T(9))) + (T((7 + T(6))) × T(T(5))))
49774 := (4 - (T(9) × ((T(7) + T(T(7))) - T(T(T(4))))))

$$\begin{aligned} 49775 &:= (T(T(4)) \times ((T(T(9)) - T(T(7))) + T((T(7) - (5)))))) \\ 49777 &:= ((T(T(4)) - ((-9) \times T(7)) \times T(7)) \times 7) \\ 49779 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) + (T((T(9) + T(7))) \times (-T(7) - 9)))) \\ 49792 &:= -((T((-4) + T(9))) - (((T(7) + 9)^{T(2)}))) \\ 49795 &:= ((4 - 9) + ((T(T(7)) + 9) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 49796 &:= (-4) - ((9 + T(T(7))) \times (-T((9 + 6)))) \\ 49798 &:= (T((T(4) + 9)) + (T((7 + T(9))) \times T(8))) \\ 49805 &:= (-T(4)) + (T((T(9) + T(8))) \times T(05)) \\ 49812 &:= ((T(-((4 - 9))) \times T(81)) - T(2)) \\ 49815 &:= (((T(4) - 9) \times T(81)) \times T(5)) \\ 49824 &:= (((4 \times T(T(9))) + (T(8) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \times 4) \\ 49825 &:= (T(4) - (T((T(9) + T(8))) \times (T(2) \times (-5)))) \\ 49855 &:= (T(T(4)) - ((T((T(9) + T(8))) \times (-T(5))) + (T(5)))) \\ 49857 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times ((T(T(9)) - 8) - T(T(5)))) - T(7)) \\ 49859 &:= (-T((4 + 9))) + (T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(9))) \\ 49866 &:= (((4 + T(T(9))) \times (8 \times 6)) - 6) \\ 49868 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(9)) + T(8)) \times (-6 \times 8)))) \\ 49872 &:= ((4 + T(T(9))) \times (-8) + (T(7) \times 2)) \\ 49875 &:= (-((T(4) - 9)) + T(T(8))) \times 75) \\ 49885 &:= (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(9)) - (8 - (-8 \times T(5)))) \\ 49886 &:= (-T(4)) - (((T(T(9)) \times 8) + T(8)) \times (-6)) \\ 49892 &:= (-4) - (9 \times (T(T(8)) - (T(T(9)) \times T(T(2)))))) \\ 49893 &:= (((T((T(T(4)) + 9)) \times (-8)) + 9) \times (-3)) \\ 49895 &:= (-((T(4) + T(9))) + (T(T(8)) \times (-T(9) + T(T(5)))) \\ 49896 &:= (((T(4) \times 9) + T(T(8))) \times (T(9) + T(6))) \\ 49932 &:= ((T(4) + 9) \times T((9 \times (T(3) + 2)))) \\ 49935 &:= (((T(T(4)) + 9) \times T((T(9) - T(3)))) + (T(5))) \\ 49938 &:= (T((-4) + T(9))) \times ((T(9) + T(T(3))) - 8) \\ 49945 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) + T((4 \times T(5)))) \\ 49946 &:= ((T(T(4)) + T((9 + 9))) \times (-T(4) + T(T(6)))) \\ 49962 &:= ((T(4) \times T(99)) - (T(T(6)) \times (-2))) \\ 49965 &:= ((T(4) \times T(99)) + T((6 \times 5))) \\ 49968 &:= (((4 \times 9) + (T(T(9)) \times 6)) \times 8) \\ 49972 &:= ((4 + T(T((T(9)/9))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(2))) \\ 49974 &:= ((49 \times T(T(9))) - T((T(7) + T(4)))) \\ 49975 &:= (T(T(4)) + ((T((9 \times 9)) + (7)) \times T(5))) \\ 49982 &:= (((T(4)^{T(9)/9}) - T(8))/2) \\ 49992 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(9))) \times 99) - T(2)) \\ 49995 &:= ((4 \times T(9)) + (T((9 \times 9)) \times T(5))) \\ 50232 &:= (T(T((T(5) - 02))) \times (T(3) \times 2)) \\ 50238 &:= (-T(50)) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 8)) \\ 50439 &:= (((T(5)^{04}) - T(T(T(3)))) + T(9)) \\ 50475 &:= (T(50) + ((4 + T(T(7))) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 50547 &:= (-50) + ((T(5)^4) - T(7)) \\ 50597 &:= ((T(5)^{-05+9}) - T(7)) \\ 50622 &:= ((T(5)^{06-2}) - T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 50625 &:= (T(5)^{-06+2 \times 5}) \\ 50646 &:= ((T(5)^{0 \times 6+4}) + T(6)) \\ 50654 &:= ((50 - T(6)) + (T(5)^4)) \\ 50695 &:= ((-50) \times (T(6) - T(T(9)))) - (5) \\ 50736 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(07))) + T((3 \times T(6)))) \\ 50745 &:= ((T(5)^{0 \times 7+4}) + T(T(5))) \\ 50755 &:= (5 - ((0 - T(T(7))) \times (T(T(5)) + (5)))) \\ 50853 &:= ((T(5) + 08) \times T(T((5 + T(3)))) \\ 51036 &:= (-T(5)) + ((-10) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(6))) \\ 51045 &:= (T((T((T(T(5))/10)) + 4)) \times T(5)) \\ 51066 &:= (T(5) - ((10 - T(T(6))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 51120 &:= (T((5 + T(11))) \times 20) \\ 51156 &:= ((T((5 + T(11))) - T(T(5))) \times T(6)) \\ 51162 &:= (-T(T(5))) + ((T(T(11)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 51194 &:= ((51 \times (-1) + T(T(9))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 51216 &:= ((T(T(5)) + T(T(12))) \times 16) \\ 51222 &:= (T(51) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(2))^{T(2)})) \\ 51225 &:= (-T(5)) - ((T(T((1 + T(T(2)))) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(5)))) \\ 51228 &:= (((-T(T(5))) + T(T(T((1 + T(2)))))) + T(2)) \times T(8) \\ 51235 &:= (-5) - ((T(T((1 + T(T(2)))) + (T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(5)))) \\ 51243 &:= (T((51 + T(T(2))) \times (T(4) + T(T(3)))) \\ 51245 &:= (5 + (T((1 + T(T(2)))) \times T((4 \times T(5)))) \\ 51272 &:= (((T(51) \times 2) \times T(T(7)))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 51276 &:= (T(T(5)) + ((-T((1 + 2))) \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(6))) \\ 51281 &:= (((T(T((5 + 1)))/T(2)) \times T(T(8))) - 1) \\ 51282 &:= (((T(T((5 + 1))) \times 2) \times T(T(8)))/T(T(2))) \\ 51291 &:= ((T(5)^{1+T(2)}) + T(T((9 - 1)))) \\ 51292 &:= (T((5 - 1)) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 9) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 51295 &:= ((-T((T(5) + 1))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9))) \times 5) \\ 51296 &:= ((T(5) - 1) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-9) + T(T(6)))) \\ 51330 &:= (T((T(T((5 - 1))) + 3)) \times 30) \\ 51336 &:= (T((T(T(5)) - T((1 + T(3)))) \times (T(3) + (6))) \\ 51357 &:= (51 \times (T((3 \times T(5))) - T(7))) \\ 51360 &:= (T(T(5)) + (T((1 + T(3))) \times T(60))) \\ 51375 &:= (T(5) + (((1 + T(T(3))) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 51379 &:= (((T(T(5)) + (1 + 3)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(9))) \\ 51384 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(T((1 + T(3)))) + (T(T(8)) \times 4)) \\ 51393 &:= (-T(T(5))) - (((-1) - T(T(T(3)))) + 9) \times T(T(T(3))) \\ 51399 &:= ((T((T(5) + 1)) \times T((3 \times 9))) - 9) \\ 51425 &:= ((T(T(5)) + 1) \times 425) \\ 51429 &:= (((T(5)^{1 \times 4}) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9))) \\ 51436 &:= (((T(51) + T(4)) \times T(T(T(3))))/6) \\ 51445 &:= ((T(5)^{1 \times 4}) + T((T(T(4)) - (T(5)))) \\ 51465 &:= ((T(T(T((5 - 1)))) + T((T(T(4)) + (6)))) \times T(5)) \\ 51495 &:= ((-51) - (-T(4) \times T(T(9)))) \times 5) \\ 51525 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((T(T((1 + 5))) - 2) \times (-T(5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 51528 &:= ((T(5)^{-1+5}) + T((T(T(2)) + T(8)))) \\ 51558 &:= (T((T(T(5))/T(-((1-5)))))) \times (-5) + T(T(8))) \\ 51567 &:= (5 + (((1 + T(T(5))) + (6)) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 51577 &:= (T(5) + ((T(15) + (7)) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 51585 &:= ((T(5)^{-1+5}) + (8 \times T(T(5)))) \\ 51645 &:= (T(T((5-1))) \times ((T(T(6)) \times 4) + T(5))) \\ 51646 &:= ((T(T(T((5-1)))) - (T(6))) \times (T(T(4)) - (T(6)))) \\ 51665 &:= (5 + (T((-1) + T(6))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(5))) \\ 51667 &:= ((T(T(5)) + 1) \times (T(6) + T((T(6) + (7)))))) \\ 51673 &:= (((T(T(5)) + 1) \times (T(6) + T(T(7)))) + T(3)) \\ 51693 &:= ((T(51) \times (-6) + T(9)) - T(T(3))) \\ 51714 &:= (T(51) \times ((T(7) + 1) + T(4))) \\ 51723 &:= (((T(T((5+1))) - (7)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) - (T(T(3)))) \\ 51728 &:= (((T(T((5+1))) \times (-T(7))) + 2) \times (-8)) \\ 51734 &:= (((T(T((5+1))) - (7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(4)) \\ 51735 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T((1 + T(7)))) - T((T(3) \times 5))) \\ 51737 &:= (((T(T((5+1))) - (7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 7) \\ 51738 &:= (-((5+1) + ((-T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-8)) \\ 51744 &:= (T(T((5+1))) \times (T(7) \times (4+4))) \\ 51750 &:= (T(T((T(5) + ((1-7)))) \times 50) \\ 51755 &:= (T(T((5-1))) \times (T((T(7) + T(5))) - (5))) \\ 51765 &:= (T((T(5) - 1)) \times (T(7) + T((6 \times 5)))) \\ 51773 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times T((1 + T(7)))) - T(T(7))) - T(T(3))) \\ 51786 &:= (((T(T(5)) - 1) \times T((-7) + T(8))) + T(6)) \\ 51789 &:= ((T(T((5+1))) \times (T(7) \times 8)) + T(9)) \\ 51812 &:= -((T(T(5) + 1) - (T(T(8)) \times T(12)))) \\ 51828 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (-1)) + (T((T(8)/T(2))) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 51829 &:= -(((T(T(5)) - 1) - (T(T(8)) \times T((T(2) + 9)))) \\ 51872 &:= ((T(5) + 1) \times ((8 \times T(T(7))) - T(T(2)))) \\ 51875 &:= (5 + ((-1) + T(T(8))) \times T((7+5))) \\ 51893 &:= -((T(T((5-1))) - (T(T(8)) \times T((9+3)))) \\ 51897 &:= (T((5+1) - (-T(8)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 51924 &:= (-51) + ((-T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4))) \\ 51925 &:= ((-T((5-1))) + (T(9) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times 5) \\ 51928 &:= ((5 + (T((1 + T(9))) \times T(T(2)))) \times 8) \\ 51933 &:= (-T(5) - (T(T(-((1-9)))) \times (-T((T(3) + T(3))))) \\ 51936 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (-1) + T(9)) + T(3)^6) \\ 51938 &:= (-T((5-1))) + (T((9+3)) \times T(T(8))) \\ 51943 &:= (-5) - (T(T(-((1-9)))) \times (-T((4 \times 3)))) \\ 51947 &:= (((T(T(5+1)) \times T(9)) \times T(T(4))) - T(7)) \\ 51948 &:= (T(((5-1) \times 9)) \times T((4+8))) \\ 51950 &:= ((-((5-1)) - T(T(9))) \times (-50)) \\ 51953 &:= (5 - (T(T(-((1-9)))) \times (-T((T(5) - 3)))) \\ 51959 &:= (-((T(5) + 1) + ((T(T(9)) + T(T(5))) \times T(9))) \\ 51963 &:= (T(5) - (T(T(-((1-9)))) \times (-T((6 + T(3))))) \\ 51965 &:= (-T((5-1))) + ((T(9) \times T(T(6))) \times 5) \\ 51969 &:= (((T(5) + 1) - T(T(9))) \times (-6) - T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 51975 &:= (T(((5+1) \times 9)) \times (7 \times 5)) \\ 51984 &:= ((T(5) + 1) \times (9 + T((8 \times T(4)))) \\ 51996 &:= ((T((T(5) + T((1+9)))) - 9) \times T(6)) \\ 52065 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T(2)) + (T(T(06)) \times T(5)))) \\ 52068 &:= (T(T(5)) - (-T((2 \times 06))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 52095 &:= (((5 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(09)) + T(T(5)))) \\ 52122 &:= ((T((T(5) + T(T((T(2) + 1)))) - T(2)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 52125 &:= (((T(5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T((1 + T(2)))) \times T(5)) \\ 52156 &:= ((5 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(-((1-5)) - T(T(6)))) \\ 52170 &:= -((T(5) + (-21) \times T(70))) \\ 52175 &:= (-((5^2)) + (T((1 + T(7))) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 52182 &:= (T((T(5) - T(2))) \times (T(T((1 \times 8))) + T(2))) \\ 52185 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T((21 + 8))) - (T(5))) \\ 52195 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(T(T(2))) - ((1-9)))) - 5) \\ 52203 &:= (((-5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 03) \\ 52206 &:= ((-5) + T(T((2 \times T(2)))) \times T(T(06))) \\ 52212 &:= (((-5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T((1 + 2))) \\ 52213 &:= (((-5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (1 + T(3))) \\ 52215 &:= (((T(5)^2) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1)) + T(5)) \\ 52221 &:= (((-5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T((T(T(2)) - 1))) \\ 52224 &:= (((T(5) + 2) \times T(2)) \times (2^{T(4)})) \\ 52227 &:= (((-5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(2) \times 7)) \\ 52228 &:= (-5) - ((2 - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8)))) \\ 52233 &:= (-T(((T(5) \times T(2)) + 2)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 52234 &:= (-T((T(5) - 2)) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T(34))) \\ 52236 &:= (-(((T(5)^{T(2)})/T(2)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6)))) \\ 52237 &:= (((-5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (3 + T(7))) \\ 52238 &:= (5 - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (2 - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(8)))) \\ 52242 &:= (((-5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T((4 \times 2))) \\ 52245 &:= ((T((T(T(5))/2) + T((2 + T(T(4)))) \times T(5)) \\ 52248 &:= (T((5+2) \times (T((T(T(2)) \times T(4))) + T(8))) \\ 52262 &:= (-T(T((5+2))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(2)))) \\ 52267 &:= (5 - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(2) - T(T(6))) + (T(T(7)))) \\ 52272 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times T(T(2))) + T(T(2))) \times 72) \\ 52275 &:= (-((T(5) + 2) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T((7+5)))) \\ 52277 &:= ((T(5) \times (T(T((2 \times T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7)))) - (T(7))) \\ 52279 &:= (((-5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(7) + T(9)))) \\ 52283 &:= (T((T((T(5) - 2)) + T(T(2))) \times (8 + 3)) \\ 52284 &:= (((-5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T((8 + 4))) \\ 52288 &:= (((5^2) - (T(2)^8)) \times (-8)) \\ 52290 &:= (T(5) \times T(((T(T(T(2)))/(-T(2)) + 90))) \\ 52296 &:= (((5 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + 2) \times T(9)) + T(T(6))) \\ 52299 &:= ((T(5) - (-T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(9))) \times 9) \\ 52321 &:= (-T(T(5)) + ((-2) + T(T(T(3))))^2 \times 1) \\ 52323 &:= (-T((T(5) \times T(2))) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) - 3)) \\ 52326 &:= ((T(5) + 2) \times (-3) + T(T((2 \times 6)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 52329** := $((T(T(T((5-2)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (-T(2) + T(T(9))))$
52332 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T((T(T(3))/3)) \times T(T(T(2))))$
52335 := $((T(5)^2 \times T(T(T(3)))) - (-3 \times T(T(5))))$
52338 := $((T(T(5)) + 2) \times (-T(3) + T((T(T(3)) + 8))))$
52339 := $((T(5) - 2) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(9))))$
52341 := $(T(5) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T((T(4) - 1))))))$
52342 := $(((-5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T((4^2)))$
52344 := $((5 - T(T(T(2)))) + (34 \times T(T(T(4))))$
52345 := $((T(T(5 \times 2))) \times 34) - (T(5))$
52346 := $(-T((T(5) - 2)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (4 - T(T(6))))$
52347 := $(T(T(5)) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(7))))))$
52353 := $((T(T(5) - 2) \times T(T(3))) + (T(5))) \times T(T(3))$
52356 := $((T(5) + 2) \times T(T((-3) + T(5)))) - (T(6))$
52359 := $(-T(5) - (T(T(T(T(2))/3))) \times (-T(T(5) + 9)))$
52364 := $(T(52) \times (T(T(3)) + (T(6) - 4)))$
52365 := $((5 + T(((T(T(T(T(2))))/3) + 6))) \times T(5))$
52368 := $(-((T(T(5)) - ((2 \times 3^6) \times T(8))))$
52372 := $((T(T(5)) + (T(2) \times 3)) \times T(T(7))) - 2$
52374 := $((T(T(5)) + (T(2) \times 3)) \times T((7 \times 4)))$
52375 := $((T(T(5 \times 2))) \times (T(3) + T(7))) + (T(5))$
52377 := $((T(5) + 2) \times T(T((-3) \times T(7)/(-7))))$
52380 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(2)) + T((3 + 80))))$
52381 := $((T(5)^2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T((8 - 1)))$
52383 := $((T(5) + (2^{T(3)})) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(T(3)))$
52391 := $((5 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 9)) - 1$
52392 := $((T(T(5) - 2) \times ((T(T(T(3))) - 9) \times 2))$
52397 := $((5 \times ((2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(9))) - (T(7)))$
52398 := $(-((T(T(5)) + T(2)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (9 - T(T(8))))$
52416 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(2))) \times 416)$
52421 := $(-T(5) + (((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1))$
52422 := $(-T(5) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-4 + T(T((2 \times T(2))))))$
52425 := $(-(((T(5)^2) \times (T(4) - (T(2)^5))))$
52426 := $(-5) + (((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 6))$
52428 := $((5 - T(2)) + T(T(T(4))) \times (-2) + T(8))$
52431 := $(-5) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (4 - T(T(T(3)))) + 1)$
52432 := $((-5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times ((4 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(2)))$
52436 := $((5 - T(T(2))) + ((-4) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(6)))$
52437 := $(T(T(T((5 - 2)))) \times (-4) + T((3 \times 7)))$
52440 := $(T(T(5)) \times (-T(2) - 440))$
52442 := $(5 + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-4) + T(T((4 + 2))))$
52443 := $(T(5) - ((2 + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(4)) - T(T(3))))$
52445 := $((T(5) + 2) \times ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4)))) + 5))$
52448 := $((5 - (T(2)^{4+4})) \times (-8))$
52452 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times ((-4) - T(T(5))) \times (-T(2)))$
52454 := $((5 + (T(2)^{T(4)})) - (T(T(5)) \times T(T(4))))$
52458 := $(T(T(5)) - (T((2 + T(4))) \times (-5) - T(T(8))))$
52462 := $((5^2) + ((-4) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$
52463 := $((5 + T(T(T(2)))) + ((-4) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
52467 := $(5 - ((T(2) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-6) - T(7)))$
52468 := $(-5) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-4) + T(T(6))) + T(8))$
52476 := $((T(5) \times (-T(2)) + T((T(T(4)) + T(7)))) + T(T(6)))$
52478 := $((T(5) \times T((T(T(T(2))) \times 4)) - (T(T(7)) + T(T(8))))$
52480 := $((T(T((5 + T(2)))) - T(4)) \times 80)$
52482 := $((T(5) - T(T(2)))^4 \times 8) - T(T(2))$
52484 := $((T(5) - T(T(2)))^4 \times 8) - (4)$
52485 := $((-T(5) \times T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(4)) \times (-8)) \times T(T(5))))$
52486 := $((5^{T(T(2))}) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(6))))$
52495 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(2))) \times (T(T(4)) + 9)) + T(5))$
52497 := $(T((T(5) + T(2))) \times (T(T(4)) - (-9) \times T(7)))$
52500 := $((5 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times 500)$
52524 := $((T(5) + T(2)) \times (T(52) + T(T(T(4))))$
52526 := $(-((T((T(T(5))/T(2))) + T(5))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6))))$
52528 := $((5 + T(2)) \times (5 + (T(2)^8)))$
52536 := $(T(T(5)) - ((T(T(T(2))) + 5) \times (-T((3 \times T(6))))))$
52542 := $((T(5) + 2) + T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
52554 := $((T(T(5)) - T(T(2))) \times (T((T(5) + T(5))) - 4))$
52563 := $((-((T(5) + 2)) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T(6)))) \times T(T(3)))$
52566 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(2)) + ((-5) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(6)))$
52575 := $(T(5) - ((-2^5) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(5)))$
52578 := $((T(T(5)) + (2 + 5)) \times (T(T(7)) + 8))$
52584 := $((T(5) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(5)) \times 8) \times T(T(4))))$
52593 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-5) + T((9 \times 3)))$
52612 := $(((-5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6))) + T(T((1 + T(T(2))))))$
52623 := $(-((T(5) \times T(2))) + ((T(T(6)) - T(2)) \times T(T(T(3))))$
52624 := $((T(T(5)) + (2^6)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4))))$
52625 := $((5^{T(2)}) \times (T(T((T(6)/T(2)))) + T(5))$
52626 := $((T((T(T(5) - 2)) - (T(6)))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(6)$
52628 := $((5 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T((6/2)))) - 8))$
52629 := $(T(5) + ((T(T(2)) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 9))$
52632 := $((T(T(T(5 - 2)))) \times T(T(6)) - ((3^{T(T(2))}))$
52634 := $(((-T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(6)) - T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4))))$
52635 := $((T(5)^2) \times (T(T(6)) + 3) - (T(5)))$
52638 := $((T(5)^2) \times T(T(6)) - 3) + T(T(8))$
52641 := $(-((T(T(5)) \times T(T(2)))) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(T((4 - 1))))))$
52644 := $((T(5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times ((T(6) \times T(4)) + 4))$
52645 := $((T(5) \times T(26)) \times T(4) - 5)$
52646 := $(-T(T(5)) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(6)))) + T((T(T(4)) - (T(6))))))$
52662 := $((-((5 - 2)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(2)))$
52663 := $(-((T(5)/T(2))) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(6)) - 3)))$
52664 := $((-((5 - 2)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(6)) - 4)$
52665 := $((T(T(5)) \times (-2) + (T(6) \times T(6))) - (T(5)))$
52667 := $(((-T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(6)) - (T((-6) + T(7))))$

- 52668 := (((T(T(5)) - T(T(2))) × T(T(6))) × (-6 - 8))
52673 := (5 - ((T(2) - T(T(6))) × T((7 × 3)))
52675 := (T((T(5 + 2)) + T(6))) × (T(7) + T(5))
52695 := (((T(T(5)) - 2) × T(6)) + T(T(9))) × T(5)
52723 := (-5) + (((-2) + T(7))^{T(2)} × 3)
52724 := (T((5 + 2)) × ((7^{T(2)}) + T(T(T(4))))
52725 := ((-T((5 × 2))) + T((T(7) × T(2)))) × T(5)
52728 := (T((T(5) - T(2))) × ((7 + T(2)) + T(T(8))))
52732 := (-((T((T(5) × T(2))) - T(T(7)))) + (T(T(T(3))))²)
52733 := (5 - (((-2) + T(7))³) × (-3))
52736 := (-((5^{-T(2)+7}) - (T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(6))))))
52739 := -(T(T((T(5) - 2))) + (-T((7 + 3))) × T(T(9))))
52742 := ((-5) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (7 × T(T(T(4)))))) - T(2)
52745 := ((T(T(T((5 - 2)))) - (7 × T(T(T(4)))) × (-5)
52746 := ((T(5) × (T((T(2) × T(7))) - T(T(4)))) + (T(6)))
52749 := (-T((T(5) + T(2)))) + (T((-7) + T(T(4))) × T(9))
52752 := (((T(T(5)) × T(T(T(2)))) - (-7) + T(5)) × T(T(T(2))))
52754 := ((-5) - T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(T(7)) × (T(T(5)) + T(4))))
52755 := (((5 + T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(7))) - 5) × 5
52763 := ((T(T((T(5) - 2)))/(-7) + (T(T(6)) × T(T(T(3))))))
52765 := (-T(5)) - ((2 × T(T(7))) × (-65))
52766 := -(T((T((5 - 2)) + T(7))) - (T(T(6)) × T(T(6))))
52767 := ((T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(7)) + T((T(T(6))/7)))
52773 := ((T(((5 × 2) × 7)) + T(7)) × T(T(3)))
52775 := (((-5) × (2 - T(7))) × T(T(7))) - (5)
52779 := ((T((5 + T(T(2)))) × (T(7) × T(7))) + T(T(9)))
52782 := ((T(T(5)) - T(T(2))) × ((T(T(7)) + T(8)) + T(T(T(2))))
52785 := (T((52 - 7)) × (T(8) + T(5)))
52794 := ((T(T(5)) + T(T(2))) × (T(T(7)) + (9 + 4)))
52795 := (-5) - ((T((T(T(2)) + T(7))) - T(T(9))) × T(T(5)))
52800 := (T((5 + T(T(2)))) × 800)
52815 := (T(5) × (T(T(2)) - (T((T(8) + 1)) × (-5))))
52822 := (((T(T(5))/T(T(2))) + T(T(8))) × T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(2))
52824 := (5 + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + 8) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4)))
52826 := ((T(T(5)) + 2) × ((T(T(8)) - 2) - T(T(6))))
52829 := (-T((T(5) - 2))) + (T((8 × T(T(2)))) × T(9))
52833 := (-528) + (T(T(T(3))) × T(T(T(3))))
52834 := (T(5) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) + 8) × (T(T(T(3))) - T(4)))
52836 := ((-5) × T((T(T(2)) + 8))) - (T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(6))))
52837 := ((T(T(5)) × T((T(T(T(2)) + 8))) + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(7))))
52838 := ((T((T(T(5))/2)) - 8) × (T(T(3)) + 8))
52839 := (T((T(5) + T(2))) × (T((8 × 3)) + 9))
52845 := ((T(T(5)) + T(-((2 - 84)))) × T(5))
52848 := ((T(52) × T(8)) + T((T(4) × 8)))
52858 := ((-T(T(5))) + T(T((T(T(2)) - 8)))) × (5 + 8)
52866 := ((T(5) × (T(2) - T(8))) + (T(T(6)) × T(T(6))))
52874 := (((5 + T(T(T(T(2)))) × (8 × T(7))) + T(4))
52875 := ((T(T(5)) + T(T(T(2)))) × ((-T(8)) + T(T(7))) + (5))
52880 := (((T(5)/T(2)) - T(T(8))) × (-80))
52884 := ((-((T(5) - T(2))) - T(T(8))) × (-T((8 + 4))))
52893 := ((T((T(5) - T(2))) × T(T(8))) + (T(9) × T(T(3))))
52894 := (T(T((5 + 2))) + ((8 × (9⁴)))
52895 := (5 × ((T((T(T(2)) × 8)) × 9) - 5)
52897 := (5 - ((T((T(T(2)) × 8)) × (-T(9))) + (T(7))))
52932 := (T((5 + T(T(2)))) × ((T(T(9)) - T(T(T(3)))) - 2))
52935 := ((T(T(5)) × (T(29) + T(3))) + (T(5)))
52938 := ((T(5) + T(2)) + (T(9) × T((T(3) × 8))))
52943 := (-5) - (-T(-((2 - 9))) × T((T(T(4)) + T(3))))
52947 := ((-T(T(5))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × ((-T(T(9)) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(7))))
52948 := (T((5 + 2)) + (T(9) × T(48)))
52962 := (((-5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9))) × (T(6) × 2))
52963 := (((T(T(5)) × T((T(T(2)) + T(9)))) - T(T(6)))/3)
52965 := (((T((T(5) - T(2))) × T(9)) + (T(6))) × T(5))
52983 := (((-5) × T(T(T(2)))) + T((9 × 8))) × T(T(3))
52986 := (T((5 + T(T(2)))) + ((T(9) × T((8 × 6))))
52988 := (52 × (T(T(9)) - (8 + 8)))
52992 := ((-5) + T(T(T(2)))) × (-9) + T((9²)))
52994 := (5 + ((T(T(2)) + T(9)) × (T(T(9)) + (4))))
52995 := (-5) × ((T((T(2) + T(9))) × (-9)) - (T(5)))
53025 := (T(5) - (T(30) × (T(T(2)) - T(T(5))))
53036 := (-T(-((5 - 30))) - (T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(6))))
53064 := (T(T((5 + T(3)))) × (06 × 4))
53115 := (-T(5)) - (T(T(T(3))) × (1 - T((1 + 5))))
53122 := (-5) - (((T(T(T(3))) - 1) × T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2))
53123 := (-5) - ((T(T(T(3))) + 1) × (2 - T(T(T(3))))
53124 := ((T(T(5)) - T(3)) × (1 + T((T(2) × T(4))))
53125 := ((5^{T(3)-1}) × (2 + T(5)))
53126 := (-5) + (((T(T(T(3))) - 1)²) + T(T(6)))
53145 := (T(5) - (T((T(T(3)) + 1)) × (-T((4 × 5))))
53166 := (T((5 + 3)) - ((1 - T(T(6))) × T(T(6))))
53196 := ((-T(T(5))) + T(T((T(3) + 1))) × (-T(9)) + T(T(6)))
53213 := (-T(T(5))) + ((T(T(T(3)))²) - T((1 + T(3))))
53231 := (-T(T(5))) + ((T(T(T(3)))²) - T((3 + 1)))
53232 := (-T(T(5))) + ((T(T(T(3)))²) - (3²))
53233 := ((-((5³) - T(2)) + (T(T(T(3))) × T(T(T(3))))
53234 := (-T(T(5))) + ((T(T(T(3)))²) - (3 + 4))
53235 := (T((T(5) × T(3))) × ((2³) + 5))
53236 := ((-((5³)) + (T(T((2 × 3))) × T(T(6))))
53237 := (-T(T(5))) + ((T(T(T(3)))²) + ((3 - 7)))
53238 := (-T(T(5))) + ((T(T(T(3)))²) - T(-((T(3) - 8))))
53240 := (((5 + T(3))^{T(2)}) × 40)
53241 := ((T((T(5) + T(3)))²) - T(T((4 + 1))))
53242 := (-T(T(5))) + ((T(T(T(3)))²) + (4 - T(2)))

- 53243** := $(-T(T(5)) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) + (-4) + T(3)))$
53244 := $(T((5+3)) \times (-((T(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
53245 := $((T((T(5) + T(3)))^2) + (4) - T(T(5)))$
53246 := $(T(T(5)) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) - (4 + T(T(6))))$
53247 := $(T((T(5) \times T(3))) + (T(2) \times (4^7)))$
53251 := $(-T(T(5)) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) + T(5 - 1)))$
53252 := $(5 + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(2))))$
53253 := $(-T(T(5)) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) + (T(5) - 3)))$
53256 := $((T((T(5) + T(3)))^2) + (-5) \times T(6))$
53261 := $(-T(T(5)) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) + (T(6) - 1)))$
53262 := $(((-5) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(2))) + (T(T(6))^2)$
53265 := $(T(5) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) - ((T(T(6)) - T(T(5))))$
53266 := $((-5) \times (T(T(3)) - 2)) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(6)))$
53267 := $(-T((5 + T(3))) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(6)))) + (T(7)))$
53268 := $(-T(T(5)) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(2)) - T(T(6)))) + (T(T(8))))$
53271 := $(-((T(5) \times T(3))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(7 - 1))))$
53272 := $(-T(T(5)) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) + (T(7) + T(2))))$
53273 := $(-T(5) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) - 73))$
53275 := $(-5 - ((T(T(3)) - T(2 + T(7))) \times T(T(5))))$
53277 := $((T(T(5)) + (3^2)) \times (T(T(7)) + (7)))$
53278 := $(-5) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) - (78))$
53279 := $(-T(T(5)) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) + (-7) + T(9)))$
53291 := $(-T(5) + ((T(T(T(3)))^2) - T(9 + 1)))$
53292 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(3))) \times T((T(2) \times 9)) - T(T(2)))$
53294 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(3))) \times T((T(2) \times 9)) - (4))$
53295 := $(T(((5 + T(3)) \times T(2))) \times 95)$
53297 := $(5 \times ((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(2))) \times T(9)) - (T(7)))$
53298 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(3))) \times T((T(2) \times (T(9) - T(8))))$
53313 := $((T((T(5) \times T(3))) + T(3)) \times 13)$
53316 := $((T(5) \times (-3)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(1 \times 6))))$
53317 := $((5^3) + T(3)) \times (1 + T(T(7)))$
53318 := $(-T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(-((1 - 8))))$
53321 := $(T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T((2 + 1))))$
53322 := $(-T(5) + (((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(2)))$
53323 := $(-T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 23)$
53324 := $(T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (-T(2) + T(T(4))))$
53325 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))) + T(T((3^2))) \times T(5))$
53326 := $(((-5) \times T(T(3)))/3 + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(6))))$
53327 := $((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(2)) + T(7)))$
53328 := $((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(2) - T(8))))$
53329 := $(T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (2 + T(9))))$
53331 := $(-T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T((T(3) - 1))))$
53332 := $(-5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(3)) + T(2)))$
53333 := $((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T((T(3))/3))$
53334 := $(-T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (3 \times 4)))$
53335 := $((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(3)) + (5)))$
53336 := $(-((5^{T(3)/3}) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6))))$
53338 := $(T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 38)$
53339 := $(5 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (3 \times 9))$
53340 := $(T(5) \times (T((3 \times T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4 + 0))))$
53341 := $(-T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (4 + 1)))$
53342 := $(5 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (4 \times T(T(2))))$
53343 := $(-T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T((-4) + T(3))))$
53344 := $((T(5) \times (T((3 \times T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) + 4)$
53345 := $(5 - ((T(3 \times T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(5))))$
53346 := $(-T(5) - (-T((3 \times (3 + 4))) \times T(T(6))))$
53347 := $((T(5) \times (T(3 \times T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) + 7)$
53348 := $(5 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(4) + 8))$
53349 := $((T(5) \times (T(3 \times T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) + 9)$
53351 := $((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T((5 - 1)))$
53352 := $(T((T(5) + 3)) \times (T(3) \times 52))$
53353 := $((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (5 + 3))$
53354 := $(5 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(5))/T(4))))$
53355 := $(T(T(5)) + (T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(5))) + (T(5))))$
53356 := $(-5 - (-((T(3)^3) + T(5)) \times T(T(6))))$
53358 := $((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((5 - 8))$
53359 := $(-((5 - 3) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T((5 - 9))))$
53360 := $(5 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (6 + 0))$
53361 := $(T((T(5) + T(3)))^{-3+6-1})$
53362 := $(-5) + ((T(T((3 + 3))) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(2)))$
53363 := $(5 + ((T(T((3 + 3))) \times T(T(6))) - 3)$
53364 := $((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T((6 - 4))$
53365 := $(5 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (6 - 5))$
53366 := $(5 - (-T(((3^3) - 6)) \times T(T(6))))$
53367 := $(T(T((5 + T(3)))) - (-((T(3) \times T(6)) \times T(T(7))))$
53368 := $(T(5) + ((T(T((3 + 3))) \times T(T(6))) - 8)$
53369 := $(5 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - ((6 - 9)))$
53372 := $((5 + T(3)) + (T((3 \times 7))^2)$
53373 := $(5 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(7) - T(T(3))))$
53374 := $(-T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (7 \times 4))$
53375 := $(-((5^3)) \times ((-T(3) - T(T(7)) - (T(5))))$
53376 := $(T(5) - (-((33 \times 7) \times T(T(6))))$
53377 := $(T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (7/7))$
53379 := $(-T(53) - ((-3) \times T(T(7)) \times T(9)))$
53381 := $(-T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(8) - 1))$
53382 := $((-T(5) + T((T(3) \times T(3)))) \times 82)$
53384 := $(5 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (8 + T(4)))$
53385 := $((T(T(5)) + 3) \times T((T(3) + 8)) - (T(T(5))))$
53386 := $(-5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(8) - (6)))$
53388 := $((T((T(5)/3)) + (-3) + T(T(8))) \times T(8))$
53391 := $(-T(5) - (((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(9)) \times (-1)))$
53393 := $(5 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (9 \times 3))$

- 53396** := $(5 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (9 + T(6))))$
53397 := $(T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(9-7))))$
53398 := $((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(9) - 8))$
53399 := $(T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(9))/T(9))))$
53415 := $(-T(T(5))) - ((T((T(T(3)) \times 4) - 1) \times (-T(5))))$
53422 := $((T(T(5-3))) + T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(2))))^2$
53423 := $((T(T(5) - 3) - T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
53424 := $((T(T(5)) + T(3)) \times 424)$
53425 := $(-(5^3) - (T((4 \times T(T(2)))) \times (-T(5))))$
53426 := $((-5) \times (-3 - T(4))) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)))$
53432 := $((-5) + T(T(3))) + T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(3))))^2$
53433 := $((T(5) + 3) \times 4) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
53435 := $(-T((5 \times T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-35)))$
53436 := $((T(5) + T(3) \times T(4)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6))))$
53445 := $((T((5+3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)))) - T(5))$
53448 := $((T(T(5)) + (3^{4+4})) \times 8)$
53452 := $(-T(T(5))) + (-((T(T(T(3))) - 4) \times (-5 - T(T(T(2))))))$
53471 := $(5 - (T(T(3)) \times (T(4) - T(71))))$
53472 := $(-T(T(5))) + (T((T(T(3)) - T(4)) \times (T(T(7)) \times 2)))$
53475 := $((5 \times 3)^4 + T(75))$
53481 := $(T(T(5)) - ((T(T(T(3)))^{T(4)-8}) \times (-1)))$
53484 := $((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(8))) \times 4)$
53486 := $((5^3) + (T(T(T(T(4) - 8)))) \times T(T(6)))$
53487 := $((T(5) \times T((3 \times T(4)))) + T(T(8))) \times 7$
53488 := $((-T(53)) - T(T(4))) \times (-T(8)) - 8$
53493 := $(-T(5)) - ((3 - T(T(4))) \times (T(T(9)) - T(3)))$
53495 := $((T(5) \times T((T(T(3)) \times 4)) - T(T(9-5)))$
53496 := $((T(5) \times T(34)) - 9) \times 6$
53514 := $(((-T(5)) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(5)) - 1) + T(T(T(4)))$
53515 := $((-T(5)) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(5)) + T(T(T(-((1-5))))))$
53520 := $(T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3))) + (5 + T(20)))$
53524 := $((T(5) - (3^5)))^2 + T(T(T(4)))$
53526 := $((5 + T(3)) \times (T(5) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(6))))$
53532 := $(T((T(5) + 3)) + (T((T(5) + T(3))))^2$
53534 := $((5 - T(T(3))) - (-T(5) \times T((T(3)) \times 4)))$
53535 := $((T(5) \times T((T(3) \times T(5)) - T(3))) - T(5))$
53536 := $((5 \times 35) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6))))$
53542 := $(-(5+3) - (-T(5) \times T((4 \times T(T(2))))))$
53544 := $((T(T(5)) - (-T(3)) \times T(T((T(5) - 4)))) \times 4)$
53545 := $((T(5) \times T((T(3) + T(5)) \times 4)) - 5)$
53562 := $((-5) + T((T(3) + T(5)))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(2)))$
53565 := $((T(5) \times T((T(3) \times T(5)) - 6))) + T(5))$
53566 := $(T(T(T(5))/T(3)) + (-5) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))))$
53568 := $((5 + 3^5) \times 6) \times T(8)$
53571 := $((T(5) + T(3)) \times (-5) + T(71))$
53577 := $(-T(5)) - (-((T(3) \times (T(5) + 7))) \times T(T(7)))$
53586 := $(T((T(5) - 3)) \times ((T(5) + T(T(8))) + 6))$
53592 := $((T(T(5)) + (-3) + T(5)) \times T(T(9-2)))$
53595 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - ((5 \times T(T(9))) \times (-5)))$
53597 := $(5 - ((3 - (T(5) \times 9)) \times T(T(7))))$
53612 := $((T(T(5))/T(3)) + ((T(T(6)) + 1) \times T(T(T(2))))$
53613 := $((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times (T(T(6)) + 1)) + T(T(3)))$
53622 := $((-T(5)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6)))) + T((2 + T(T(T(2))))))$
53625 := $((5 \times T((3+62))) \times 5)$
53628 := $(T((T(5) + T(3))) + ((T(T(6)))^2 + T(8)))$
53632 := $(-5 - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6)))) - T((T(T(3)) + 2)))$
53634 := $(T(T(5)) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6)))) - T((T(T(3)) - 4))))$
53635 := $(-5 - (((T(T(3)) \times (-T(6))) - T(3)) \times T(T(5))))$
53652 := $(T(T(5)) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6)))) - T((T(5) + T(2))))$
53655 := $(5 \times (T(3) - (T(65) \times (-5))))$
53664 := $((T(5)^3 - T(6)) \times (6 + T(4)))$
53666 := $((5 + T((3 + T(6)))) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))))$
53668 := $((T(5) \times T(T(3))) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))) - 8))$
53669 := $((-T(T(5))) + T(T((T(T(3))/T(6)))) \times (-T(T(6)))/(-9))$
53671 := $((T(5)/(-3)) + (T(6) \times T(71)))$
53676 := $(T(((5-3)^6) + 7)) \times T(6)$
53677 := $(T(T(5)) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6)))) + (-7) \times T(7)))$
53680 := $((5 + T(36)) \times 80)$
53684 := $(T(5) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6)) + 8))) + T(T(T(4))))$
53685 := $(-T(5)) \times (T(3) + ((T(T(6)) + 8) \times (-T(5))))$
53694 := $((T(T(5)) - T(3)) \times (T(6) + (T(9) \times T(4))))$
53712 := $(T((5 + T(T(3)))) + (T(T((7-1)))^2))$
53716 := $((T(T(5))/3) + (T(71) \times T(6)))$
53722 := $((T(5) \times (-3)) + T(T(7))) + (T(T(T(2))))^2$
53724 := $((-T(T(5))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(7)) + T((2 + T(4))))$
53732 := $((53 \times 7) + (T(T(T(3))))^2)$
53736 := $((-T(5)) \times (3 - T((T(7) \times 3))) + T(T(6)))$
53739 := $((T(5) \times T((3 \times T(7)))) + (T(T(3)) \times 9))$
53742 := $((5 + T(3)) + T(7)) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(2)))$
53743 := $((-T(5)) + T(T(T(3)))) + 7) \times (T(4) + T(T(T(3))))$
53745 := $((T(T(5)) + T(3)) \times T(7)) + T(T(4)) \times T(5)$
53748 := $((T(53) + 7) + T(T(4))) \times T(8)$
53755 := $((-5) + T(T(3))) \times T(7) \times T(T(5)) - 5$
53760 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))) + (T(7) \times T(60)))$
53761 := $((T(T(5)) \times ((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) + T(6))) + 1)$
53762 := $((T(5)/(-3)) + T(T(7))) + (T(T(6)))^2$
53763 := $((T(T(5)) \times ((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) + T(6))) + 3)$
53764 := $((T(T(5)) \times ((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) + T(6))) + 4)$
53765 := $(5 + ((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) + T(6)) \times T(T(5)))$
53766 := $((5 - T(3)) + T(T(7))) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(6)))$
53767 := $((T((5-3) \times 7)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(7))$
53768 := $((T(T(5)) \times ((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) + T(6))) + 8)$

- 53769 := ((T(T(5)) × ((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) + (T(6)))) + 9)
53774 := -((T(T(5)) + (T(3)))) - ((-7) - T(7)) × T(T(T(4))))
53775 := ((T(5) + T((T(3) × (7 + 7)))) × T(5))
53794 := ((-5) - T(T(3))) × (T(T(7)) - (T(9) × T(T(4))))
53795 := (5 × (-T(T(3)) + (7 × T(T(T(9 - 5))))))
53796 := (T(T(5)) - (-T(T(3))) × T((-7) + T((-9) + T(6))))
53799 := ((T((T(5) - 3)) × T((T(7) + 9))) - T(T(9)))
53835 := (-5) × ((T(T(3)) × (-8³)) - (T(5)))
53844 := -((T(T((T(5) - 3))) + (T(T((T(8)/4))) × (-T(T(4))))))
53847 := (-T(53)) + (T(T(8)) × (T(T(4)) + T(7)))
53856 := (((5 + T(3)) × T(8)) × T((-5) + T(6)))
53862 := ((T((5 × T(3))) + T(8)) + (T(T(6))²))
53864 := -((T((T(T(5)/3)) + (T(8) × (T(6) - T(T(4))))))
53865 := (((T(5)³) + (T(8) × 6)) × T(5))
53872 := (((5 + T(T(3))) × 8) × (T(7) + T(T(T(2))))))
53874 := ((T(T(5)) + 3) × ((T(8) + T(T(7))) - (4)))
53880 := (T(T(5)) + ((T(3) + T(T(8))) × 80))
53892 := -((T(5) - T(3)) × ((T(T(8)) × (-9)) + T(T(2))))
53895 := (-5) × (T(T(3)) - (T(8) × T((9 + T(5))))))
53922 := (((T(T(5)) - (T(3))) × T((T(9) - 2)))/2)
53924 := ((5 + T(T(3))) × ((T(T(9)) × 2) + (4)))
53928 := ((T(T(5)) + T(((T(3) × 9) - 2))) × T(8))
53934 := ((T(T(5)) - (T(3))) + (T(T(9)) × (-3) + T(T(4))))
53943 := ((T(T(5)) + 3) + (T(T(9)) × (T(T(4)) - 3)))
53945 := (5 - (T((T(3) + 9)) × (4 - T(T(5))))))
53946 := (T(T((5 + 3))) × (9⁻⁴⁺⁶))
53949 := ((T((5 + T(3))) + T(T(9))) × 49)
53955 := (-T(5)) × (3 + (-T(T(9) - T(5))) × T(T(5))))
53964 := (T(5) - (-T(T(3)) × ((T(T(9)) - (6)) + T(T(T(4))))))
53977 := ((5 × ((T(T(T(3))) × T(9)) + (T(T(7)))) - (T(7)))
53985 := (((-T(5)) - T((T(3) × 9))) × (-T(8))) - (T(5)))
53992 := (T((-5) + T(T(3))) × (-9) + T(T(9 - 2)))
53994 := ((53 × T(T(9))) - T((T(9) - (4))))
53995 := (-5) + ((T((T(3) × 9)) - T(T(9))) × T(T(5)))
54075 := ((5 + T(T(T(4)))) × (07 × 5))
54115 := ((T((-T(5)) + T(T(4))) × T(11)) - 5)
54123 := -((T(T(5)) + (-T(T(41) × T(2))) × T(T(3))))
54132 := (T((T(T(5))/T(4))) × (1 + (T(T(T(3))) × T(2))))
54187 := (((5 × (T(T(T(4)) + 1)) + T(8)) × 7)
54189 := (((5 - T(T(T(4))) + 1) × (-T(8))) - T(T(9)))
54195 := ((T(5)⁴) + T(-T(-((1 - 9)) - T(T(5))))))
54222 := (T((5 + T((4 × 2)))) + (T(T(T(T(2))))²))
54223 := ((T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(2)) + T(T(T(3))))))
54225 := (T(5) × (((T(4) × T(T(2)))²) + (T(5))))
54235 := (-5) - ((-T(4)) - (-2) × T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(T(5)))
54236 := ((5 × (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(2)))³))) + T(T(6)))
54237 := -((T(T((T(5) - (4)))) - (T((T(2) × T(T(3))) × T(7))))
54238 := (-T(5)) + ((-4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(T(3))) + 8))
54240 := (T(T(5)) - (T((-T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(40))))
54245 := ((-T(5)) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T((T(2) × T(4))) × T(T(5)))
54252 := (((T(5) × T(T(4))) - T(2)) × T((5 + T(T(2))))
54255 := ((-5) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T((2 × T(5))) × T(T(5)))
54257 := ((-T(5) + T(4)) + (T(T(2))⁵) × 7)
54264 := (((T(5) × T(42)) + T(6)) × 4)
54265 := (-T(5)) + (((-4) - T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(6)))) - 5)
54268 := (T(5) + ((-4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × (T(T(6)) + 8))
54275 := ((T(5) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T((2 + T(7))) × T(T(5))))
54279 := ((T(5)^{T(4)-T(2)}) - (T(T(7)) × (-9)))
54284 := (-T(T(5))) - (((4 × T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(8)))) + T(T(T(4))))
54285 := -((T(5) × (T((4 × 2)) - T(85)))
54288 := (((T(5) × (T(4)²) + 8) × T(8))
54315 := ((-T(T(5))) + T((T(T(4)) + 31))) × T(5)
54320 := ((T(T(5) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) × 20)
54322 := ((T(5) + T(43)) + (T(T(T(T(2))))²))
54326 := ((5 × (T(T(T(4))) - T(3))) + (T(T(2))⁶))
54336 := ((T(T(5)) × (4³)) + (T(3)⁶))
54356 := ((5 × T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(3)⁵) × (-6)))
54357 := (-5) - ((T(4) - (T(3)⁵) × 7)
54362 := ((5 × T(T(T(4)))) - (-T(T(3)⁶) - T(T(2))))
54366 := ((5 + (T(4)³)) + (T(T(6)) × T(T(6))))
54372 := ((T(5) × (T(T(4)) + T((3 × T(7)))) - T(2))
54375 := (T(5) × (T(T(4)) + T((T(3) + T((7 + 5))))))
54384 := (((T(T(5)) + (4)) - T(T(3))) × T((8 × 4)))
54385 := (-5) - ((T((T(T(4)) - (T(3))) × (-T(T(8))))/T(5))
54396 := ((T((T(5) + T(T(4))) × T(T(3))) + T((T(9) + T(6))))
54425 := ((T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) × (T(4) + (25)))
54426 := (((T(5)⁴) + T((4 × T(T(T(2)))))) + T(T(6)))
54432 := ((T(54)/T(T(4))) × T((T(T(3)) × T(2))))
54435 := (-T(5)) - ((T(T(4)) × T(T(4))) × (-3) - T(5))
54436 := -(((T(T(T(5)/4)) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(6))))))
54442 := (-5) - ((T(T(4)) × (-T(44))) + T(2))
54445 := ((T(((T(5) - (4)) × 4) × T(T(4))) - (5))
54447 := (T(5) - (-T((4 + 4)) × (T(T(T(4))) - (T(7))))))
54465 := (T(5) - (T(T(4)) × (-T((4 × (6 + 5))))))
54477 := (-T(T(5) - (4)) - ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(7)))) × (-T(7))))
54480 := ((T(5) + T(T((4 + 4)))) × 80)
54488 := (-T(T(5))) + (((T(T(T(4))) × 4) + (T(T(8)))) × 8)
54494 := -((T(T(T(5) - (4)))) - ((-4) + T(T(9))) × T(T(4))))
54495 := ((T(T(5)) × (4 + (T(4) × T(9)))) + (T(5)))
54516 := (((T(T(5)) - (4)) + T(T(5))) × T(T((1 × 6))))
54522 := (T((T(T(5))/T(4))) × ((T(T(5)) × T(T(2))) - T(T(T(2))))
54525 := -((T(5) × (T(4) - (T(5) × (T(2)⁵))))

- 54527 := ((T(5) - 4) × (T((T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))))) + 7))
54528 := (((T(T(5)) × T(T(4))) - (T(5))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × 8)
54536 := ((5 × 4) + ((5 + T(T(T(3)))) × T(T(6))))
54538 := ((T(5) - 4) × (T((T(T(5)) - T(T(3)))) + 8))
54566 := ((5 × T(4)) - ((-5) - T(T(6))) × T(T(6)))
54572 := (((T(5) × T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(-((T(5) - T(7)))))) × 2)
54575 := (5 × ((T(T((-4) + T(5)))) - (T(7))) × 5)
54585 := (T(T((5 + 4))) + (T(5) × T((-T(8)) + T(T(5))))))
54594 := ((-T(T(5))) - T(T((-4) + T(5)))) + (T(T(9)) × T(T(4)))
54595 := (-5) - ((-T(4)) + T(-((T(5) - T(9)))) × (-T(T(5))))
54615 := (-T(5)) × (T(T(4)) + (T(T(6)) × (-1) - T(5)))
54623 := (-((T(T(5)) + 4)) - (-((T(T(6)) + T(T(2)))) × T(T(T(3))))))
54628 := (T((5 × T(4))) + ((T(T(6))²) - 8))
54632 := -(((T(T(5)) + 4) - ((T(T(6)) + 3)²))
54633 := (T((5 × T(4))) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T(T(3)))) - 3))
54635 := (((-T(5)) - T(T(T(4)))) - 6) × (-35)
54636 := (T(T(5)) - (((-4) - T(T(6))) × T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(6)))
54639 := (((T(T(5)) + 4) × T(6)) × T(T(3))) - T(9))
54648 := ((T((T(T(5))/T(4))) × T(T(6))) + (T(T(4)) × T(T(8))))
54652 := ((T((-T(5)) + T(T(4)))) + T(T(6))) × 52
54663 := (((T(T(5)) + 4) × (T(6) × T(6))) - T(T(3)))
54665 := ((T((-T(5)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(6))) × 65
54667 := (-5) - (-((4 × 6) × T(67)))
54682 := (((T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4)))) + 6) × (-T(8))) - 2
54683 := (5 - (((T(T(T(4))) - T(6)) × (-T(8))) + T(3)))
54684 := ((T(T(5)) + 4) × (T(6)^{8/4}))
54685 := (T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(6)) - T(T(8))) × T(T(5))))
54694 := (((T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(6))) × (9 - T(T(4))))
54699 := (((T(5)⁴) - T(6)) + T((T(9) + T(9))))
54717 := (5 - ((T((T(T(4)) + 7))) + 1) × (-T(7)))
54723 := -((T((T(T(5))/4)) + (-T(72)) × T(T(3))))
54725 := ((-5) × T(T(4))) × (-T(7)) - T((T(2) + T(5))))
54726 := ((T((5 × T(4))) + T(7)) × (2 × T(6)))
54732 := (-T(5)) + (T(T(T(-((4 - 7)))))) × (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(2))))
54735 := ((T((5 × (T(4) + 7))) - (T(3))) × T(5))
54742 := -((T(T(5)) + (T(4) - ((T(7) + T(4))^{T(2)})))
54751 := -((T((T(T(5))/4)) - ((T(T(7)) × T((T(5) + 1))))))
54752 := ((T(T(5)) - 4) × (7 + T((T(5) × 2)))
54756 := ((5 + 4) × ((T(T(7)) × T(5)) - 6))
54759 := (-T(5)) - ((4 + (T(T(7)) × (-T(5)))) × 9)
54762 := (T((T(T(5))/T(4))) + ((T(7) × T(62))))
54768 := (T(T(5)) - ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(7) - 6)) × (-T(8))))
54779 := (((5 + T((T(T(4)) + 7))) × T(7)) - T(9))
54783 := (T(T(5)) + (((T(T(T(4))) - (T(7))) × T(8)) + T(T(T(3))))))
54787 := (5 - (((T(T(T(4))) - 7) × (-T(8))) + (T(T(7))))))
54793 := (-5) - ((4 + (T(T(7)) × (-T(9)))) × 3)
54795 := (((T(5) × T((4 × 7))) × 9) - T(5))
54798 := ((T((T(T(5))/T(4))) × T((T(7) + 9))) - T(8))
54811 := ((T(5)⁴) + T(T((-8) + T(T(T(1 + 1))))))
54813 := ((T((T(T(5))/T(4))) × T((T(8) + 1))) - (T(T(3))))
54815 := (-((5⁴) + (T(8) × T(T(T(-((1 - 5)))))))
54822 := ((-5) × T(4)) + ((T(8) + 2)^{T(2)})
54823 := (((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8)) - (T(T(T(T(2))))/3)
54824 := ((((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8)) - T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4)))
54825 := (T(5) × T((T((4 + 8)) + (2 + 5))))
54828 := (((T(54) + T(8)) + 2) × T(8))
54832 := (((T(5)⁴) + T(T((-8) + T(T(3)))))) + (T(T(T(2))))
54834 := (T((5 + (4 × 8))) × T((3 × 4)))
54835 := (-5) - ((T(T(4)) - 8³) × T(T(5)))
54837 := (-T(5)) - (((T(T(4)) × (-T(8))) + T(T(3))) × T(7))
54842 := (((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8)) - (T(T(4)) + T(2))
54843 := (((T((-T(5)) + T(T(4)))) × (-T(T(8))))/(-T(4))) + T(T(T(3))))
54846 := ((-T(5)) × T(T(4))) - ((-T(8)) × T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(6)))
54849 := -((T(T((T(5) - 4)))) + (-T(8)) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(9)))
54850 := (((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8)) - 50
54855 := ((T(T(5))/4) + (T(85) × T(5)))
54857 := ((T(5) × (4 + T(85))) - T(7))
54867 := (T(5) - (((T(T(4)) × (-T(8))) + (T(6))) × T(7)))
54868 := ((T(T(5)) - 4) × (8 + T((-6) + T(8))))
54871 := (((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8)) - (T(7) + 1))
54872 := ((T(((5 - 4) + 8)) - 7)^{T(2)})
54873 := ((-T(5)) + T((T(T(T(4)) + 8))/T(7))) × T(T(3))
54878 := (-T(T(5))) + ((T(T(T(4))) × T(8)) - (T(T(7)) + T(8)))
54879 := (((5 + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8)) - (T((-7) + T(9))))
54880 := (((5 × 4) + T(T(8))) × 80)
54882 := (((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8)) - (T(8)/2)
54884 := (T(T(5)) - ((T(T(T(4))) × (-T(8))) + (T(T(8)) + T(4))))
54885 := (T(5) × (-((4 - 8) + T(85)))
54886 := (((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8)) - (8 + 6))
54887 := (T(T(5)) - ((T(T(T(4))) × (-T(8))) + (T(T(8)) + 7)))
54891 := (((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8)) - (9 × 1))
54894 := ((-T(5)) - T((T(T(4)) + 8))) + (T(T(9)) × T(T(4)))
54897 := (((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8)) - T((9 - 7))
54899 := (((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8)) - (9/9))
54915 := (((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T((9 - 1))) + T(5))
54918 := (54 × (T(T(9)) - 18))
54924 := (T(5) + ((-4) × T(T(9))) + (T(2)^{T(4)}))
54925 := (((5 × (4 + 9))^{T(2)})/5)
54936 := ((T(T(5)) + ((T(T(4)) × T(9)) + T(T(3)))) × T(6))
54944 := ((T(T(5)) - ((T(T(T(4))) × 9) - 4)) × (-4))
54945 := ((T(5)⁴) - ((9 × 4) × T(T(5))))
54972 := ((-54) + (-T(9)) × T(T(7))) × (-T(2))
54974 := ((T((5 × T(4))) × T(9)) - (7⁴))

- 54975 := $(-T(5) \times (-T(4) - T((T(9) - T(7)) \times 5)))$
54981 := $((T(5)^4 + T(T(9))) + T(81))$
54983 := $(5 - ((T(4) - T((9 \times 8))) \times T(T(3))))$
54984 := $-(((T(T(T(5))/4) - 9) + (-T(8)) \times T(T(T(4))))))$
54988 := $(-T(T(5))) - (((T(T(T(4))) - 9) \times (-T(8))) + 8)$
54996 := $((T(5)^4) + T((99 - 6)))$
55056 := $((T(5) \times T((T(50)/T(5)))) + T(T(6)))$
55122 := $((5 \times (T((T(5) - 1))^2)) - T(2))$
55125 := $((5 \times T((5 + 1))^2) \times 5)$
55132 := $(T(55) + ((1 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(T(2))))))$
55146 := $(T(5) - (-51) \times T(46))$
55162 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(5)) + 1) + (T(T(6))^2)$
55176 := $((T(T(5)) + T(5)) \times (1 + T(T(7)))) + T(T(6))$
55184 := $(-((T(T(5)) + T((5 + 1)))) - (-T(8)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
55188 := $(T(55) + ((1 - 8)) \times T(8))$
55215 := $-((T(T(5)) + (T((5 \times 2)) \times (1 - T(T(5))))))$
55216 := $(T(((5 \times 5) + T(2))) \times T(16))$
55221 := $(5 + (T((-5) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(T(2)) + 1))))$
55222 := $(((-5) - (T(T(5)) \times (-2)))^2) - T(2)$
55224 := $((-T(55) + T(T(2))) \times (-T((2 \times 4))))$
55225 := $((-5) - (T(T(5)) \times (-2)))^{-T(2)+5}$
55231 := $(T(5) - (T((-5) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T((3) + 1))))))$
55233 := $((T((5 \times 5)) - 2) \times T(3 \times T(3)))$
55236 := $((T(5) \times (5^{T(2)})) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6)))))$
55237 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(T(3))) - T(7)))$
55240 := $(T(T(5)) - (T(52) \times (-40)))$
55245 := $(T(T(5)) - ((-T(5)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(5))))$
55247 := $((5 \times 5) \times T(T(T(T(2))) - T(4))) - (T(7))$
55248 := $(-T(T(5))) + (((-5) + T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8))$
55257 := $(-T(5) - ((T(T(5)) + (T(T(2))^5)) \times (-7)))$
55264 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(4))))$
55272 := $(T(-((5 - 52))) \times (7^2))$
55275 := $((5 \times 5) \times T((2 \times (T(7) + 5))))$
55278 := $((5 + T((T(5) - T(2)))) \times T((T(7) + 8)))$
55283 := $(5 - (T(T((5 + T(2)))) \times (-83)))$
55284 := $((T(5) - T((T(5) + T(2)))) - (-T(8)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
55287 := $((T(5) \times T(5))^2) + (T(T(8)) \times 7)$
55293 := $((5 + T((5 + T(2)) \times 9)) \times T(T(3)))$
55296 := $((T(T(5))/5)^2) \times 96$
55315 := $((5 - T(T(5))) \times (-T(31) - T(5)))$
55332 := $((T(55) - 3) \times (T(3)^2))$
55335 := $((T(T(5)) - (-5) + T(3)) \times T((T(3) \times 5)))$
55344 := $((T(T(5))/5) \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(4)) - 4))$
55345 := $(-5) - ((T(T(5)) + T((T(T(3)) \times 4))) \times (-T(5)))$
55346 := $(-T((5 \times 5))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(4) + T(T(6))))$
55349 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T((4 + 9)))$
55362 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T((6 \times 2)))$
55363 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(6))/3)$
55364 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(6) + T(T(4)))$
55365 := $(-T(5)) \times (((5 - T(T(3))) \times T(T(6))) + 5)$
55370 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 70$
55373 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((5 \times T(3)))) - T(T(7))) - T(T(3))$
55374 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T((7 + 4))$
55383 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(8) + T(T(3)))$
55389 := $(-T(5)) - (T((T(5) + 3)) \times (T(8) \times (-9)))$
55392 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(9) + T(2))$
55394 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (-9) + T(T(4)))$
55395 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (9 \times 5)$
55398 := $(T(T(5)) - ((-5) - T((3 + 9))) \times T(T(8)))$
55412 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T((1 + T(T(2))))$
55414 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 1)) + T(4))$
55419 := $-((T(T((T(5)/5))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times T(-((1 - 9))))))$
55420 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - 20)$
55422 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((T(T(5))/4))) - (T((T(2)^{T(2)})))$
55424 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (2^4))$
55425 := $((T(55) \times T((4 \times 2))) - T(5))$
55427 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(2)) + 7))$
55428 := $(-T(T(5))) - ((5 + T(T(T(4)))) - 2) \times (-T(8))$
55429 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (2 + 9))$
55432 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(3) + 2))$
55433 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(3))/3))$
55434 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(T((3) - (4))))$
55435 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T((4 + T(3)))) - 5)$
55437 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(3))/7))$
55438 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(3) - 8))$
55452 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(5) - T(2)))$
55453 := $(-5) - (T(T((T(5)/T(4)))) \times (-T(5) + 3))$
55455 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T((4)/5)))) + T(5))$
55456 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (-5) + T(6))$
55461 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((6 \times 1)))$
55463 := $(5 - (T(T((T(T(5))/T(4)))) \times (-6 \times 3)))$
55464 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (6 \times 4))$
55465 := $((5 \times 5) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (T(6) + T(5))))$
55472 := $((T(T(5)) \times 5) + (((T(4) + T(7))^{T(2)}))$
55475 := $((-((5^5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-7 \times 5))$
55476 := $(T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (7 - 6)))$
55482 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(8) + T(T(2))))$
55485 := $(-T(T(5))) - ((5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(8))) + T(5))$
55486 := $(-5) - (((5 - T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8)) - T(T(6)))$
55487 := $((5 \times T(5)) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(8))) + T(7)))$
55488 := $(-((T(T(5)) + T(T(5)))) + ((T(T(T(4))) + 8) \times T(8)))$
55495 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T((9 - 5)))$
55497 := $(-T(5)) + (54 \times (T(T(9)) - 7))$

- 55512 := $(T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times (T(T(T((5-1)))) + 2))$
55524 := $((-5) + T(T((T(T(5))/T(5)))) \times (T(T(T(2))) \times 4)$
55536 := $((-5) + (T(T((T(5)/5)))^3)) \times 6$
55543 := $(-5) + (T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 3))$
55544 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((T(5) + T(5)))) - (4^4))$
55545 := $(-T(5) + ((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5))))$
55548 := $((T(((5+5)/5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8))$
55575 := $(T((5 \times 5)) \times T((T(5) + T((7-5))))$
55576 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((T(5) + T(5)))) + (7)) - T(T(6))$
55584 := $((T(T(5))/5) + T(T(5))) - (-T(8) \times T(T(T(4))))$
55617 := $(-5) + ((T((-5) + T(6))) + 1) \times T(T(7))$
55623 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(5)) + ((T(T(6)) + 2) \times T(T(T(3))))$
55624 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((5 \times 6))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4))))$
55626 := $((5+5) + (T(6)^{T(2)})) \times 6$
55629 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((5 \times 6))) - T((2 \times 9)))$
55646 := $(-(5 \times 5) + ((T(T(6)) + T(4)) \times T(T(6))))$
55647 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((5 \times 6))) - T((T(4) + (7))))$
55648 := $((T(T(5))/(-T(5))) - ((6 + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(8))))$
55656 := $((T(55) + 6) \times (T(5) + T(6)))$
55662 := $((T(T(5)) - ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(6)))) \times (-2))$
55664 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((5 \times 6))) - T((6 + T(4))))$
55665 := $(-T(5) \times (((-T(5)) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(6))) - (T(5)))$
55666 := $(-5) + ((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(6)))) + T(T(6)))$
55671 := $((5+5) + T(T(6))) \times T(T((7-1)))$
55692 := $(T(-((5-56))) \times (T(9) - T(2)))$
55695 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((5 \times 6))) - (T(9+5)))$
55725 := $((T(T(5)) + ((T(5) \times 7^2)) \times 5)$
55728 := $((5 + T((T(5) + (7)))) \times T(T(2))) \times T(8)$
55734 := $(T(T(5)) + (T((T(T(5)) - T(7))) \times (3 + T(4))))$
55749 := $(-T((55-7))) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(9)))$
55755 := $((T(T(5)) - (T(5))) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(5))) + (5)))$
55776 := $((T((5 \times 5)) + (7)) \times T(7)) \times 6$
55785 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((T(5) + ((7+8)))) - (T(5)))$
55795 := $((T(T(5)) \times ((T(5) \times T(7)) + T(9))) - (5))$
55815 := $((T(T(5)) \times (-5) + T(8)) + 1) \times T(5)$
55824 := $(-((T(T(5)) - ((T(T(5)) - T(8)) \times T(T((2 \times 4))))))$
55825 := $((5 \times 5) - (T((T(8) - T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(5))))$
55826 := $(5 - ((-T(T(5))) \times T((T(8) - T(T(2)))) - (T(6))))$
55836 := $(T(5) + ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(8) - T(3)))) + (T(6))))$
55839 := $((-((T(T(5)) \times T(T((5+8)))) - T(T(T(3)))))/(-9))$
55842 := $((T((5 + T(5))) + T(8)) \times (-4) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
55845 := $(-((T(T(5)) + (T((5 + T(8))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(5))))))$
55847 := $((5/5) - ((-T(8)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(7))))$
55864 := $((-5) - T(5) + (T(T(8)) \times T(6))) \times 4$
55867 := $((T(55) \times T(8)) + T(6)) + T(T(7))$
55872 := $((T(T(5))/(-5)) - (T(T(8)) \times (-T(7)))) \times T(2)$
55875 := $((-5) - T(T(5))) \times ((-T(8)) - T(T(7)) - (5))$
55884 := $(-5) + (((T(T(5)) - T(8)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(4)))$
55914 := $((T(T(5))/5) - (T(T(9)) \times (1 - T(T(4))))$
55915 := $(-5) - ((T(-((T(5) - T(9)))) + 1) \times (-T(T(5))))$
55932 := $((5 + T(T((T(5) - 9)))) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(2))))$
55935 := $(55 \times (T(T(9)) - (3 + T(5))))$
55936 := $((T(55) + T(T(9))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6))))$
55944 := $((5 \times T(5) + 9) \times T(T((4+4)))$
55945 := $((((-5) - T(5)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(5))$
55968 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(-((T(5) - T(9)))) + (T(6) \times 8))$
55995 := $((T(5) \times T((5 + (9 \times 9)))) - T(T(5)))$
55997 := $((T((5 + T(5))) + T(T(9))) \times T(9)) - T(7)$
56115 := $(T(((T(T(5))/6) + (T(11)))) \times T(5))$
56133 := $((5 + T(T(6))) + (1 + T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))$
56160 := $(T((5 + T(6))) \times 160)$
56168 := $((5 + T(T(6))) \times ((-1) + T(T(6)) + 8))$
56173 := $((5^{6+1}) - (T(7)^3))$
56196 := $((T(5) + T(6)) \times (T(T((1+9))) + (T(6))))$
56214 := $((T(T((T(5) - 6)))) + T(T(2))) \times (-1) + T(T(4)))$
56224 := $((T((T(5) + 6)) + T(T(2)))^2 + T(T(4)))$
56229 := $(T(5) + (((T(T(6)) + T(T(2)))^2 + T(9)))$
56232 := $((T(56) \times T(T(2))) + (T(3)^{T(T(2))}))$
56238 := $((-T((T(5) \times 6))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(3)) - 8))$
56244 := $(-((T(T(5)) + (T(T(6)) \times (-244))))$
56249 := $(-(((5 + T(6))^2) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(9))))$
56250 := $(-5) \times ((T(T(6)) - T(T(2))) \times (-50))$
56252 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T((2+5))) \times 2)$
56253 := $(T(T(5)) - (T(T(6)) \times (-T(2)^{T(5/3)})))$
56255 := $(5 - ((T(6) - T(2)) \times (-5^5)))$
56256 := $((T(T(5)) + (((T(6)^{T(2)}) - (5)))) \times 6)$
56257 := $((5 + T(T(6)))^2 + T((5 + T(7))))$
56259 := $(-((T((T(5) + T(6))) + (-T((2 \times 5))) \times T(T(9))))$
56265 := $((5 + 6)^2 \times T((6 \times 5)))$
56268 := $((T((T(5) + T(6))) \times 2) + T(T(6))) \times T(8)$
56274 := $(((-5) + T(T(6))) \times T(2)) \times (T(7) + T(T(4)))$
56275 := $((T(T(5)) \times ((T(6)^2 + T(7))) - (5))$
56286 := $((T(T(5)) + (T(6)^{T(2)})) \times (T(8)/6))$
56295 := $((T(56) \times T(2)) - T(T(9))) \times T(5)$
56313 := $((T(T(5)) - (6)) \times T(31)) - T(T(T(3)))$
56322 := $((T(T(5)) + (T(6)^3) + T(T(2))) \times T(T(2)))$
56324 := $((T(5) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 2)) - T(4)$
56327 := $((T(5) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 2)) - 7$
56328 := $(-((T(T(5)) + (T(63) \times (-28))))$
56334 := $((-T(5) - T(T(6))) \times ((T(3) - T(T(T(3)))) - 4))$
56337 := $((T(T(5)) - T(T(6))) - (T(3 \times T(T(3)))) \times (-T(7)))$
56342 := $((T(T(5)) - (T(T(6))/(-3))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(2))))))$
56343 := $((T((T(5+6)) + T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3))$

- 56344 := ((-5) + (T(T(6)) × (T(3) + T(T(4)))) × 4)
56346 := ((T(T(5)) + ((T(6)³) + T(4))) × 6)
56348 := ((5 + T((T(6) + T(T(3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(8))))
56349 := (-T(5)) - (-T(T(6)) × (T(T(T(3))) + (4 + 9)))
56364 := ((5 + T((6 × T(3)))) × (T(6) × 4))
56379 := (T(5) - (-T(T(6)) × (T(-((T(3) - T(7)))) - 9))
56383 := (((5 + T(T(6))) × (T(T(T(3))) + 8)) - (T(T(3))))
56385 := ((-5) × T(6)) × (3 - (T(8) × T(5)))
56400 := ((T(T(5)) + (T(6))) × 400)
56424 := ((T(T(5)) - (-T(6) × T(T((4 × 2)))) × 4)
56425 := (-5) - ((-6) × T(T(4))) × T((T(2) + T(5)))
56432 := ((-((T(T(5)) × T(T(6)))) - T((T(4) + T(T(3)))) × (-2))
56435 := (5 - ((-6) × T(T(4))) × T((3 + T(5))))
56439 := ((T(T(5)) × T((T(6) + T(4)))) - T(T((3 + 9))))
56445 := ((T(T((T(5) - 6))) × T(T(4))) + (-4) × T(T(5)))
56448 := ((T(T(5)) + 6) × 448)
56463 := (((T(T((T(5) - 6))) × T(T(4))) - T(T(6))) - T(T(T(3))))
56469 := -(((T(T(5)) + 6) + (T(T(4)) × (6 - T(T(9))))))
56475 := (((T(5) × T(T(6))) + T((-4) + T(7))) × T(5))
56476 := ((T(5) × T((T(6) × 4))) + (T(76)))
56478 := ((5 × 6) - ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(7))) × (-T(8))))
56484 := (((5⁶) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(8)) × 4
56488 := ((-5) + (-6 × T(48))) × (-8)
56496 := -(((T(T(5)) - (T(6))) - (T(T(4)) × (T(T(9)) - 6))))
56534 := ((T(T(5)) × (-T(6))) - (-5 - (3^{T(4)})))
56535 := ((T(T(5)) × (T((6 × 5) + T(3))) + T(5))
56544 := ((T(T(5)) - 6) × T((-5) + T((4 + 4))))
56565 := (((5 + T(T(6))) × (-T(5))) - T(T(6))) × (-T(5))
56589 := (((T(T(5)) - 6) × T((-5) + T(8))) + T(9))
56594 := (-56) - ((5 - T(T(9))) × T(T(4)))
56616 := (((T(5) + T(T(6))) × T(T(6))) - T((-1) + T(6)))
56628 := (((T(56) - T(6)) - 2) × T(8))
56629 := (-T(T(5))) - ((T(66) × T(T(T(2)))) / (-9))
56634 := -((T((T(5) × 6) - T(6))) - (3^{T(4)})))
56637 := ((-T(56)) - T(T(6))) × (-3 - T(7))
56638 := (-5) - ((-6) - T(T(6))) × (T(T(T(3))) + 8))
56672 := (T((-((5 - 6) + T(6))) × (-7) + T(T(T(2))))))
56679 := (((T(T(5)) × T(T(6))) - (T(6))) + (T(7) × T(T(9))))
56682 := ((T(T(5)) + (T(6))) × (T(T(6)) + T((T(8)/2))))
56684 := (((-5) + T(6)) + T(6)) × (-8) + T(T(T(4)))
56685 := (((T(56) - T(6)) × T(8)) - T(5))
56694 := (((T(T((5 + 6))) × T(T(6))) / 9) - T(T(4)))
56695 := (-5) - ((-T(6)) - T(T(6))) × (T(9) × 5))
56721 := ((T(5) + 6) × T((72 + 1)))
56726 := (5 - (-T(6)) × T((T(7) + T((T(2) + (6))))))
56728 := (T(T(5)) + (((T(T(6)) + 7)²) - T(8)))
56732 := ((5 + (T(6) × T(73))) + T(T(2)))
56733 := (T(5) + ((T(6) × T(73)) - 3))
56736 := (T(5) - (-T(6) × T((T(7) + T((3 + 6))))))
56742 := (((5 × T(T(6))) + 7) + T(T(T(4))) × T(T(T(2))))
56748 := (((T((-5) + T(6))) × T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4))) - 8)
56749 := (((-5) × T(T(6))) × T(T((7 + 4))) / (-T(9)))
56755 := -((T(T(5)) + ((T(T(6)) - T(T(7))) × T((5 × 5))))
56760 := (T(((T(5) + T(6)) + 7)) × 60)
56763 := ((T(5) × T(6)) + (T(7) × T(63)))
56764 := (T(T(5)) + ((T(T(6)) + 7)⁶⁻⁴))
56775 := (-5) × ((T(67) - 7) × (-5))
56784 := (((5 + T(6)) × T(7)) × T((8 + 4)))
56796 := ((-5) - (-T(6) × (T(T(7)) + T(9)))) × 6)
56799 := (T(T(5)) - (T(6) - ((T(7) × T(9)) × T(9))))
56814 := ((T(T(5)) - T(T(6))) + (T(T((8 + 1))) × T(T(4))))
56821 := (-5) - (T(T(6)) × (-T(8) - T((T(T(2))) - 1))))
56823 := (((T(5) + T(T(6))) × T(T((8 - 2)))) - 3)
56824 := ((T(T(5)) × T((-6) + T(8))) + (2^{T(4)}))
56826 := ((-T(5)) - T(T(6))) × ((-8) - T(2)) × T(6))
56829 := (((T(T(5)) × T((-6) + T(8))) - T(T(2))) + T(T(9)))
56831 := (((T(T(5)) - T(T(6))) × (-8³)) - 1)
56832 := ((T(T(5)) - T(T(6))) × (-8^{T(3)/2}))
56835 := ((T(T(5)) × T((-6) + T(8))) + T((3 × T(5))))
56844 := ((T(5) - (-T(6) × (T(T(8)) + T(4)))) × 4)
56847 := ((5 × T(T(6))) - (-T(8) × (T(T(T(4))) + 7))
56849 := ((T(5) - T((T(6) - 8))) + (T(T(4)) × T(T(9))))
56856 := ((5 - (T(T(6)) × (-T(8) + 5)))) × 6)
56862 := (T((5 + T(6))) × ((8 × T(6)) - T(T(2))))
56867 := (-T(5)) + ((T(T(6)) + 8) × (T(T(6)) + 7))
56874 := (T(56) - (T(T(8)) × (-T(7)) - T(T(4))))
56875 := (-5) - ((-68) - T(T(7))) × T(T(5))
56880 := ((T((T(5) - 6)) + T(T(8))) × 80)
56882 := (((T(5) + T(T(6))) - 8) × (8 + T(T(T(2))))))
56884 := (-5) - (T((6 + T(8))) × (-8 - T(T(4))))
56895 := (T(5) + ((T((-6) + T(8))) + 9) × T(T(5)))
56897 := ((T(-((5 × (6 - 8)))) × T(T(9))) - T(7))
56899 := ((-5) - T(6)) - (T(T((T(8)/9))) × (-T(T(9))))
56904 := (-((T(5) + 6)) + (T(T(9)) × T(T(04))))
56914 := (-T((5 + 6)) + ((T(T(9)) + 1) × T(T(4))))
56919 := ((T(5) - T(6)) + (T(T(9)) × T((1 + 9))))
56922 := (((5 × T(T(6))) × T(T(9))) / T(T(T(2)))) - T(2))
56924 := ((T(T(5)) - T(T(6))) + ((T(T(9)) + 2) × T(T(4))))
56925 := ((T(5) × 69) × T((2 × 5)))
56926 := (((-5) × T(T(6))) × T(T(9))) - T(T(T(2))) / (-T(6))
56931 := (-((T(5) - T(6)) + (T(T(9)) × T((3 + 1))))
56934 := ((T(5) - 6) + (T(T(9)) × T((T(3) + 4))))
56936 := (((-5) × T(T(6))) × T(T(9))) - T(T(T(3))) / (-T(6))
56937 := (-T(T(5))) - (T(T(6)) × ((-9) - T(T(T(3))) - 7))

- 56941** := $((-5) + T(6)) - ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(4))) \times (-1))$
56942 := $((5 + 6) + ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(2))))$
56943 := $((T(5) + (6)) + ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(4))) - 3))$
56944 := $((T(5) - (6)) + ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(4))) + T(4)))$
56945 := $((((5 + 6) \times T(T(9))) + (4)) \times 5)$
56946 := $((T(5) \times 69) \times T(T(4))) + (T(6))$
56947 := $((T(5) - T(6)) + ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(4))) + T(7)))$
56949 := $((-(T(5) + (6))) + ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(4))) + T(9)))$
56951 := $((5 + T(6)) + (T(T(9)) \times T(T((5 - 1))))$
56952 := $((-5) + T(T(6))) \times (9 \times T((5 + 2)))$
56954 := $((-T(5) - T(T(6))) + ((T(T(9)) + (5)) \times T(T(4))))$
56955 := $((5 \times T(T(6))) + (T((T(9) - T(5))) \times T(T(5))))$
56965 := $((-5) + ((T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) \times T((-6) + T(5))))$
56969 := $((5 - 6) - ((T(T(9)) + T(T(6))) \times (-T(9))))$
56973 := $(((-5) + T(T(6))) \times (9 \times T(7))) + T(T(3))$
56974 := $((T(5) - T(6)) - ((-9) - T(7)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
56991 := $(T((5 + 6)) + (T(T(9)) \times T((9 + 1))))$
56994 := $((T(5) + ((6 \times 9))) + (T(T(9)) \times T(T(4))))$
56995 := $((-5) \times (((T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) \times (-9)) - (5)))$
56996 := $(5 - (((T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) \times (-T(9))) - (T(6))))$
57036 := $((T(5) + T((70 + 3))) \times T(6))$
57122 := $((((T(5) - T(7)))^{1+T(2)}) \times 2)$
57126 := $((-T(T(5))) - (-T(T(7))) \times (T(T((-1) + T(T(2)))))) + (T(6))))$
57132 := $(T((-5) + T(7)) \times (T((-1) + T(T(3)))) - T(2))$
57134 := $((T((T(5) + (7))) + 1) \times T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))))$
57155 := $((-5) + T(7)) \times T((-1) + T(5) \times 5))$
57162 := $((-T(T(5)) - (T(T(7)) \times (1 + 6))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
57200 := $((T(T(5)) - T(T(7))) \times (-200))$
57222 := $((-T((-5) + T(7))) - (T(T(T(2)))^{T(2)})) \times (-T(T(2))))$
57224 := $((-T(T(5)) - ((T(7) \times 2) \times (2^{T(4)})))$
57225 := $(5 \times (((T(7)^2) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(5)))$
57227 := $((-5) + ((T(7) + T((T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \times T(7)))$
57228 := $((-T(T(5)) + ((T(T(7) \times 2) - T(2)) \times (-T(8))))$
57231 := $((-T(5)) - (-T(T(7))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T((3 - 1))))))$
57233 := $((T(5) + T(7)) \times ((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(3)))^3))$
57234 := $((-5) + ((T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(4)))$
57237 := $(5 + ((T(7) + T((T(2) \times T(T(3)))))) \times T(7))$
57239 := $((-T(-T(5) - T(7))) \times (T(T((T(T(T(2)))/3))) - T(T(9))))$
57240 := $(T(T(5)) \times (-((7^{T(2)}) - T(40))))$
57241 := $((-5) - (-T(T(7))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T((4 + 1))))))$
57242 := $(T(T(5)) + (((7 + T(T(2)))^4) \times 2))$
57246 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + (T(T((T(2) + (4)))) \times T(6)))$
57248 := $(((-T(5) - T(T(7))) \times (-T((2^4)))) - 8)$
57249 := $((5 - (-T(7)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 4)) \times 9)$
57251 := $(5 - (-T(T(7))) \times (T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(5)) \times (-1))))$
57252 := $((-T(5)) - ((-T(T(7))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)))))) - T(T(T(2))))$
57253 := $((T(5) + T(T(7))) \times T((T(T(T(2))) - 5)) - 3)$
57256 := $((-T(5) - T(T(7))) \times (-T((2 \times 5) + 6)))$
57261 := $(T(5) - (-T(T(7))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T((6 - 1))))))$
57266 := $((-T((T(5) + T(7)))) + ((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(6))))$
57267 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(T(2)))) - (-T(6)) \times T(T(7)))$
57275 := $(T(5) - ((T(T(7)) + T(2)) \times (T(7) \times (-5))))$
57276 := $((T(T(5)) + T(7)) \times ((2 + T(T(7))) - (T(6))))$
57277 := $((T(T(5)) + (7)) \times (T((2 + 7)) + T(T(7))))$
57282 := $((T(T(5) + T(7)) \times 2) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(2))$
57283 := $((-5) - (((T(7) + T(2)) \times (-8)) \times T(T(T(3))))$
57288 := $(T(T(5)) - ((T((T(7) \times 2)) - 8) \times (-T(8))))$
57293 := $(5 - (((T(T(7)))/(-2)) - T(9)) \times T(T(T(3))))$
57316 := $(T(T(-T(5) - T(7)))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (1 - T(T(6))))$
57324 := $(T(57) - (-T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)))$
57325 := $((-5) - ((T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(2)) \times (-T(5))))$
57328 := $((5 - (-T(7) + 3)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 8)$
57342 := $(57 \times (T(3) + (T(4)^{T(2)})))$
57343 := $((-T(5)) - ((7 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(4) - T(T(T(3))))))$
57345 := $((T((5 \times 7)) \times T((3 + T(4)))) + (T(5)))$
57348 := $((T(57) - (T(3) \times T(4))) \times T(8))$
57349 := $((T(5) + T(T(7))) + 3) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(9)))$
57352 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) - (-T(T(T(3))) + T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$
57357 := $((-T(T(5)) + ((7 \times T(T(3))) \times (T(5) - T(T(7))))))$
57358 := $(T(T(5)) + ((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(5)))) - 8))$
57366 := $(T((5 - (T(7) \times (-3)))) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))))$
57372 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(2))))$
57375 := $((-5) \times ((-T(73)) + T(T(7))) \times 5)$
57378 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + ((T(3) + (7)) \times T(T(8))))$
57396 := $((T((5 \times (7 + 3))) \times T(9)) + T(6))$
57399 := $((T((T(5) + (7))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (9 + T(T(9))))$
57431 := $((-T((T(5) + (7)))) \times (4 - T(T(T(3 \times 1))))))$
57432 := $((T(5) \times ((T(T(7)) \times T(4)) - T(T(T(3)))) - T(2))$
57435 := $((-T(5)) \times ((T(T(7)) \times (-T(4))) + T((T(3) + T(5))))$
57436 := $((T(5) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(4)))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6))))$
57438 := $((T((T(5) - (7))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (-3) \times T(T(8)))$
57450 := $((T(5) - T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 50$
57452 := $((-T(T(5)) + T(7)) - (4 \times (T(T(5))^2)))$
57456 := $(T(((5 + 7) - 4) \times T(56))$
57464 := $((T((T(5) + (7))) - (4)) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(4))$
57465 := $((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(65)))$
57474 := $((T(57) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(7) - T(4)))$
57475 := $((-5) \times (((T(T(7)) + (4)) \times (-T(7))) - (T(5))))$
57477 := $(((-T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(-((4 - 7)))) \times 7)$
57484 := $((T(T(5)) \times (-7))/(-T(4)) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(T(4)))$
57485 := $((5 \times T(T(7))) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(8))) - T(5)))$
57486 := $((57 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8)) - 6$
57488 := $((T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) + (T(4) \times T(T(8)))) \times 8$

$$\begin{aligned} 57492 &:= (T((5 + T(7))) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(2)))) \\ 57494 &:= ((T(T((5 + 7))) - T(T(4))) \times (9 + T(4))) \\ 57495 &:= ((T((T(T(5)) + (-7) \times T(4))) \times T(9)) + (T(T(5)))) \\ 57522 &:= (-T((5 + 7))) + ((T(T(5)) \times 2)^2) \\ 57525 &:= ((57 + T(T(5))) \times T(25)) \\ 57528 &:= ((T(57) - T((5 \times 2))) \times T(8)) \\ 57532 &:= ((-T(5)) + T(T((T(7) - T(5)))) + (T(T(T(3)))^2)) \\ 57562 &:= ((T(5) + T(T((T(7) - T(5)))) + (T(T(6))^2)) \\ 57564 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) + (T(T((5 + 6))) \times 4)) \\ 57567 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times T(7)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(6)))/7) \\ 57569 &:= ((T(5) - T(T(7))) - (-56) \times T(T(9))) \\ 57572 &:= ((T(T(5)) + T(7)) \times ((-T(5)) + T(T(7))) - 2) \\ 57624 &:= -((T(((T(5) - 7) \times 6)) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(4)))) \\ 57629 &:= (5 - (-((T(7) + T(6))) \times T((T(2) + T(9)))) \\ 57633 &:= (T((T(T(5)) - T(7))) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(3))) \\ 57639 &:= (T(5) - (-((T(7) + T(6))) \times T((3 + T(9)))) \\ 57645 &:= ((T(5) + T((T(7 + 6) - 4))) \times T(5)) \\ 57652 &:= ((-5) + (7 \times T(6))) \times T(T((5 + 2))) \\ 57657 &:= (5 - (((-7) \times T(6)) + 5)) \times T(T(7))) \\ 57667 &:= (T((T(T(5)) - T(7))) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(6))) + T(7))) \\ 57672 &:= (T((T(5) - 7)) \times (6 + T((T(7) \times 2))) \\ 57673 &:= (((-5) + (7 \times T(6))) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(3))) \\ 57675 &:= (-5) - ((T(T(7)) + 6) \times (T(7) \times (-5))) \\ 57682 &:= (T((5 + T(7))) + ((T(T(6)) + 8)^2)) \\ 57684 &:= (T((T(5) + 7)) \times ((T(6) + T(8)) \times 4)) \\ 57692 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(7)) + ((T(T(6)) + 9)^2)) \\ 57722 &:= -T(T(-T(5) + T(7))) + T(7) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(2))) \\ 57729 &:= -((T(T(T(T(-(5 - 7)))))) - ((T(7) \times 2) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 57736 &:= ((T(-(T(5) - T(7))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(6))) \\ 57743 &:= (-((T(T(5)) - 7)) \times ((7 - T(T(T(4))))/3) \\ 57744 &:= ((5 - T(T(7))) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(4) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 57750 &:= (T(5) \times (77 \times 50)) \\ 57764 &:= (((-5) \times T(T(7))) \times (-7)) + T(T(6)) \times 4) \\ 57765 &:= ((T((T(T(5)) - T(7))) - (T(T(7)) + (T(6)))) \times T(5)) \\ 57772 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(T(7))) \times ((-7) \times T(7)) - T(T(2))) \\ 57785 &:= ((5 + T((T(7) + 7))) \times T((8 + 5))) \\ 57792 &:= (((T(5) + T(7)) \times T(7)) \times (T(9) + T(2))) \\ 57794 &:= ((T((5 + 7)) \times T((-7) + T(9))) - 4) \\ 57798 &:= (T((5 + 7)) \times T((-7 - 9) + T(8))) \\ 57816 &:= (T((-5 - 7) \times T(8)) \times (1 + T(6))) \\ 57822 &:= (((T(5) + 7) \times T((T(8) \times 2))) + T(T(2))) \\ 57824 &:= -((T((57 - 8)) - (T(2)^{T(4)})) \\ 57825 &:= (5 + (T(7) \times (T(8^2) - T(5)))) \\ 57827 &:= (((5 \times 7) \times T((T(8) + T(T(T(2)))))) - T(7)) \\ 57834 &:= (T(((5 \times 7) - 8) \times T((T(T(3)) - 4))) \\ 57840 &:= (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(7)) + ((T(8) + 40))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 57844 &:= (((-T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times (T(8) \times 4) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 57855 &:= (T(57) \times ((8 \times 5) - 5)) \\ 57856 &:= (((5 - 7)^8) \times (-5) + T(T(6))) \\ 57876 &:= (T((5 + 7)) \times (T(T(8)) + 76)) \\ 57877 &:= ((T(5) + T(T(7))) + (T(8) \times T((T(7) + T(7)))) \\ 57878 &:= ((T((5 + 7)) + 8) \times (7 + T(T(8)))) \\ 57882 &:= ((T(5) + 7) \times (T((T(8) + T(8))) + T(2))) \\ 57885 &:= ((-57) + T(88)) \times T(5) \\ 57888 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times 7) - T(8)) \times (T(8) + T(8))) \\ 57889 &:= (-T(5) - (-7) \times (-8) - (-8) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 57893 &:= (5 - ((T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) \times (-9) \times T(3))) \\ 57897 &:= ((T((T(5) + 7))) + T(T(8))) \times (9 \times 7) \\ 57925 &:= (((-T(5)) + (T(7) \times T(T(9)))) \times 2) - 5) \\ 57927 &:= (-5) - (((T(7) \times T(T(9))) \times (-2)) + T(7)) \\ 57937 &:= (-T((T(5) + 7))) \times ((9 - T(T(T(3)))) - 7) \\ 57938 &:= -((T(T(5)) + (T(T(7)) \times ((T(9) \times (-3) - 8))) \\ 57939 &:= (((57 \times T(T(9))) - T(T(3))) - T(T(9))) \\ 57942 &:= ((T((5 + 7)) + 9) \times T(T((4 \times 2))) \\ 57945 &:= (((T(T(5)) - T(7)) \times T((T(9) - T(4)))) - T(5)) \\ 57947 &:= (T(5) - (T(7) \times ((-T(9)) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(7)))) \\ 57948 &:= ((5 + T(7)) \times ((T(T(9)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(8)))) \\ 57955 &:= (((T(T(5)) \times (-7)) \times T(T(9)))/(-T(5)) - 5) \\ 57960 &:= (T(T(5)) \times (7 \times (9 + 60))) \\ 57961 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times ((T(7) \times 9) + T(T(6)))) + 1) \\ 57962 &:= ((5 - ((T(7) \times T(T(9))) + 6)) \times (-2)) \\ 57963 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times ((T(7) \times 9) + T(T(6)))) + 3) \\ 57964 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times ((T(7) \times 9) + T(T(6)))) + 4) \\ 57965 &:= (5 - (((T(7) \times (-9)) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 57966 &:= (-T(5) - (((T(7) \times (-9)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(6)))) \\ 57967 &:= (((T(T(5)) + T(7)) + T(T(9))) \times (T(6) + T(7))) \\ 57968 &:= ((-5) + ((7 \times T(T(9))) + 6)) \times 8) \\ 57969 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times ((T(7) \times 9) + T(T(6)))) + 9) \\ 57972 &:= (-((5 - 7) \times ((T(T(9)) \times T(7)) + T(T(2)))) \\ 57974 &:= (((T(T(5)) + (T(7) - 9)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 57975 &:= (((-5 - 7) \times T(T(9))) \times T(7)) + T(5)) \\ 57985 &:= (((-5) + (-7) \times T(T(9))) \times (-8)) - T(5)) \\ 57986 &:= (5 - (((-7) \times T(T(9))) \times 8) - T(6)) \\ 57987 &:= ((57 \times T(T(9))) - ((T(8) \times T(7)))) \\ 57996 &:= (T(5) - ((-T(7)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(9)))) - T(6)) \\ 58134 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(T((8 + 1)))) + ((3^{T(4)})) \\ 58174 &:= (-T(58) \times (T(-(1 - 7))) - T(T(4))) \\ 58177 &:= ((-5) + (T(8) \times T(T(-(1 - 7)))) \times 7) \\ 58179 &:= ((T(T(5)) + (8 + 1)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(9))) \\ 58207 &:= (-5) + ((T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 07) \\ 58212 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(8)) \times (T(21) \times T(2))) \\ 58217 &:= (5 + ((T((8^2) - 1) \times T(7))) \\ 58224 &:= -(((T(5) \times T((8 + 2))) - (T(2)^{T(4)})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 58225 &:= -((T(5) - (T(8^2) \times T((2+5)))) \\ 58227 &:= (T(5) - ((T(8) \times T(T(2 \times T(2)))) \times (-7))) \\ 58229 &:= -((T((5 \times 8)) - (T(2) \times (T(2^9)))) \\ 58233 &:= (((T(T(5)) - T(8)) \times T(2)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(3))) \\ 58235 &:= ((T((T(5) - 8)) \times T(2^{T(3)})) - (5)) \\ 58236 &:= (T((T(5) + 8)) \times T((-2) + T(T(3)))) + (T(6))) \\ 58237 &:= ((5 - 8) + (T(2^{T(3)})) \times T(7)) \\ 58239 &:= (((T((T(5) - 8)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) + 3) \times 9 \\ 58242 &:= (-(((T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) - (T(2)^{T(4)})) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 58245 &:= (-5) \times (((T(8)^{T(2)})/(-4)) + T(5)) \\ 58247 &:= ((5 + (T(8) \times T(T(2+4)))) \times 7) \\ 58248 &:= (((5+8) \times T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8) \\ 58249 &:= ((T((T(5) + T(8))) - 2) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 58254 &:= ((-T(5)) + T(T((T(8)/T(2)))) \times (T(5) + (4))) \\ 58263 &:= ((T(5) + T(8)) + ((T(T(T(2))) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 58275 &:= (((5 \times T(T(8)))/(-2)) \times (-7 \times 5)) \\ 58276 &:= (T(5) + ((T(8^2) \times T(7)) + T(6))) \\ 58279 &:= (-5) + ((-8) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(7)))) \times (-9)) \\ 58293 &:= (((T(5) \times (T(8)^2)) - 9) \times 3) \\ 58295 &:= (-5) \times (((T(8)^2) \times (-9)) + (5)) \\ 58296 &:= ((58 - 2) \times (T(T(9)) + (6))) \\ 58297 &:= (5 + (((T(8)^2) \times T(9)) - T(7))) \\ 58317 &:= ((T(5) + (T(8) \times T(T(T(3)))))) \times (1 \times 7) \\ 58331 &:= (-((T(T(5)) - 8) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(T(3)) + 1)))) \\ 58332 &:= (T(T(5)) - ((T(8) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(3)))/(-T(2)))) \\ 58335 &:= (T(5) + ((T((T(8) - T(3))) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 58344 &:= (T((T(5) + T(8))) \times (34 + T(4))) \\ 58345 &:= (-5) \times (((T(8)^3)/(-4)) - (5)) \\ 58353 &:= (-T(5)) + ((8^3) \times (T(T(5)) - (T(3)))) \\ 58364 &:= ((((-T(5)) \times T(T(8))) + (T(3))) \times (-6)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 58365 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(3))) - (T(6) \times (-5))) \\ 58368 &:= ((T(T(5)) + 8) \times (T(T(3)) + T((T(6) + 8)))) \\ 58373 &:= ((T(T((5+8))) \times (T(T(3)) - (7))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 58375 &:= (-5) - ((T(83) + T(T(7))) \times (-T(5))) \\ 58377 &:= (((5 + T(T(8))) \times (-T(3))) \times T(T(7)))/(-T(7)) \\ 58395 &:= ((T(5) - T(T(8))) - (3 - 9^5)) \\ 58419 &:= -((T(T(5)) - (T(T((8+4)) \times 19))) \\ 58422 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(T(8))) \times ((T(T(4)) \times (-2)) + T(2))) \\ 58424 &:= (-((5^8-4)) + (T(2)^{T(4)})) \\ 58425 &:= (T(5) \times (T(84) + T(25))) \\ 58426 &:= (((T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))))/T(6)) \\ 58428 &:= (((T(T(5)) - (T(T(8)) \times (-4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(8)) \\ 58443 &:= (T(-((T(5) - T(8))) \times ((4^4) - 3)) \\ 58444 &:= ((-5) - (-T(8)) \times T((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)))))) \times 4 \\ 58457 &:= (((-T(5)) + T(T(8))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times 5)) \times 7 \\ 58462 &:= (((T(T(5)) - (T(T(8)) \times (-4))) \times T(6)) - 2) \\ 58464 &:= ((T(T(5)) - (T(T(8)) \times (-4))) \times T(T(T((6-4)))) \\ 58472 &:= (5 - (((T(8) \times (-4)) \times T(T(7))) - T(2))) \\ 58473 &:= (T(5) - (((T(8) \times (-4)) \times T(T(7))) + (T(3)))) \\ 58476 &:= (T(T(5)) - (T(8) \times (-4) + (-7 \times T(T(6)))) \\ 58477 &:= (-T(5)) - (((T(8) \times (-4)) \times T(T(7))) - T(7)) \\ 58478 &:= (((5 + T(8)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (7 \times T(T(8)))) \\ 58479 &:= ((-5) - T(8)) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (-7 + T(9))) \\ 58480 &:= (((T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) - T(T(4))) \times 80) \\ 58485 &:= (-T(5)) - (-T(8)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (85)) \\ 58487 &:= ((T(5) + 8) + ((4 \times T(8)) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 58488 &:= ((-T(5)) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(4))) - T(T(8)))) \times 8 \\ 58492 &:= (T((T(5) - 8)) \times (T(4) + (9 \times T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 58497 &:= ((T(5) + T((8+4))) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(7)))) \\ 58520 &:= (T((T((5+8)) - T(5))) \times 20) \\ 58522 &:= ((T((-5) + T(8))) \times (T(T(5)) - 2)) - T(T(2)) \\ 58524 &:= ((T(5) - (T(8) \times T(5))) + (T(2)^{T(4)})) \\ 58525 &:= (5 \times ((T(8) \times T((5^2))) + (5))) \\ 58528 &:= (T((-5) + T(8))) \times ((T(T(5)) + T(T(2))) - 8) \\ 58545 &:= (-T(5)) - ((-8) + (T(T(5)) \times (-4))) \times T(T(5)) \\ 58547 &:= ((T(T(5)) + (-8) + T(5)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 58548 &:= (T((5 + T(8))) \times ((T(5) \times 4) + 8)) \\ 58563 &:= (T(T(5)) - (-T(-((8 - (5 \times 6)))))) \times T(T(T(3))) \\ 58568 &:= ((-5) - (T(T(8)) \times (-5 + 6))) \times 8 \\ 58575 &:= (((T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) - (5)) \times 75) \\ 58584 &:= (T(T(5)) - (T(T((-8) + T(5)))) \times (T(8) \times (-4))) \\ 58593 &:= (-T(5)) - (T(T(8)) \times (5 - 93)) \\ 58594 &:= ((T(T((5+8))) \times (5+9)) - T(4)) \\ 58597 &:= ((T(T((5+8))) \times (5+9)) - (7)) \\ 58608 &:= ((T((T(5) - 8)) + (60)) \times T(T(8))) \\ 58621 &:= ((-5) + T(8)) \times T((62 - 1)) \\ 58624 &:= ((T(T(5)) + 8) \times ((T(T(6)) \times 2) - (4))) \\ 58629 &:= (((T(5) + 8) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(9)) \\ 58635 &:= ((((-T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 6) + 3) \times T(5) \\ 58638 &:= (58 \times (T(T(6)) + T((3 + T(8)))) \\ 58642 &:= (((-5) + T(8)) \times T((6 + T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 58648 &:= ((5 - (T(T(8)) \times (-T(6) - T(4)))) \times 8) \\ 58650 &:= (((5 \times 8) + 6) \times T(50)) \\ 58653 &:= (((T(T(5)) - 8) + T(T(6))) \times T((T(5) + 3))) \\ 58664 &:= (((T(5) + 8) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(6))) - T(4) \\ 58665 &:= ((-5) + T(((8 \times T(T(6)))/T(6))) \times T(5)) \\ 58667 &:= (((T(5) + 8) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(6))) - (7)) \\ 58671 &:= ((T(5) \times T(86)) + T(71)) \\ 58674 &:= (((T(5) + 8) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(T((7-4)))) \\ 58680 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T(8)) + (6 + T(80)))) \\ 58688 &:= (-T((5 \times 8))) + (T((T(6) + T(8))) \times T(8)) \\ 58695 &:= ((5 \times T((-8) + T(6))) \times (9 + T(T(5)))) \\ 58697 &:= (((T(5) \times T((8 + T(6)))) \times 9) - T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$58722 := (((T(5) \times T(T(8))) + (T(T(7)) / (-2))) \times T(T(2)))$$

$$58724 := -((T(((5 - 8) + T(7))) - (T(2)^{T(4)}))$$

$$58725 := (((T(5) \times 87) \times T(2)) \times T(5))$$

$$58734 := ((T(T(5)) - T((T(8) - (7)))) + ((3^{T(4)}))$$

$$58765 := (5 + ((T(T(8)) - T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) - (5))))$$

$$58785 := (T(5) \times (T(87) + T((8 + 5))))$$

$$58788 := ((T(5) + 8) \times T((7 + (8 \times 8))))$$

$$58795 := (-5) - (-((8 \times 7) \times (T(T(9)) + (T(5))))$$

$$58812 := (58 \times (T(T((8 + 1))) - T(T(T(2))))$$

$$58815 := ((-5) - T(88)) \times (-15)$$

$$58823 := -((T((-5) + T(8))) - (((T(8) + T(2))^3)))$$

$$58824 := ((T(5) \times T(88)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-4)))$$

$$58825 := (-5) - ((-T(88)) - T(T(2))) \times T(5)$$

$$58842 := (((5 \times T(T(8))) - T((8 \times 4))) \times T(T(T(2))))$$

$$58855 := (T(T(5)) + ((T(88) \times T(5)) - (5)))$$

$$58857 := ((T(5) - T(T(8))) + (T(8) \times T(57)))$$

$$58866 := ((T(5) \times T(88)) - (-6 \times T(6)))$$

$$58872 := (T(T(5)) - (T(8) \times (-T(8)) - T((T(7) \times 2))))$$

$$58873 := ((-5) + T(T(8))) + ((T(8) \times 7) \times T(T(T(3))))$$

$$58878 := ((T(-T(5) - T(8))) \times (T(8) \times 7)) + (T(T(8)))$$

$$58884 := ((T(5) \times T(88)) + (T(8) \times 4))$$

$$58895 := ((-T(5 \times 8)) + T(T(8))) + (9^5)$$

$$58896 := ((T(5) \times (T(88) + 9)) + T(6))$$

$$58905 := ((T(5) + T(8)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(05))))$$

$$58910 := (5 - ((T(8) + T(T(9))) \times (-T(10))))$$

$$58921 := -(((T(T(5)) + 8) - (9^{T(T(2)-1)}))$$

$$58926 := ((T(T(5)) - T(((T(T(8))/9) + 2))) \times (-T(6)))$$

$$58929 := ((T(5) \times (-8)) - ((9^{T(T(2))}) / (-9)))$$

$$58938 := ((T(T(5)) + T((8 + T(9)))) \times 38)$$

$$58944 := (T(T(5)) - (T(8) \times (-94 - T(T(T(4))))))$$

$$58946 := ((5 + T(8)) - (-T(9) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(6))))$$

$$58947 := ((T(5) \times T(89)) - T(47))$$

$$58949 := ((58 \times T(T(9))) - T((T(T(4)) - 9)))$$

$$58962 := (((T(T(5)) \times 8) - 9) \times 62)$$

$$58963 := (-5) - ((-T(8)) \times T((-9) + T(6))) \times T(T(3)))$$

$$58965 := ((T(5) + T(-((8 - 96)))) \times T(5))$$

$$58968 := ((T(T(5)) + T(8)) \times (9 \times (6 + T(8))))$$

$$58982 := (-((5 + 8) + (T(T(9)) \times (T(8) + T(T(T(2))))))$$

$$58983 := (((T(T(5) + T(8))) \times T(9)) - T(T(8))) - T(T(3)))$$

$$58992 := ((-T(5) - (8 \times 9)) \times T(T(9))) - T(2)$$

$$58994 := ((T(5) \times T(89)) - T((-9) + T(T(4))))$$

$$58995 := (((T(5) + 8) \times T((9 + 9))) \times T(5))$$

$$59034 := -((T(5) - ((9/03)^{T(4)}))$$

$$59054 := (-((5 - (9^{05}))) + T(4))$$

$$59057 := (T(5) + ((9^{05}) - 7))$$

$$59064 := (T(5) + ((9 - 06)^{T(4)}))$$

$$59085 := ((T(T(5)) - (T(90) - T(8))) \times (-T(5)))$$

$$59124 := (T(T(5)) + ((T(9) \times (-1)) + (T(2)^{T(4)}))$$

$$59133 := (((T(5) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(13))) \times 3)$$

$$59136 := (((5 - 9)^{1+3}) \times T(T(6)))$$

$$59163 := (T(T(5)) + ((9^{-1+6}) - T(3)))$$

$$59169 := (T(T(5)) + (((9 \times 1)^6) / 9))$$

$$59214 := (T(T(5)) + (T(9) + (T(2)^{T(1 \times 4)}))$$

$$59220 := ((-T(T(5))) + T(T((9 + T(2)))) \times 20)$$

$$59223 := ((T(T(5)) \times T(9)) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (2 + T(T(T(3))))))$$

$$59224 := (((T(5) + T(T(9))) / T(T(2))) + (T(2)^{T(4)}))$$

$$59227 := -((T(T(5)) - (((T(9) - T(T(2)))^{T(2)} + T(7))))$$

$$59232 := ((T((T(5) + T(9))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 32)$$

$$59246 := (5 + ((T(9) - T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(6))))$$

$$59256 := (T(T(5)) - ((T(T(9)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-56)))$$

$$59262 := ((T(5) + T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(T(2))))))$$

$$59265 := (-T(5)) \times (T(9) - (T(T(2)) \times T((T(6) + T(5))))))$$

$$59274 := ((T(T(5)) - 9) \times (T(T(2)) + T((T(7) + (4))))$$

$$59276 := (((-T(5)) + T(T((9 + T(2)))) \times (-T(T(7)))) / (-T(6)))$$

$$59292 := ((-T(5)) + T(T((9 + 2))) \times (9 \times T(2)))$$

$$59295 := ((T(5) + T(T((9 - T(2)))) + (9^5))$$

$$59314 := (-5) + ((T(9) - T(3))^{-1+4})$$

$$59322 := (((5 \times 9) - T(3))^{T(2)} + T(2))$$

$$59323 := (((T(T(5)) \times T((9 \times T(3)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) / 3)$$

$$59324 := (-5) + (((T(9) - T(3))^{T(2)} + T(4)))$$

$$59325 := (T(5) \times (-T(T((9 - 3)))) + T(T((-2) + T(5))))$$

$$59327 := (T(5) + (((T(9) - T(3))^{T(2)} - (7)))$$

$$59328 := ((-5) + T((9 \times T(3)) + T(2))) \times T(8)$$

$$59332 := (T(5) + (((T(9) - T(3))^3) - 2))$$

$$59334 := (5 + (((T(9) - T(3))^3) + T(4)))$$

$$59342 := (5 + ((T(T(9)) + T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) + 2)))$$

$$59343 := (T((T(5) + 9)) + (((3^{T(4)}) - T(3)))$$

$$59346 := ((T((T(T(5)) - T(9))) - (T(3) \times 4)) \times T(6))$$

$$59349 := (T((T(5) + 9)) + (3^{T(T(4)) - T(9)}))$$

$$59355 := (-5) \times (9 + ((T(T(3)) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(5))))$$

$$59358 := -((T((T(T(5)) - T(9))) - ((T(3)^5) \times 8)))$$

$$59367 := (((T(T(5)) \times T(9)) + T(T((T(3) + (6)))) \times 7)$$

$$59374 := ((5 + 9) \times (T(T((T(3) + (7)))) + (T(T(4))))$$

$$59385 := ((T(T(5)) \times (T(9) \times (3 + 8))) - (T(5)))$$

$$59388 := (T(5) + (9 \times ((3^8) + T(8))))$$

$$59395 := (((-5) + T(9)) \times T((T(3) \times 9))) - (5)$$

$$59508 := (T((T((T(T(5)) - T(9))) / 50)) \times T(8))$$

$$59515 := ((T(T(5)) \times T(((T(9) - T(5)) + 1))) - (5))$$

$$59532 := (((-T(5)) + T((-T(9)) + T(T(5)))) \times T(T(3))) - T(2)$$

$$59534 := ((5 + 9) + (T(T(5)) \times T((T(T(3)) + T(4))))$$

$$59535 := (((T(T(5)) \times T(9)) - T(53)) \times T(5))$$

- 59544** := ((T(5) + 9) × (T((T(5) + T(T(4)))) - 4))
59547 := ((T(T(5)) + (9⁵)) + T((T(T(4)) - T(7))))
59549 := ((5 + (9⁵)) - (T(T(4)) × (-9)))
59554 := -((T(T(5)) - ((9⁵ + (5⁴))))
59556 := ((-((5 + 9)) + T((5 × T(5)))) × T(6))
59565 := (((T(T(5)) × (-T(9))) - (T(5))) × (-6 + 5))
59572 := (((T(T(5)) + (9⁵)) + T(T(7))) - T(2))
59577 := ((-T(5)) + (T((-9) + T(5)) × T(T(7)))) × 7
59586 := ((-59) + (T(5) × T(T(8)))) × 6
59598 := (T(T((T(5) - 9))) × (-T(T(5)) - T((-9) + T(8))))
59622 := (((T(T(T(5)) - T(9))) × T(6)) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(2))
59625 := ((T(T(5)) - T((9 × T((6 - 2)))) × (-T(5)))
59628 := (T(T(5)) - (T((T(9) + (6 × 2))) × (-T(8))))
59634 := ((T(5) × (T(9) - (6))) + (3^{T(4)}))
59645 := (5 - (-((T(9) - T(6))) × T((T(T(4)) + (T(5))))))
59646 := ((T(5) × (T(T(9)) + T((T(6) + T(T(4)))))) + T(T(6)))
59647 := ((5 × ((T(9) × T(T(6))) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(7)))
59649 := (59 × (-((6 × 4) + T(T(9))))
59652 := ((T(5) + (-9) × T(T((6 + 5)))) × (-T(2)))
59655 := (-T(5)) - (-T(9) × T((T(6) + T(5)) + T(5)))
59665 := (-5) - (-T(9) × T((T(6) + ((6 × 5))))
59676 := -((T(59) - (T(6) × T(76))))
59677 := (-5) - ((T(T(9 - 6))) × T(T(7))) × (-7))
59679 := ((T(5) + ((T(T(9)) × 6) + T(T(7)))) × 9
59682 := ((T((5 × (9 + 6)) - 8) × T(T(T(2))))
59685 := ((-T(5)) × (9 - (6 × T(T(8)))) - T(T(5)))
59688 := (((-5) × T((9 × 6))) - T(8)) × (-8))
59692 := (-5) - (T((T(9) + T(6))) × (-9) × T(2))
59694 := (-T(5)) - ((T(9) - (6)) × (9 - T(T(T(4))))
59695 := (-5) × ((-9) × T((6 + T(9)))) - (5))
59696 := (5 - ((-T(9)) × T((6 + T(9)))) - (T(6)))
59697 := ((T(T(T(5)) - T(9))) × T(6)) - T((T(9) - T(7)))
59703 := ((T(T(T(5)) - T(9)) - 7) × T(T(03)))
59727 := ((5 × 9) + ((7 × T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(7)))
59737 := (((5 - T(T(9))) × T(T(7))) + T(T(3)))/(-7))
59740 := -((T(T(5)) - ((T(9) + T(7)) × T(40)))
59742 := ((-T(5)) + (-9) × T(T((7 + 4)))) × (-T(2))
59745 := -(((T(T(5)) + T(T(9))) + (T(T(7)) × (-T(4) × T(5))))
59766 := (((T(T(5)) - T(T(9))) × (-7)) + (T(T(6)) × T(T(6))))
59768 := ((-5) - ((T(T(9)) × (-7)) - T(T(6)))) × 8
59775 := ((T(T(5)) - T(9)) × ((T(T(7)) + T(T(7))) - (T(5))))
59784 := (((T(5) + T(9)) - (7)) × T((-8) + T(T(4))))
59785 := (T(T(-(5 - 9))) × ((T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) + (T(5))))
59795 := ((5 + T((T(9) - (7)))) + (9⁵))
59796 := (((T(T(5)) + T(9)) × (T(T(7)) - T(9))) + T(T(6)))
59832 := -((T(T(5)) + (((-T(9)) × T(T(8))) - (T(3)) × 2))
59835 := (-T((5 + 9)) - (T(T(8)) × (-T(3) × T(5))))
59862 := ((T(T(5)) - (T((T(9) + 8)) × T(6))) × (-2))
59865 := (((T(5) + T(T(9))) × (T(8) + T(6))) + (T(5)))
59868 := ((T(-(5 - 9)) + T((T(8) + T(6)))) × T(8))
59886 := ((T((5 + T(9))) × T(8)) + (T(T(8)) × T(6)))
59890 := ((-5) - T(9)) - (T(T(8)) × (-90))
59892 := ((T(5) - (9 - 8)) × T(92))
59895 := ((T(T(5)) + T(9)) × (T((T(8) - 9)) - (T(5))))
59922 := (((T(5) × T((T(9) - 9))) - T(2)) × T(T(2)))
59925 := (T((5 + T(9))) × ((T(9) - T(2)) + (5)))
59928 := (((5 + 9) × T(92)) + T(8))
59935 := (((-T(5)) × T((T(9) - 9))) × (-T(3))) - (5))
59943 := (-((T(5) - 9) - T(9)) × (T(T(T(4)) - 3))
59944 := (-((T(5) - 9) + ((T(T(9)) + T(T(4))) × T(T(4))))
59945 := ((T(T(-(5 - 9))) × (T(T(9)) + T(T(4)))) - 5)
59954 := -(((T(T(5)) - T(T(9))) + (-((9⁵ + T(4))))
59955 := (T((T(5) - 9) × (T((-T(9)) + T(T(5)))) + 5))
59957 := (((T(T(5)) + 9) × T((T(9) - T(5)))) - T(7))
59964 := -(((T(T(5)) - T(T(9))) - ((9 - 6)^{T(4)}))
59976 := (T((T(5) - 9) × (T(9 + 7)) × T(6)))
59982 := ((T((T(5) - 9) + (T(9) × T(T(8)))) × 2)
59984 := ((59 × T(T(9))) - T((T(8) + T(4))))
59985 := ((T(T(5)) + 9) × T((9 + T(8)) - T(5)))
60228 := ((T(T(6)) + T(T(T(02)))) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 8))
60273 := (T(60) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × T((T(7) - T(3))))
60375 := (((-T(60)) × T(T(T(3))))/(-7) - T(5))
60385 := ((T(60) × (-3) + T(8)) - (5))
60522 := (((T(T(6)) + T(05))²) + T(T(2)))
60525 := ((-60) + T((T(5) × T(T(2)))) × T(5))
60594 := (-6) + ((0 - T(T(5))) × (T(T(9)) - T(T(T(4))))
60645 := ((60 - T(6)) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(5)))
60837 := (T(T(6)) - ((0 - T(T(8))) × T((T(3) + (7))))
60924 := ((T(60) + T(9)) + (T(2)^{T(4)}))
61215 := (T(T(6)) × (T((-1) + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(-(1 - 5))))
61226 := (-T((T(6) + 1)) × ((T(T(T(T(2))))/(-T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(6))))
61236 := ((6 + T(12)) × (3⁶))
61248 := ((T(T(6)) + 1) × (T(24) - T(8)))
61250 := (T(((6 + 1)²) × 50)
61278 := (6 + ((1 + T((T(T(2)) + (7)))) × T(T(8))))
61296 := (((61 - 2) × T(T(9))) + T(T(6)))
61320 := ((61 + T(T(T(3)))) × T(20))
61335 := ((T(T((6 - 1)) × T(3)) - (T(3))) × T(5))
61376 := ((T((T(6) + 1)) + T(T(3))) × (-7) + T(T(6)))
61383 := (T(T(6)) + (T(13) × (T(T(8)) + (T(3))))
61422 := ((-T(6)) × (1 - T((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))))) - T(2))
61425 := (T(6) × ((-1) + T(4) × T(25)))
61426 := (-((T(6) - 1) + (T((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) × T(6))))

- 61427** := $(61 \times ((T(4)^{T(2)} + (7)))$
61435 := $(-((6-1) + ((4^{T(3)} \times T(5))))$
61438 := $((T(6) \times T((T(T((1 \times 4))) + T(T(3)))))) - 8)$
61443 := $((T(6) \times T((T((1 + T(4))) + T(4)))) - 3)$
61446 := $(6 - (T((1 + 4) \times (-4^6)))$
61466 := $((T(6) - 1) + (T((T(T(4)) + (T(6)))) \times T(6)))$
61467 := $(-T(6) \times (-1 - T(((T(T(4)) \times (-6)) + T(T(7))))))$
61479 := $(T((T(6) + 1) \times ((T(T(4)) - T(7)) \times 9))$
61488 := $((T(T(6)) + T((-1) + T(T(4)))) - 8) \times T(8)$
61494 := $(-6) \times (1 - ((-T(4) + T(T(9))) \times T(4)))$
61569 := $((-T(61) - T((T(T(5)) - T(6)))) \times (-9))$
61594 := $(-6) - (((1 \times 5) - T(9)) \times T(T(4)))$
61596 := $((6 \times T(-((1 - 59))) \times 6)$
61635 := $((T(6) - 1) \times T(T((6 + T(3)))) + T(5))$
61642 := $((-T(6) - ((-1) + T(6)) \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (-2))$
61648 := $((6 - ((1 - 6) \times T(T(T(4)))) \times 8)$
61655 := $((T(T(6)) - 1) - (T((6 \times T(5))) \times (-T(5))))$
61656 := $((T((6 - 1)) \times T((6 \times T(5)))) + T(T(6)))$
61676 := $(T(T(6)) + (-1) + (T(6) \times T(76)))$
61677 := $(T(T(6)) \times ((1 + T(T(6))) + (T(7) + (7))))$
61682 := $((6 - 1) - (-T(T(6)) + T(8))) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$
61683 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(T((1 \times 6))) + T(8))) + T(3))$
61694 := $(-T(T((6 + 1))) + ((6 \times T(T(9))) \times (-T(4))))$
61698 := $((-6) \times (1 - (T(T(6)) \times T(9)))) - T(T(8))$
61732 := $(T((T(6) + 1) \times (T(7) + (T(3)^{T(2)})))$
61734 := $(-T(T(6)) + ((-1) + T(T(7))) \times T((T(T(3)) - (4))))$
61747 := $(-T(6) - ((T(T((1 + 7))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(7))))$
61748 := $(-T(6) - 1) - (-T(7) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8))))$
61793 := $(61 \times ((-T(7) + T(T(9))) + T(3)))$
61824 := $(T((6 + 1) \times ((T(T(8)) + 2) + T(T(T(4))))$
61869 := $(-T(T(6)) + ((T(18) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(9))))$
61887 := $(-T(T(6)) + (-T(((1 + 8) + 8))) \times T(T(7)))$
61938 := $((T((6 - 1)) + T(9 + 3)) \times T(T(8)))$
61989 := $(-T(6) - (T((-1) + T(9)) + 8) \times (-T(9)))$
61995 := $((T((61 - 9)) \times T(9)) - T(5))$
62094 := $(-6) - ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(9))) \times (-T(4)))$
62118 := $(T(T((T(6)/T(2)))) \times T(-((1 - 18)))$
62124 := $(6 + (T(T((T(T(2)) + 1))) \times T((T(T(T(2))) - 4)))$
62139 := $(T(T(6)) \times (-((2 - 1) + (T(3) \times T(9))))$
62160 := $((T(T((6 + T(2)))) + 1) \times 60)$
62208 := $((6 \times 2)^{T(2)} \times T(08))$
62229 := $(-T(T(6)) + (((T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + 2) \times T(9)))$
62232 := $(T(T(6)) + (((T(2) \times T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3))))^2))$
62235 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(2))) - T(2)) \times (3 \times T(5))$
62244 := $((T(6) \times T(2)) \times (-2) + T(44))$
62253 := $((-T(T(6))) - (T((T(2) \times T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5)))) \times (-3)$
62256 := $((6 + 2) \times ((T(T(2))^5 + (6)))$
62271 := $(T((T(6) - (2 + 2))) \times (T(T(7)) + 1))$
62272 := $((T((T(6) + 2) + 2) \times (-7) + T(T(T(T(2))))))$
62283 := $((T((T(T(6))/T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T((T(8) + 3)))$
62286 := $(-T(6) - ((T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2))) - T(8)) \times (-T(6))))$
62288 := $((T(T(6)) - 2) \times (2 \times T((8 + 8))))$
62292 := $(-T((6 \times 2)) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(9)) \times T(T(2))))$
62293 := $((T(T(6))/(-T(2))) - ((T(T(2)) \times (-T(9))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
62294 := $(-T(6) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(2)) \times T(9))) - (T(T(4))))$
62295 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(2))) - 2) \times T(9) + T(5))$
62298 := $((6 \times (-T(T(2))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9))) - T(8))$
62319 := $(-6) - (((-T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + 1) \times T(9))$
62325 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(2) \times T(3))) - T(2)) \times T(5)$
62328 := $(T(6) - (-T(T(T(2)))) \times (T((T(T(T(3))/T(2))) - T(8))))$
62346 := $((T(T(6)) \times T((T(2) \times 3))) - (4) \times 6)$
62347 := $((T(T(6)) - 2) - (T((T(T(3)) - (4))) \times (-T(T(7))))$
62349 := $(-T(6) - ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(3))) \times T(T(4))) \times (-9))$
62352 := $(6 \times ((T(2) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5)) - T(2))$
62355 := $((62 + T((T(3) \times T(5)))) \times T(5))$
62364 := $(-6) - (((T(2)^3) \times T(T(6))) \times (-T(4)))$
62365 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(23) - (6))) - (5))$
62369 := $((-6)/T(T(2)) + ((-T(3)) \times T(T(6))) \times (-T(9)))$
62385 := $((T(T(6)) \times ((T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) + T(8))) + T(5))$
62391 := $(-T(6)) \times ((-2) \times T((T(3) \times 9)) - 1)$
62393 := $(T(6) + 2) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(9) \times T(3)))$
62394 := $(-6) \times ((T(T((2 \times 3))) \times (-T(9))) - (4))$
62398 := $((6 \times (T(T(2)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(9))) - 8)$
62412 := $(-T(6)) \times ((-2) \times T((T(T(4)) - 1)) - 2)$
62418 := $(6 \times ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(4) - 1)) + 8))$
62424 := $((-6) + T((T(2) \times T(4))) \times T((2^4)))$
62425 := $(T(T((6 - 2))) \times ((-4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 5))$
62426 := $((T(6)/T(2))^4 \times 26)$
62433 := $((T((T(T(6))/T(2))) - (T(4) \times 3)) \times T(T(3)))$
62436 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(2))) \times T(43)/T(6))$
62439 := $(T(T(6)) - ((T(T(2))^4) \times (-3) - T(9)))$
62440 := $((T(T((6/2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 40)$
62443 := $(-T(6) + ((2^{T(4)}) \times (T(T(4)) + T(3))))$
62444 := $((T(T(6)) - ((-2) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(4))) \times 4)$
62447 := $((T(T(6))/(-T(2))) - ((T(T(T(4)))/(-T(4))) \times T(T(7))))$
62454 := $(-T(6) - ((T(T(2)) - T(T(4))) \times T((5 \times T(4))))$
62455 := $(-T(T((6 \times 2))) - (4^{T(T(5))/T(5)}))$
62457 := $(T(6) + (T((T(T(T(2))) - T(4))) \times T((T(5) + T(7))))$
62464 := $((6/T(2))^{T(4)} \times (6 + T(T(4))))$
62468 := $((T(6) + 2) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T((6 \times 8))))$
62469 := $(-T((6^2)) + ((T(T(4)) + (6)) \times T(T(9))))$
62472 := $((T(T(6)) - T(2)) \times ((T(4) \times T(7)) - T(T(2))))$
62474 := $(-6) + (((-2) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)))) \times (-T(T(4))))$

- 62475** := $(T(((T(6) + T(2)) + T(4))) \times (7 \times T(5)))$
62478 := $((T(T(6)) + T(2)) \times (T(T(T(-(4-7)))) + T(8)))$
62479 := $((T(T(T((6-2))))/T(4)) \times T(T(7))) - T(9))$
62481 := $((T(6) \times T((T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)))))) + T(T((8+1))))$
62488 := $((T(62) \times (4 \times 8)) - 8)$
62489 := $((T(6) \times T((T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)))))) + (8 + T(T(9))))$
62496 := $((-T(6)) \times T(T(2))) \times (-496)$
62517 := $((T(T(6)) - 2) \times (T(T(5)) + T(17)))$
62524 := $((-6) - (25^{T(2)})) \times (-4)$
62526 := $(6 \times (T(T(T(2)))) + (5 \times T((2^6))))$
62532 := $((6^{T(T(2))}) + ((T(T(5)) + (T(3)))^2))$
62538 := $(T(6) + (T((-2) + T(5))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(8))))$
62548 := $((T((T(T(6))/T(2))) - (T(5) + (4^8))))$
62553 := $((-T(T(6))) - ((T(T((-2) + T(5)))) \times (-T(5))) + T(3))$
62557 := $((-T(T(6) + 2)) - (-T(5) \times T(T(-(T(5) - T(7))))))$
62559 := $((-T(6)) \times ((T(T(2)) + (T((5 \times 5)))) \times (-9)))$
62565 := $((-T(6)) + T(T((-2) + T(5)))) + 6 \times T(5)$
62574 := $((-6) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-T(T(5))) + (7 \times T(T(T(4))))))$
62583 := $((T(T(6)) - (T(25))) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(3)))$
62586 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(2) \times T(5))) + T(8)) \times 6$
62592 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(2))) + (5) \times T(9)) - T(2)$
62595 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(2))) + (5)) \times (9 \times 5)$
62619 := $((-T(6)) + (T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(6)) + 1) \times T(9))))$
62621 := $((T(T(6))^2) + ((T(6)^{T(2)} - 1))$
62622 := $((T(T(6))^2) + (T(T((6/2)))^{T(2)}))$
62628 := $((T(T(6)) \times (-2) + T((T(6) + 2))) - T(T(8)))$
62634 := $((T(T(6)) - (2 \times 6)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4))))$
62643 := $((T((T(6) \times 2)) + T(64)) \times T(T(3)))$
62646 := $((T((T(6) + 2)) \times (T(T(6)) - (4))) - (6))$
62647 := $((T((T(T(6))/T(2))) \times T(6)) + (-T(4)) - T(T(7)))$
62648 := $((6^{T(T(2))})/6 + T(T(4))) \times 8$
62657 := $((T((T(T(6))/T(2))) \times (6 + T(5))) - (T(T(7))))$
62658 := $((T(T(6)) - T(2)) \times T(T(6))) + (T(5) \times T(T(8)))$
62664 := $((-T((T(6) \times T(2)))) - (-((T(6) + T(6))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
62679 := $((-6) - (((T(T(2)) \times T(T(6))) + (7)) \times (-T(9))))$
62682 := $(62 \times (T(T(6)) + T((T(8) + T(2))))$
62685 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (6 + T(T(8)))) \times T(5)$
62694 := $((-6) - (T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(6)) \times (-T(9))) - T(T(4))))$
62712 := $((T(T(6)) - T(T((2+7)))) \times (-T(12)))$
62715 := $((-6) + T(T((T(2)) + (7)))) + 1 \times T(5)$
62724 := $((-T(6)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(7)))) + (T(2)^{T(4)}))$
62727 := $((-6) + ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(7)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times 7$
62735 := $((-T(T((6-2)))) - (T(T((7+T(3)))) \times (-T(5))))$
62742 := $((T(6) - T(2)) \times T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) - T(T(2)))$
62744 := $((T(6) - T(2)) \times T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) - 4)$
62746 := $((T(T(6)) - 2) \times ((T(7) \times T(4)) - (6)))$
62748 := $((T(T(6)) - (T(27) \times (-4))) \times T(8))$
62766 := $((T(6) - T(2)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T((6+6))))$
62769 := $((-T(6) + ((2 - T(7)) \times T(69)))$
62772 := $((-T(6)) \times ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(7)))) \times (-7))) + T(2)$
62775 := $((T(T(6)) - T(T(2))) \times ((-7) + T(T(7))) - T(T(5)))$
62776 := $((T(T(6)) + T((T(T(2)) + T(7)))) \times 76)$
62784 := $((-6) - (-T(-(2-7))) \times T((T(8) + T(T(4))))$
62792 := $((6 - (T(T((T(T(2)) + (7)))) \times (-T(9))))/T(2)$
62793 := $((-6) + (T((2 + T(7))) \times (-T(9)))) \times (-3)$
62796 := $(6 + (T(T((T(T(2)) + (7)))) \times (9 + 6))$
62811 := $(T(6) \times (T((T(2) + T(8))) + T(T(11))))$
62826 := $((T(T(6)) \times (2 \times T((8 \times 2)))) - (6))$
62832 := $(T(T(6)) \times (-((2^8)) + T(32)))$
62835 := $((T((T(T(6-2))) + T(8))) + 3) \times T(5)$
62838 := $((T(T(6)) + T(T(T(2))))^{8-T(3)} - (T(T(8))))$
62845 := $(T(T((6-2))) - (T((T(8) + T(T(4)))) \times (-T(5))))$
62853 := $((-T(T(6 \times 2))) - (T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(3))))$
62865 := $((T(T(6)) - ((T(T(2)) - T(T(8))) \times 6)) \times T(5))$
62867 := $((T((T(T(6))/T(2))) - 8) \times T(6)) - (T(7))$
62874 := $((T(6) \times T(2)) \times ((T(8) \times T(7)) - T(4)))$
62880 := $((6 + T((T(2) + T(8)))) \times 80)$
62894 := $((6 - T(T((2+8)))) \times (-T(9) - (4)))$
62895 := $((T((T(T(6))/T(2))) - 8) \times T((-9) + T(5)))$
62916 := $((T(T(6)) + 2) \times T(9)) + 1 \times 6$
62922 := $((T(T(6)) + 2) \times T(9)) + 2 \times T(T(2))$
62924 := $((T(T(6)) - T(2)) \times (T(9) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - 4)$
62925 := $((T(T(6)) + 2) \times T(9)) \times T(T(2)) + (T(5))$
62928 := $((T(6) - 2) \times 92) \times T(8)$
62937 := $((T(6)^{T(2)} - (T(9) \times T(3))) \times 7)$
62943 := $(T(T(6)) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9))) \times (-T((4 \times 3))))$
62944 := $((-T(6)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(9)))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
62946 := $((-6) - ((T(2) - T(T(9))) \times (T(T(4)) + (6))))$
62964 := $((-6) \times (T(T((2+9))) - (T(T(6)) \times T(T(4))))$
62972 := $((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(9))) - ((T(7)^2))$
62985 := $(T(-((T(6)/T(2)) - T(9))) \times 85)$
62988 := $((6 \times ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9)) - 8)) + (T(T(8))))$
63000 := $(T(6) \times 3000)$
63063 := $(T(T(6)) \times ((T(T(3)) + T(T(06))) + T(T(3))))$
63072 := $((T(6) + 3) \times T(072))$
63105 := $((T(6) + T(T((3+10)))) \times T(5))$
63126 := $((-T(6)) \times (-3) - T((-1) + T((2 \times 6))))$
63129 := $((-6) + ((T(T((3+1))) + T(T(2))) \times T(T(9))))$
63134 := $((-6) - (((T(T(3)) - 1) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(4))))$
63135 := $((6 + T(T((3+1)))) \times T((3 \times T(5))))$
63179 := $((-T(6)) - ((T(T(3)) - 1) \times (-T(79))))$
63189 := $((-T(6)) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T((-1) + T(8) + T(9))))$
63217 := $((T(T(6)) - ((T(T(3))^{T(2)} + 1)) \times (-7))$

$$\begin{aligned} 63224 &:= (((T(T((6+T(3)))) + T(2)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 63225 &:= (((T((T(T(6)/3)) + 2) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(5)))) \\ 63231 &:= (T(T(6)) + (T((T(T(3)) + T(2))) \times T((T(T(3)) - 1)))) \\ 63249 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 2)) + (T(4) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 63252 &:= ((T((T(T(6)/3)) - ((T(T(2)) - (T(5)))))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 63273 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(T(3)))^2) - T((7 \times 3))) \\ 63279 &:= -((T(T((6+T(3)))) - (T(T(T(2))) \times T(79)))) \\ 63282 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(T(3)))^2) - (T(T(8))/T(2))) \\ 63286 &:= ((T((T(T(6)/3)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (8 - T(T(6)))) \\ 63287 &:= ((T((T(T(6)/3)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (-8 \times T(7))) \\ 63288 &:= ((T(T(6)) + (3 \times (T(2) - T(T(8)))) \times (-T(8))) \\ 63292 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(T(3)))) + (-2 + T(9))) - 2) \\ 63294 &:= (T(T(6)) \times ((3 \times 2) \times T(9)) + (4)) \\ 63316 &:= ((T((T(T(6)/3)) \times T(T(3))) + (T((1 + T(6)))) \\ 63324 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (-3 \times T((T(2)^4))) \\ 63339 &:= (((T((T(T(6)/3)) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(T(3)))) + T(9)) \\ 63342 &:= ((T(6) + T(3)) \times T((34 \times 2))) \\ 63345 &:= (((-6) \times T(3)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \times 5) \\ 63348 &:= ((6/3) \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(8)))) \\ 63354 &:= (-T((6 \times 3)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-5 \times T(T(4)))) \\ 63355 &:= ((T(((T(T(6))/T(T(3))) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - 5) \\ 63357 &:= (T(6) - ((-((T(3) \times T(3))) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 63360 &:= ((-T(6)) - T(T((3 \times 3))) \times (-60)) \\ 63363 &:= ((T((T(T(6)/3)) \times T(T(3))) + (T((T(6) + 3)))) \\ 63378 &:= -((T(6) \times (T(3) + ((-3) \times T(7)) \times T(8)))) \\ 63384 &:= ((T(T(6)) - 3) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (-8) + T(T(4)))) \\ 63396 &:= (6 \times (T((3 \times T(3))) + (T(9) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 63399 &:= (-6) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(3) \times T(9))) - T(T(9))) \\ 63415 &:= ((-T(6)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(4))) - 1) \times 5) \\ 63423 &:= ((6 + (3^4)) \times (T(2)^{T(3)})) \\ 63424 &:= ((T(T(6)) + ((T(T(3)) + (4))^{T(2)})) \times 4) \\ 63427 &:= ((-T(6)) \times (T(3) - (T(T(4))^2)) + T(7)) \\ 63429 &:= (-T(6)) + ((T(T(T(3))) + 4) \times (T(T(2)) \times T(9))) \\ 63435 &:= (((T(T(6)/3)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(3)) \times T(5)) \\ 63441 &:= (-T(6)) \times (3 - ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(4))) - 1)) \\ 63445 &:= ((-6) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + T(4)) \times 5) \\ 63448 &:= ((T(T(6)))/(-3)) \times (-4 - T((4 + T(8)))) \\ 63459 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(T(3)))^{T(4)/5}) - T(9)) \\ 63462 &:= (T(6) \times (-3 + (T((4 + 6))^2)) \\ 63465 &:= (((-6) - T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(6)))) \times 5) \\ 63468 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(T(3)))^{-4+6}) - T(8)) \\ 63476 &:= ((T(6) \times T(T((3 \times 4)))) - T((T(7) + T(6)))) \\ 63483 &:= (((T(6) \times T(T(3))) \times (4 \times T(8))) - T(T(3))) \\ 63485 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T((T(3) + 4)))) - 8) \times 5) \\ 63492 &:= (6 + ((T(T(T(3))) - (-T(4)) \times T(T(9)))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 63494 &:= (T(T(6)) - ((3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(9) - 4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 63495 &:= (((6^{T(3)})/4) + T(T(9))) \times 5) \\ 63497 &:= (((T(6)^3) - T((T(4) + 9))) \times 7) \\ 63498 &:= (6 \times (((T(T(T(3))) + 4) \times T(9)) + 8)) \\ 63504 &:= ((T(6) \times T(3)) \times 504) \\ 63516 &:= ((T(T(6)) + (T(3))) \times (T(5) + T((1 + T(6)))) \\ 63519 &:= (-6) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-5) \times T((1 + 9))) \\ 63524 &:= ((-6)/T(3)) - ((5 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \\ 63525 &:= (T(T(6)) \times ((3 + 52) \times 5)) \\ 63528 &:= (((T((T(T(6))/T(T(3)))) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 8) \\ 63531 &:= (6 - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-5) \times T(T((3 + 1)))) \\ 63534 &:= ((6 + 3) - ((5 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \\ 63543 &:= (T(6) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times (5 \times T(T(4)))) - 3)) \\ 63546 &:= ((T((63 + T(5))) - T(T(4))) \times T(6)) \\ 63547 &:= (-6) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-5) \times T(T(4))) - (T(7))) \\ 63549 &:= (-T(6)) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times (5 \times T(T(4)))) + T(9)) \\ 63555 &:= ((6 + (T(T(T(3))) \times 55)) \times 5) \\ 63567 &:= (T(T(6)) - ((T(3) \times (-5) - T(6))) \times T(T(7))) \\ 63582 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(5) \times T(T(8)))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 63597 &:= (6 - ((T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times (-T(9) - T(T(7)))) \\ 63645 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T(3)) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) \\ 63648 &:= (T((6 + T((3 + 6)))) \times 48) \\ 63666 &:= -((T(T((6 + 3))) + (-T(6)) \times T(T((6 + 6)))) \\ 63672 &:= ((T(T((6 + T(3)))) - (T(6) + T(7))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 63693 &:= (-T(6)) \times (((-3) - T(6)) + T(T(9))) \times (-3)) \\ 63735 &:= ((-63) - T(T((7 + T(3)))) \times (-T(5))) \\ 63742 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times 3) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(2))) \\ 63746 &:= (((T(6)^3) \times 7) - T(46)) \\ 63748 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(((T(3) + 7) + T(4)))) - 8) \\ 63762 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(T(3))) \times T((T(7) - 6))) + T(T(2))) \\ 63777 &:= (T(6) \times ((T(3) + T(7)) + T(77))) \\ 63783 &:= (T((6 \times 3)) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(8) - 3))) \\ 63784 &:= (T(63) - (-T(7)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 63791 &:= (((T(6)^3) \times 7) - T(T(9))) - 1) \\ 63798 &:= (T(6) \times ((3 + T(7)) \times 98)) \\ 63822 &:= (((T((T(T(6)/3)) + T(8)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(2)) \\ 63825 &:= (((T(T((6 + T(3)))) - T(8)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(5)))) \\ 63828 &:= ((T((T(6) + 38)) + T(2)) \times T(8)) \\ 63834 &:= (T((6 + T(3))) - (-T(8)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 63840 &:= (T(((T(6)/3) \times 8)) \times 40) \\ 63847 &:= (-T(6)) - ((T(38) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(7))) \\ 63855 &:= ((-63) - (-T(8)) \times T(T(5))) \times T(5) \\ 63864 &:= (-T(63)) + (T(8) \times T((6 \times T(4)))) \\ 63882 &:= ((T(6) \times (3 + T(8))) \times T((T(8)/T(2)))) \\ 63887 &:= ((T(T((T(T(6))/T(T(3)))) - 8) \times (T(8) - 7)) \\ 63888 &:= ((-6) + (T(3) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(8)))) \times 8) \\ 63910 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(3) \times T(9))) + T(T(10))) \\ 63924 &:= (-T(6)) \times (((-3) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(2))) + T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

- 63936 := ((T(T(6)) - (3 × T(9))) × T(36))
63939 := -((T(T(6)) + (((-3) × T(T(9))) × T(T(3))) + T(T(9))))
63942 := (((T(T(6)) × T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(9)) × T(4))) + T(T(T(T(2))))
63954 := (T((T(T(6))/T(T(3)))) × (T(T(9)) - T((T(5) - (4))))
63955 := (T((6 + T(3))) × T((T(9) - (5))) - (5))
63966 := ((T(T(6)) - T(T(3))) - ((-T(9)) - T(T(6))) × T(T(6)))
63973 := (T((T((T(6)/3)) + 9)) × T((7 + T(3))))
63987 := (T(T(6)) × ((T(3) × (9 + T(8))) + (7)))
63989 := -((T(T(T(6)/3))) - (T(9) × T((8 + T(9))))
63990 := ((T((6 × T(3))) + T(9)) × 90)
63993 := (6 + ((T(T(T(3))) × T((T(T(9))/T(9)))) + T(T(T(3))))
63996 := ((T(T(6)) × (T(T(T(3))) + T(9))) - (-9 - T(T(6))))
63998 := ((T(6) × T(T((3 + 9)))) - T((T(9) - 8)))
64021 := (T(6) + ((40²⁺¹)))
64034 := (-((T(6) - ((40³)))) + T(T(4)))
64039 := (-((6 - (40³))) + T(9))
64125 := (((T(T(6)) × T(T(4))) + T(T((-1) + T(T(2)))))) × 5)
64149 := (-T(6)) - ((4 - T((1 + T(4)))) × T(T(9)))
64152 := ((T(T(6)) + T((T(4) + 1))) × (-T(5) + T(T(T(T(2))))))
64162 := (T((T(6) - (4))) + (T((1 + T(6)))²))
64174 := ((T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) × (1 + T(7))) + (T(T(4))))
64218 := (T(T(6)) × (T(T(4)) + ((T(21) - 8)))
64222 := ((T(T(6)) - ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(T(2)))) + 2)) × (-2))
64233 := (-6) - (((T(T(T(4))) × 2) - (T(T(3)))) × (-T(T(3))))
64234 := (((T(T(6)) - (4))²) - (T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(4))))
64238 := (((-((T(6)⁴) - T(T(T(T(2)))))/(-3)) - (T(T(8))))
64239 := ((-6) + T(T(4))) × (T(23) + T(T(9)))
64242 := ((T(6) × ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(2))
64248 := (((T(T(6)) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(2)))) + (4⁸))
64249 := (((-T(6)) + T(T(4))) × T((T(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) - T(9))
64251 := ((T(T(6)) + T((4 × T(T(2)))) × (T(T(5)) + 1))
64255 := ((T((T(6) × 4)) × (T(2) + T(5))) - (5))
64272 := ((T((T(6) - (4))) + T(2)) × (T(T(7)) + T(T(2))))
64273 := ((T((6 + T(T(4)))) × (T(T(2)) + T(7))) - (T(T(3))))
64274 := (((-T(6)) × T(T(T(4)))) × (-2)) - (T((7 × 4)))
64281 := (-T(6)) × (((T(T(4))²) + T(8)) × (-1))
64284 := (-6) × (-4 - (T(2) × T(84)))
64287 := ((T(6) × T(T((T(4) + 2)))) - (8 + T(T(7))))
64294 := ((T(6) + T(4)) × ((2 × T(T(9))) + (4)))
64323 := ((T(6) × T(T((4 × 3)))) - T((T(2)³)))
64329 := (-T(6)) - (T(T(4)) × (T(3) - T((T(2) + T(9))))
64331 := (((T(6)⁴)/3) - T(31))
64335 := (((-T(T(6)) + T(T(4))) × (T(3) - T(T(T(3)))) - T(5))
64344 := (-T(6)) × (((T(4) + T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(4))))
64356 := (6 - (-((T(4) + 3)) × T((T(T(5)) - (T(6))))))
64365 := (T(6) × (T(T((4 × 3))) - (T(6) - (5))))
64368 := (((-T(6)) + T((T(4) × T(3)))) - (T(6))) × T(8))
64371 := ((T((T(6) + T(T(4)))) × (-T(3) - T(7))) - 1)
64372 := (T((T(6) + T(T(4)))) × ((-3) + T(7)) - T(2))
64386 := (((T(6) + T(T((4 × 3)))) - T(8)) × T(6))
64387 := ((T(6) + T(4)) × (-3) + T((T(8) + T(7))))
64389 := (-6) + (T((T(T(4)) + ((T(3) - 8))) × T(9))
64394 := ((T(T(6)) × ((T(4) + T(T(3))) × 9)) - T(T(4)))
64416 := ((6 + T(T(4))) × (T(T((T(4) - 1))) + (T(6))))
64422 := (((6 - T(T(T(4)))) × (-42)) - T(T(2)))
64424 := (((6 - T(T(T(4)))) × (-42)) - 4)
64425 := ((-T((T(6) + (4)))) + (T(T(T(4))) × T(2))) × T(5))
64427 := ((T(6) + ((T(4) × 4)^{T(2)})) + T(T(7)))
64428 := ((6 - T(T(T(4)))) × (-((4 + 2)) - T(8))
64429 := ((-T(6)) + T(T(4))) - (T((T(T(4)) - 2)) × (-T(9)))
64439 := (-T(6)) - (T(T(4)) × (4 - T((3 + T(9))))
64449 := (T(T(6)) × ((T(4) + T((-4) + T(4))) × 9))
64452 := ((T(T(6)) × (4 - (T(T(4)) × (-5)))) + T(2))
64454 := ((-6) - T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(4) × T(T(5))) × T(T(4)))
64455 := ((T(6) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(5) × T(5))))
64456 := (((T(6) × T(T(4))) - (4)) × 56)
64465 := ((T(64) × (T(4) + T(6))) - T(5))
64473 := (-T(T(6))) + ((-4) - (T(T(T(4))) × 7)) × (-T(3))
64476 := (6 × (((T(T(T(4))) - 4) × 7) - 6))
64477 := (-T(T(6))) - ((-T(T(4))) × T((T(T(4)) - (7)))) - (T(7))
64482 := (((T(6) + T((4 + T(T(4)))) × T(8)) + T(T(2)))
64484 := (((T(6 × T(4))) + (4)) × T(8)) - T(T(T(4)))
64485 := ((T(6) + T((T(4) × T(4)) - 8)) × T(5))
64491 := (-T(6)) × (T(4) - T(T((4 + 9) - 1)))
64495 := (((T(6) + T(4)) × T((T(T(4)) + 9))) + T(5))
64512 := (T(6) × ((4⁵) × (1 + 2)))
64522 := (((-T(6)) - (T(T(4)) × (-5)))²) + T(T(2))
64526 := ((T(T(6)) × (-T(T(T(4)))) - T((-5) + T(T(T(2)))))/(-6))
64530 := ((6 + T(-((T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))))) × 30)
64533 := ((T(6) × ((4⁵) × 3)) + T(T(3)))
64539 := (((T(T(6)) × T(T(4))) × 5) - T(T(3))) + T(T(9))
64542 := (((T(6) × (4⁵) + T(4)) × T(2))
64547 := (((6 × T(T(T(4)))) - (T(5) + (4))) × 7)
64548 := ((T((T(6) - ((4 - 5))) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8))
64554 := (-T(6)) × (T(T(4)) - ((5⁵) + 4))
64569 := -((T(T(6)) + ((T(4) × T(T(5))) × (-6 × 9))))
64572 := (((6 × T(T(T(4)))) - T(5)) × 7) - T(2))
64575 := (T((T(6) + ((4 × 5)))) × 75)
64584 := ((-6) + T((4 + T(5)))) × T((T(8) - T(4)))
64588 := ((T(T(6)) + T(4)) × (T((T(5) + 8)) - 8))
64596 := (((T(6)⁴) × T(5))/T(9)) - T(T(6))
64599 := ((6 + T(T(4))) × ((T(5) + 9) + T(T(9))))

- 64617 := ((T(T(6)) + T((4 × T(6)))) × 17)
64623 := (6 - ((4 - T(T((6 × 2)))) × T(T(3))))
64625 := (((T(T(6)) + (4)) × T(T((6 - 2)))) × 5)
64629 := ((T(64) - (T(6)^{T(2)})) × (-9))
64632 := (((-T(6)) × T(T(T(4)))) + (T(6) + 3)) × (-2))
64635 := (-T(T(T(6) - T(4))) - (-T(6) × T(T((-3) + T(5))))))
64638 := (((T(6) × T(T(4))) - (T(6))) × (T(T(3)) + T(8)))
64652 := ((6 - T(T(4))) - (-T(6) × T(T((T(5) - T(2))))))
64655 := (((T(T(6)) × T(T(4))) + T(T(6))) - (5)) × 5)
64659 := (-T(6) - (T(T(4)) × ((-T(6) - T(T(5))) - T(T(9))))))
64662 := (-T(6) - ((T(T(T(4))) × (-T(6) + T(6)))) - T(2))
64664 := (-6) - ((T(T(T(4))) × (-T(6) + T(6))) + T(4))
64665 := ((T(T((6 + 4))) × (T(6) + T(6))) - (T(5)))
64667 := (-6) - ((T(T(T(4))) × (-T(6) + T(6))) + 7)
64668 := (((-T(6)) × T(T(T(4)))) + 6) × (6 - 8)
64672 := (-6) - (((T(4) × T(T(6))) × (-T(7))) + 2)
64674 := (-6) - ((T(4) × T(T(6))) × (-7 × 4))
64675 := ((T(T(6)) × ((4 + 6) × T(7))) - (5))
64678 := (6 - (((T(4) × T(T(6))) × (-T(7))) + 8))
64692 := (((-T(6)) × T(T(T(4)))) - T(-((6 - 9))) × (-2))
64695 := ((T(T(6)) - (4)) × ((6 × T(9)) + T(5)))
64701 := (T(6) × T(T(((4 + 7) + 01))))
64704 := (6 × ((T(T(T(4))) × 7) + 04))
64714 := (-T(6) - ((T(T(T(4)) - (7))) + 1) × (-T(T(4))))
64716 := (6 × ((T(T(T(4))) × 7) + (1 × 6)))
64719 := (T((T(6) - (4))) × (T((T(7) - 1)) + T(9)))
64722 := (-T(6)) × ((T(T(4)) - T((T(7) × 2))) × 2)
64725 := ((T(T(6)) × (T(4) × T(7))) + (T(2) × T(5)))
64728 := (((64 × T(7)) + T(T(2))) × T(8))
64729 := (((6 × T(T(T(4)))) + 7) × (-2 - 9))
64752 := (((-T(6)) × T(T(T(4)))) - T((-7) + T(5))) × (-2))
64755 := ((T(T(6)) × (T(4) × T(7))) - (-5) × T(5))
64756 := (T((6 + 4) - (T(T((7 + 5))) × (-T(6))))
64757 := ((-T(6)) × (-4 - T(T((7 + 5)))) - T(7))
64758 := (6 × ((T(T(T(4))) × 7) + (5 + 8)))
64763 := (-64) - (-7) × (T(6)³)
64764 := ((T(T(6)) × (T(4) × T(7))) - (T(6) × (-4)))
64782 := ((T(6) × (4 + T(78))) - T(2))
64785 := (((T(T(6)) × T(T(4))) - (-7) × T(8)) × 5)
64794 := (6 × ((T(T(T(4))) × 7) + (9 + T(4))))
64812 := (((T(6)⁴) - T((8 + 1)))/T(2))
64821 := (T(6) - (-T((T(4) × 8))) × (T(T(T(2))) - 1))
64822 := (((-T(6)⁴) + T((8 - T(2))))/(-T(2)))
64823 := (((T(6)⁴) - (T(8)/T(2)))/3)
64824 := (-6) × (-4) - (T(8) × T(24))
64827 := ((T(6)⁴)/(8 + 2) - 7)
64828 := ((-((T(6) - (4⁸))) - T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(8))))
64832 := (((T(6)⁴) + T((8 - 3)))/T(2))
64833 := (((T(6)⁻⁴⁺⁸)/3) + T(3))
64836 := (((T((6 × 4)) × T(8)) + T(3)) × 6)
64839 := (((T(6)⁴) + T(8)) × 3)/9)
64842 := (((-T(6)⁴) - T((T(8)/4)))/(-T(2)))
64843 := ((T(T(6)) + (4⁸)) + (-4) × T(T(T(3))))
64844 := ((T(6) × ((T(T(T(4))) + 8) + T(T(T(4)))) - 4)
64845 := ((T((6 × T(4))) × T(8)) - (T(45)))
64848 := (-T(6)) × ((T(T(T(4))) × (-8/4)) - 8)
64849 := -(((T(6) - (4⁸)) + T((4 × 9)))
64854 := (-6) - (T((T(4) + T(8))) × (T(5) × (-4)))
64855 := (((T(T(6)) + (4)) × T((8 + T(5)))) - (5))
64860 := (T(((6 + 4) + T(8))) × 60)
64862 := (((T(6)⁴) + T((8 + 6)))/T(2))
64869 := (-T(6)) × ((T(T(T(4))) × (-8 - 6)) - 9)
64872 := (((T(T(6)) + (4)) + T(T(8))) × 72)
64876 := (((T(6) × T(T((4 + 8)))) + T(T(7))) - T(T(6)))
64882 := (((6 + (4⁸)) - T(T(8))) + T(T(2)))
64884 := (((-T(T(6))) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(8))) + T((-8) + T(T(4))))
64885 := ((((-6) + T(4))⁸) - T(T(8))) + (T(5))
64911 := (T(T(6)) - ((T(T(4)) - T(T(9))) × T(11)))
64920 := ((T(T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(9))) × 20)
64922 := ((T(T(6)) - T(4)) + (T(T((9 + T(2)))) × T(T(T(2))))
64924 := (-((6⁴)) - (-((T(9) - 2)) × T(T(T(4))))
64925 := (T((-6) + T(T(4))) × ((T(9) + T(2)) + (5)))
64926 := (((6 + T(T(T(4)))) × (T(9) - T(2))) - 6)
64929 := (((-6) + T(T(4))) × (T(T(9) + T(T(2)))) - T(9))
64931 := (((6 + T(T(T(4)))) × (T(9) - 3)) - 1)
64932 := (((-6) - T((T(4) + T(9)))) × T(T(3))) × (-2))
64935 := (((T(T(6)) + T((T(4) × 9))) + 3) × T(5))
64936 := ((T(T(6)) + (4)) - (T(T((9 + 3))) × (-T(6))))
64938 := (((-6) + T(T(4))) × (T(T(9) + T(3))) - T(8))
64944 := ((T(T(6)) - T(T(4))) × (T(T(9)) - T(T((4 + 4))))
64945 := ((T(6) + T(4)) × (T((9 + T(T(4)))) + T(5)))
64949 := ((64 × (T(T(9)) - (4))) - T(T(9)))
64953 := (T(6) × ((-4) + T((9 × 5))) × 3)
64959 := ((T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(9))) × 59)
64962 := -((T(T(6)) + ((4 + (T(T(9)) × (-T(6)))) × T(2)))
64964 := (((-6) + T(T(4))) × (T(T(9) + (6)))) - T(4))
64965 := ((T((T(6) + (4))) - T(96)) × (-T(5)))
64967 := (((-6) + T(T(4))) × T((T(9) + (6)))) - (7))
64974 := ((-6) + T(T(4))) × T((T(9) + T((7 - 4))))
64983 := (((6 + T(T(4))) × T(T(9))) - (-8) × T(T(T(3))))
64984 := -(((T(T(6)) - T(4)) - (T(T(9)) × (8 + T(T(4))))))
64985 := ((T(T((6 + 4))) + T(9)) × (T(8) + (5)))

$$\begin{aligned} 64989 &:= ((T((T(6) - T(4))) \times T(T(9))) - T((T(8) + T(9)))) \\ 64992 &:= (((-T(T(6))) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(9)) \times (T(9) + T(2))) \\ 64995 &:= (T((T(6) \times 4)) - (T((T(9) + T(9))) \times (-T(5)))) \\ 64998 &:= ((-64) \times (9 - T(T(9)))) - T(T(8))) \\ 65088 &:= ((T(T(6)) - 5) \times (08 \times T(8))) \\ 65107 &:= ((T(6) \times T(T((T(T(5))/10)))) + (T(T(7)))) \\ 65136 &:= ((T(T(6)) + 5) \times T((-((1 - 3) + T(6)))) \\ 65142 &:= ((T(T(6)) + 51) \times T(T((4 + 2)))) \\ 65145 &:= ((T(T(6)) - ((T(51) \times T(4)))) \times (-5)) \\ 65163 &:= (((T(T(6)) + 51) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(3))) \\ 65184 &:= (-T(6)) \times (T((T(5) + 1)) - T((8 \times T(4)))) \\ 65185 &:= -(((T(T(6)) - ((5 - 1)^8)) + T(T(5)))) \\ 65223 &:= (((-T(6)) \times T((T(5) \times T(2)))) - T(T(2))) \times (-3)) \\ 65226 &:= (((-T(6)) \times T((T(5) \times T(2)))) \times (-T(2))) + (T(6))) \\ 65232 &:= ((T(T(6)) - (T(5))) \times (2 + T((T(T(3)) + T(2)))) \\ 65247 &:= (T(6) \times (T((-5) + T((2 + T(4)))) + (T(T(7)))) \\ 65259 &:= (((T((T(6) + 5))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(5)))) \times 9) \\ 65268 &:= (((6 \times T(5)) + (2 + 6)) \times T(T(8))) \\ 65274 &:= (6 \times ((T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) + (7 \times T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 65280 &:= ((T((T(6) - 5))) \times T(T(2))) \times 80) \\ 65283 &:= ((T(6) + T(T(5))) \times (-2) + T((T(8) - T(3)))) \\ 65292 &:= ((T((T(6) + 5))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(9))) + T(T(2))) \\ 65295 &:= (((-T(6)) \times (-5 - (T(2) \times T(T(9)))) - (T(5))) \\ 65319 &:= (-T(6)) + (T((5 + T(3))) \times T((-1) + T(9))) \\ 65325 &:= ((T(T(6)) - (5 \times T(3))) \times T(25)) \\ 65334 &:= -((T(T(6)) - ((T(T(5)) + T(T(3))) \times T((3 \times T(4)))))) \\ 65346 &:= (((-6) \times T(T(5))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(6)))))) \\ 65373 &:= (T(T(6)) \times ((5 \times T(3)) + T((T(7) - T(3)))) \\ 65379 &:= (((6 \times T(5)) + 3) \times T((T(7) + 9))) \\ 65384 &:= -((T(T(6)) - (5 + ((3^8) \times T(4)))) \\ 65387 &:= (T(6) - ((-(5^3) - T(8)) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 65394 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T(5)) \times (3 + T(T(9)))) / T(T(4))) \\ 65415 &:= (((T(6) - 5)^4 - 1) - T(T(5))) \\ 65416 &:= (((T(6) - 5)^4 - T(T(-(1 - 6)))) \\ 65422 &:= ((6 - T(T(5))) + (4^{2^{T(2)}})) \\ 65425 &:= -(((T(T(6)) - T(T(5))) - (4^{T(2)+5})) \\ 65428 &:= (((T(6) - 5)^4 - (T(2) \times T(8))) \\ 65436 &:= (((-T(6)) \times T(T((5 + 4)))) \times (-3)) + T(T(6))) \\ 65444 &:= ((-6) - (((T(T(5)) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(4))) \times (-T(4)))) \\ 65450 &:= ((T((6 + T(5))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-50)) \\ 65456 &:= ((T((6 \times T(5))) - 4) \times (-5) + T(6)) \\ 65457 &:= (T(6) \times (T(T((T(T(5))/T(4)))) + T((T(5) - 7)))) \\ 65468 &:= (((T(6) - 5)^4 - 68) \\ 65472 &:= ((T((T(6) - 5))) - 4) \times T((T(7) + T(2)))) \\ 65474 &:= (((T(6) - 5)^4 - 7) - T(T(4))) \\ 65475 &:= ((-6) + T(((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) + T(7))) \times T(5)) \\ 65478 &:= (-T(6)) \times ((T(T(5)) + T(4)) - (T(T(7)) \times 8)) \\ 65484 &:= (-T(6)) + ((T(5) + T(48)) \times T(T(4))) \\ 65485 &:= (((T(6) - 5)^4 - T(8)) - T(5)) \\ 65487 &:= (((-6) - T(5)) + (4^8)) - T(7) \\ 65491 &:= (((T(6) - 5)^4 - T((9 \times 1))) \\ 65493 &:= ((T(T(6)) - (T(T(5)) \times (-4 \times T(9)))) \times 3) \\ 65505 &:= ((T(6) \times (5^5)) - T(T(05))) \\ 65515 &:= ((T((6 \times T(5))) \times (T(5) + 1)) - 5) \\ 65534 &:= ((T(6) \times (5^5)) - T((3 + T(4)))) \\ 65535 &:= ((T(6) \times (5^5)) - (T(3) \times T(5))) \\ 65536 &:= ((T(6) - 5)^{-5+3+6}) \\ 65537 &:= (((T(6) + T(T(5))) \times T((5 \times T(3)))) - T(7)) \\ 65541 &:= (T(6) \times (((5^5) - 4) \times 1)) \\ 65542 &:= (((6 + 5) + 5)^4 + T(T(2))) \\ 65548 &:= ((6 + T((T(5)/5))) + (4^8)) \\ 65556 &:= ((T(6) + T(5)) \times ((T(T(5)) \times T(5)) + (T(6)))) \\ 65562 &:= (T(6) \times ((5^5) - (6/2))) \\ 65564 &:= (((T(6) \times (5^5)) - 6) - T(T(4))) \\ 65565 &:= ((T(6) + T(T(5))) \times T(((T(5) - T(6)) \times (-5)))) \\ 65568 &:= (((T(6) \times (5^5)) - T(6)) - T(8)) \\ 65571 &:= (6 + (T(5) \times T((T(T(5)) - (T(7) - 1)))) \\ 65576 &:= (((T(6) \times (5^5)) - T(7)) - T(6)) \\ 65583 &:= (((T(6) \times (5^5)) - T(8)) - T(3)) \\ 65584 &:= (((-T(6)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(5))) \times T(8)) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 65585 &:= ((T(6) \times (5^5)) - (8 \times 5)) \\ 65595 &:= (((T(6) \times (5^5)) - T(9)) + T(5)) \\ 65598 &:= (((T(6) \times (5^5)) + 9) - T(8)) \\ 65616 &:= ((6 + T((T(5) \times 6))) \times 16) \\ 65625 &:= (T(6) \times (5 \times 625)) \\ 65637 &:= (((6 - T(T(5))) + T(T(6))) \times T((T(T(T(3)))/7))) \\ 65646 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times (5^6))/T(T(4))) + (T(6))) \\ 65649 &:= -((T(T(6)) - (T(T(5)) \times ((6 + T(T(4))) \times 9))) \\ 65655 &:= ((6 \times 5) + (T(6) \times (5^5))) \\ 65664 &:= ((T(T(6)) - (T(5))) \times (-T(6)) + T((T(6) + 4))) \\ 65667 &:= ((T(6) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T((6 + 6)))) \times 7) \\ 65681 &:= (((T(T(6)) + (T(5))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(8))) - 1) \\ 65682 &:= -((T(T(6)) - ((T(T(5)) - (T(6))) \times T(T(8)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 65685 &:= (((T(6) + T(T(5))) \times T((-6) + T(8))) + T(T(5))) \\ 65687 &:= -((6 - 5) + (T(68) \times T(7))) \\ 65688 &:= (((5^5) + T((T(6) + 8))) \times 8) \\ 65715 &:= -(((T(T(6)) \times ((T(T(5)) - T(T(7))) + 1)) + T(T(5)))) \\ 65723 &:= (((T(6) \times T(5)) - T(7)) \times (-2) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 65736 &:= ((T(6) \times T((5 + 7))) + T(T(3 + 6))) \\ 65737 &:= -(((T(T(6)) - (T(T(5)) \times T(7))) \times T(T(3))) - T(7)) \\ 65739 &:= (((T(6) \times T(T((5 + 7)))) + 3) + T(T(9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 65758 &:= (((T(6) \times 5) - (7)) \times (5 + T(T(8)))) \\ 65764 &:= ((-T(6)) \times ((T(T(5)) \times (-T(7))) + T(T(6)))) + T(T(4)) \\ 65769 &:= -(T(T(6)) - (T(T(5)) \times (T((T(7) + (6))) - T(9)))) \\ 65772 &:= ((-((T(6) + (5)) + T(7))) \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(2)) \\ 65778 &:= ((-T(6)) \times ((T(T(5)) - (7)) \times (-T(7)))) - T(T(8)) \\ 65784 &:= (-((T(6) - (5^7))) + (-8) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 65793 &:= ((6 + T(5)) \times (T(7) + (T(T(9)) \times 3))) \\ 65796 &:= -(((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(7)))) + (T(9) \times 6)) \\ 65799 &:= ((T((6 + 5)) - (-7) \times T(T(9)))) \times 9 \\ 65814 &:= (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) - T(T((1 + 4))) \\ 65815 &:= ((((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) + 1) - T(T(5)) \\ 65824 &:= (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) + (-2) \times T(T(4))) \\ 65832 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (-T(5) - T((8 \times 3)))) - T(2)) \\ 65835 &:= (T(T(6)) \times (5 + (8 \times 35))) \\ 65843 &:= (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) - T((T(4) + 3)) \\ 65854 &:= (-((T(6) + (5))) + (T(8) \times T((T(5) \times 4))) \\ 65856 &:= (T(((T(6) - T(5)) \times 8)) \times 56) \\ 65859 &:= ((((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(5))) + T(9)) \\ 65864 &:= (-((T(6) - (5))) + (T(8) \times T((6 \times T(4)))) \\ 65867 &:= (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) - (67)) \\ 65877 &:= (T(6) + ((T(T(5)) - T(8)) \times (T(7) \times T(7)))) \\ 65878 &:= (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) - (7 \times 8)) \\ 65886 &:= (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) - (8 \times 6)) \\ 65889 &:= (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) - (T(8) + 9)) \\ 65892 &:= (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) - (T(9) - T(2))) \\ 65897 &:= (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) - (9 + T(7))) \\ 65898 &:= (((-(6 + 5)) \times T(T(8))) \times (-9)) - T(8)) \\ 65913 &:= (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T((9 - 1)))) - T(T(3)) \\ 65916 &:= (-6) \times ((T((T(5) + T(9))) + 1) \times (-6)) \\ 65925 &:= ((-65) \times (-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(2)))) + T(5) \\ 65926 &:= (6 + ((5 - T(T(9))) \times (-2^6))) \\ 65928 &:= (-6) + ((T(T(5)) - T((9 - T(2)))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 65934 &:= (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T((9 + 3) - 4))) \\ 65944 &:= (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times T((9 \times 4))) + T(4) \\ 65952 &:= ((T(6) + T(5)) \times (T((T(9) + T(5))) + 2)) \\ 65955 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (-T(5)) + T((9 + T(5)))) + T(T(5))) \\ 65988 &:= ((T(T((6 + 5))) - T((-9) + T(8))) \times T(8)) \\ 65994 &:= (-6) + (((T(T(5)) + T(T(9))) + T(9)) \times T(T(4))) \\ 66066 &:= ((T(T(6)) + (T((60/6)))) \times T(T(6))) \\ 66088 &:= (((6 + T(60)) \times T(8)) - 8) \\ 66129 &:= (-T(T(6))) + (T(6) \times T((1 + T((T(2) + 9)))) \\ 66189 &:= -((T(T(6)) - ((T(6) - 1) \times T((T(8) + T(9)))))) \\ 66214 &:= (-6) + (((T(6) \times 2) + 1) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 66219 &:= (-T(6)) + (((T(6) \times T(2)) + 1) \times T(T(9))) \\ 66225 &:= (((T(66) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 5) \\ 66229 &:= ((T(T(6)) / (-T(6))) + ((2^{T(T(2))}) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 66234 &:= (-T(6)) \times (6 - T(-((2 - (3^4)))))) \\ 66239 &:= (-((6/6)) + ((2^{T(3)}) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 66240 &:= ((-6) \times T((T(6) + 2))) \times (-40) \\ 66241 &:= ((T(6) \times T(T((6 \times 2)))) + T(T(T((4 \times 1)))) \\ 66248 &:= ((T(6) - T(T(6)) / (-T(2))) \times (T(4) + T(T(8)))) \\ 66252 &:= ((6 + (T((T(6) + 2)) \times T(T(5)))) \times 2) \\ 66255 &:= (((T(66) \times 2) - (5)) \times T(5)) \\ 66276 &:= (-T(6)) + ((T(T(6)) + (2 \times T(7))) \times T(T(6))) \\ 66288 &:= ((6 + (T(T((6 + T(2)))) \times 8)) \times 8) \\ 66294 &:= (-6) \times (T(T(6)) + (T((2 + T(9))) \times (-T(4)))) \\ 66297 &:= (T(T(6)) \times ((-((6 - 2)) + T(9)) \times 7)) \\ 66324 &:= (-6) + (T(T((T(T(6)) / T(T(3)))) \times (T(2) \times T(4))) \\ 66330 &:= (T((T(6) + T((6 + 3)))) \times 30) \\ 66345 &:= (((T(66) \times 3) \times T(4)) + T(5)) \\ 66354 &:= (6 \times ((T(T((T(T(6)) / T(T(3)))) \times 5) + 4)) \\ 66355 &:= (((T(66) \times T(3)) + (5)) \times 5) \\ 66374 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(3))) \times 7) - T(T(T(4))) \\ 66375 &:= ((6 - T(T(6))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(7)) + T(T(5)))) \\ 66384 &:= ((6 \times 6) \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times 8) - 4)) \\ 66394 &:= (((6^6) + (3^9)) + T(T(4))) \\ 66399 &:= (-T(6)) + (((-T(6)) \times T(T(3))) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(9))) \\ 66420 &:= (T((T(6) + (6 \times T(4)))) \times 20) \\ 66423 &:= (((-T(T(6))) - T((T(6) + T(T(4)))) - T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(3)))) \\ 66424 &:= ((-T((6 \times 6))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)))) \\ 66435 &:= (((6 \times T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) + (T(T(3)))) \times 5) \\ 66444 &:= (-T(6)) \times (((T(6) \times (-4)) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 66456 &:= (T(((T(6) \times 6) - T(T(4)))) \times (5 + T(6))) \\ 66457 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(4)))) + (-T(5)) + T(T(7))) \\ 66465 &:= (((T(6) \times T(6)) \times T(4)) + T(6)) \times T(5) \\ 66471 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)) - 1)) \\ 66472 &:= -((T((T(6) + T(6))) + (T(T(4)) \times (-T((7^2)))))) \\ 66474 &:= (-6) \times (T(6) + (-4) \times T(74)) \\ 66478 &:= ((-6) - T(T((6 + 4))) \times (-7 - T(8))) \\ 66492 &:= ((T(T(6)) + (64 \times T(T(9)))) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 66528 &:= (T(6) \times (6 \times 528)) \\ 66544 &:= (-6) + (((T(T(6)) \times 5) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 66549 &:= (-6) + ((-6) + T(54)) \times T(9)) \\ 66564 &:= ((T((T(6) + (6))) - T(T(5)))^{6-4}) \\ 66570 &:= ((T(T(6)) - (-6) \times T(T(5)))) \times 70) \\ 66594 &:= (-6) + (T((T(6) + T(5))) \times (T(9) + T(T(4)))) \\ 66612 &:= (-((T(T(6)) - T((T(6) + (61)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 66647 &:= (((T(6) \times T(T((6 + 6)))) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)))) \\ 66675 &:= (((T(6) \times T(T(6))) - T((T(6) + (7)))) \times T(5)) \\ 66693 &:= -((T(T(6)) - (66 \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(3)))))) \\ 66699 &:= ((-6) \times T(6)) + (T((6 \times 9)) \times T(9)) \\ 66717 &:= ((-T(6)) \times T(T(6))) + ((T(71) \times T(7))) \\ 66725 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T(6) \times 7)) + (2^{T(5)})) \\ 66738 &:= (-T(6)) + (T(T(6)) \times (T((T(7) - 3)) - T(8)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 66744 &:= (-6) \times ((6 + T(74)) \times (-4)) \\ 66753 &:= (-6) + (T(T(6)) \times ((T(T(7)) - T(T(5))) + 3)) \\ 66759 &:= (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(6)) + ((T(7) - T(5)) + T(9))) \\ 66765 &:= (((T(6) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(7))) + 6) \times T(5) \\ 66787 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (T((-6) + T(7))) + T(8))) + T(7) \\ 66789 &:= (((-6) + T(T(6))) - T(T(7))) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(9))) \\ 66795 &:= ((6 + 67) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(5)))) \\ 66797 &:= ((T((T(T(6) + 6)))/7) \times T(9)) - (T(7)) \\ 66801 &:= (T(6) \times (T(6) + T((80 - 1)))) \\ 66816 &:= (((6 \times 6) \times 8) \times (1 + T(T(6)))) \\ 66819 &:= (-6) + (T((6 \times (8 + 1))) \times T(9)) \\ 66822 &:= (T((T(6) + T(6))) \times ((T(8) \times 2) + 2)) \\ 66825 &:= ((T((6 + (6 \times 8))) \times T(2)) \times T(5)) \\ 66879 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times ((6 + T(8)) \times 7)) - T(T(9))) \\ 66885 &:= ((-6) + T((6 + 88))) \times T(5) \\ 66922 &:= ((-66) \times (-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(2)))) - 2 \\ 66924 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(6))) - T(9)) \times T((2 + T(4)))) \\ 66934 &:= ((66 \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(3)))) + T(4)) \\ 66939 &:= -(T(6) - ((T((6 \times 9)) + 3) \times T(9))) \\ 66945 &:= (((T(6) + 6) \times T(9)) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(5))) \\ 66947 &:= (((-6) + T(6)) \times T(94)) - T(7) \\ 66960 &:= (-6) \times ((T(T(6)) - T(9)) \times (-60)) \\ 66969 &:= ((66 \times (T(T(9)) - T(6))) + T(9)) \\ 66975 &:= (((T(T(6)) - (T(6) + T(9))) \times T(T(7))) - T(5)) \\ 66984 &:= ((-6) - (T((T(6) + 9)) \times T(8))) \times (-4) \\ 66999 &:= -(T(T(6)) - ((T((6 \times 9)) + 9) \times T(9))) \\ 67074 &:= (-T(6)) + (-T(70)) \times (T(7) - T(T(4))) \\ 67089 &:= (-6) + (T(70) \times (T(8) - 9)) \\ 67134 &:= (-T(6)) + (((T(T(7)) + 1) \times 3) \times T(T(4))) \\ 67144 &:= ((T(6) - (7^{1+4})) \times (-4)) \\ 67158 &:= (T(((6 + 7) - 1)) \times T((5 + T(8)))) \\ 67187 &:= (T(6) + (71 \times T((T(8) + 7)))) \\ 67210 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(7))) - T(2)) \times T(10)) \\ 67221 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(2)) \times T((T(2) + 1)))) \\ 67225 &:= (-T(T(6))) - (-T((T(7) + T(2)))) \times T((T(T(2))) - 5)) \\ 67228 &:= (((T(6) + T(7))^2) \times 28) \\ 67235 &:= (-T((6 + T(7))) \times ((T(T(T(2)))/3) - T(T(5)))) \\ 67242 &:= ((T(T(6)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(2))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 67248 &:= ((6 + (T(7) \times T(24))) \times 8) \\ 67252 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(7))^2) + T((T(5) + T(2)))) \\ 67254 &:= (-T(6)) + (T(T((7 + 2))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))) \\ 67255 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times T((2 \times 5))) - T(T(5))) \\ 67263 &:= (T(T(6)) + (T((T(7) \times 2)) \times (T(6) + T(T(3)))) \\ 67265 &:= (-((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7)))) + ((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6))^5)) \\ 67275 &:= ((T((6 \times 7)) - T(T(2))) \times 75) \\ 67277 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(7))^2) - (-7) \times T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 67284 &:= (-T(6)) \times (((T(T(7)) - T(T(2))) \times (-8)) - (4)) \\ 67296 &:= (((67 - 2) \times T(T(9))) + T(6)) \\ 67312 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((T(7) + T(T(T(3))))^{1 \times 2})) \\ 67314 &:= (-6) + ((T((T(7) + T(T(3)))) - 1) \times T(T(4))) \\ 67315 &:= ((T((T(T(6))/7)) \times T(T((T(3) - 1)))) - 5) \\ 67335 &:= ((67^{T(3)/3}) \times T(5)) \\ 67344 &:= (-T(6)) + ((T((T(7) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4))) - T(4)) \\ 67347 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times T((T(3) + 4))) - T(7)) \\ 67353 &:= ((6 + 7) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(T(3)))))) \\ 67354 &:= (-T(6)) + (T((7^{-3+5})) \times T(T(4))) \\ 67359 &:= (-6) - (((7 \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(5)))) \times (-T(9))) \\ 67368 &:= (((-6) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(3))) + (T(6)) \times 8) \\ 67372 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times T((3 + 7))) - T(2)) \\ 67374 &:= (((-6) + T(T(7))) - T(3)) \times T((T(7) - T(4))) \\ 67375 &:= (T((T(6) + T(7))) \times T((-3) + T(7)) - T(5)) \\ 67389 &:= (-T(6)) \times (((T(T(7)) - T(3)) \times (-8)) - 9) \\ 67419 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times T(T(4))) + (-1) + T(9)) \\ 67424 &:= (((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(2))) + T(T(4))) \\ 67425 &:= (-6) + (T((T(7) + T(4))) \times T((-2) + T(5))) \\ 67428 &:= (((6 + T(7)) \times T(T(4))) + T(2)) \times T(8) \\ 67429 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(2)) \times 9)) \\ 67431 &:= (T((6 + 7)) \times T((T(4) + T((T(3) + 1)))) \\ 67437 &:= (6 + (T((T(7) + T(4))) \times T((T(3) + 7)))) \\ 67441 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times T(T(4))) + T((T(4) + 1))) \\ 67442 &:= (67 + (T(T(4)) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))))) \\ 67445 &:= (((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(4))) + T(5)) \\ 67452 &:= (T(T(6)) \times (((T(7) \times T(4)) + T(5)) - T(2))) \\ 67453 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times T(T(4))) + T((T(5) - 3))) \\ 67456 &:= (T((T(T(T(6)/7))) + T(4)) \times T((-5) + T(6))) \\ 67465 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times T(T(4))) - (-6) \times T(5)) \\ 67473 &:= ((-T(6)) \times T((7 + T(4)))) \times (-7 \times 3) \\ 67479 &:= -(T((T(T(6))/7)) - ((T(T(T(4))) - T(7)) \times T(9))) \\ 67483 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times T(T(4))) - (T(8) \times (-3))) \\ 67486 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times T(T(4))) - (T(T(8))/(-6))) \\ 67487 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(7))^{T(4)-8}) + T(T(7))) \\ 67488 &:= ((-T(6)) \times (T(7) - T((T(4) \times 8)))) + T(8) \\ 67494 &:= (-T(6)) \times (((T(T(7)) - T(T(4))) \times (-9)) - T(T(4))) \\ 67495 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(7))) \times (T(4) + T(9))) + T(T(5))) \\ 67499 &:= ((T(T(6)) - 7) + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(9)) \times T(9))) \\ 67521 &:= (((T(6) + T(7)) \times T(52)) - 1) \\ 67522 &:= (((T(6) \times 7) \times T(52))/T(2)) \\ 67536 &:= ((6 \times T(7)) \times (T((T(5) + 3)) + T(T(6)))) \\ 67543 &:= (((T(6) + 7^5) \times 4) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 67551 &:= (T(T(6)) + (T((T(7) + 5)) \times T(T((5 \times 1)))) \\ 67556 &:= ((T((T(T(6))/7)) \times T(T(5))) + (5 + T(T(6)))) \\ 67573 &:= ((T((T(T(6))/7)) \times T(T(5))) + T((T(7) - T(3)))) \\ 67578 &:= (-T(6)) \times (-T(7)) + (-5) \times (-T(7) + T(T(8)))) \\ 67579 &:= (((T(6) + T(7)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 67596 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times (-7)) + T(T(5))) \times (-T(9))) + T(T(6))) \\ 67599 &:= (-T(6)) + (T(7) \times T(((T(5) + 9) + T(9)))) \\ 67620 &:= ((T(T(6)) + (T((7 + 6)))) \times T(20)) \\ 67626 &:= (6 + (T(7) \times T(((T(6) \times T(2)) + (6)))) \\ 67627 &:= (((-6) + T(T(7))) + (T(6)^{T(2)})) \times 7 \\ 67635 &:= ((T(T(6)) + T((-T(7)) + T((T(6) - T(3)))))) \times T(5)) \\ 67646 &:= ((67 + T(T(6))) \times (-4) + T(T(6))) \\ 67662 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times (-7)) + (6)) \times (T(6) \times (-2))) \\ 67683 &:= (T(T(6)) \times (-((T(7) - T(6)) - T((8 \times 3)))) \\ 67694 &:= ((-6) + T(7)) \times (T(T((T(6) - 9))) - 4) \\ 67722 &:= (-6) \times ((-T(7)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(2))) - T(2)) \\ 67725 &:= ((T((6 \times 7)) \times (7 - 2)) \times T(5)) \\ 67743 &:= (((6 \times T(T(7))) \times T(7)) - T((T(4) \times 3))) \\ 67745 &:= (((T(T(6) + T(7))) + (7)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(5))) \\ 67746 &:= (((T(6) \times 7) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(6))) \\ 67747 &:= (((6 \times T(T(7))) \times T(7)) - T(T(4))) - T(T(7))) \\ 67749 &:= -(T((T(T(6))/7) - (T((7 + 4)) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 67754 &:= (-6) + (((7 \times 7) - 5) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 67767 &:= (-T(6)) \times ((-T(77)) - T(T(6))) + (7)) \\ 67781 &:= (((-6) + T(7)) \times T(78)) - 1) \\ 67782 &:= ((-6) + T(7)) \times T(T((T(7) - ((8 \times 2)))) \\ 67788 &:= (-T(6)) \times (((-7) + T(T(7))) \times (-8)) - T(8)) \\ 67789 &:= ((T(67) \times T(7)) + T(89)) \\ 67795 &:= (-((T(T(6)) - T(T(7)))) + (T(7) \times T((T(T(9))/T(5)))) \\ 67802 &:= (-((T(T(6)) + (7))) - (-T(80)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 67815 &:= ((T((T(6) + T(7))) + 8) \times T(T(-((1 - 5)))) \\ 67823 &:= (T(6) + (-T(T(7))) \times ((8^2) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 67831 &:= (T(T(6)) + (((T(T(7)) - T(T(8))))^{3-1})) \\ 67845 &:= (((T(6) + T(T(7))) + (8^4)) \times T(5)) \\ 67848 &:= (((-T(6)) \times T(T(7))) \times (-8)) - ((T(4) \times T(8))) \\ 67851 &:= (T(T(6)) + (T(7) \times T((-T(8)) + T((T(5) - 1)))) \\ 67869 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (7 \times (T(8) + (6)))) - T(9)) \\ 67872 &:= (((6 + T(T(7))) - 8) \times T(7)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 67893 &:= ((T(6) + T(T(7))) \times (T((8 + 9)) + T(3))) \\ 67896 &:= ((-6) - (-7 \times T(8))) \times (T(9) + T(T(6))) \\ 67914 &:= (T(T(6)) \times (7 \times (T(9) + ((1 - 4)))) \\ 67924 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (7 \times (T(9) - T(2)))) + T(4)) \\ 67925 &:= ((T(6) - T(T(7))) + (T(T(9)) \times T((T(T(2)) + (5)))) \\ 67929 &:= ((-67) \times (-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(2)))) - 9) \\ 67932 &:= (((T(6) \times 7) - T(9)) \times T((T(3)^2)) \\ 67934 &:= ((67 \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(3)))) - (4)) \\ 67938 &:= (6 + ((T(T(7)) - T(T(9))) \times (-3) \times T(8))) \\ 67943 &:= ((-6) - T(T(7))) + (T(9) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(3)))) \\ 67956 &:= ((T(6) \times T(79)) + T(56)) \\ 67968 &:= (((T(6) \times T(T(7))) - (9 + T(6))) \times 8) \\ 67977 &:= (T(6) \times (T(79) + 77)) \\ 68012 &:= ((T(6) \times T(80)) - T((1 + T(T(2)))) \\ 68013 &:= ((T(6) \times (T(80) - 1)) - T(3)) \\ 68019 &:= (T(6) \times (T(80) - (1^9))) \\ 68020 &:= ((T(6) \times T(80)) - (20)) \\ 68022 &:= ((T(6) \times T(80)) - (T(2) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 68024 &:= ((T(6) \times T(80)) - ((2^4))) \\ 68025 &:= ((T(6) \times T(80)) - (T(2) \times 5)) \\ 68027 &:= (((T(6) \times T(80)) - T(T(2))) - (7)) \\ 68029 &:= ((T(6) \times T(80)) - (2 + 9)) \\ 68032 &:= (((T(6) \times T(80)) - T(3)) - 2) \\ 68033 &:= ((T(6) \times T(80)) - (T(T(3))/3)) \\ 68034 &:= ((T(6) \times T(80)) - T(T((T(3) - (4)))) \\ 68037 &:= ((T(6) \times T(80)) - (T(T(3))/7)) \\ 68038 &:= (((T(6) \times T(80)) + T(3)) - 8) \\ 68052 &:= (((T(6) \times T(80)) + T(5)) - T(2)) \\ 68055 &:= ((T(6) \times (T(80) - (5))) + T(T(5))) \\ 68056 &:= (((T(6) \times T(80)) - (5)) + T(6)) \\ 68061 &:= ((T(6) \times T(80)) + T((6 \times 1))) \\ 68064 &:= ((T(6) \times T(80)) + ((6 \times 4))) \\ 68075 &:= ((T(6) \times T(80)) + (7 \times 5)) \\ 68082 &:= (((T(6) \times T(80)) + T(8)) + T(T(2))) \\ 68095 &:= ((T(6) \times T(80)) + T(T((9 - 5)))) \\ 68103 &:= (T(6) \times (T((8 \times 10)) + 3)) \\ 68124 &:= (T(6) \times (T((8 \times T((1 + T(2)))) + 4)) \\ 68145 &:= (T(T(6)) \times ((T((8 - 1)) \times T(4)) + T(5))) \\ 68148 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times 8) + T((-1) + T(4))) \times T(8)) \\ 68166 &:= (T(6) \times (T(T((8 + 1))) + T(66))) \\ 68172 &:= (-6) \times ((T(T((8 - 1))) \times (-T(7))) + T(T(2))) \\ 68187 &:= (T(T(T(-((6 - 8)))) \times (-1) + (8 \times T(T(7)))) \\ 68197 &:= (6 + (T((T(8) + 1)) \times 97)) \\ 68208 &:= ((T(6) \times 8) \times T((20 + 8))) \\ 68219 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T((8 \times T(2)))) - T((1 + T(9)))) \\ 68223 &:= (((T(6) + T(8))^2) \times T(T(T(2))) - T(3)) \\ 68229 &:= (T(6) \times (T((82 - 2)) + 9)) \\ 68232 &:= (((T(6) + T(8))^2) \times T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\ 68235 &:= (-T(6)) + (T(8) \times (T((T(2) \times T(3)))) - (T(T(5)))) \\ 68238 &:= ((T(T(6)) - 8) \times (T(T(2)) + T((3 \times 8)))) \\ 68262 &:= ((T(T(6)) + (T(T(8)) \times (-2))) \times (-62)) \\ 68265 &:= (((T(T(6)) + ((8^2))) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(5))) \\ 68271 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((8 \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(7)) - 1))) \\ 68278 &:= (6 - (8 \times ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(7)))) - 8)) \\ 68284 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times (-8)) - T(T(2))) \times (-T(8))) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 68289 &:= (-T(6)) + (T((8 + T(2))) \times T((T(8) + 9))) \\ 68292 &:= (-6) \times (((-8) - T(2)) \times T(T(9))) + T(2)) \\ 68294 &:= (-6) + ((T((8 + T(2))) \times T(T(9))) - T(4)) \\ 68295 &:= (((68 - 2) \times T(T(9))) - (T(5))) \\ 68297 &:= (-6) + ((T((8 + T(2))) \times T(T(9))) - (7)) \\ 68327 &:= ((-((T(T(6)) - T(83))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(7))) \end{aligned}$$

- 68328** := $((T(6) + (8 - 3)) \times T((2 \times T(8))))$
68339 := $((T(6) + 8) + (T((T(T(T(3))))/T(T(3)))) \times T(T(9)))$
68344 := $((T(T(6) + 8) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)))) - T(4))$
68347 := $((T(T(6) + 8) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)))) - 7)$
68349 := $((-6) + ((-T((T(8)/T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(9))$
68352 := $((T(T(6) + T(8)) \times ((T(T(3)) - (5))^2))$
68354 := $((T(T(6) + 8) \times (T((T(3) + T(5))) + T(T(4))))$
68355 := $(T(6) \times (((T(8) \times T(3)) \times T(5)) + T(5)))$
68373 := $((T(T(6)) \times (8 \times 37)) - 3)$
68375 := $(T(6) - ((8 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(7)) - T(T(5))))))$
68376 := $(T(T(6)) \times (8 \times ((3 + T(7)) + (6))))$
68382 := $((T(T(6) \times T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 8) + T(T(2))$
68384 := $((-6) + (T(T(8)) \times T((T(3) + 8)))) - T(T(T(4)))$
68394 := $((-T((6 + T(8))) + 3) - (-T(9) \times T(T(T(4))))$
68397 := $((-T(T(6)) + (T(83) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(7))))$
68415 := $((T((T((6 + 8)) - T(4))) + 1) \times T(5))$
68418 := $((T(T(6)) + (T(84))) \times 18)$
68434 := $((-6) - (-((T(8) + 4)) \times T((3 + T(T(4))))))$
68439 := $((-T(T(6))) - (((-8) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(3)) \times (-T(9)))$
68440 := $(T(((6 \times 8) + T(4))) \times 40)$
68442 := $((-6) + T((-8) + T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))$
68445 := $((T(T(6)) - T(8)) \times T(((-4) + T(4)) + (5)))$
68448 := $((T(T(6)) \times 8) - (-((T(4) \times T(4)) \times T(T(8))))$
68453 := $((-((T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(T(T(4))))/(-5)) - T(T(T(3))))$
68467 := $((T(6) \times T((8 \times T(4)))) + (T(6))) + T(T(7))$
68475 := $((T((6 + T(8))) + T(4)) \times 75)$
68476 := $((T(T(6)) + T(T(8))) + (4)) \times 76)$
68494 := $((-T(68)) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (9 - T(T(4))))$
68499 := $((T(T(6)) - (T((T(8) + 4)) \times (-9))) \times 9)$
68535 := $((-6) + ((T(8) - 5) \times T(T((T(3) + 5))))$
68541 := $((T((-6) + T(8))/T(5)) \times T(T((T(4) + 1))))$
68544 := $(T(6) \times ((T((8 \times 5)) - 4) \times 4))$
68547 := $(6 + ((T(8) - 5) \times T(T((4 + 7))))$
68549 := $((T(T(6)) + 8) + (T((T(5) - 4)) \times T(T(9))))$
68552 := $((T(6) \times T(T(8))) \times 5) - (T(52))$
68562 := $(T(6) - (-((T(8) - 5)) \times T(T((T(6))/T(T(T(2)))))))$
68565 := $((T(T(6)) - T(8)) \times T((5 + T(6)))) + T(T(5))$
68586 := $(T(T(6)) + ((T(T(8)) - (T(5))) \times T((8 + 6))))$
68589 := $((T(T(6)) - 8) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)) - 9$
68592 := $((-6) + (T(T(8)) \times (T((5 + 9)) - 2)))$
68595 := $(T(T(6)) - ((T(8) - (T(5) \times T(95))))$
68598 := $((6 - 8) + T((5 + 9))) \times T(T(8))$
68607 := $((T(T(6)) \times (-T(8))) \times T(T(6)))/(0 - T(7))$
68628 := $((T(6) \times (-86)) \times (-2 - T(8)))$
68634 := $(6 + (T((T(8) + 6)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(4))))$
68649 := $((-T(6)) + ((-((8 + 6)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(9))$
68655 := $(((-T(6)) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(6))) \times (-5) - T(T(5))$
68684 := $((-T(T(6)) - 8) \times ((T(T(6)) \times (-8)) + T(T(T(4))))$
68694 := $((-6) + ((T(T(8)) + (T(6))) \times (T(9) + T(T(4))))$
68712 := $((T(6) \times 8) \times (T(T(7)) + (1 + 2)))$
68733 := $((-T(6)) \times ((-T(8)) \times T((7 + T(3)))) + 3)$
68739 := $((T(6) \times 8) \times (T(T(7)) - 3) + T(T(9)))$
68742 := $((T(6) + T(8)) \times ((T(T(7)) - 4) \times T(2)))$
68769 := $((-6) \times T(T(8))) - ((-7) \times T(T(6))) \times T(9))$
68775 := $((T(6) \times T(T(8))) - T((-7) + T(7))) \times 5$
68793 := $((T(68) \times T(7)) + (T(T(9)) \times 3))$
68796 := $((T(6) - 8) \times T(7)) \times 9 \times T(6)$
68802 := $(T(6) \times (T(8) + T(80))) + T(T(2))$
68829 := $((-T(6)) + ((T(T(8)) - (T(8) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \times (-9))$
68832 := $((T(T(6)) + 8) \times (8 \times (T(3)^2)))$
68838 := $((6 + T((8 \times 8))) \times (-3 + T(8)))$
68848 := $((T(6) - 8) \times ((T(T(8)) - 4) \times 8))$
68849 := $((T((6 + 8)) \times T(T(8))) - T((T(T(4)) - 9)))$
68853 := $((-68) + ((T(8) + 5)^3))$
68859 := $((6 \times T(T(8))) + (T(85))) \times 9$
68880 := $((T(T(6)) + T(T(8))) - T(8)) \times 80$
68892 := $((T((6 + 8)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(9))) - T(2)$
68894 := $((-T(T(6 + (8/8)))) - (-T(9) \times T(T(T(4))))$
68895 := $((T((6 + 8)) \times T(T(8))) - T((9 \times 5)))$
68910 := $((-T(6)) - ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(9)))/(-10)))$
68919 := $((-T(6)) - ((8 - T(T(9 + 1))) \times T(9)))$
68922 := $((-T(6) \times ((T(8) - T(9^2))) + T(2)))$
68925 := $((-6) + ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(9)))/(2 \times 5)))$
68928 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(8)) + T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) \times 8$
68929 := $((-T(6)) - T(T(8))) \times T((T(9) - T(2)))/(-9)$
68931 := $((T(6) \times T(T(8))) \times T(T(9)))/T((T(T(3)) - 1))$
68934 := $((-6) \times T(T(8))) + (T((T(9) + T(3))) \times T(T(4)))$
68937 := $(6 + ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(9)))/(3 + 7))$
68942 := $(T(6) + ((T(8) + ((9 - 4))^{T(2)}))$
68943 := $(6 + (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(9)))/T(4)) + (T(3))))$
68946 := $((-6) + (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(9)))/T(4)) + (T(6))))$
68949 := $((T(6) \times T(T(8))) \times 9) - (T(T(4)) \times T(T(9)))$
68952 := $(T(((6 + T(8)) + 9)) \times 52)$
68957 := $((-T(6)) \times ((T(T(8)) - 9) \times (-5))) - T(7)$
68979 := $((-6) + ((T(T(T((T(8)/9)))) - 7) \times T(9))$
68982 := $((6 + T(T(8))) + (T(T(9)) \times T((8 + T(2))))$
68985 := $((-T(6)) \times ((-((T(8) - T(9))) - T(T(8))) \times 5))$
68997 := $((-6) + (T((8 + 9)) \times (T(9) + T(T(7))))$
69024 := $((-6) + (T(9) \times ((0 - T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4))))))$
69054 := $((-T(6)) + (T(9) \times ((0 - 5) + T(T(T(4))))))$
69114 := $((-T(T(6)) - (T(T(9)) \times (1 + T((1 + T(4))))))$
69124 := $((T(-((T(6) - T(9))) - 1) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4))))$
69132 := $((-T(6)) \times (-T((T(9) + 1))) - T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2))))))$
69144 := $((-T(6)) + (T(9) \times ((1 + T(T(T(4)))) - 4))$

- 69152 := (T(T(6)) + ((T(9) + ((1 - 5)))^{T(2)}))
69168 := (-6) × ((T(T(9)) + T(T((1 + 6)))) × (-8))
69174 := ((6 + T((9 + 1))) × (-T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4))))
69178 := (-6) + (T((T(9) + 1)) × (T(7) + T(8)))
69195 := ((T(6) - (9 × T(T((1 + 9)))) × (-5))
69204 := (-T(T(6))) + (T(9) × (T(2) + T(T(T(04))))))
69216 := ((T(T(6)) + T((T(9) × 2))) × 16)
69222 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - T((2 × T(T(2))))
69223 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - (T(T(T(T(2))))/3))
69224 := (-T(6)) + ((T(9) × T(T(T(2 + 2)))) - (T(T(4))))
69225 := ((T(T(6)) - (9 × 2)) × T(25))
69228 := (((T(T(6)) - T(9))²) × 2) + T(8)
69229 := ((T(6) × T((9²))) - (2⁹))
69231 := (T(6) + (T(9) × (-2) + T(T(T((3 + 1))))))
69234 := (-T(T(6))) + (((T(T(9)) - T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))) × T(T(4)))
69237 := (((T(T(6) + 9)) + T(T(2))) × T(T(3))) × 7)
69242 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - (T(T(4)) + T(2)))
69244 := (-T(6)) - ((T(9) × (2 - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(4))))
69246 := (-((6 × 9)) - (-T(24)) × T(T(6)))
69249 := ((-6) + T(9)) + ((-2) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(9))
69250 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - (50))
69257 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - (T(5) + T(7)))
69258 := (T(6) × ((T(9²)) - T(5)) - 8)
69261 := (6 + (T(9) × (T(T(T(-((2 - 6)))) - 1)))
69264 := ((T(T(6)) - 9) × (T((2 × 6)) × 4))
69267 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - (T(T(6))/7))
69271 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - (T(7) + 1))
69272 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - (7 + T(T(T(2))))
69273 := (-T(6)) + ((T(9) × T(T((T(2) + (7)))) - T(3)))
69276 := ((T(T(6)) + T(9)) × (-2) + T((T(7) - (6))))
69279 := (-T(6)) + (T(9) × T(((T(2) + (7)) + T(9))))
69282 := (-T(6)) + ((T(9) × T(T((2 + 8)))) + T(2))
69284 := (-6) + ((T(9) × T(T((2 + 8)))) - T(4))
69285 := ((T(T(6)) × T(((9/T(2)) × 8))) - (T(5)))
69286 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - (8 + 6))
69287 := (-6) + ((T(9) × T(T((2 + 8)))) - (7))
69288 := ((T(6) + ((9 + T(T(T(2)))) × T(8))) × 8)
69291 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - (9 × 1))
69294 := (-6) + (T(9) × T(T((2 × (9 - 4))))))
69295 := ((T(T(6)) × T(((T(9)/T(2)) + 9))) - (5))
69297 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - T((9 - 7)))
69299 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - (9/9))
69405 := ((-T(6)) - (9 × T(T(T(4)))) × (0 - 5))
69410 := (((T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) - (4)) × T(10))
69411 := (T(6) + (T(9) × (T(T(T(4))) + (1 + 1))))
69414 := (-6) + ((T(9) × T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T((1 + 4))))))
69415 := (-T(6)) + ((T(9) × T(T(T(4)))) + T((1 + T(5))))
69420 := (((T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) × T(T(4))) - (T(20)))
69423 := (-6) - ((-T(9)) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(2))) + T(3))
69424 := (-T(6)) - ((-T(9)) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(2))) - T(4))
69426 := (T((T(6) + (9 × 4))) × (2 × T(6)))
69427 := (((T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) × T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7)))
69429 := (-6) + ((T((T(9) + T(4))) + T(2)) × T(9))
69432 := (6 + ((T(9) × T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(T(3)) × T(T(2))))))
69434 := ((T(T(6)) × T(9)) - ((T(4) - (3^{T(4)})))
69435 := (((T(T(6) + 9)) × T(4)) - T(T(3))) × T(5))
69441 := (T(6) + ((T(9) × T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T((4 + 1))))))
69442 := (6 - ((-T(9)) × T(T(T(4)))) - T((4²)))
69445 := (T((-6) + T((9 + 4))) × (4 + T(5)))
69447 := (T(6) + (T(((T(9) × 4)/T(4))) × T(T(7))))
69453 := (T(T(6)) + ((T(9) × T(T(T(4)))) - T((T(5) - 3)))
69454 := (((-6) + T(T(9))) × T((-4) + T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))
69459 := (-T(6)) + (((-9) - T(T(T(4)))) + 5) × (-T(9))
69462 := ((6 + T(9)) × ((-4) + T(6))) × T(T(2))
69465 := ((T((6 + T(9))) × T(T(4))) - (T(T(6)) × T(5)))
69468 := (-T(6)) × (((-T(9)) × T(T(T(4))))/T(6)) - 8)
69472 := (-T(T(6))) - ((-T(9)) × T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(7)) - T(2)))
69474 := (-6) + (T(9) × ((T(T(4)) × T(7)) + (4)))
69477 := ((6 + T(9)) + (T(-((T(4) - T(7)))) × T(T(7))))
69479 := (T(T(6)) + ((T(9) × T(T(T(4)))) - (7 + T(9))))
69483 := ((6 - T((T(9) + (4)))) × (-T(8)) - T(T(3)))
69484 := (T(T(6)) + ((T(9) × T(T(T(4)))) - (-8) + T(T(4))))
69489 := ((T(6) × 9) + (T(T(T(4))) × (T(8) + 9)))
69492 := (T(T(6)) + ((T(9) × T(T(T(4)))) - (T(9) - T(T(2))))
69495 := (((T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) × T(T(4))) - (9 × T(5)))
69498 := (-((T(6) + T(9))) × ((-T(4)) - T(T(9))) - 8)
69504 := (-T(6)) + (T(9) × (5 + T(T(T(04))))))
69519 := (-6) + (T(9) × (5 + T(T((1 + 9))))))
69524 := ((T(6) × (9 + (T(5)^{T(2)}))) - T(T(T(4))))
69525 := ((T((T(T(6)) - (9 × T(5)))) - T(T(T(2)))) × T(5))
69531 := (T(T(6)) × (T((9 + (5 × 3))) + 1))
69534 := (-6) + ((T(T(9)) - T(T(5))) × (T(T(3)) + T(T(4))))
69543 := (T(6) - ((T(9) × (-5) - T(T(T(4)))) + 3))
69546 := (T(6) + (T(9) × (5 + T(T((4 + 6))))))
69547 := (-6) + ((T(9) × (5 + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(7))))
69549 := (-T(6)) - (((-9) + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) × (-T(9))
69552 := ((T(T(6)) + ((T(9) × T(55)))) + T(T(T(2))))
69558 := ((T(T(6)) × (T(95)/T(5))) - T(T(8)))
69564 := -((T(T(6)) - ((T((T(9) + (5))) - (6)) × T(T(4))))
69573 := ((T(T(6)) + (T((T(9) - (5))) × T(7))) × 3)
69575 := (((6 × T(9)) + (5)) × T((7 + T(5))))
69588 := ((T(T(6)) × T((9 + T(5)))) - (-8) × T(8))
69594 := ((T(6) × (9 + 5)) - (-T(9)) × T(T(T(4))))
69597 := ((-6) + T((9 + 5))) × T((9 + T(7)))

$$\begin{aligned} 69615 &:= (-T(6) \times ((-9) + T(T(6))) - 1) \times (-T(5))) \\ 69621 &:= (T(6) - (-T((T(9) - T(6)))) \times (T(T(T(2)))) + 1)) \\ 69624 &:= (-6) + ((T(T(9)) + T(T(6))) \times T((T(2)) + (4))) \\ 69625 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) + (T(25))) \\ 69642 &:= (6 + (((T(T(9)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(2)))) \\ 69645 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) \times T((6 + 4))) + (T(5))) \\ 69651 &:= (T(6) + ((T(T(9)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T((5 - 1)))) \\ 69654 &:= ((-6) + T(9)) \times ((T(T(6)) + (T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 69657 &:= (T(T(6)) + (T((9 - 6) + T(5))) \times T(T(7))) \\ 69678 &:= (T(6) \times (T(T(9)) + ((T(T(6)) \times 7) + T(T(8)))) \\ 69687 &:= ((T(6) + T((T(9) - 6))) \times 87) \\ 69693 &:= (((T(6) + T(T(9))) \times (T(6) + T(9))) - 3) \\ 69696 &:= ((T(6) + T(T(9))) \times T(((T(6) + T(9))/6))) \\ 69697 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))) - 9) + T(T(7))) \\ 69726 &:= (T(-((T(6) - T(9)))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T((T(2) \times 6)))) \\ 69727 &:= (T(6) - ((-T(9)) \times T(T((7 + T(2)))) - (T(T(7)))) \\ 69732 &:= (((6 \times T(9)) + T(7)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2))) \\ 69734 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times 9) - T(7)) \times 34) \\ 69735 &:= ((T(6) \times T(T(9))) + ((T(T(7)) - (T(3))) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 69741 &:= (T(6) \times T((9^{7-4-1})) \\ 69744 &:= (-6) + (T(9) \times ((T(7) \times T(T(4))) + T(4))) \\ 69747 &:= ((-6) - T(T(9))) \times (-74 - 7)) \\ 69756 &:= ((T(T(6)) - T(T(9))) + ((T(7) \times T(T(5))) \times T(6))) \\ 69762 &:= (T(T(6)) \times ((9 - 7) + T((T(6) + T(2)))) \\ 69765 &:= ((T(69) \times T(7)) + T(65)) \\ 69768 &:= (((69 \times T(7)) + (6)) \times T(8)) \\ 69776 &:= ((T(T(6)) + (T(97))) \times (-7) + T(6)) \\ 69783 &:= (-T(6)) \times (((9 + T(T(7))) \times (-8)) - 3) \\ 69789 &:= (-6) - ((T(9) - T((7 \times 8))) \times T(9)) \\ 69795 &:= (T((6 \times 9)) \times ((7 + T(9)) - (5))) \\ 69822 &:= ((6 \times 9) \times ((T(8)^2) - T(2))) \\ 69825 &:= -((T(T(6)) + (9 \times (-8) - (T(T(2))^5))) \\ 69828 &:= ((T(T(6)) + T(9)) \times T(((8 + T(T(2))) + 8)) \\ 69834 &:= (-6) - (T(9) \times ((T(8)/(-3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 69846 &:= (T(6) + ((T((T(9) + T(8))) + (4)) \times T(6))) \\ 69849 &:= ((T(6) \times 9) - ((8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(9)))) \\ 69852 &:= ((T(6) \times (T((T(9) + T(8))) + (5))) + T(T(2))) \\ 69855 &:= ((T(((T(6) - 9) \times 8)) \times T(5)) + (T(5))) \\ 69858 &:= (6 \times (T(T(9)) + (8 \times T((T(5) + T(8)))) \\ 69861 &:= ((T(6) \times T((T(9) + T(8)))) + T(T((6 - 1)))) \\ 69864 &:= (-T(6)) + (T(9) \times ((-8) + T(6)) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 69867 &:= (T(6) \times (T((T(9) + T(8))) + T((T(6)/7))) \\ 69876 &:= (-((6 \times 9)) + (T(T(8)) \times T((-7) + T(6)))) \\ 69879 &:= ((T(6) \times (T((T(9) + T(8))) + (7))) - 9) \\ 69888 &:= (((-T(6)) - T(T(9))) - T(8)) \times (-8 \times 8)) \\ 69891 &:= (T(T(6)) - (T(9) \times (-8) - T(T(9 + 1)))) \\ 69925 &:= ((T(6) \times (9 + T(9^2))) - (5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69927 &:= (((T(6) + T(9)) \times T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(2)))) \times 7)) \\ 69942 &:= (T(T(6)) - ((T(9) \times (-9) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(2)))) \\ 69945 &:= ((T(6) \times (T((9 \times 9)) + (4))) + T(T(5))) \\ 69948 &:= ((T(T(6)) - T(T(9))) \times (-9) - T((4 + 8))) \\ 69951 &:= (T(6) \times (T((9 \times 9)) + T((5 - 1)))) \\ 69954 &:= -((T(T(-((6 - 9)))) + (T(9) \times (-T(5) - T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 69955 &:= (((T(6) \times T((T(9) - 9))) + (5)) \times 5) \\ 69958 &:= (((T(6) - T(T(9))) \times T(T(9)))/(-T(5))) - 8) \\ 69963 &:= ((69 \times (T(T(9)) - (T(6)))) - 3) \\ 69966 &:= (T(T(6)) + (((T((9 \times 9)) \times T(6)) - (6)))) \\ 69969 &:= -((T(T(6)) - ((T(9) + T(9)) \times T((-6) + T(9)))) \\ 69972 &:= (T(T(6)) - ((T((9 \times 9)) \times (-7)) \times T(2))) \\ 69978 &:= -((((T(T(6)) - (9 \times T(9))) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(8)))) \\ 69993 &:= (T(6) \times (T((9 \times 9)) + (9 + 3))) \\ 69994 &:= (((6^{T(9)/9}) \times 9) + T(4)) \\ 70224 &:= (T((70 + T(T(2)))) \times 24) \\ 70226 &:= (T((70 + T(2))) \times 26) \\ 70488 &:= ((T(7) - T(04)) \times T(88)) \\ 70735 &:= ((T(70) \times T(7)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times 5)) \\ 70756 &:= (T(7) \times (07 - (T(T(5)) \times (-T(6)))) \\ 70896 &:= ((7 \times 08) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(6)))) \\ 70910 &:= ((70 \times T(T(9))) - T(T(10))) \\ 70948 &:= (T(7) - ((0 - T(9)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(8)))) \\ 70965 &:= ((70 \times (T(T(9)) - (T(6)))) - (T(5))) \\ 71139 &:= (((T(7) \times 11) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 9) \\ 71148 &:= ((T(7) \times 11) \times T(T(T(T((4) - 8)))) \\ 71176 &:= (T(7) - ((-11) \times T(7)) \times T(T(6))) \\ 71225 &:= ((T(T(7)) + 1) \times (T(T((2 + 2))) + T(T(5)))) \\ 71244 &:= (-T((7 + 1))) + ((T(T(2))^4) \times T(T(4))) \\ 71246 &:= (T(T(7)) + (T(T(T((1 + T(2)))) \times 46)) \\ 71253 &:= ((T(7) + 1) \times ((-T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 71280 &:= ((T(7) - T((1 + 2))) \times T(80)) \\ 71282 &:= (-7) + ((T(T(T((1 + 2)))) + T(8))^2) \\ 71295 &:= (T(((T(7) + T(12)) - 9) \times T(5)) \\ 71340 &:= (((T(7) + 1) \times 3) \times T(40)) \\ 71344 &:= ((-((T(7) \times T(13))) \times T(T(T(4))))/(-T(T(4)))) \\ 71346 &:= (T(((7 + 1) + 3)) \times T(46)) \\ 71372 &:= (T(7) + (T(13) \times (T(7)^2))) \\ 71379 &:= (T(T((7 - 1))) \times (-T(3) - (7 \times T(9)))) \\ 71414 &:= (-T(T(7))) - (T((1 + T(T(4)))) \times (-T((-1) + T(4)))) \\ 71424 &:= ((T((7 + 1)) \times 4) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + T(4))) \\ 71426 &:= (71 \times ((T(4)^{T(2)}) + (6))) \\ 71427 &:= (-((T(7) + 1)) - ((-T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(7)))) \\ 71428 &:= (T(7) + (T(T((1 + 4))) \times T((-2) + T(8)))) \\ 71442 &:= (-T((T(7) - 1))) \times (-T((T(4) + T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 71448 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(T(-((1 - 4)))) - (T(T(4)))) - 8) \\ 71453 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times ((1 + T(T(4))) + T(T(5)))) - 3) \end{aligned}$$

- 71456** := $(T(T(7)) \times ((1 + T(4)) \times (-5) + T(6)))$
71457 := $((T(T(7)) + 1) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(7))))$
71462 := $((T(T(7)) \times ((-1) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(6)))) + T(T(2))$
71463 := $(T((T(7+1) + 46)) \times T(T(3)))$
71568 := $(T(7) \times T((1 + (5 \times (6 + 8))))$
71595 := $((T((T(7) + 1)) + T(T(5))) \times (9 + T(T(5))))$
71596 := $(T(7) \times (1 + T(((5 + T(9)) + T(6))))$
71632 := $((T(T(7)) + 1) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T((T(3) - 2))))$
71644 := $(-T(T(7))) + (((-1) + T(T(6))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
71657 := $((-T(7)) \times T(T((1 \times 6))) + (5^7))$
71679 := $((((T(7) + 1) \times 6) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(9)))$
71685 := $((T(T(7)) - 1) \times ((T(6) + T(8)) + T(T(5))))$
71694 := $(-T(T(7))) + (T((1 + 6)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(T(4))))$
71736 := $(T(7) \times ((T(T(1 \times 7))) + T(T(3))) \times 6)$
71774 := $((T(71) + 7) \times T(7)) + T(4)$
71778 := $((T(71) \times T(7)) + T((T(7) - 8)))$
71820 := $((T((T(7) - 1)) - T(8)) \times T(20))$
71827 := $(7 - (-T((1 + 8))) \times T((2 \times T(7))))$
71829 := $(-T(71)) + (T((T(8) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9)))$
71861 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(18) + 6)) - 1)$
71862 := $(T(T(7)) \times (T(18) + T((6/2))))$
71886 := $((7 - (18 \times T(T(8)))) \times (-6))$
71924 := $((71 \times T(T(9))) - T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))$
71925 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(-((1 - 9))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 5)$
71928 := $(-(((T(7) - 1) - (T(9)^2)) \times T(8)))$
71942 := $((71 \times T(T(9))) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(2)$
71955 := $((T((T(7) - 1)) + (T(T(9)) \times (-5))) \times (-T(5)))$
71974 := $(-T(T(7)) + ((-1) + T(T(9))) \times (-7 \times T(4)))$
72128 := $(-((T(7)^2) \times (-1 - T((T(T(2)) - 8))))$
72184 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(2) + T(18))) + T(T(T(4))))$
72198 := $(7 \times ((T(T(2) + 1)) \times T(T(9))) - T(8))$
72219 := $((T((T(7) \times T(2))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 19)$
72226 := $(T(T(7)) + (T((T(2)^{T(2)})) \times T((-2) + T(6))))$
72240 := $(T((7 \times T(T(2)))) \times (2 \times 40))$
72268 := $(T(T(7)) \times (T(2 + 2)) + (T(6) \times 8))$
72275 := $((T(T(7)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times ((2 + T(T(7))) + 5))$
72282 := $((T(7) \times T(T((2 \times T(T(2)))))) - (T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(2))))$
72288 := $((T(((7 \times T(2)) \times T(2)) - 8) \times T(8))$
72289 := $((T((T(7) - T(T(2))))^2) - (-8 \times T(T(9))))$
72303 := $((7^{T(2)} - 30) \times T(T(T(3))))$
72324 := $((T(7) \times T(2)) \times T((T(3^2)) - 4))$
72338 := $((-7 - T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(3 \times T(T(3)))) \times (-T(8)))$
72342 := $(-T(72)) + (T((T(T(3)) \times 4)) \times T(T(T(2))))$
72345 := $((T(7) - T(2 \times (-T(3)) + T(T(4)))) \times (-T(5)))$
72348 := $((T(7) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(3) \times T(4))) \times T(8))$
72349 := $((T((T(7) - T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4)))) - 9)$
72352 := $((-T((T(7) \times 2)) \times T((T(T(3)) - 5)))/(-T(2)))$
72353 := $(-T(T(7))) + (((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5)) - T(3))$
72356 := $(-(((T(T(7)) + T(2)) + ((T(T(3)) \times (-T(5))) \times T(T(6))))$
72359 := $(-((T(T(7)) - (T(2) \times T(T(3))) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(9))))$
72365 := $(-(((T(T(7)) - T(T(2))) + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(6))) \times (-T(5))))$
72377 := $((7 \times T(T(2)))^3 - T((T(7)/7))$
72379 := $((T(7)^2) \times T((T(3) + 7))) + T(T(9))$
72393 := $(-((T(T(7)) + T(2)) \times ((T(3) \times 9) - T(T(T(3))))$
72394 := $(-7 \times ((2^3) - (T(T(9)) \times T(4))))$
72416 := $(T((T(7) + T(2))) \times (T(4) + T(16)))$
72424 := $((T((T(7) - T(2))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4)$
72429 := $(-7 \times (T(2) + ((-4) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(9))))$
72432 := $(72 \times ((T(4)^3) + T(T(2))))$
72435 := $(T(T((7 + 2))) - (T((T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))) \times (-T(T(5))))$
72436 := $(-7 \times (2 - (T(4) \times T(T((3 + 6))))$
72448 := $((T(T(7)) \times (-2)) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(8))))$
72468 := $(-7 - (T((T(T(2)) + 4)) \times (-T(T(6)) - 8)))$
72478 := $(T(7) + (T(T(T(2))) \times (T((T(4) + T(7)) - T(8))))$
72482 := $(7 - (T((T(T(2)) + 4)) \times (8 - T(T(T(T(2))))$
72488 := $((T(7) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4))) \times T((8 + 8)))$
72491 := $((7 \times (T(T(2)) - (-T(4) \times T(T(9)))) - 1)$
72492 := $(T(7) \times ((T(2) \times T((-4) + T(9))) + T(T(2))))$
72499 := $(-7 \times (2 - ((T(4) \times T(T(9))) + 9))$
72512 := $(-((T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) \times (T(T((5 - 1))) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
72524 := $(-((T(T(7)) - (T((2 + T(5)) \times T(2))) \times T(T(4))))$
72525 := $((T((7 \times 2)) + (T(T(5))^2)) \times 5)$
72527 := $(T((7 + T(T(2)))) \times (-T(5) + (2 \times T(T(7))))$
72528 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(2)) + T((T(5) + T(2)))) + T(T(8)))$
72532 := $((-((T(T(7)) - (T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 2)$
72534 := $((-T(T(7))) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(5)))) - (-T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
72548 := $(-T(7)) + (T((T(2) + (T(5) \times 4)) \times T(8)))$
72549 := $((T(7) \times T(((T(2) + T(5)) \times 4)) - T(T(9)))$
72555 := $((7 + T(-((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(5)))))) - (T(T(5))) \times T(5))$
72557 := $(-T(T(7))) + (T(T((T(T(2)) + 5))) \times (5 + T(7)))$
72558 := $(T(72) + ((T(T(5)) - T(5)) \times T(T(8))))$
72562 := $((T(T(7)))/(-2) - ((-T(5)) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
72569 := $(-7 \times (T((2 + 5)) - (T(T(6)) \times T(9))))$
72576 := $(-7 \times (((T(T(2))^5) \times (-T(7)))/T(6)))$
72577 := $((T(7)^{T(2)} + (T(5)^{T(7)/7}))$
72582 := $((T((-T(7)) + T((-2) + T(5)))) \times T(8)) + T(T(2))$
72585 := $((T((T(7) - T(2))) \times T(5)) - T(8)) \times T(5)$
72618 := $(-7 \times (T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(6)) \times T((1 + 8))))$
72624 := $((T(T(7)) + 2) \times ((T(T(6)) + 2) - T(T(4))))$
72625 := $((-T(7)) + (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(6)) \times T(2)))) \times 5)$
72639 := $(7 \times ((T(2) \times (-6)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(9))))$
72644 := $(-((T(7) - 2) \times (T(T(6)) - (T(T(4)) \times T(T(4))))$

- 72645** := (((T(7) × T((T(2) × 6))) + T(T(4))) × T(5))
72648 := (((-7) + T((2⁶))) - T(T(4))) × T(8))
72653 := (-7) × ((T((2⁶))) × (-5) + T(T(3)))
72655 := (((7 - (T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(6)))) × (-T(5))) - 5)
72658 := (T(7) + T(T(2))) × (T(65) - 8))
72674 := ((T((T(7) - T(2))) × T(T(6))) - ((7⁴)))
72684 := ((T(T(7)) × (T((T(2) × 6) + 8) + T(4))
72688 := ((T((T(7) + T(T(2)))) + T(T(6))) × 88)
72695 := (-7) × ((-2) + (T(T(6) × 9)) × (-5))
72699 := ((-7) × (T(2) - (T(T(6) × T(9)))) - T(9))
72709 := ((T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) - ((70) × T(T(9)))
72723 := (7 × (-T(T(2))) + (T((7 + 2) × T(T(T(3))))))
72726 := ((T(7) + T(2)) × T(((T(T(7) + 2)/6)))
72732 := (T(((T(T(7)) × T(T(2)))/T(7))) × (T(T(3)) - 2))
72737 := (((7 × T((2 + 7))) × T(T(T(3)))) - (T(7)))
72739 := (-((T(7) - 2) - ((7 × T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(9))))
72744 := (-T(7)) × (T(T(T(2))) + ((T(T(7)) - (T(T(4) × T(T(4))))))
72758 := (-7) × ((2 - T(T(7))) - (T(5) × T(T(8))))
72762 := (((7 × T((2 + 7))) × T(T(6))) - T(2))
72764 := (T(T(7)) - (T(-((T(T(2)) - T(7)))) × (-T(T(6) + T(T(4))))))
72765 := ((T(((7 × 2) + 7) × T(6)) × T(5))
72768 := ((T(72) - (-T(7) × T(T(6)))) × 8)
72769 := ((7 - T(2)) - ((-7) × T(T(6))) × T(9))
72772 := ((T(T(7)) × (-2)) + ((T(7) × T(72))))
72779 := (-7) × (-2) - (T((-7) + T(7)) × T(9))
72785 := ((T((T(7) - T(2))) × (T(7) × 8) - (T(5)))
72786 := (((T(T(7)) - T(T(2))) × 7) + T(T(8))) × T(6))
72793 := (T(7) + ((T(T(T(2))) + (T(7))) × T((9 × T(3))))
72796 := ((T(7) + T(2)) - ((-7) × T(9)) × T(T(6)))
72800 := (T((7 + T(T(2)))) × 800)
72825 := (((T(T(7)) - 2) × (-T(8))) - T(T(T(2)))) × (-5)
72828 := ((7 + T((T(2) × T((8 - 2)))) × T(8))
72842 := -((T(T(7)) - (2 × ((T(T(8)) × T(T(4))) - T(T(2))))))
72844 := -((T(T(7)) - ((2 × T(T(8))) × T(T(4))) - T(4)))
72847 := (-7) + (((2 × T(T(8))) × T(T(4))) - T(T(7)))
72848 := (-T(T(7))) + (((T(T(2)) × 8) × T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(8))))
72849 := (7 × (T(T(T(2))) + (T(8) - (-T(4) × T(T(9))))))
72854 := -((T(T(7)) - ((T(T(2)) + T((T(8) + T(5)))) × T(T(4))))
72855 := ((T(T((7 + T(T(2)))))) + (T(T(8) + 5))) × T(5)
72856 := (T(7) × (T((2 × T(8))) - (5 + T(6))))
72857 := (-T(7)) + ((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(8)))) × (-T(T(5) - 7)))
72863 := -((T((7²)) - ((T(8) + 6)³))
72864 := ((T((7 + T(T(T(2)))) + 8) × (T(T(6)) - T(T(4))))
72880 := ((T((7 × T(T(2)))) + 8) × 80)
72881 := ((T(7) × T((2 × T(8)))) - T((T(8) + 1)))
72884 := (-T(7)) × (T(T(T(2))) - (T((T(8) + T(8))) - (4)))
72885 := ((T(((T(7)²)/8) + 8) × T(5))
72895 := (((T((7 + 2)) × T(8)) × T(9)) - 5)
72899 := ((-7) + T(T(2))) + ((T(8) × T(9)) × T(9))
72912 := ((T(7)²) × (91 + 2))
72918 := ((T(7) × T((2 × T((9 - 1)))) - T(T(8)))
72922 := (T(7) + (((T(T(2)) × T(9))²) - T(T(2))))
72923 := (-7) + (T((T(T(2)) + T(9))) × T(T((-2) + T(3))))
72924 := (T(7) + (((T(T(2)) × T(9))²) - (4)))
72925 := ((T((7 + T(2))) × T((T(9) + T(T(2)))) - 5)
72926 := (7 × ((T(T(T(2))) × T(9)) + (2 + T(6))))
72927 := (T((7 + T((2 + 9)))) × 27)
72928 := ((7 + T(T(T(2)))) + (((T(9)²) × T(8)))
72943 := ((T(T(7)) - T(2)) × (T(9) + T((T(4) + T(3))))
72945 := ((T(((7 × T(T(2))) + 9) × T(T(4))) + T(5))
72948 := ((T((T(7) × 2)) × T(9)) + T((T(T(4)) - 8)))
72949 := (T(7) + ((T((T(T(2)) + T(9))) × T(T(4))) - 9))
72953 := (-T(7)) + ((T(T(2)) + T(9)) × T(53))
72954 := ((T(T(7)) - (T(T(T(2))) × (-T(9)))) × 54)
72955 := (((-T(T(7))) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9))) × T(T(5)) - 5)
72960 := ((T((7²)) - 9) × 60)
72961 := (7 × ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(9)) + T((6 + 1))))
72963 := (((7 × T(T(2))) - 9) × T(T((T(T(6)))/T(T(3))))))
72964 := ((T(7) + T(T(2))) + (T((T(9) + 6))) × T(T(4)))
72967 := ((-T(7)) - (T(T((2 + 9))) × T(T(6))))/(-7)
72968 := (7 × (T(T(T(2))) + ((T(9) × T(T(6))) + 8)))
72975 := (((T(T(7)) × (T(2) + 9)) - 7) × T(5))
72988 := ((-T(7)) × (T(T(T(2))) - T((9 × 8))) - 8)
72990 := (((7 - T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9))) × 90)
72996 := ((T((7 + (2 × 9))) - 9) × T(T(6)))
73065 := ((T(T(7)) × (30 × 6)) - (T(5)))
73073 := (-7) + ((-30) × T(T(7))) × (-T(3))
73125 := ((-T(7)) + T((T(T(3)) + 1))) × T(25))
73185 := (((T(7) × 3) + 1) × T((T(8) + 5)))
73206 := (T((T(7) + T(T((T(3) - 2)))) × T(06))
73227 := ((T(T(7)) + T(T((T(3) × 2)))) × (T(2) × 7))
73233 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T((T(3) × 2)))) × T(T(3))) + T(3))
73234 := (T(7) + (T(T(3)) × T((2 + (3⁴))))
73245 := ((T(7) + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(T(2)))) + 4)) × T(5))
73248 := (T(7) × ((-3) + (T(T(2)) × T(T(4))) × 8))
73255 := ((T(T(7)) + T(T((3 × 2)))) × (T(T(5)) - 5))
73260 := (((T(T(7)) × (-3)) - T(2)) × (-60))
73264 := ((T(7) + T((T(T(3)) + 2))) × (T(T(6)) + T(4)))
73269 := (((T(T(7 + T(3)))) × 2) - T(T(6))) × 9)
73273 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T((T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))))) × T(7)) - 3)
73276 := ((T(T(7)) + T(T((T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))))) × (7 + T(6)))
73278 := (((T(T(7)) - T(T(T(3)))) + 2) × (T(T(7)) + 8))
73286 := (-T(T(7))) + (T((T(T(3)) + 2)) × (T(8) + T(T(6))))
73288 := (T(7) + (T(T((T(3) - 2))) × (T(T(8)) + T(T(8))))

- 73297** := ((T(7) + T(T(T(3)))) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(9) + (7))))
73332 := (((T(7) × T(T(3))) - (T(3))) × T(T(3))) × T(T(2)))
73345 := ((T(7) + ((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))⁴) × 5)
73346 := ((T(T(7)) - 3) × ((T(3) - T(T(4))) + T(T(6))))
73347 := (((7 × T(3))³) - T((T(4) + T(7))))
73348 := (T(7) - (T((-T(3) + T(T(3)))) × (T(T(4)) - T(T(8))))
73353 := ((T(7) - (T(T(3+3))) × (-T(5))) × T(T(3)))
73359 := (((-T(7) × T(T(3))) × (-3 - T(T(5)))) + T(T(9)))
73368 := (((T(7) - T(3)) + T(3 × T(6))) × T(8))
73369 := (T(T(7)) + (33 × T((T(6) + T(9))))
73374 := (-((T(7)³) - ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(7)))) - T(T(T(4))))
73388 := (T(7) × ((T(T(3)))/(-3)) + T((T(8) + T(8))))
73392 := ((T(7) - T(3)) × (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(9)) × T(2))))
73416 := (-T(7)) × (T(3) - T((T(T(4) + 1)) + (6))))
73428 := ((T(7) × T(3)) - ((T(T(4)) × (-2)) × T(T(8))))
73429 := ((7^{T(3)}) - (-T(T(4))) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9))))
73458 := ((-7) + T((T(T(3)) + (4)))) × T(-((T(5) - T(8))))
73472 := (T(7) × ((T(3) - T(4)) + T(72)))
73478 := (((T(7) + T((T(T(3)) - (4)))) × T(T(7))) - 8)
73482 := ((73 - (T(T(T(4))) × 8)) × (-T(T(2))))
73486 := (T(T(7)) × ((3 + T(4)) + (8 × T(6))))
73492 := ((T(T(7)) × (T((T(3) + T(4))) + T(9))) + T(T(2)))
73493 := (-((T(T(7)) + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) × (T(9) + 3)))
73500 := ((7 × T(T(3))) × 500)
73514 := (-T(T(7))) + (-((3 - 51) × T(T(T(4))))
73524 := (((T(T(7) + T(T(3)))) × T(5)) + T(T(2))) × 4)
73528 := (T(7) × ((3 - 5) + T((2 × T(8))))
73530 := (((T(T(7)) × T(3)) + (T(5))) × 30)
73536 := ((T(T(7)) × T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(5)³) × (-6)))
73538 := (-T(T(7))) + (T(T((-3) + T(5))) × (3 × 8))
73539 := ((T(7) × T((-3) + T(5)) × T(3))) - T(9)
73542 := ((7 + T(T(T(3)))) × (T((T(T(5))/T(4))) + T(T(T(T(2))))))
73545 := ((T(T(T(7) + T(3))) × T(T(5))) + T(-((T(T(4)) - T(T(5))))))
73548 := ((T(7) × T((3 + T(5)) × 4)) - T(8))
73549 := ((T(T(7)) - (T(T(T(3))) × (-T(5)))) × (T(4) + 9))
73563 := ((T(7) × T((T(3) + T(5 + 6)))) - T(T(3)))
73569 := -(((T(T(7)) + (-T(3)) × T(T(5))) × T(T(6))) - T(T(9)))
73574 := ((T(7) × T((T(3) × (5 + 7)))) - T(4))
73577 := ((T(7) × T((T(3) × (5 + 7)))) - (7))
73582 := ((T(7) × T((-3 - 5) × T(8))) - 2)
73584 := (T(7) × T((T(3) × (-5 - 8) × 4)))
73594 := ((T(7) × T((3 + 5) × 9)) + T(4))
73629 := ((T(7) × T((36 × 2))) + T(9))
73634 := (((T(T(T(7) - 3)) - (6)) × T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4))))
73644 := ((T(T(T(7) × 3)) × T(6)) - T((-4) + T(T(4))))
73647 := ((7 × 3) × (T(6) + T((T(T(4)) + T(7))))
73648 := (-((T(7) + T(3))) + (6 × T(T(T(4)))) × 8)
73655 := (-T((T(7) + T(3))) + (T((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) × T(5)))
73656 := ((T(7) + 3) × (T(65) + T(T(6))))
73668 := (T(7) × (3 + T(((6 × 6) + T(8))))
73675 := ((T(T(7)) - T(T(T(3)))) × (T((T(6) + (7))) + T(5)))
73682 := -((T(T(7)) - ((3 × (6 + 8))^{T(2)}))
73689 := ((-T(7) + T(T(T(3)))) × ((-6) - T(T(8))) + T(T(9)))
73695 := ((T(T(T(7) × 3)) × T(6)) - T((T(9) + (5))))
73697 := ((T(T(T(7) - 3)) × T(T(6))) - T((T(9) + (7))))
73725 := (((7 × T(37)) - T(T(2))) × T(5))
73728 := ((T(T(7)) - ((3 + T(T(7))) × T(T(2)))) × (-T(8)))
73748 := ((T(T(7)) + T(3)) × (T((T(7) - T(4)) + 8))
73749 := ((T(T(7)) - 3) × (-7) + T((T(4) + 9)))
73752 := (T(7) × (T(3) + T((75 - T(2))))
73763 := -((T(T(7) - 3)) - ((7 × 6)³))
73773 := (((T(73) + T(T(7))) + T(T(7))) × T(T(3)))
73794 := ((7 × T(T(3))) × (7 - (-9) × T(T(4))))
73812 := ((T((-7) + T(T(3))) × T((T(8) + 1))) - T(2))
73815 := ((7 × T((38 - 1))) × T(5))
73824 := (((T(7) × 3) - T(8)) × (-2) + T(T(T(4))))
73828 := ((T(T(7)) + ((T(3) + T(8))^{T(2)}) - T(T(8)))
73835 := (-T((7 + T(3))) + (T(T(8)) × (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(5))))))
73836 := ((-7) + T((3 × 8))) × (T(T(3)) + T(T(6)))
73842 := (((-7) - T(3)) - (-8) × T(T(T(4)))) × T(T(2))
73843 := ((T(7) + T(T(3))) × ((-T(8)) + T(T(T(4))) + 3))
73844 := (-T(T(7))) - (T(3) × ((-8) × T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(4))))
73853 := (-T(T(7))) + ((3 + T(T(8))) × (-T(T(5))) + T(T(T(3))))
73864 := (T(7) × (T((T(3) + 8) + (6))) + T(4))
73885 := ((-7) + (T(T(T(3))) × (8 × 8))) × 5)
73892 := (T(T(7)) × ((3 + 8) + T((9 × 2))))
73894 := (T(T(7)) - ((T(3) × 8) × (9 - T(T(T(4))))))
73895 := (-((T(7) + 3)) + (T(T(8)) × (-9) + T(T(5))))
73898 := (-T(7)) + ((-3) × T(T(8))) × (-T(9) - 8))
73913 := (-7) + ((3 + T(9)) × T(T(T(1 + 3))))
73934 := ((-7) + T(T(3))) + ((T(9) + 3) × T(T(T(4))))
73935 := (((T(7) × T(3)) - 9) × T((T(3) × 5)))
73942 := (T(7) - (((-3) - T(9)) × T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(2)))
73944 := (T(7) + (((3 + T(9)) × T(T(T(4)))) - 4))
73948 := (T(7) - ((-T(3)) × T((T(9) + T(4))) × 8))
73950 := (((7 + T(3)) + T(9)) × T(50))
73962 := (7 × ((T(T(T(3))) × T(9)) + T((T(6) - T(2))))
73975 := (7 - ((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(9))) × (-T(7) + T(T(5))))
73979 := -((T(T(7)) - (T(3 × (-9) + T(7))) × T(9)))
73982 := (-((T(T(7)) - 3)) + (T(9) × T((T(8) + T(T(T(2))))))
73983 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T(3 + 9))) + T(8)) × T(T(3)))
73984 := ((T(T(7)) × (T(T(T(3))) - T(9))) + (8 - T(T(T(4))))
73986 := ((T(7) - T((T(3) + T(9)))) × (-T(8) + T(6)))
73987 := (T(T(7)) - (3 - (T(9 × 8)) × T(7)))

- 73995** := (((T(T(7)) × 39) – T(T(9))) × 5)
74088 := (T(7) × ((T(T(4)) × T(08)) + T(T(8))))
74100 := (T((T(7) + T(4))) × 100)
74137 := ((–(T(7)) – T((T(4) – 1))) × (–(T(T(3)) + T(7))))
74145 := ((T((T(7) + T(T(4)) – 1)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(5))
74172 := (T(7) × (T(T((4 – 1))) + (T(72))))
74182 := ((T(T(7)) – (T(T(4)) × (–(1) – T(T(8)))) × 2)
74214 := ((T(7) + T(4)) × T(((T(T(2)) + 1) + T(T(4))))
74222 := (–(T(7)) – (–(T(T(4))) × ((T(T(T(2))) – T(T(2))) × T(T(2))))
74224 := ((T(T(7)) + ((T(T(4))²) × T(T(2)))) × 4)
74228 := (–(T(7)) × ((T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) × (–(T(2) + 8))))
74229 := (((T(7) × 4)²) × T(T(2))) – T(T(9))
74232 := ((T(7) + (4^{T(T(2))})) × (T(3) × T(2)))
74235 := (((T((7 × T(4))) × 2) – T(T(3))) × T(5))
74241 := ((T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) × T(T(T(2)))) + T(T((T(4) – 1))))
74245 := (((–(T(7)) + T((T(T(4)) – T(2)))) × T(T(4))) – 5)
74250 := (T(((T(7) – T(4)) × T(2))) × 50)
74253 := (((T(T(7)) × (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) – (T(5))) × 3)
74256 := ((7 × T((T(4) + 2))) × T((–(5) + T(6))))
74268 := (((–(7) – T(4)) + T((2⁶))) × T(8))
74277 := (7 × (T(T(4)) – ((2 – T(7)) × T(T(7))))
74278 := (T(T(7)) + ((T((4^{T(2)})) – T(7)) × T(8)))
74284 := (–(T(7)) × ((–(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) – (T(T(8)) × 4)))
74289 := (–(T(T(T(7 – 4))) – ((2 × T(8)) × T(T(9))))
74295 := (((T(7) – 4)^{T(2)}) + T(T(9))) × 5)
74298 := (T(T(7)) × ((T(4) × T(2)) + T((9 + 8))))
74318 := (T(T(7)) + (((T(T(T(4))) × T(3)) – 1) × 8))
74326 := (T(T(7)) + ((T(T(4)) × T(T(3))) × (2⁶)))
74328 := ((T((7 + T(T(4)))) + 3) × (2 + T(8)))
74333 := (–(T(T(7))) – ((T((4 × T(T(3)))) × (–T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(3))))
74334 := ((7 + T(43)) × T((3 × 4)))
74345 := (((T(T(7)) + T(43)) × T(T(4))) – (T(5)))
74349 := (((T(T(7)) – T(4)) × T(T(3))) – T(T(4))) × 9)
74352 := (((7 × (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) – 5) × T(T(2)))
74355 := ((7 + (T(T(4)) × (T(3) × T(5)))) × T(5))
74358 := ((T(7) – T(4)) × (T((T(3) × T(5))) + T(8)))
74368 := (T(7) × ((4 × T(36)) – 8))
74382 := ((T(T(7)) – (4 × T(T(3)))) × T(T((8 – 2))))
74384 := (((T(7) + T(4)) × 3) × T(T(8))) – T(T(T(4)))
74385 := (T((T(7) – T(4))) × T(((3 × 8) + 5)))
74394 := (–(T(T(7))) + ((T((4 + T(T(3)))) + T(T(9))) × T(T(4))))
74398 := (T(T(7)) – (((T(T(T(4))) × T(3)) + 9) × (–8)))
74424 := ((T(7) – 4) × ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4))))
74428 := (T(7) + ((T(T(T(4))) + T(4)) × (T(T(2)) × 8)))
74429 := (–(T(T(7))) + ((T(4) + T((T(T(4)) + 2))) × T(9)))
74430 := ((T((7 × T(4))) – 4) × 30)
74431 := (((T(7)/4)⁴) × 31)
74448 := (T((T(7) + 4)) × (T((T(4) + 4)) + T(8)))
74452 := (–(T(7)) × (–(T(T(4))) + ((–(4) – T(T(5))) × T(T(T(2))))))
74466 := ((–(T(7) – 4)) + T((4 × T(6)))) × T(6))
74473 := ((T(7) × (T(T(T(4))) + (T(47)))) – T(T(T(3))))
74492 := (–(T(7)) – ((T((4 + 4)) × T(T(9))) × (–2)))
74496 := ((T((7 – 4)) + T(4)) × T(96))
74514 := (((–(T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) – 5) × T((1 + T(4))))
74522 := (–(7) + (((T(T(4)) × 5) – 2)²))
74523 := (((T((7 + T(4))) + T(T(5)))²) – (T(3)))
74528 := ((T(T(7)) × (–T(4))) + ((T(T(5)) – 2) × T(T(8))))
74529 := ((T(–((7 – (4 × 5))))²) × 9)
74532 := (((T((7 × T(4))) × 5) – 3) × T(T(2)))
74535 := ((T((7 × T(4))) × (5 × T(3))) – (T(5)))
74536 := ((T(7) × T(T(T(4)))) – (T((–(5) + T(T(3)))) × (–T(T(6))))
74542 := (((T((7 × T(4))) × T(5)) – 4) × 2)
74543 := (–(7) + (T((T(T(4)) + (T(5)))) × (T(4) × 3)))
74545 := (((T((7 × T(4))) × T(T(5)))/4) – 5)
74562 := (((T((7 × T(4))) × T(5)) + 6) × 2)
74564 := (–(T(T(7))) + (T(T(T((T(4)/5)))) × T((T(6) × 4))))
74565 := ((T((7 × T(4))) × (5 × 6)) + (T(5)))
74592 := ((T(7) × 4) × T(((T(5) – 9)²)))
74613 := ((–(7) – (T(T(4)) × (–6))) × T(T(T((1 × 3))))
74628 := ((–(7) + T((4^{6/2}))) × T(8))
74642 := (7 – (–(T(T(4))) × (–(T(6)) + T((T(T(4)) – T(2))))))
74648 := (T(7) × (–((4 – 6)) – (–(4) × T(T(8))))
74655 := (((–(T(7)) + T(T(4))) + T((–(T(6)) + T(T(5)))) × T(5))
74663 := (–(T(T(7)) – ((T((4 + T(6))) × T(T(6))) – (T(3))))
74664 := ((T((T(7) + 4)) + (T(6))) × T((6 + T(4))))
74669 := (–(T(T(7))) – (–(T((4 + T(6)))) × T(T(T(–((6 – 9))))))
74673 := (–(((T(T(7)) – 4) – (T(T(6)) × T((T(7) – 3))))
74676 := (((–(7) + T((4 × T(6)))) – 7) × T(6))
74682 := ((T(T(7)) + T(T(4))) × ((T(6) × 8) – T(T(2))))
74683 := (–(((T(T(7)) × ((T(T(4)) – T(T(6))) – 8)) + T(T(3))))
74704 := (–(T(7)) × (–(T(47)) – T(T(T(04))))
74725 := (7 × ((T(T(T(4))) + T((T(7) + T(T(2)))) × 5))
74727 := (T((T(7) – T(4))) × (–(T(7)) + T((2 + T(7))))
74732 := (–(T(7)) – ((T(4) – T((T(7) × 3))) × T(T(T(2))))
74736 := ((T(74) – 7) × (T(3) + T(6)))
74746 := ((T(7) × T(T(4))) – (T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) × (–T(6))))
74749 := ((–(T(7)) × (–(T(47)) – T(T(T(4)))) + T(9))
74784 := (((–(7) + T(T(4))) – (–(T(7)) × T(T(8)))) × 4)
74787 := (((7 × T(T(T(4)))) × 7) – (T(T(8)) + 7))
74788 := (–(7) × ((–(T(4)) × (T(T(7)) + T(T(8)))) + T(8)))
74794 := (((7 × T(T(T(4)))) × 7) – T((9 × 4)))
74795 := (7 × ((T(T(T(4))) × 7) – 95))
74816 := (–(T(7)) + ((4 × 81) × T(T(6))))

- 74822 := (((T(7) × 4) × (T(T(8)) + 2)) + T(T(2)))
74823 := (((T(7) × 4) × T(T(8))) + T(T(2 × 3)))
74826 := (((T(7) × 4) × T(T(8))) + T(2)) + T(T(6)))
74834 := (((T(T(7)) × T(T(T(4))))/8) - T(3⁴))
74835 := (((T(7) × 4) × T(T(8))) + (3⁵))
74837 := (((-T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) × T((8 + 3))) - 7)
74842 := (-((T(7) + T(4))) - (-T(8) × T(4^{T(2)})))
74844 := (T(T(T(7 - 4))) × (T((8 × T(4))/T(4)))
74850 := (((-7) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(8)) × 50)
74854 := (T(T(7)) + (T((T(T(4)) - 8)) × T((T(5) - 4))))
74855 := (((T(T(7)) + T(4)) × T(8)) - (5)) × 5)
74857 := ((-T(7)) - T((T(4) × 8))) + (5⁷)
74865 := ((T((7 + T(4))) + 8) × T((6 × 5)))
74872 := (T(7) × ((T(4) + T(8)) + T(72)))
74892 := (((T(7) × 4) × T(T(8))) + T((T(9) - T(T(T(2))))))
74893 := ((T(7) × (T(T(4)) + T((8 × 9)))) - T(T(T(3))))
74897 := ((T(74) × (T(8) - 9)) - T(7))
74899 := ((T(7) × (T(4) + T(8 × 9))) + T(T(9)))
74908 := (T(7) + (T((T(T(4)) + 9)) × T(08)))
74922 := (((T(74) × 9) × T(2)) - T(2))
74925 := (T(74) × (-9 × (2 - 5)))
74926 := (T(T(7)) + ((4 × T(T(9))) × (T(2) × 6)))
74928 := (T(7) × ((T(T(4)) × (T(9) + T(2))) + T(8)))
74929 := ((T(T(7)) × T((T(4) + 9))) - T(T(2 + 9)))
74938 := (T(7) + (T(T(4)) × (T((T(9) + T(3))) + T(8))))
74942 := (-T(7)) + (T(-((T(4) - 94))) × T(T(T(2))))
74956 := (T(7) × (T((T(T(4)) - 9)) + T(56)))
74963 := (-7) + (T(((T(4) × 9) - 6))) × T(T(3)))
74964 := (((T(T(7)) + T(4)) × (-T(9))) - (T(6))) × (-4)
74965 := ((T((-7) + T((4 + 9))) × T(6)) - 5)
74973 := ((74 × T(T(9))) - (7 × T(T(T(3))))
74976 := (T((T(7) + 4)) × (T((9 + 7)) + 6))
74982 := ((T(T(T(7 - 4)))) + (T(T(9)) × T(8))) × 2)
74985 := (((7 × T(4)) × (T(T(9)) + T(8))) + T(5))
74995 := (T(T(7)) + (T((T(T(4)) - 9)) × (T(T(9))/T(5))))
74998 := ((-7) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(9) × (T(T(9)) + T(T(8))))
75103 := (T(7) + (T((T(5) + 10)) × T(T(T(3))))
75124 := ((T(7) × T((51 + T(T(T(2)))))) + T(T(T(4))))
75174 := ((T(7) + 5) × T((1 + T((7 + 4))))
75183 := ((7 - T(51)) × (-T(8) - T(T(3))))
75184 := -((T(T(7)) - ((T(T(5)) × T((-1) + T(8))) - T(4)))
75187 := (-7) + ((T(T(5)) × T((-1) + T(8))) - T(T(7)))
75194 := -((T(T(7)) - (T(T(5)) × T(-(1 - (9 × 4))))))
75222 := ((T(7) + T((T(5) + T(2)))) × T((T(2)^{T(2)})))
75229 := (7 × (-5) + (T(T(T(2))) × (2⁹)))
75234 := (-T(T(7))) - ((T(T(5))/(-T(2))) × T((T(3) + T(T(4))))
75243 := (((T(7) × (T(T(5)) + T(T(2)))) + T(T(4))) × T(T(3)))
75246 := (T((T(7) - 5))) + (T(T(T(2))) × T((4 × T(6))))
75247 := (7 - (-T(T(5))) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(4) - T(T(7))))
75248 := (-T(7)) - ((-T(T(5))) + T(T((T(T(T(2))) - T(4)))) × (-T(8)))
75249 := (((-7) + T(T(5))) × T(T((2 × 4))) - 9)
75252 := (((-7) + T(T(5))) × T(T((T(2) + 5)))) - T(T(2))
75254 := (((-7) + T(T(5))) × T(T((T(2) + 5)))) - 4)
75255 := (((T((7 × 5)) - T(2)) × T(T(5))) + T(5))
75257 := ((7 + T((T(T(5))/T(2)))) × T(-(T(5) - T(7))))
75258 := ((-7) + T(T(5))) × T((T(2 + 5) + 8))
75264 := (T((-7) + T((5 × 2))) × 64)
75268 := (T(7) + ((T(T(5)) - T(T(2))) × (-6) + T(T(8))))
75273 := ((T((T(7) - 5)))²) - T((7 × T(3)))
75285 := ((T((-T(7)) + T(T(5))) + T((2 + T(8)))) × T(5))
75286 := (T(T(7)) + (-T(T(5)) × (T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(8)) - (T(6))))))
75288 := ((T(75) + (T(2)⁸)) × 8)
75292 := ((-T(7)) - (T(T((T(5) - 2))) × (-9))) × 2)
75334 := (((-T((T(7) - T(5)))³) + T(T(T(3))))/(-T(4)))
75339 := ((T(T((T(7) - T(5)))) × (3 × T(3))) - 9)
75342 := (((-T(7)) - T(T(5))) - (T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(4)))) × T(T(2)))
75348 := ((-T((7 + 5))) × T(T(3))) × (-T(4) + T(8))
75364 := ((-T(7)) - (T(T(5)) × (-3))) × (T(T(6)) - 4))
75376 := (T(7) + ((T(5) + 3) × T(T((7 + 6))))
75384 := (-T(T(7))) + (T((-5) + T(T(3))) + T(8)) × T(T(4))
75388 := (T(7) + (T(T(5)) × (-38) + T(T(8))))
75422 := ((T(7) + ((5 × T(T(4)))²) - T(T(T(T(2))))
75424 := (-T((-7) + T(5))) + (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(T(2)) - T(T(4))))
75425 := (7 × (-5) + (T(T(T(4))) × (2 + 5)))
75427 := (-((T(7) + 5)) + (T(T(T(4))) × (T(T(T(2))) + T(7))))
75432 := (((7 + T(5)) + T((4 × T(T(3)))) × T(T(T(2))))
75435 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T(5))) × (-T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(5)))
75437 := (-((T(7) - 5)) + (T(T(T(4))) × (T(T(3)) + T(7))))
75453 := ((-7) - ((T(T(5))/(-4)) × T(T(5))) × T(T(3)))
75455 := (((-T(7)) + T(T(5))) × T((T(T(4)) - (T(5)))) + T(5))
75466 := ((T(T(7)) - T(5)) + (T((4 + T(6))) × T(T(6))))
75472 := ((7 + 5) + (T(T(T(4))) × (7²)))
75473 := ((T(7) - T(5)) + (T(T(T(4))) × (T(7) + T(T(3))))
75475 := ((7 × (-T(5)) + (T(T(T(4))) × 7)) + (T(T(5))))
75481 := (T(T(7)) + (T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))) × (T(8) - 1))
75494 := (-((T(T(7)) - (T(T(5)) × T(T(4)))) - (-T(9)) × T(T(T(4))))
75495 := (-7) × ((T(T(5)) × (T(4) × (-9))) + (T(5)))
75516 := (T(T(7)) × (((T(5) + T(5)) + 1) × 6))
75518 := -((T(T(7)) - ((T(T(5)) - 5) + 1)) × T(T(8)))
75522 := ((T(T(7)) × (T(5) + T((T(5) + T(2)))) + T(T(2)))
75523 := ((T((7 × 5)) × T(T(5))) - (T(T(T(T(2))))/3))
75524 := (((-T(7)) + T((T(T(5))/5)))²) + T(T(T(4)))
75528 := (((T(7) × 5) × T(5)) - 2) × T(8)
75534 := ((T((7 × 5)) × T(T(5))) - T((T(T(3)) - T(4))))

- 75542** := (((T((7 × 5)) × T(T(5))) - T(T(4))) - T(2))
75550 := ((T((7 × 5)) × T(T(5))) - (50))
75557 := ((T((7 × 5)) × T(T(5))) - (T(5) + T(7)))
75565 := (-7) × ((T(T(5)) × (T(5) × (-6))) + (5))
75567 := ((T((7 × 5)) × T(T(5))) - (T(T(6)/7))
75571 := ((T((7 × 5)) × T(T(5))) - (T(7) + 1))
75572 := (T(7) × (T((-5) + T((5 + 7)))) - 2))
75577 := (-((T(7) - 5)) + (T(T(5)) × T((T(7) + (7))))))
75579 := ((T((7 × 5)) × T(T(5))) - T(T(T(-((7 - 9))))))
75582 := ((T((7 × 5)) × T(T(5))) - (T(8)/2))
75585 := (((T((7 × 5)) × T(5)) × 8) - T(5))
75586 := ((T((7 × 5)) × T(T(5))) - (8 + 6))
75588 := (-((7 + 5)) - (T(T(5)) × (T(8) - T(T(8))))))
75591 := ((T((7 × 5)) × T(T(5))) - (9 × 1))
75593 := (-7) + (T(T(5)) × (T((5 + 9)) × T(3)))
75594 := -((T(T((7 - 5))) - (T(T(5)) × T((T(9) - T(4))))))
75595 := ((T(T(7)) - (T(5) × T((5 × 9)))) × (-5))
75597 := ((T((7 × 5)) × T(T(5))) - T((9 - 7)))
75599 := ((T((7 × 5)) × T(T(5))) - (9/9))
75612 := (-T(7) + ((T(T(5)) × (-T(61)))/(-T(2))))
75615 := ((T((7 × 5)) × T(T((6 - 1)))) + (T(5)))
75622 := ((T(7) × T((-5) + T((6 × 2)))) - T(T(2)))
75624 := ((T(7) × T((-5) + T((6 × 2)))) - (4))
75628 := (T(7) × T((-5) + T(((6 - 2) + 8))))
75635 := (-7) - (T(T(5)) × (T(6) × T(3))) × (-5))
75636 := ((T(7) × T(T((T(5) - 6)))) + (T(3)⁶)
75642 := ((-T(7)) - (-T((5 + 6)) × T(T(4)))) × T(T(T(2))))
75648 := (((-7) + T(5)) × 6) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(8))
75670 := (T((T(T(7) - 5))/6)) × 70
75680 := (T(((7 + T(5)) + T(6))) × 80)
75684 := (T(7) × (T(5) + ((6 + T(T(8))) × 4)))
75686 := (-7) + (((T(T(5)) - 6) × T(T(8))) - T(T(6)))
75699 := ((T(T(7)) × ((T(5) + 6) × 9)) - T(T(9)))
75712 := (7 × (((T(5) × 7) - 1)²))
75726 := ((T((-7) + T(5))) + T((T(7) × T(2)))) × T(6))
75728 := ((7 - 5⁷) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(8))))
75734 := (T((-T(7) + T(T(5)))) - (-T(T(7)) × (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4))))))
75744 := -(((T(T(7)) + T(T(5))) × (T(T(7)) - (T(4) × T(T(4))))))
75762 := (((T(T(7)) - T((5 + 7))) × T(T(6))) - T(T(2)))
75764 := ((T(75) - T(T(7))) × (T(6) + T(4)))
75768 := (-(((T(7) - T(5)) + T(7))) × T(T(6))) × (-8))
75769 := (T((7 + T(5))) + (T(T(7)) × (T(T(6)) - T(9))))
75783 := (7 + ((T(T(5)) + T(7)) × (8³)))
75784 := (-T(T(7))) - ((5 - T(T(7))) × T((-T(8) + T(T(4))))))
75785 := ((T(7) - 5) × ((-7) + T(T(8))) × 5))
75789 := ((T(T(7)) - 5) × (7 × (T(8) - 9)))
75792 := ((T(T(7) - 5)) + (-T(T(7))) × (T(9) - T(T(T(2))))))
75796 := (T(7) × ((-T(5)) + T((T(7) + T(9)))) + (T(6)))
75812 := (-T(7) + (T(T(5)) × (T((T(8) - 1) + 2)))
75823 := ((-7) + T(T(5))) × (T(T(8)) + (2 + 3))
75824 := (T(7) × (((5 + T(T(8))) + T(T(2))) × 4))
75826 := (T((T(7) + T(5))) + ((T(8) × T((2⁶))))
75828 := ((T((T(7) - 5)) + 8) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(8)))
75846 := (((T(T(7)) × (-5) + T(8))) + T(T(4))) × 6)
75852 := ((T(7) + T(T((5 + 8)))) × (T(5) + T(2)))
75853 := (T(7) + ((T(T(5)) × T(T(8))) - T((T(5) × T(3))))))
75855 := (((T(T(7)) + T(5)) × T(8)) + (T(5))) × 5)
75888 := (((-7) + T(T(5))) × T(T(8))) - T(8) + T(T(8)))
75922 := ((T(T(7)) × T((5 + T((9 - 2)))))/T(2))
75924 := (((7 × T(5)) + 9) × T(T((2 × 4))))
75927 := ((T(T(7)) + 5) + ((-T(9)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) × T(T(7)))
75932 := (-T(7) + (-T(T(5)) × ((-T(T(9))) - T(T(T(3))))/2))
75936 := ((-7) + T(T(5))) × (T((T(9) - 3)) - T(T(6)))
75937 := ((T(T(7)) + T(5)) + ((-T(9)) + T(T(T(3)))) × T(T(7)))
75943 := ((T(7) + T(5)) + ((-T(T(9))) × T(T(T(4))))/(-T(T(3))))
75960 := ((T(T(T(T(7 - 5)))) + T(T(9))) × 60)
75964 := (T(7) × (((T(T(5)) + 9) × T(6)) + (4)))
75967 := (7 + (T(T(5)) × (T(9) + (T(6) × T(7))))
75975 := ((7 + T(5)) - T(T(9))) × (-75))
75978 := (T(T(T(7 - 5))) × ((9 × T(T(7))) - T(8)))
75993 := ((T(7) + (5 × 9)) × (T(T(9)) + T(3)))
75998 := ((T(T((-7) + T(5)))/9) × (T(T(9)) - 8))
76024 := (-((T(T(7)) + T(60)) × (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(4))))
76125 := ((T(T(7)) - T(T(6))) × T((1 + T((2 + 5))))
76146 := ((T(7) + T(T(6))) × (14 × T(6)))
76195 := ((T(7) + T(6)) × (T(T((1 + 9))) + T(5)))
76215 := (((T(7) - 6) × T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1) × T(5))
76223 := (-7) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T((2 + 2)))) × T(3))
76224 := (-7) + ((T((T(6) + 2))²) + T(T(4)))
76237 := ((T(T(7)) × T((T(6) - 2))) - T((T(3) × 7)))
76239 := (((T(T(7)) × T(6)) - T(T((-2) + T(3)))) × 9)
76243 := (7 + (((T(T(6)) × T(T(2))) × T(T(4))) + (T(3))))
76244 := ((T(7) + T(6)) × ((2⁴) + T(T(T(4))))
76245 := (((7 × T(T(6))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(4))) + T(5))
76246 := (T(7) + (-6) × (2 - (T(T(4)) × T(T(6))))))
76249 := (T(7) + (((T(T(6)) × T(T(2))) × T(T(4))) - 9))
76258 := (T(T(7)) + (T((T(6) × 2)) × (T(T(5)) - T(8))))
76264 := ((T(7) + 6) + ((T(T(2)) × T(T(6))) × T(T(4))))
76265 := ((7 + (T((T(T(6)))/T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(6)))) × 5)
76272 := ((7 + (T(T(6)) × T((T(2) + 7)))) × T(T(2)))
76293 := ((T(7) + T(6)) × (T((T(T(2)) + T(9))) + T(T(T(3))))
76294 := ((76 - 2) × (T(T(9)) - 4))
76296 := (((T(7) + 6))²) × (T(9) + T(6))
76299 := (((7 × T(6)) × (2⁹)) + T(T(9)))

- 76325** := $((-(T(7)) + T(T((6 + T(3)))) \times 25)$
76328 := $-(((T(7) - ((6^3))) \times T(28)))$
76329 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - T((3^2))) \times 9)$
76335 := $((T(T(7 + 6))) + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(3)))) \times T(5))$
76342 := $((T(7) + T(6)) \times ((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(2)))$
76349 := $(-(T(T(7))) + (T(6) \times T(-(T(3) - T((4 + 9))))))$
76351 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) - T(3)) \times (T(T(5)) + 1)$
76398 := $((7 + T(T(6))) \times (-3) + (9 \times T(8)))$
76425 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T((T(4)/2))) - T(5))$
76426 := $(T(T(7)) - (-(T(6)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T((2^6))))$
76428 := $((-(T(T(7)) + (6))) - T((T(T(4)) + T(2)))) \times (-T(8))$
76433 := $((-(T(7)) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(4))) \times T(3))) + T(T(T(3))))$
76434 := $((T(7) + T(6)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) - T(T(4)))$
76440 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T((T(T(4)) - 40))$
76455 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T((T(4) + 5))) + T(5))$
76464 := $((T(7) + T(6)) + T(4)) \times (6^4)$
76468 := $(-(T(7)) \times ((T(T(6)) - T((T(T(4)) + (T(6)))) - T(8)))$
76482 := $(-7) \times (((-T(6)) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \times T(T(2)))$
76492 := $((T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(9)) - T(2))$
76493 := $(-7) + (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(4))) + T(9)) \times T(3))$
76495 := $((T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((9 \times 5))$
76517 := $((T(T(7)) + T((6 \times T(5)))) \times 17)$
76524 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-4))$
76530 := $((T(T(7)) + (T(65))) \times 30)$
76546 := $(T(T(7)) + (-6) \times (T(5) - (T(T(4)) \times T(T(6))))$
76555 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))) - (5) + T(T(5))$
76566 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))) - (-6) \times T(6))$
76568 := $((T(T(7)) - (-6) \times T(T(5))) \times 68)$
76582 := $(T((7 + T(6))) + (T((T(5) + 8))^2))$
76583 := $((-(T(T(7)) - ((T(65) \times T(8)))) - T(T(T(3))))$
76584 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))) + (T(8) \times 4)$
76589 := $((T((7 + T(6))) - (T(58) \times T(9)))$
76593 := $((T(T(7)) \times (-T(6))) + (T(5))) \times (-9) - (T(3))$
76594 := $(-(T((7 + T(6)))) - ((-5) - T(9)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
76608 := $(-7) \times ((-6) \times T(60)) + T(8))$
76615 := $((7 - (-6) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(-(1 - 5)))$
76632 := $((T(T(7)) + (6)) \times (T(T(6)) - T((3^2))))$
76635 := $((T((7 + T(6 + 6))) \times T(T(3))) - T(T(5)))$
76642 := $(T(T(7)) + ((6 \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(2)))$
76678 := $(-7) \times (((-6) - T(6)) \times T(T(7))) + 8)$
76689 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(6) + (T(6) \times 8))) - T(9))$
76692 := $(-T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - (T((6 \times 9)) \times 2))$
76695 := $((T(T(7)) \times (-T(6))) + (6)) \times (-9) + T(5))$
76698 := $((T((7 + T(6))) \times (T(6) \times 9)) - T(8))$
76713 := $((-(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T((T(7) - 1))) - T(T(3))$
76715 := $((7 - (-6) \times T(71)) \times 5)$
76724 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(6) \times (7 + 2))) - T(4))$
76727 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(6) \times (7 + 2))) - (7))$
76732 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(6) + (T(7) \times T(3)))) - 2)$
76734 := $(T(T(7)) \times (T(6) \times ((7 + T(3)) - (4))))$
76741 := $(7 + ((-T(6)) \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(4) - 1))$
76744 := $((-(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T((-(T(7)) + T(T(4)))) + T(4))$
76748 := $(-7) + (T(6) \times T((7 + T((4 + 8))))$
76755 := $(T((7 \times 6)) \times (-((7 \times 5)) + T(T(5))))$
76762 := $(T(7) + ((-T(6)) \times T(T(7))) \times (-6 - T(2)))$
76779 := $((T((T(7) + (6))) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(7))) + T(9))$
76783 := $(T(7) + (T(((T(6) + T(7)) + T(8))) \times T(T(3))))$
76798 := $(T(7) + (((-T(6)) \times T(T(7))) \times (-9)) + T(8))$
76824 := $(-((7^6) + 8)) + (T(T(T(2)))^4)$
76826 := $((T(7) \times ((6 + 8)^{T(2)})) - (6))$
76831 := $((T(7) \times ((6 + 8)^3)) - 1)$
76832 := $(T(7) \times (((6 + T(8))/3)^{T(2)}))$
76836 := $(76 \times (T((T(8) + 3)) + T(T(6))))$
76846 := $(T(76) + ((-8) \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (-6))$
76852 := $(T(76) + (-T(T(8))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(T(T(2))))))$
76853 := $(-(T(7) - (T(6) \times (T(85) + T(3))))$
76855 := $((T(T(7)) + T(6)) \times (T(8) \times 5)) - (5)$
76860 := $((T(7) + (6 + 8)) \times T(60))$
76869 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + (T(8) - T(6))) \times 9)$
76875 := $((7 \times T(T(6))) + (T(T(8)) \times (-7) + T(T(5))))$
76888 := $((7 + T(6)) \times (T(T(8)) + T((8 \times 8))))$
76893 := $((T(T(7)) \times (-T(6))) + 8) \times (-9) + T(T(T(3)))$
76912 := $((T(7) + T(T(6))) + T(9)) \times T((1 + T(T(T(2))))$
76923 := $((T(7) \times (T(6) - 9)) - T(2)) \times T(T(T(3)))$
76934 := $((-(7) + T(T(6))) + T(9)) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4))))$
76937 := $((T(7) - T(T(6))) \times ((9 \times 3) - T(T(7))))$
76944 := $(T(7) \times ((T(6) + T((9 \times 4))) \times 4))$
76959 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(6) \times 9)) - (-5) \times T(9))$
76962 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(6) \times 9)) + T(T(6))) - T(2)$
76965 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(6) \times 9)) + T((6 + T(5))))$
76972 := $((7 + T(T(6))) + ((9 \times T(T(7))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
76985 := $(-(T(76) + 9)) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(5)))$
76992 := $((T(((7 + 6) + T(9))) \times T(9)) - T(2))$
76995 := $(T(((7 + 6) + T(9))) \times (9 \times 5))$
77042 := $(7 + (-T(70)) \times (-T(4) - T(T(T(2))))$
77112 := $(-T(7)) \times (T(T(7)) - T((1 + T(12))))$
77125 := $((T(T(7)) \times T((7 + 12))) - (T(5)))$
77133 := $(-7) + (T(T(7)) \times T((13 + T(3))))$
77168 := $((T(7) + T(7)) \times T((16 + T(8))))$
77224 := $(-T(7)) \times (((T(T(7)))/(-2)) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4))))$
77226 := $((T((T(T(7)))/7)) \times T((T(2)^2))) + T(T(6))$
77228 := $(-T(7)) + (((T(T(7)) \times T(T(2)))/T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(8)))$
77229 := $((7 \times T((7^2))) + T(T(2))) \times 9)$

- 77238 := $(T(T(7)) + ((T(7)^{-2+T(3)})/8))$
77245 := $((-T(7)) + (7 \times T(T((T(T(2))) - T(4)))) \times 5)$
77248 := $(T(7) + (T((7 + T(2)) + T(T(4)))) \times T(8))$
77252 := $(-7) \times ((-T(7)^{T(2)}) - T(T(5)))/2)$
77256 := $((T(T(7))/7) \times 2) \times T((T(5) + T(6)))$
77257 := $-(((T(7) \times (T(7) + T(2))) - (5^7)))$
77265 := $((T((T(T(7))/7)) + T(T(2))) \times T((-6) + T(5)))$
77283 := $((T((7 \times 7)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(8)) \times 3$
77285 := $((-7) - T(72)) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(5)))$
77294 := $(-T(T(7))) + (T(7) \times T((T(T(2) + 9) - 4)))$
77295 := $((-7) \times T(7^2)) \times (-9) + T(T(5))$
77322 := $((T(7) - (T(T(7)) \times (-3^2))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
77329 := $(T(T(7)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 9)$
77343 := $((T(7) + T((7 + T(3 \times 4)))) \times T(T(3)))$
77350 := $((-7) - T(T(7 + 3))) \times (-50)$
77357 := $((T(7) + 7) \times T(T((T(3) + 5)))) - (T(7))$
77364 := $-((T(T(7)) - (T(7) - (-T(3)) \times T(T(6)))) \times T(T(4)))$
77378 := $(T(7) + ((T(T(7)) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(8)))$
77382 := $((T(7) + 7) \times T(T(3 + 8))) - T(2)$
77385 := $-(((T(7) - (7 \times T(38))) \times T(5)))$
77427 := $(7 - (-T(7)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(T(2))) + (T(7))))))$
77429 := $((T(7) + T(T(7))) + (T((T(T(4)) + T(2))) \times T(9)))$
77439 := $((T(7) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times T(3))) - 9)$
77444 := $(T(7) \times T(74)) - (4^4)$
77445 := $((T((T(T(7))/7)) + T(4)) \times 45)$
77448 := $(-7) \times ((T(74) \times (-4)) + T(8))$
77462 := $(-T(7)) + (-((T(T(7)) - (4^6))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
77463 := $((T(7) \times T(74)) - T(T(6))) - (T(3))$
77469 := $((-7) + T(7)) - T(T(T(4))) \times (-6) - T(9)$
77476 := $((T(7) \times T(74)) + 7) - T(T(6))$
77482 := $((T(7) \times (T(74) - 8)) + T(T(2)))$
77488 := $((T(T(7))/7) \times ((4 + T(T(8))) + T(T(8))))$
77490 := $(T((-7 + 7)) + T(T(4))) \times 90$
77494 := $-((T(T(7)) - ((T(T(7)) + 4) \times T(9 + T(4))))$
77496 := $(T((T(7) + T(7))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(9))))/(-T(6))))$
77525 := $((T(7) - (-7) \times T(T((5 + T(T(2)))))) \times 5)$
77532 := $(T(7) \times ((T(7) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(3)))) - T(2)))$
77539 := $(7 \times (7 + ((T(5) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(9)))$
77543 := $(T(T(7)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T((T(5) + 4))) - 3))$
77546 := $(T(T(7)) \times (T(T(7)) - (5 + (T(4) \times T(6))))$
77557 := $((-7) - T((T(7) + 5))) + (5^7)$
77572 := $(-(((T(7) \times T(7)) - (5^7))) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
77589 := $((T(7) \times T(7 + 5)) \times T(8)) - T(T(9))$
77616 := $(T((-7) + T(7))) \times (T(6) \times 16)$
77622 := $((T(7) + T(7)) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(2))$
77623 := $(7 + ((-T(7)) \times T(T(6))) \times (-2) \times T(3))$
77679 := $((T((7 + 7)) - (-T(6)) \times T(T(7)))) \times 9$
77685 := $((-7) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(8)) - T(T(5))$
77686 := $(T(7) + (T((7 \times 6)) \times 86))$
77693 := $(-7) + (T(7) \times T(((T(T(6)) - 9)/3)))$
77694 := $-((T(T(7)) - ((T(T(7)) - (T(6)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(4))))$
77728 := $(T(7) \times ((T(T(7)) \times 7) - T((T(2) + 8))))$
77729 := $((T(T(7)) \times ((T(7) \times 7) - 2)) - T(T(9)))$
77746 := $((T(T(7)) \times (T(7) \times 7)) - T((T(4) \times 6)))$
77756 := $(T(7) \times ((T(77) + 5)) - T(T(6)))$
77769 := $((T(7) - T(T(7))) \times (T(7) - T(T(6)))) + T(T(9))$
77779 := $((T(7) \times T(7)) - (T((T(T(7))/7)) \times (-T(9))))$
77784 := $((-7) \times ((-T(7)) \times T(T(7))) + T(8)) - T(T(T(4)))$
77785 := $(T((7 \times 7)) - ((T(7) - T(T(8))) \times T(T(5))))$
77826 := $((T((7 + 7)) \times T((T(8) + 2))) + (T(6)))$
77845 := $((T(7) + T(T(7))) \times (-T(8)) + T(T(4))) \times (-5)$
77868 := $((T(7) \times 78) - T(6)) \times T(8)$
77888 := $((T((7 \times 7)) - 8) \times (8 \times 8))$
77893 := $((-T(7)) \times (-7 - T((T(T(8))/9)))) - 3$
77894 := $-((T(T(7)) - (T((-7) + T(8))) \times (T(9) \times 4)))$
77895 := $((T(7) + T(T(7))) \times T(8)) - T(9) \times 5$
77896 := $(T(7) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(8) \times (T(9) + T(6))))$
77922 := $((T(T(7)) - ((T(7) + T(9)))) \times (T(2) + T(T(T(T(2))))))$
77924 := $(-T(7)) + (T(T(7)) \times ((T(9) + T(2)) \times 4))$
77946 := $((-T(7) + T(T(7))) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(4)) + T(T(6))$
77952 := $(T(T(7)) \times ((79 - T(5)) \times T(2)))$
77957 := $((-T(7)) \times T(T(-(7 - 9)))) + (5^7)$
77973 := $((T((7 + 79)) - T(7)) \times T(T(3)))$
77983 := $(7 + ((T(T(7)) - T(9)) \times (T(8) \times T(3))))$
77995 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(7))) + 9) \times 95$
78134 := $(-T(T(7))) + ((T((8 + 1)) + T(3)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
78142 := $((T(T(7)) + (T((T(8) + 1)) \times T(T(4)))) \times 2)$
78148 := $(-7) + ((-T(T(8 - 1))) \times T(T(T(4))))/(-8)$
78204 := $(-T((7 \times 8))) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(04)))$
78225 := $((T(7) \times T(T(8))) - T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)))) \times 5$
78228 := $((T(T(7)) - (T(T(8)) \times (-T(2)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8)$
78246 := $((T(T(7)) + 8) \times (T((2 \times T(4))) - (T(6))))$
78249 := $((-T((7 \times 8))) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(4)))) + T(9)$
78252 := $((T(T(7)) - (-T(8)) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + 5))) \times T(T(2))$
78255 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(8)) + T((T(2) \times T(5)))) \times 5$
78262 := $(-7) + (T(82) \times (T(6) + 2))$
78265 := $((T(7) + ((8 - T(2))^6)) \times 5)$
78267 := $((-T(T(7))) \times (T(8) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) - (T((6 \times 7)))$
78272 := $((T(7) + T(8)) \times (-2) + T(7^2))$
78274 := $((-T(7)) \times T(T(8))) \times (-T(2)) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(4)))$
78288 := $(-T(7)) \times ((-8) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T((T(8) + T(8))))$
78294 := $-((T(T(7)) + ((-8) + (T(2)^9)) \times (-4)))$
78318 := $((-7) + T((T(8) - T(3)))) \times T(18)$

$$\begin{aligned}78325 &:= (7 - ((T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(5)))))) \\78326 &:= -((T(T(7)) + ((T(8) \times (-3)) \times (T(2)^6))) \\78328 &:= (T(T(7)) + (T(T(8)) \times (3 \times (T(2) + T(8)))) \\78329 &:= (T((7 + T((8 + 3)))) \times 29) \\78343 &:= (7 - (-((8^3) \times T((-4) + T(T(3))))) \\78344 &:= (T(7) \times ((T(8) \times T((3 \times 4))) - T(4))) \\78345 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times (-8) + T(T(3)))) - T(T(4))) \times T(5) \\78352 &:= (((7 + T(8))^3) - (5 \times T(T(T(2)))))) \\78355 &:= ((((-7) + T(T(8))) - (T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - (5)) \\78357 &:= (((-7 - 8) + T(T(T(3)))) + (5^7)) \\78358 &:= (T(T(7)) \times (((T(8) \times T(3)) - T(5)) - 8)) \\78364 &:= (T(7) + ((8^3) \times T((T(6) - 4)))) \\78372 &:= (-T(7)) \times (T(T(8)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times T((7 - 2)))) \\78390 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T((T(8) - T(3)))) \times 90) \\78393 &:= (((T(7) \times T(8)) \times T((3 + 9))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\78408 &:= (((-T(7)) + T(T(8))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(08) \\78421 &:= ((-7) + T(T(8))) \times (T(T((T(4)/2))) - 1) \\78422 &:= ((T(7) + T(T(8))) \times ((T(T(4)) \times 2) + T(2))) \\78428 &:= (-T(7)) \times ((-T(T(8))) - T(T(T(4)))) - T((-2) + T(8))) \\78429 &:= (((T((7 + T(8))) \times 4) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9))) \\78432 &:= ((7 + T(8)) \times (T((T(4) \times T(3))) - T(T(2)))) \\78450 &:= (((-7) + T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 50) \\78453 &:= ((-7) \times T(8)) + (T(T(4)) \times T(53)) \\78454 &:= (-((T(T(7)) - ((T(T(8)) + 4) \times T(T(5)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\78456 &:= ((T(T(7)) - (T(T(8)) \times (T(4) - T(5)))) \times T(6)) \\78457 &:= -((T(7) - ((T(8) \times T(4)) + (5^7)))) \\78458 &:= ((78 - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(8)))) \\78462 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times (-T(8))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-6) + T(T(2))) \\78464 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T((T(8) + 4))) \times 64) \\78470 &:= ((-7) + T((-8) + T(T(4)))) \times 70) \\78477 &:= (7 + (T((-T(8)) + T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(7)) + (7))) \\78485 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times T(8)) + T((T(4) + T(8)))) \times 5) \\78492 &:= ((7 + T(T((8 - 4)))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(T(2)))))) \\78512 &:= (-T(7)) + (T((-T(8)) + T(T(5))) \times (1 + T(T(T(2)))))) \\78518 &:= (T((7 + T(8))) \times (T(T(5)) - (1 + T(8)))) \\78523 &:= ((T(T(7)) - 8) + (5^{T(T(2))/3})) \\78526 &:= (T(T(7)) + ((-8) \times T((T(5) \times 2))) \times (-T(6))) \\78533 &:= (-T(7)) + (T((8 + T((T(5) - 3)))) \times T(T(3))) \\78535 &:= (T(7) + ((T(T(8)) + 5) \times (-3) + T(T(5)))) \\78562 &:= ((T(7) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(5)))) - (T(T(6)) \times T(T(2)))) \\78567 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T(8)) + (5^{-T(6)+T(7)})) \\78569 &:= -((T(T(7)) - ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(5))) - (T(6) \times T(9)))) \\78573 &:= (T(T(7)) + (((T(8) + 5^7) + T(3)))) \\78575 &:= (T((-7) + T(8)) - (-((5^7) - T(5))) \\78579 &:= (((T(7) \times T(8)) \times T((5 + 7))) - T(9)) \\78582 &:= (((T(78) - 5) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(T(2))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}78588 &:= -(((T(7) - T((8 + 58))) \times T(8))) \\78595 &:= (7 + (T(T(8)) \times (T(59)/T(5)))) \\78622 &:= (((T(7) \times T(8)) \times T((6 \times 2))) - 2) \\78624 &:= ((T(7) \times T(8)) \times T(((6/2) \times 4))) \\78634 &:= (((T(7) \times T(8)) \times T((6 + T(3)))) + T(4)) \\78645 &:= (7 \times ((T(8) + T(T((T(6) - T(4)))) \times 5)) \\78652 &:= (T(7) \times (((8 \times 6) + 5)^2)) \\78669 &:= (((T(7) \times T(8)) \times T((6 + 6))) + T(9)) \\78724 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) \times 72) + T(T(T(4)))) \\78728 &:= (-((T(T(7)) + T(8)) - (-T(T(7))) \times (T(T(T(2)))) - T(8))) \\78748 &:= (T(7) + (-T((8 + 7))) \times (T(4) - T(T(8)))) \\78758 &:= ((T(7) + (T(T(8)) \times T((T(7) + T(5)))))/8) \\78764 &:= (T(T(7)) \times (T(8) - ((T(7) \times (-6)) + T(4)))) \\78774 &:= ((-7) + T((T(8) + T(7)))) \times (T(7) + T(4)) \\78792 &:= (T(7) \times (-T(8)) + T(((T(7) + T(9)) + 2))) \\78793 &:= (((-T(7)) + T(T(8))) \times T((-7) + T(9)))/T(3) \\78833 &:= (-7) + (T(8) \times (T(T((8 + 3))) - T(T(3)))) \\78842 &:= (-T(T(7))) - (8 \times (-T(T(8)) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(2)))))) \\78844 &:= (((T(7) \times (-T(8)) - T(T(8))) - T(T(4))) \times (-4)) \\78846 &:= ((7 + 8) + T(8)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \\78848 &:= (T(7) \times ((88 \times 4) \times 8)) \\78855 &:= (((-7) + T(T(8))) \times 8) - (T(5)) \times T(5) \\78868 &:= (T(7) + (T((T(8) + T(8))) \times (-6) + T(8))) \\78884 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T((T(8) + T(8)))) \times (T(8) - T(4))) \\78885 &:= -((T(T(-((7 - 8) - 8))) - (T(T(8)) \times T(T(5)))))) \\78893 &:= (-T(7)) + ((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(9)))/T(3)) \\78930 &:= ((T((7 \times 8)) + T(T(9))) \times 30) \\78939 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (-T(8))) - ((9 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (-T(9)))) \\78943 &:= ((7 + (T((8 + T(9))) \times T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(3)))) \\78946 &:= (T(T(7)) - ((T(8) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(4))))/(-T(6))) \\78967 &:= ((T(T(7)) - (8 + 9)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(7))) \\78975 &:= (((T(7) \times T(8)) + T(9)) \times 75) \\78976 &:= ((T(7) + T(8)) \times (9 + T((T(7) + T(6)))) \\79050 &:= -(((T(7) - 90) \times T(50))) \\79135 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T((1 + 3)))) - T(T(5))) \\79142 &:= (T(T(7)) + ((T(T(9)) + 1) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))))) \\79152 &:= (-((T(7) - T(9))) \times T(((1 + T(5)) \times T(T(2)))) \\79165 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (-T((9 - 1))) + T(T(6))) - (5)) \\79167 &:= ((7 + T(T(9))) + (((-1 - 6)^7))) \\79192 &:= ((7 + T(T(9))) \times (T((1 + 9)) + T(T(T(2)))) \\79212 &:= (T(7) \times (T((-T(9)) + T(T((T(2) - 1)))) - (T(T(T(2)))))) \\79226 &:= (-7) + (((9 - 2)^{T(2)}) \times T(T(6))) \\79227 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T((2 + 2)))) - T(7)) \\79228 &:= (T(7) - (T((T(9)/T(2))) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(8)))) \\79232 &:= ((T(T(7)) + (T(T(9)) \times 2)) \times 32) \\79233 &:= ((7^{9/T(2)}) \times T(T((3 + 3))) \\79234 &:= (-T(T(7))) - (((T(T(9)))/(-T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)))\end{aligned}$$

- 79236** := (((-(T(T(7)) - T(T(9)))) × T(T(T(2)))) - 3) × 6)
79242 := ((7 - ((9 + T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(4)))) × T(T(2)))
79244 := (-T(T(7))) - (-T(9) × T(-((T(T(2)) - T(T(4))) - T(4))))
79245 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) + 2) × T(T(4))) - T(T(5)))
79252 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) × T((2 × 5))) - T(2))
79254 := ((T(T(7)) - T(T(9))) × ((-2) - T(T(5))) - (4))
79255 := ((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) × T((T(2) × 5) - (5)))
79264 := (((T(T(7)) - T(T(9))) × T(T(2))) × (-T(6))) + T(4))
79275 := (((-T(7)) - T(T(9))) + T(T(2))) × (-75))
79276 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) × T((T(2) + (7)))) + T(6))
79283 := (-((T(T(7)) - (T(T(9)/T(2))) × T(T(8)))) - T(T(T(3))))
79285 := (((T(T(7)) - T(T(9))) - T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)) × T(T(5))))
79289 := -(T(T(7)) - (T(T(9)) × (T(2) - (T(T(8)) / (-9))))
79292 := (-T(T(7))) + (((-T(T(9))) × T(T(T(2)))) - 9) / (-T(2)))
79298 := (-T(T(7))) + ((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) × T((T(9) + T(8))))
79324 := (-T(7)) × (-((T(93) + 2) + T(T(T(4))))
79335 := (((T(7) × 9) × T(T(3))) - 3) × T(5))
79342 := (T(T(7)) - ((-T(9)) - T(T(T(3)))) × (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(2))))))
79344 := ((-7) + T((T(9) + T(T(3)))) × T((4 + 4)))
79352 := (-T(7)) + (T(9 × 3) × T((T(T(5)) / T(T(2))))))
79362 := (((-T(7) × T(9)) × T(T(3))) + (6)) × (-T(2))
79365 := (((T(7) × T(9)) × 3) × T(6)) - T(5))
79373 := (-7) + ((T(9) × T(T(3))) × (T(7) × 3))
79375 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) × T((3 + 7))) + T(T(5)))
79376 := ((T(T(7)) + T(9)) × (-T((3 + 7))) + T(T(6)))
79387 := (7 + (T(9 × 3) × T((-8) + T(7))))
79389 := (((-7) + T((T(9) + T(T(3)))) × T(8)) + T(9))
79392 := ((T(T(7)) - (T(T(9)) × (-T(3)))) × (9 + T(2)))
79395 := (((T(T(7)) × (T(9) - T(3))) + T(9)) × 5)
79420 := ((T(T(7)) - T(9)) × (T(4) + T(20)))
79422 := (7 × T((T(9) + ((4²)))) × T(T(2)))
79423 := (((7 + T(T(9))) × (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(3))))
79426 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) × T(T(4))) + T((T(2) × 6)))
79432 := (7 - (-T(9)) × ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(2))))
79436 := (-T(7)) + ((T(9) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(6))))
79442 := (-T(7)) - (T(9) × (-T(T(4))) - T((T(T(4)) + T(2))))
79443 := (((T((T(7) + 9)) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(4))) × T(T(3)))
79445 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) × T(T(4))) + T((4 + T(5))))
79447 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) + (4)) × T(T(4))) - T(7))
79458 := ((T(7) - 9) × (-4 + T(T((5 + 8))))
79464 := ((T((7 + (9 × 4))) × T(6)) × 4)
79472 := ((T(T(7)) + (T(T(9)) × (T(4) + T(7)))) × 2)
79477 := (7 + (T(9) × (T(T(4)) + T((T(T(7)) / 7))))
79485 := (-7) × ((T((9 + 4)) + T(T(8))) × (-T(5)))
79486 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) × T(T(4))) + T(T((T(8) / 6))))
79488 := (T((T(7) - ((9 - 4))) × (8 × T(8)))
79489 := (((T(7) - 9) × T((T(T(4)) + T(8)))) - T(9))
79497 := ((-T(T(7)) + T(9)) + T(T(T(4)))) × (T(9) + T(7))
79498 := (((T(7) - 9) × T(T((4 + 9)))) - T(8))
79522 := (7 + (T((T(9) - T(5)) × T((T(2) × T(T(2))))))
79523 := -(((T(T(7)) - 9) - (T(T(5)) × T(T((2³))))))
79524 := (((T((7 + 9)) + (5))²) × 4)
79527 := (((T(T(7)) + (9 × T(5))) × T(T(T(2)))) × 7)
79532 := (-T(7)) + ((T(T(9)) - T(5)) × T((T(3) × 2)))
79534 := ((T(7) - 9) × T(T((T((5 - 3)) + T(4))))
79536 := ((7 + 9) × (T(T(5)) + (T(T(3)) × T(T(6))))
79540 := ((T(7) - (T(T(9)) / (-T(5)))) × T(40))
79544 := ((T(7) × T((-T(9)) + T(T(5)))) - (4⁴))
79545 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) + (5)) × T(T(4))) + (T(5))
79548 := (T(7) × (-9) + T((-5) - (T(4) × (-8))))
79553 := (-7) + ((T(T(9)) - T(5)) × T((T(5) - 3)))
79559 := -(T(T(7)) - (((-T(9)) × T(T(5))) × (-T(5)) - T(T(9))))
79563 := ((T(7) × T((-T(9)) + T(T(5)))) - (T(T(6)) + (T(3))))
79568 := (-T(7)) + (T(((9 × 5) + T(6))) × T(8))
79569 := (((7 × T(T(9))) + T(56)) × 9)
79572 := (((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) + (5⁷)) + T(T(2)))
79575 := (((7 × T(9)) × T((T(5) + (7)))) - T(T(5)))
79576 := (T(T(7)) × (T((9 + 5)) + T((7 + 6))))
79579 := (((T(7) - 9) × T(T(-((T(5) - T(7)))))) + T(9))
79582 := ((T(7) × (T((-T(9)) + T(T(5)))) - 8) + T(T(2)))
79587 := ((T(7) + T(9)) + ((T(T(5)) × T(T(8))) - T(T(7))))
79588 := ((T(T((7 + 9) - 5)) × T(8)) - 8)
79596 := (T((T(-((7 - 9)) + (5))) × T((T(9) + T(6))))
79622 := (-T(7)) + (T(9) × T((62 - T(2))))
79624 := (T(7) + (T((T(9) + T(6))) × T((2 × 4))))
79629 := (((-7) × T(T(9))) + (6)) × (-2 + 9))
79632 := ((79 × T(63)) / 2)
79646 := (-T(7)) - ((T(9) × (-T(T(6))) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(6)))
79648 := ((T(7) - 9) × (6 + T((T(T(4)) + T(8))))
79649 := -((T((T(7) + T(9))) - (T((6 × T(4))) × T(9))))
79653 := (-7) × ((T(T(9)) × (-6 + 5)) + (T(3)))
79657 := (7 + (T(9) × T((T((6 + 5)) - (7))))
79667 := ((((-7) × T(T(9))) / (-T(6))) × T(T(6))) - T(7))
79668 := ((-7 - 9) + T(66)) × T(8))
79674 := (-T(T(7))) - (-((T(9) - T(6)) + T(7)) × T(T(T(4))))
79678 := (T(7) + (T(9) × T((67 - 8))))
79682 := ((-7) + (T((9 + 6)) × T(T(8)))) - T(T(T(T(2))))
79683 := ((-T(7)) + ((T(T(9)) × T(T(6))) - 8)) / 3)
79689 := ((T(7) × (T(T(9)) + (T(T(6)) × 8))) - T(T(9)))
79692 := -(T(-((7 - 9)) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T(9))) / (-T(2))))
79693 := ((7 - 9) - ((T(T(6)) × T(T(9))) / (-3)))
79694 := (-T(T(7))) + (T(9) × ((T(T(6)) + 9) + T(T(T(4))))
79695 := ((-7) × T(T(9))) × (-T(6) - T((9 - 5)))
79723 := (T(7) + ((T(T(9)) × T((7 × T(2)))) / 3))

- 79724** := (((7 + T(T(9))) + (7)) × (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4))))
79725 := ((T(7) + T(T(9))) × ((7 - 2) × T(5)))
79744 := (-T(7) × (-T((9 + T(7)))) - T((T(4) + T(T(4))))))
79749 := ((T(-T(7) - T(9))) × T((T(7) + (4)))) - T(T(9))
79758 := ((T(7) - T((-9) + T(7))) + (T(T(5)) × T(T(8))))
79772 := (((T(T(7)) × (-9)) + T(7)) × (-T(7) + T(T(2))))
79778 := -((T(T(7)) - ((T(T(9)) - (7)) × 78))
79785 := ((T(7) × T(-((T(9) - T((7 + 8)))))) - T(5))
79828 := (-T(7) × ((-T((9 × 8)) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) + 8)
79841 := (-79) + (T(T(8)) × T(T((4 + 1))))
79848 := ((7 + T(T((9 + (8/4)))))) × T(8)
79853 := (-((T(7) + T(9))) + ((T(T(8)) × T(T(5))) + (T(3))))
79859 := ((-7) - T(9)) + ((T(T(8)) × T(T(5))) - 9)
79868 := ((-7) - T(9)) + (T((T(8) - T(6))) × T(T(8)))
79882 := ((7 - T(9)) - (-T(T(8))) × T(T((8 - T(2))))))
79883 := (-((T(7) + 9)) + (T(T(8)) × T(T((8 - 3))))
79884 := (T(7) × (T(9) + (T(8) × T((8 + 4))))
79885 := (-((T(7) × T(9))/T(8))) + (T(T(8)) × T(T(5)))
79892 := (-T(7) + ((T(9) × (-8)) × (9 - T(T(T(2))))))
79893 := (((T(-7) + T(9))) × (-T(8))) + T(9) × (-3)
79899 := -((T(T(T(-7 - 9)))) - (T(T(8)) × T(T((9/9))))))
79913 := (-7) + (T((T(9) - 9)) × T(T((-1) + T(3))))
79922 := (T(T(7)) + (9 + ((T(9) - 2)^{T(2)})))
79924 := (T((7 + T(9))) × ((T(9) + T(2)) + T(4)))
79926 := ((T(T(7)) - (T(9) + (T(9)/T(2)))) × T(T(6)))
79927 := (7 + (T((T(9) - 9)) × T(T(-(2 - 7))))))
79928 := ((T(7) + (T((9 × 9)) × T(2))) × 8)
79933 := (7 + (((T(T(9))/9) + T(T(T(3)))) × T(T(T(3))))))
79948 := ((T((T(7) + 9)) + T(T(9))) × (T(4) + T(8)))
79956 := (((T(7) + T(T(9))) × (-T(9) + T(T(5)))) + T(T(6)))
79968 := ((T((T(7) + T(9))) - T(T(9))) × (6 × 8))
79982 := (T(T(7)) × ((T(T(9))/9) + (82)))
79994 := (-((7 - (9 × 9))) × T((-9) + T(T(4))))
80352 := (T(8) × (T(T((T(03) + (5)))) + T(T(T(2))))))
80385 := (T((T(8) - T(03))) + (T(T(8)) × T(T(5))))
80583 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(05))) + T(T(8))) - 3)
80595 := ((T(T(8)) × T(T(05))) + (T(9) × T(5)))
80655 := (((T(T(8)) + 06) × T(T(5))) + (T(5)))
80755 := (((T(T(8)) + 07) × T(T(5))) - (5))
80892 := (T(8) × (T(08) + T(T((9 + 2))))))
80955 := ((T(T(8)) - (T(T(09)) × (-T(5)))) × 5)
81073 := (-8) - ((T(10) - T(T(7))) × T(T(T(3))))
81075 := (T((T(8) + 10)) × 75)
81142 := (((T(8) × T(T(11))) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(2)))
81200 := (T(T((8 - 1))) × 200)
81243 := (81 × (T(2) + (T(4)³)))
81244 := ((T(81) × 24) + T(T(T(4))))
81251 := ((T(T(8)) × ((1 × 2) + T(T(5)))) - 1)
81252 := (T(T(8)) × (T(((1 + 2) × 5)) + 2))
81276 := (-T(8)) - ((-1) - T((-2) + T(7))) × T(T(6)))
81312 := ((T((T(8) - T((1 + 3)))) + 1) × T(T(T(T(2))))
81396 := (T((8 × (1 + T(3)))) × (T(9) + (6)))
81432 := ((T(T(8)) + T((1 + T(T(4)))) × (T(3)²))
81445 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T((1 + 4)))) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(5))
81537 := ((T(T(8)) × T(15)) + (T(T(T(3))) × 7))
81542 := ((T((T(8) + 1)) × (T(T(5)) - (4))) - T(T(2)))
81543 := ((T((8 - 1)) + T((T(5) + T(4)))) × T(T(T(3))))
81544 := ((T((T(8) + 1)) × (T(T(5)) - (4))) - (4))
81548 := (T((T(8) + 1)) × (T(T(5)) + ((4 - 8))))
81549 := ((T(T(8)) × (T(15) + (4))) - T(T(9)))
81564 := ((T(T(8)) × (-1) + T(T(5))) + (T(T(6)) × T(4)))
81567 := (81 × (T(T((T(5) - (6)))) - (T(7))))
81627 := ((T(T(8)) + T(T((1 × 6)))) × T((T(T(2)) + (7))))
81647 := ((T(((8 + 1) × 6)) × T(T(4))) - T(7))
81648 := ((81 × T(6)) × 48)
81684 := (T(8) × (T((1 + T(6))) + T((8 + T(T(4))))))
81694 := (-T(8)) - ((-1) - T((6 × 9))) × T(T(4)))
81729 := (-81) × ((T(7) - 2) - T(T(9)))
81738 := ((-T(8)) + T((-1) + T(7))) × (T(T(T(3))) + 8)
81746 := ((T(T(8)) - 1) + ((T(T(7)) - T(T(4))) × T(T(6))))
81747 := (T(T(8)) + (T(T(-((1 - 7)))) × (-T(T(4)) - T(T(7))))))
81756 := (T(8) × ((17 × T(T(5))) + T(T(6))))
81795 := ((T(T(8)) - 1) × (T(7) + (95)))
81843 := (T(8) + ((1 + T(8)) × T(T((-T(4)) + T(T(3))))))
81864 := (T(8) × ((-1) × T(8)) + (T(T(6)) × T(4)))
81945 := (T((8 + 1)) × (-9) + T((4 × T(5))))
81952 := ((-T(8)) - T(T((1 + 9)))) × (-52)
81972 := ((T(8) × (1 × 9)) × T((T(7) - T(T(2))))))
82012 := ((-8) + T(20)) × T(T((1 + T(T(2))))))
82128 := ((8 × T(T(2))) × T(((1 + T(T(2)))) + T(8)))
82144 := (-T(((T(8) × 2) - 1)) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(T(4))))))
82173 := (T(-((8 - 21))) × T((7 × T(3))))
82179 := (-T(8)) - (T(T(T(2))) × (T((1 + T(7))) × (-9)))
82188 := ((T((T(8) + T(T(T(2)))) + (T((-1) + T(8)))) × T(8))
82215 := ((T((T(8) + T(2))) + T(2)) × T((-1) + T(5)))
82224 := (T(8) × (T(T(2)) + T(((2 × T(T(2))) + T(T(4))))))
82225 := (T(((8 + T(2)) × 2)) × T(25))
82228 := ((T((82 + T(T(2)))) × T(T(T(2)))) - 8)
82233 := ((T((82 + T(T(2)))) × T(T(3))) - 3)
82236 := (T((82 + (2 × 3))) × T(6))
82239 := ((82 - T(2)) × (T(3) + T(T(9))))
82244 := (8 - (T(T(T(2))) × (-T((2 × 44))))))
82246 := (82 × ((2^{T(4)}) - T(6)))
82251 := (T((T(8) + 2)) × (T(T(2)) + T(T(5) - 1)))

- 82269** := (((-T(T(8))) + T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(2)))) + 6) × 9
82272 := (T(8) - (-T(T(2))) × T((-T(2) + T((7 + T(T(2))))))
82284 := (-T(T(8))) - ((-T(T(2))) + (T(T(T(2))) × T(8))) × (-T(4)))
82287 := ((T(T(8)) + T(2)) × (T(2) + T((8 + 7))))
82296 := (T(8) × ((T(2) + T((T(2) × 9))) × 6))
82297 := ((T(8) × T(T((T(T(T(2))))/T(T(2)))))) + T((T(9) + T(7)))
82320 := ((T((8 × T(T(2))))/3) × T(20))
82338 := ((-T(82)) × (-3 - T(T(3)))) + T(T(8))
82341 := (T(T(8)) + (T(T((-2) + T(3)))) × T((T(4) - 1)))
82342 := (-8) - (-T((T(2) × 3))) × T((T(4) × T(T(2))))
82344 := ((8 × T(2)) × (T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(4))))
82350 := ((T((T(8) + T(T(T(2)))) - T(3)) × 50)
82353 := ((T(T(8)) × ((-2) + T(3) + T(T(5)))) - T(T(T(3))))
82359 := (-T(T(8))) - (T(2) × ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(5)))) + T(9)))
82362 := ((T((82 + T(3)) + 6)) × T(T(T(2))))
82368 := (T(8) × ((T(T((-2) + T(3)))) + T(T(6))) × 8)
82383 := ((-T(82)) × T(T(3))) + (T(T(8)) × T(T(T(3))))
82384 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(2))) × T(T(3))) + 8) - T(T(T(4)))
82385 := (-T((8 + 2))) + ((T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) × T(T(5)))
82392 := (8 × ((T(T(T(2)))³) + (T(T(9)) + T(2)))
82412 := ((T(T(8)) + (2 × T(T(T(4)))) × (1 + T(T(T(2))))
82416 := ((T(T(8)) - (T(T(2)) × T(4))) × T(16))
82422 := ((8 + (T(T((T(2) + 4)))²))/2)
82425 := (((T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) × T(T((T(4)/2))) - T(5))
82432 := ((8^{T(2)}) × (-T(4) + T((T(3) × T(2))))
82440 := ((T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) × T((T(T(4)) - 40))
82446 := ((T(((T(8) - T(2)) + T(T(4)))) + T(4)) × T(6))
82448 := (((T(8) × (T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)))) + T(4)) × 8)
82450 := ((T((T(8) + T(T(T(2)))) - 4) × 50)
82455 := (((T(T(8)) + T((2 + 4))) × T(T(5))) + (T(5)))
82462 := (T(T(8)) + ((T((T(T(2)) + 4))) + T(T(6)))²)
82467 := (((T((8 + 2)) - 4) × T(T(6))) × 7)
82473 := ((T(T(8)) × (2 + T((T(4) + T(7)))))/T(3))
82475 := (((T(T(8))/T(T(2))) + (4⁷)) × 5)
82476 := (T(8) × (T((T(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)) - 6)))
82482 := (((-((8^{T(2)})) × T(T(4))) + T(T(8))) × (-T(2)))
82484 := (((T(8) × T(T(T(2)))) × T(4)) - (T(T(8)) + T(4)))
82485 := (-((T(8) + T(2))) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(85)))
82487 := (((T(8) × T(T(T(2)))) × T(4)) - (T(T(8)) + 7))
82489 := -((T(T(8 + T(2))) - (T(T(T(4))) × T(T((T(8)/9))))))
82492 := (-T(T(8))) + (((T(T(2)) × T(T(T(4)))) × 9) - 2)
82494 := (-T(T(8))) - (-((2 + 4) × 9) × T(T(T(4))))
82496 := (-((T(T(8)) - 2)) + (T(T(T(4))) × (9 × 6)))
82524 := (((T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(5))) - (T(T(T(2))) × (-4)))
82539 := ((T(T(8)) × ((-2) + T(T(5))) + (T(3)))) - T(9)
82542 := ((T(T(8)) × (-T(2)) + T(T(5))) + (T(T(T(4))) × T(2)))
82544 := (((8 + T((2⁵))) × T(T(T(4))))/T(4))
82548 := (-T(8)) - (((T(T(2)) - T(T(5))) - T(4)) × T(T(8)))
82555 := (((T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(5))) - (5 - T(T(5))))
82563 := ((T(T(8)) × ((-2) + T(T(5)) + 6)) - T(T(3)))
82566 := (T(T(8)) + (-T(25)) × (-T(6) - T(T(6))))
82572 := (((T(8) - T(2)) × T(T(5))) - T(7)) × T(T(T(2)))
82574 := ((T(T(8)) × ((-T(2)) + T(T(5)) + 7)) - T(4))
82577 := ((T(T(8)) × ((-T(2)) + T(T(5)) + 7)) - 7)
82582 := (((8/2) + T(T(5))) × T(T(8))) - 2
82584 := (T(T(8)) × (2 × (58 + 4)))
82592 := ((8 + T(T(T(2)))) × (T((T(T(5)) - T(9))) - 2))
82629 := (((T(T(8)) - 2) × T(6)) × T(T(2))) - T(T(9))
82648 := (-((8^{T(2)})) - (T(T(6)) × (-T(4) × T(8))))
82650 := (T((T((T(8)/T(2))) - T(6))) × 50)
82656 := (T(8) × ((T((2⁶)) - T(5)) + T(T(6))))
82657 := ((T((T(8) + 2)) × (T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) + T(T(7)))
82665 := (((T(T(8)) - T(T(2))) - (-T(6) × T(T(6)))) × T(5))
82678 := (((-8) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(6))) × T(T(7)) + (T(T(8)))
82684 := (-T(8)) - (T(T((-2 - 6))) × (T(8) - T(T(T(4))))))
82686 := (T(8) + (T((-2) + T(6))) × T((8 + T(6))))
82692 := (T(T(8)) - ((T(T(T(2))) × (-T(T(6)) - T(9)))) × T(T(T(2))))
82719 := ((-T(T(8))) - ((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(7))) - 1)) × (-9)
82722 := ((T(8) - 2) × ((T(T(7)) × T(T(2))) - T(2)))
82725 := (-T(T(8))) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(7)) - (T(2) × T(5))))
82728 := (((82 × T(7)) + 2) × T(8))
82733 := ((-8) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-7 + T((3³))))
82734 := (T(8) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(7)) + (-T(3) × T(T(4))))))
82738 := (82 × ((7³) + T(T(8))))
82744 := ((T(T(8)) + ((T(T(2)) + 7) × T(T(T(4)))) × 4)
82755 := ((T(T(8)) + T(((T(T(2)) - T(7)) + T(T(5)))) × T(5))
82764 := ((T(8) - (-T(2)) × T(T(7))) × T((T(6) - T(4))))
82776 := ((8 - ((T(T(2)) + T(7)) × T(T(7)))) × (-6))
82779 := (((T(8) + (T(T(2)) × T(7))) × T(T(7))) - T(9))
82782 := (((T(8) × 2⁷) - T(T(8))) × T(T(T(2))))
82784 := ((-T((8²))) × (T(T(7)) - 8))/(-T(4))
82787 := (((8 - T(2))⁷) + (T(T(8)) × 7))
82788 := (-T(8)) - (T(T(T(2))) × (-T(7) + T(88)))
82795 := (((T(8) × T(2)) - T(7)) × T(T(9))) - 5)
82796 := -((T((T(8) - 2)) - (T(T(7)) - T(9)) × T(T(6))))
82824 := (T((8 × 2)) × ((T(T(8)) - 2) - T(T(4))))
82836 := (T(8) × (-T((T(2) + T(8))) + T(T((T(3) + 6))))))
82839 := (T(T(8)) - (T((T(T(2)) - 8)) × (-T((-3) + T(9))))))
82842 := ((T(T(8)) + (T((2 + T(8))) × T(T(4)))) × 2)
82844 := ((-8) × T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-8) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(T(4))))))
82845 := (T((8 + T(T(2)))) × (-T(8)) + (T(T(4)) × T(5)))
82846 := ((T(T((8 - T(2)))) × T(T(8))) + T((T(T(4)) + T(6))))
82872 := ((8 - ((2 - T(8)) × T(T(7)))) × T(T(2)))
82875 := ((T(T(8)) - T(2)) × (T((8 + 7)) + 5))

- 82881** := $(T(T(8)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(88) - 1)))$
82902 := $(T(T(8)) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(90 - 2)))$
82923 := $((T(8) \times ((T(2) + T(9))^2)) - T(T(3)))$
82926 := $(((-8) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(9))) - (T(2) + T(T(6)))$
82928 := $(8 \times ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(9)) - (T(T(T(2))) + 8)))$
82929 := $(((-8) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(9))) - T(T(-((T(2) - 9))))$
82932 := $(((-8) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(9))) - (T(T(T(3))) - T(2))$
82933 := $((8 + T(T(T(2)))) \times ((T(T(9)) + (T(3)))/3))$
82936 := $(-8) + (((T(T(T(2))) - T(9))^3) \times 6)$
82938 := $((T(T(8)) / (-T(2))) + ((T(9) \times T(T(3))) \times 8))$
82941 := $((T((T(8)/T(2))) \times T(T(9))) + T(T((T(4) + 1)))$
82942 := $((-((T(8)^2)) \times (-9 - T(T(4)))) - 2)$
82944 := $((T(8)^{T(2)})/9) \times (4 \times 4)$
82945 := $(T((T(8) - 2)) + (T(9) \times T((4 \times T(5))))$
82952 := $(8 + (((T(2) + 9)^5) / T(2)))$
82953 := $((T(T(8)) + (-2 + T(9))) \times (T(T(5)) - 3))$
82962 := $((T(T(8)) / T(2)) + T(T(9))) \times (T(T(6)) / T(T(2))))$
82968 := $(((-((8 + 2)) \times T(T(9))) - (T(6))) \times (-8))$
82971 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T(2))) - T(9)) \times T(7 - 1)$
82977 := $(-8) - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(9) - T(T(7)))) + (T(T(7))))$
82992 := $(T((T(8) + 2)) \times ((T(T(9)) / 9) - T(2)))$
82995 := $((8^{T(2)} - 9) \times (T(9) + T(T(5))))$
82998 := $((-8) + T((2 + 9))) \times T((T(9) + 8))$
83052 := $((-T(8)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(05)))) \times T(2)$
83127 := $((T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) \times (1 + T(T(-(2 - 7))))$
83145 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 1) \times T(4) - 5$
83152 := $(-8) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(15) \times T(2)))$
83155 := $((T(8) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(-((1 - 5)))) - 5$
83187 := $(T(T((T(8)/3))) \times (-((1^8)) + T(7)))$
83192 := $(8 \times ((3 + 1) + (T(9) \times T(T(T(2))))))$
83196 := $(T(8) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (1 + (9 \times T(T(6))))))$
83205 := $((T(T(8)) - T(T(3)))^2) / 05$
83214 := $((T(8) \times (-3)) / (-2)) \times (1 + T(T(T(4))))$
83223 := $((T(T(8)) - (T(3))) \times T(T(2))) + T(2) \times T(T(3))$
83229 := $(-T(T((8 - 3))) - ((T(T(T(2)))^{T(2)}) \times (-9)))$
83232 := $(T(8) \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times T((-2) + T(3))) + 2))$
83235 := $((8 + T((T(3) \times T(2)))) \times T((T(3) \times 5)))$
83238 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) - 2) \times T(3) - T(T(8))$
83265 := $(T((8 + T(3))) - ((-T(2)) \times T(T(6))) \times T(T(5)))$
83268 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) + T(2)) \times 6 - T(T(8))$
83278 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) \times T(T(2))) + T(7) - T(T(8))$
83284 := $((T(8)^3 - 2) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(4))))$
83286 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(3)) + T(T(2))) - T(8) \times T(6)$
83292 := $((8 \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(2)) \times T(9) - T(2)$
83294 := $((T((T(8)/T(3)))^{T(2)}) \times 9) - T(T(4))$
83295 := $((8 \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(2)) \times (9 \times 5)$
83312 := $(8 \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(31)) - 2))$
83319 := $(((-8) \times T(T(3))) \times (-T(31))) - 9$
83322 := $((T(T(8)) \times (-T(3))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T((T(2)^{T(2)}))))$
83328 := $((-8) \times T(T(3))) \times (-T((3 + 28)))$
83334 := $((T(8) + T(T(3))) \times (-T((T(3) + T(3)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
83341 := $(-8) + ((T(T(3))^3) \times (T(4) - 1))$
83343 := $(((-T(8)) \times (T(T(3))^3) / (-4)) - T(3))$
83344 := $(-T(8)) - (((-3) - T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
83349 := $((T(T(8)) + T(T((3 \times 3)))) \times 49)$
83376 := $(8 \times ((T(T(3)) \times T((3 + T(7)))) + (6)))$
83379 := $(T(8) / (-3)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(9)))$
83385 := $(T(83) - T(T(3))) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(5)))$
83397 := $((T(8) / T(3)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(7))))$
83412 := $(T(8) \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(4)) + (1 + T(T(2))))$
83413 := $((T(8) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + T((1 + T(T(3))))$
83424 := $(T(83) - T(4)) \times 24$
83427 := $(T(8) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(4) - T((-2) + T(7))))$
83432 := $(8 \times (-T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times T((T(T(3)) - 2))))$
83433 := $((T(83) \times 4) \times T(3)) - T(T(T(3)))$
83434 := $((T(T(8)) / (-T(3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4))))$
83439 := $(-T(T(8))) - (-T(T(3))) \times T((-T(43) + T(T(9))))$
83445 := $((T(8) \times T((T(T(3)) - 4))) + (T(T(4))) \times T(5))$
83446 := $((T(8) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(6))))$
83448 := $(8 \times ((T(3) + T(T(4))) \times T((T(4) + 8))))$
83449 := $((T(8) \times T(3)) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + T(T(9))))$
83458 := $((T(T(8)) \times 3) + T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(8))))$
83464 := $((-T(8)) - T(T(3))) + (((-4) + T(6))^4)$
83472 := $((T(T(8)) / (-3)) \times (-T(47) / T(2)))$
83484 := $(T(8) \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(4)) + (T(8) / 4)))$
83488 := $(8 \times (((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-8)) - T(8)))$
83492 := $(8 - ((T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-9) \times T(T(2))))$
83494 := $(T(8) \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(4)) + 9)) + T(4)$
83495 := $((T(T((-8) + T(T(3)))) \times 4) - T(9)) \times 5$
83496 := $(((-T(8)) + T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) \times T(9)) + (T(6)))$
83512 := $(-8) + ((-3) \times T(T(5))) \times (-1 - T(T(T(T(2))))$
83514 := $((T(T(8)) \times (3 + T(T(5)))) + T((1 + T(T(4))))$
83521 := $((8 - T(3)) + T(5))^{T(2)+1}$
83524 := $(T((8 - T(3))) + (((T(5) + 2)^4))$
83529 := $((T(T(8)) - 3) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(2)))) - 9$
83532 := $((T(T(8)) - 3) \times (T(T(5)) + T(3))) - T(T(2))$
83534 := $((T(T(8)) - 3) \times (T(T(5)) + T(3))) - (4)$
83538 := $(T(T(8)) - 3) \times ((T(5) \times T(3)) + T(8))$
83542 := $((8 - T(3)) + T(5))^4 + T(T(T(2)))$
83556 := $(T(8) - (-3) \times (T(T(5)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))))$
83565 := $((T(T(8)) \times (T(3) + T(T(5)))) - T((T(6) + (5))))$
83573 := $((T(T(8)) \times (T(3) + T(T(5)))) - ((7^3)))$

83574 := (((T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) × T(T(5))) - T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4))))
83578 := (((8 + 3) + T(T(5))) × (-T(7) + T(T(8))))
83584 := (8 × (((3 + T(5)) × T(T(8))) - T(T(T(4))))
83592 := ((8 × (3⁵)) × (T(9) - 2))
83595 := (((T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) × T(T(5))) + T(T(9))) + T(T(5)))
83622 := ((-8) + (T(T(3)) × T((T(6) - 2)))) × T(T(T(2)))
83624 := (8 × (3 + (T((T(6) - 2)) × T(T(4))))
83625 := (T((T(8) - T(3))) - ((T(T(6)) × (-T(2))) × T(T(5))))
83628 := ((T(83) × (T(6) + T(2))) - T(8))
83640 := (((T(8) × 3) - (6)) × T(40))
83643 := ((T(83) × (6 × 4)) - T(T(3)))
83644 := (-T(T((8 + 3)))) + ((T(6) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(T(4)))
83652 := (((T(8) + 3) × T(65)) - T(2))
83655 := ((T(8) - 3) × ((T(6) × T(T(5))) + T(5)))
83664 := (T(83) × (T(6) + T((6 - 4))))
83682 := ((-((T(8) + 3)) + (T(6) × T(T(8)))) × T(T(2)))
83685 := ((T(T(8)) × (T(3) × T(6))) - T((T(8) - T(5))))
83712 := (-8) - (T(T((T(3) + 7))) × (1 - T(T(T(2))))))
83715 := ((-T(8)) × (T(T(T(3))) - T(71))) + T(5)
83720 := (T((T(8) + T((3 + 7)))) × 20)
83731 := (T((T(8) + (37))) × 31)
83739 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(3))) - T(7)) × T(3)) - 9)
83744 := ((-8) + T(T(T(3)))) + (((7 + T(4))⁴))
83748 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(3))) - T(7)) × T(T((T(4) - 8))))
83756 := (T(8) + (T(T((T(3) + 7))) × (T(T(5)/6)))
83763 := (((T(T(8)) × (-T(3))) + 7) × (-T(6))) - T(3))
83769 := (((T(T(8)) × T(3)) - 7) × T(T(-(6 - 9))))
83776 := ((T((T(8) + 3)) - T(T(7))) × (-7) + T(T(6)))
83784 := ((T(T(8)) × (-T(3))) - (-T((7 × 8))) × T(T(4)))
83790 := ((T((T(8) + T(3))) + T(7)) × 90)
83797 := ((T(T((T(8)/T(3)))) × (T(T(7)) - T(9))) + (T(T(7))))
83799 := (-T(8)) + (3 × ((T(7) × T(T(9))) - T(T(9))))
83824 := (-8) + (T(T(3)) × ((T(T(8)) × T(T(2))) - 4))
83825 := -((T((-8) + T(T(3))) - (T(T(8)) × (T(T(2)) + T(T(5))))))
83826 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(3))) - T(8 - T(2))) × 6)
83829 := ((T(T(8)) + 3) + ((-8) × T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(9)))
83832 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(3))) - (8 + T(3))) × T(T(2)))
83833 := (-83) - ((T(T(8)) × T(T(3))) × (-T(3)))
83835 := -((T(T(8)) - ((T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) × (3 + T(T(5))))))
83848 := ((-8) + T(T(T(3)))) × ((-8) + T(T(4))) × 8)
83853 := (((T(T(8)) × T(3)) - (8 - 5)) × T(T(3)))
83859 := -((T(T((T(8)/3))) - ((-T(8) + T(T(5))) × T(T(9))))
83862 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(3))) - 8) × 6) - T(T(2))
83864 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(3))) - 8) × 6) - 4)
83865 := (-T(8)) - (((T(3) × T(T(8))) × (-T(6))) + (T(5)))
83868 := ((T(8)/T(3)) × ((T(T(8)) × T(6)) - 8))
83889 := ((8 + T(T(T(3)))) × T((T(8) - T((T(8)/9))))

83892 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(3))) - (T(8)/9)) × T(T(2)))
83895 := -((T((T(8) - T(3))) - (T((-8) + T(9))) × T(T(5))))
83913 := (((T(T(8)) × (3 - T(9))) + 1) × (-3))
83916 := (T(T(8)) × (T(3) + T((9 × 1) + 6)))
83922 := (((T(T(8)) × (3 - T(9))) - 2) × (-T(2)))
83923 := (((T(T(8)) × (-T((3 × 9)))) - T(T(T(2))))/(-3))
83942 := ((-T(8)) + (T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(9)) + T(T(4)))))/(-T(2))
83944 := ((-T(8)) × T(T(3))) + (T((T(9) + T(4))) × T(T(4)))
83946 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(3))) + (9 - 4)) × 6)
83952 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(3))) + (-9) + T(5)) × T(T(2)))
83955 := ((8 + T(T(3))) × (T(9) + T((5 × T(5))))
83965 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(3))) + 9) × 6) - 5)
83967 := ((-8) + T(T(3))) × (-9) - (T(T(6)) × (-T(7)))
83972 := (((-8) × T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(9))) - (T(T(7)) × (-2))
83978 := ((T((T(8)/3)) × T(T(9))) + (T(T(7)) × 8))
83982 := (-T(8)) - (T((T(T(3)) + T(9))) × (-T(8) + 2))
84034 := (-T(T(8))) + (T(T(T(4))) × T(T((0 × 3) + 4)))
84044 := (-T(T(8))) + ((T(T(T(4))) × T(T(04))) + T(4))
84124 := ((-T(T(8))) × (-4) - T(T((-1) + T(T(2)))))) + T(T(T(4)))
84128 := ((8 × 4) × (1 + T((2 × T(8))))
84132 := (T(8) × (T(T((T(4) + 1))) + (T(T(3)) × T(T(2))))))
84134 := ((T(8) + T(4)) × (-1) + T((T(3) × T(4))))
84144 := (-T(T(8))) - ((T(T(T(4))) + 1) × (-T(T(4))) - (T(T(4))))
84150 := (T(((8 + 4) - 1)) × T(50))
84216 := (T((84 + T(2))) × (1 + T(6)))
84224 := ((-T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) × (2 × T((T(2) + (4))))
84225 := ((T(((T(8) + T(T(4))) - 2) × T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(5))))
84227 := (((8 × T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(2)) + T(T(7)))
84229 := (((-8) + T((4 × T(T(2))))²) - T(T(9)))
84235 := ((-T(8) × T(4)) × (-T(2) - T(T(T(3)))) - 5)
84240 := ((T(8) - T(4)) × T((2 × 40)))
84244 := ((-8) × (T(T(4)) + 2)) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(T(4))))
84245 := (((-8) + T(T(T(4)))) × T((T(T(2)) + (4)))) - T(5)
84246 := (((T(T(8)) × T((4 + 2))) + T(T(4))) × 6)
84249 := (-T(T(8))) - ((-4) + T((T(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) × (-T(9)))
84252 := ((T(8) + ((4^{T(T(2))}) - T(T(5)))) × T(T(T(2))))
84254 := -((T(T(8)) + ((-4) - T(T((2 × 5)))) × T(T(4))))
84255 := (((T(T(8)) + T((4 × 2))) × T(T(5))) + (T(5)))
84273 := (((T(T(8)) + 4) × T(T(2))) - 7) × T(T(3))
84275 := (((8 - T(T(T(4)))) × (-T((T(2) + 7)))) + T(5))
84279 := (-T(8)) + ((T(T(4)) × T(T(T(2)))) × (T(7) + T(9)))
84282 := (T(8) - ((-T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(2))) × T(T(8)))) × T(T(2)))
84288 := ((8 × 4) × (T(T(2)) + T((T(8) + T(8))))
84318 := (T((T(8) + T(4))) × T((3 + 1) + 8))
84328 := ((T(8) + T((T(4) + 3))) × (-2) + T(T(8)))
84334 := (-T(8)) - ((T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) × (-T((T(3) + 4))))
84336 := (8 × ((T((T(4) + T(T(3)))) + T(3)) × T(6)))

$$\begin{aligned} 84343 &:= -(T(T(8))) - (((T(T(T(4))) + T(3)) \times (-T(T(4)))) + (T(T(3)))) \\ 84344 &:= -(T(8)) - (((T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times (-T(T(4)))) - T(4)) \\ 84348 &:= (((8 \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)))) \times T(8)) \\ 84355 &:= ((T((T(8) + (4 - 3))) \times T(T(5))) - 5) \\ 84362 &:= (-8) - ((T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times (-T(T((6 - 2)))))) \\ 84364 &:= -((T(T(8)) + (T(T(4)) \times (-T(3) - T(T((6 + 4)))))) \\ 84374 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T((T(4) + T(3)) - 7))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 84375 &:= ((T((-8) + T(T(4)))) - 3) \times 75 \\ 84384 &:= (T(8) \times ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) + T(T((T(8)/4)))) \\ 84385 &:= (T(((T(8) + T(T(4))) + 3)) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(5)))) \\ 84392 &:= (8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(9) - T(T(2)))))) \\ 84394 &:= ((T(8) \times ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(9)))) + T(4)) \\ 84397 &:= (T(T(8)) - ((-T(4) - T(T(3))) \times T((T(9) + T(7)))) \\ 84406 &:= (T(8) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 06))) \\ 84414 &:= -((T(T(T(T((8/4)))))) - ((T(T(T(4))) - 1) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 84425 &:= (T(T((8 - 4))) \times (T(T((4 + T(T(2)))) - 5)) \\ 84428 &:= (((8 - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(2))) \times 8)) \\ 84429 &:= -(T(T(8))) - (T((T(T(4)) + (4 + 2))) \times (-T(9))) \\ 84432 &:= (8 - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(3)) + 2))) \\ 84433 &:= -(T(8)) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + (T(T((3 + 3)))))) \\ 84436 &:= (T(8) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + T((3 + T(6)))) \\ 84437 &:= (((8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(4))) - T(37)) \\ 84439 &:= -((T(T(8)) - T(4)) + (T((T(T(4)) + (T(3)))) \times T(9))) \\ 84442 &:= -(T(8)) + (((T(T(T(4))) - 4) \times T(T(4))) - 2) \\ 84443 &:= -(T(8)) - (((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(4)))) - T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 84444 &:= ((T(T((8 - 4))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - 4^4) \\ 84448 &:= (8 \times T((T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)))) \times (-T(4) - T(8))) \\ 84452 &:= (-8) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times 2)) \\ 84454 &:= -(T(8)) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + (T((5 \times 4)))) \\ 84456 &:= (T(8) \times T((-4) \times ((4 - T(5)) - (6)))) \\ 84461 &:= (-8) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(4)))) - (T(T(6)) \times (-1))) \\ 84462 &:= ((T(8) \times T((-4) \times (4 - T(6)))) + T(T(2))) \\ 84463 &:= ((T(T((8 - 4))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(6)) + (T(3)))) \\ 84468 &:= (((8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(4))) - (6 + T(T(8)))) \\ 84469 &:= (((T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(4))) - T((T(6) + T(9)))) \\ 84472 &:= (-8) - ((T(T(T(4))) - 4) \times (-T((7 + T(2)))))) \\ 84473 &:= (((-8) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(4)))) \times T(7)) - 3 \\ 84474 &:= -((T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) - ((T(T(T(4))) + 7) \times (-T(T(4)))) \\ 84476 &:= ((-8) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(4)))) \times (7 + T(6)) \\ 84477 &:= (8 - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + (T((-7) + T(7)))) \\ 84482 &:= (((8 - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + (T(T(8))/T(2))) \\ 84483 &:= (((8 - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(4))) - 8) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 84484 &:= (((8 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(4))) - ((T(T(8)) - T(4))) \\ 84492 &:= (T(8) \times (T((4 \times 4) + T(T((9 + 2)))))) \\ 84496 &:= (T(8) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(4)))) - (-9) - T(T(6)))) \\ 84525 &:= ((T(T(T((8 - 4)))) + T((T(5) \times T(T(2)))) \times T(5)) \\ 84528 &:= ((T((8 + (4 \times T(5)))) + 2) \times T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 84529 &:= -((T(T(8)) - (T(T(4)) \times (T(T((5 \times 2))) + 9)))) \\ 84534 &:= -(T(T(8))) + ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)))) \times (T(3) \times T(4))) \\ 84538 &:= (((T((T(8) - T(4))) + (T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - 8) \\ 84541 &:= (T(T(8)) - ((T(T(T(4))) - T(5)) \times (T(T(4)) \times (-1)))) \\ 84544 &:= ((-T(8)) - T((T(4) + 5))) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \\ 84545 &:= (((T(T(T((8 - 4)))) - 5) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)))) \\ 84546 &:= ((T(T(8)) - (T((4 \times 5) + 4))) \times T(T(6))) \\ 84548 &:= ((8 + T((4 \times T(5)))) \times (T(4) + T(8))) \\ 84564 &:= (T(8) \times (T((T(T(4)) + (T(5)))) - T((6 + T(4)))) \\ 84573 &:= -((T(T(8)) + ((-T((4 \times 5))) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(3)))) \\ 84574 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(7))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 84576 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T((T(4) + 5))) + (7))) - (6) \\ 84578 &:= ((-8 - 4) + ((T(T(5)) + 7) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 84582 &:= (T(T(8)) \times (45 + 82)) \\ 84584 &:= ((-((8^4) \times 5) - T(T(8))) \times (-4)) \\ 84586 &:= (((T(T(8)) + 4) \times T(T(5))) + T(T((-8) + T(6)))) \\ 84595 &:= ((T((-8) + T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(9))) - 5 \\ 84623 &:= ((((-8) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(T(2))))/(-3) \\ 84627 &:= (T(8) - ((-T(4) - T(T(6))) \times T((-2) + T(7)))) \\ 84628 &:= (-T(8)) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T((6 - 2)))) + T(8)) \\ 84643 &:= (-T(8)) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T((6 + 4)))) - T(T(3))) \\ 84644 &:= (((T((T(8) + T(4))) \times T(6)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times 4) \\ 84645 &:= (T(T((8 - 4))) \times ((-6) + T(T(T(4)))) + 5) \\ 84664 &:= (-T(8)) - (T(T((4 + 6))) \times (-T((6 + 4)))) \\ 84666 &:= ((T((8 + T(T(4)))) \times (T(6) + T(6))) - 6) \\ 84671 &:= (((T(8) \times 4) \times T(6)) \times T(7)) - 1 \\ 84672 &:= (T((8/4)) \times ((6 \times T(7))^2)) \\ 84674 &:= (-T(8)) - (T(4) \times ((-T(6)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(4)))) \\ 84678 &:= (-T(T(8))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(6))) - ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(8)))))) \\ 84692 &:= (-8) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T((T(6) - (9 + 2)))))) \\ 84694 &:= (((T(T(8)) + 4) + T(T(6))) \times 94) \\ 84697 &:= (8 - ((T((T(T(4)) + 6))) \times (-T(9))) + (T(T(7)))) \\ 84699 &:= (((T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 6) - T(9)) \times 9 \\ 84724 &:= ((8 \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times 7) + T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 84728 &:= ((T(T((8 + 4))) \times T(7)) - T(T((2 + 8)))) \\ 84732 &:= (-T((8 \times 4))) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 84733 &:= (T(8) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T((7 + 3)))) - 3)) \\ 84734 &:= (((T(T((8 + 4))) \times T(7)) + (T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 84735 &:= ((8 + T(T(4))) \times (T((T(7) + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(5)))))) \\ 84736 &:= (T(8) + (T(T(4)) \times T(((7 - 3) + 6)))) \\ 84740 &:= (T((-T(8)) + T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(7)) + 40) \\ 84742 &:= (T(8) - (((T(T(4)) \times (-T(7))) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(2)))) \\ 84755 &:= (((T(8) \times 4) + (7^5)) \times 5) \\ 84756 &:= ((-T((8 \times (4 + 7)))) - T(T(5))) \times (-T(6)) \\ 84757 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(4)) - (T(7) - 5^7)) \\ 84777 &:= (((T(8) \times T(4)) + 7) \times T((-7) + T(7))) \\ 84778 &:= ((-T(T(8))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T((7 + 7)) - 8) \end{aligned}$$

- 84792** := (((T(T(8)) × T(4)) + T(T(7))) × (9 + T(2)))
84795 := (((T(T(8)) × T(4)) + T(7)) - T(T(9))) × T(5)
84816 := (T((8 + T(4))) × T((T(8) + (1 - 6))))
84824 := (8 - (-T((T(4) + 8))) × T((T(T(2))) + T(4)))
84844 := ((T(8) × 4) + (T(T(8 - 4))) × T(T(T(4))))
84846 := (T(T(8)) - (-((T(4) + T(8))) × T((T(4) × 6))))
84852 := (T(8) × (T(T(T(4))) + (T((8 × 5)) - T(2))))
84864 := ((8 × T((4 + 8))) × T((6 + T(4))))
84872 := (8 × (((T(T(4)) + T(T(8)))/7)²)
84888 := (((84 × T(8)) - T(T(8))) × T(8))
84896 := (8 × (4 + (8 × T((T(9) + (6))))))
84924 := (84 × (T(T(9)) - 24))
84942 := ((8 + T((T(T(4)) - 9))) × T((T(4) + 2)))
84945 := (((8 × T(4)) × T(T(9))) + T(-((T(T(4)) - T(T(5))))))
84955 := ((T(8) × (T(T(T(4))) + (T((T(9) - (5)))))) - 5)
84960 := (-T(8)) × (T(T(4)) - (T((9 + 60))))
84966 := (((8 × (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(9)))) + 6) × T(6))
84967 := (-8) - ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9))) × (T(T(6)) / (-7)))
84972 := (((T(T(8)) - T(4)) - (T(T(9)) × T(7))) × (-T(2)))
84973 := ((T((-T(8)) + T(T(4)))) + 9) × (T(T(7)) + T(T(3)))
84975 := ((T(T(T(8 - 4)))) + T(T(9))) × (T(7) + (5))
84983 := (8 - ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9))) × (-T(8) - 3)))
84984 := (-T(8)) - ((T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) × (-T((8 + 4))))
84992 := (8 × ((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(9)) × (-9))) - T(T(T(T(2))))))
85095 := ((T(T(8)) × T(T(5))) + (T(T(09)) × 5))
85125 := ((T(T(8)) + (T(5))) × 125)
85134 := (-((T(T(8)) - ((T(T(5)) × 13) × T(T(4))))))
85217 := ((T(T(8)) + (5)) × (T(T((T(2)) - 1))) + 7)
85224 := (-T(8)) + (T(T((5 + 2))) × T((2 × T(4))))
85229 := ((-((8 - 52)^{T(2)}) + T(9))
85233 := ((-((T(T(8)) - T((T(5) × T(2)))) × T(T(T(3))) - T(3))
85237 := ((-8) - T(5)) + ((T(T(T(2))) - T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(T(7))))
85239 := (((T(8) + (5)) × T(T((2 × 3)))) × 9)
85242 := (((8 + T(T(5))) × T(T((2 × 4)))) - T(T(2)))
85244 := (((8 + T(T(5))) × T(T((2 × 4)))) - (4))
85245 := ((T(T((-8) + T(5))) × T((2 × T(4)))) - T(5))
85247 := (-((8 + 5)) + (T((2 × T(4))) × T(T(7))))
85248 := (T(T(8)) × ((5 × 24) + 8))
85252 := (-8) - (-T(T((5 + 2))) × T((T(T(5)) / T(T(2))))))
85254 := (-((T(T(8)) - (T(T(5)) × ((T(T(2)) × T(T(5))) - 4))))
85260 := (-((T(T((-8) + T(5))) × (T(T(T(2))) - T(T((6 + 0))))))
85261 := (-((T(T((-8) + T(5))) × (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(6)))) - 1))
85262 := (-((T(T((-8) + T(5))) × (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(6)))) - 2))
85263 := (8 + ((T(T(5)) + T(2)) × T(T(6)))) × 3
85264 := (-((T(T((-8) + T(5))) × (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(6)))) - 4))
85265 := (((T(8) + (5)) × T((2⁶))) - T(5))
85266 := ((T(T(8)) - (-T(5)) × T((2 × T(6)))) × 6)
85267 := (((T(T(8)) + ((T(5)^{T(2)}))) × T(6)) + T(T(7)))
85268 := -(((T(T((-8) + T(5))) × (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(6)))) - 8))
85269 := -(((T(T((-8) + T(5))) × (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(6)))) - 9))
85272 := (8 + (((T(T(5)) - T(T(2))) - T(T(7)))²))
85273 := (-8) + ((T((T(T(5)) / T(T(2)))) × T(T(7))) + (T(T(3))))
85274 := (-T(8)) - ((5 - (T(T(T(2))) × (-T(T(7)))) × (-T(4)))
85275 := ((T(((8 × 5) / 2)) × T(T(7))) + T(5))
85284 := ((-T(T(8))) - (-T(T(5)) × T(T(T(2)))) × (T(8) + T(4)))
85288 := (8 × (5 + ((2 × 8) × T(T(8))))
85293 := (((8 × T(5)) - T(2)) × (9³))
85294 := (((T(8) + (5)) × T(T(T(T(2)))) × 9) + (T(T(4))))
85323 := (-T(T(8))) - ((-T((T(5) × T(3))) × T(T(T(2)))) + T(3))
85328 := (8 - (T(T(5)) × (-T((3²))) - T(T(8))))
85329 := ((T((T(8) - (5))) + 3) × T((2 × 9)))
85332 := (-((T(T(8)) - ((T((T(5) × T(3))) × T(T(3))) + T(2))))
85338 := ((T(T(8)) × T(T(5))) - (-T(3) × T((T(3) + T(8))))
85344 := ((T(T(8)) - (-T(5)) × T((-3) + T(T(4)))) × 4)
85365 := (((8 × 5) + T(T(T(3)))) × (T(6) × T(5)))
85374 := (-((T(8) - (5)) × (T(T(3)) - (T(74))))
85378 := (((-8) + T(T((T(5) - 3))) × T(7)) - (T(T(8))))
85386 := ((T(T((8 + 5))) - T(T(-((3 - 8)))) × T(6))
85392 := (-T(8)) + ((-5) + T(T(T(3))) × T((9 × T(2))))
85415 := (((8 + 5) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(T(-((1 - 5))))
85422 := (T(8) + ((-T(T(5)) + T(T((T(4) + T(2)))) × T(T(T(2))))
85425 := (85 × ((T(4)^{T(2)}) + (5))
85428 := (((T(8) × T((T(5) - 4))) - T(2)) × T(8))
85444 := ((T(T(8)) + T((T(T(5)) / T(4))) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(T(4))))
85448 := ((T(T(8)) + ((T(5) + (T(4)⁴))) × 8)
85455 := ((8 + (5⁴)) × (T(T(5)) + (T(5))))
85464 := (-T(T(8))) - (((5 + T(T(T(4))) + (T(6))) × (-T(T(4))))
85472 := ((T(8) + ((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4))) × T(7))) × 2)
85489 := (-T(8)) - ((-T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) × T(T((T(8) / 9))))
85536 := ((-((T((8 - 5)⁵)) × T(T(T(3))) / (-T(6)))
85540 := (T((8 + 5)) × (T(T(5)) + (T(40))))
85574 := (-((T(T(8)) + (-((T(55) + T(7))) × T(T(4))))
85575 := (((T((8 × 5)) - (5)) × 7) × T(5))
85596 := ((T(8) - T(T(5))) × ((-5) - T(T(9))) + (T(6)))
85624 := ((T((-8) + T(5))) × T((T(T(6)) / T(2))) + T(T(T(4))))
85626 := (T(T(8)) - (T(T(5)) × (T(6) - (T(2)⁶))))
85632 := ((8 + T(T(5))) × (T((6 × T(3))) + T(2)))
85644 := (-T(8)) - (56 × (T(4) - T(T(T(4))))
85645 := (((T(8) - (5⁶)) - T(T(T(4)))) × (-5))
85649 := ((T(8) + (5)) × (T(64) + 9))
85672 := (-8) - (T(T(5)) × ((T(T(6)) + (7)) × (-T(2))))
85674 := ((T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) × (T((T(6) - (7))) + (4)))
85680 := (((T(8) + T(5)) × T(6)) × 80)

$$\begin{aligned}85688 &:= (8 - (T(T(5)) \times ((6 \times 8) - T(T(8)))))) \\85695 &:= ((T((-T(8)) + T(T(5)))) \times (-T(6) - T(9))) + T(5)) \\85698 &:= (((8 + T(5)) \times 6) \times (-T(9) + T(T(8)))) \\85716 &:= (T(8) + (T((5 \times 7)) \times T(16))) \\85720 &:= ((-8) - T((T(T(5)) - T(7)))) \times (-20) \\85722 &:= (((T(85) + T(T(7))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\85723 &:= (((8^5) - T(T(7))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\85743 &:= (((8 + T(5)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(4)))) \times T(T(3))) \\85744 &:= (-T((T(8) - (5)))) - ((T(7) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \\85746 &:= ((T(8) - (5)) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times 6)) \\85749 &:= ((-T(8) - T(T(5))) - ((-T(7) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(9)))) \\85756 &:= (T((T(8) - (5))) + (T(T(7)) \times T((T(T(5))/6)))) \\85764 &:= (-T(8) - ((T(T(5)) - T(T(7))) \times T((6 \times 4)))) \\85767 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(6)))/T(7)) \\85792 &:= (-8) - ((T(T(5)) - T(T(7))) \times T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) \\85794 &:= -(T(T(8)) + (-T(5)) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) \times 4)) \\85797 &:= (-T(8) + (T((5 + T(7))) \times T((T(9) - T(7)))) \\85824 &:= ((T(8) - (T((T(T(5)) - T(8))) \times (-T(T(2)))) \times 4) \\85833 &:= ((-T(8) + T(5)) \times T((T(8) - 3))) \times (-3) \\85843 &:= (((8 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) + T((T(T(4)) - T(T(3)))) \\85844 &:= -(T(T(8)) - ((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(4)))) - T(4))) \\85847 &:= -(T(T(8)) - ((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(4)))) - (7))) \\85848 &:= ((T(8) - T(5)) \times (8^4 - 8)) \\85854 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(8))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(4)))) \\85876 &:= (T(T((-8) + T(5))) - ((T(8) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(6)))) \\85888 &:= ((T(T(8)) + (5)) \times ((8 + 8) \times 8)) \\85893 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times ((T(5) \times 8) + 9)) - T(T(3))) \\85904 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9)) - T(04)) \\85907 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9)) - 07) \\85911 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9)) - T((1 + 1))) \\85912 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9)) - (1 \times 2)) \\85913 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9)) - (1^3)) \\85914 &:= (T(T(8)) \times ((T(5) + 9) + T(14))) \\85915 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9)) + (1^5)) \\85932 &:= ((T(T(8)) - (T(5))) \times ((T(9) \times 3) - T(2))) \\85935 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9)) + (T(3) + T(5))) \\85938 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9)) + (3 \times 8)) \\85942 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9)) + T((T(4) - T(2)))) \\85947 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(5))) - (T((T(9) - (4))) \times (-7))) \\85949 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9)) - ((T(4) - T(9)))) \\85954 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9)) + (-T(5) + T(T(4)))) \\85957 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9)) + (T(5) + T(7))) \\85959 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9)) + (5 \times 9)) \\85967 &:= (((T((8 + 5)) \times T(9)) \times T(6)) - T(7)) \\85968 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(5))) - (9 \times (-6) - T(T(8)))) \\85978 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9)) + (T(7) + T(8))) \\85983 &:= (T(T(8)) - ((T(T(5)) \times (-T(9)) - T(T(8)))) + 3)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}85986 &:= (T(T(8)) - (T(T(5)) \times (T(9) - (T(8) \times T(6)))) \\85992 &:= (((T(8) - T(5)) \times T((T(9) + T(9)))) - T(2)) \\85995 &:= ((T(8) - T(5)) \times T((9 + 9) \times 5)) \\86148 &:= (T(8) \times (((6 + 1)^4) - 8)) \\86163 &:= ((8 + T((T((6 - 1)) \times 6))) \times T(T(3))) \\86184 &:= ((T(8) + T(6)) \times (-T(-((1 - 8)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\86188 &:= (T(8) + ((T(6) + 1) \times T(88))) \\86226 &:= ((T(((T(8) - (6)) \times T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(6))) \\86229 &:= ((T(8) + (6/2)) \times T(T((2 + 9)))) \\86232 &:= (-T(8) - (-T(T((6 \times 2)))) \times T((T(T(3))/T(2)))) \\86253 &:= (-T((T(8) + T(6))) - (T(T((-2) + T(5)))) \times (-T(T(3)))) \\86265 &:= (-((T(8) - T(62))) \times T((-6) + T(5))) \\86273 &:= (8 - ((T(T((6 \times 2))) \times (-T(7))) + 3)) \\86274 &:= -(T(T(8)) + ((-T(6)) \times T(T((2 + 7))) \times 4)) \\86275 &:= (-8) - ((T(T((6 \times 2))) \times (-T(7))) - (T(5))) \\86276 &:= (8 - (T(T((6 \times 2))) \times (-7) - T(6))) \\86279 &:= ((8 + T(T(T((6/2)))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(9))) \\86286 &:= ((-T(8)) \times (T(T(6)) - T((2 \times T(8)))) - (6)) \\86292 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(6)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(9)) \times T(T(2)) \\86295 &:= ((T(T(8)) + T((T(6) \times 2))) \times T(T(9 - 5))) \\86297 &:= ((8 + T(6)) + (T(T((T(2) + 9))) \times T(7))) \\86328 &:= (((8 \times T((T(6) + 3))) - 2) \times T(8)) \\86344 &:= (-T(T(8)) - ((T(6) + T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(4)))) \\86346 &:= (T(T(8)) - ((T(6) + 3) \times T((4 \times T(6)))) \\86352 &:= ((-8) + (T((T(6) - T(3))) \times T(T(5)))) \times T(T(2)) \\86367 &:= (T(T(8)) + (T(T(6)) \times (T((T(3) + T(6))) - (7)))) \\86374 &:= (8 - ((-T(6)) \times T(T((T(3) + (7)))))) + T(T(T(4))) \\86385 &:= (((8 \times T((T(6) + 3))) \times T(8)) - (T(5))) \\86392 &:= (-8) - ((-6) \times (T((T(3) + 9))^2)) \\86394 &:= (T(T((T(8)/6))) \times (T((3 \times 9)) - (4))) \\86400 &:= (T(8) \times (6 \times 400)) \\86428 &:= (((T((8 \times 6)/4)^2) - 8) \\86436 &:= ((-8) \times (T(6^4)))/(-3 \times 6)) \\86452 &:= (-8) - ((-6) \times (T(4) + (T(T(5))^2))) \\86456 &:= ((T(8) \times 6) + (T(T(T(4))) \times 56)) \\86472 &:= (((-8) + T(T(6))) - T(4)) \times T(T(7)) - T(T(2)) \\86474 &:= (((-8) + T(T(6))) - T(4)) \times T(T(7)) - (4)) \\86480 &:= (T((T(8) + (6 + 4))) \times 80) \\86481 &:= (((-T(8)) \times T(T(6))) \times (-T(4))) + (T(81)) \\86496 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(T(6))) + (4)) \times 96) \\86526 &:= ((T(8)/6) \times ((T(T(5))^2) + (T(6)))) \\86534 &:= (((T(8) \times T(6)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(3 + T(4)))) \\86535 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(6)) \times T(T(5))) + T((T(3) \times T(5)))) \\86544 &:= (T(8) \times (((T(T(6)) - T(5)) \times 4) + T(T(T(4)))) \\86545 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(T(6))) \times (-T(5))) + (T(4)^5)) \\86555 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times (-T(6) + (5))) + (5)) \times (-5))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}86556 &:= (T(T(8)) - ((T((6 \times T(5))) - (5)) \times (-T(6)))) \\86561 &:= (((T(T(8)) + (T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) + (6))) - 1) \\86562 &:= (((T(T(8)) + (T(6))) \times (T(5) + (6))) \times T(T(2))) \\86565 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (-6) + T((-5) + T(6)))) - (T(5)) \\86583 &:= (((T(8) + T((6 \times T(5)))) - 8) \times T(T(3))) \\86588 &:= (8 - (-65) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(8)))) \\86589 &:= (-T(8)) - (T(T(6)) \times (-T(5) - (-8) \times T(9)))) \\86592 &:= (-8) \times (T(T(6)) - (5 \times T(T(9+2)))) \\86625 &:= ((-T(8) - T(6)) \times T(T(6))) \times (-25) \\86633 &:= (8 + (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(6) + T(3)) - 3))) \\86644 &:= (-T(8)) - ((-6 \times 6) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(4))) \\86646 &:= (((T(T(8)) + (T(6))) \times 6) + (4)) \times T(6) \\86652 &:= (((T(T(8)) + (T(6))) \times T(6)) + (T(5))) \times T(T(2))) \\86657 &:= (T(8) \times (6 + T(T(6)))) + (5^7) \\86661 &:= (T(T(8)) + (T(6) \times T((6 \times T((6-1)))))) \\86688 &:= (T((T(8) + (6))) \times (6 \times (8 + 8))) \\86691 &:= ((T(T(8))/6) \times (T((-6) + T(9)) + 1)) \\86694 &:= (-T(T(8))) - ((T(6) + T(6)) \times T((9 + T(T(4)))))) \\86696 &:= (8 - (T((T(6) + T(6))) \times (-96))) \\86697 &:= (((T(T(8))/6) + (6)) \times T((T(9) - (7)))) \\86724 &:= ((8 \times ((-6) + T(7))^{T(2)}) + T(T(T(4)))) \\86733 &:= (T((T(8) - (6))) - (-T(7) \times T(T(T(3) + T(3)))))) \\86743 &:= (-8) + ((T(T(6+7)) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(3))) \\86745 &:= (8 + (T((T(6) - (7))) \times T(T(4))) \times T(5)) \\86747 &:= ((8 - T(T(6))) \times ((7 + T(4)) - T(T(7)))) \\86757 &:= (8 + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(5) + T(7))) \\86764 &:= (-T(8)) - ((T(T(6)) - T(T(7))) \times T((T(6) + T(4)))) \\86775 &:= ((T(8) + T(T(6))) \times T((T(7) - T(7-5)))) \\86778 &:= ((T(8) \times ((6 \times T(T(7))) - (7))) - T(T(8))) \\86784 &:= -((T(T(8)) - ((-6) + T((7 \times 8))) \times T(T(4)))) \\86793 &:= (((T(8) \times 6) \times T(T(7))) - T((T(9) - 3))) \\86797 &:= ((T(8) - T((T(6) + T(7)))) \times (-T(9) + T(7))) \\86829 &:= (T(T(8)) - (-T(6) \times (8 + T((2 \times T(9)))))) \\86832 &:= (T(8) \times (T((T(6) + (8 \times T(3)))) - T(2))) \\86835 &:= (-T(86)) + (T(T(8)) \times T((T(3) - (5)))) \\86848 &:= (((8 \times T(T(6))) \times (-8) + T(T(4))) - 8) \\86849 &:= -((T((-8) + T(6)) - (84 \times T(T(9)))) \\86856 &:= (8 \times T(T(6))) \times (T(8) + (5 + 6)) \\86892 &:= (T(8) - (T(T(6)) \times (-8) \times (T(9) + 2))) \\86904 &:= (-T(8)) - ((-T(6)) \times T(T(9)) \times 04) \\86912 &:= ((T(8) \times T(69)) - T((1 + T(T(2)))) \\86914 &:= ((T(8) \times (T(69) - 1)) + T(4)) \\86920 &:= ((T(8) \times T(69)) - (20)) \\86922 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times (-6)) + T(9)) \times (-22)) \\86924 &:= ((T(8) \times T(69)) - (2^4)) \\86925 &:= ((T(8) \times T(69)) - (T(2) \times 5)) \\86927 &:= (((T(8) \times T(69)) - T(T(2))) - (7))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}86929 &:= ((T(8) \times T(69)) - (2 + 9)) \\86932 &:= (((T(8) \times T(69)) - T(3)) - 2) \\86933 &:= ((T(8) \times T(69)) - (T(T(3))/3)) \\86934 &:= ((T(8)/(-6)) + ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(3))) \times 4)) \\86935 &:= ((T(8) \times T(((T(6) + T(9)) + 3))) - (5)) \\86937 &:= (-T((8-6)) + (T(T(9)) \times (3 \times T(7)))) \\86938 &:= (((T(8) \times T(69)) + T(3)) - 8) \\86939 &:= -((T(T((-8) + T(6))) - ((T(9)^{-T(3+9)}))) \\86952 &:= (((T(8) \times T(69)) + T(5)) - T(2)) \\86955 &:= ((T(8) \times T((6 \times 9) + T(5))) + (T(5))) \\86956 &:= (((T(8) \times T(69)) - (5)) + T(6)) \\86961 &:= ((T(8) \times T(69)) + T((6 \times 1))) \\86964 &:= ((T(8) \times T(69)) + ((6 \times 4))) \\86972 &:= ((-8) + (-T(6) \times T(T(9)))) \times (-7 + T(2)) \\86975 &:= ((T(8) \times T(69)) + (7 \times 5)) \\86976 &:= (T(8) \times (T(69) + (7 - 6))) \\86979 &:= -((T(86) - (T(9) \times T((7 \times 9)))) \\86982 &:= ((T(8) + (6)) \times (-9) + T((8^2))) \\86985 &:= (((T(8) - T(T(6))) - (-9) \times T(T(8))) \times T(5)) \\86995 &:= ((T(8) \times T(69)) + T(T((9-5)))) \\87012 &:= (T(8) \times (T((70-1)) + 2)) \\87114 &:= -((T(T(8)) - (T((T(7) \times (1+1)) \times T(T(4)))))) \\87123 &:= (T(8) - ((-T((T(7)-1)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(3)))) \\87142 &:= -((T(T(8)) - (T(7) \times ((1 + T(T(4)))^2))) \\87176 &:= ((8 + T(71)) \times (T(7) + (6))) \\87192 &:= ((T(8) \times (-7)) \times (-1) + (T(T(9))/(-T(2)))) \\87219 &:= (-T(T(8))) - (T((7 + T(T((2+1)))) \times (-T(9))) \\87224 &:= -((T(T(8)) - ((T((T(7) \times 2)) + 2) \times T(T(4)))) \\87225 &:= (-T(T(8))) - ((T(T((7 + T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(T(2)))) + T(5))) \\87228 &:= ((8 + T((72 - T(2)))) \times T(8)) \\87235 &:= (-T(T(8))) - ((T(T((7 + T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(3)))) + 5)) \\87242 &:= (T(T(8)) - (-T(7) \times ((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4))) \times 2))) \\87246 &:= (T(T(8)) \times (-7) + (T(2) \times 46)) \\87255 &:= ((-T(T(8))) - ((-T(7) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(5)) \times T(5)) \\87256 &:= (-8) - ((T(T(7)) - 2) \times (T(5) - T(T(6)))) \\87262 &:= ((T(8) \times ((T(T(7)) - 2) \times 6)) - 2) \\87264 &:= (T(8) \times ((T(T(7)) - 2) \times T((6-4)))) \\87268 &:= (-8) - (-T(7) \times (T(T((2 \times 6))) + T(8))) \\87275 &:= (((T(8) \times T(T(7))) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(7))) - (T(5)) \\87276 &:= ((T((T(8) + T(7))) - 2) \times (7 \times 6)) \\87282 &:= (-8) - (-T(T(7))) \times ((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(8))))/(-T(2))) \\87289 &:= -((T(8) - (7))) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T((T(8) - 9)))) \\87293 &:= (8 - (T((T(7) - T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(9))/(-3))) \\87297 &:= (((T((T(8) + T(7))) \times T(T(2))) - 9) \times 7) \\87298 &:= ((8 - T(7)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T((-9) + T(8)))) \\87317 &:= -((8-7) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T((-1) + T(7)))) \\87324 &:= ((8 - T(T((7+3))) \times (-2) - T(T(4)))\end{aligned}$$

- 87326** := $(8 + (T((T(7) - (3 - 2))) \times T(T(6))))$
87333 := $((8 + 7) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T((3^3))))$
87336 := $((-T(T(8))) - T(T((7 + T(3)))) \times (-3 \times 6))$
87339 := $(T(8) + ((T(7) \times T(T((T(3) + T(3)))) + T(T(9))))$
87342 := $((T(8) \times ((T(T(7)) \times T(3)) - T(4))) + T(T(2)))$
87347 := $((T(8) - 7) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(7))))$
87354 := $((8 + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(3)) + T((T(5) + 4))))$
87355 := $((8 \times T((7 + T(3)))) \times T(T(5)) - 5)$
87372 := $((T(8) - T(7))^{T(3)} - T(7)) / T(2)$
87374 := $((8 \times 7) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T((-T(7) + T(T(4))))$
87375 := $((T((T(8) + T(7))) \times (T(3) \times 7)) + T(5))$
87384 := $((T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(3)) - T(T(8))) \times 4$
87393 := $((T(8) \times ((T(T(7)) \times T(3)) - 9)) + T(T(3)))$
87396 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) \times T(3) - T((T(9) - T(6))))$
87408 := $((-8) \times T(T(7))) + (T(40)) \times (-T(8))$
87416 := $((T(T(8)) \times 7) - T(T(T(4)))) \times T(1 + 6)$
87422 := $((8 \times 7) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(2)))$
87423 := $((T(T(8)) + T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(3))))$
87426 := $((8 \times T(T(7))) - T(4)) \times (T(T(2)) + T(6))$
87429 := $((-T(8) + T(T(7))) + 4) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9))$
87432 := $(8 \times ((7 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(3)))) + 2))$
87435 := $(87 \times ((T(4)^3) + 5))$
87444 := $((T(T(8)) + T(7)) \times (T((4 \times 4)) - T(4))$
87455 := $((T((8 \times 7)) \times T(T(4))) - T((5 \times 5)))$
87456 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(4))) + (T(5)) \times 6$
87464 := $(8 \times ((7 \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((T(6) - 4))))$
87465 := $((T((8 \times 7)) \times T(T(4))) - T(6) \times T(5))$
87472 := $((8 \times 7) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(7) - T(T(2))))$
87486 := $((8 - T(7)) + T((T(T(4)) + T(8)))) \times T(6)$
87489 := $(-T(8)) + ((T((7 + T(T(4)))) - 8) \times T(9))$
87492 := $((T(8) \times (7^4)) + T(T(9))) + T(T(T(2)))$
87497 := $((-8) + T((7 + T(T(4)))) \times T(9)) - T(7)$
87498 := $(-T(8)) + ((-T(T(7))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(9)) - T(8))$
87522 := $(T(T(8)) - (-T(7)) \times (T(T((T(5) - T(2)))) + T(T(T(2))))$
87523 := $((T(8) + 7) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T(2)^{T(3)})))$
87534 := $(-T(T(8)) - ((T(7) \times T(5)) \times T(T(3))) \times T(4))$
87536 := $(8 \times (7 + (T(5) \times (3^6))))$
87546 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) - (T(5) + T(4))) \times 6$
87552 := $((8^{T(7-5)}) \times T((T(5) + T(2))))$
87574 := $((8 \times T(T(7))) - T(T(5))) \times T(7) - T(4)$
87576 := $((T((T(8) + 7))) \times T(5)) + T(T(7)) \times 6$
87577 := $((8 \times T(T(7))) - T(T(5))) \times T(7) - 7$
87584 := $(8 \times (T(7) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(8) + T(T(4))))$
87622 := $((T(8) \times ((T(T(7)) \times 6) - 2)) - 2)$
87624 := $(T(8) \times ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + ((2 - 4))))$
87633 := $((8 + T(T((7 + 6)))) - T(T(3))) \times T(T(3))$
87641 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) \times 6) - T(T((4 \times 1)))$
87647 := $((T(T(8)) - 7) \times (T(6) - (-4 \times T(7))))$
87648 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) \times 6) - 48$
87655 := $(-T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5))) - 5))$
87659 := $(8 + ((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5))) - T(9)))$
87675 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) \times 6) - T(T(T((7 - 5))))$
87679 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) \times 6) + ((T(7) - T(9)))$
87682 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) \times 6) - 8) - T(T(2))$
87683 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) \times 6) + 8) - T(T(3))$
87684 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) \times 6) - (8 + 4)$
87688 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) / 6) \times T(8) - 8$
87693 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) \times 6) - (9 / 3)$
87696 := $((8 + T(7)) \times (T(69) + T(6)))$
87712 := $(8 \times ((T(T(7)) \times (T(7) - 1)) + 2))$
87716 := $((-8) + T(T(7))) + (T((T(7) - 1)) \times T(T(6)))$
87723 := $((T((8 + T((T(7)/7))))^2) \times 3)$
87724 := $((-8 \times 7) + (T((T(7) \times 2)) \times T(T(4))))$
87725 := $((T(8) - 7) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(5))))$
87726 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) + (7 - 2)) \times 6$
87729 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) + 7) \times T(T(2)) - 9$
87732 := $((8 + T(7)) \times T(T(7))) + (T(3)) \times T(T(2))$
87734 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) + 7) \times T(3) - 4$
87738 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) + 7) \times T(T(-(T(3) - 8)))$
87742 := $(-T(8)) + ((T((T(7) + T(7))) \times T(T(4))) - 2)$
87744 := $(-T(8)) - (-T((7 + 7) \times 4)) \times T(T(4))$
87745 := $((T((-8) + T(7))) \times T(T(7))) + T((T(T(4)) + T(5))))$
87752 := $(8 \times ((T(7) \times (T(T(7)) - T(5))) + T(T(T(2))))$
87753 := $((-T(8)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(75))) - T(T(T(3)))$
87754 := $((T(8) - 7) \times (T(T((7 + 5))) - T(T(4))))$
87772 := $(-T(8) + ((T(7)/(-7)) \times (T(7)^{T(2)})))$
87775 := $((T((8 \times 7)) \times T(T((T(7)/7)))) - 5)$
87783 := $(87 - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(8) \times T(3))))$
87786 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) + (7 + 8)) \times 6$
87792 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) + (7 + 9)) \times T(T(2))$
87793 := $(-T(T(8)) - (T(7) \times T(79))) + T(T(3))$
87795 := $((T(T(8)) - (-7) \times T((-7) + T(9))) \times T(5))$
87822 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) + T((8 - 2))) \times T(T(2))$
87825 := $((T(T(8)) - 7) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) / 5$
87842 := $(-T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) \times (-8 - T((T(4) \times 2))))$
87843 := $((87 + (8^4)) \times T(T(3))$
87844 := $(T(8) - ((T(7)^{T(8/4)}) \times (-4)))$
87849 := $(-T(8)) - (T((7 + T(T(8 - 4)))) \times (-T(9)))$
87856 := $((T(T(8)) - (T(7) - 8)) \times T((-5) + T(6)))$
87863 := $(-T(T(8) + 7)) - (T(T((-8) + T(6))) \times (-T(T(3))))$
87864 := $((8 \times 7) \times ((8 + T(6)) + T(T(T(4))))$
87872 := $(8 - ((T(T(7)) \times (-T(8))) - T(7)) \times T(T(2)))$
87892 := $((T(8) - T((T(7) + T(8)))) \times (-T(9) - 2))$

- 87894** := (((T(T(8)) × 7) - T(8)) × (9 + T(4)))
87906 := (T(((8 - 7) + 90)) × T(6))
87912 := (T(T(8)) × ((T((7 + 9)) - 1) - T(2)))
87933 := ((T(T(8)) × (T(-(T(7) - T(9)))) - (T(T(3)))) + (T(T(3))))
87939 := (((-8) × T(T(7))) - 9) × (-3 × 9))
87942 := (((T(8) × T(T(7))) + (T(9) - (4))) × T(T(2)))
87944 := ((T(T(8)) × T(7)) + ((T(9) × T(T(4)))) - 4)
87948 := ((T(T(8)) × (T((7 + 9)) - (4))) + T(8))
87955 := (((-8) + T((-7) + T(9))) × T(T(5))) - (5)
87958 := ((T(8) + T(T(7))) × ((T(T(9))/5) - 8))
87963 := (((-T(8)) × T(T(7))) - T(9)) × (-6) - 3)
87969 := (T(T(8)) + ((T(7) × T(T((-9) + T(6)))) + T(T(9))))
87976 := (8 × (-T(7)) + (9 × T((T(7) + T(6))))))
87978 := (-((T(8) + (7))) × (T(T(9)) - T(78)))
87984 := (T(((8 × 7) - 9)) × T((8 + 4)))
87993 := ((T(T(8)) + (7 × T((T(9) + T(9)))) × 3)
87999 := (((T(87) × T(T(9)))/T(9)) - T(9))
88128 := ((8 × 81) × T((2 × 8)))
88143 := (((T(T(8)) + T(T(8))) × T((1 + T(4)))) + T(T(T(3))))
88164 := (T(8) × (-T(8)) + T(((1 + 6) × T(4))))
88192 := ((8 × 8) × T((T((1 + 9)) - T(2))))
88215 := (T(8) - (T((T(8) + 2)) × (1 - T(T(5)))))
88218 := (T(T(8)) + ((8^{T(2)}) × T(18)))
88227 := (((-8) × T(T(8))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(7))))
88236 := (T(8) × (T(8) + T((T(T(2)) + (3 × T(6))))))
88240 := ((T(T(8)) + T(T((8 + 2)))) × 40)
88242 := ((T((8 × 8)) + T(T(T(2)))) × 42)
88245 := ((T(T(8)) + ((T(T(8)))/(-2)) × T(T(4))) × (-5))
88252 := -((T(T(8)) - ((T((T(8) + 2)) × T(T(5))) - 2))
88254 := -((T(T(8)) - (T((T(8) + 2)) × T((5 + T(4))))))
88256 := (((-T(8)) - T(T((8 + 2)))) × (-56))
88264 := (8 × (((8 × T(T(2))) × T(T(6))) - T(T(4))))
88270 := ((T(T(8)) + T((T(8) - 2))) × 70)
88272 := (T(8) × ((8 × 2) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(2))))
88326 := (((T(T(8)) + T(8)) × T(3)) - T(T(2))) × T(6))
88335 := (((8 × T(T(8))) + T(33)) × T(5))
88344 := ((T(T(8)) + (T(8) × T(34))) × 4)
88362 := (T(T(8)) + ((T(8) × T(3)) × T(T((6)/T(2))))))
88395 := (((-8) × T(T((8 + 3)))) + 9) × (-5)
88423 := (((8 × 8) × T(T(T(4)) - T(2))) + T(T(T(3))))
88425 := (((T(T(8)) × T(T(8))) - T((T(T(4)) - 2)))/5)
88432 := (-8) + ((T(8) + (4)) × T(T((T(T(3)))/T(T(2))))))
88438 := (((-8) + T(T(8))) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(T(3)) + T(8))))
88440 := (T(T((8 + T((8/4)))) × 40)
88444 := ((T(8) × ((-T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(4))))
88446 := ((T(T(8)) - (-T(8)) × T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(6))))
88452 := ((T(8) × T((T(8) - T(4)))) × (5 + 2))
88464 := ((T(8) + T((-8) + T(T(4)))) × (T(6) + T(T(4))))
88473 := (((T(8) × T((T(8) - T(4)))) × 7) + T(T(3)))
88474 := ((T(T(8)) - (T(T((8 + 4))) × (-T(7)))) + T(T(T(4))))
88480 := ((T(T(8)) - (-8) × T(T(4))) × 80)
88482 := ((T(T(8)) + T(8)) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-T(8) - T(T(T(2))))))
88493 := (((-8) + T(T(8))) × (-4) + ((T(9)³))
88495 := (((-T(T(8)) × T(T(8))) + T((T(T(4)) - 9)))/(-5))
88524 := (-T(8) - (T(8) × ((T(5) + T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(4))))
88525 := (((-T((8 × 8))) - (5^{T(T(2))})) × (-5))
88528 := (-8) - ((T(T(8)) - T(5)) × (-T((2 × 8))))
88536 := -((T((8 + 8)) × (T(5) - T(36))))
88542 := (-T(8) + (T(T(8)) × (T(T(5)) + (T(4) + T(2))))
88544 := (8 - ((T(T(8)) - T(5)) × (-T((4 × 4))))
88560 := (T(8) × ((T(8) + (5)) × 60))
88566 := (T(T(8)) - ((T(T((8 + 5))) × (-T(6))) + (6)))
88569 := ((T(T(8)) × ((-8) + T(T(5))) + (T(6)))) - 9
88572 := (T(T(8)) - (T(T((8 + 5))) × (-7 × T(2))))
88578 := (T(T(8)) × ((8 + 5) + T((7 + 8))))
88586 := (8 + (T(T(8)) × (T(T(5)) + (-8) + T(6))))
88624 := (8 × (((8 × T(T(6))) × T(T(2))) - T(4)))
88647 := (((-8) × T(8)) + ((T(T(6)) × T(T(4))) × 7))
88654 := (-T(T(8))) - ((8 - T((6 + 5))) × T(T(T(4))))
88659 := (T(8) + ((T(T(8)) + T(6)) × (T(T(5)) + 9)))
88661 := (((T(8) + T(T((-8) + T(6)))) × T(6)) - 1)
88662 := ((T(8) + T(T((-8) + T(6)))) × T(T((6/2))))
88665 := (((T(T(8))⁸⁻⁶ - T(T(6)))/5)
88668 := (((8 × 8) × 6) × T(T(6))) - T(8))
88683 := (-T(T(8))) - ((-8 - T(6)) × T(T((T(8)/3))))
88689 := ((T((T(8) + T(8))) - T(T(6))) × (-8 + T(9)))
88722 := (-T((T(8) + T(8))) + (-T(T(7)) × (T(T(2)) - T(T(T(2))))))
88739 := (8 + (((T(8) × T(T(7))) × T(3)) + T(T(9))))
88749 := -((T(T(8)) + ((-T(8)) × T((7 × T(4)))) + T(9)))
88792 := ((8 + T(8)) × (T((7 × 9) + 2))
88794 := (-T(T(8))) - (-T(8) × T((-7) × (T(9) - T(T(4))))))
88836 := ((8 + T(8)) × ((T(T(8)) × 3) + (T(6))))
88872 := (((T(8) + T((8 × 8))) × 7) × T(T(2)))
88896 := ((8 × 8) × ((T(8) × T(9)) - T(T(6))))
88924 := ((8 + T(8)) × ((T(9)²) - (4))
88925 := (((T((8 × 8)) - (T(9)^{T(2)})) - T(T(5)))
88927 := (-8) - ((T(T((T(8)/9))) × T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-7))
88943 := (8 - ((T(T(T((T(8)/9))))/4) × (-T(T(T(3))))))
88956 := ((T(T(8)) + (T((89 - 5)))) × T(6))
88968 := ((8 + T(T(8))) × (96 + T(8)))
88992 := (T(8) × ((T((8 + T(9))) + T(T(9))) + T(T(2))))
89133 := (T(((8 × 9) + 1)) × 33)
89136 := (T(8) × (-9) + T((T(13) - T(6))))
89155 := (((T(8) × T(9)) + 1) × 55)

- 89210** := (((T(8) × T(9)) + 2) × T(10))
89223 := (((T(T(8)) × T(9)) - T(T(T(2)))) + 2) × 3)
89232 := (8 × (((T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(T(3))))/T(T(T(2))))))
89234 := (-((T(T(8)) - (T(9)^{T(2)}))) - T((-T(3) + T(T(4))))
89235 := (((T(T(8)) × 9) - T((T(2) × 3))) × T(5))
89236 := (T(T(8)) - ((9^{T(T(2))}) - T(T(3)))/(-6))
89237 := ((-T(T(8))) × ((-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(3)) - 7)
89238 := (((T(T(8)) × (-T(9))) + 2) × (-3)) - T(T(8))
89242 := ((8 + (T(9)^{T(2)})) - T((T(T(4)) + T(T(2))))
89244 := (T(T(8)) × ((T(9) × T(2)) - (4/4))
89248 := (((T(T(8)) × (T(9) × T(2))) + (4)) - T(T(8))
89250 := (((8 × 9) - 2) × T(50))
89252 := (8 - ((-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(5)) + T(T(T(T(2))))))
89259 := (-((T(8) - (T(9)^{T(2)}))) - T((T(5) + T(9))))
89273 := (((T(T(8)) × (T(9) × T(2))) - T(T(7))) - T(T(T(3))))
89281 := ((-8) + (T(9) × T(2))) × T((T(8) + 1))
89283 := -(((T(T(8)) - (T(9)^{T(2)})) + T((8 × T(3))))
89284 := (-T(8)) + ((T(9 + 2)) - 8) × T(T(T(4)))
89289 := (((T(T(8)) × (T(9) × T(2))) - T(T(8))) + T(9))
89295 := (((T(8) + 9)^{T(2)}) - T((T(9) + T(5))))
89316 := (T(8) × ((T(9) × T(T(3 + 1)))) + (6))
89324 := (-T(T(8))) + ((T((T(9) - T(T(3))))²) - T(4))
89327 := (-T(T(8))) + ((T((T(9) - T(T(3))))²) - 7)
89334 := (-T(T(8))) - (T((T(9) - T(T(3)))) × (-T((T(3) × 4))))
89337 := (T((8 + T(9))) - (-T(T(3))) × T(T((T(3) + (7))))))
89346 := ((T((8 × 9)) × 34) - (6))
89349 := ((-8) + T(T(9))) × T((3 × 4) + 9)
89351 := (((T(T(8)) - 9) × T((T(T(3)) - (5)))) - 1)
89352 := (T((8 × 9)) × (T(3) + T((5 + 2))))
89355 := (((-8) + T(9)) × T(T(3))) × (T(T(5)) - (5))
89373 := ((T((8 × 9)) × (T(3) + T(7))) + T(T(3)))
89375 := (T(T((T(8)/9))) × (T((-3) + T(7)) × 5))
89376 := (T((8 × (9 - 3))) × 76)
89379 := -((T(T(8)) + (T(T(9)) × ((T(3) × (-7)) - T(9))))
89385 := ((-8) - (9 × (3 - T(T(8)))) × T(5))
89387 := -(((T(T(8)) - ((T(9)³))) + T(T(8))) + T(T(7)))
89424 := ((T(8) × 9) × T(((T(4) + T(2)) + T(4))))
89425 := (((T(8) × T(9)) × T(T(4))) + (T(25)))
89433 := (T(8) - ((9 × 43) × T(T(T(3))))
89445 := (89 × (T(44) + T(5)))
89452 := (-8) - (((T(T(9)) × (-4)) - T(T(5))) × T(T(T(2))))
89455 := (T(8) × T(((T(9) + T(4)) + T(5)))) - (5)
89475 := ((T(8) × T((-T(9)) + T(T(4)) × 7)) + T(5))
89488 := ((-8) + T(9 × 4)) × T((8 + 8))
89496 := (T(T(8)) - ((-94) × T(9)) × T(6))
89497 := (((T(8) × T(9)) × T(T(4))) - 9) + T(T(7))
89526 := ((T(8) × T(9)) - (T(T((T(5) - 2))) × (-T(6))))
89532 := ((T((T(8) + T(9))) - (5)) × (3^{T(2)}))
89535 := (((T(T(8)) × (-T(9))) + T(T(5))) × (-3)) - (T(5))
89562 := ((T(T(8)) - (T(95))) × (-T(6) + 2))
89568 := ((-T(8)) - T((T(9) + T(5)))) × (-6 × 8))
89586 := ((T(T(8)) + T(9)) × ((T(5) - T(8)) × (-6))
89593 := ((8 - T(T(T(9 - 5)))) + ((T(9)³))
89595 := (((T(T(8)) × 9) - T((T(5) - 9))) × T(5))
89604 := ((T(T(8)) - (T(T(9)) × (-T(6)))) × 04)
89622 := (((T(T(8)) + T(9)) × T(6)) + T(T(2))) × T(T(2))
89625 := (((T(T(8)) × 9) - (T(6) - 2)) × T(5))
89644 := ((T(T(8)) - ((T(T(9)) × (-T(6))) - T(4))) × 4)
89646 := (((T(T(8)) + T(9)) × T(6)) + T(4)) × 6)
89648 := (((8 × T(T(9))) + T((T(6) + T(T(4)))) × 8)
89649 := (((T(T(8)) - (T(T(9)) × (-T(6)))) × 4) + T(9))
89655 := (((-8) + T(T(9))) + T((-T(6)) + T(T(5)))) × T(5)
89664 := (-T(8)) - ((-T(9)) - T(T(6))) × T((T(6) + (4))))
89667 := (T((T(8) + T(9))) × (-((6/6) + T(7)))
89676 := (T(8) × ((T(T(9)) + T(T(6))) + T((T(7) + T(6))))
89685 := (((T(T(8)) × 9) + ((T(6) - T(8))) × T(5))
89688 := ((T(T(8)))/(-9)) × (-T((6 × 8)) + T(8))
89698 := ((8 + T(T(9))) × (T((T(6) - 9)) + 8))
89733 := ((T((-8) + T(9))) + T((T(7) × 3))) × T(T(3))
89735 := ((T(89) - (T(7)³)) × (-5))
89739 := (-T(8)) - ((-T((9 × 7))) + T(T(3))) × T(9))
89743 := ((8 + 9) - (-T(T(7))) × (-T(4) + T(T(T(3))))))
89745 := (((T(T(8)) × 9) - (7 + 4)) × T(5))
89748 := ((T((T(8) + T(9))) × T(7)) - T((T(4) × 8)))
89763 := (((T(T(8)) × (-T(9))) + (T(7) + T(6))) × (-3))
89766 := (((T(8) × (9 + T(T(7)))) + (T(6))) × 6)
89768 := (8 - (T(9 + 7)) × (6 - T(T(8))))
89775 := ((T(T(8)) + 9) × (-7 + (T(7) × 5)))
89784 := (T(8) × (9 + T((7 × T((8 - 4))))))
89793 := ((T(8) × (-9) - T(7)) + (T(9)³))
89796 := ((T(T(8)) × T(9 + 7)) - T((T(9) - (6))))
89802 := (((T(T(8)) × (-T(9))) + T(8)) × (0 - T(2)))
89823 := (((T(T(8)) × (-T(9))) + T(8)) × (-T(2))) + T(T(3))
89827 := (-((T(T(8)) + T(9))) + ((-8) + T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(7))))
89829 := (-T(8)) - (((T(9) × T(T(8))) × (-T(2))) + T(9))
89835 := (((T(T(8)) × 9) - (8 - 3)) × T(5))
89838 := (((T(T(8)) × (-T(9))) + T(8)) × (-3)) + T(8))
89846 := (8 - (T((T(9) - 8) + T(T(4)))) × (-T(6)))
89853 := (-T(8)) - (((-9) × T(T(8))) × T(5)) + T(T(3)))
89855 := -((T(T((T(8)/9))) - (T(T(8)) × (T(T(5)) + (T(5))))))
89856 := (-((T(8) - T(9))) × ((T(T(8)) × T(5)) - (6)))
89865 := (((T(T(8)) × 9) - T((8 - 6))) × T(5))
89874 := (-T(8)) - ((T(9) × T(T(8))) × (-7 - 4))

- 89875** := (((T(T(8)) × (9 - T(8))) + (7)) × (-5))
89886 := (((T(T(8)) × (-T(9))) + 8) × (-T((8 - 6))))
89893 := (-((8 + 9) - (T(T(8)) × (T(9) × (-3))))
89895 := (((T(T(8)) × 9) + ((8 - 9))) × T(5))
89905 := ((T(T(8)) × (T(9) + (90))) - (5))
89910 := (T(T(8)) × (T(9) + ((9 × 10))))
89912 := (((T(T(8)) - T(T(9))) × T(9)) - 1) × (-2))
89919 := (((T(T(8)) × T((T(9)/9))) + 1) × 9)
89922 := (((T(T(8)) - T(T(9))) × (-T(9))) + T(T(2))) × 2)
89925 := (((T(T(8)) × (-T(9))) - T(9)) × (-T(2))) - T(T(5)))
89928 := ((-((T(T(8)) - (T(99)))) × T(T(T(2)))) - T(8))
89937 := (((T(T(8)) × T(9)) + 9) × T(T(3)))/7)
89952 := (((T(T(8)) × (-T(9))) - (9 + 5)) × (-T(2)))
89955 := (((T(T(8)) × 9) + (T(9)/T(5))) × T(5))
89962 := (((T(T(8)) - (T(99))) × (-T(6))) - 2)
89964 := ((T(T(8)) + (9 × T(9))) × (T(6) × 4))
89973 := (((T(T(8)) × (-T(9))) - T(T(T(9 - 7)))) × (-3))
89976 := -(((T(T(8)/9)) + ((T(T(9)) - (T(T(7)) × T(T(6)))))))
89982 := (((T(T(8)) - T(T(9))) × (-T(9))) + T(8)) × 2)
89984 := ((T(T(8)))/(-9)) × ((9 × T(8)) - T(T(T(4))))
89992 := (-8) + (T((9 + T((T(9)/9))))²)
90112 := ((T(90) + 1) × (1 + T(T(T(2))))
90222 := ((T(90) + T(T(2))) × 22)
90228 := (((T(9)^{T(02)}) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(8))))
90585 := (9 × ((05 + T(T(8))) × T(5)))
90846 := ((-T(90)) - T(T(T(T(8/4)))) × (-T(6)))
90939 := ((90 × T(T(9))) - T((T(T(3)) + T(9))))
91114 := (((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) - 1) - T(4))
91115 := ((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) - T(-((1 - 5))))
91117 := ((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) - (1 + 7))
91118 := ((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) + ((1 - 8)))
91121 := (((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) - T(2)) - 1)
91122 := ((T(9)^{1×1+2}) - T(2))
91123 := ((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) - (T(T(2))/3))
91124 := (((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) + T(2)) - (4))
91125 := (T(9)¹⁻¹⁻²⁺⁵)
91126 := ((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) + (T(T(2))/6))
91128 := (((T(T(9)) × 11) + T(T(2))) × 8)
91131 := ((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) + T((3 × 1)))
91132 := ((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) + (T(T(3))/T(2)))
91136 := ((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) - (T(T(T(3)))/(-T(6))))
91138 := (((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) + T(T(3))) - 8)
91142 := (((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) - (4)) + T(T(T(2))))
91145 := ((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) + ((4 × 5)))
91146 := ((T(9)^{T(1+1+4)}) + T(6))
91155 := (((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) + T(5)) + T(5))
91167 := ((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) + (6 × 7))
91182 := (((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) + T(8)) + T(T(T(2))))
91245 := ((T(9)¹⁺²) + T((T(4) + (5))))
91272 := ((T(9)¹⁺²) + (7 × T(T(T(2))))
91293 := (((9 - 1) × T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(9)³)))
91332 := ((T((T(9) - 1)) - (T(3)^{T(3)})) × (-2))
91335 := (((-T(9)) × T(T((1 + T(3)))) + 3) × (-5))
91344 := (((T(9) - 1)³) + (T(T(T(4)) × 4))
91345 := (T(9) - (-T(T((1 + 3)))) × (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5))))
91346 := (((T(9)^{1×3}) - T(4)) + T(T(6)))
91362 := (((T(9)^{1×3}) + T(T(6))) + T(T(2)))
91388 := ((T(9) - 1) × (-3) + T((8 × 8)))
91392 := ((T((9 - 1)) + T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(9)^{T(2)})))
91395 := (T(9) × (T(((1 + T(3)) × 9)) + (T(5))))
91422 := ((-9) + (T((1 + T(4)) × T(T(T(T(2)))))) × T(T(2)))
91432 := ((T(9) - 1) × (T((4³) - 2))
91476 := ((T((9 - 1)) × (4 + 7)) × T(T(6)))
91485 := -((T(T(9)) + ((-T(14)) - T(T(8))) × T(T(5))))
91539 := (9 × (1 - ((-5) + T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(9))))
91575 := (T(9) × ((-((1⁵)) - T(T(7))) × (-5)))
91584 := (-T((9 - 1))) × (T(T(5)) + (T(T(8)) × (-4)))
91637 := ((T(T(9)) - T((1 + 6))) × T((T(3) + (7))))
91656 := ((T(T(9)) - T(T((1 × 6)))) × (T(T(5)) - (6)))
91679 := (-T(91)) + (T(T(6)) × (T(T(7)) + 9))
91697 := (-((9 + 1)) - (T(T(6)) × (9 - T(T(7))))
91728 := (T((-9) + T(-((1 - 7)))) × T((T(T(2)) × 8)))
91755 := (-T(9)) + ((-T(17)) × T(T(5))) × (-5))
91756 := (T((T(9) - (17))) × (-5) + T(T(6)))
91765 := (9 + (T(T((1 × 7))) × (T(T(6)) - (5))))
91834 := (T((T(9) + T(-((1 - 8)))) × 34)
91854 := (((T(T(9)) × (-1)) - T(T(8))) × (-54))
91857 := ((T(T(9) + 1)) × 85) - T(7))
91872 := (((9 - 1) × T(87)) × T(2))
91885 := (T((T(9) + (1⁸))) × 85)
91945 := ((T(9) + ((1 - 9))) × T((T(T(4)) + (T(5))))
91971 := (-T(9)) + (T(-((1 - 9))) × T(71))
91974 := ((91 × T(T(9))) - T(T((7 + 4))))
91995 := ((T(T(9)) × ((-1) + T(9)) + T(9)) - T(T(5)))
92028 := ((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T((T(T(02)) + T(8))))
92085 := ((T(9)^{T(2)}) + (08 × T(T(5))))
92115 := ((T(9)^{T(2)}) + (T(11) × T(5)))
92136 := ((T(T(9)) × (-2) + T(13)) + (T(6)))
92137 := (T(9) + ((T(T(T(2))) + 1) × T(T((T(3) + (7))))))
92139 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) - T(T((1 × 3)))) + T(T(9)))

- 92145** := $((T(9) \times (2^{1+T(4)})) - T(5))$
92149 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} - 1) - T(4)) + T(T(9))))$
92159 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} - 1) + T((5 \times 9))))$
92162 := $(T(T((9 - 2))) \times ((-1) + T(T(6))) - T(2)))$
92167 := $(-((T(9)^2) - ((-1) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(7))))$
92178 := $(9 - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times ((-1) - T(T(7))) + 8)))$
92183 := $((((T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2)))) - 1) \times T((-8) + T(T(3))))$
92197 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} + T(T(-(1 - 9)))) + (T(T(7))))$
92198 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} + T((1 + T(9)))) - 8)$
92211 := $((T((T(9) - T(T(T(2))))^2) + (T(T(11))))$
92224 := $((T(9)^{T(2)} - ((T(T(T(2))))^2 - T(T(4))))$
92232 := $(((-9) + T(22)) \times T(3^{T(2)}))$
92235 := $((T(9) - 2) \times T(-((T(T((-2) + T(3)))) - (T(T(5))))))$
92237 := $(((-9) - T(T(T(2 + 2)))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7))))$
92243 := $((T(T(9 - 2))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(T(4))) + 3))$
92245 := $((T(9) \times T((T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(5)))$
92246 := $((T(T(9 - 2))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T((4 + 6)))$
92247 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} - T(T(2))) + (T(47))))$
92248 := $(((-T(9) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(T(T(2))) + T(4)))) - 8)$
92253 := $((T(9)^{T(2)} + T((2 + (T(5) \times 3))))$
92255 := $((T(9)^{T(2)} - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5) \times (-5)))$
92256 := $(((-T(9) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((25 + 6))))$
92259 := $((T(9)^{T(2)} - ((T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times (-9)))$
92265 := $((T(9)^{T(2)} - ((T(2) - T(T(6))) \times 5))$
92268 := $((9 + 2) \times ((-2) - T(T(6))) \times (-T(8)))$
92272 := $((((T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(T(2)) + 7)))) - 2)$
92274 := $((T(9) - T(2)) \times ((T(2)^7) + T(4)))$
92283 := $((-((T(T(9)) - (2 \times (T(2) + (T(8)^3))))$
92284 := $((((T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(T(T(2))) - 8))) + T(4))$
92287 := $((T(9)^{T(2)} - ((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(8))) - (T(T(7))))$
92295 := $((((T(T(9)) - 2) \times T(T(2))) - T(9)) \times T(5))$
92325 := $((T(9)^{T(2)} + (T((T(3) - 2)) \times T(T(5))))$
92334 := $(T(9 + 2) \times (T(T(3)) + T((-3) + T(T(4))))$
92337 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} - T(3)) - (-3) \times T(T(7))))$
92343 := $((T(9)^{T(2)} - (-3) \times T(T(4 + 3))))$
92345 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} + T((-T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - 5)$
92346 := $((T(T(9)) \times (-2) + T((3 + T(4)))) + T(T(6)))$
92349 := $((T(9)^{T(2)} - (T((T(3) + T(4))) \times (-9)))$
92352 := $((T(9^2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (5 + T(T(T(2))))$
92355 := $((((T(T(9 + T(2)))) \times (-T(3))) + T(5)) \times (-5))$
92372 := $((-T((9 - 2))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(2))))$
92373 := $(((-9) \times T(2)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(3))))$
92376 := $(((-T(9) + T(T(T(2)))) + ((-T(3)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(6))))$
92379 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} - T(3)) + (T(7) \times T(9))))$
92382 := $((T(T(9)) + T(2)) \times (T((T(T(3)) - 8)) - 2))$
92385 := $(T(9) \times ((2^{3+8}) + 5))$
92391 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} + T(T(T(3)))) + T(T((9 \times 1))))$
92393 := $((((T(T(9)) + 2) + T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(9)^3)))$
92394 := $((9 \times T(T(2))) \times T(((3 + T(9)) + T(4))))$
92400 := $(T(T((9 - T(2)))) \times 400)$
92412 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} + T(T(T(4)))) - T((1 + T(T(T(2))))))$
92418 := $(((-T(T(9))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4)) + 18)))$
92420 := $((T(T((9 + T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 20)$
92422 := $((((T(T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) + 4^2) + T(T(2))))$
92424 := $((((T(9)/T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(2))) \times 4)$
92425 := $((T(9)^{T(2)} - (-4) \times T(25)))$
92427 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - 7)$
92442 := $((T(T((9 + 2))) - T(4)) \times 42)$
92443 := $((T(9) - 2) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (T(4) \times T(3))))$
92445 := $(T(9) - ((T(2) \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (-4 \times 5)))$
92448 := $((T(T(9)) - (T(2) + 4)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8)$
92451 := $((T(9)^{T(2)} + T(((T(4) \times 5) + 1)))$
92454 := $((9 \times T(T(2))) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (T(5) \times 4)))$
92455 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} + T(T(T(4)))) - (T((5 + T(5))))$
92460 := $((T(T((9 + T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times 60)$
92466 := $((((-T(9)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4))) + T(T(6))) \times 6)$
92470 := $((((T(T(9)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)))) \times 70)$
92475 := $(T(9) \times (((T(2) \times T(T(4))) - T(7)) \times T(5)))$
92482 := $((((T(T(9)) - T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8)) - 2)$
92484 := $((T(9) - T(2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(8)) - 4)))$
92485 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(8) \times 5))$
92488 := $((T(T(9)) + 2^4) \times 88)$
92496 := $(T((T(9) + 2)) \times (4 + T((-9) + T(6))))$
92497 := $((T(9)^{T(2)} - (-49) \times T(7))$
92519 := $((T((T(9) - T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) - T((1 + T(9))))$
92523 := $((-T(9)) - (-T(T(2 + 5))) \times (-T(2) + T(T(T(3))))$
92524 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} - T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4))))$
92525 := $(T(9) - ((T(T(T(T(2))) - 5)^2) \times (-5)))$
92526 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} + T(5)) + (T(T(2)) \times T(T(6))))$
92529 := $((((T(9) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(2)))) \times 9)$
92542 := $((((T(9)^{T(2)} - T(T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(2))$
92545 := $((((T(9)^{-2+5} + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5))))$
92547 := $(((-T(9)) - (-T(T(2))) \times T(T((5 - 4)))) \times 7)$
92565 := $((-T(T(9)) - (T(((T(2) + T(5)) + T(6))) \times T(T(5))))$
92568 := $((T(9) + T(T(2))) + 5) \times T((T(6) + T(8)))$
92574 := $(9 - ((-T(2)) \times T((5 + T(7)))) \times T(T(4)))$
92576 := $((T(T(9)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7)))) / (-6)$
92577 := $(9 + ((2 \times T(57)) \times T(7))$
92578 := $((-T(9)) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (5 - T(T(7)))) + 8))$
92583 := $(9 \times ((T(T(2)) \times T(58)) + T(T(3))))$

- 92584** := (((9 - (T(T(T(2))) × (-T(T(5)))))) × T(8)) + T(T(T(4))))
92595 := (((T(T(9)) × (-2)) + (T(5))) × (-T(9))) + T(T(5)))
92613 := (T(9) - ((T(2) - T(T(6))) × T(T((1 + T(3))))))
92614 := -((T((T(9) + T(T(2)))) + (-61) × T(T(T(4))))))
92622 := (((T(T(9)))/(-T(2))) + (6^{T(T(2))})) × 2
92625 := (9 + T((2 + T(6)))) × T(25)
92627 := ((T(9) × (T((2⁶)) - T(T(T(2)))))) - (T(7))
92628 := (((9 - (T(T(2))⁶)) × (-2)) - T(T(8)))
92634 := ((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) + ((T(6)³) × T(4)))
92637 := ((T(9)^{T(2)}) + ((6³) × 7))
92642 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) - T(6)) + T(T(T(4)))) - 2
92644 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) - T(T(T((6 - 4)))))) + T(T(T(4)))
92654 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) - (6 + 5)) + T(T(T(4))))
92655 := (((T(T(9)) - T(2)) × 6) - (T(5))) × T(5)
92658 := (-T((T(9) + 2))) - (-T(T(6))) × T(T((T(5) - 8))))
92659 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) - (6)) + T(T(T(-(5 - 9))))))
92664 := ((9 × T((2 + 6))) × (T(T(6)) + T(T(4))))
92665 := ((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T(T((T(6) - (6 + 5))))))
92673 := (-((T(T(9)) + (T((2 × 6)))))) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(T(3))))
92676 := ((T(9) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) + ((-6) + T(T(7))) × T(T(6)))
92682 := (-T(T(9))) - (-T(T(26)) × (T(8) + T(T(T(T(2))))))
92685 := ((T(9)^{T(2)}) - (-((T(6) - 8)) × T(T(5))))
92688 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T(T(6))) + T(T(8))) + T(T(8))
92691 := (-T(9)) - (T((T(2) × T(6))) × (-T(9) + 1))
92694 := ((T(9) - T(2)) × (T((T(6) + T(9))) - 4))
92714 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) - 7) + T((1 + T(T(4))))
92715 := (((T(T(9)) × T(T(2))) - (T(7) + 1)) × T(5))
92721 := ((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T((T(7) × (2 × 1))))
92723 := (-T(T(9))) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(7)))) + T((T(T(T(2))))/3))
92725 := (-T(T(9))) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(7)))) + (T(T(T(2))) + 5))
92741 := (-T(T(9))) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(7)))) + T((4 × 1)))
92742 := ((T(9)^{T(2)}) - (-7) × T(T((4 + 2))))
92743 := ((T(9)^{T(2)}) - ((T(T(7)) × (-4)) + (T(3))))
92745 := (((T(T(9)) × T(T(2))) + T(7)) - T(T(4))) × T(5)
92748 := (-T(T(9))) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(7)))) + T((T(4) - 8)))
92751 := (-T(T(9))) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(7 × (5 - 1))))
92752 := (((T(9) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(T(7)))) × T((-5) + T(T(T(2))))
92753 := -(((T(T(9)) - 2) - (T(T(7)) × T((T(5) + T(3))))))
92755 := (((T((T(9) - T(T(2)))) - 7) × T(T(5))) - 5)
92757 := (-T(T(9))) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(7)))) - T(T(-(5 - 7))))
92758 := (-T(T(9))) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(7))) + (T(5) - 8))
92762 := (-T(T(9))) + ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(7))) + (T(T(6))/T(T(T(2))))))
92763 := (((T(9²)) × T(7)) - T(T(6))) + (T(3))
92764 := -(((T(T(9)) - T(2)) - ((T(T(7)) × T(T(6))) + T(4)))
92766 := -(((T(T(9)) + T(T(2))) - ((T(T(7)) × T(T(6))) + (T(6))))))
92769 := ((9 × 2) + ((T(T(7)) × T(T(6))) - T(T(9))))
92772 := (-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(2))) + ((T(T(7)) × T((7 × T(2))))))
92773 := (-((T(T(9)) + T(T(2))) - T(7))) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(T(3))))
92776 := -(((T(T(9)) + ((T(2) - T(7)))) - (T(T(7)) × T(T(6))))))
92778 := ((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T(((7 × 7) + 8))
92779 := ((T(T(9 - T(2)))) × T(T(7))) - (-T(7) + T(T(9)))
92787 := (9 - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(7)))) + ((T(8) × T(7))))))
92790 := ((T(T(9)) + ((T(2) - 7))) × 90)
92792 := ((T(9²) - 7) × T((9 - 2)))
92793 := (T(9) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T(7)))) + (T(T(9)) + 3)))
92796 := (((9 + T(2)) + T(T(7))) × (-9) + T(T(6)))
92798 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) - T(7)) + T(T(9))) + T(T(8))
92799 := ((-9) × T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7) × T((9 × 9)))
92817 := -((T((9 × 2)) - (T(81) × T(7))))
92820 := ((T(T(9 - 2))) + T(8)) × T(20)
92826 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T(T(8))) + T(T((T(2) + 6))))
92827 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) + (T(8)²)) + T(T(7)))
92829 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T(T(8))) + T(2)) + T(T(9))
92832 := (((-9) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(8)³) × 2
92835 := (T(9) × ((2⁸⁺³) + T(5)))
92836 := ((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T((-8) + T((T(T(T(3)))/T(6))))))
92850 := ((9 - (T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-8))) × 50)
92853 := (T((9 × 2)) × ((T(8) × T(5)) + 3))
92857 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T((T(8) + T(5)))) + T(T(7)))
92859 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) - T(8)) + T(59))
92861 := ((T(T(9 + 2))) × (T(8) + 6)) - 1
92862 := ((T(9) - T(2)) × T(T((8 + (6/2))))))
92865 := (((T(9) × T(2)) × (T(T(8)) + (T(6)))) + T(T(5)))
92876 := -(((T((T(9) - 2)) - T(8)) - (T(T(7)) × T(T(6))))))
92880 := (-T(9)) × (T((T(T(2)) × 8) - (T(80))))
92883 := (-T((T(9) - T(2)))) - (-T((-8) + T(8))) × T(T(T(3)))
92884 := (((T(T(9)) + T(2)) × 88) + T(T(T(4))))
92886 := ((-T(9)) × (T(T(T(2))) - T((8 × 8)))) + T(T(6))
92895 := (((T(T(9)) × T(T(2))) - (8 + 9)) × T(5))
92896 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T(T(T((T(8)/9)))))) + T(T(6))
92919 := ((-T(T(9))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + (91 × T(T(9))))
92922 := (((T(T(9)) - T(2)) × T(9)) + T(T(T(2)))) × 2
92925 := (((T(T(9)) × T(T(2))) - (T(9)/T(2))) × T(5))
92928 := ((T(T(9)) + T(T(T(2)))) × ((9 + 2) × 8))
92934 := (9 × (T(T(2)) + ((T(T(9)) - 3) × T(4))))
92937 := ((-T(9)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(3))) × T(T(7))))
92943 := (9 × (((-2) + T(T(9))) × T(4)) - 3)
92946 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) - 9) + T((T(4) × 6)))
92952 := (((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T((T(9) + T(5)))) - T(2))
92955 := ((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T((9 - 5) × T(5)))

$$\begin{aligned} 92961 &:= (-9) \times (T(T(T(2))) - (T(9) \times (T(T(6)) - 1))) \\ 92964 &:= (((T(9)^{T(2)}) + 9) + T((6 \times T(4)))) \\ 92967 &:= (((9 \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times T(9)) - (T(6) \times T(7))) \\ 92968 &:= -((T(T(9)) + ((2 - T(T(9))) \times T((T(6) - 8)))) \\ 92972 &:= (((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T(T(9))) + (T(T(7)) \times 2)) \\ 92973 &:= ((-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-9) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))))) \\ 92976 &:= ((T(9) \times (-2 \times 9)) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 92979 &:= ((T((9^{T(2)})/9) \times T(7)) - 9) \\ 92982 &:= ((T((9 - 2)) \times T((T(9) + T(8)))) - T(T(2))) \\ 92984 &:= ((T((9 - 2)) \times T((T(9) + T(8)))) - (4)) \\ 92985 &:= (-T(9)) - (((T(T(2)) \times T(T(9))) - 8) \times (-T(5))) \\ 92988 &:= (T(9 - 2)) \times T(((9 + T(8)) + T(8))) \\ 92997 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (2 \times T(9))) - T((T(9) - T(7)))) \\ 93127 &:= (T(T(9)) - (-((T(T(3)) + 1) \times T(T((T(2)) + (7)))))) \\ 93132 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T((T(3) - 1))) - 3) \times T(T(2))) \\ 93135 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T(3)) - 1) \times (3 \times 5)) \\ 93145 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (T(3) \times T((1 + 4)))) - (5)) \\ 93165 &:= ((T(9)^3) + (T(16) \times T(5))) \\ 93177 &:= (-9) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T((-1) + T(7))) \times T(7))) \\ 93195 &:= (9 \times ((T((3 + 1)) \times T(T(9))) + (5))) \\ 93213 &:= (-T(T(9))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-2) - T(T((1 + T(3))))) \\ 93221 &:= (((T(9) - (T(3)^{T(2)})) \times (-2)) - 1) \\ 93222 &:= ((T(9) - ((T(3)^2)^{T(2)})) \times (-2)) \\ 93225 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T(3)) + (2 + T(2))) \times T(5)) \\ 93226 &:= (((T(9)^3) + T(T(T(2)))) + T((2^6))) \\ 93237 &:= ((-T((T(9) - T(3)))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 93242 &:= ((-T(9)) + ((T(3)^{T(2)}) + T(4)) \times 2) \\ 93247 &:= (((T((T(9) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(2))) + (T(T(4))) \times 7) \\ 93248 &:= (((-T(9)) + T(T(T(3))))/T(2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(8))) \\ 93249 &:= (((T(9) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4))) \times 9) \\ 93252 &:= ((-T(9)) + ((T(3)^{T(2)}) + T(5))) \times 2) \\ 93255 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T(3)) + (2 + 5)) \times T(5)) \\ 93264 &:= ((-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times ((T(T(2)) \times (-T(6))) + T(4)) \\ 93267 &:= ((9 - T(32)) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 93272 &:= ((T((9 + T(3))) - (T(T(2))^7))/(-T(2))) \\ 93273 &:= (-((T(9) - T(3))) + ((T(T(2))^7)/3)) \\ 93275 &:= ((T(T(9)) - T((T(3) - 2))) \times T((T(7) - T(5)))) \\ 93276 &:= ((-T(9) + 3) + ((-2) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(6))) \\ 93279 &:= ((T(T(9 - 3))) \times (-2) + T(T(7))) - T(9) \\ 93282 &:= ((-9) - T(T(3))) - (-2) \times (T(8)^{T(2)}) \\ 93285 &:= (T(9) - ((3 - T(T(2) + T(8)))) \times T(T(5))) \\ 93312 &:= (((9 - 3)^{T(3)}) \times (1 \times 2)) \\ 93321 &:= (9 - ((T(3)^{T(3)}) \times (-2 \times 1))) \\ 93324 &:= ((-T(9) - T(T(3))) \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 93325 &:= (((9 + (T(3)^{T(3)})) \times 2) - (5)) \\ 93327 &:= ((9/3) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (-2) + T(T(7)))) \\ 93328 &:= (((T(9)^3) + T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2))))) - 8) \\ 93330 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times (-3)) - (T(3))) \times (-30)) \\ 93331 &:= ((T(93) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(T(3 + 1)))) \\ 93333 &:= (((T(9)^3) - 3) + T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3))))) \\ 93334 &:= (((T(93) \times T(T(3))) + 3) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 93336 &:= ((T(9)^3) + T((T(3 \times 3)) + T(6))) \\ 93339 &:= (((T(9)^3) + 3) + T((T(T(3)) + T(9)))) \\ 93342 &:= (((T(9)^3) + T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + T(T(2))) \\ 93345 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T(3)) + (3 + T(4))) \times T(5)) \\ 93348 &:= (((T(T(9)) + (3 \times T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8)) \\ 93357 &:= (T(9) + ((T(3)^{T(3)}) \times (-5 - 7))) \\ 93366 &:= ((T((T(9) + 3)) + T(T(3))) \times T((6 + 6))) \\ 93372 &:= ((-T(9)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(3) + T((T(7) + T(2)))) \\ 93375 &:= (T(9) \times (T((T(3) \times T(3)) + T(7))) - (5)) \\ 93377 &:= (-((9/3)) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(7)))) + (T(T(7)))) \\ 93384 &:= ((T(9) \times T((3 \times T(T(3))))) + (T(T(8)) \times 4)) \\ 93387 &:= ((T(93) \times T(T(3))) + T((8 \times 7))) \\ 93393 &:= ((T(9)^3) + (T(3) \times T((9 \times 3)))) \\ 93429 &:= ((9 \times T(3)) \times T((T(T(4)) + T(2)))) + T(T(9)) \\ 93432 &:= ((T(9) + T(3)) \times (T((T(4) \times T(3))) + 2)) \\ 93435 &:= ((T(9)^3) + (T(4) \times T((T(3) + T(5)))) \\ 93436 &:= (((T(9)^3) + T((4^3))) + T(T(6))) \\ 93437 &:= ((T(9) \times (-3) + T((4^3))) - T(7)) \\ 93441 &:= (T(T(9)) - (T(3) \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(4))) - 1)) \\ 93448 &:= (9 - ((T((3 + T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + (T(T(8)))) \\ 93456 &:= ((T(T(9)) - T((3 + T(4)))) \times (T(T(5)) - (T(6)))) \\ 93465 &:= (T(T(9)) - (T(T(3 \times 4))) \times (-6 \times 5)) \\ 93469 &:= (((T(9)^3) + T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 93476 &:= -((T((T(9) - T(T(3)))) + (T(4) - (T(T(7)) \times T(T(6))))) \\ 93477 &:= (((T(9)^3) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 93483 &:= ((T(9) + T(3)) \times ((T(T(4)) - T(T(8))) \times (-3)) \\ 93484 &:= (((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8)) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 93485 &:= (((T(9)^3) + T(T(T(4)))) + T((8 \times 5))) \\ 93489 &:= ((-T(9) - T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(9)))) \\ 93492 &:= (9 \times (-((3 + 4) + (T(9) \times T(T(T(2))))) \\ 93495 &:= (((9 \times T(T(T(3)))) - 4) \times T(9)) + (T(T(5))) \\ 93519 &:= (((T(9) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (5 - 1)) \times 9) \\ 93522 &:= ((T(93) - T(T(5))) \times 22) \\ 93523 &:= ((T((T(9) - T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - (T(T(T(T(2))))/3)) \\ 93524 &:= (((T((T(9) - T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(4)))) \\ 93525 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times T(3)) + (5^2)) \times T(5)) \\ 93527 &:= ((9 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(5) \times T(2))) - (T(7)) \\ 93528 &:= ((T((T(9) - T(3))) \times T(T(5))) + (-2) \times T(8)) \\ 93534 &:= ((T((T(9) - T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) \\ 93537 &:= -((T(9) - (T(3) \times ((5^{T(3)}) - T(7)))) \\ 93542 &:= (((T((T(9) - T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(4))) - T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

- 93543** := (((9 × T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(5))) + 4) × (-3))
93546 := (-9) + ((3 × T(54)) × T(6))
93550 := ((T((T(9) - T(3))) × T(T(5))) - (50))
93555 := ((T(T(9)) + T(T((3 + 5)))) × 55)
93557 := ((T((T(9) - T(3))) × T(T(5))) - (T(5) + T(7)))
93567 := ((T((T(9) - T(3))) × T(T(5))) - (T(T(6))/7))
93571 := ((T((T(9) - T(3))) × T(T(5))) - (T(7) + 1))
93572 := (((T((T(9) - T(3))) × T(T(5))) - (7)) - T(T(T(2))))
93573 := ((-93) - T(T(5))) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(T(3))))
93576 := (((T(9) × T(3)) × T(5)) + T(T(7))) × T(6)
93579 := ((T((T(9) - T(3))) × T(T(5))) - T(T(T(-(7 - 9))))))
93582 := ((T((T(9) - T(3))) × T(T(5))) - (T(8)/2))
93584 := (((T(T(9)) - (T(3))) × T((5 + 8))) - T(T(4)))
93585 := ((T(9) × T((3 + 5) × 8)) - T(5))
93586 := ((T((T(9) - T(3))) × T(T(5))) - (8 + 6))
93591 := ((T((T(9) - T(3))) × T(T(5))) - (9 × 1))
93595 := (((T(9) × T(T(T(3)))) + 5) × 9) - 5)
93597 := ((T((T(9) - T(3))) × T(T(5))) - T(9 - 7))
93599 := ((T((T(9) - T(3))) × T(T(5))) - (9/9))
93609 := (9 × (T(3) + (T(T(6)) × T(09))))
93615 := ((T(9) × T((3 + 61))) + T(5))
93624 := ((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) + ((T(6)^{T(2)}) × T(4)))
93628 := (((T(9) + T(3)) × 6²) - 8)
93639 := (T((T(9 + 3)/6)) × (-T(3) + T(T(9))))
93645 := (T(9) × ((T(3) + T(64)) - (5)))
93646 := ((T(9) × T(3 × T(6))) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(6))))))
93647 := (T(9 × T(3))) + ((T(T(6)) - (4)) × T(T(7)))
93654 := (-(((T(9)³) + T(6))) - (-T(T(5))) × T(T(T(4))))
93666 := ((T(9)³) + ((T(T(6))/T(6)) × T(T(6))))
93672 := -((T(9 + T(3))) - ((T(T(6)) × T(T(7))) + T(T(2))))
93675 := -((T(T(9 - 3))) - ((T(T(6)) × T(T(7))) + T(T(5))))
93684 := ((-T(T(9))) - T(T(T(3)))) × (6 + (-8) × T(4)))
93711 := (-9) + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(7))) - (T(11)))
93713 := (-T(9)) - ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(7)))) + T((1 + T(3))))
93717 := ((T(T(9)) + (T(3) × T(T(7)))) × (-1) + T(7))
93720 := (-T(9)) + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(7))) - T(T(T((2 + 0))))))
93721 := (-T(9)) - (((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(7)))) + T(T(T(2)))) - 1)
93722 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) - (2^{T(T(2))})
93723 := (((9 × T(T(3))) × T((T(7) + T(2)))) - T(T(3)))
93724 := (-T(9)) - (((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(7)))) + T(T(T(2)))) - 4)
93725 := (-T(9)) - (((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(7)))) + T(T(T(2)))) - 5)
93726 := ((T(T(9) + T(3))) + ((T(T(7)) - T(T(2))) × T(T(6))))
93727 := ((9 + ((T(3)⁷)/T(2))) + T(T(7)))
93728 := (-T(9)) + (((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(7))) - T(T(T(2)))) + 8)
93729 := (9 + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(7))) - (T(2 + 9))))
93731 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) - T(T(3 + 1)))
93732 := ((-9) × T(3)) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(3 × 2)))
93734 := (((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) + 3) - T(T(4)))
93735 := (T(9) × (3 + T((T(7) + T(3 + 5))))))
93737 := (((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) - T(T(3))) - T(7))
93738 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) - (T(3) × 8))
93740 := (9 + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(7))) - (T(T((4 + 0))))))
93741 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) - T((T(4) - 1))
93742 := (((T(9) + 3) × T((7 + T(T(4)))))) - 2)
93743 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) - 43)
93744 := ((93 × T(7)) × T((4 + 4)))
93745 := (9 - ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(7)))) + (T(4) × 5)))
93746 := (9 - ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(7)))) + (T(T(4)) - (6))))
93747 := (9 - ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(7)))) + (T(T(4)) - (7))))
93748 := (9 + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(7))) - (T(T(4)) - 8)))
93749 := (9 - ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(7)))) + (T(T(4)) - 9)))
93751 := (-T(9)) - ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(7)))) - T((5 - 1)))
93752 := (-T(9)) - ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(7)))) - (5 + T(T(2))))
93753 := ((T(9)³) + T((75 - 3)))
93755 := ((T(9)³) + ((T(T(7)) + T(T(5))) × 5))
93756 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) - (5 × 6))
93758 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) - T((T(5) - 8)))
93759 := (-((9 × 3)) - (-T(T(7)) × T((T(5) - 9))))
93761 := ((-T(9)) + T(T(3))) + ((T(T(7)) × T(T(6))) - 1)
93762 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) - (T(6) + T(2))
93764 := (-((9 + 3)) + ((T(T(7)) × T(T(6))) - T(4)))
93765 := (T((9 - 3)) × T((T(7) + T((6 + 5))))))
93766 := (-9) - ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6))/T(6)))
93767 := (-((9 + 3)) + ((T(T(7)) × T(T(6))) - (7)))
93768 := (9 - (((3 - T(T(7))) × T(T(6))) - T(T(8))))
93770 := (-9) + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(7))) - (7 + 0))
93771 := ((T(9)/(-3)) + (T(T(7)) × T(T((7 - 1))))))
93772 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) - (7 × 2)
93773 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) - (7 + T(3))
93774 := (9 + (T(T(3)) × T((T(7) + T((7 + 4))))))
93775 := (-9) - ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(7)))) + (7 - 5))
93776 := (-((9/3) + 7)) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(6)))
93777 := (-9) - ((-3) × T(T(7)) × 77)
93778 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) + ((T(7) - T(8))))
93779 := (9 - ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(7)))) + (7 + 9))
93782 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) - (8/2)
93783 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) - T((8 - T(3)))
93784 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) - (8/4)
93785 := (((9 + T(T(T(3)))) × T(T(7))) - (T(85)))
93786 := (T(((9 × 3) - 7) + 8)) × T(T(6))
93787 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) + (8 - 7)
93789 := (((93 × T(7)) × T(8)) + T(9))
93792 := ((T(T(9 - 3))) × T(T(7))) + (9 - T(2))
93794 := (9 + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T(7))) - (-9 + T(4))))

- 93795** := ((T(T(9-3))) × T(T(7))) + (T(9)/5))
93797 := (9 - ((T(T(T(3))) × (-T(T(7)))) - (9 - 7)))
93813 := ((9 × 3) - (-T(T((8-1)))) × T(T(T(3))))
93816 := ((9 + T(T(3))) + (T(T((8-1)))) × T(T(6)))
93825 := (T(9) × ((3 + T((8 × 2))) × T(5)))
93828 := -((T(T(9) - T(3))) - (T(8) × T((2 × T(8)))))
93829 := (((T(T(9) - T(T(3)))) + 8)² - T(T(9)))
93831 := (T(9) + (T(T(T(3))) × T(T(((T(8)/T(3)) + 1))))
93834 := ((T(T(9) - (T(T(3)) × (-8))) × T(3 × 4))
93837 := ((T(9) + T(3)) + (T(T((T(8)/T(3)))) × T(T(7)))
93844 := ((T(9)³) + ((T(T(8)) × 4) + T(T(4)))
93852 := (T(9) + ((T(T(T(3))) × T(T((-8) + T(5)))) + T(T(T(2))))
93855 := ((T(9)³) + ((T(T(8)) - T(T(5))) × 5))
93867 := ((9^{-T(3)+8}) + (T(T(6)) × T(T(7)))
93885 := ((T(9) × (T(3) + T((8 × 8)))) + T(5))
93894 := (9 - (((-T(3)) - T(T(8))) - T(T(9))) × T(T(4)))
93895 := (((T(9)³) + T((T(T(8))/9))) - 5)
93897 := (T(T(9) - (T(T(T(3))) × ((T(8)/9) - T(T(7))))
93911 := (((T(T(9)) - 3) × 91) - 1)
93912 := ((T(T(9)) - 3) × T((9 + 1) + T(2)))
93915 := (((-T(9)) - (T(3) × (T(T(9)) + 1))) × (-T(5)))
93924 := (9 - (3 × (T(T(9)) - (T(T(T(2))) × T(T(T(4))))))
93927 := ((T(T(9) + 3)) - T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(7)))
93933 := (9 × (T((3 + T(9))) + (T(T(3))³)))
93945 := (((-T(9)) + T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(5))
93948 := (((T(T(9)) - 3) × T((9 + 4))) + T(8))
93957 := (T(9) + ((-3) + T(T(9))) × T(-((T(5) - T(7))))
93961 := (((9 × T(T(T(3)))) × T(9)) + T(T((6 + 1)))
93967 := (((9 × T(T(T(3)))) × T(9)) + (6 + T(T(7)))
93972 := (((-T(9)) + (T(T(-((3 - 9)))) × T(T(7)))) + T(T(T(T(2))))
93975 := ((T(9)^{-T(3)+9}) + T(75))
93978 := (T(9 × 3) - (-T(9)) × T((T(7) + T(8))))
93984 := ((T(T(9) + T(T(3))) × (9 - (-8) × T(4)))
94114 := (9 + (T(T(4)) × T((T((1 + 1)) + T(T(4))))))
94116 := (T((T((9 + 4)) + 1)) × (1 + T(6)))
94122 := (((-9) - T((T(T(4)) - 1))) × T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(2))
94137 := ((-T(T(9))) - (T(T(T((4 - 1)))) × (-T(3)) - T(T(7))))
94139 := ((9 - T(T(4))) - (-T(13)) × T(T(9)))
94162 := ((T((9 × T(4))) - 1) × (T(6) + 2))
94176 := ((-9) + (T(T((T(4) - 1))) × T((7 + 6))))
94182 := ((T(T(9)) × T(((4 + 1) + 8))) - T(2))
94185 := (T((9 + 4) × T(((1 + 8) × 5)))
94194 := (9 + (T(T((T(4) - 1))) × T((9 + 4)))
94206 := ((T(T(9)) × T((T(4) + T(2)))) - (0 - T(6)))
94213 := ((T(T(9)) × T((T(4) + T(2)))) + T((1 + T(3))))
94224 := (9 + ((T(T(T(4)) + T(2))) + 2) × T(T(4)))
94227 := (((T(T(9)) × (T(4) + T(2))) + T(T(2))) × 7)
94230 := ((T(94) × T(T(T(2)))) + (T(30)))
94234 := (((T(T(9)) × T((T(4) + T(2)))) - (T(3))) + T(T(4)))
94236 := ((T(9) × T(4)) - (T(T((T(T(2))/3))) × (-T(T(6))))
94237 := (((T(9) × T((4^{T(2)}))) + T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(7))))
94239 := ((T(T(9)) × T((T(4) + T(2)))) + (T(3) × 9))
94254 := (9 - ((T(T(4) + T(T(2))) × (-5) - T(T(T(4))))))
94257 := ((9⁴) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(5)) × (-T(T(7))))
94261 := ((-T(9)) - ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(2))) × (-61)))
94262 := ((T(T(9)) × T((T(4) + T(2)))) - (T(T(6)) / (-T(2))))
94263 := ((T(T(9)) × T((T(4) + T(2)))) + T((6 + T(3))))
94266 := ((T(9) × T((4^{T(2)}))) + T((6 × 6)))
94273 := (((-9) + T((T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(T(3))))
94275 := (T(T(9)) - (T(T((4 × 2))) × (T(7) × (-5))))
94276 := ((T(T(9)) × T((T(4) + T(2)))) + (T((7 + 6))))
94279 := (94 + (T((T(T(2)) + 7)) × T(T(9)))
94281 := ((9 × T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-T(T((8 - 1))))))
94284 := (9 × (((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) × 8) + 4))
94305 := ((T(T(9)) × T((T(4) + 3))) + T(T(05)))
94322 := (((-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(3)^{T(T(2))}) × 2)
94323 := ((T((9 × T(4))) + (T(3))) × 23)
94325 := (((-T((T(9) + 4))) × T(T(T(3)))) / (2 - 5))
94327 := ((T(9) + T((T(4) + T(T(3)))))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(7)))
94329 := (9 × (-4) + ((T(T(T(3))) + 2) × T(9)))
94332 := (((-T((T(9) + 4))) × T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(3))) / (-T(2)))
94333 := (((-9) + T(T(4)))³ - T((T(T(T(3))/3)))
94341 := (((-9) - (-T(4) × T(T(T(3)))) × 41)
94345 := ((-T(T(9))) - ((T(T(T(4))) × 3) - (T(4)⁵)))
94365 := (((T(T(9)) + T(4)) × T(3)) + (T(6))) × T(5))
94367 := ((T(T(9)) + (-4) + T(3)) × T((6 + 7)))
94368 := (((T(94) - 3) × T(6)) + T(T(8)))
94372 := ((-T(T(9))) - (((-4) - T(T(T(3)))) × T(T(7))) + T(2))
94376 := (9 + ((-T(4) + T(T(T(3)))) × (T(T(7)) + (T(6))))
94395 := ((T(T(9)) - T((T(4) + T(3)))) × T((9 + 5)))
94416 := ((T(T(9)) × T((T(4) + (4 - 1)))) + T(T(6)))
94425 := ((T(94) + T((T(4) × T(T(2)))) × T(5))
94426 := ((-9) + (T(T(4)) × (T((T(T(4)) + T(2))) + 6)))
94428 := (((T((-9) + T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(4)))) + 2) × T(8))
94434 := (((9 + T(T(T(4)))) × (T(T(4)) + (T(3)))) - (T(T(4))))
94438 := (((-9) + T(T(4))) × (T(T(4)) - (-3) × T(T(8))))
94440 := (((-T(T(9))) - T((-4) + T(T(4)))) × (-40))
94445 := ((-T(T(9))) - (T(T(T(4))) × (4 - T((-4) + T(5))))))
94446 := (T((9 + 44)) × T(-((T(4) - T(6))))
94458 := ((9 + 4) × ((T(T(4)) × T(T(5))) + T(T(8))))
94464 := (9 × ((T(4)⁴) + T((T(6) + T(4))))
94465 := (((9 + T(T(4))) × T(T(T(4)))) - (T((6 × T(5))))

- 94482** := (((T(T(9)) × (T(4) - T(T(4)))) - T(T(8))) × (-2))
94494 := (((T(T(9)) + (4)) × T((4 + 9))) - T(T(4)))
94495 := (((-T(9)) + T((T(4) + T(T(4)))) × T(9)) - 5)
94527 := ((T((T(9) - (4))) - T(T(5))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(7))))
94535 := ((T(9) - T(4)) × T((-5) + T((-3) + T(5))))
94536 := (((T(T(9)) × (T(4) + (5))) + T(T(T(3)))) × 6)
94545 := (T(9) × (T(T((-4) + T(5)))) + (T(4) - T(T(5))))
94550 := (T(((9) + T(T(4))) + (T(5)))) × 50)
94567 := ((T(T(9)) + (T(4)⁵)) + (T(T(6)) × (-T(7))))
94572 := (T((9 × 4)) × ((5 × T(7)) + 2))
94577 := (((T(T(9)) + (4)) × T(-(T(5) - T(7)))) + (T(7)))
94587 := (((9⁴) × T(5)) - T(87))
94635 := (((9⁴) - T(T(6))) - T(T(3))) × T(5)
94637 := ((-T(9)) - T(T(T(4)))) + (((T(T(6)) + (T(3))) × T(T(7))))
94645 := ((-9) × T((T(T(4)) - (T(6)))) + (T(4)⁵))
94647 := (T((T(9) - (4))) - (T(T(6)) × (-T((4 × 7))))
94662 := -(T(T(9)) + ((T(T(4)) - (6)) × (-T(62))))
94667 := ((T(T(9)) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(6)) × (6 + T(T(7))))
94668 := ((T(94) × T(6)) + T((6 + T(8))))
94674 := ((-9 × 4) + (T(T(6)) × (T(T(7)) + (4))))
94686 := ((T(T(9)) + T(-(T(4) - T(6)))) × 86)
94695 := (T(T(9)) - ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(6))) × (-T(9) + T(5))))
94722 := (9 - (((-4) - T(T(7))) × T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(2)))
94725 := -(T(T(9)) + ((-4) × T((T(7) × 2))) × T(5)))
94727 := (T(9) - (((-4) - T(T(7))) × T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7))))
94728 := (T(T((9 - 4))) + (T(72) × T(8)))
94735 := -(T((-9) + T(T(4))) + (-T(T(7))) × (T(T(T(3))) + 5)))
94743 := (-9) - ((T(47) × (-4)) × T(T(3)))
94746 := (9 × 4) + ((T(T(7)) + (4)) × T(T(6)))
94752 := ((94 × T(7)) × T((5 + T(2))))
94755 := (T(9) + ((4 + T(T(7))) × T(T(T(T(5)/5))))
94763 := ((T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + ((T(T(7)) × T(T(6))) - 3))
94765 := ((T(9) × ((T(T(4)) - T(T(7))) × (-6))) - 5)
94766 := ((T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + (T((7 + T(6))) × T(T(6))))
94773 := (-T((T(9) - T(4))) - ((-7) - T(T(7))) × T(T(T(3))))
94776 := (T(((T(9) × T(4)) - T(T(7)))) + ((T(T(7)) × T(T(6))))
94779 := ((T(9)⁻⁴⁺⁷) - (T(T(7)) × (-9)))
94788 := (((94 × T(7)) × T(8)) + T(8))
94797 := (T(9) + (47 × T(9 × 7)))
94815 := (9 × (-T(4)) + (T((T(8) + 1)) × T(5)))
94821 := (T(T(9)) - (T(T(T(T(T(4) - 8)))) × (-T(T((T(T(2)) + 1))))))
94825 := (T((T(9) + (4))) + (T((T(8) + T(2))) × T(T(5))))
94827 := ((T(T(9)) + T(T((T(4) - 8)))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) × T(T(7))))
94845 := (((T(T(9)) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8)) + T(-(T(T(4)) - T(T(5))))
94852 := (((T(T(9)) - (4)) × T((8 + T(5))))/T(2))
94857 := (((9 × (T(T(T(4))) - T(8))) + T(5)) × 7)
94867 := ((T(T(9)) + (T(4) + T(8))) + (T(T(6)) × T(T(7))))
94875 := (((-T(T(9))) × T(T(T(4))))/(T(8) × (-7))) × T(5))
94876 := ((9 + T((T(4) + T(8)))) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(6))))
94887 := (-9) + ((4 × T(8)) × (T(T(8)) - (7)))
94892 := ((-T((9 + 4))) × (-8 - T(T(9)))) - T(T(T(2)))
94922 := ((9 - T(T(T(4)))) × ((-T(9)) + T(T(T(T(2))))/(-T(2))))
94932 := (-9) - (((-4) × T(9)) - T(T(T(3)))) × T(T(T(T(2))))
94962 := ((T(9) + (4)) × (T(T(9)) + T((T(6) × 2))))
94965 := (((T(T(9)) × T(T(4)))/9) + (6)) × T(5)
94968 := (((-9) + T(T(4))) × 9) × T(T(6)) - T(T(8))
94994 := ((-T((9 + 4))) × (-9 - T(T(9))) - T(4))
94995 := (T(9) × ((-4) + T(T(9))) + (9 × T(T(5))))
94997 := ((-T((9 + 4))) × (-9 - T(T(9))) - 7)
95127 := (-T(9)) + (T(T((5 + 1))) × (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))))
95172 := (T(T((-9) + T(5))) × (T(T((1 × 7))) + T(T(2))))
95175 := ((T(9) × T(5)) × (1 + (T(7) × 5)))
95215 := ((T(T(9)) × (T((T(5) - 2)) + 1)) - 5)
95219 := (((T(T(9)) × T((T(5) - 2))) - 1) + T(T(9)))
95232 := ((T(95) × T(T(T(2)))) - T(32))
95235 := ((T(T(9)) × (T(T(5)) - T((T(T(T(2)))/3))) + T(5))
95238 := ((9 × T(5)) + (2³)) × T(T(8))
95256 := ((T((-9) + T(5)))²) × (-T(5) + T(T(6)))
95264 := ((T(95) × T(T(T(2)))) - (T((T(6) + T(4))))
95265 := -(T(9) × (T((5 + 2)) - T(65)))
95267 := (95 - (T(T(T(T(2)))) × (-6) - T(T(7))))
95274 := ((T(T((-9) + T(5))) + T(T(2))) × (T(T(7)) - (4)))
95277 := ((T((-9) + T((T(5) - 2))) × T(7)) - 7)
95295 := ((T(95) × T(T(T(2)))) - (T((T(9) - T(5))))
95322 := (((T(95) - T(T(3))) × T(T(T(2)))) + T(2))
95325 := ((-T(9)) + T((T(T(5))/3))) × (T(2) + T(T(5)))
95326 := (T(T(T(9 - 5))) - (T(T((T(T(3))/T(2)))) × (-T(T(6))))
95328 := (((T(T(T(9))/T(5))) + T(T(T(3)))) + 2) × T(8)
95337 := ((T(T(9)) × (T(5) × T(3))) + (3⁷))
95349 := ((9 - T(T(5))) × (T(T(T(3))) - ((T(T(4)) + T(T(9))))))
95355 := (T(T(9)) + ((T(T(5)) + T(T((3 + 5)))) × T(T(5))))
95367 := (T(T(9)) + (((T(5)³) - (6)) × T(7)))
95427 := ((T(T(9))/(-5)) × (4 - T((2 + T(7))))
95437 := (((-9) + T(T(5))) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(3))) × T(T(7)))
95445 := ((T(T(9)) × T(5)) + (T(T((4 + 4))) × T(T(5))))
95455 := -(T(95) - ((T(4)⁵) + T(5)))
95469 := ((T(9) × T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))) - (T(6) + T(T(9))))
95472 := (T((-9) + (T(5) × 4)) × 72)
95474 := ((9 - T(5)) - (T(T(T(4))) × (-7) - T(T(4))))
95475 := ((T(T(T(9 - 5)))) × (T(T(4)) + (7))) - 5)
95505 := (((T(9) - T(T(5))) × (-T(50))) - T(T(5)))
95524 := ((9 + T((5 × 5))) × (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4))))
95535 := (((T(T(9) + (5))) × 5) - (T(3))) × T(5))
95565 := (((T(95) - T(5)) × T(6)) + T(T(5)))

- 95571** := $((-9) + T(T(5))) \times T((5 + T((7 + 1))))$
95585 := $((T(T(9) + (5))) \times (-T(5))) + 8) \times (-5)$
95586 := $(T(T(9)) + ((T(T(5)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)))) + T(T(6))))$
95589 := $((9 + T(T(5))) \times ((T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) - T(9)))$
95597 := $(((-T(9)) + T(T(5))) \times T((5 + T(9)))) - T(7)$
95613 := $((T(95) - (6 + 1)) \times T(T(3)))$
95616 := $(T((T(9) + T(5))) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T((1 + 6))))$
95622 := $((T(T(9)/5) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(2))) \times 2$
95624 := $((T(95) \times T(6)) - T(2^4))$
95625 := $((-T(9)) + T(T(5))) \times T((T((6 - 2)) \times 5))$
95627 := $((T(T(9)/5) \times T(T(6))) \times 2) - (7)$
95632 := $((T(95) - (6)) \times T(T(3))) - 2$
95634 := $((T(T(9)/5) \times T(T(6))) \times (T(3) - (4)))$
95637 := $(T((T(9) - T(5))) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(3) + T(T(7))))$
95642 := $((T(T(9)/5) \times T(T(6))) + (4)) \times 2$
95655 := $((T(95) \times T(6)) - T(T(5))) + (T(5))$
95676 := $((T(T(9)/T(5)) \times T(T(6))) + (7)) \times 6$
95679 := $(9 - ((T(5) \times (-6)) \times (T(7) + T(T(9))))$
95680 := $((T(95) \times T(6)) - (80))$
95682 := $((T(95) \times T(6)) - T((T(8)/T(2))))$
95688 := $((T(95) \times T(6)) - T(8)) - T(8)$
95697 := $((T(95) \times T(6)) - ((9 \times 7)))$
95724 := $((9 + (-T(5)) \times T((T(7) \times 2))) \times (-4))$
95725 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(-((T(5) - T(7)))) + T(T((2 \times 5))))$
95742 := $(9 \times (5 + (7 \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2))))))$
95745 := $((T(95) \times T(T((7 - 4)))) - (T(5)))$
95746 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(-((T(5) - T(7)))) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(6)))$
95748 := $((T(T(9)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(7))) + T((4 \times 8)))$
95755 := $((T(95) \times T(T((7 - 5)))) - 5$
95756 := $((-T(9) + T(5)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-5 - T(T(6))))$
95775 := $((T(95) \times (-7 + T(7))) + T(5))$
95787 := $((T(9)^{T(-5+7)}) + (T(T(8)) \times 7))$
95795 := $(T(T(9)) + ((T(T(5)) - T(7)) \times (T(T(9)) - (5))))$
95796 := $((T(T(9)) / (-T(5))) + ((T(T(7)) + 9) \times T(T(6))))$
95823 := $((9 \times (-5) + (8^{T(2)})) \times T(T(3)))$
95825 := $(9 - (-T(T((T(5) - 8)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 5))$
95832 := $((T(9) - T(5)) + T(8))^3 / T(2)$
95835 := $((-T(9)) - ((-T((5 \times 8))) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(5)))$
95837 := $((T(T(9)) + T(T(5))) \times 83) - T(7)$
95838 := $((T(T(9)) \times T((5 + 8))) + T((T(T(3)) + T(8))))$
95845 := $((T(T(9)) \times T((5 + 8))) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)))$
95862 := $((9 + T(T((T(5) - 8)))) \times T(T(6))) - T(2)$
95865 := $((T(9) - T(T(5))) - 8) \times T(T(6)) \times (-5)$
95868 := $(((-9) - T(5)) \times T(T(8))) \times (-6) - T(8)$
95883 := $((9 - 5) \times T(8)) \times T(T(8)) - T(T(3))$
95925 := $(T(9) + ((-T((-5) + T(9))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(5))))$
95955 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(5))) \times T((9 + 5))) - T(T(5))$
95976 := $((-9) + T(T(5))) - ((-9) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(6)))$
95982 := $((9 \times T(5)) \times (T(9) + T(T(8)))) - T(2)$
95985 := $(9 \times ((T(5) \times T(9)) + T(8)) \times T(5))$
96075 := $(T(9) \times ((-T(6)) - T(T(07)))) \times (-5))$
96165 := $(T(9) \times ((T(61) + T(T(6))) + T(5)))$
96177 := $((-T(9)) + ((T(T(6)) - ((1 - 7))) \times T(T(7))))$
96207 := $(T(T(9)) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(07))))$
96213 := $((-9) - ((T(T(6)) + T(T(2))) \times T(T((1 + T(3))))))$
96216 := $((T(T(9)) + T(T(6))) \times (T(T((T(2) + 1))) + T(6)))$
96222 := $(T(((9 + T(6)) - 2)) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(T(T(2))))))$
96225 := $((-9) \times T(T(6))) + (T(2) \times (2^{T(5)}))$
96227 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(62)) / T(T(T(2)))) - (T(7))$
96228 := $((T(9) + T(((6^2) \times 2))) \times T(8))$
96231 := $(9 - ((T(T(6)) + T(T(2))) \times T(T((T(3) + 1))))$
96237 := $((T(9) + (6)^2) \times 37)$
96242 := $((T(96) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(2))$
96252 := $((T(T(9)) \times (T((6 \times 2)) + T(5))) - T(2)$
96255 := $(T(T(9)) \times ((T(6) \times T(2)) + T(5)) + T(5))$
96266 := $((T(T(9)) \times (-T(62))) - T(T(6))) / (-T(6))$
96267 := $(T(9) - ((6^{T(2)} + T(6))) \times T(T(7)))$
96273 := $(T(9) + ((T(T(6)) + T(T(2))) \times T(T(7))) + (T(3)))$
96327 := $(((-T(9)) + T(T(6))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T((T(2) \times 7))$
96333 := $(((-T(9)) + T(T(6))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(3)$
96345 := $((-T(9)) + (T(T(6)) \times T((3 + 4)))) \times T(5)$
96348 := $((9 - T(T(6))) \times (T(3) - (T(T(4)) \times 8)))$
96372 := $(T(9) - ((T(T(6)) / T(T(3))) + T(T(7)))) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$
96384 := $((9 + T((T(T(6)) / 3))) \times (8 \times 4))$
96387 := $((-T(9)) - ((T(6)) \times (T(T((T(3) - 8))) + T(T(7))))$
96390 := $((-T(9) + (6)) \times T(T(3))) \times (-90)$
96426 := $((-T(T(9))) - ((-T(T(6)) - T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times T(6))$
96432 := $((T(96) - (4^3)) \times T(T(T(2))))$
96435 := $(9 \times ((T(T(6) \times 4)) \times 3) + (5))$
96441 := $((T(9) + (6)) \times T((T(T(4)) + T((4 - 1))))$
96447 := $((-T(T(9)) + (T(T(6)) \times (-((4 \times 4)) - T(T(7))))$
96459 := $((-T(9) + T(6)) - (T(-((T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))) \times (-T(9))))$
96462 := $((T(9) + (6)) \times T((T(T(4)) + (6)))) + T(T(T(2)))$
96465 := $((T(T(9)) \times 6) - T(4) + T(T(6))) \times T(5)$
96475 := $(((-9) - T(T(6))) \times (4 - T(T(7)))) - (5)$
96492 := $((-T((-9) + T(6))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T((9 + 2))$
96495 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(-((4 - 9)))) + T(5))$
96497 := $((T(9) - (6)) \times T(T(4))) \times T(9) - T(7)$
96514 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) - 1) - T(4)$
96515 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) - T(-((1 - 5))))$
96517 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) - (1 + 7))$
96518 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) + ((1 - 8)))$
96521 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) - T(2)) - 1$
96522 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) - T(T(2))) + T(2)$

- 96523** := $((T(9) \times T(65)) - (T(T(2))/3))$
96524 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) + T(2)) - (4)$
96525 := $(T(9) \times T(((6+5)+2) \times 5))$
96526 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) + (T(T(2))/6))$
96528 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(6))) \times T(5)) + T(T(2)) \times 8$
96531 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) + T(3 \times 1))$
96532 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) + (T(T(3))/T(2)))$
96536 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) - (T(T(T(3)))/(-T(6))))$
96538 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) + T(T(3))) - 8$
96542 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) - (4)) + T(T(T(2)))$
96545 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) + ((4 \times 5)))$
96546 := $((T((9 \times 6)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))) + (T(6)))$
96549 := $((T(9) - T(6)) + (T((T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))) \times T(9)))$
96552 := $(9 \times ((T(65) \times 5) + T(2)))$
96555 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) + T(5)) + T(5)$
96564 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(5))) - (T(6) \times (-4))$
96567 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) + (6 \times 7))$
96576 := $((-T(9)) + T(T(6))) \times T(5)) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(6)))$
96582 := $((T(9) \times T(65)) + T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))$
96585 := $((9 + T((T(6) - 5))) \times T(T(8))) + T(5))$
96615 := $((T(T(9)) \times (-6)) - T(T(6))) \times (-15)$
96624 := $(T(9) - (-T(6) \times (-T(6) + (T(2) \times T(T(T(4)))))))$
96637 := $(9 + ((T(T(6)) + (T(6)/3)) \times T(T(7))))$
96642 := $((T(T(9)) + (T(6) + 6)) \times T((T(4) + T(2))))$
96645 := $((T(9) \times T((T(-6) + T(6))) - T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)))$
96648 := $((T(96) \times T(6)) - T((T(T(4)) - 8)))$
96669 := $(T(T(9)) - (T(T(6)) \times (-6 \times 69)))$
96735 := $((9 + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) - 3)) + T(5))$
96737 := $((9 + T(T(6))) \times T(T(7))) - T(37)$
96745 := $((T(9 + T(6))) \times (-7)) + (T(4)^5)$
96756 := $((T(9) \times T(((6+7) \times 5))) + T(T(6)))$
96768 := $(-96) \times ((-7) - T(6)) \times T(8))$
96774 := $((T(T(9)) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(7)))) + T((7 + T(T(4))))$
96784 := $((9 + T(T(6))) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(8)) + T(4)$
96792 := $((T((T(9) + 6))) \times (T(7) + T(9))) - T(T(2))$
96794 := $((T((T(9) + 6))) \times (T(7) + T(9))) - (4)$
96795 := $(T(T(9)) - (-T(6) \times T(((T(7) - 9) \times 5))))$
96798 := $(T((T(9) + 6))) \times ((T(7) + 9) + T(8))$
96822 := $(9 \times ((T(6) \times (8^{T(2)})) + T(T(2))))$
96824 := $((T(T(9)) + (T(6) + 8)) \times T((T(2) + T(4))))$
96843 := $(-9) - (-T(6) \times (-8) + (T(T(T(4)) \times 3)))$
96867 := $(T(T((96/8))) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))))$
96873 := $((T(96) - T(8)) - (7)) \times T(T(3))$
96876 := $((T(9) + T(T(6))) \times T(((8) + T(7)) + (6)))$
96885 := $((-9) + (T(T(6)) \times (-8) + T(8))) \times T(5)$
96915 := $((T(9) - 6) \times T((T(9) + 1) + T(5)))$
96945 := $(-T(T(9))) - (-69) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5))))$
96957 := $((9 \times T(6)) \times (9 \times 57))$
96975 := $((T((T(9) - 6))) + (T(T(9)) \times (-7))) \times (-T(5))$
97065 := $(T(9) - ((-T(7)) \times T(T(06))) \times T(5))$
97128 := $((T(9) - 7) \times T((-1) - (-2) \times T(8)))$
97146 := $(9 \times ((7 \times (-1) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(6))))$
97155 := $((-9) - (T(7) \times T(T((1+5)))) \times (-T(5))$
97185 := $((T((T(9) + T(7))) - 1) \times T(8)) - (T(5))$
97209 := $(9 \times (T(T(7)) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (0 - T(9))))$
97228 := $((T((T(9) + T(7))) \times T((2^{T(2)}))) - 8$
97233 := $((T((T(9) + T(7))) \times T((2^3))) - 3$
97236 := $((9 + T(7)) \times T((2 \times 36)))$
97242 := $((T((T(9) + T(7))) \times T((2 \times 4))) + T(T(2)))$
97243 := $((9 + T(T(7))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T((T(T(4)) - 3)))$
97244 := $((T(9) \times (T(7)^{T(2)}))/T(4)) - T(T(T(4)))$
97245 := $(T(9) \times ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) \times (-5))))$
97251 := $((9 + T(T(7))) + T(T(2))) \times T(T((5+1)))$
97257 := $(T(T((9-7))) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(5) - T(T(7))))$
97263 := $(T(T(9)) + ((T(T(7)) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(6)))) + (T(3))))$
97266 := $((T(T(9)) \times T((7 + T(T(2)))) + T(T((6+6))))$
97272 := $((-9) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(7) \times T(T(2))))$
97275 := $(-((T(9) \times (T(7) - (T(2)^7))) + T(T(5)))$
97280 := $((-9) + T((7^2))) \times 80$
97281 := $(T(9) + (T(72) \times (T(8) + 1)))$
97285 := $((T(T(9)) \times (T(7) + T((T(2) + 8)))) - (5)$
97308 := $(T((T(9) - T(7))) \times (-30) + T(T(8)))$
97323 := $((T(9) + 7) \times T(3)^2) - T(T(3))$
97328 := $((-9) + T((7+3))^{T(2)}) - 8$
97333 := $((-9) + T((7+3))^3) - 3$
97335 := $((T(9) \times 7) - T(3)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(5)$
97336 := $((-9) + T((7+3))^{-3+6})$
97344 := $((T((T(9) + T(7))) + 3) \times T((4+4)))$
97345 := $((T((T(9) - 7)) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(4))) - 5$
97356 := $((T(97) + 3) - T(T(5))) \times T(6)$
97359 := $(9 + (T((7+3)) \times T(59)))$
97362 := $((T((T(9) + T(7))) \times T(3)) + (T(6))) \times T(T(2))$
97365 := $((T(T(9)) - (T((T(7) + T(3)) + 6))) \times T(T(5)))$
97383 := $((T(T(9)) - (T(T(7)) \times T(T(3)))) \times (8 - T(T(3))))$
97389 := $((T((T(9) + T(7))) + 3) \times T(8) + T(9))$
97392 := $(-T(9)) - ((-T(T(7))) \times (T(T(T(3)) + 9)) + T(2))$
97394 := $(9 - ((-T(T(7))) \times (T(T(T(3)) + 9)) + T(T(4))))$
97395 := $(-T(9)) - (T(T(7)) \times ((3 + T(9)) \times (-5)))$
97416 := $((-T(9)) - T(T(7))) \times (T((4+1)) - T(T(6)))$
97417 := $(9 \times ((7 \times T(T(T(4)))) - 1)) + (T(T(7)))$
97422 := $((-9) - (-T(T(7))) \times T(T((T(4)/2)))) \times 2$
97424 := $((-9) + T(7)) + ((-T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(4))))$
97425 := $(9 \times ((7 \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(2) \times T(5))))$

- 97431** := $(-9) - (-T(T(7))) \times ((T(4) + T(T(3)))) - 1))$
97434 := $(9 \times ((7 \times (T(T(4))) + T(3))) + 4)$
97442 := $((9 + T(7)) + (-T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(T(2))))))$
97443 := $((T(9) - 7) - (-T(T(4))) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3))))))$
97445 := $((-T(T(9))) + (7 \times T(T(T(4)))) \times T(4) - 5)$
97449 := $(9 - (-T(T(7))) \times (T(T((-4) + T(4)))) + 9))$
97455 := $(-T(9) - (T(T(7) - 4)) \times (-T((5 \times 5))))$
97461 := $(9 \times ((7 + T(T(T(4)))) \times (6 + 1)))$
97476 := $((9 \times (T(T(7)) + 4)) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(6))))$
97479 := $((T(9) \times T(T((7 + 4)))) - (T(7 \times 9)))$
97482 := $((-(9 \times 7) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T((8 + T(2))))$
97485 := $(T(9) - (T(T(7)) \times (-48 \times 5)))$
97488 := $((9 \times T((T(7) - 4))) + 8) \times T(8)$
97495 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(7))) \times (-((T(4) - T(9)) + T(T(5))))$
97524 := $((9 \times 7) \times ((5 + T(2)) + T(T(T(4))))$
97525 := $((9 + T(T(7))) \times ((T(T(5)) \times 2) - 5))$
97533 := $((-T(T(9)) - ((T(7) + T(T(5))) \times T((T(3) \times T(3))))))$
97545 := $((-97) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(4)))) \times T(5)$
97563 := $(-T(9) - (T(7) \times ((-T(5)) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(3))))$
97575 := $((9 + ((T(T(7)) \times T(5)) + T(T(7)))) \times T(5))$
97578 := $(9 \times (((T(T(7)) + 5) \times T(7)) - T(T(8))))$
97587 := $(T(T(T(9 - 7))) \times (-T(5) + (T(T(8)) \times 7)))$
97596 := $((T((T(9) - 7))) - (-T(5) \times T(T(9)))) \times 6$
97602 := $((-T(T(9))) + ((T(T(7)) + T(6))) \times T(T(T(T(02))))))$
97623 := $((-T(T(9)) - (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) + (2 \times T(3))))))$
97627 := $(-9) - ((T(T(7)) + T(T((6 \times 2)))) \times (-T(7)))$
97638 := $(-T(T(9))) + (((T(T(7)) + T(6))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(8))$
97645 := $((9 + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) + 4)) + T(T(5))$
97653 := $(T(9) - (T(7) \times ((T(T(6)) \times (-T(5))) - T(T(3))))$
97656 := $((-9) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(5)) - 6)$
97662 := $((-9) + T(T(7))) \times ((T(6) + T(T(6))) - T(T(2)))$
97663 := $(T(T(9)) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(6)/3)))$
97668 := $((T((T(9) + T(7))) + (6 + 6)) \times T(8))$
97671 := $((9 \times T(T(7))) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(7)) + 1)))$
97679 := $(-97) \times ((T(6) + 7) - T(T(9)))$
97683 := $((T((T(9) + T(7))) + 6) \times T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))$
97695 := $((9 + T(T(7))) \times T(T(6))) + T((T(9) + T(5)))$
97713 := $((-9) + (7 \times T(T((7 + 1)))) \times T(T(3)))$
97725 := $(T(9) + (((T(T(7)) + T(T(7))) + 2) \times T(T(5))))$
97734 := $((T(9) \times T(7)) - 7) \times T((3 \times 4))$
97749 := $((9 \times 7) \times (T(7) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(9)))$
97755 := $((T(9) \times 7) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5))))$
97768 := $((T((-9) + T((7 + 7)))) \times T(6)) - 8$
97776 := $(T((97 - 7/7))) \times T(6)$
97782 := $((97 \times T(7)) \times T(8)) + T(T(2))$
97783 := $((T(T(9)) \times 7) + (-T(T(7))) \times (8 - T(T(T(3))))$
97796 := $((T(T(9)) + T(7)) \times (-T(7) - T((9 + 6))))$
97833 := $(-T(T(9))) + ((-7) + T((8 + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
97836 := $(-T(9) - (((-7) \times T(T(8))) \times T(T(3))) + T(6)))$
97839 := $((9 \times T(T(7))) + (T((-8) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(9)))$
97845 := $(-T(T(9))) + ((T(7) + T(8)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 5))$
97846 := $(T(T(((9 \times T(7))/T(8)))) \times (T(4) + T(T(6))))$
97848 := $((T((T(9) + 7)) - 8^4) \times (-T(8)))$
97853 := $((-T(9) - T(T(7))) + (8^5 \times 3))$
97857 := $(-T(9) - ((-7) \times T(T(8))) \times T(T(T(-((5 - 7))))))$
97863 := $(-T(9) - (((7 \times T(T(8))) \times (-T(6))) - T(3)))$
97866 := $((T(9) \times T(T(7))) + ((T(8) \times T(66))))$
97867 := $((-T(9) - T(T(7))) \times (T(8) - T((-6) + T(7))))$
97873 := $(97 \times (T(T(8)) + ((7^3))))$
97875 := $(T(9) \times ((-7) + T(8)) \times 75)$
97893 := $(-9) - ((7 \times T(T(8))) \times (-T((9 - 3))))$
97923 := $((T(97) + (T(9) \times (-2))) \times T(T(3)))$
97934 := $((9 + T(T(7))) + 9) \times T(T(T(3))) - T(4)$
97937 := $((9 + T(T(7))) + 9) \times T(T(T(3))) - 7$
97942 := $((T(T(9)) + 7) \times 94) - T(T(2))$
97944 := $((T(T(9)) + 7) \times 94) - 4$
97945 := $((-9) + T(7)) \times ((T(T(9)) - 4) \times 5)$
97956 := $(9 \times ((T((-7) + T(9))) \times T(5)) - T(T(6)))$
97965 := $(T(9) - ((T((7 + 9)) \times (-6)) \times T(T(5))))$
97966 := $(T((-9) + T(7))) + ((T(96) \times T(6)))$
97972 := $(T((T(9) + 7) - T(9))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))))$
97983 := $(9 \times (((7 + 9) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(T(3))))$
98145 := $(T(9) \times (T(8) + T((-1) + T((-4) + T(5))))))$
98217 := $((-T(9) + (T(T(8)) \times (-21))) \times (-7))$
98226 := $((-9) + (T((T(8) + T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times 6)$
98229 := $((T(9) \times T(T((8 + T(2)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9)))$
98235 := $(-T(9) - ((-8) \times T(2)) \times T((T(3) \times T(5))))$
98245 := $((-T(9) \times (T(8) + T(2))) - (T(4)^5))$
98248 := $((9 - (8 \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(T(4)))))) \times 8)$
98253 := $((-9) + 8) + (2^{T(5)}) \times 3$
98259 := $((T(9) \times (8^{T(T(2))})/T(T(5))) - T(9))$
98265 := $(-T(9) + ((-T(T(8)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(6)) - 5))))$
98271 := $(T(T(9)) + ((T(8) \times T((2 + 71))))$
98275 := $(((-9) + T(8))^{T(2)} - T(7)) \times 5$
98295 := $(-9) + (((8^{T(T(2))}) \times T(9))/T(T(5)))$
98297 := $((98 - T(2)) \times T(T(9))) - T(7)$
98313 := $(9 - (8^{T(3)-1}) \times (-3))$
98319 := $(T(T(9)) - (T(T((8 + 3))) \times (1 - T(9))))$
98322 := $((9 + 8^3) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
98325 := $(T(T(9)) \times ((T(8) - T(3)) \times T(2)) + 5))$
98343 := $((9 - (T(T(8)) \times (-3))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(3)))$
98346 := $((T(T(9)) \times (T((8 + T(3))) - T(4))) + T(6))$
98347 := $(-T(9) - (8 \times (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + T(T(7))))$

- 98379** := $(T(T(9)) - (T(8) \times (-3) - T((T(7) + T(9)))))$
98385 := $((T(9) + T(8)) + ((3 \times (8^5))))$
98388 := $((T((9 \times 8)) + T((T(3) + 8))) \times T(8))$
98427 := $((-T((T(9) + 8))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T((T(T(2)) \times 7))$
98437 := $(T(9) - (8 \times ((-T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(7))))$
98445 := $(T(9) + (T((T(8) + 4))) \times T((T(4) + (5))))$
98467 := $((-T(9)) + T(T(8))) - ((-T(4) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(7)))$
98469 := $((T(T(9)) + T(8)) \times T(4) + T(T(6))) \times 9$
98475 := $(T(T(9)) - ((-((8/4) \times T(T(7))) \times T(T(5))))$
98482 := $(((-9) - (-8) \times T(T(T(4)))) \times 8) - T(T(2))$
98484 := $(((-9) - (-8) \times T(T(T(4)))) \times 8) - 4$
98485 := $(T(9) + (((-8) \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (-8)) - (T(T(5))))$
98487 := $(-T(9)) + (((-8) \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (-8)) - (T(7))$
98488 := $((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-8 \times 8)))$
98496 := $((T(T(9)) - (T(8)/4) \times 96)$
98522 := $(-T((T(9) - 8))) + (T(5) \times T(T(T(2))))^2$
98523 := $(9 \times ((-T(85)) + T(T(2))) \times (-3))$
98526 := $((-9) + ((8^5) \times T(2))) + T(T(6))$
98532 := $((T(T(9)) + T(8)) \times ((T(5) \times T(3)) + 2))$
98535 := $(9 - (-8) \times T((T(5)/3))) \times T(5)$
98545 := $((9 - T(T(8))) \times (-T(5) \times T(4))) - (5)$
98553 := $(T(9 + 8) - (-T(T(5))) \times T((T(5)/3)))$
98568 := $(((-98) + T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(8))$
98577 := $(T(9) + (T(8) \times ((-T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 7))$
98587 := $(T(T(9)) - (-T((8 + 5))) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(7))))$
98592 := $((T(T(9)) - 8) \times (T(5) + (9^2)))$
98595 := $(T(9) \times ((T(T(8)) - (T(5))) + T(T(T(9 - 5))))$
98637 := $((T(98)/T(6)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(7))))$
98658 := $((T(9) + T(8)) \times T(6)) \times 58$
98682 := $((T((9 + 8)) \times (-T(6)) + T(T(8)))) - T(2)$
98685 := $(9 \times T((8 - 6))) \times T(85)$
98687 := $(T((-9) + T((-8) + T(6)))) \times (T(8) - (7))$
98739 := $((T(9) - T(T(8))) \times (-((T(7) \times T(3)) - 9))$
98743 := $((-9) - (-((T(8) + T(7))) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 3))$
98745 := $((-T(T(9)) - ((T(8) \times T(74)))) + T(T(5)))$
98746 := $(-T(9)) + (((T(8) + T(7)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(6)))$
98748 := $((T((9 + 8)) \times T(T(7))) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(8))))$
98782 := $((98 \times T(7)) \times T(8)) - 2$
98784 := $((98 \times 7) \times T(8)) \times 4$
98793 := $((T(9) + T(8)) \times T(T(7))) + T(9) \times 3$
98829 := $((T((9 \times 8)) \times (T(8) + 2)) - T(T(9)))$
98856 := $((T(T(9)) \times 8) + (T(T(8)) \times T((-5) + T(6))))$
98865 := $((-T(T(9)) - (T(T(8)) \times ((T(8) - (6)) \times 5)))$
98884 := $(9 \times T(8)) + ((8 \times 8) \times T(T(T(4))))$
98892 := $((-T(T(9)) - T(T(8))) \times ((8 - T(9)) - T(T(T(2))))$
98928 := $((T((9 \times 8)) + T((T(9)/T(2)))) \times T(8))$
98937 := $(T(T(9)) - (T(T(8)) \times (T((9 - 3)) \times (-7))))$
98945 := $((98 \times T(T(9))) - T((T(T(4)) + (T(5))))$
98946 := $((-T(T(9)) - ((T(T(8)) + T((9 \times T(4)))) \times T(6)))$
98955 := $(T(9) \times ((-T(T(8))) + T((-T(9)) + T(T(5)))) + T(5))$
98965 := $((-T(T(9)) - (((T(8)/9) + (6))^5))$
98982 := $((-9) \times T(T(8))) + ((9 \times T(8))^2)$
98985 := $((-T(T(9)) - (T((T(T(8)/9)) \times (-T(8))) - (T(T(5))))$
99127 := $((T(T((T(9)/9))) - 1)^2) \times 7$
99135 := $(T(9) \times (-((9 - 1)) + T(T((T(3) + (5))))$
99176 := $((T(9) \times T(9)) - 1) \times (T(7) + T(6))$
99180 := $(-T(9)) \times (T(T(9)) - (-1 + T(80)))$
99216 := $((-9) + (T(T(9)) \times T(T(2)))) \times 16$
99222 := $((T(9) \times (9 - 2))^2) - T(2)$
99225 := $(9 \times T(9)) \times (2 + (T(2)^5))$
99228 := $((T(9) \times T(T((9 + 2)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8))$
99234 := $(9 - (-((T(9)^2) \times (-T(3)) + T(T(4))))$
99246 := $((-T(9) \times T(9)) \times (T(T(2)) - T(T(4)))) + (T(6))$
99255 := $((T(9) \times T(T((9 + 2)))) - T(T(5)) - T(T(5)))$
99262 := $((T(9) \times T(T((9 + 2)))) - T(T(6)) - 2)$
99264 := $((T(9) \times T(T((9 + 2)))) - T(T(T(T((6 - 4))))$
99267 := $(T((T(9) + T(9))) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-6 - T(T(7))))$
99288 := $((-9) + ((T(T(9)))/(-T(2)) \times (-T(8)))) \times 8$
99315 := $(-T(9)) + (T(T(9)) \times (T(3) \times (1 + T(5))))$
99324 := $(9 - (T(T(9)) \times (T(T(3)) + T(2)))) \times (-4)$
99327 := $((T(9) \times T((T(9) + T(T(3)))) - (T(T(2)) \times T(7)))$
99336 := $((T(T(9)) \times 93) + T(T((T(3) + 6))))$
99342 := $((T(9) \times T((T(9) + T(T(3)))) - T((-4) + T(T(T(2))))$
99344 := $((T(T(9)) \times (-T(9)) + T(T(3))) + (4)) \times (-4)$
99345 := $((T(T(9)) \times ((-T(9)) + T(T(3))) \times (-4)) - (T(5)))$
99351 := $((-9) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(3) \times (T(5) + 1))))$
99355 := $((T(T(9)) \times ((-T(9)) + T(T(3))) + T(T(5))) - (5))$
99372 := $((T(9) \times T(9)) + 3) \times (7^2)$
99375 := $((T(9) \times T((T(9) + (3 \times 7)))) - T(T(5)))$
99378 := $((T(T(9)) \times T((9 + 3))) - (-T(7) \times T(T(8))))$
99387 := $(T((9 + T(9))) - ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) \times (-7))$
99396 := $((T((9 + T(9))) + T(T(3))) \times (T(9) + T(6)))$
99429 := $((-T(T(9))) + (-T(T((9 + 4)))) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T(9)))$
99435 := $(T(T(9)) + (T(((9 + T(4)) + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(5))))$
99462 := $((-T(99 \times T(4))) - T(T(6))) \times (-2)$
99465 := $((-T(9)) + ((T(9) \times T(T(-(T(4) - T(6)))) + T(5)))$
99467 := $((T(9) \times T(T((9 - 4) + 6))) - T(7))$
99468 := $(9 + ((T(9) \times T(T(-(T(4) - T(6)))) - T(8)))$
99477 := $(9 \times ((T(9) + (-4) \times T(T(7)))) \times (-7))$
99478 := $((-9) + ((T(9) \times T(T((4 + 7)))) - 8))$
99486 := $((-9) + (T(9) \times ((T(T(4)) \times T(8)) + T(T(6))))$
99492 := $((T(T((9/9) + T(4))) \times T(9)) - T(2))$
99495 := $(T(9) \times T(((T(9) + (4 \times 9)) - T(5))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99504 &:= (9 - (-T(9)) \times T(T((T(5) + (0 - 4)))))) \\
 99516 &:= ((T(9) \times T((T(9) + T((5 + 1)))))) + (T(6)) \\
 99522 &:= ((T(T(9)) - 9) \times (T((T(5) - 2)) + T(T(2)))) \\
 99525 &:= (T(9) + ((-9) - T((T(T(5))/T(2)))) \times (-T(T(5)))) \\
 99531 &:= (-9) + (T(9) \times (T(T((5 + T(3)))) + 1)) \\
 99535 &:= (T(9) + ((T(9) \times T(T((5 + T(3)))) - 5)) \\
 99555 &:= (T(T(9)) + ((T((T(9) - 5)) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(5)))) \\
 99567 &:= (9 \times ((T(9) \times (T(5) + T(T(6)))) - (7))) \\
 99582 &:= (((T((9 \times 9)) \times 5) - 8) \times T(T(2))) \\
 99595 &:= ((T(9) \times (-9)) + (T(-((5 - 9)))^5)) \\
 99613 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times 96) + T((1 + T(T(3)))) \\
 99615 &:= ((T(9) \times T((T(9) + T(6)))) + (T(15))) \\
 99625 &:= ((T(9) \times (T((T(9) + T(6))) + T(2))) - (5)) \\
 99627 &:= ((T(T(9)) - T(9)) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(7)))))) \\
 99645 &:= ((T(9) \times T((T(9) + T(6)))) + (T(4) \times T(5))) \\
 99646 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times 96) + T(T(4))) + T(T(6))) \\
 99647 &:= ((T(9) \times (T((T(9) + T(6))) + (4))) - T(7)) \\
 99648 &:= (((T(T(9)) + T(T(9))) + (6)) \times 48) \\
 99655 &:= (((T((9 \times 9)) \times 6) + (5)) \times 5) \\
 99666 &:= (((T(9)/(-9)) + T(T(6))) \times (T(6) \times T(6))) \\
 99672 &:= (T(T(9)) + (T(T(T((9 - 6)))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))))) \\
 99675 &:= (T(T(9)) + ((9 + T(T(6))) \times (T(T(7)) + (5)))) \\
 99693 &:= (T(9) + (96 \times (T(T(9)) + 3))) \\
 99726 &:= -((T(9) - ((T(97) - 2) \times T(6))) \\
 99732 &:= (T(9) + ((T(97) - T(3)) \times T(T(T(2)))))) \\
 99747 &:= (-T(9)) + (9 \times ((T(T(7)) - T(4)) \times T(7))) \\
 99753 &:= (T(9) + ((T(97) - 5) \times T(T(3)))) \\
 99756 &:= -((T(T((T(9)/9))) + (T(T(7)) \times (-T(5) - T(T(6)))))) \\
 99762 &:= -((T(9) - (T(97) \times T(6)))) - T(T(2)) \\
 99764 &:= -((T(9) - ((T(97) \times T(6)) - (4)))) \\
 99765 &:= (T(9) \times (T(T((9 - 7))) + T(T((6 + 5)))) \\
 99768 &:= (-9) + ((T(97) \times T(6)) - T(8)) \\
 99784 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times 97) - T(T(8))) + T(T(4))) \\
 99786 &:= (((99 \times T(7)) \times T(8)) - (6)) \\
 99792 &:= (((9 + T(9)) \times T(7)) \times T((9 + 2))) \\
 99810 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times (-9)) - T(T(8))) \times (-10)) \\
 99813 &:= (T(((T(9) + T(9)) + (8 - 1))) \times T(T(3))) \\
 99828 &:= (((9 + T(9)) \times 8) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(8) \\
 99834 &:= (9 + ((T(T(9)) + T((T(8) + 3))) \times T(T(4)))) \\
 99846 &:= (-9) + (T(9) \times (8 + T(T(-(T(4) - T(6)))))) \\
 99864 &:= (9 + (T(9) \times (8 + T(T((T(6) - T(4)))))) \\
 99873 &:= -((9 \times 9)) \times (-8) - T((T(7) + T(T(3)))) \\
 99876 &:= (((T(9) + T((T(9) + 8))) \times T(T(7)))/6) \\
 99885 &:= ((T(T(9)) - (T((T(9) - 8)) \times (-8))) \times T(5)) \\
 99895 &:= (((T(9) - 9) \times T((T(T(8))/9))) - 5) \\
 99936 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) + (T(T((9 - 3))) \times T(T(6)))) \\
 99945 &:= -((T(((9/9) + 9)) - (T(4)^5)) \\
 99955 &:= -((T(9) - (((T(9)/9) + (5))^5))
 \end{aligned}$$

3 Summary: Selfie Numbers

The author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides of the expressions are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers** [2, 3, 4]. Friedmann [6, 7] also made some study in this direction. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Following subsections give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. Examples of selfie numbers are with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, **Quadratic numbers**, **Cubic numbers**, etc. In two variables, we obtained selfie numbers with **binomial coefficients**, **S-gonal numbers**, **centered polygonal numbers**, etc. The other way of writing **selfie numbers** is by use of **permutable powers**, where **bases** and **exponents** are of same digits. See the subsection below with some examples.

3.1 Permutable Powers

Below are some examples of **permutable power selfe numbers**. By **permutable powers**, we understand that bases and exponents are of same digits with different permutations. Some times we may call them as **flexible power selfie numbers**.

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 &:= 1^1 & 1654 &:= -1^6 + 6^1 + 5^4 + 4^5 \\
 23 &:= -2^2 + 3^3 & 1837 &:= 1^8 - 8^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 \\
 1239 &:= 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 & 2137 &:= -2^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 7^2 \\
 1364 &:= 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^3 & 2173 &:= -2^3 + 1^2 - 7^1 + 3^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2537 &:= 2^5 - 5^2 + 3^7 + 7^3 & 46350 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 0^4 \\
 3125 &:= -3^2 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 5^5 & 46360 &:= 4^0 + 6^6 - 3^4 - 6^3 + 0^6 \\
 3275 &:= -3^3 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 5^5 & 397612 &:= 3^2 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 6^7 + 1^9 + 2^3 \\
 3435 &:= 3^3 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 5^5 & 423858 &:= 4^3 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 5^8 + 8^5 \\
 3529 &:= -3^3 + 5^5 + 2^9 - 9^2 & 637395 &:= 6^5 + 3^3 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 9^6 + 5^7 \\
 4316 &:= 4^6 + 3^1 + 1^4 + 6^3 & 758014 &:= 7^7 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 0^5 + 1^4 - 4^8 \\
 4355 &:= 4^5 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 5^5 & 778530 &:= 7^7 + 7^3 + 8^5 - 5^7 + 3^0 + 0^8 \\
 39339 &:= -3^3 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 9^3 & 804637 &:= 8^0 + 0^4 - 4^8 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 7^7 \\
 \\
 15647982 &:= 1^5 - 5^9 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 7^7 - 9^1 + 8^8 + 2^6 \\
 17946238 &:= 1^6 + 7^8 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 6^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 8^7 \\
 57396108 &:= -5^6 + 7^9 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^7 + 1^1 + 0^0 + 8^8 \\
 134287690 &:= 1^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 8^9 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 0^1 \\
 387945261 &:= 3^3 + 8^2 + 7^6 + 9^9 + 4^7 + 5^8 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 1^5 \\
 392876054 &:= 3^0 + 9^9 - 2^2 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 + 0^3 - 5^4 + 4^6 \\
 392876540 &:= -3^0 + 9^9 - 2^4 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 - 5^3 + 4^6 + 0^2
 \end{aligned}$$

More details can be seen in author's work [20].

3.2 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples in both orders:

$$\begin{aligned}
 13825 &:= 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5} &= ((5-2) \times 8)^3 + 1 \\
 14641 &:= (1+4+6)^4 \times 1 &= (1+4+6)^4 \times 1 \\
 15552 &:= (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 2 &= 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 1 \\
 16377 &:= (1+6-3)^7 - 7 &= -7 + (7-3)^{6+1} \\
 23328 &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 &= (8-2)^{3+3} / 2 \\
 116565 &:= (-1+16) \times (-5+6^5) = 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1) \\
 131072 &:= (1+3)^{1+0+7} \times 2 &= 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1} \\
 147419 &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 &= 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\
 147429 &:= 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 &= 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1) \\
 147491 &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 &= 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\
 156252 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 &= 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6-5} + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits:

$$\begin{aligned}
 656250 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 0 = 0 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656251 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 1 = 1 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656252 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 2 = 2 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}656253 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 3 = 3 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\656254 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 4 = 4 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\656255 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 5 = 5 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\656256 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 6 = 6 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\656257 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 7 = 7 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\656258 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 8 = 8 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\656259 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 9 = 9 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6.\end{aligned}$$

The past work up to 6 digits numbers can be seen in [14, 15, 16, 30].

3.3 Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! & 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! \\1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! \\5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & 403199 &:= 40319 + 9! \\317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! & 408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! & 715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! & 720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!\end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and are only with positive and negative coefficients. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways:

$$\begin{aligned}35280 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35281 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35282 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35283 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35284 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35285 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35286 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35287 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35288 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35289 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!.\end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [26, 27].

3.4 Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples in both orders, i.e., in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$1764 := 1 \times (7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}}$ $2378 := -23 + \sqrt{7^8}$ $19454 := 19 \times 4^5 - \sqrt{4}$ $19459 := 19 \times 4^5 + \sqrt{9}$ $19684 := 1 + \sqrt{9\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}/4}}$ $839793 := (-8 + (-3 + 9)^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 3$ $839795 := -8 + (-3 + 9)^7 \times \sqrt{9} - 5$ $839804 := (-8 + (3 - 9)^8 + 0) / \sqrt{4}$ $839816 := (8 + (3 - 9)^8) / \sqrt{\sqrt{16}}$ $995544 := ((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 54) \times 4$ $999916 := -9 \times 9 - \sqrt{9} + (9 + 1)^6$ $999976 := -\sqrt{9} \times 9 + \sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{9} + 7)^6$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$ $1024 := \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 1}$ $1296 := 6^{\sqrt{9+2-1}}$ $2189 := \sqrt{9^{8-1}} + 2$ $3867 := (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 3$ $9375 := \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 9}$ $12289 := \sqrt{9} \times 8^{2 \times 2} + 1$ $19693 := 3^9 + 6 + \sqrt{9} + 1$ $42436 := (6 \times 34 + 2)^{\sqrt{4}}$ $59051 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} + 0 + 9^5$ $999901 := (10^{9-\sqrt{9}}) - 99$ $999991 := (1^9 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9$
--	---

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details refer author's work [14, 15].

3.5 Factorial and Square-Root

Below are some examples with **factorial** and **square-root** written in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and its reverse

$936 := (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6!$	$= 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}}$
$1296 := \sqrt{(1+2)!^9/6}$	$= 6^{(\sqrt{9+2-1})}$
$2896 := 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!)$	$= (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2$
$331779 := 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}}$	$= \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3$
$342995 := (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5$	$= -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3$
$759375 := (-7 + 59 - 37)^5$	$= (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9-5+7}}$
$759381 := 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1$	$= -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7.$
$5040 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 0 = 0 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$	
$5041 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 1 = 1 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$	
$5042 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 2 = 2 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$	
$5043 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 = 3 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$	
$5044 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 4 = 4 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$	

$$\begin{aligned} 5045 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 5 = 5 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\ 5046 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 6 = 6 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\ 5047 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 7 = 7 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\ 5048 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 8 = 8 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\ 5049 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 9 = 9 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \end{aligned}$$

The following examples are in **digit's order** and its **reverse** separately:

$120 := ((1 + 2)! - 0)! $	$25 := 5^2$
$127 := -1 + 2^7$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$
$1673 := -1 - 6 + 7!/3$	$289 := (9 + 8)^2$
$1679 := 1 + (-6 + 7!)/\sqrt{9}$	$3894 := (\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(\sqrt{9})!^8}) \times 3$
$1680 := (1 + 6)!/\sqrt{8 + 0!}$	$4957 := 7! - 59 - 4!$
$38970 := -3!! + 8! - 9 \times 70$	$6992 := 2^9 + 9 \times 6!$
$38986 := -3 + 8! - \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 8)^6}$	$26493 := (2 + 6)! - 4!^{\sqrt{9}} - 3$
$40310 := (\sqrt{4^{03}})! - 10$	$30792 := 3! \times ((0 + 7)! + 92)$
$90894 := -(\sqrt{9})! + ((0! + 8)! + (\sqrt{9})!!)/4$	$54476 := (5! + 4!^4 - 7!)/6$
$91560 := ((\sqrt{9})! + 1)! + 5! \times (6! + 0!)$	$75989 := \sqrt{9} \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!!) + 5^7$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For details refer author's work [14, 15, 16].

3.6 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n + 1) = F(n) + F(n - 1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Below are examples of **selfie numbers** by use of **Fibonacci sequence values**. This we have done in different situations, such as using $F(\cdot)$ and $F(F(\cdot))$ in separate works. See below examples:

$$\begin{aligned} 143 &:= -1 + F(4 \times 3) &= F(3 \times 4) - 1 \\ 986 &:= F(9) \times (F(8) + F(6)) &= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) \\ 1178 &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) &= F(8) + F(7) \times F(11) \\ 2585 &:= F(2) + F(5 + 8 + 5) &= F(5 + 8 + 5) + F(2) \\ 12819 &:= 1 + F(2 \times (8 - 1)) \times F(9) &= F(9) \times F((-1 + 8) \times 2) + 1 \\ 24297 &:= F(2 \times 4) \times F(2 + 9) \times F(7) &= F(7) \times F(9 + 2) \times F(4 \times 2) \\ 39394 &:= -3 + 93 + F(9)^{F(4)} &= (-4 + F(9)) \times 3 + F(9)^3 \\ 74997 &:= -7 \times 4 + F(9 + 9 + 7) &= F(7 + 9 + 9) - 4 \times 7 \\ 87937 &:= -8 + F(7) \times F(9 \times 3 - 7) &= F(7) \times F(3 \times 9 - 7) - 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$98703 := 9 \times (F(8) + F(7 \times 03)) = (F(3 \times 07) + F(8)) \times 9$$

$34 := F(3 \times F(4))$	$36 := 6^{F(3)}$
$233 := F(F(-2 + 3 \times 3))$	$143 := F(3 \times 4) - 1$
$630 := F(F(6)) \times 30$	$231 := F(13) - 2$
$1178 := F(11) \times F(7) + F(8)$	$377 := F(-7 + 7 \times 3)$
$2079 := (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 9$	$986 := (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9)$
$4864 := F(F(4))^8 \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(4)))$	$1165 := 5 \times F(F(6 \times 1 + 1))$
$8759 := -F(9 - 5)^7 + F(F(8))$	$1596 := F(F(6) + 9) - F(F(F(5 - 1)))$
$8849 := -9 \times F(F(F(F(F(4)))) - 8) + F(F(8))$	$2592 := F(2 \times 9) + F(5 + F(2))$
$9349 := -F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + F(F(F(-3 + 9)))$	$9756 := F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 7 \times F(9)$

$$834660 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 0 = 0 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834661 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 1 = 1 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834662 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 2 = 2 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834663 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 3 = 3 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834664 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 4 = 4 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834665 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 5 = 5 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834666 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 6 = 6 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834667 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 7 = 7 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834668 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 8 = 8 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8))$$

$$834669 := (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 9 = 9 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)).$$

$$21960 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21961 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21962 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21963 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21964 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21965 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21966 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21967 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21968 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$21969 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2.$$

First three blocks are in both ways. In the last block the first column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [23, 24].

3.7 Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics. The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2).$$

The examples given in above subsections are with **factorial**, **square-root**, **Fibonacci sequence** numbers, etc. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Triangular numbers**. See below some examples:

1069 := $T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9))$	874 := $T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8)$
1081 := $T(1 + T(08 + 1))$	0105 := $50 + T(10)$
2887 := $T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7)$	1155 := $-T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1)$
4965 := $T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5)))$	1224 := $T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) - 2 + 1$
4999 := $49 + T(99)$	2418 := $T(81) - T(42)$
99545 := $T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5$	99632 := $2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$
99546 := $T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6.$	99633 := $3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9).$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2210} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 0 = 0 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2211} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 1 = 1 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2212} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 2 = 2 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2213} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 3 = 3 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2214} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 4 = 4 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2215} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 5 = 5 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2216} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 6 = 6 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2217} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 7 = 7 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2218} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 8 = 8 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2219} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 9 = 9 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))). \end{aligned}$$

For more details see author's work [21].

3.8 Binomial Coefficients

Binomial coefficients are well known in literature. They are given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m-r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbf{N}.$$

In above subsections, we gave examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, etc. Still, one can have similar kind results using **binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways**, **digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6435} &:= C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5) = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6) \\ \mathbf{15504} &:= C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\ \mathbf{42504} &:= C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) = C(4!, -05 + 24) \\ \mathbf{54264} &:= C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4)) = C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4} + 5)!) \\ \mathbf{74613} &:= C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) = C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12650 &:= C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!) \\ 12870 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!) \\ 14950 &:= C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!) \\ 18564 &:= C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!) \\ 19448 &:= C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8) \\ 26334 &:= C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4}) \\ 43758 &:= C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8) \\ 53130 &:= C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28 &:= C(8, 2) \\ 792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7) \\ 924 &:= C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!) \\ 2024 &:= C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!) \\ 4845 &:= C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4) \\ 00378 &:= C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0! + 0!) \\ 00792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!) \\ 00924 &:= C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!)). \end{aligned}$$

Consecutive sequential representations:

$$\begin{aligned} 25920 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 0 \\ 25921 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 1 \\ 25922 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 2 \\ 25923 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 3 \\ 25924 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 4 \\ 25925 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 5 \\ 25926 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 6 \\ 25927 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 7 \\ 25928 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 8 \\ 25929 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 9. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98280 &:= 0 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98281 &:= 1 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98282 &:= 2 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98283 &:= 3 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98284 &:= 4 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98285 &:= 5 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98286 &:= 6 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98287 &:= 7 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98288 &:= 8 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98289 &:= 9 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}). \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [22].

3.9 S-gonal numbers

The formula for **S-gonal numbers** is given by

$$P(n, s) := \frac{n(n-1)(s-2)}{2} + n, \quad s > 2.$$

This subsection brings some examples of selfie numbrs using **S-gonal numbers**. These examples are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 4992 &:= P(4!, 9 + 9 + 2) & 8967 &:= 7 \times P(P(6, \sqrt{9}), 8) \\
 7744 &:= (P(7, 7) - 4!)^{\sqrt{4}} & 9504 &:= 4! \times P(\sqrt{0! + 5!}, 9) \\
 7896 &:= 7 \times P(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 6) & 9744 &:= 4! \times P(4 \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \\
 65485 &:= -P(6, 5) + \sqrt{4} \times 8^5 & 49281 &:= 1 \times 8! + P(29, 4!) \\
 65943 &:= P(6, 5) \times ((\sqrt{9})!^4 - 3) & 49548 &:= -8! - P(4!, 5) + 9!/4 \\
 67977 &:= (6 + 7) \times (P(9, 7) + 7!) & 50424 &:= 4! \times P(-2 + 4!, \sqrt{0! + 5!}) \\
 72495 &:= -P(7 + 2, 4) + 9!/5 & 52895 &:= (5 + P(9, 8))^2 - 5 \\
 83544 &:= \sqrt{P(8, 3)} \times (5! - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}}. & 53995 &:= (5! - P(9, \sqrt{9})) \times 3!! - 5.
 \end{aligned}$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 86640 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 0 & 5640 &:= 0 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86641 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 1 & 5641 &:= 1 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86642 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 2 & 5642 &:= 2 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86643 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 3 & 5643 &:= 3 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86644 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 4 & 5644 &:= 4 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86645 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 5 & 5645 &:= 5 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86646 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 6 & 5646 &:= 6 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86647 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 7 & 5647 &:= 7 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86648 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 8 & 5648 &:= 8 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86649 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 9. & 5649 &:= 9 + P(4!, 6) \times 5.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [17].

3.10 Centered Polygonal Numbers

The formula for **centered polygonal numbers** is given by

$$K(n, t) := \frac{t n(n-1)}{2} + 1, \quad t > 2.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **centered polygonal numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inverse order of digits**:

$$2883 := K(2 \times 8, 8) \times 3$$

$$2888 := K(2 + 8, 8) \times 8$$

$$3640 := K(3!, 6) \times 40$$

$$14939 := -1 + (K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 3) \times 9$$

$$14959 := (-1 + K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 5) \times 9$$

$$15144 := K(15, (-1 + 4)!) \times 4!$$

$$15347 := (-1 + 5)! \times 3!! - K(4!, 7)$$

$$15399 := K(1 \times 5!/3!, 9) \times 9$$

$$00938 := K(\sqrt{K(8, 3!)}, (\sqrt{9})!) \times (0! + 0!)$$

$$01051 := K(15, 010)$$

$$01199 := K(9, \sqrt{9}) \times (1 + 10)$$

$$59938 := K(8, 3!) + (\sqrt{9})!! + 9^5$$

$$62424 := 4! \times K(2 + 4!, 2 + 6)$$

$$63384 := 4! + (K(8, 3) + 3) \times 6!$$

$$63744 := 4! \times (K(4!, 7) + 3 + 6!)$$

$$63973 := K(3! + 7, 9) \times K(3!, 6).$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$99360 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99361 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99362 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99363 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99364 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99365 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99366 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99367 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99368 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99369 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}.$$

For more details refer author's work [17].

3.11 Quadratic-Type Selfies

The formula for **quadratic numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^2, n > 0, n \in N.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **quadratic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$48 := -Q(4) + Q(8)$	$49 := Q(-9 + Q(4))$
$81 := Q(8 + 1)$	$89 := Q(9) + 8$
$128 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(8)$	$224 := (Q(4) - 2) \times Q(Q(2))$
$292 := Q(Q(Q(2))) + 9 \times Q(2)$	$275 := Q(5) \times (7 + Q(2))$
$322 := Q(Q(3) \times 2) - 2$	$736 := Q(Q(6) - Q(3)) + 7$
$1036 := 10^3 + Q(6)$	$0107 := 7 + Q(010)$
$1125 := Q(11 + Q(2)) \times 5$	$0231 := -Q(13) + Q(20)$
$1729 := 1 \times 7 \times (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 9)$	$1257 := 7 + Q(Q(5)) \times 2 \times 1$
$9843 := (Q(-9 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3$	$2239 := -Q(9) + Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2))$
$10025 := 100^2 + Q(5)$	$08136 := Q(6) + Q(Q(3) + 1 + 80)$
$10384 := (-1 + Q(Q(03))) \times 8 \times Q(4)$	$99712 := Q(Q(2)) \times 1 \times (Q(79) - 9)$
$99378 := 9 \times (Q(93) + Q(Q(7))) - 8$	$37293 := -3 + (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(2)) - Q(Q(7))) \times Q(3).$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 12680 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12681 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12682 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12683 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12684 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12685 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12686 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12687 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12688 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12689 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [25].

3.12 Cubic-Type Selfies

The formula for **cubic numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^3, n > 0, n \in N.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **cubic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$125 := 1^2 \times C(5)$	$512 := C(2 + 1 + 5)$
$522 := 5 \times 2 + C(C(2))$	$991 := (C(1 + 9) - 9)$
$991 := -9 + C(9 + 1)$	$0235 := 5 \times (C(3) + 20)$
$1371 := (1 + 3) \times C(7) - 1$	$0263 := C(3) + C(6) + 20$
$1715 := 1 \times C(7) \times 1 \times 5$	$1735 := 5 \times (3 + C(7) + 1)$
$2587 := -C(2) + 5 \times (C(8) + 7)$	$5974 := -4 + 7 \times (C(9) + C(5))$
$9945 := C(9) + 9 \times 4^5$	$00157 := -C(7) + 5 \times 100$
$10125 := (10 - 1)^2 \times C(5)$	$01928 := 8 \times (C(C(2)) + C(9) - C(10))$
$16444 := C(16) \times 4 + C(4) - 4$	$45194 := -4 + C(9) \times (1 + C(5) - C(4))$
$30375 := C(30) + C(3 + 7 + 5)$	$99535 := 5 \times (C(C(3)) + C(5) + 99)$
$99873 := C(9) \times (9 + C(8) / (7 - 3))$	

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 22950 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 0 = 0 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22951 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 1 = 1 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22952 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 2 = 2 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22953 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 3 = 3 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22954 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 4 = 4 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22955 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 5 = 5 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22956 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 6 = 6 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22957 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 7 = 7 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22958 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 8 = 8 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22959 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 9 = 9 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 3.1. The notation $C(., .)$ in two variables represent **binomial coefficients**, while the $C(.)$ in single variable represent **cubic numbers**.

For more details refer author's work [25].

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